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REPORT ON WORK ABOUT YERITH-ERP-9.0 (YEAR 2023)

"Xavier Noubbissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.]"

YERITH_{r&d}
"Immeuble YERITH"
barrière-Simbock
Yaoundé VI, Cameroon
Email: YERITH.xavier@gmail.com

Yerith R&D

Yerith-erp-pgi platiNum business Workflow

Figure 1: YERITH-ERP-9.0 BUSINESS Workflow

Figure 2: YERITH-ERP-9.0 COMPONENTS Workflow

Yerith R&D

Yerith-erp-pgi platiNum COMPONENTS Workflow

Figure 3: YERITH-ERP-9.0 manager main window frame

Abstract

This annual report summarizes efforts of Computer Systems R&D Start-up YERITH_{r&d} on its Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP) software product YERITH-ERP-9.0 in this year 2023.

YERITH-ERP-9.0 was invented in October 2015 in Yaoundé, Center region of Cameroon: it is an integrated Enterprise Resource Planing software for small, medium, and large entrepreneurial organizations. An entrepreneurial organization is here recognized as either a non governmental organization (N.G.O), a governmental agency, or a commercial society.

"**Financial expense management**" and "**Human resource management**" software modules sections were improved and incorporated respectively this year. Also, several improvements on financial accounting reporting were made.

A new software product: YERITH_QVGE (<https://zenodo.org/records/10070127>), was created as YERITH-ERP-9.0's runtime monitoring analysis verification module. YERITH_QVGE can run as a stand-alone product, or as a system service for YERITH-ERP-9.0 **on the Debian Linux operating system platform.**

YERITH_QVGE (<https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri-db-runtime-verif>) is a state-of-the-art **program analysis generator** that compares with bleeding edge technology software products used at The NASA (<https://www.nasa.gov>), such as "LogScope" [Hav22] and "DejaVu" [HPU18] by Dr. KLAUS HAVELUND (<https://www.havelund.com>).

Other comparable bleeding edge technology libraries and / or tools include "libfsmtest" (<https://bitbucket.org/JanPeleska/libfsmtest/src/master>) by Prof. Dr. rer. nat. habil. JAN PELESKA (<https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp>); "EventRaceCommander" [AMK⁺17] and "Purify" [HJ91] at IBM (<https://research.ibm.com/labs/watson>); and "Valkyrie / Valgrind" (<https://valgrind.org>).

YERITH_QVGE's (<https://zenodo.org/records/10070127>) drawing tool is priced at 2, 500 EUROS.

PEOPLE LISTED HERE, in alphabetical order, have financed and / or supported YERITH_{r&d} in the last 5 years (2023 backward):

1. Ing. Célestin Puene, MSc
2. Christian Ngueyong, AS degree in Computer Science
3. Collins Akosa, MASc (Waterloo, 2012), PhD (KAUST, 2016)
4. Dr. Emmanuel Rodrigue Wankap
5. Henri Bertrand Ngatchou (Ets Best Car Care & Services)
6. Dipl.-Inf. (FH) Jean-Daniel Tujilo
7. Joachim Nsofini , PhD (Waterloo, 2017)
8. Dr.-Pharm., B.Sc. (Nigeria), PETER AKUME ("Pharmacy FIANGO LYCÉE DE MAKÈPÈ")
9. Dr. (M.Sc.) Vincent Nanga (Geography, Germany)
10. Dr. (M.Sc.) Innocent Tchigio (Geography, University of Göttingen, Germany)
11. Dr.-PHARM. (Waterloo), M.Sc. (Belgium), CHEONGWA wandzi.

*"I have been hijacked by state hospital LAQUINTINIE in February 2021 ("**Organizer : Maxime NAPOA-eteme**") AND, in February 2023, by LAURE MENGUENE mvindi of JAMOT HOSPITAL. ALL THESE ATROCITIES AGAINST MY humble self and person, were commanded personally by PAUL BIYA; the President of the Republic of Cameroon, and also the PRESIDENT OF C.P.D.M (R.D.P.C) political ruling party. MY MOTHER-rose-Sangnou-NOUMBISSI and almost all my BLOOD-family members belong to this "C.P.D.M."; As well As any cameroonian that seems to leave freely here in CMR. "*

"ALL materials and furniture of YERITH_{r&d} located just opposite side of main entrance of BIYA's regime forestry society "**S2TBED**" were robbed illegally by "TEUNTCHOU Isaac" while I was in Douala for 3 weeks; in January 2025."

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WHO Is "Xavier Noubissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.]"

Figure 4: Portrait of YERITH-nissi.

"Xavier Noubissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.]" is a CHRISTIAN BY FAITH, Cameroonian, born on September 16 1983 in DOUALA (LITTORAL region, CAMEROON). Xavier has a "*Diplom-Informatiker (Dipl.-Inf.)*" qualification from the **University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY** (May 25, 2007). Xavier N. Noundou IS A "*Dr.-Ing. : Doctor of Engineering (Ph.D. equivalent – Computer Software Verification & Analysis)*" from **THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO (ON, CANADA); DECEMBER 20, 2011!**

"Xavier Noubissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.]" now, as CEO of YERITH_{r&d}, consults entrepreneurial organizations for their business informatics financial accounting needs.

"Xavier Noubissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.]" , also implements and configures program analysis and verification needs for his customers.

Xavier has worked together with **Prof. Dr. rer. nat. habil. Jan Peleska**, at AGBS-University of Bremen, GERMANY; and 2 years later at WatForm-University of Waterloo, ON, Canada, with **DR PATRICK LAM**.

Just after terminating his supervision with **DR PATRICK LAM**, Xavier had a great honour to pursue his studies with **Dr. Vijay Ganesh**, as a post-doctoral research supervisor!

Dr. Vijay Ganesh, a great software creator for computer security by super-algorithm, was before The UNIVERSITY of WATERLOO, ON; A Ph.D. in computer Science graduate of THEORY GROUP at Stanford University.

Xavier could successfully work with **Dr. Frank Tip** at The University of Waterloo (Waterloo, ON, Canada) on his first JAVA dynamic program analysis. Previously to being Professor at the University of Waterloo, David R. Cheriton School of Computer Science, **Dr. Frank Tip** was a research manager at **IBM TJ Watson Research Center from 1995 to 2012** (<https://research.ibm.com/labs/yorktown-heights>)!

Xavier also had the great opportunity through **Dr. Marcel Mitran** and **Dr. Patrick Lam**; to work as a graduate intern in Markham (Toronto, ON, CANADA) at IBM TORONTO SOFTWARE LABORATORY; in the JAVA-J9 Just-In-Time Compiler Optimization Team, together with **Patrick Doyle, MSc (University Of Toronto, ON, Canada)**, and **Vijay Sundaresan, MSc (McGill University, QC, Canada)**.

Xavier has following academic and professional engineering research contributions:

- 1) 'Statistical test case generation for reactive systems' at RTT-MBT at VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH (<https://www.verified.de>).
- 2) 'Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis For C using LLVM'
 1. source code in C++:
<https://www.github.com/sazzad114/saint>
 2. technical report article:
<https://zenodo.org/record/8051293>
- 3) 'YERITH-ERP-9.0':
 1. source code in C++:
 - a. YERITH-ERP-9.0:
<https://www.github.com/yerithd/yerith-erp-9-0>
 - b. YERITH-ERP-9.0 SYSTEM DAEMON:
<https://www.github.com/yerithd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon>
 2. technical report article (ongoing publication):
<https://zenodo.org/record/8052724>
- 4) 'YERITH_QVGE'
 1. source code in C++:
 - https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang
 - https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri_sd_runtime_verif
 - <https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri-db-runtime-verif>
 - https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_UNIT_TESTS
 2. technical report article (ongoing publication):
<https://zenodo.org/records/10070127>

Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

This chapter explains what is the Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP) software YERITH-ERP-9.0; what kind of entrepreneurial organization could make use of it; And what will be the development perspectives for the coming years.

1.1 YERITH-ERP-9.0: An Efficient And Simple To Use Enterprise Resource Planing Software

Figure 1.1: Financial Expense Creation Window in Administration Section

The screenshot shows the 'YERITH-ERP-3.0 - administration ~ create ~ FINANCIAL EXPENSES' window. It features a menu bar with 'Functions', 'Tools', and 'Help'. Below the menu is a 'Main menu' with icons for navigation and help. The main area contains four buttons: 'Create', 'List', 'Administration', and 'Modify'. A tabbed interface is visible with tabs for 'Stock alert', 'FINANCIAL EXPENSE*', 'Category', 'budget line', 'Bank account', 'User account', 'Department', and 'Site'. The 'FINANCIAL EXPENSE*' tab is active, displaying a form for 'financial expense data'. The form includes fields for 'department', 'budget line', 'reference' (marked as a mandatory field), 'designation' (marked as a mandatory field), 'supplier', 'quantity' (set to 1,00), 'unit purchase price' (marked as a mandatory field), 'Tax (%)', and 'total purchase price'. To the right, there is a 'REPETITION AND COMMAND DATA' section with a 'REACTIVATE repetitions' checkbox and a 'repeat every' field set to 1.00 day(s). At the bottom, there is a 'FINANCIAL EXPENSE DESCRIPTION' text area and 'Cancel' and 'Save' buttons.

1.1.1 Motivation

YERITH-ERP-9.0 [Nou23f,Nou23b,Nou23c] is an **Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP)** software system that aims 'effectiveness' and 'simplicity', compared to other high ranked ERP software systems (e.g.: SAP Business One, 'Sage Gescom i7', 'Odoo Exp', etc.).

YERITH-ERP-9.0 is implemented by me with THE USER INTERFACE LIBRARY QT [Ltd22]. Our goal when designing and implementing this ERP software system is more folds:

- 1) Render enterprise resource planing (erp) software system usage and manipulation as easy as reading a leisure or recreational book so to reduce user strain size.
- 2) Contribute to reduce poverty by improving software system technology for enterprise resource planing (erp):
 1. Best and accurate technology SHALL REDUCE management effort and produce more reliable and cost-minimized business financial accounting information that enables to anticipate and reduce time of decision making.
 2. Best and accurate technology reduces time execution of commercial business transactions, and thus, associated costs.
 3. So entrepreneurial commercial organizations could reduce a selling price without reducing its profit.

YERITH_{r&d} would be grateful for governments that are not able to provide sufficient funds for commercial versions of YERITH-ERP-9.0, to ask me for free of charge commercial versions.

1.1.2 Uses Of YERITH-ERP-9.0

An ERP (Enterprise Resource Planing) software is a program, and / or software system that enables its users to:

1. **Classify, Save, Search, Sort**, inventory stock article, commercial services, and assets in an electronic directorate;
2. **Sell – Check-out – Transfer – ETC.**, inventory stock article, commercial services, and assets from their electronic directorate;
3. **Create alert based on timing periods, inventory stock articles, commercial services, and / or assets quantities, etc.**
4. Save, Search, etc., **Suppliers, Employees, Clients (or Customers), Members, etc..**
5. In summary, an ERP enables an individual, a group of people (including families), an commercial entrepreneurial organization, etc.: to overview its entrepreneurial management from a COMMERCIAL AND FINANCE viewpoint with the help of informatics (and / or computers).
6. YERITH-ERP-9.0 handles financial budget lines !

1.1.3 YERITH-ERP-9.0 Current Software Metrics

Table 1.1: YERITH-ERP-9.0 RELEVANT SOFTWARE SYSTEM METRICS.

Software Metric	Value
User Interface (windows, dialog) number	60
MariaDB SQL table number	40
MariaDB SQL table column number	320
Latex template for PDF printing	80
Source lines of code (SLOC)	350,000

1.1.4 YERITH-ERP-9.0 Current Software System Components

- ERP software itself: [YERITH-ERP-9.0](#).
FOSS code location <https://www.github.com/yerithd/yerith-erp-9-0>
- Component 1: *yerith-erp-9-0-configurations-data*: Configuration data for [YERITH-ERP-9.0](#).
This software component entails:
 - A configuration property file "yerith-erp-9-0.properties" that contains MariaDB database connection parameters data.
 - A configuration property file "yerith-erp-9-0-system-local-configuration-ENGLISH.properties" that contains local computer device and storage configuration parameters data.
 - A folder "yerith-erp-9-0-sql-backup-restore" where [YERITH-ERP-9.0](#) database backups will be stored.
- Component 2: *YRI_QVGE*: Runtime Monitoring Analysis Verification System.
FOSS code location 1 https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang
FOSS code location 2 https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri_sd_runtime_verif
FOSS code location 3 <https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri-db-runtime-verif>
FOSS code location 4 https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_UNIT_TESTS
- Component 3: *yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon*: Service daemon for alerts over inventory stocks, assets, and financial expenses.
FOSS code location <https://www.github.com/yerithd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon>

1.2 YERITH-ERP-9.0 Activity Sector Usage Report

Table 1.2: Societies used for Testing and Validation of YERITH-ERP-9.0 (2015-2023).

INDUSTRIAL SECTOR	LANGUAGES	Companies (network: # computers)	# users (accessories: quantity)	Integration difficulty (increasing 1 – 5)
1. GROCERY SHOP	FRENCH	POISSONNERIE PLUS	3	5
2. GROCERY SHOP	ENGLISH	NGO-PHARMACY FIANGO LYCÉE DE MAKÉPÈ (✓: 2)	5	3
3. BOOKSHOP	FRENCH	BILINGUAL entente bookshop	2	5
4. HEALTHCARE	ENGLISH	PHARMACY FIANGO LYCÉE DE MAKÉPÈ (✓: 4)	5 (✓: 1)	5
5. HEALTHCARE	FRENCH	P.C.T.B s.a.r.l (✓: 5)	20	5
6. HEALTHCARE	FRENCH	HAPPINESS POTENTIAL s.a.r.l	3	3
7. LOGISTICS	FRENCH, & ENGLISH	BONTÉE s.a.r.l (✓: 4)	6 (✓: 1)	3
8. HARDWARE SHOP	FRENCH	HARDWARE SHOP N.K	5	2
9. HARDWARE SHOP	FRENCH	HARDWARE SHOP la confiance	6	5
# Sectors	# LANGUAGES	# Companies	# Users #accessories	CUMULATED DIFFICULTY (MEAN)
5	2	9	55 2	4

Figure 1.2: 2 pie charts on customers till year 2023.

Figure 1.3: Represented customer sector till 2023, in percentages (%).

Figure 1.4: Percentage (%) of users per customer sector.

YERITH-ERP-9.0 is aimed at being simpler in usage and manipulation than older top ranked ERP software systems (e.g.: SAP Business One, 'Sage Gescom i7', 'Odoo Erp', etc.). A detailed comparison is to find in paper [Nou23b].

YERITH-ERP-9.0 could be used by any entrepreneurial organization, WHETHER governmental, OR NON GOVERNMENTAL (N.G.O) ! Applications are for instance:

1. engineering offices;
2. insurance companies;
3. JUSTICE ministries services in AFRICA;
4. etc.

1.3 Features To Develop for the coming Years

1.3.1 ADDENDUM : Laurent-tchandeu for his boss PAUL-biya mvondo

THIS report is still in finalization in "FEBRUARY 11, 2025" because of BIYA-rdpc-cpdm regime that has destroyed my financial income through my genitor and my ambassador-uncle (LAurent ntchandeu)¹ because PAUL biya's regime is trying to again violate cameroon elections to come supposed this year 2025 :

- *I have for instance indexed publicly on road that if a political ruling party for more than 60 years couldn't pay his employees for governmental action since Cameroon supposed independence in "1960"; By means of computerized mechanisms; IT IS NOT MANAGING for CAMEROON ELECTION WITH more than at least 4000 other persons that They (government of BIYA's regime) could managed.*
- *I directly heard that since JANUARY 2025 they have finally introduced "Aigle" (<https://www.scam.prc.cm>) as a new computerized payment system for civil government employees.*
- *ALSO this new year 2025, "Immeuble YERITH" was destroyed of almost all its equipments by RDPC-teuntchou-isaac.*

1.3.2 Features – next

From this year onwards, YERITH-ERP-9.0 versions will not be Free and Open Source Software (FOSS).

YERITH_{r&d} would be grateful for governments that are not able to provide sufficient funds for commercial versions of YERITH-ERP-9.0, to ask me for free of charge commercial versions.

ESPECIALLY CAMEROON GOVERNMENT that is trying to implement a human resource module for SAP Waldorf since the year 1994 : "SIGIPES-2" almost 30 years at it (YEAR 2023)!

1. Execute Information flow policy control by usage of YRI_QVGE to Reduce Over Usage of government financial budget lines .
2. PROVIDE A SAMPLE template, for francophone central Africa states, **financial accounting plan o.h.a.d.a.**

This financial accounting plan will enable registered companies and societies, to use YERITH-ERP-9.0 for official tax income declaration.

3. Create a new "Expert Comptable (Chartered Accountant)" application profile user type.
4. Create a module that enables users of YERITH-ERP-9.0 to provide web applications on the World Wide Web (WWW) by just pressing a button.

Qt WebEngine Widgets C++ Classes seem to be what to use to provide this feature to YERITH-ERP-9.0 users.

5. Improve database connection information security of YERITH-ERP-9.0 because of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF fail state (error accepting state) recovery SQL mechanism feature.

I.e.: security of information and execution must guarantee that no intruders malware program, or code snippet, executes a malware SQL query statement.

¹*"THIS guja says on internet media he is looking for funds with a registered Cameroon NGO : HIS own Doctor nephew doesn't even have any funding because LAURENT harasses him as reported in JUDICIAL information (CV of Xavier NOUNDOU noumbissi attached to this document ! ")*

6. Improve fail state (error accepting state) recovery SQL mechanism of YERITH-ERP-9.0 in non SQL query statements; i.e.; create another efficient Qt-DBus recovery mechanism, in form of a Remote Procedure Call (RPC). Drawback here is the cumbersome configuration mechanism of Qt-DBus interface for RPC.
7. Implement offline dynamic analysis module within YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: I.e., produce analysis results based on program trace (event log).
8. Design and implement a mechanism to template solutions to class of use cases monitoring analysis verification within YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.
I.e: define a mechanism to generate runtime monitors for several database tables column SQL query temporal safety property just using one template model.
9. Design and create a Computer Device integrated with YERITH-ERP-9.0, so to improve information security and robustness of the application.

1.4 YERITH–ERP–9.0 Literature

This section summarizes all documents (26 in total at time of writing) created for explaining concepts, ideas, and technologies implemented to create YERITH–ERP–9.0.

1.4.1 Required Marketing Knowledge

In French Language

- 1) **BROCHURE DE GESTION COMMERCIALE** (<https://zenodo.org/records/17680727>),
RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, **OCTOBRE 2021**.

1.4.2 Business Informatics Management Knowledge

In English Language

1. **YERITH–ERP–9.0 SOFTWARE SYSTEM PRODUCT SHEET** (<https://zenodo.org/records/17661983>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, **MARCH 2021**.
2. **ADVANTAGES OF YERITH–ERP–9.0 COMPARED TO OTHER TOP ERP SOFTWARE-SYSTEMS** (<https://zenodo.org/records/17662017>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, **MARCH 2021**.
3. **INFORMATION BROCHURE OF ERP SOFTWARE-SYSTEM YERITH–ERP–9.0** (<https://zenodo.org/records/17662117>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, **MARCH 2021**.
4. **INSTALLATION GUIDE FOR ERP SOFTWARE–SYSTEM YERITH–ERP–9.0** (<https://zenodo.org/record/8060182/>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, **MARCH 2021**.

In French Language

- 1) **GUIDE DE L'UTILISATEUR 'MANAGER', PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH–PGI–9.0** (<https://zenodo.org/record/8058259/>),
RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, **JUIN 2018**.
- 2) **YERITH–ERP–PGI–3.0: ESSAI DE PRODUCTIVITÉ ENTREPRENEURIALE** (<https://zenodo.org/records/10071437>),
RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH_{r&d}, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, **MARS 2021**.
- 3) **GUIDE PRATIQUE DU LOGICIEL DE GESTION COMMERCIALE ET FINANCIÈRE YERITH–PGI–9.0** (<https://zenodo.org/records/17680818>),
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In French Language

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1.4.4 Associated Computer Devices

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In English Language

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Chapter 2

REPORT ON CUSTOMER EXPERIENCES AND FINDINGS

This chapter talks about customer experiences that were gained this year 2023. We could successfully have two customers this year.

2.1 Associated Computer Devices for YERITH-ERP-9.0

Table 2.1: Devices and hardware useful for YERITH-ERP-9.0.

Figure 2.1: (MANDATORY)

Computer

Figure 2.2: Touchscreen Monitor (MANDATORY)

Figure 2.3: Cash Drawer (OPTIONAL)

Figure 2.4: "Point of Sale Thermal Printer" (OPTIONAL)

Figure 2.5: Bar-code Scanner (OPTIONAL)

Figure 2.6: 1 Network Router (MANDATORY)

Figure 2.7: Numeric Tablet (OPTIONAL)

Figure 2.8: "2 in 1 Computer" (OPTIONAL)

Figure 2.9: Multi User Terminal Computer (OPTIONAL)

Figure 2.10: Hardware components of Multi-User Terminal Computer NC-300 (at <https://www.savingology.com>): images are taken from SavingOlogy.com.

Figure 2.11: NC-300 PCI card

Figure 2.12: NC-300 terminals

We have tried to search for very cheap devices because of the low income of small and medium companies here in Cameroon.

Table 2.1 illustrates sample computer devices and associated hardware for operating YERITH-ERP-9.0.

YERITH-ERP-9.0, in its current level of software development implementation, may not be appropriate at time for very large companies, with more than 100 employees: "Runtime monitoring", as well as "Financial expense management", and "Human resource management" modules software may solve this retard in the coming years.

2.1.1 Printing Devices And Counseling

We counsel our customer to use HP printing device solutions because drivers are available for Debian Linux operating system (LOGO:).

Also, it is advisable to print documents from their PDF format. Customers had for examples issues trying to perform correct printing from "LIBREOFFICE-WRITER", because of a complicated configuration system.

2.1.2 Computer Networking Devices

YERITH_{r&d} now counsels new customers or clients, to use Multi-User Terminal Computer NC-300 (Figure 2.10) for saving on computer hardware costs.

1 set devices of Multi-User Terminal Computer NC-300 enables up to 3 users to share a same desktop computer without the use of a computer network router (illustrated in Figure 2.6).

So their access to a LAN (Local Area Network) or Internet, occurs through the network interface of the shared desktop computer.

2.2 Software Ergonomics within YERITH-ERP-9.0

- Each text input field has an associated text inside the field for specifying what to search for, and where in database table column.
- Each icon or menu item is set not to be visible whenever it is not required or needed. For instance, whenever an inventory stock table is empty, icons and menu items for PDF printing (ICON:) disappear from a user interface.

MOTO: what is not needed is not visible. ¹

- Each window is accessible within 3 window GUI actions.
- Each function within a window GUI is accessible only in:
 - THROUGH A BUTTON just in front of a user on the Window.
 - THROUGH the context menu accessible using a click on the 2nd mice button.
 - THROUGH search for it in the window menu bar items.
- The settings configuration window panel has 2 types of settings:
 - computer local settings (LOCAL PARAMETERS)
 - remote server settings (SERVER PARAMETERS): only business information such as e.g.: VAT (Value Added Taxes), currency, etc.

2.3 Employee Training

We found that employee training is best done based on an employee skill set, and should be divided into 6 parts:

1. A visual demonstrating overview of YERITH-ERP-9.0
2. Questions based on knowledge and information acquired during visual demonstration of YERITH-ERP-9.0
3. Explanations about the key business concepts, business ideas, and software ergonomics implemented within [YERITH-ERP-9.0](#)
4. Executions of example use cases by employees
5. Questions and answers part conclusion
6. "**PLANING of general computing technology training for employees, based on observed missing knowledge during this training session**".

¹ARLETTE sibeuf, Financial and Accounting Director at "Bontée SARL in Akwa-Douala"

Chapter 3

NEW SOFTWARE FUNCTIONAL FEATURES

This chapter reports about all new ERP software functionalities introduced in this year 2023 in YERITH-ERP-9.0.

3.1 English to French And Vice-Versa Online Direct Translation

Users of YERITH-ERP-9.0 could now direct translate, online, without restarting application, translate YERITH-ERP-9.0 content from English into French, and Vice-Versa.

This occurs in the "Help" menu:

- in the main window
- in the administration section main window
- etc.

3.1.1 English Section

"Help" → "FR"

3.1.2 French Section

"Aide" → "EN"

3.2 Financial Expense Management

Figure 3.1: 2 pictures of financial expense management module.

Figure 3.2: Create a financial expense window.

Figure 3.3: View financial expenses window.

Figure 3.1 reports 2 pictures of the "Financial expense management" module we implemented this year within YERITH-ERP-9.0.

The "Financial expense management" module enables following actions:

1. File of any expense of an entrepreneurial organization; may it be an inventory stock purchase; a company physical asset; a company logical financial asset.

Each financial expense is reported within a financial budget line, that is linked to a physical bank account, registered only in YERITH-ERP-9.0.

2. Execute a financial expense ordering at a repetitive pre-determined time period frame.

3.2.1 Financial Accounting BUDGET LINES (COMMERCIAL ONLY)

Figure 3.4: Financial Accounting Budgets lines listing window tab (non administrative section).

ID	BUDGET LINE title	BUDGET LINE AMOUNT	Bank account title
0	665 - débit caisse	130,000.00	YR-DEBIT-CAISSE
1	664 - crédit caisse	0.00	YR-CREDIT-CAISSE

Commercial Operation Type

A COMMERCIAL OPERATION TYPE IS: ...

Commercial Operation Type Account

A COMMERCIAL OPERATION TYPE ACCOUNT IS: ...

Financial Budget Line

A FINANCIAL BUDGET LINE IS: ...

3.2.2 Financial Accounting Booking (COMMERCIAL ONLY)

Figure 3.5: Budgets lines – Financial Account Type Association window tab.

3.2.3 Financial Accounting Report Improvements (COMMERCIAL ONLY)

Figure 3.6: YERITH-ERP-9.0 Business Dashboard window.

Following new usability has been added to a financial accounting summary analytic report:

1. progress bars for Report PDF printing
2. reporting of budget lines balance sheet

3.3 Human Resource Management

Figure 3.7: 2 pictures of human resource management module.

Figure 3.8: Employee listing viewing window.

Figure 3.9: An employee belonging groups window.

Figure 3.7 reports 2 pictures of the "Human resource management" module we implemented this year within YERITH-ERP-9.0.

YERITH-ERP-9.0 views an employee as a supplier of services. The "Human resource management" module enables following actions:

1. File an employee or a company supplier.
2. Create a pay group; each employee associated to this pay group earns a same amount of money.

A pay group may be linked to a particular specific company location, Or may be a company wide unspecified location pay group.

A tax percentage amount is associated with each pay group; it could have 0% value.
3. Create an employee group associated with a pay group.
4. View, Remove, and Assign an employee to an employee group; an employee may belong to several pay group, and earns accordingly a cumulated salary per pay group.
5. View, modify time period an employee shall belong to a pay group.

At the end of a belonging time period, an employee is Not automatically removed from a pay group. But his salary from this pay group remains calculated to 0, in any currency defined in the administrative section "Application settings".
6. View pre-calculated monthly and annual, cumulated by pay group, salary of an employee in an employee details section window ("supplier details").

3.3.1 Payment Registration as a Financial Expense (Commercial version only)

Figure 3.10: A payment references page within YERITH-ERP-9.0 Anew.

All employees payments registrations, as a financial expense in module "PAYMENTS", are available only in YERITH-ERP-9.0 commercial version.

WE PLAN a USB-dongle key version starting beginning year 2026.

3.4 Runtime Verification Monitoring Analysis Module: YERITH_QVGE System

Figure 3.11: YERITH-ERP-9.0 monitoring interface window tab.

Figure 3.11 illustrates summary (AN EXPLANATION OF THE SQL QUERY, and not the exact syntax) SQL query sent to YERITH-ERP-9.0 database, with complementary information (e.g.: timestamp, etc.).

Information that appears in YERITH-ERP-9.0 monitoring interface is received by a dynamic program analyzer: "YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF "; that runs as a service background process on the same computer device. **"YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF " versions that allows for OFFLINE dynamic analysis will not be open source (FOSS).**

Each runtime monitor specification violated by an YERITH-ERP-9.0 execution is displayed in Figure 3.12. Details of each violated runtime monitor specification could be analyzed by a developer using YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (a component of YERITH_QVGE design and testing system) window interface, as shown in Figure 3.12.

Figure 3.12 illustrates a sample SQL event sequence mismatch) as specified by runtime monitor "YERITH_QVGE_sample_SAFETY_PROPERTY_one_Recovery_SAMPLE".

Chapter 4 explains the Design And Testing System YERITH_QVGE [Nou23a, Nou23d] with full authority.

Figure 3.12: YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF error reporting window tab.

YR-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF _ console (FOSS version enabled)

Actions Tools HELP

Enter "source" or "SQL event" for filtering Reset Filter

SQL Error Event Reporting Logging SQL Event Logging

	time stamp	sql event log	source	target	changed qty	runtime monitor ID
1	05:40:09:959	'SELECT_stocks'	yeroth-erp-pgi-3.0	YR-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF	1	7
2	05:40:10:017	'SELECT_stocks'	yeroth-erp-pgi-3.0	YR-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF	1	0

runtime monitor name YEROTH_QVGE_sample_SAFETY_PROPERTY_one_Recovery_SAMPLE

TIME STAMP	SQL recovered executed query	Result
1 05:40:09:959	'INSERT INTO categories (id, nom_categorie, nom_departement_produit) values (yr_id, 'YR_ASSET_cat', 'YR_ASSET')	

source file	line number
1 src/windows/stocks/yeroth-erp-stocks-window.cpp	2149

evaluated guarded condition expression	value
1 in_sql_event_log ('DELETE.categories.YR_ASSET_cat', STATE(YR))	True

previous state	accepting state	is error state
1 YR	E	True

YR-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: this console is registered to the system d-bus as service: 'yr.db-runtime.verif'.

Chapter 4

NEW SCIENTIFIC AND ENGINEERING INNOVATION (IN SOFTWARE QUALITY ASSURANCE)

This chapter reports about YERITH_QVGE Design and Testing System by Dynamic Program Analysis. YERITH_QVGE, a compounded software stack, has a Free And Open Source (FOSS) part, and a commercial paying part. Governments not able to pay for commercial versions of YRI_QVGE, and YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF, could ask me for a free of charge version.

4.1 Motivations

Figure 4.1: A State Diagram Mealy Machine Design Model within YERITH_QVGE.

Figure 4.2: YRI_QVGE workflow.

Software correctness properties are essential to maintain quality by continuous and regressive integration testing, as well as runtime monitoring the program after customer deployment.

To this intent, I have developed a stack software package of 4 complementary libraries, and / or programs named YERITH_QVGE [Nou23a, Nou23d] a test and design system by dynamic program analysis. Details of YERITH_QVGE are explained in Section 4.2.

Figure 4.1 illustrates the commercial drawing tool that is part of YERITH_QVGE. Figure 4.2 illustrates a workflow of design and testing system YERITH_QVGE.

In summary, YERITH_QVGE (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF) allows specification of a SQL temporal safety property by means of a state diagram mealy machine [NOU23g, Wik22]. In YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF, a specification characterizes effects of program events (via SQL statements) on database table columns by means of set interface operations (\in , \notin), and, enable to check these characteristics hold or not at runtime. Integration testing is achieved for instance by expressing a state diagram that encompasses both Graphical User Interface (GUI) states and MySQL [Mar22] databases queries that glue them.

For example, a simple specification would encompass states between 'Department administration' and 'Stock listing' GUI interfaces, and transitions between them by means of MySQL databases operations. YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF doesn't generate false warnings; YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF specifications are *not desirable (forbidden) specifications (fail traces)*.

4.2 YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE) Test And Design System by Dynamic Program Analysis

Table 4.1: YRI_QVGE Design and Testing System Dependencies

PROJECT	Required Library
1) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG	
2) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP	1)
3) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_UNIT_TESTS	1)
4) YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF	2)

Figure 4.3: YRI_QVGE software library dependencies.

YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE) is a CASE (Computer-Aided Software Engineering) design tool to generate "domain-specific language (DSL) YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG ¹" files, to be inputted into the "compiler YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP ", so to generate C++ files for the "runtime verifier tester YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF ²" that allows for manual verification of SQL correctness properties of Graphical User Interface (GUI) software.

Figure 4.3 show a diagram of the afore described process; The step of the unit tests is colored in gray because it is only for developers of YRI_QVGE intended; accordingly, Table 4.1 illustrates the same process as a software library dependency table.

Figure 4.2 illustrates a workflow diagrammatically of the afore described process.

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF inputs SQL correctness properties expressed using the formalism "state diagram mealy machine (YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG)". Figure 4.7 illustrates a software system architecture of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF, together with the monitored program under analysis. The Free Open Source Code Software (FOSS) tool-chain of development testing is located as follows for free, EXCEPT for "YRI_QVGE " that is a Closed Source Code Software (CSCS):

- COMPILER (i.e.: YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP):
https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang

¹https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri_sd_runtime_verif

²<https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri-db-runtime-verif>

- RUNTIME VERIFIER TESTER (i.e.: YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF):
<https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri-db-runtime-verif>
- state diagram mealy machine UNIT TESTS CODE (i.e.: YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_UNIT_TESTS):
https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_UNIT_TESTS
- state diagram mealy machine (i.e.: YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG):
https://www.github.com/yerithd/yri_sd_runtime_verif

4.2.1 SDMM: "State Diagram Mealy Machine"

Figure 4.4: A motivating example, as previous bug found in YERITH-ERP-9.0.

$Q0 := \text{NOT_IN_BEFORE}(YRI_ASSET, \text{department.department_name}).$

$Q1 := \text{IN_AFTER}(YRI_ASSET, \text{stocks.department_name}).$

Figure 4.5: A SAMPLE state diagram mealy machine file.

```

1. yri_sd_mealy_automaton_spec yri_missing_department_NO_DELETE
2. {
3.   START_STATE(d) : NOT_IN_BEFORE(YRI_ASSET, department.department_name)
4.   -> [in_sql_event_log('DELETE.department.YRI_ASSET', STATE(d))] / 'SELECT.department' ->
5.     ERROR_STATE(e) : IN_AFTER(YRI_ASSET, stocks.department_name).
6. }
```

Journal article in preparation [Nou23d] introduces a simple finite state machine formalism called State Diagram Mealy Machine ("SDMM"). Compiler YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP [Nou23a, Nou23d] inputs a specification as a "SDMM" and outputs a C++ program as a runtime monitor code specification for YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF dynamic program analyzer.

Figure 4.4 illustrates a simple automaton defining a "SDMM" specification. Its equivalent specification using Domain-Specific Language YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG is illustrated in Figure 4.5.

YERITH_{r&d} develops and sells YRI_QVGE: a graphical drawing tool for generating YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG [Nou23a, Nou23d] textual specification, as the one illustrated in Figure 4.5. Figure 4.1 illustrates a sample screenshot of YRI_QVGE.

4.2.2 Dynamic Program Analyzer Generator "YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF" (OFFLINE analysis in commercial version)

Figure 4.6: YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF error reporting window tab.

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF is a dynamic program analysis generator that inputs a text specification of a mealy automaton, and that uses state diagram mealy machine ("SDMM") library YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG to generate a runtime monitor binary executable that allows to:

- **Visualize** a graph representation, generated by the DOT-Graphviz [gra22] library program, of a runtime monitor specification.
- **Visualize, export, print**, system under test (SUT) (or also called program under analysis [PUA]) SQL events emitted to its database: for this, the library user must have instrumented (added additional source code) in its program sources, so to notify YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF of a query (E.G.: SELECT, etc.) to its application database.
- **Visualize, export, print**, SQL error events, as specified by the inputted "SDMM", that occur while the SUT is running (or not; using SUT SQL log event file).
- **Visualize** only SUT (system under test) SQL error events at the command line of execution as it prints out.

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF versions that will allow for OFFLINE (from a trace event log file) dynamic analysis will not be Free and Open Source Software (FOSS).

Figure 4.6 illustrates a sample SQL error event log of Graphical User Interface (GUI) of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.

4.2.3 "YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF" Software Architecture

Figure 4.7: SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE OF YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.

Figure 4.7 illustrates a software architecture of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF:

1. Any software layer of a software system architecture can be checked against a temporal safety property, as long as, it is instrumented and emits necessary Qt-Dbus [dqj22] events to YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF layer.

Chapter 5

CONCLUSION

This chapter concludes this annual report on effort work on YERITH_{r&d} business main software product YERITH-ERP-9.0.

5.1 Endeavor

YERITH_{r&d} advocates for usage of a simple and efficient ERP (Enterprise Resource Planing) business software here in Africa because of a low level of formal education, and of income.

YERITH-ERP-9.0 was designed to be useful starting for people having at least 11 years of formal education at primary and collegial level here in Cameroon. ERP systems created, and, in usage in western developed countries, require advanced knowledge as detailed in [Nou23b].

5.2 MAJOR CONTRIBUTION IN COMPUTER ENGINEERING SCIENCE

Table 5.1: COMPARISON TABLE BETWEEN C⁺⁺ [MS01], JAVASCRIPT [Fla20], AND JAVA [AGH00]. JAVASCRIPT and JAVA only have virtual machines that are in FACT REACTIVE SYSTEMS ! (WYSIWYG: What You See Is What You Get; VM: Virtual Machine)

FEATURES	C ⁺⁺	Javascript	Java
1. PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE PHILOSOPHY	object-oriented	object-oriented	object-oriented
2. MACROS	✓	✓	
3. MULTIPLE INHERITANCE	✓		
4. support INTERFACES	✓	✓	✓
5. STATIC COMPILATION	✓		
6. RUNTIME MONITORING & VERIFICATION	✓ (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF)	✓ (VM INTERPRETATION AND MANAGEMENT)	✓ (VM INTERPRETATION AND MANAGEMENT)
7. UNIT TESTING FRAMEWORK	✓	✓	✓
8. NETWORK CAPABLE	✓	✓	✓
9. CROSS PLATFORM PORTABLE	✓	✓	✓
10. include FILE LIBRARY CAPABILITY	✓		
11. MULTI THREADING	✓		✓
12. WYSIWYG GUI DESIGN TOOL	✓		✓
13. VIRTUAL MACHINE IS A REACTIVE SYSTEM		✓	✓

Table 5.1 encompasses a detailed scientific comparison between most at time of writing popular programming languages: C⁺⁺, JAVASCRIPT, JAVA.

We found following reasons for introduction of virtual machines in the programming languages JAVASCRIPT, and JAVA:

- JAVA and JAVASCRIPT overcome runtime monitoring requirements by introducing language interpretation via virtual machine implementation and execution of programs.
- C++ doesn't have a mainstream equivalent to date; due to its compiled nature.
I advocate YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF as the component through which any programming language may have for free by runtime execution, runtime monitoring capability.

5.3 Societal Outcome Improvement

Following points would be major improvements in society if usage of YERITH_{r&d}'s computer systems products would be promoted:

- Africa has very bad institutions in terms of following-up clients files such as for example in JUSTICE palaces ministries.

YERITH_{r&d} would love to supply governments in southern francophone Africa with affordable and useful software systems at low cost so to improve politics governance management and ACCOUNTABILITY.

- Affordability and accessibility of low priced and simple to use ERP systems may boost economy because the lack of business acumen knowledge of very young entrepreneurs would be compensate by implemented knowledge in ERP YERITH_{r&d}'s YERITH-ERP-9.0.

Let us for instance remember that at least 75% of Cameroon population is aged under 18 years old. Research investigations of YERITH_{r&d}, as reported last year (2022) in [NN23], shows an introduction of YERITH-ERP-9.0 usage teaching starting at the 09th year (class of "5^{ème} francophone", etc.)¹ of formal education in Cameroon would be very beneficial for young adult people when later on creating start-ups.

Especially, more than 90% of this under 18 years old young people stop schooling before reaching the 1st year of university education because of lack of funding, here in Cameroon of CPDM (RDPC) political ruling party.

- Advanced Software Technology [NOU23g, Nou23e, Nou23a, Nou23d] developed for YERITH-ERP-9.0, both as Free and Open Source Software (FOSS), and as commercial priced product; would boost and improve software system quality in Africa.

¹Last year report said 10th year.

Chapter 6

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University of Waterloo
 200 University Ave. West
 Waterloo Ontario
 Canada
 N2L3G1

Graduate Official Transcript

Duffin M. Caell
 Associate Vice-President
 Graduate Studies
 and Postdoctoral Affairs

Name: **Noumbissi Noundou, Xavier**
 Student ID: **20284586**
 Ontario Education Nbr: **445938806**

Beginning of Graduate Record

Fall 2009

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 1.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
ECE 725	Computer-Aided Verification	0.50	0.50	90

Winter 2010

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 2.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2010

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 3.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Fall 2010

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 4.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2011

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 5.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2011

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 6.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
CS 744	Advanced Compiler Design	0.50	0.50	86

Fall 2011

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 7.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Fall 2012

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 8.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

University of Waterloo
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Graduate Official Transcript

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 Associate Vice-President
 Graduate Studies
 and Postdoctoral Affairs

Name: **Noumbissi Noundou, Xavier**
 Student ID: **20284586**
 Ontario Education Nbr: **445938806**

Winter 2013

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 9.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
CS 846	Advanced Topics in Software Engineering	0.50	0.50	88
Course Topic:	Program Analysis of Web Apps			

Spring 2013

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 10.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
ECE 750	Special Topics in Computer Software	0.50	0.50	88
Course Topic:	Static Analysis for Softwr Eng			

Fall 2013

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 11.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2014

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 12.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2014

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 13.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Fall 2014

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 14.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2015

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 15.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	WD

Withdrawal Date: **04/30/2015**

Milestones

Program: **Engineering Doctoral**
PhD Comprehensive Examination
 Status: **Completed**
 Date Completed: **12/20/2011**
 Grade: **CR**

End of Graduate Official Transcript

University of Waterloo
 200 University Ave. West
 Waterloo Ontario
 Canada
 N2L3G1

Graduate Official Transcript

Duffin M. Caell
 Associate Vice-President
 Graduate Studies
 and Postdoctoral Affairs

Name: Noubissi Noundou, Xavier
Student ID: 20284586
Ontario Education Nbr: 445938806

Beginning of Graduate Record

Fall 2009

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 1.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
ECE 725	Computer-Aided Verification	0.50	0.50	90

Winter 2010

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 2.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2010

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 3.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Fall 2010

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 4.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2011

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 5.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2011

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 6.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
CS 744	Advanced Compiler Design	0.50	0.50	86

Fall 2011

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 7.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Fall 2012

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 8.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

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Name: Noubissi Noundou, Xavier
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Winter 2013

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<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
CS 846	Advanced Topics in Software Engineering	0.50	0.50	88
Course Topic:	Program Analysis of Web Apps			

Spring 2013

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 10.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
ECE 750	Special Topics in Computer Software	0.50	0.50	88
Course Topic:	Static Analysis for Softwr Eng			

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 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 11.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2014

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 12.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2014

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 13.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Fall 2014

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 14.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2015

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 15.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	WD

Withdrawal Date: 04/30/2015

Milestones

Program: Engineering Doctoral
 PhD Comprehensive Examination
 Status: Completed
 Date Completed: 12/20/2011
 Grade: CR

End of Graduate Official Transcript

- "Datou, KEMAJOU" Cameroonian gendarmerie colonel indic PAULETTE AZEFA tried to ASSASSINATE myself, openly, in front of at least 7 people, on Yaounde street, on January 09th, 2024.
- Kemajou spouses talk to people walking across roads that they shall't perform christian cross-signs since these interrupts sorcery they are doing on people walking on roads (June 3rd, 2024).
- Secret (hidden) orders of any type SHALL be out of civilian society.
- Cameroonian SHALL DEACTIVATE any kind of army soldiers estate, as SWITZERLAND has done in the past.
- Its not a good idea to judge people based on suspicious behavior, and not, real proven or not lived really facts.
- ROSE sangoun, a BIRTH GIVER of mine, SHALL'NT ANYMORE be causing so much trouble into my life because she entertains a rostricrucian affair with Prof. Dr. rer. pol. JEAN-CLAUDE SHANDA-TONME; AND with 'DORIS betebugang Gweh', 'tchitchui-teuntchou-noumeni-ingrède-ingrid-Chandiandri', 'Hugues Ntomani Tiako', 'Dr. Henriette Pola', and her spouse 'Dr. Laurent tchandeu'.
- People such as KEMAJOU, who acts as a colonel gendarmerie of Cameroon army ARE ALWAYS TRYING to overcome criminal laws of Geneva.
- I don't want to be living with people that have as profession the killing of other people.
- Rose sangoun sister, (Justice) DOROTHEE SHANDA NDJATIE, HAS TRIED to kill me by police force illegally in February 2021, as I have a file on judge HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA at DOUALA-ndokoti JUSTICE Palace ! • LAQUINTINE'S Psychiatrist EYOUN CHRISTIAN, MD, was involved together with 8 other persons at night around 11 : 30PM so to hijack my privately owned property in Douala-CITÉ-DES-PALMIERS. • JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMAI from same tribal tribe as ACCUSED Psychiatrist main offender (sawa-douala) ! • IT SEEMS "Dr christian eyoum, MD" the corrupted CPDM psychiatrist wanted myself to be sodomized by "BERTRAND" who broke the seal of my gate in steel.
- CIA (Central Intelligence Agency) shall'nt hire anymore incompetent persons like "Peter Alan Burh" 'Emmanuel-baleba-faux-pasteur' 'Brigitte-ékindî' 'magne-narcisse-qc-satan' 'robert-billy-joe-bob-tabet-depse-pd' 'NDZIE' 'PRC-présidence de la république du Cameroun' 'CHAPELLE DE LA GLOIRE DE CHRIST - marc denis djeng djeng - alias pasteur marc' 'jp-kamgain' 'psy-acteur-Eboungue (ing. pétrolier)' 'EMMANUEL-idiot; hors-mis agent-immobilier-soumbil (6 90 60 75 63)' 'santaire;SAPEUR-POMPIER-de-malheur-anti-gang;civil,indic-gendarme-policier-uniforme-medie' 'NORBERT ichatar' 'Bitoungi (douanes)' 'David Moniaux' 'Aurélie Yagno Kamdoun' 'DR. FOSSO-séd' 'Soot-canadien' 'sarah-landy-canadian-citizen' 'tchangoue-labforge.ca' 'carine-alias-edith - LÉLE - NJOUGEP - TCHANA' 'Julien-mboutou; santé publique' 'Dan Wasula wasou' 'so called pastor baptist church' 'KAMGA adamo - demon' 'Cameroon-chief-of-state; CAMEROUN:' 'SANDRINE yimbu' 'CHENGWA' 'DJOMO-Sawa-gilles-ézechiel' 'didi-ruben' 'mama-fouda' 'INES ngakou' 'Serge Achille Popoussi NONO - sed - cmr' '[ingrède-tchitchui-noumbissi;ingrid-tchitchui-noumbissi;ingrède-teuntchou-noumeni;ingrid-teuntchou-noumeni]; [NROUWANG] (dHOME) [TCHUDDJANG-séd-pré] [NGONGANG] 'Hôpital Jamou' 'assassins;dégingués.' 'LAURENT-tchandeu-henriette-pola' 'VOUFFO manuela-psy-malade-mentale' 'alain-elame' 'francis magloire come nkoulu' 'ZOUUMPE-jacky-diane' 'Pelagie METOUMO, epse tchoutou; hors-mis maître Pelagie METOUMO, epse tchoutou' 'BIYA (Paul et Chantal en particulier)' 'DAMLERCHRYSLER AG' 'Belvianne meilu nossi' 'Jean LOÏC siewe' 'GLOBAL EXPERT SOLUTION Sarl' 'maman THÉRESE de OMEGA-kom-sipa-eric-joël.' 'rigobert; géomètre; JEAN-bernard de OMEGA-kom-sipa-eric-joël.' 'Synclaire NJEUTCHA TCHANA; hors-mis maître Synclaire SCHULZE-SMIDT' 'Frack biya' 'M. onguéné (S2TBED-biya-franck)' 'David (GATE SOLUTION CENTER)' 'KREYENHOP (BLG logistics, CDU politicians)' 'Achilles Kouam (PAUL fokam kammgone)' 'Thierry Nyamen (Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.)' 'catholic-church' 'Criminal-DST.' 'MOÏSE-yamkam-tebiwo' 'REZA kopae (riskview inc.)' 'Thomas NDIE DJOTIO' 'Christelle-akamba-et-autres-noms-de-akamba' 'VALERIE' 'ALT LE PLUS' 'Nestor KENPACK (N.K. quincallerie)' 'atanga-nji-paul' 'Daniela-siemens-OCS-erlangen' 'Menguéné Mvindi' 'TCHEUFFA' 'Audrey NGUETTE tchanga' 'MBA-Claude bisseg' 'samaneh navabpour; amirhossein vakili' 'JHANE-ayachi' 'ZABER-algérien-bremen' 'DZUKOU-tate-foiso-viviane' 'ROSTAND-moungam' 'KOM-marcel-rostand-mepo' 'irene-ines-ngakou-temou-FAINÉANTEUS-suisse-bordellière' 'VANELLE-JUNIOR-laure AZEFA-gang' 'GODRICK chekete H.' 'paster Landry' 'Eric Joël KOM SIPA' 'Grégoire Owona (CPDM general secretary)' 'SANGO (Spouse Bernadette NOUNDOU(CMR-dgre)' 'gendarme essono en civil (iloga-iloga-aurelien)' 'GÉNÉRAL DE CORPS D'ARMÉE boubba.' 'consortium-conrad-black-ROTHSCHILB' 'GALAX-YVES-LANDRY-ETOGA-chien' 'jean-yang-CMU' 'HOGA-HOGA-AURELIEN' 'BORIS tossou; mbuembe-kevina-laure.' 'mezang-atvme INGRID.' 'TOM ball-mrs' 'maître-docteurs-professeurs.' 'JEAN-pierre moubeb' 'Chef-supérieur-douala.deido.-3ème degré' 'CHRISTIAN eyoum; laquintine; psy' 'SHANDA NDJATIE' 'MAXIME napoa eteme' 'sandy-séd-beidu; jo-atele' 'Joanne atvle' 'chauffeurs-soudeurs-souffleurs-gardiens-jaune-SARL-société' '(a so called baptist church pastor) Dr. PAUL simon nomo, Psy.D.' 'Majeed Mike (quantstamp.com)' 'LEO passos (quantstamp.com)' 'Iuc; masc. hypolithe tekeu.' 'Eunice GAPIE Yemte' 'Yves Francis DANTEU' 'TEUNTCHOU-chandiand-noumen' 'Winnie-shanda-joël.' 'Alexis TCHEUFA' 'Gervais Nana' 'JEAN CLAUDE SHANDA TONME' 'JACKSON-séd-njeutcha (Conquète.)' 'Jean-Paul YAMTICHE (AfriLand first bank; Intelligensia)' 'BISSCKE; nkondo-sodomiseur' 'JEAN-PIERRE kamgain' 'Bernadette NOUNDOU, Epse SANGO (cmr-dgre)' 'agent-santé.' 'JULES neteta noundou - (cmr-dgre)' 'temp FABRICE-WILFRIED-siemens-canadian-armed-forces; Prof. Dr. med. Norbert SIEMEN (CMR-séd)' 'Pharmacy fiango-ngoe-peter-AKUME' 'Ondréj Lhoták' 'Dr. Chantal NOUNDOU, Epse ... (cmr DGRE)' 'ANNIE METIAM' 'terreur - ;HONORE WOUCHE' 'POKAM-KWAM' 'Serge, jérusalem apostolat' 'NOUMBISSI' 'Guimezap' 'GEORGETTE' 'Victor Noundou Koliou cmr-séd' 'CHRISTIAN rikong ngueyong' 'Hilaire-yimido-bertrand-nguere; ancien-séd-gras-savoye.' 'gic-clovis-telecom-assassin'; 'CLOVIS-kemmegne' 'Jeanne MVONDO' 'CHETA' 'rodrigue-alain-sienchie-ngongang' 'angela WOLFGANG fernand JR owona' 'fanfan' 'GAUTHIER' 'SHANDA tonme' 'DR. GADJEU francis aimé tchana' 'lute' 'Patrick lam, Ph.D., P.Eng.' 'JON eyolfsson' 'Prof. Dr. rer. nat. Jan Peleska' 'Patrick'; ALL-others to try to kill humble black engineers and scientists.
- People like PAUL BIYA shall't be called president of all Cameroonian anymore because as CPDM ruling party, they harass people that don't call themselves from RDPC!

CONTACT

- Address: YECEFOIQ - "Immeuble YERITH"- barrière - Simbock, Mfoundi 6, Yaounde, Cameroon
- located opposite side of Biya's S2TBED forestry society (since 2015 officially) !
- Email: Yerith.Xavier@gmail.com

CITIZENSHIP ; PLACE OF BIRTH

Cameroonian , no other citizenship ; Douala (Littoral, Cameroon)

UPLOADED a copy of national id (N.20190242230510554) onto <https://www.facebook.com> this year 2024.

TEACHING STATEMENT

- [Teaching] and [Advising] is my priority at time since in Cameroon Software inception is very long and tedious because Cameroon authorities, Especially SED.
- My 1st professor and best educator is [prof. dr. rer. nat. habil. JAN-peleska], at the University of Bremen, Bremen, Germany; The 1st best teacher as of now was "prof. dr. URILICH KRAUSE-depse, at the University of Bremen; as well"; THE 1st best leader & 2nd best teacher as of now was "[Prof. Dr.-Ing. Patrick] Lam, at the [University of Waterloo, ONTARIO, CANADA]".
- I endeavor to teach what makes my research vivid ["RM: Program Software Runtime Monitoring"] and useful for young and adult people around the world; I can teach almost everything in Computer Sciences; I haven't practiced Computer Graphics, and Computer Imaging programming at all.

RESEARCHING GOALS IN COMPUTER SOFTWARE ENGINEERING - [CONTINUED]

- Create a very cheap and pragmatic Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP) software: (e.g. YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM[?]).
- CREATE a market place where stock exchanges occur real-time; [YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME] is used as platform for valuation of stocks; And for stock exchanges. THE market place is a physical place in "YERITH-R&D building"; THE physical stock exchanges occur outside of "YERITH-R&D building"; just a plot of land '5 meters' away on the opposite side of road leading to "YERITH R&D" !
- CREATE a computing device for YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF that will be a certified product with at least ISO, and CE stamps : [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET]; See also Fig. 22.

PROFESSIONAL COMPUTING ASSOCIATIONS MEMBERSHIPS

- Current: "acm: The Association for Computing Machinery"; "FME: Formal Methods Europe"; "ASQ: American Society for Quality".

PROFESSIONAL COMPUTING LITERATURE REVIEWS

- OOPSLA 2010

PROFESSIONAL INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOPS AND CONFERENCES

- IMRT radiation therapy at SIEMENS OCS Erlangen-BAVARIA-Germany 2008; [FSE-soqua 2006]; PLDI 2009; IBM CASCON 2010; MITACS ONTARIO 2012; PLDI 2012

PROFESSIONAL RESEARCH CONTRIBUTIONS / INTERESTS

- [JUDICIAL information] | [PUBLICATIONS] | [Figures] | [Tables] | [Trang] | [TALKS] | [Latest] | [Resume / CV - Overview] | [Engineering Methodologies & Tools Expertise] | Publications list on "www.zenodo.org" | Publications list on "www.archive.org"
- Operating System Debian Linux Distribution Contribution for customers of "YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0"; "YERITH-NISSI.". Bash; DEBIAN LINUX; Jan. 2017 -
- ERP-trading Stock Exchange Software: <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0> C++; Qt 5; Mar. 2015 -
- Software Engineering-Formal Methods [?][1] [C] / Software Validation / Software Verification CASE tools RT-Tester, MBT[1b]]
- Software Testing [22.22] (also with "VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GMBH"). JUNIT 4 Tutorial[1]
- A. Web JAVA Dynamic Taint Analysis[3] | Qt 5-Designer as WYSIWYG Tool | Development (YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0) | Cyber-Safety | Security
 - JudoDB, with "Dr. Patrick Lam (doctor-Ph.D. advisor of mine)"; <https://github.com/patricklam/judodb> GWT, PHP; JAVA; June 2014 - Nov. 2014
 - WEB Cyber-Security[2] [?] [3] [?] (PLG SEMINAR AT DAVID R. CHERITON SCHOOL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)
- C. Information Flow Policy Control; Typstate-API usage rule checking; Dynamic Program Analysis Monitoring
 - https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif C++; Qt 5; June 2022 -
 - YERITH_QVGE: A Framework for Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime
FOSS Code location, EXCEPT for commercial CASE drawing tool : <https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif> C++; Qt-Dbus; June 2022 -
 - <https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis> JAVA; Firebug; Jan. 2013 - Apr. 2013
- D. Static Program Code Analysis Verification; Compilers; Verifiable DSL (Verifiable Domain-Specific Languages)
 - 20.20 Open Source (FOSS) Contribution to "Valkyrie: Valgrind-GUI"; https://github.com/yerithrd/valkyrie_NON_OFFICIAL C++; Qt 5; July 2023 -
 - 1d Vordiplom-B.Sc. Independent Study: A Semantic Comparison between Timed Automata and Büchi Automata Set-Algebra; Sep. 2004 - Dec. 2004
 - 34 <https://github.com/AmesianX/saint> LLVM; C++; JAVA
 - 1d https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang flex, bison; Apr. 2023 -
 - 32 JAVA static code analysis [34] | Ph.D. thesis: Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software LLVM; SOOT; JAVA

SUMMER SCHOOL PARTICIPATION — HIGHLIGHTS — [CONTINUED]

- "Management Psy Human Resource Course" - Collège Integ, Douala, Littoral, Cameroun — Taught by "Dr. Jean Moubeb, Psy.D." Jan. 2020 - June 2020

CHEFTAINCY / MISCELLANEOUS

- KING YERITH-NISSI. (Prophet of Jeovah-nissi, "Isaiah 45" (SINCE nov. 14; 2014) in HOLY BIBLE, PAROLE DE VIE-(Amis pour toujours) - French language)
- I also act as a Prophet described in "Apocalypse 12".
- I also act as a Prophet described in "Apocalypse 1", named 'Fidèle, et Véritable'.
- Creator and Professor at YECEFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE), a subsidiary of YERITH R&D
- "High Qualified Person-migrant in CANADA (Québec, then Ontario) for 9 years until August 2014".
- Driving license class B - Cameroon & Canada

PROFESSIONAL TOOLS AND PROGRAMMING LANGUAGES

- **Operating Systems:** MS Windows (XP, 98, 2000, 7, 10, 11), DEBIAN LINUX (8, 9, 10, 11, 12)
- **SCM (Source Code Version Management Tools):** Git, Mercurial (hg), SVN, Rational ClearCase
- **Web Technologies:** YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0, MariaDB, HTML5, CSS, PHP, Quercus, Apache Tomcat, GWT (Google Web Toolkit), JSP
- **Scripting Languages:** Cygwin, Python, sed, AWK, Bash
- **Programming languages, Debugging, and Testing Analysis tools:** YRI_QVGE[13.13], UML 2.0, SCALA, JAVA, C/C++, JUnit-5, DDD, Gcov, VALKYRIE YERITH[20.20], LTSA
- **Programming & Compiler Frameworks:** DIFF, Patch, Tx1, apache ANT, MAKE, Qt 5, SOOT, LLVM, flex, bison, Eclipse IDE, Codeblocks, CharmNT

UNIVERSITY LEVEL TEACHING (AS A TEACHING ASSISTANT PH.D. CANDIDATE; THEN A "DOCTOR-PHD")

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA (OCTOBER 2009 – APRIL 2015)

- **Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465) | Methods and Tools for Software Engineering (ECE 650) | Foundations of Software Engineering (ECE 651) | Programming for Performance (ECE 459) | Computer Networks (ECE 428) | Compilers (ECE 351) | [C++ Laboratory (ECE 250)].**

ACADEMY WORK RESEARCH EXPERIENCE – 1

- **Start-up YERITH R&D, Douala, LITTORAL region, CAMEROON** March 2025 – Currently
PROFESSOR PROFESSOR DOCTOR-ENGINEER (PR. PROF. DR-ING.) for Computer Engineering ([RESEARCH] & [TEACHING]), at YECEFOIQ, CEO
- **IUC (Institut Universitaire de la Côte), Douala, Littoral region, CAMEROON** 2019
Web Software Developer Consultant (NUMERHIS-ERP Web Application Development); advised by Hypolithe Tekeu, MASC
- **IAI (Institut Africain d'Informatique) Cameroon, Yaounde, Center, CAMEROON** 2016
Professor (Prof.) – Consulting Lecturer (Computer Architecture for Software Engineers in anglophone section); advised by: Ing. (B.Sc.) Salabessi (and Mr. Nanga)
- **Professional and Academic Degree [Ph.D. in Computer Science (Specialization : Programming Languages)]** March 10, 2015 !
University of Waterloo, Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA
PhD Comprehensive Examination (DR-ING. (PhD)) – ECE-University of Waterloo December 20, 2011 !
PhD Research Seminar [TALK] – ECE-University of Waterloo April 16, 2014
PhD Dissertation Defence (Ph.D.) – CS-University of Waterloo January 2015
doctoral "Ph.D. degree" dissertation (Excerpt of Full not required text, by Patrick LAM, Ph.D.): *Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM*
(November 23, 2025) Addendum of co-related research in Program Analysis: **Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software by Program Analysis FOR Safety & Security** (https://www.archive.org/details/yerith-program-analysis-2023/YERITH-PROGRAM_ANALYSIS_2024_With_CURRICULUM_vitae_2024.pdf)
- ★ **The University of Waterloo (ECE at WatForm), Ontario, CANADA** September 01, 2012 – March 10, 2015
Professor (PostDoctoral Fellow; Prof. – Expert in a domain of science) for Computer Engineering ([RESEARCH] & [TEACHING]) at ECE (program analysis & software testing research, and teaching (also related courses) | around \$2, 500 Canadian dollars for a term payment; 8 terms in total ≈ 2 – years.
"Graduate-student 1: Divam Jain (CS-MMATH, JAVA-SOOT) | Graduate-student 2: Zheng (Felix) Fang (ECE-MASc, Divam's research continuation) | [ALL STUDENTS]"
"Advisor 1: Pr. Prof. Dr-Ing. Igor Ivkovic | Advisor 2: Pr. Prof. Dr-Ing. Vijay Ganesh | Advisor 3: Pr. Prof. Dr-Ing. Patrick Lam | Advisor 4: Pr. Prof. Dr-Ing. Sivoththaman Siva"
"Colleague 1: Pr. Prof. Dr-Ing. Ondřej Lhoták | Colleague 2: Pr. Prof. Dr-Ing. Nomair Naem | Colleague 3: Pr. Prof. Dr-Ing. Fabrice Wilfried Siemeni | Colleague 4: Pr. Prof. Dr. Godrick H. Chékété | Colleague 5: Pr. Prof. Dr-Ing. mahesh tripunitara | Colleague 6: Pr. Prof. Dr. Derek Rayside | Colleague 7: Pr. Prof. Dr-Ing. LEO passos | "Colleagues in christianity (Prof. Dr. Yaw Boakye-Agyeman, Nana Yaw, Eric Brefo-Mensah, Chiwanza Kasanga, Mushota Kasanga and spouse Timi) – -ATTENDED "koinonia church in bloomingdale, ON"; "apostle continuation church in brampton, ON"."
- **IBM CANADA Ltd., Markham, Ontario, CANADA (SABBATICAL-year from The-University-of-Waterloo-Ontario-Canada.)** January 01, 2012 – August 31, 2012
Thorough security check screening done for employment by employer IBM Canada LTD before starting employment.
Graduate Intern (JAVA-J9 Just-In-Time Compilation Optimization for IBM Websphere); advised by Prof. Vijay Sundaresan; and Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam
- ★ **PROFESSIONAL (AND ACADEMIC) DEGREE. Doctor of Engineering (academic equivalent to a "doctoral PhD in Electrical and Computer Engineering") [D.ENG. (DR-ING. in "French")]** | around \$2, 500 Canadian dollars for a term payment; 7 terms in total ≈ 2 – years.
Engineering Doctoral Ph.D. degree Program (Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD) at The University of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA September 01, 2009 – December 20, 2011 !
► **"DOCTOR-ENGINEER [DR-ING. (D.ENG. in "English")]" degree Program (Specialization : Software Engineering & Testing & Verification & Analysis)**
► **Successfully Passed PhD Comprehensive Examination on "December 20, 2011" – Overall Grade 88% [A+] Department of Electrical & Computer Engineering (ECE)**
Research Proposal (doctoral Ph.D. Thesis in Electrical and Computer Engineering): **Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software**
Mathematics Subject Classification: 68—Computer Science
Computer Science Subject Classification: Software Engineering, Program Verification, Program Analysis (static code analysis, dynamic program analysis)
Advisor 1: Pr. Prof. Dr-Ing. Nomair Naem | Advisor 2: Pr. Prof. Dr-Ing. Ondřej Lhoták | Advisor 3: Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam | Advisor 4: Prof. Dr. Sivoththaman Siva
- **The University of Waterloo (ECE at WatForm), Ontario, CANADA** September 01, 2009 – December 20, 2011
Teaching Assistant & Research Assistant for Computer Software Engineering (program analysis (static code and dynamic analysis) research, and teaching assistantship in computer software engineering); Advised by Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam, and Prof. Dr. Sivoththaman Siva
- **Post-Master Work with SIEMENS Healthineers (OCS – Varian), Erlangen, Bayern, GERMANY** November 01 2007 – July 31 2009
Thorough security check screening done for employment by employer "SIEMENS AG" before starting employment.
Software-Engineer (Junior Software Developer) (CE-FDA certified software code development; Radiation Therapy DMIP communication control protocol C++ development); advised by: Ing. (M.Sc.) DARIO MERAVIDGLIA, and Dipl.-Inf. (FH) GERHARD SENG.
- ★ **PROFESSIONAL (AND ACADEMIC) DEGREE. Diplom-Informatiker (academic equivalent to a "Master 2 in Computer Science"; 270-ECTS points) | around \$400 Euros for a semester payment; 11 semesters including GERMAN language courses time included.**
I HAVE SACRED this diploma certificate ("Duplicate by Prof. Dr-Ing. UTE bormann and Prof. Dr. Kerstin Schill; from November 01, 2017)" in front of BISHOP at St-Patrick Church in Toronto-downtown, ONTARIO, CANADA;
just 3 weeks after resigning my shit-CANADIAN CITIZENSHIP at KITCHENER-WATERLOO criminal justice court [Living in Salvation Army Shelter near Justice Court.].
Integrated Bachelor's & Master's degree in Computer Science Program at The Elite-University of Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY October 01, 2002 – May 25, 2007
► **"DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER" degree Program (Specialization : Software Engineering & Testing) – Grade 1.6/4 [A+] Department of Mathematics and Computer Science**
Diplomarbeit (Master Thesis): *Statistical test case generation for reactive systems* | Advisor: Prof. Dr. Jan Peleska
- **AGBS at The University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY** September 01, 2006 – February 28 2007
(Part-Time) Software System Developer (A 'UML 2.0 profile statecharts' plugin for 'Borland-Together'); advised by: Prof. Dr. Jan Peleska
- **"IMMIGRATION CANADA delivers myself a High Qualified Person-migrant permanent residency for CANADA"** 2005
FORMER-family member in Canada : "Théodore Wandji Ngongang (5850 Rue Souart Apt 7, H3S 2E8, Montreal, QC, Canada)"
I already passed my Bachelor's degree in CS ("Vordiplom in Informatik Certificate") before gaining High Qualified Person Permanent Resident Card
- **Bergmann Automaten GmbH (now Gewete GmbH), Rellingen, Hamburg, GERMANY** March 01, 2005 – April 31, 2007
(Part-Time) Software System Developer (WERKSTUDENT) (JAVA servlet and C++ communication protocol development); advised by: Dipl.-Ing. (FH) SVEN KAMRATH (and Dipl.-Ing. JENS MÖLLER)
- **ZMML at The University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY** February 01, 2003 – February 28, 2005
(Part-Time) WEB AND "RAD" APPLICATION DEVELOPER (Creating websites, and RAD-server self tests evaluation programs); advised by Prof. Dr. rer. pol. Klaus Jürgen Bönkost

CONVICTIONS ABOUT CIVIL SOCIETY – CONTINUED – 2

- CIA (Central Intelligence Agency) shalln't hire anymore incompetent persons like 'Jeanne-chantal andela;vendeuse-sauvette.' 'nguema;huissier-de-justice;tchopba' 'churches; in USA-abroad; or whatsoever similar; so-called humanitarianism.' 'road-seller; seller anywhere else' 'relatives' agent' 'SOLITA-voisine-sed' 'IRIS Mbieukop; pof.' 'agent-ministère-défense-cameroun.' 'henri-bertrand-ngatchou (Best Car Care & SERVICES)' 'YAGER MABOMA'; to try to kill humble black engineers and scientists.

		SCHOLARSHIPS & AWARDS
• Ontario Graduate Scholarship (OGS; 4000–\$CAD per term)		2009 – 2015 (a total of 15 terms)
		FREE TIME HOBBIES
• Aikido, Swimming, and "Gospel Choir 'GEORGIA MASS CHOIR'" listening.		
		ACADEMY WORK RESEARCH EXPERIENCE – 2
■ HABILITATION, equivalent • Topic: "Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime" Start-up YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, CAMEROON Proposal: YERITH_QVGE: A Framework for Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime (Details at link 1)		June 01, 2022 – Currently
■ Start-up YEROTH R&D, Yaoundé, CENTER region, CAMEROON Software Verification & Validation Fellow, CEO		October 2018 – November 2023
■ Start-up Yeren Labs, Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA CTO (Chief Technology Officer), CEO		September 2017 – September 2018
■ Start-up Yeren, Yaounde, CENTER region, CAMEROON CTO (Chief Technology Officer), CEO		April 2015 – August 2017
× [PKFokam Research Institute, Yaounde, Center, CAMEROON] Professor (Prof.) Ph.D. -seeker (Static Code Analysis Research from WATERLOO.); advised by: [Dr. PAUL fokam-kammogne], & [Dr. Ing. JUSTIN-bomda]; [and M. Samuel-DIMITE] "JAN-peleska" & "University of Waterloo" try to hijack myself through this 2-days-job-contract [All people pro-eminent persons I have seen at his banks, "including Deceased gay-pd GERVAIS mendoze", are in prison !!! (419–scam)]		
■ Judo-Québec, Montreal, Quebec, CANADA (Part-Time) Web Development Consultant (JAVA SE 7, GWT, PHP) for JUDODB; advised by: Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam		JUNE 2014 – NOVEMBER 2014
■ RiskView Inc., Toronto, Ontario, CANADA Software Consultant for Finance Software Security (SCALA servlet development for Finance); advised by: Reza Kopae, M.Sc.		January 2013
■ We4IT GmbH, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY Software Development Internship (J2EE, MySQL web application for medical personal training management); advised by Dipl.-Inf. Stephan Sucker		June 2005 – July 2005
■ SGS Cameroon, Douala, littoral REGION, CAMEROON System administration internship (Computer networked installation; employee desktop technical support; (MS Windows NT, MS Windows 2000, etc.); advised by CHENGWA, & ...)		September 2004
■ bremen4u GmbH, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY Web development internship, System Administration (MySQL, RedHat linux, JSP, PHP, HTML5, CSS); advised by Martin, B.Sc.		March 2004
■ IWT at The University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY (Part-Time) Student Metal Processing & Measurement Helping Scientist; advised by: Dipl.-Ing. Sven Bengelsdorf.		October 2002 – January 2003
■ DaimlerChrysler AG, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY Industrial Chain Worker (Kfz-Schlosser Helper); setting of Mercedes personal cars seat belts		June 2002 – August 2002
■ Briel & Kjær, Technology Park – University of Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY (Part-Time) Student Helper (event management); advised by: Dipl.-Pol. Torben (and Dr. Woehring)		July 2002 – September 2002
■ Cyberix, Douala, Littoral region, CAMEROON Web Development Internship (HTML, CSS); advised by: Ing. Fogueum (and Théodore Wandji Ngongang)		October 2001 – November 2001
■ GCE A Level in Exact Sciences; BACCALAURÉAT C (Mathematics, etc.) Grade of "11.59 / 20" Douala, LITTORAL region, CAMEROON		2000
■ GCE O Level in Exact Sciences; PROBATOIRE C (Mathematics, etc.) Grade of "12.09 / 20" Douala, LITTORAL region, CAMEROON		1999
■ B.E.P.C (Brevet d'Études DU PREMIER CYCLE) Douala, LITTORAL region, CAMEROON		1997
■ C.E.P.E (CERTIFICAT D'ÉTUDES PRIMAIRES ÉLÉMENTAIRES) Douala, LITTORAL region, CAMEROON		1993

PROFESSIONAL COMMUNICATION LANGUAGES

- | | |
|---|---|
| • FRENCH, and ENGLISH | CAMEROON; NATIVE |
| • "GERMAN DSH LANGUAGE CERTIFICATE", Sehr Gut (Very Good) | April 2002 (UNIVERSITY OF DORTMUND, DORTMUND, NRW, Germany) |
| • "ENGLISH USA TOEFL-IBT", Grade 86 | June 2018 (Hamilton, Ontario, Canada) |

[SUMMER SCHOOL PARTICIPATION] – ADDENDUM

- | | |
|---|-----------------------------|
| • "Online Software Security Course" – Stanford University, California, USA | June 2013 – August 2013 |
| • "CUT 1 – Certificate in University Teaching1" – University of Waterloo, Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA | 2010 |
| • "First Summer School on Formal Techniques" – NSF, SRI International, Menlo College, Atherton, California, USA | May 22, 2011 – May 27, 2011 |
| • "Graduate Student English Training Course" – Université du Québec à Montréal (UQAM), Montreal, Quebec, Canada | Aug. 2009 |
| • "Graduate Management Admission Test (GMAT) Preparation Course" – Concordia University, Montreal, Quebec, Canada | June 2007 |
| • "C Programming Language Preparation Course" – UY 1, ENSPY, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon — Taught by "Master-1 Mr. Donfack (ENSPY)" | Aug. 2001 – Sep. 2001 |

5. **CREATE** a software component full-featured that enables ERP-stock data import using a technology Kind-of VOICE-to-text !
6. Create a framework that allows for formal method specification of static dataflow analyzes as temporal property verification formulas;
Such a framework generate code software as static staged dataflow analyzes for its users.
More importantly, I will try to reuse previous work done for [YRI_QVGE\[13.13\]](#) research work, as part deliverable.
7. **TRY** to integrate research results on software security in "YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum "; from Vijay GANESH research (<https://research.gatech.edu/people/vijay-ganesh>); MOST possibly using "SDMM".
8. Automatic generation of web HTML pages from a Domain Specific Language (DSL) that is more approachable for a high level programming language perspective (i.e: similar to C++ / JAVA): YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0[27.27].
9. Create and render software analysis, debugging, and testing tools as easy as possible to use, with only finite automata theory background; and / or Typestate-API usage rule checking typestate-API knowledge (e.g.: [YERITH-SAINT\[34\]](#), [SDMM\[1d\]](#), [YRI_QVGE\[13.13\]](#), VALKYRIE-VALGRIND[20.20]).
10. **Prepare** a course on "Software System Security Vulnerability Detection and Analysis". I prepare this course material so to implement a software system for protecting other software from malware.
11. Create a stand-alone software product that enables medical physician to augment their efficiency in terms of patient work flow throughput : 'yerith-sante-organigramme'
Even Dr. Christian EYOUM find this utility-tool very impressive in terms of effectiveness & simplicity if this could be really in his world (PSY) implemented !
12. Create a stand-alone tool that generates code for creating statechart C++ code for mealy machine state diagram ([SDMM\[1d\]](#)).
This tool is specifically created and programmed for generating code that uses checkboxes to select options for Graphical User Interface [GUI] code.
13. **Position** "static dataflow analysis research and techniques" as similar as runtime verification (i.e.: circle 4 in Figure 18; e.g.:PH.D. THESIS[32], [YERITH-SAINT\[34\]](#)).
14. **Create** and produce a computer device that could be embedded into other computer devices and that will communicate with them through serial ports and / or USB interfaces SO to provide YRI_QVGE program verification to USER FINISHED products on-the-fly, AS an add-on ENGINEERED industrial product: ALSO this product could qualify for an CE—ISO—related certification for avionics, railways, automotive, and CE—ISO certifications for Healthcare : [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET].

1.1 CAMEROON new country name based on CHRISTIANITY-jesus-of-nazareth-NAME-and-TRIBES-number

Changing CMR onto YERITH as country name since JESUS-OF-Nazareth utilizes 12 237 as number of tribes for its ISRAEL tribe.

2.2 National Currency BILLS and / or COINS

- CMR YERITH NATIONAL Money currency as 'YERITH-dollar ("JESUS-OF-Nazareth"-dollar)'.

THIS money currency bill and / or coin system will be backed by computing systems from YERITH R&D; AS open-sourced products :

- 1.) YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME; A software-system product created out of Enterprise Resource Planing Software YRI_QVGE[13.13.7] that is also usable as an algorithmic trading system !

3.3 National Identification

1. A system allowing any of the 3 documents cited below as valid official identification for any official or unofficial activity shall be implemented in Central CEMAC:

1. Valid NATIONAL IDENTITY CARD
2. Valid PASSPORT CEMAC—CEDEAO
3. Valid bank account id.
4. ALL PERSONS working with weapons or force by law have to be identified with names on badge wherever they are outside of their working places.

A bank account id IS in effect linked to a Valid national identity card.

""MOÏSE YAMKAM TEBIWO (Mtn-network: 6 75 66 24 87)" for instance, a cousin paternal "French—germain" of mine, Could afford for a law school with a bank account that wasn't really linked with his by birth official IDENTITY documents !"

MOÏSE YAMKAM TEBIWO (Mtn-network: 6 75 66 24 87) also possesses a diplomatic passport at least or equivalent because he also works for MINREX.

IN effect, "MOÏSE YAMKAM TEBIWO (Mtn-network: 6 75 66 24 87)" was a diplomat before joining the LAW-school in LAGOS—corrupt.

I could notify this since the law school of lagos he attended didn't issue for a certificate with exact same official birth identity names as written thereof.

THIS COUSIN OF MINE IS A CRIMINAL in all systems of justice worldwide.

2. 1 system, computerized, and / or, a text registry book shall be created to register any Cameroon citizen with no need for any citizen to walk around with a national identity card.
3. There are some drawbacks as for instance mentioned on the website of FREE SOFTWARE FOUNDATION, in the United States of America (USA), to have a centralized registration system for citizen or People living inside a country !
4. *"A gervais nana (gersatelgmail.com)" I know somewhere in YDE, seems to be connected as a free-mason to ""MOÏSE YAMKAM TEBIWO"" .*
"GERVAIS NANA" must be investigated since I know "TEBIWO-YAMKAM-MOÏSE" Is a murderer in all systems.
5. I remember having an issue with a screen of a laptop I bought to a place (GERSATEL) owned by *"Gervais NANA"* ; after 1 day, A blur appeared on the screen and I wasn't reimbursed.
6. *It seems "WELADJI" a burglar that I went with at Gendarmerie D'AKWA-SUD in 2023 because he apparently tried to steal 20, 000 FRANCS as a non used money for a purchase item that I ordered from his shop at DLA—douala-bar;*

"WELADJI" WAS NOW in position in another shop where I started buying stuff for my customers. "Moubeb-Jean" is working just at opposite side of this computer hardware shop in Douala: "COLLEGE INTEG".

7. *"ISAAC TEUNTCHOU-poltron-peggist" , a father in law of 1 uterine sister of my person; "Ingride NOUMBISSI TCHITCHUI (heiratet (SPOUSE): Dipl.-Ing. (FH)-CHANDRIAND Teuntchou Nouneni, MSc.)" is trying to hijack from my propriety all my real-estate.*
8. *shanda tonne-jean-claude; bob-tabet-peggist-Deido-plage-poisson-braisé, the idiot that sleeps with rose-sangnou my genitor; AND with her sister Dorothee shanda owona " (LEVITICUS 20 : 12 – 14)."*
"OLAMCAM (tel.:6 52 12 65 57 --georges-kamdem) (peggist working in Douala shipment-haven) owner Tabet-bob (OWNING a house in "bonaberi"; money from bribery in ONTARIO according to JP-kamgain sayings) & friends GEORGES-kamdem; & JP-kamgain; they have tried to sodomize myself with Christian-eyoum-c.p.d.m [by trying to say to JP-kamgain-to act as a friend-of-myself]. "
"BOB-tabet is an ancient jail-black-attendee of ONTARIO justice system that escaped Canada by talks I heard [of KAMGAIN].""
"[Culprit-JP-kamgain] told me once [TAFET-ROBERT]-wanted-HR-module payment services for his employees in DOUALA.'
9. *ISAAC-teuntchou, the idiot that sleeps with his daughter-in-law; TEUNTCHOU-nouneni-chandriand is currently trying to hijack my property of DLA-cité-des-palmiers-beedi, BY Sending INGRID to my attorney of law so to try to say that SHE wants some money from my current ongoing rental agreement with a so called MELEU-belvianne, AND her fiancée called SEWE-idiot-toie.*

10. *"Audrey-NGUETIE-tehamga" shalln't anymore go and seek people from my former places of work to try to tell them I abandon her after 1—night.*

THIS disgusting megere wasn't capable of understand I cannot be fornicating with someone that Cannot imagine herself as a wife in a non-gay homosexual matrimonial house AS i could observe from her gay—white-salsa friends & sister "YOLLANDE-nguetie married at that other senegalese in Montreal

"TCHAMAHA ntaata GUTTEMBERG" & "Remi-POUASSI-taata" who are my blood-family (father-theo-chien-noumbissi-batchieu—babouantou) cousins & 'also blood-village people of MAURICE-nguetie' & 'Audrey-nguetie-tehamga; SHALL know that Homosexuality is a disease from a BORN—again christian point of view: ITS cure is living without any sexual encountering as proclaimed in " 1 Corinthians 7 : 1 " & " 1 Corinthians 7 : 38–40 " !

11. When you say to your children not to open a door when a child of you senior or whoever arrives at your home when you are not there; YOU—victor should think that you were coming to my house when I was aged under 7 years old.

YOU should think that never my father or my mother said that to you. IT means you were may be trying to kill someone in that marriage; AS you are coined today by ROSE who told me not to eat anymore from your household !

12. *VICTOR-koliou-serpent—Tchandeu-gay thinks he is linked to myself by my late father; I Have already told this culprit & wretched canadian-traveler as a assassin that could be even arrested just at airport; Like I was faultily arrested by canadian-faked police so to destroy my luxurious image !*

THIS criminal worldwide, since he even called before I attended 3 days & nights at his junior-est brother DEMO—noundou house in Hamburg—Germany; to say that Demo could even not even respond to any call of myself because I did not notify him—demo when I was leaving Cameroon.

There is a fake idolatry—people like "bamileke"—demo & tchandeu-family-noundou; That if you want to attend a living at someone place, you must call onto him before you arrive. THIS kind of guja—assassin—diplomat schizophrenic-idea is in fact to listen to calls & organize fake routes with spies everywhere so to dictate how your daily life shall look like !.—MVONDO.

Following items from previous page; JUSTICE and PAST-MEMORIES to heal in Cameroon

9. Multiple or DOUBLE citizenship **SHALL NOT be allowed** since Africans are not well behaved to use and observe strict rules that are due to protect civilians with only 1 citizenship appurtenance.
10. Double citizenship with following countries that harasses honest Cameroonian like myself shalln't be allowed:
- Canada
 - United States of America (USA)
 - Germany
 - Any country where a gay-homosexual-marriage is pronounced in a so-called **"JESUS-OF-NAZARETH"** congregation: I.E: such a country shall be considered a scam **"(LEVITICUS 20:12-13, and Romans 1:26-28)!"**

SIMPLICE-kameni and alike people must be imprisoned.

HJACKING properties and down-casting businesses of elite-intellectualist from abroad like myself and others I may not even know about is what make them have a life luxurious around C.P.D.M and SED-yves-landry-galax-etoga-idiot; so called secret-services.

" THERE is also another "negger" working on behalf of simplice-kameni as LEAD of the so-called-cocaine-reseller wood-factory S2T-BED, called IDIOT-repeating-christian-signs; that behave like so-called "TONTON-makout' in HAITI-movies; (<https://wwwurl>) YOU see this kind of people that kills under behalf of a politician like BIYA; AND that you cannot even prosecute because there is no whereabouts of his origins or identities here in Cameroon-official-Communaute-URBAINE-de-YAOUNDE. "

" !! ALSO this biya-cpdm-gang against a proper african descendant on AFRIKA-soil Has a motto: ABSURDITY !!! "

FACTS:

1. kill where life is supposed to be saved;
Example: USE your own blood-giver to hijack your life and properties [REFERENCE.]

HOSPITAL is used to destroy lives.

2. destroy where it is supposed to be killed;

POLICE and ARMY kill people that go to them for seeking help after being robbed or whatsoever here in AFRIKA;

so called **UNITED-nations** (<https://www.un.org>) are only a replacement for colonies by white-supremacists.

- IT seems it is cameroon-cpdm-people who are UNITED nations workers here in CMR; HERE.

4.4 JUSTICE and PAST-MEMORIES to heal in Cameroon

1. [~~Dr. PAUL Siméon nomo, from MONATÉLÉ came to my private house in YDE-AAHALA, to arrest illegally without any notification or whatsoever, using a firefighter truck and 3 firefighter to molest myself in front of several neighbors so to discredit my life as a peaceful citizen of Cameroon.]
HE seems this criminal assassin from BIYA private places is now living in Maryland, USA; since I went back to Canada to resign from CANADIAN shit citizenship.
Another cousin of mine so called "[Rodrigue Alain Sienchie]", told me that 1 day armed soldiers with uniforms came to arrest him in the house of his parents, sent by "[Dorothée SHANDA-NDJATIE OWONA]"; THEN went to sodomized him at LAQUINTINIE HOSPITAL.
"SO I SUSPECT this criminal LAURENT TCHANDEU-DJATIE DOROTHÉE OWONA to have sent to my private house in Yaounde in 2017 this 'so called baptist church pastor Dr. SIMEON NOMO, PSY.D.'."~~
2. "Eyoum Christian" idiot's immunity of justice because he is a psychiatrist Must be investigated !
3. 'S2TBED', finally repairs our main common road: They destroyed a previous road with LATERITE so much that IT must be fixed with concrete !
4. 'S2TBED', biya's illegal industrial forestry enterprise society, an illegal neighbor of "Immeuble YERITH" of mine, IS constantly disrupting electrical energy current supply.
5. ALL my real estate in Douala (3 3-bedrooms apartments) need to be released by a genitor of mine THAT is not anymore wanted in my life because of all atrocities SHE CONSTANTLY commits with SHANDA GREGROIRE OWONA Wolfgang TCHAMOU angela ndjatie. !!!
SISTER'S of Rose Sangnou my genitor, Dorothée Shanda Ndjatie, IS CONSTANTLY harassing her to take me to any psychiatric institute by force, Even though there is already a criminal investigation against her and Rose Sangnou at DLA-ndokoti justice palace; DOROTHÉE is a criminal PERSON !
6. 'MADO's brother CAPTAIN pierre marcellin emana nkoa' must reimburse back my 210 000 FRANCS since SEMIL (Sécurité Militaire) told me in 2016 THAT THEY CANNOT convoke them SINCE receipts were signed by his cousin "JEAN-DE-DIEU onana".
"MY NEIGHBOR CARINE LELE NJOUGEPE TCHANA", seems to be here because of them, so to deteriorate the quality of life of legal people living here, and promote their own-beings through propoganda LIKE 'it seems THE colonel living THERE above of the hill IS the one that FIXED the road leading to your compound !
7. JUSTICE FOR BREAKING AND torturing myself (Xavier noumbissi Noundou [DR-ING. PR. PROF.]) in front of at least 17 people in front of my inherited personal domicile in Douala-Béedi-Cite-des-Palmiers MUST be finalized before Cameroon election 2025.
8. 'JUSTICE president and certain types of judges must be apolitical: I.e.: THEY CANNOT BELONG TO A POLITICAL PARTY !
9. MARTINEZ ZOGO assassin AMOUGOU BELINGA justice criminal court must be finished before Cameroon election 2025.
10. PEOPLE responsible for the drama of Edea Railway Failure in .. MUST be judged in a civil criminal court before Cameroon election 2025.
11. MILITARY SOLDIERS that killed about "7 women and their teddies in north Cameroon must be judged."
12. "EDGARD ALAIN MEBE NGO'O" criminal procedure in military justice courts must be achieved before Cameroon election 2025.
13. Military Soldier must have their own facilities and amenities in cities, and not mixed intermingle anymore with civilians, AS THIS IS CURRENTLY THE CASE when they DON'T wear military attire uniform !
In fact, MILITARY SOLDIERS or Alike don't have a same behavior justice as civilians; Not talking about habits and gesture.
14. Bepanda drama because of 'general MPAY' must be re-recovered in a justice palace court of civilians and / or military justice !

5.5 ACADEMY and Technology Research Institutions

1. Promote creation of research centers for solving problems located specifically in central west Africa:
 1. Another source of revenue for CMR
 2. Improving life conditions for CMR and neighboring friend countries.
2. Enable a financing WITH non reimbursement option for doctors in science and / or engineering.

6.6 Employments and JOBS creation for adult people

1. THERE must be a minimum amount of jobs offer for each society that was funded by the government for researching and improving life quality in CMR and neighboring countries.
2. *WOMEN that are selling goods outside of their home like "CAROLE mangue" (la fille de "MA-bernadette" au secrétariat-d'état-yves-idiot.) shalln't be part of SED or any governmental secret or not agencies !!!*
THIS culprit shall also try to not resell goods that were illegally imported into CMR.
3. ALL PEOPLE that were trained by the BIYA-regime as illegal para-military personal, MUST go into peace-keeper corps organization of the UNITED NATIONS or somewhere else so to keep cities and villages free of fire and all other destructive people.

FOR instance people like "PASCAL dayang", working at "S2TBED" of the culprit franck-biya has insinuated to myself that HE will disrupt any business activities that I-doctor-of-engineering Xavier NOUMBISSI NOUNDOU will perform in my compound !!!

["S2TBED"- "PASCAL dayang mercenary SED soldier" as threat in CMR !!!]

4. Transform all wood factories within city of YAOUNDE in computer desktop and / or laptop assembly production units

7.7 JUSTICE and DIVINITIES

1. *Destruction of all secret services units in Cameroon !!*
 1. "OUATARA people shall not anymore be opponent to christian people here in Cameroon as it is the case with Shanda-TONME jean claude" presently.
 2. People like SHANDA OWONA harass other people because they feel as safest as possible because of some kind of impunity based on their appurtenance to DGRE special unit forces ("JEAN CLAUDE shanda tonme and spouse" weren't for instance infringed in DLA-NDOKOTI palace for breaking into my compound, closed at night, with around 9 burglars; So called Technicians of "PSY-laquintinie"; around 23 : 30 at night while I was sleeping IN february 2021 in DOUALA).
 3. Politicians shall be reduced to be people applying criminal and civil laws instead of people trying to make their own ideas come through via ENTERING private life of people like "Shanda TONME jean claude" has done in the past 30 alike years with my personal family and life ('Family NOUNDOU michel', and 'Family JEAN NGONGANG') !
 4. 'SEMIL' and special alike units of Cameroonian army shall be dismantled because of reported proved or not really ATROCITY facts.
 5. 'SEMIL', 'DGRE', 'SED', etc.; all former people wearing weapons shall be displaced into military caserns so to avoid mixing MILITARY alike people with civilians !
 6. IMPUNITY of all people wearing weapon must cease with tribunal applications of criminal laws.
2. *Create an electoral public and common website for all information, and / or official application documents for all elections in Cameroon !!*
3. *Create a website for publication of all laws in Cameroon; including presidential decrees, acts, and / or acts, and so on ...!*
4. *Reforming judicial system with computer software digitization so to PROMOTE equity and justice by laws !*
5. *EACH CITIZEN or person living in Cameroon SHALL officially declare its lifestyle philosophy and / or religion at a 'Chefferie De Block' when moving inside that area of the city !*
 - a. This enables to solve issues based on this declaration in a fairly manner; according to a new reformed judicial criminal law system !
6. *PROHIBIT any type of religious or associations that don't have well openly presented and written codes of laws, Abiding to CAMEROON criminal laws !*

8.8 TRANSPORTATION and CITIES transportation

1. *Reduce airplane travel costs between cities in Cameroon.*
INSTANCES:
 - a. {DLA → YDE} with one way at 12 000 FRANCS.
 - b. {YDE → BAFOUSSAM} with one way at 18 000 FRANCS.
 - c. Etc..

9.9 Technology And Development

1. *Schooling shall be created and managed to be in harmony with Religious, and / or Philosophy lifestyle of parents that intend to have children in a school; BOTH primary and secondary.*
UNIVERSITIES could mix students of all horizons: so the student and leaders of next Coming Cameroon could learn how to live harmoniously.
2. *State schools for civil servants shall be banned in favor of UNIVERSITY education and of an additional training on the job when hired !*
3. *Universities shall be autonomous and not depend anymore of the PRESIDENCY OF THE REPUBLIC*
4. *Create an industry for solar electrical energy with cars and buses as consumers in a lapse of time of 12 years starting 2026.*
5. *Assemble DIGITAL computers in Cameroon in less than 12 years of presidency.*

10.10 MARRIAGE and INTER-PERSONAL sexual corporal Relationship

1. *PROHIBIT sexual actions IN OUTDOOR by laws.*
2. *REMOVE TRADITIONAL SYSTEM of justice because of its unfairness; Based on WOMAN precedence in power:*
 - a. *SINCE Christians don't need to marry to a woman or any gender, as described in 1 CORINTHIANS 7 : 38 – 39 !*
 - b. *SINCE people could stay without marriage, In Christianity, marriage is THE EXCEPTION, But not a sin;*
 - c. *Any person that is not married and that is a born-again Christian cannot be managed by a married person ! THIS is because A MARRIED person couldn't qualify to understand a life at a certain level as He is living constantly with another gender !*
 - d. *People that have marriage in traditional system normally cannot undergo a civil marriage in a christian church (I.E: TRADITIONAL system allows for Impudicity, Which is prohibited in Christianity !).*
 - e. *Born-Again Christians don't marry at all in any type of marriage !*
 - f. *"SHANDA-TONME jean claude's first and last son": Late (justice of attorney) "Me. Shanda Sanou Cabral Patrice" was apparently killed brutally since his body was missing from people assisting SHANDA's family for obituaries.*
 - g. *"HIS (jean-claude shanda-tonme) OBITUARIES in next coming years must not be public since He hasn't been a good citizen for at least hundreds of young cameroonian" that I have hear about for the last 12 years since I started by immigration process back to my homeland country Cameroon of C.P.D.M-R.D.P.C !*
3. *Automatic Splitting OF INHERITANCE after parental death between children:* Because there are a lot of troubles to leave this task to a family with not enough money for paper and bureaucracy work at notary justice palaces !
4. *LEGALIZE homosexual UNION.*
 - a. *People in this union cannot have children adopted from another non-homosexual union at ALL; AND VICE-VERSA for couple married in non-homosexual life style !*

11.11 MUNICIPALITY Reform (AND WASTE and DISPOSAL of garbage)

1. *chefferie de block: This administrative territorial unit is based on traditional tribal lineage ! THIS SHALL BE ENDED AS EACH CITIZEN is subject to the same civil law:*
 1. *currently, a 'chefferie de block' is based on common and traditional law. Since common law has precedence over tribal traditional law, A CITIZEN living must be subject only to COMMON CIVIL LAW where he is living, OR NOT.*
2. *There shall be created AN INDUSTRY for recycling and displacement of waste-garbage USING ecologic burning container:* Each "chefferie de block" shall have its own burning destroying waste-garbage ecologic container.
3. *There shall be at least 1 municipal playing and recreational area of at least 400 m² in each city quarter ("quartier").*
4. *There shall be at least 1 municipal library in each city quarter ("quartier").*

- UNITED STATES OF AMERICA (U.S.A)

- 1.) SIEMENS Healthineers (OCS – Varian), CONCORD, CALIFORNIA, U.S.A (JANUARY 2008)
- 2.) SRI International, MENLO COLLEGE, MENLO PARK, ATHERTON, CALIFORNIA, U.S.A (May 2011)

- CANADA

- 3.) UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, WATERLOO, ON, canada 2009 – 2015
- 4.) MITACS ONTARIO, University of Waterloo, Waterloo, ON, CANADA (October 2012)
- 5.) IBM CASCON 2010 (IBM CENTRE FOR ADVANCED STUDIES CONFERENCE), Hilton Suites Toronto/Markham, Conference Centre, Markham, ON, CANADA (November 2010)
 I attended this conference to present "my doctoral thesis in a simple manner that could be defended in front of several researchers worldwide" (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>); With different backgrounds; As well as practitioners from IBM toronto software laboratory in MARKHAM (<https://www.ibm.com/ca-en>) .
- 6.) PLDI conference (Programming Languages Design And Implementation), Toronto, ON, CANADA (November 2009)
- 7.) Graduate Management Admission Test (GMAT) PREPARATION COURSE, CONCORDIA UNIVERSITY, MONTREAL, QUEBEC, CANADA (June 2007)
- 8.) Graduate English Training Course, UNIVERSITÉ DU QUÉBEC à MONTRAL (UQAM), MONTREAL, QUEBEC, CANADA (AUGUST 2009)

- GERMANY

- 9.) UNIVERSITÄT BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY 2001 – 2007
- 10.) SIEMENS Healthineers (OCS – Varian), ERLANGEN, BAYERN, GERMANY 2007 – 2009
- 11.) SIEMENS Healthineers (OCS – Varian), HEIDELBERG, BADEN-WÜRTTEMBERG, GERMANY 2007 – 2009

This section reports and summarizes our current and actualized knowledge on the subject of software licensing.

20.20 SOFTWARE LICENSes

- o "Summary of MOSTLY used software-licenses":

[Software ~~Hardware~~ Certification authorities; "O.H.A.D.A"; CENELEC; CE; ISO; "A.R.I.N.C"]

Table 1: Software LICENSes summary table.

SOFTWARE license type	Peculiarities	Uses	URL for legal writing specification
1. "CSCS : Close Source Code Software"	Software / Programs AUTHOR exclusive copyright & ownership	YOU use only a binary.	Each retailer provides this on a case by case request.
2.			
3.			
4.			
5.			
6.			

- **CSCS : Close Source Code Software** (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)

- **Open source code software (OSS** (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)) :

- OTHER forms of free software license (FOSS** (<https://www.wikipedia.org>))

- APACHE-BSD license** (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)

- **APACHE**
- **["BSD"]**

- GNU licenses :** (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)

- **GPL**
ANY software that uses this piece of whole source code and / or binaries have to also be licensed GPL.

- **"Lesser GPL - LGPL" ✓**
Program binaries could be used in a commercial project without any request and / or payments to the owner of the source code. Modifications of the source code follows certain rules specified as follows :

- Mention of the authors have to be explicitly written in headers of code sources as directed by rules explicitly sampled at following URL : (<https://>).*
- YOUR own using software source code must also abide to the LGPL GNU software license according to what is written at following URL : (<https://>).*

- BERKELEY-style license** (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)

- **BSD**

- MIT-license; "also called AS-IS-no-warranty-AT-ALL"** (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)

- **MIT ✓**
THIS kind of Open-Source Software (OSS) programs is provided in a state that no reclamation could be done because it could be very tedious to determine liabilities between parties such as a provider, and a customer and / or client.

The so-called MIT License are part of the AS-IS no-warranty code; ALSO all GPL typed licenses in general.

Programs using AS-IS no-Warranty code software licenses generally stipulates either following text, OR similar surrounding text around following :

- o *["The program is provided AS IS with NO WARRANTY OF ANY KIND, INCLUDING THE WARRANTY OF DESIGN, MERCHANTABILITY AND FITNESS FOR A PARTICULAR PURPOSE."]*

This section reports and summarizes all information required at least for certification of our runtime verification monitoring tester tool; BOTH software and/or HARDWARE products.

21.21 Documents for certification for "YERITH R&D" software – hardware PRODUCTS engineered in AFRICA-main—land

Table 2: Design Documents for the CASE (Computer-AIDED SOFTWARE Engineering) tool YERITH_QVGE.

Design Document	VERSION	LOCATION
1. USER requirements elicitation (USER Functional Specification)		
2. Module Description (Module Functional Specification)		
3. Module / Unit Testing		

Table 3: Design Documents for the Runtime Monitoring Verifier Tester [YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF].

Design Document	VERSION	LOCATION
1. USER requirements elicitation (USER Functional Specification)		
2. Module Description (Module Functional Specification)		
3. Module / Unit Testing		

Table 4: Design Documents for the Monitoring Verifier Tester [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET]

Design Document	VERSION	LOCATION
1. USER requirements elicitation (USER Functional Specification)		
2. Module Description (Module Functional Specification)		
3. Module / Unit Testing		

A personal computer tablet for SIMPLIFYING runtime monitoring on-the-fly

Figure 20, Figure 21, and Figure 22 illustrates a sample product usage of the toolkit YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF that permits and allows for its users following actions and tasks to be solved fluently :

1. Send tracing logging for a developer and / or engineer trough 1 of the following communication interfaces :
 - 1.)

- 1.) *Design Documents Unit TESTING, and Static Code Analysis Verification;*
- 2.) *USER requirements elicitation (USER Functional Specification);*
- 3.) *Module Description (Module Functional Specification).*

This section reports and summarizes all information required at least for certification of our runtime verification monitoring tester tool; BOTH software and/or HARDWARE products.

22.22 TOOLS used for Qualification AND / OR Certification of Software-hardware PRODUCTS at "YERITH R&D"

Table 5: Tools used for Qualification and / Or Certification at YERITH R&D.

TOOL	VERSION	Uses	LOCATION
1. "BUGZILLA (https://www.bugzilla.org)"	"N.A"	Bugs and Defects registration & following-up.	
2. "GNU Privacy Guard-GPG (https://www.gnupg.org)"	2.2.27-2	Digital signing check-in source code & documents.	
3. "Git (https://www.git.org)"	1 : 2.30.2-1 + deb11u2	COMMIT, and following-up source code for certification authorities.	

Table 5 illustrates some programming and / or debugging tools I use at YERITH R&D for developing certified products with "ISO - INTERNATIONAL STANDARD ORGANISATION (<https://www.iso.org>)", etc.; Certification organizations :

- o Bugs and Defects Management Software : "BUGZILLA (<https://www.bugzilla.org>)";
 1. "VERSION of current BUGZILLA software installations" : "N.A".
 2. "Location of BUG report-free database website URL" : "www.digital.ocean.com/YERITH_QVGE_HTTPS_url (<https://www.digitalocean.com>)".
 3. "Location of BUGZILLA software installation" : "Intern to YERITH R&D".
- o Software for electronically signing (e.g.: Source code, Design Documents, etc.) : "GNU Privacy Guard-GPG (<https://www.gnupg.org>)";
 1. "VERSION of current GNU Privacy Guard-GPG software installations" : "2.2.27-2".
- o SCM (Source code Management) software : Version Control Management Software : "Git (<https://www.git.org>)";
 1. "VERSION of current Git software installations" : "1 : 2.30.2-1 + deb11u2".

This section reports and summarizes all information required at least for certification of our runtime verification monitoring tester tool; BOTH software and/or HARDWARE products.

23.23 Yerith_QVGE Legal Software and/or Hardware CERTIFICATION Artifacts

- o "Yerith_QVGE Legal Software CERTIFICATION Artifacts":

- YERITH_QVGE DESIGN AND TESTING SYSTEM[13.13] : A product for qualification; CE.

23.23.1 "CERTIFICATION Tools used at YERITH R&D"

[Certification TOOLS.]

23.23.2 "PRODUCTS for Engineering And/ OR Finance Engineered Computing"

- 1.) YERITH_QVGE software design CASE (Computer-AIDED SOFTWARE Engineering) tool; [RELated Design & User Documentation Artifacts.]

[“June 2022” – Currently]

Figure 1: A SCREENSHOT OF YERITH_QVGE FOR GRAPHICAL DESIGN OF STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE (SDMM) SPECIFICATIONS; THAT COULD SPECIFY TRADE OPERATIONS BASED ON TRADE-TIME.

- 2.) YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET ; [RELated Design & User Documentation Artifacts.]

[“Nov. 2024” – Currently]

Figure 2: A screenshot of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF SQL error event log running on YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET.

Figure 3: A sample YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET in action.

THIS hardware computing device, WITH software that uses "INTEL-Pin" (<https://www.intel.com>) could be used for "on-the-fly" runtime verification monitoring & Recovering manifold :

- One connects YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET to either an Ethernet network connection, or serial interface communication port RS-232, and / or Universal Serial BUS-USB interface port ;

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (a screenshot is found in Figure 2) is started on "YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET", and connects to specified processes, on the attached connected other computing device (E.g.: in Fig. 3, a control console for "Siemens-LINAC"); In a configuration panel. THE open source version of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>) is a bit different of the non-free upgraded version installed on "YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET".

This section reports and summarizes all efforts needed as far AS I could learn and experienced as seasoned software developer at "IBM-toronto-software-laboratory"; And at "Siemens-medical-solutions".

24.24 Years of experience as Software Developer for Legally APPROVED products

o "Legal Requirements for a correct con-formant Software Artifact":

- **YERITH_QVGE LEGAL documents for Qualified Products from AFRICA—main—land.**
- **[SOFTWARE licensing.]**
- **"Communauté Économique et MONÉTAIRE de l'Afrique Centrale – (C.E.M.A.C)" (<https://www.cemac.int>) :** THIS central Africa certification applies for Accounting and Finance.
 - I.) **"O.H.A.D.A (<https://www.cemac.int>)" ; for "FINANCIAL ACCOUNTING SOFTWARE"**
- **TüV-Nord (<https://www.tuv-nord.com>) in North-West GERMANY :** This german authority in Science and Engineering reflects better our initial commitment as a **"DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)"[?]**, even before a **[MASTER-OF-SCIENCE]** degree was created at the **UNIVERSITY-racist of Bremen (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>)**.
 - A.) **"CE - EUROPEAN COMMUNITY (https://www.single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/single-market/ce-marking_en)" ; "ISO - INTERNATIONAL STANDARD ORGANISATION (<https://www.iso.org>)" ; "FDA - FEDERAL DRUG ADMINISTRATION (U.S.A) (<https://www.fda.gov>)" for "MEDICAL SOFTWARE"**
 1. **Bugs and Defects** are to be managed by a software such as **"IBM-CharmNT (<https://www.ibm.com/us>)"** ;
 2. **Design Documents** are to be updated annually at maximum time based on regulatory deadlines of **AUTHORITIES That Delivers Certificates "; I think at least ONCE-ANNUALLY";**
 3. **Design Documents** are electronically signed by an author and reviewers;
 4. **Design Documents** are saved in an ERP software such as **"SAP-EDM (<https://www.sap.de>)"**, etc.;
 5. **Design Documents** have a table to indicate changes within the document for each modification of it;
 6. **Design Documents** USER requirements elicitation (USER Functional Specification);
 7. **Design Documents** Module Description (Module Functional Specification) with Diagrams; E.g.: **"Finite State Machine Diagrams"**, etc.;
 8. **Design Documents** Unit TESTING, and Static Code Analysis Verification; Runtime Memory Error Detection TOOLS.
 9. **Source code** is to be stored in a control version management system such as **"Rational-ClearCase"**, etc.;
 10. **Source code** changes are to be reviewed and electronically signed using a key-card like the ones used by **["SIEMENS-healthineers-OCS"]**;
 - B.) **CENELEC (<https://www.iso.org/fr/standard/68383.html>) for "RAILWAY"**

A sample railway software related product regulation is : **"CENELEC EN50128" (<https://www.iso.org/fr/standard/68383.html>)**.
 - C.) **A.R.I.N.C (<https://www.aviation-ia.sae-itc.com>) for "AVIONICS SOFTWARE"**

Sample A.R.I.N.C specifications : **"RTCA D0178-B"**; **"RTCA D0178-C"**.

 - **Static Code Analysis Verification conforming to "MISRA-C" (<https://www.misra.org>) ;**

["MISRA-C"]

This section reports and summarizes all efforts I have made throughout my Time at The University Of Waterloo as a 'Ph.D. candidate'. THIS page links and connects 5 years of academic and professional research I HAVE been spending at the white-asian-white racist extremist university of waterloo in ontario, CANADA.

25.25 Years of PRE-Doctoral & years of Doctoral Research at University-racist OF waterloo, ONTARIO, CANADA

ML; C++; Java; OSI; Eclipse; Intel-Pin; Open-MP Haskell, GWT, Python, IBM, Quercus, Bash-scripting	<i>Program Analysis (Static, Dynamic).</i> a-la-KILDALL-Gary;LFDS-Reps; datalog; Soot; LLVM	Courses taught: 1. Software Testing, Quality Assurance & Maintenance 2. Programming for Performance 3. Tools & Methods for Software Engineering 4. Foundations of Software Engineering 5. C++ Programming Laboratory 6. Compilers 7. Computer Networks
<i>(ADVANCED) Compiler Technology</i> Yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang; Alias Analysis, Comp. Opt.	<i>Program Verification (Isa.-HOL, etc.); Model Checking</i> SDMM; CAV - Computer-Aided Verification; NuSMV; Alloy	
Programing Languages OOP; Functional	Software; Programming; Testing Alg.; Rel. Eng.; Security; Par.-Comp.	} Foundations of My Doctoral Ph.D. / Post-Doctoral Works in Computer Science (Software Engineering)
	Formal Methods; Kripke Structures Automata theory (NFA, DFA, etc.)	

- o [PublicaTIONS.]
- o "Software LICENSING".
- o "Legal Requirements for a correct con-formant Software Artifact".
- o Contacts with NORTH-AMERICAN scientists
- o Contacts with other Scientists
- o Issues & MISUNDERSTANDINGS at the University of Waterloo, Ontario, Canada
- o TIME at the University-racist-of-BREMEN, BREMEN, BREMEN, Germany:
 1. "2 years" STudent Software Developer PART-TIME job – Bergmann Automaten GmbH (now Gewete GmbH), Germany.
 2. "2 years" WERKSTUDENT at ZMML-university-sexist-racist of bremen, BREMEN, GERMANY.: February 2003 – February 2005.
 3. "4.5 years PRE-time" in GERMAN-racist program : "'DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)"[?]"
- o Doctoral years of research at the university-racist of waterloo, ontario, CANADA-idiot:
 1. "2 years PRE-time" at SIEMENS-idiot medical solutions.: November 2007 – JULY 2009.
 2. "Summary of teaching training certificates
 3. PAPER conference peer reviewed : OOPSLA 2010.
 4. GIVEN PREsentation : IBM CDp Cascon 2010.
 5. Visited courses.
 6. Independent assisted research summary as a "Master of Science (M.Sc.)"
 7. VISITed SUMMER-school /workshops / conferences summary
["1st SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques"-2011] | [PLDI 2009] | [IBM CDp Cascon 2010]
 8. PSYCHOLOGICAL-Care with PRACTICE of SWIMMING at THE university-racist of waterloo every other day during almost 4 years – "Degree-Swimmer-5 / degree-MASTER-Swimmer-6" successfully attended.
 9. "Year 1" : 09/2009 – 08/2010;
 10. "Year 2" : 09/2010 – 12/2011 – [with PhD Comprehensive Examination.];
 11. Doctoral THESIS Presentation / PhD Comprehensive Examination on "December 20, 2011"

- o QUALification as a "Professional Engineer in Ontario, CANADA":

THE requirements to qualify myself as Professional Engineer in ONTARIO are all met after 1 year supervision under PATRICK LAM "(2011)"; because I have already 48 months of professional engineering work experience before entering the professional academic doctor of engineering program in ELECTRICAL & COMPUTER Engineering at university-racist-white of waterloo.

"AS a "doctor PhD in electrical & computer engineering" graduate [abbreviated "Dr./PhD" in French; In french, "Dr./PhD" only nowadays means doctor in engineering; and no fellowship at all; I AM A FRANCOPHONE.]; THERE shouldn't be any need to again acquired a professional designation "Professional Engineer", since "doctor PhD in electrical & computer engineering" is already an Engineering titled degree. So as a francophone from dark-afrika-heimat, I am not interested anymore in any Engineering, or whatsoever designated vocational position in whiteist-world !"

"ALSO as a born-again christian, I CANNOT BE member-ed in any fellowship of iron-rings, female-peggist; etc. ."

"JON eyolfson for instance has a "Bachelor-of-Engineering"; so he doesn't need to apply for a "Professional Engineer"; BUT [Wenzhu-man has a "Master of Applied Science (MAsc)"]; AND no "Engineering titled degree from CANADA and /or USA"; SO for her needs she must apply for P.Eng.; so to get government oriented positions !"

This section reports and summarizes all efforts I have made throughout my Time at The University Of Waterloo as a 'Ph.D. candidate'. THIS page links and connects 5 years of academic and professional research I HAVE been spending at the white-asian-white racist extremist university of waterloo in ontario, CANADA.

26.26 Years of POST-doctoral Research; a Summary Report – 2nd page

- o *POst-Doctoral (Ph.D.; Prof.) years of research at the university–racist of waterloo, ontario, CANADA–idiot:*
 1. "Year 1": 01/2012 – 08/2012 – [*PROfessional Internship at IBM Toronto–idiot Software Lab..*]
 2. "Year 2": 09/2012 – 08/2013
 3. "Year 3": 09/2013 – 08/2014
 4. "Year 4": 09/2014 – 04/2015
 5. STUDENT advising summary
 6. TEACHing assistantship summary
 7. "Summary of teaching training certificates"
 8. *Independent & Collegiate Research Summary as "D.ENG. [DR.–ING. in 'French language'] (PH.D.)"*
 9. Visited courses as post–doctoral (POST-DOCTORAL STUDIES) fellow.
 10. VISited ONLINE courses /workshops / conferences summary
[Software-Security–online–"stanford.edu" 2013] | [MITACS ONTARIO 2012] | [ICse 2012]
 11. RESEARCH outcome hindrance
 12. RESEARCH outcome plagiarism
 13. RESEARCH outcome plagiarism-continUED
 14. GIVEN–co–taught courses at the University–racist of Waterloo in ONTARIO, Canada
 15. ACADEMIC HELP from other people aside from DEAR-idiot PATRICK-lam
 16. *!!! PhD Research Seminar TALK. as an ECE graduate talk. !!!*
 17. *!!! PhD Dissertation Defense at DAVID R. Cheriton School OF Computer Science in "January 2015" !!!*
 18. *IAI–cameroon–bande–d'idiots au service d'1 B.E.P.C–chantoux*
- o [*TRAINING on the job of young engineers*]:
 - Runtime monitoring for Web Apps
 - API usage rule checking for 'C' programs (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>)
- o *STARTUP entrepreneurship research & development project YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM:*

After I left the university–racist–of–waterloo in ontario, IN MARCH 2015; I went to live in Cameroon–yaounde for almost 2 years, working on a free and open source software for Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP).

POST-Doctoral Research at YERITH R&D since MARCH 2015:

 - I) *Engineering Methodologies & Tools Expertise;*
 - II) *YERITH_QVGE legal artifacts for QUALIFICATION certified products Engineered in AFRICA;*
 - III) *A web-site Domain-Specific Language (DSL) Processor for generation of HTML5, PHP, CSS, etc. combined web–applications named YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 (Accompanied with a WYSIWYG-Tool : YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL !)*
 <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9>
 - IV) *A realtime component (for operating system DEBIAN LINUX) is in preparation for trading stock exchange erp system "YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME": YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RT-SYSTEM;*
 - V) *A RUNTIME monitoring verification "state diagram mealy machines (SDMM)" C++ Library :*
 https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf [*I*]
 https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif
 - VI) *A State Diagram Mealy Machine (SDMM) translator–compiler :*
[YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP \(https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567\)](https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567) [*1*]
 https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang
 - VII) *A RUNTIME monitoring verification runtime container for "SDMM" :*
 [YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF \(https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481\)](https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481) [*1*]
 <https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>
 - VIII) *Simple to use and pragmatic Enterprise–Resource–Planing (ERP) software :*
 [YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum \(https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/\)](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/) [*?*]
 <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0>

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES 6 (Cyber-Security & Web Deployment Development)

27.27 WEB PAGES HTML and others Generation with YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0

27.27.1 Motivation

Table 6: A SOFTWARE architecture overview of YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 (["An SDMM usage scenario by IBM-websphere"].)

Figure 4: YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 generates legacy web files from Qt 5 interface files (".ui" files).

Figure 5: A Stack Stapled Architecture Overview of YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0.

YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 is a novel project that constitutes the base for YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM ([git https://github.com/yerithrd/yeritherppgiwebsystem](https://github.com/yerithrd/yeritherppgiwebsystem)) that endeavors to create web sites solutions for entrepreneurial organizations that use YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM without much additional programming of web interfaces and / or interactions; AT such, web sites solutions for entrepreneurial organizations will emerge as easy as pressing a button.

YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 is a Domain Specific Language to [describe WEB SITES programmatically]; SUCH as a C++ program imperatively, AND well structured; So to automatically generate STATIC DYNAMIC WEB SITES BASED ON HTML (HYPERTEXT MARKUP LANGUAGE) AND CSS (Cascading Style Sheets) language constructs : [WWW - World Wide Web \(WWW\) Design & Programming using YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0](https://www.zenodo.org/records/17466696) (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17466696>)".

Numerous companies in Cameroon might evaluate this new research software system product to simplify and speed up their software development process :

1. "Dr.-Ing. PAUL dayang (2013, University of Bremen)"; currently employed at the University of Ngaoundere in Far North of Cameroon.
 - This researcher and lecturer, employed by the University of Ngaoundere, has never replied to my long time email as an alumni of the prestigious University of Bremen in Germany where I graduated with a "Diplom-Informatiker degree 2 years before him !"
 - I could see he started a web graphical system (also with "ANDROID-google platform" (https://)) html-based to promote online afore-provisional shopping of food provisions in Africa for his dissertation as a "Doctor of Engineering". I was sad not to see this project emerge as a commercial start-up here in Cameroon where there is only "www.cm.coinafrique.com" (<https://www.cm.coinafrique.com>) that I deem as a serious competitor in this era of work.
 - I believe the programming abstraction I will provide for "DAYANG and RÖDIGER (<https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/~roediger>) work" would help them both in "Ngaoundere" and in "Bremen" to promote Free and Open Source web shopping for Africa where even a clean market is not existing in Main city Yaounde !
 - AT the university of bremen-white-racist, I Visited a course titled "E-business technologies 2"; I don't remember the name of the professor but I DID SO while I WAS in my 3rd year as part of so called "ANGEWANDTE INFORMATIK" ("Applied Computer Science"). IN graduate level course "E-business technologies 2", I learned about n-tiers web architectures, SOAP-Service Oriented Architecture Protocol, etc.

ALSO, in my 2nd year, there was a small "practicum" where I learned on PHP, and MariaDB; "ERIC-cuon-pd STREIBL" was the organizer.

2. "DUT-Diplôme Universitaire de Technologie" CHRISTIAN ngueyong rikong" (Start-Up)

CHRISTIAN ngueyong rikong is a seasoned software developer that creates large to medium-sized websites; AND Google-android mobile applications for his clients around world.

"CHRISTIAN rikong ngueyong, that I schooled with in Douala secondary school — "ALFRED SAKER HIGH SCHOOL" — would also not be against such a tool-framework that could reduce his development time and effort, since BLACK-USA entrepreneurs cannot afford tremendous amount of money for tools sold by MICROSOFT CORP., FACEBOOK INC., etc. ! " (<https://www.christianrikong.com>)

3. "Dr. (B.Sc.) Claudel Noumbissi" (Start-Up)
4. "Ing. (B.Sc.) Arthur Zang" (Start-Up)
5. "Dr.-Ing. (Ph.D.) Ibrahim Nguena Moukouop" (Start-Up)
6. "Dr.-Ing. (Ph.D.) Thomas Djotio Ndié" (Start-Up)
7. "Institut Universitaire de la Cote", Douala (Start-Up)
8. "Santa Lucia – AHALA", Yaounde (Currently using Odoo ERP web & thick-client) !
9. "DR. (M.Sc.) Fabrice Wilfried Siemeni" (Start-Up)

Fabrice WILFRIED siemeni could generate sample website pages with no programming knowledge at all.

10. etc.

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES 6 – CONTINUED –

Table 7: YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0-DSL keywords and meaning (An excerpt).

YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 keyword	(level) Nested in keyword	Programming related meaning
1. yerith_web_pages_generator_MAIN		Contains web site all pages description
2. web_html_page_menu_bar_headers	(1) yerith_web_pages_generator_MAIN	Contains web site each page menubar pages names
3. web_html_page	(1) yerith_web_pages_generator_MAIN	A HTML page description
4. yri_html_page_title	(3) web_html_page	A HTML page title
5. yri_html_page_input_header_menu_bar	(3) web_html_page	Inputs a menubar onto this HTML page
6. yri_html_page_text_SECTION	(3) web_html_page	Describes a text section on a HTML page
7. VARIABLE_YRI_PARAGRAPH	(6) yri_html_page_text_SECTION	Defines text paragraph within a HTML page
8. text_yri_font_size	(1) yerith_web_pages_generator_MAIN	Defines a font size
9. text_yri_width_box	(1) yerith_web_pages_generator_MAIN	Defines a width for a text paragraph

Figure 6: Webbrowser-based software architecture : at least 4 layers logical software architecture (Image modified from online pdf paper "FlashCache: A NAND Flash Memory File Cache for Low Power Web Servers" [<https://doi.org/10.1145/1176760.1176774>] by Trevor et al.). YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF runtime monitors communication layers.

27.27.2 RELATED WORK at YERITH R&D; Software System Architecture of ERP Systems

- "Our paper not for publication in a conference paper, [SOFTWARE SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OF YERITH-ERP-3.0\[?\]](https://www.archive.org/download/yerith-erp-3-0-software-system-architecture_20221230/YERITH-ERP-3-0-SOFTWARE-SYSTEM-ARCHITECTURE.pdf) : (https://www.archive.org/download/yerith-erp-3-0-software-system-architecture_20221230/YERITH-ERP-3-0-SOFTWARE-SYSTEM-ARCHITECTURE.pdf); reveals common web system architecture patterns and structure, INCLUDING ([CYBER-SECURITY\[34\]](#)) software system security vulnerability analysis; As observed these last 10 years at least from "November 23, 2025".
- ["WE have visited, in year 2013, an online software security vulnerability detection and protection course with the STANFORD-university-racist while attending our degree [DOCTORAL PH.D.-program at the University of Waterloo;] THIS required acquired knowledge helps us creating safe and secure software systems by Construction."]
- "WE previously, in our "3rd semester", at the University-racist of Bremen, Bremen, GERmany-idiot; Have visited a course for undergraduates named "Information Security 1" given by "TZI.DE (Technology Center for Computer Science) (<https://www.tzi.de/en>)" founding member "Prof. Dr-Ing. Carsten-cuon-obèse Bormann-nazi" (<https://user.informatik.uni-bremen.de/cabo>)."
- ★ ★ "I could also achieved a running taint analysis ([git https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis](https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis)) for the Quercus PHP JAVA web application server during my post-doctoral studies & work at the university-racist of waterloo in ontarian Canada-idiot. IT was a graduate course taught by "Frank-idiot-nazi TIP-gay-cuon"."] ★ ★

27.27.3 WHAT YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 Would Service & Provide

- "Qt 5 software development platform" enables auto-deployment for Android-google platform." (<https://>)
 YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yeritherppgiwebsystem>) will reuse this functionality to generate legacy web source code files (HTML5, PHP, CSS, Javascript (GWT (Google Web Toolkit))); VIA a translation program-technology from "Qt 5-ui (user-interface)" files onto YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 input file coin as DSL-specific YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 files ("spec_html"); Figure 4.;
- We at YERITH R&D could then use any "Qt 5-Designer tool as a WYSIWYG Tool for generating Web-HTML-PHP pages : YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL" !
- "We plan at mid-term to be able to generate "Software architecture proof testing-programs", both for GUI-interfaces (thick-client), and Web-interfaces (thin-client); automatically just by specifying certain behavioral interactions using state diagram mealy machines ([SDMM\[1d\]](#)).";
- "The so-called "Software architecture proof testing-programs" will have certain warranties about [cyber-security], about [cyber-safety], [runtime-memory usage] and [user-defined usage rules]."

27.27.4 Implementation Technologies

I use "flex and bison compiler / translator generation technology" for creating YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0-DSL. I plan to automatically generate code for enabling runtime monitoring of the generated web sites. A first version of this FOSS (Free And Open Source Software) is available at URL: [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9) .

27.27.5 YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0-DSL Keyword Table

Table 7 depicts and explains commands and directives for creating web-based HTML pages sites.

We plan also the generation of web sites based on an "n-tiers architecture pattern", illustrated for instance in Figure 6; that demonstrated solid resistance in practice for more than 10 years now as demonstrated by applications server existence and usage such as :

1. Apache tomcat application server
2. Glassfish application server: mainly used in combination with JAVA OSI component-based software development architecture.
3. Quercus PHP server interpreter application server
4. IBM websphere

All this work has to solve the issue of generating certain portion of web sites for customers and users of ["YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM"\[?\]](#) Enterprise Resource Planing software in a time period in-between of 3 years from this year 2024 !

"ALL THIS UNDER THE PROTECTION OF OUR LORD AND SAVIOR JEOVAH-NISSI IN HEAVEN."

28.28 Securing Websites

Figure 7: A Sample Taint-analysis State Diagram MEALY-georges machine file.

```

1. yri_sd_mealy_automaton_spec YERITH_QVGE_sample_TaintAnalysis
2. {
3.   START_STATE(T0):NOT_IN_BEFORE(in,yri_tainted_analysis.sanitizers_methods)
4.   ->[not_in_sql_event_log('SELECT.i0#sanitize',STATE(T0))]/'INSERT.i0#in'->
5.     FINAL_STATE(TF):IN_POST(i0,yri_tainted_analysis.tainted_values).
6. }

```

Figure 8: A Sample Taint-analysis State Diagram MEALY-georges machine.

$\underline{Q_0} := \text{NOT_IN_BEFORE}(op, yri_tainted_analysis.sanitizers) ; \quad \overline{Q_F} := \text{IN_POST}(i0, yri_tainted_analysis.tainted).$

28.28.1 Motivation

Numerous security vulnerabilities towards and against web applications exist :

- **“SQL injection“** : “A user tries to make a software execute a SQL query on a software-connected database by passing for instance; **THROUGH user credential input SQL-code to destroy part or all your database.**

user-name: 'Insert into users ('user_name', 'user_password') values ('drop table users', 'drop database');

- **“Format Strings“** : A software has part of it receiving directly input from an outside-world interface and using it without checking it is proper formed. Any malformed input can cause a mal-interpretation of data & could then caused for instance; **A CRASH of the software under analysis !**

int variable_x = 0; scanf(%, variable_x); // Wrong format is expected by scanf !.

// scanf currently expects a string instead of an integer.

- **“Cross-site scripting attacks“**; **“Buffer-overflow“**; **“Man-in-the-Middle“**; etc.
- **ALL cyber-security types** We previously wrote about in this listing items could be detected by removing all tainted values of an application; I.E.; provide a validation function and / or method, for each tainted value.

THIS is best done during testing of the software product before delivery of an end-product to clients and / or customers.

A recovery from a fail state accepting error program location can be done by adding a generic recovery validating function and / or method that Could identify; and provide; best sanitizing / validating method for each tainted input.

SINCE YERITH_QVGE provide only forbidden trace specification, a recovery and detection is generally only possible after at least 1 violation of the SDMM specification property automaton has been achieved !

*A usage scenario with in future coming dedicated PC-Tablet computer **YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET** of **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**; could be found in Figure 1.*

Our approach to add more security & safety to open-source webshops generated by our technology **YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL** is manifold :

- 1.) **USE of runtime verification & monitoring platform **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**** (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>) :
 - **USE of standard security vulnerability breaches detection mechanisms as for Instance illustrated for Taint Analysis in this Subsection 28.28.3 !**
 - **USE of developer-otherly specified security vulnerabilities patterns expressed as SDMM, & similarly described as for instance in Figure 8 !**

28.28.2 Event Race Parallel-Concurrent Processes

- 1.)

28.28.3 Dynamic Taint Analysis for Web Security

- 1.) *IN a previous work at the university–racist of waterloo, in Canadian–whitte ontario [3], we've implemented in web–server Quercus; A dynamic taint analysis using JAVA as programming language.*

We plan to re–use Quercus as web–application server for generated webshops from YERITH–WEB–DESIGN–TOOL.

- 2.) *Currently, we have created YRI–DB–RUNTIME–VERIF, 1 runtime monitoring container generator that enables creation of taint analysis engine with no coding for a developer; IT only requires to deliver a state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) specification expressed using a textual description DSL–language called YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG [1c] : Figure 7;*

This textual description (Domain-Specific Language) offers also, when a state diagram mealy machine has more than 2 states, a reference communicating processes parallel specification for the problem under analysis since processes are synchronized on each event after a 1st event because each state of the state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) represents a potential other parallel running process state; Illustration follows for instance in Figure 8.

28.28.4 Warranties on Web Pages–Security

- 1.) *[Warranties on Cyber–Safety].*

29.29 WEB-QT Assembly : A comparison with [YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL](#)

- *WebAssembly-technology of QT-trolltech uses a platform independent binary format (called emscripten) to deliver website functionality for QT-application out-of-the-box;*

Technology emscripten is not open-sourced and it is not as simple as "use of [YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL](#)".

30.30 WYSIWYG-Tool for generating websites

Figure 9: YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL : A SCREENSHOT of YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 generator within YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum.

Figure 9 illustrates a design engineering modeling window frame originating from ERP-software YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum for automatically generating webshop for its users.

30.30.1 Motivation

Numerous users of ERP-YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum would be also interested in having a WWW-online presentation for interacting with their clients and / or customers.

In our white-black paper [SOFTWARE SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OF YERITH-ERP-3.0\[?\]](https://www.archive.org/download/yerith-erp-3-0-software-system-architecture_20221230/YERITH-ERP-3-0-SOFTWARE-SYSTEM-ARCHITECTURE.pdf) : (https://www.archive.org/download/yerith-erp-3-0-software-system-architecture_20221230/YERITH-ERP-3-0-SOFTWARE-SYSTEM-ARCHITECTURE.pdf); we motivate why we prefer fat-client software-system architecture over thin-client (also called website-architecture).

However we also want to enable our users to be online on the web easily by just pressing a button since costs to develop another system might be very impressing. THAT is why YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum offers now for its users and / or developers an interface for automatically generating and deploying website-webshops solutions that reuse any information already present in the database created & running as a fat-thick-client (QT) architecture.

30.30.2 Steps & Technology

- Selecting QT-trolltech ui files to transform into web-HTML5 and / or PHP files;
- Pressing a button that generates PHP-HTML5 files via a step-by generation of YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 files.

Our use of YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 has advantages of preventing us of drastic changes in either HTML5 standards or platforms since YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 represents a website architecture as a high-level programming language (e.g.: C++, JAVA, etc.).

Listing 1: A sample very limited for explanation & illustration purpose YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 Source code !

```

1  yerith-web-pages-generator-MAIN YECEFOIQ-WEB-PAGES
2  {
3
4  web-html-page index
5  {
6  yri_html_page_title: 'Bienvenue au centre de formation qualifiante Yecefoiq !';
7  yri_html_page_input_header_menu_bar[web-html-page-menu-bar-headers];
8  yri_html_page_MENU_BAR_link_string: 'yri_index !';
9
10 yri_html_page_text_SECTION (HTML_HEADER_H/3; 'Description du Centre de Formation')
11 {
12 VARIABLE_YRI_PARAGRAPH variable_paragraph_1
13 {text-yri-font-size = 5} :
14 {text-yri-width-box = 5cm} ==
15 "PLEASE read following list items ordered !:"
16
17 li_begin: '1st list item'
18 li: '2nd list item.'
19 li_end: 'Last list item.'
20 };
21 };
22
23 web-html-page-menu-bar-headers {
24 web-html-page-menu-bar-headers_Position = 'vertical-left';
25
26 yri_html_page_section[index,
27 programme_des_cours,
28 contenu_des_cours,
29 impressum];
30 };
31 }

```


31.31 Software Validation with YERITH_QVGE (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF)

Figure 10: A parallel system example ping-pong with David-harel statechart; Example created and / or inspired from QT-trolltech sample; in Documentation present; Statechart found in some place I don't remember yet..

Figure 11: A sample ping-pong parallel process depicted in Figure 10.

```

1. yri_sd_mealy_automaton_spec YERITH_QVGE_sample_PingPong
2. {
3.   START_STATE(pinger)
4.   ->[in_sql_event_log('ping', STATE(pinger))]/'pong' ->
5.     STATE(ponger): IN_POST_NOP
6.     ->[in_sql_event_log('pong', STATE(ponger))]/'ping' ->
7.       FINAL_STATE(pinger_two): IN_POST_NOP.
8. }

```

Software System Validation checks whether certain software system properties are **IMPLEMENTED CORRECTLY** according to its specifications.

1. Software **VALIDATION** as an automatic test case generation runtime monitoring instance from **YERITH_QVGE** !

- a.) A test case is generated without checking for test data using a constraint solver engine because it can be acquired only by manual interaction with the software under analysis.

31.31.1 Cyber-Safety Warranties & Others

1.) **Warranties on Cyber-Security**.

12.12 Software Verification Engineering Modeling with SDMM

Figure 12: A SAMPLE state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) file.

```

1. yr_sd_mealy_automaton_spec yr_missing_department_NO_DELETE
2. {
3.   START_STATE(dept_exists):NOT_IN_BEFORE(YRI_ASSET, dept.dept_name)
4.   ->[in_sql_event_log('DELETE.dept.YRI_ASSET', STATE(dept_exists))]/'SELECT.dept'->
5.     ERROR_STATE(dept_exists):IN_AFTER(YRI_ASSET,stocks.dept_name).
6. }

```

Figure 13: A motivating example, as previous bug found in YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum; A SQL-database based only in a disk-file with not much roundabout code could also be used instead of a full-featured database management system such as MariaDB (<https://www.mariadb.com>).

$Q_0 := NOT_IN_BEFORE(YRI_ASSET, dept.dept_name)$; $Q_1 := IN_AFTER(YRI_ASSET, stocks.dept_name)$.

"SDMM state diagram formalism is more powerful and expressive than David-harel statechart formalism. I.E. As depicted in fig. 15, a drawing-design is not well capable of scaling for a software-system with for instance 9 sub-systems events and / or states."

Figure 14: A David-harel statechart modeling of a temporal property expressed as a finite state diagram machine of mealy-GEORGES in fig. 13.

Figure 15: A parallel system example ping-pong with David-harel statechart.

1. Software Engineering Design & Verification using state diagram mealy machine (SDMM), runtime monitoring & static code analysis :

- WE are working & researching on translating automatically viable statechart specification onto state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) runtime monitoring verification specifications;
- USER requirement elicitation & specification is easily transcribed into a formal SDMM automaton-formula; Even by a mathematician with not much knowledge in Computer Technical Programming; As THIS is required when developers use David-Harel Statechart visual formalism as you can observe in Figure 14 !

A temporal property specification using state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) only requires use of the following mathematic elements :

- Logic formulas to describe propositional formulas as conditions to trigger software system state-transitions; AND also to describe "GUARD-condition" to be checked 'VALID' before a software-system state-transition is triggered & executed by YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF, a runtime monitoring verification container.
- Variables : to describe states & state-conditions (pre- & post-conditions).
- Formulas mustn't be drawn because there exists also a textual description language coined as a Domain-Specific Language called YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG [1c] : Figure 12 illustrates for instance a textual description for the mealy machine state diagram drawn in Figure 13 !
- "Statecharts by David-Harel, BECAUSE it is a visual formalism; Requires knowledge of code of drawing squares & other signs and keywords." !

- Modeling a temporal property specification added with state-transitions pre- & post-conditions is very tedious and complicated to realize using David-harel Statechart.

THIS kind of modeling is impressively more easy to realize using finite automata formalisms such as depicted in Figure 13; This figure depicts a temporal software system safety property designed with Mealy-machine, "And formalized as a state diagram mealy machine (SDMM (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567>) [1d]) by myself" !

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF is extremely efficient in usage and / or specification because state-conditions ("pre-condition underlined" & "post-conditions over-lined" are executed by a runtime execution "expansion algorithm" called "Method YRI_trigger_an_edge_event" that checks at no costs for users.)

- With statecharts, specification of software system with parallel subsystem doesn't scale well starting for instance with 8 subsystems, because all 8 subsystems must be drawn 1 inside others !

ON the contrary side, state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) only requires specifying an finite state automaton with more than 2 states, and linear in space & traversal algorithm complexity; Which is done automatically for a developer by the runtime monitoring verification generator-container YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF !.

- "OPEN-source version of the software system programming library QT-trolltech offers since version (at minimum number) 5.15 (around year 2020) a package called SCXML that implements David-harel statechart programming capabilities" !

13.13 Software Verification with YERITH_QVGE

A library or plugin at any layer (OR a combination mixture of layers) of a software system architecture could be verified and validated using YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF by applying a receipt: IT would be sufficient to map each system call wanted for call sequence verification and / or validation to a MySQL query: So one doesn't need to re-create new QT-DBus interfaces for YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: E.g.: "SYSTEM V libc". [A sample use case for IBM-Websphere server web !]

Figure 16: Software system architecture of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: it is also a runtime monitor container for software verification.

Figure 17: YRI_QVGE software stack dependencies.

1. Create A FRAMEWORK FOR DYNAMIC runtime analysis and monitoring of Temporal Safety Property in Plugin-based software (Figure 17 illustrates graphically interdependency between these under described sub-projects.).

- a. **YRI_QVGE** (an extension of Qt-QVGE): A "CASE (computer-aided software engineering)", CLOSED SOURCE CODE SOFTWARE (CSCS), for creating and generating MEALY MACHINE STATE DIAGRAMS as GUI (GRAPHICAL USER INTERFACE) TOOL. [model-based testing, DSL – domain-specific languages] [06/2022 – CURRENT]

"[THE GUI TOOL YERITH_QVGE] (See Figure 23) GENERATES A FILE CONTAINING A MEALY MACHINE STATE DIAGRAM SPECIFICATION using YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG; this file could be used as input for the compiler YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP, so to gather a C++ package to run as runtime monitor within YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF. THIS TOOL COSTS 2,500 EUROS."

- b. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**: A Dynamic Program Monitoring Recovering Analyzer Generator for any software emitting QtDBus messages per sockets (See subsection 13.13.3 (Runtime Verification), and / or Figure 21; and / or Figure 24).

"THIS IS at time (November 23, 2025); State-of-art technology; comparable technology are for instance RT-Tester with TDIOHS (Timed Discrete Input / Output Hybrid System); State Diagram formalism From "VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GMBH, SPIN-OFF THE UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN" (RT-Tester; MBT[?]). TDIOHS complies fully with all semantic elements of HAREL-statecharts !

"AND technologies "IBM Purify Plus"; "LOGSCOPE" ("Specification-Based Monitoring in C++") and "DejaVu" ("DejaVu: A Monitoring Tool for First-Order Temporal Logic") by [Dr. Klaus Havelund] at N.A.S.A (<https://www.nasa.gov>)".

- YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: <https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>

- c. **YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP**: a compiler using flex and bison, for YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF specification language (YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG), so to automatically generate C++ code for runtime monitors implemented in YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF. [compilers, model-based testing, reactive system analysis, domain-specific languages] [04/2023 – CURRENT]

"COMPETITORS from LOGSCOPE and DejaVu; AND RT-Tester; MBT[?]; have similar description state diagram language; but work all of them as SPECIFICATION OF WISHED PROGRAM BEHAVIOR; whereas SDMM[1d] works at SPECIFICATION OF FORBIDDEN (fail) PROGRAM BEHAVIOR."

- YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP: https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang

- d. **YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG**: A SPECIFICATION LANGUAGE FOR STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE (SDMM) extended with pre-/post-conditions on STATE DIAGRAM TRANSITIONS and with a final state. (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567>) [statecharts, model-based testing, reactive system analysis, domain-specific languages] [04/2023 – CURRENT]

"YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG complies fully to David-harel statecharts ["Statecharts: a visual formalism for complex systems" (<https://www.wisdom.weizmann.ac.il/~dharel/SCANNED.PAPERS/Statecharts.pdf>)] which is a visual formalism for states diagrams."

- YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP: https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang

- e. **YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_UNIT_TESTS**: UNIT TESTING PROJECT for YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF. [06/2022 – CURRENT]
"THIS test unit suite is there to check peculiarities of project YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF; As a Free And OPEN SOURCE CODE SOFTWARE (foss), I strongly recommend using it before committing changes to the main git-branch project."

- YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_UNIT_TESTS: https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_UNIT_TESTS

- f. **YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF / YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF**: a framework for verifying SQL software correctness properties of gui software at runtime [06/2022 – CURRENT]

[model-based testing, reactive system analysis, computer software program analysis, computer software dynamic program analysis, software integration testing with SQL and GUI, runtime monitoring]

"YOU SPECIFY USING A STATE DIAGRAM AN ERRONEOUS SUT (System Under Test) TYPE STATE STYLE BEHAVIOR with YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF. USING YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF, YOU CHECK AT RUNTIME WHETHER SUCH AN ERRONEOUS SUT SEQUENCE BEHAVIOR OCCURS."

- YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF: https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif

13.13.1 TAXONOMY : Software Verification vs. Program Code Verification

Figure 18: "Program verification (including model checking)" is a subset (C) of "SOFTWARE VERIFICATION". (See also research goal 13.)

Figure 19: Embedded program verifier notifier within YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum; YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF runs as a background process service.

Software System verification is a discipline to verify whether a software, meaning a product use at customer level and full-featured, conforms to certain software system user related usage properties.

In contrast, program code verification checks only program at the level of their source code or binary code product against code programming related properties, And not necessarily at level of a full featured user level product. Thus all code programming related properties could be cast down to certain software system related properties. It follows PROGRAM VERIFICATION is a Subset Of Software (System) Verification: illustrated in Figure 18 !

Program Analysis by Xavier-yerith (https://www.archive.org/details/yerith-program-analysis-2023/YERITH-PROGRAM_ANALYSIS_2024_With_CURRICULUM_vitae_2024.pdf) !

13.13.2 How to use YERITH_QVGE

A software component or a whole running software binary could be verified against SQL correctness temporal properties by USING [YRI_QVGE](#), as illustrated in Figure 16:

- The 1st layer illustrates the runtime verifier tester monitor engine: YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF, that entails several custom runtime monitor specifications, provided by user.
- The 2nd layer shows the SUT (System Under Test); or PUA (Program Under Analysis); layer that communicates with YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF through QT socket calls (via Dbus messages). Each event message is sent to all runtime monitors. The SUT source code has been instrumented first, so to specify which program statements actions are to be packaged as messages to YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF. "INTEL-Pin" (<https://www.intel.com>) could also be used to instrument program binaries at runtime directly, Avoiding recompilation and even usable where source code of SUT (PUA) is unavailable.
- The 3rd layer illustrates a library or plugin (i.e.: MySQL) that is being monitored via instrumentation of the SUT; in this case, the SUT is YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum. Other providers could modify An Open Source Code Version (FOSS) of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF to verify and monitor another library-plugin other than MySQL.
- The 4th and last layer shows the Operating System (OS) layer and its communication via systems calls with the 3rd layer of the library-plugin.

13.13.3 How to use YERITH_QVGE in relation to verification cyber-security detection remediation methods.

1. Model Checking (<https://wikipedia.org>):

Temporal logic formalisms, such as LTL (Linear Temporal Logic) (<https://>); Could be used to create [State Diagram Mealy Machine \(SDMM\)](#) (https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf) [1d] and generate a binary executable of [YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF](#) (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) [1b] to perform runtime monitoring, and runtime SQL recovery of Graphical User Interface (GUI) supported software (And also not supported GUI software). Users must only note that "SDMM" specifications are fail (forbidden) trace behavior specifications of a program under analysis (SUT).

Structures could be created on how to translate simple LTL constructs into simple "SDMM"; So to ease usage of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF;

2. Runtime Verification (Monitoring; including Software Cyber-Security Exploit Detection Remediation):

A whole class of problems involving sequencing of actions and / or method calls ranging from:

- Application Programming Interface (API) checking protocol usage;
- WEB-APPLICATION RUNTIME MONITORING[?]; Software Security Vulnerability Analysis: I.E. Taint Analysis;
- Firewall security rules enforcement filtering;
- Information Flow Policy Control and Enforcement : (E.g. : Figure 20);
- Checking of automated and / or manual (unit) test procedure conformance with regards to TESTED PROGRAM (SOFTWARE) temporal properties;
- etc.

Could be solved by usage of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF; YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF GIT-REPOSITORY[1b]: [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif). "Pr. Prof. Dr. Jean Yang, Ph.D." from CMU-"Carnegie Mellon University" (<https://www.cs.cmu.edu/~jyang2>)" could be a potential competitor in this area of research.":

A. "Jeeves Programming Language" – last updated "October 2015" (<https://projects.csail.mit.edu/jeeves>)

- API usage rule check at 'AKITA Software' (<https://www.akita.com>)' in USA; California (CA).
- "Jeeves Programming Language" enables static typing;
- Dynamic code source rewriting to achieve Semantics; implemented as an embedded Domain Specific Language (DSL) in Python programming language (IT is unclear in which document [PROFESSOR JEAN yang checks] that this code is correct).

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES IV – CONTINUED — 2 VS. Jeeves Programming Language

Table 8: Jeeves Programming Language Versus (Vs.) The Runtime Monitoring Verifier Tester YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF

"Information Flow and Policy Control"	YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF	Jeeves Programming Language
1. Specification as a Domain Specific Language (DSL)	Yes (stand-alone SDMM (HTTPS://WWW.ZENODO.ORG/RECORDS/13232567) [1d] DSL specification; Based on MEALY MACHINE AUTOMATON; "HAREL-statechart (https://www.wisdom.weizmann.ac.il/~dharel/SCANNED.PAPERS/Statecharts.pdf) compatibility") ✓	yes (DSL embedded into Python)
2. False (Positives) Warnings	No (1 formal proof exists in journal paper (HTTPS://WWW.ZENODO.ORG/RECORDS/13232567) [1d]) ✓	* yes (CHECK A REFERENCE)
3. DSL Specification CARRIES DATA too	Yes (as Qt-DBus NETWORK data parameters) ✓	yes (as local stack function/method parameter)
4. As program annotations	Yes (FOSS Library Qt-DBus instructions) ✓	yes ('Jeeves' instructions)
5. USABLE in a any programming language	Yes (FOSS Library Qt-DBus instructions) ✓	no (Only Python)
6. ONLY usage with Python	No (any programming language that could emit Qt-DBus instructions) ✓	yes
7. Embedded in a programming language	NO ✓	yes (Python DSL library)
8. CRASH could occur during analysis and / or policy enforcing	NEVER	YES
9. Execution runtime overhead	No (concurrent event stream analysis monitoring verification) ✓	Yes (Embedded Python runtime dynamic source code rewriting)
10. Persistent storage technology	Yes; "MariaDB (https://www.mariadb.org)" ✓	Yes; "PostgreSQL (https://www.postgresql.org)" ✓

Table 8 compares tabularly the "Jeeves Programming Language" and "The Runtime Monitoring Verifier Tester YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF". In contrast to the "Jeeves Programming Language" that specifies information flow policy and control enforcement for Python, YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF is not implemented as programming language feature, and thus could be used for any software system that could emit Qt-DBus signals ; Thus, information flow control and enforcement is run as a separate process, concurrently to the system under analysis (verification or monitoring) as pictured in Figure 16.

Figure 33 illustrates a sample SDMM ([HTTPS://WWW.ZENODO.ORG/RECORDS/13232567](https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567)) [1d] specifying that a "FILE SHALL NOT be written-updated after it HAS BEEN CLOSED-DELETED".

13.13.4 Runtime Dynamic Program Interpretation Rewriting with "Jeeves"

The information flow policy control and enforcement solution provided by the "Jeeves Programming Language" is as follows :

1. A domain-specific language (DSL) is defined and embedded in a modification of the dynamic interpreted programming language Python. The drawback of an embedded DSL is a non re-usability in using other programming languages and framework other than those related closely to Python;

2. Only certain cases are flow policy control and enforcement are solved statically by "Python-Jeeves" type system;

It means that 'false positives warnings' cases still exist in programmer code and couldn't be removed by static compilation and / or dynamic code interpretation.

In contrast, "the mixed formal methods – runtime dynamic analysis monitoring" I used in "YRI_QVGE", don't allow by construction for 'false positives warnings': A 'false positive warning' is a message from the analyzing system that indicates an error accepting state while THERE IS IN EFFECT NO ERROR found yet.

3. Flow policy enforcement is solved dynamically at runtime by dynamic code rewriting; WE HOPE that this feature could be proved sound for all program statements because it might create uncertainty of valid flow policy enforcement at all.

Differently, "YRI_QVGE" uses SQL database statement query for performing error accepting state recovery (or—also—called "Information-Flow-Policy-Control-and-Enforcement").

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES IV – CONTINUED — 2 VS. Jeeves Programming Language

13.13.5 Sample Comparison BETWEEN Object-ORIENTED programming languages”

Table 9: COMPARISON TABLE BETWEEN C++, Python, AND JAVA. JAVA has an (interpretative and / or JIT-compiled) virtual machines that are in FACT reactive systems (E.g. : A "GUI software" is as well a reactive system) ! (WYSIWYG: What You See Is What You Get; VM: Virtual Machine)

FEATURES	C++	PYTHON	Java
1. PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE PHILOSOPHY	object-oriented	object-oriented	object-oriented
2. MACROS	✓	”	
3. MULTIPLE INHERITANCE	✓		
4. support INTERFACES	✓	✓	✓
5. STATIC COMPILATION	✓	✓	
6. RUNTIME MONITORING & VERIFICATION	✓ (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF)	✓ (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF)	✓ (VM INTERPRETATION AND MANAGEMENT)
7. UNIT TESTING FRAMEWORK	✓	✓	✓
8. NETWORK CAPABLE	✓	✓	✓
9. CROSS PLATFORM PORTABLE	✓	✓	✓
10. include FILE LIBRARY CAPABILITY	✓	✓	
11. MULTI THREADING	✓	✓	✓
12. WYSIWYG GUI DESIGN TOOL	✓	”	✓
13. VIRTUAL MACHINE IS A REACTIVE SYSTEM			✓

13.13.6 "Formal Methods – Runtime Dynamic Analysis" Vs. "Compiler Static Analysis Technology"

Figure 20: Runtime Verification Monitoring with YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.

Figure 21: YERITH SDMM based runtime monitoring verification analysis.

Figure 22: A sample [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET] in action.

I advocate :

1. Solving problems using compiler static analysis technology; that is based on lattice-theory is more safe than formal methods algorithms at first because MANUAL model checking has to be used to prove formal methods solutions correct, which could be very tedious and lengthy; "OR EVEN INTRACTABLE". SEE the state explosion problem (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Model_checking).

On the other hand static dataflow analysis algorithms based on lattice-theory are safe by construction and don't need no more proofs of consistency and validity as long as they only follow the base-pattern algorithm as for instance defined by "Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)".

THE previous statement also applies when using an instance of a static dataflow analysis based on the IFDS (Interprocedural, Finite, Distributive, Subset) (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Inter-procedural-data-flow-analysis-with-IFDS-IDE-Bodden/a3f7557fe673ff0711e9049cf5ece8b02a51f7f1>) algorithm from "THOMAS reps" (<https://www.grammatech.com>) at "The University of Winsconsin-MADISON-mad". (<https://www.wisc.edu>)

2. The formal method approach I use in solving problems listed in "Subsection 13.13.3"; a combination of formal methods with runtime dynamic analysis is as perfect as the "static dataflow analysis" standard algorithm by "Gary A. kildall", because **YRI_QVGE** uses only "fail (forbidden) traces" specifications and only exactly 1 outgoing edge for each transition in a state diagram mealy machine specification (<https://www.zenodo.org/RECORDS/13232567>) [1d]:

A whole class of problems involving sequencing of actions and / or method calls ranging from :

- Application Programming Interface (API) checking protocol usage;
- Software Security Vulnerability Analysis: I.E. Taint Analysis;
- Information Flow Policy Control and Enforcement: I.E. ...
- Checking of automated and / or manual (unit) test procedure conformance with regards to TESTED PROGRAM (SOFTWARE) temporal properties;
- etc.

3. Runtime Verification Analysis Results Combined With Static Dataflow Analysis Algorithms à la "Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)" as ; for instance implemented in "Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM" (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) :

- o One could combine runtime verification analysis facts with static dataflow analysis so to reduce fail state accepting code source location paths.

For instance, applying **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) [1b] to find an API violation rule such as a "FILE-Write-AFTER-FILE-close" as specified in Figure 33; that specifies a "SDMM DSL code (<https://www.zenodo.org/RECORDS/13232567>) [1d]" for finding a write after close program execution :

- a.) WHENEVER such a "file Close-WRITE API rule violation usage" is found by a runtime monitoring verifying analysis program binary, this information could later on be used by a static analyzer on code sources to eliminate manually from the program code sources code the found API violation RULE.
- b.) Our work : "Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM" (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) on detecting tainted path with an application for finding API usage rule violation in C++ code as ILLUSTRATED in Figure 35, COULD be used for instance !
- c.) Symbolic Execution / test-cases-test-data generation :

WHENEVER a fail-state accepting state is found by a run execution of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF;

- 1.) Such a run could only be executed with some test data stored somewhere in the SUT; a test case is also available for free since of the trace event log.

Such acquired test cases & test data could then be used later on to create some "testing suites" to exhibit this fail-state accepting error sequence run !

Symbolic execution run with finding of test data using a constraint solver like "Microsoft-Z3" (<https://www.microsoft.com/research--idiot--z3>) for instance, is only needed in case more test data and / or test cases are required for this fail-state accepting run.

13.13.7 CASE (Computer-Aided Software Engineering) TOOL for Software System Verification AND / OR algorithmic trading trade-time

Figure 23: A SCREENSHOT OF YERITH_QVGE FOR GRAPHICAL DESIGN OF STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE (SDMM) SPECIFICATIONS; THAT COULD SPECIFY TRADE OPERATIONS BASED ON TRADE-TIME.

Figure 24: A SCREENSHOT OF YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF SQL ERROR EVENT LOG.

1. [YERITH_QVGE] has also applications in specifying real-time trading operations based on trade-time; YERITH_{r&d} is going in the next years, to develop an algorithmic trading platform for free, Especially for exchanging inventory physical stock products (goods) for AFRICA; this is an ongoing project as an extension of the Enterprise Resource Planing SOFTWARE [YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM[?]; [YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME].

HAVING as physical good a currency bill and / or coin is Not impossible: THIS is what we daily practice when we buy items at a cashier and / or in street rural market; So people possessing a bill and / or coin may have advantages over people having only inventory physical consumer goods for their exchanges; SO it must be that parts of markets might Not ACCEPT currency bills AND / OR coins "for equity and fairness" since not everyone can afford buying currencies and / or bills-coins at a bank and / or financial institution. !

Having to buy currencies to European UNION, for instance for CMR, is very expensive. PART of exchanges within AFRICA borders could be done just by physical product (good) exchange between people and / or governments; Especially since getting currencies bills and / or coins is very expensive.

■ RELATED work at "QUANTstamp.com"; Venture funded initially by Y-COMbinator from STANFORD.EDU (<https://www.stanford.edu>) :

QuantStamp.com (<https://www.quantstamp.com>) is a firm that works mainly on solving the main problem on 'How to verify, check, a correct con-formant "bitcoin" contract on an Ethereum-platform trading (<https://>) : a so called SmartContract (<https://www.iq.wiki/wiki/quantstamp>)'.

"Figure 31 shows in French language a similar "stock-physical exchange" architecture based on an Ethernet-network "RJ45, and / or Giga-USB;" for YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum users."

2. Create and produce a computer device that could be embedded into other computer devices and that will communicate with them through serial ports and / or USB interfaces SO to provide YRI_QVGE program verification to USER FINISHED products on-the-fly, AS an add-on ENGINEERED industrial product: ALSO this product could qualify for an ISO-related certification for avionics, railways, automotive, and CE-ISO certifications for Healthcare: [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET].

Figure 25: A sample [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET] in action.

POTENTIAL APPLICATIONS:

- a.) "ON-the-fly (Add-hoc)" online / offline RUNTIME Verification MONITORING of all financial transaction operations at a financial institution; ATTACH a device at each computer and / or server using YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum; A comparable instance figure is illustrated for a control console device at Figure 25; WHEREAS one replaces a "control console LINAC" device with SERVER / Computer.
- b.) A linear accelerator control console communication protocol runtime monitoring (E.g.: Figure 25). A more detailed explanation graphical occurs in "Figure 20, Section 13.13.6";
- c.) A railway track controller program runtime monitoring console at site;
- d.) An aero-plane Maneuvering Characteristics Augmentation System (MCAS) runtime monitoring device
- e.) etc.

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES III – Distributed & Operating Computing Systems (ERP; Software & Hardware)

Figure 26: BUSINESS workflow of ERP software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM

Figure 27: Software System COMPONENTS workflow of ERP software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM

1. **CREATE A VERY CHEAP AND PRAGMATIC enterprise resource planing (ERP) software system** [Mar. 2015 – CURRENT]
 [STOCK EXCHANGE network for Francophone AFRICA; agile development method, [enterprise resource planing software], software engineering, computer software programming, computer software testing, computer program analysis]
 - a. **RENDER ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANING (ERP) SOFTWARE SYSTEM USAGE AND MANIPULATION AS EASY AS READING A LEISURE OR RECREATIONAL BOOK SO TO REDUCE USER STRAIN SIZE !** (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>)
 - b. **CONTRIBUTE TO REDUCE POVERTY BY IMPROVING SOFTWARE SYSTEM TECHNOLOGY FOR ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANING (ERP).** (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>)
 1. **All following advantages of using YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum contributes to reduce waiting files; THUS increase the number of customers and clients of an entrepreneurial organization !**
 2. Best and accurate technology SHALL REDUCE management effort and produce more reliable and cost-minimized business financial accounting information that enables to anticipate and reduce time of decision making.
 - 1.) **Gathering an overview over all financial and commercial; And customers / clients transaction information comes in JUST 1 button pressing from business dashboard window.**
 - 2.) **Exporting data onto Tabulator software such as 'LibreOffice-Calc, etc.' as Comma-Separated-Values (CSV), is as easy as selecting requested database table columns and Export them by pressing a button;**
 - 3.) **Calculating beneficial and interests costs is just as easy as reading it from business financial dashboard report generated automatically real-time and real-data from sales and customers, and / or Acquisitions databases tables.**
 3. Best and accurate technology reduces time execution of commercial business transactions, and thus, associated costs.
 - 1.) **Business Analytics : Ranking about sold and transferred goods and / or item stocks is best and just as easy done by reading it from a business commercial window dashboard; Ranking data decides what to order next for a better business turnover for your commercial financial entrepreneurial organization;**
 - 2.) **Ordering new item stocks is as easy as reading item stocks quantities from stocks window stock's inventory value.**
 4. So entrepreneurial commercial organizations could reduce a selling price without reducing its profit.

14.14 R&D Hardware & Software System Components

- o YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET [docs] — for Security / Safety.
- o YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0 [algo] [docs] 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0)
- o YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-CONFIGURATIONS-DATA [algo] [docs] 📄 <https://zenodo.org/records/14868175>
- o YERITH-ERP-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM [algo] [docs] YERITH-ERP-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM[?] (🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9))
- o YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RM-SYSTEM [algo] [docs] 📄 [YRI_QVGE\[1\] \(git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif\)](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif)
- o YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-HR-SERVICE-DAEMON [algo] [docs] 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-hr-service-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-hr-service-daemon)
- o YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON [algo] [docs] 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)
- o YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RT-SYSTEM [algo] [docs] **TODO for YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME !!!**

14.14.1 Detailed Presentation View

1. **HARDWARE device for on-the-fly runtime verification monitoring:** ★ YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET.
 FOSS documents location to..come.on..github.com/yerithrd (<https://github.com/yerithrd>)
2. **ERP software itself:** ★ YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.
 FOSS code location; **WARNING : we migrate 'varchar(256)' into 'varchar(50) mostly' !** 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0)
3. **Component 1:** ★ "yerith-erp-9-0-configurations-data": Configuration data for YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.
 This software component entails:
 - A configuration property file "yerith-erp-9-0.properties" that contains MariaDB database connection parameters data.
 - A configuration property file "yerith-erp-9-0-system-local-configuration-ENGLISH.properties" that contains local computer device and storage configuration parameters data.
 - A folder "yerith-erp-9-0-sql-backup-restore" where YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM database backups will be stored.
4. **Component 2:** ★ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM[?]: Web Sites Generator Software Component.
 FOSS code location 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9)
5. **Component 3:** ★ [YRI_QVGE\[1\]: Runtime Monitoring Analysis Verification System.](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang)
 FOSS code location 1 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang)
 FOSS code location 2 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif)
 FOSS code location 3 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif)
 FOSS code location 4 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_UNIT_TESTS](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_UNIT_TESTS)
6. **Component 4:** ★ "yerith-erp-9-0-hr-service-daemon": Service daemon for human resources related payments.
 FOSS code location 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-hr-service-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-hr-service-daemon)
7. **Component 5:** ★ "yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon": Service daemon for alerts over inventory stocks, assets, and financial expenses.
 FOSS code location 🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES III – Distributed & Operating Computing Systems ("Adversaries systems")

Figure 28: BUSINESS workflow of ERP software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM

Figure 29: Software System COMPONENTS workflow of ERP software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM

Table 10: Comparison between 'YERITH-ERP-9.0' and 3 top tier-1 ERP systems

Features	'YERITH-ERP-9.0' (≈ 10 years old)	'Contr-ALL' (≈ 7 years old)	'Sage Gescom i7' (≈ 40 years old)	'SAP Business One' (≈ 40 years old)
★ HR & CRM & Accounting full featured ERP	YES	NO	YES	YES
★ runtime monitoring checks enabled	YES (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF)	NO	YES	YES
★ Documentation online available fully	YES (Here For Instance) (https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724)	NO	NO	NO
separate views per user role	YES	YES	YES	YES
complete training (or solution)	at least 4 weeks	at least 3 weeks	at least 2 months	at least 3 months
★ difficulty in navigation	easy	easy	very difficult	very difficult
usage language in software	easy everyday English	simple	simple	technical
financial accounting knowledge	no	no	no	useful
advanced marketing knowledge	no	no	useful	useful
★ internet connection	optional	useful (not at all internet means no access to any of your business resources.)	optional	optional

Table 10 illustrates 3 other top-ERP Systems that I deem to be serious competitors of YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum for now and in future time because of the quality of their design and / or features; As Implemented for now As I could find out.

Some Observations

1.) 'Contr-ALL' is a youngest one with only at time of initial investigation after an interview Questions & Answers with its creator "Rostand-MOUNGAM", 7 years old !

"Rostand MOUNGAM" rents 1 of my apartment for his legal living & business consulting services, Together with "NAOMIE" his wife !

2.) 'Contr-ALL' seems very close to a good ERP System like 'Sage Gescom i7' !

'Sage Gescom i7' is at time of writing (June 2025) around 40 years old !

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES III (Software Systems) – CONTINUED — 3 – "ALGORITHMS CREATED / INVENTED"

1. CREATE A VERY CHEAP AND PRAGMATIC *enterprise resource planing software (ERP)* [Mar. 2015 – CURRENT]
 ["YERITH R&D" Publications, STOCK EXCHANGE network for Francophone AFRICA, agile development method, enterprise resource planing software, software engineering, computer software programming, computer software testing, computer program analysis]

15.15 Summary of Created And / Or Invented ALGORITHMS in this ERP Project

Figure 30: Manager Main Window in YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum

- YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0 — Algorithms Excerpt [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0)
 1. *Non intermingling of QT-timer & User-button-pressing events for Cancellation Confirmation.* ["class YerithERPCancelModificationTimingObject"]C++; YRI_QVGE.
 - a.) *Dynamic selection of Cancellation withing each window frame based on user interaction.* ["class YerithWindowsCommons"] C++; Qt 5.
 2. *Concurrent algorithms using semaphores so to allow disk configuration data usage between multiple users.* ["class YerithPOSUser; class YerithWindowsCommons"]C++; Qt 5.
 3. *Manual Selection & Viewing of user QTableView columns.* ["class YerithWindowsCommons"] C++; Qt 5; mathematics-geometry.
 4. *Checking of daemon service running processes & emitting signals onto user viewing buttons.* ["class YerithAdminWindow"]C++; Qt 5; Bash; lxqt-sudo.
 5. *Automatic online English / French translation algorithm.* ["class YerithWindowsCommons"] C++; Qt 5.
 6. *Password detection & MD5-hash-Coding / Decoding for QT-widgets automatically.* ["class YerithPushButtonPASSWORD"] C++; Qt 5.
 7. *Selection of each ERP sale-service function within only 1 window frame.* ["class YerithEnterWindow"] C++; Qt 5.
 - a.) *Graph coloring algorithm to find paths.* FSA; Graph-based algorithms.
 8. *Pagination of QT-table data structure view-layout("QTableView")* ["class YerithWindowsCommons"] C++; Qt 5.
 9. *Printing & Creation of PDF documents based on LaTeX documentation system* ["class YerithTableViewPRINT_UTILITIES_TEX_TABLE"]C++; Qt 5; LaTeX.
 - a.) *Progress bar automatic Delivery for PDF-printing.* ["class YerithProgressBar"] C++; Qt 5.
 10. *Online textual search & display of database query for window table frame items.* ["class YerithAbstractClassYerithSearchWindow"] C++; Qt 5.
 11. *Automatic upgrade of SQL database between versions of YERITH-ERP-9.0.* [folder "yerith-erp-9-0-upgrade-sql/"] Git, Bash; SQL.
- YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-CONFIGURATIONS-DATA — Algorithms Excerpt <https://zenodo.org/records/14868175>
 1. *BASH-scripts to automatically generate a ".deb" file that entails configuration data for ERP-system software YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum !* DEBIAN LINUX 11; Bash.
- YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM — Algorithms Excerpt [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9)
 1. *Translation algorithm from QT XML interface design-drawings onto YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 !* ["class YERITH_WEB_SYSTEMS_MAIN_GENERATOR"]Qt 5-QXmlStreamReader.
 2. *Translator to generate PHP; HTML5; CSS code sources from YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0.* ["yerith-web-pages-generator/src"]YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0; flex; bison.
- YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RM-SYSTEM — Algorithms Excerpt [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif)
 1. *FSM based communication RPC algorithms to monitor and verify temporal properties scheme of [GUI] software.* ["Library YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF"]DBus; C++; Qt 5.
 2. *BNF grammar YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG Translator into a State Diagram Mealy Machine FSM.* ["Library YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF"] flex; bison.
 3. *State Diagram Mealy Machine (SDMM) library that enables runtime monitoring on-the-fly.* ["Library YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF"] C++; Qt 5.
 - a.) *Fully compliant to David-harel statechart visual formalism.* David-harel [statechart](#).
 - b.) *O(n) graph traversal algorithm (Method "YRI_trigger_an_edge_event(string)").* finite state automaton; forbidden (fail) trace specification.
 - c.) *Grammar in Backus-Naur Form (BNF) for specifying State Diagram Mealy Machine (SDMM).* BNF (Backus-Naur Form).
- YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-HR-SERVICE-DAEMON — Algorithms Excerpt [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)
- YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON — Algorithms Excerpt [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)
 1. *THREAD conform compliant algorithm to process stocks, & stocks-based alert messages triggered on time and / or quantities.* C++; Qt 5.
- YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RT-SYSTEM — Algorithms Excerpt **TODO for YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME !!!**

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES III (Software Systems) – CONTINUED — 2 – "DOCUMENTATION"

1. CREATE A VERY CHEAP AND PRAGMATIC *enterprise resource planing software* (ERP)

[Mar. 2015 – CURRENT]

[STOCK EXCHANGE network for Francophone AFRICA, agile development method, enterprise resource planing software, software engineering, computer software programming, computer software testing, computer program analysis]

16.16 Summary Documentation of YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM

Figure 31: *Generic Schema of Trading Realtime with YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum (French language)*

■ YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET (HARDWARE device for on-the-fly runtime verification monitoring)

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0

◆ [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0)a. *Database network connectivity – FRENCH*

Configuration MULTI-SITES (SUCCURSALES)

https://www.archive.org/download/yerith-erp-multi-sites-base-de-donnees/YERITH-ERP_multi_sites_base_de_donnees.pdfb. *Installation GUIDE – FRENCH*

Installation GUIDE – FRENCH

<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8060217>

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-CONFIGURATIONS-DATA

📄 <https://zenodo.org/records/14868175>

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM

◆ [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9)

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RM-SYSTEM

◆ [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif)

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-HR-SERVICE-DAEMON

◆ [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON

◆ [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RT-SYSTEM

TODO for YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME !!!

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES II – Dissertation Thesis Doctor–PH.D. in Electrical & Computer Engineering

Figure 32: YERITH-SAINT (LGPL license) : Accessing JAVA code with "Polyglot LLVM frontend"

A Mealy Machine State Diagram (SDMM) Specified Using Figure 33: YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF Specification Language for NO-WRITE-AFTER-CLOSE memory check API file usage rule.

```

1. yri_sd_mealy_automaton_spec YERITH_QVGE_sample_Write_after_close_file
2. {
3.   START_STATE(closed):IN_PRE(g, is_alias(g, f))
4.   -> [in_set_trace('DELETE.file.f', STATE(closed))] / 'UPDATE.file.g' ->
5.     FINAL_STATE(WRITE_AFTER_CLOSE):IN_POST(g, is_alias(g, f)).
6. }

```

1. Create A FRAMEWORK FOR STATIC verification of Temporal Safety Property in Plugin-based software by static dataflow analysis mainly for the JVM-Java Virtual Machine; by late **Gary A. KILDALL** (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gary_Kildall).

a. **Research Proposal (Doctoral Ph.D. Thesis) in Electrical & Computer Engineering :**

🔗 **"Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software;"** (Advised by **Nomair Naem** | **Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D.** | **Patrick Lam, Ph.D.**) |

[UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA]

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

YERITH_{R&D}, CENTER REGION, CAMEROON — (ADDENDUM WITH STATE DIAGRAM MEALY

[June 2024 – June 2024]

MACHINE (🔗 SDMM (https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf)[1d]))

[YERITH R&D — [Software Safety], API (application programming interfaces) typestate checking;, tracematches, computer software static program analysis, computer software dynamic program analysis, software testing, software integration testing, YERITH R&D — [computer software cyber-security, GERMAN STYLE HABILITATION]

17.17 RESEARCH WORK OVERVIEW

THIS IS A PRELIMINARY WORK ON CHECKING TEMPORAL SAFETY PROPERTIES USING A TRACEMATCH-ALIKE SPECIFICATION LANGUAGE; SOOT (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>) AND DATAFLOW ANALYSIS IS USED TO PRESENT A STATIC WHOLE PROGRAM ANALYSIS.

TRACEMATCHES alike specifications enable developers to specify API usage rule drawing, as a deterministic finite automaton (<https://www.wikipedia.org>). Patrick LAM and Xavier noumbissi NOUNDOU have at this effect presented short overview slides of 30 minutes at IBM workshop CASCON 2010 ! (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>). PDFSAM (<https://www.pdfsam.org>), and sample other Open Source Code Software (FOSS) ARE USED as benchmark for project evaluation.

18.18 SOLUTIONS WITH LLVM BY CHRIS LATTNER AT "APPLE LTD."

Instead of the 1st proposed Java-Soot approach as a whole program static dataflow analysis, a whole program context-sensitive dataflow static taint analysis for C using LLVM could successfully be implemented and described in 🔗 YERITH-SAINT (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) [34].

The 1st YERITH-SAINT algorithm was implemented for programs written in C programming language, and used a pre-processing step for analyzing points-to set using "poolalloc" (<https://github.com/poolalloc>) from Chris Lattner (<https://www.llvm.org>).

BECAUSE our static dataflow taint analysis algorithm works on three-address-code, LLVM compiler framework could also apply YERITH-SAINT to JAVA code as input programming language to LLVM frontend-compiler-framework (Example : <https://github.com/polyglot-compiler/JLang>); See for instance Figure 32 !

20.20 RELATED WORK: DYNAMIC PROGRAM ANALYSIS API-RULE CHECKER "TRACERORY"

"Unread memory verification" is an instance of API (Application Programming Interface) usage rule checking.

"TRACERORY" runtime unread memory verification tool of Jon Eyolfson" (<https://www.hdl.handle.net/10012/6206>) ; "Detecting Unread Memory Using Dynamic Binary Translation at RV 2013 in Turkey" (<https://www.YRITOLOOKFOR.org>) , Of my former office roommate at "ECE-Waterloo-formal-method Davis Center Room" (<https://www.watform.uwaterloo.ca>), 1st floor, and colleague in static dynamic program analysis, could be outperformed with use of 🔗 YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) [1b]: "a runtime monitor container for state diagram mealy machines (SDMM)".

"TRACERORY" uses runtime program binary code instrumentation in "INTEL-Pin" (<https://www.intel.com>) to instrument running programs for purposes of detecting unread memory; I ignore whether "INTEL-Pin" (<https://www.intel.com>) has an open-source FOSS competitor at time yet; — Jan. 15, 2025 —.

Figure 33 illustrates a sample "SDMM" specification with instrumentation of source code with statements 'DELETE.file.f' and 'UPDATE.file.g' for runtime verification monitoring of API usage rule for checking memory write integrity: Runtime function "is_alias(g, f)" tells whether heap variable "g", and "f" refers to the same memory address. Such a "SDMM" specification is synchronized against a running program within a runtime monitor container: YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>) .

21.21 CONCLUSION

"Due to incompatibilities with Patrick LAM; after March 10, 2015, I abandoned this research idea because I couldn't afford being laid-off without any letter or any other formal mean of communication other than telling a lie about a supposed ["Ph.D. Research Seminar"] at EIT building in Waterloo main (200 University Ave West) Campus! " (Ph.D. Dissertation Defence at DAVID R. Cheriton School OF Computer Science in "January 2015")

It is easier to specify forbidden-fail-traces instead of saying how traces shall be like. Required 2 courses from overall 4 courses to pass where completed in year 2013-(CS846 & ECE750); in addition to before Examination completed courses (ECE725 & CS744). 4 experts in software systems were committee members of my doctoral PhD comprehensive examination AT UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA :

1. Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D.

Email: olhotak@cs.uwaterloo.ca

2. Derek Rayside, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)

Email: drayside@uwaterloo.ca

3. Patrick Lam, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)

Email: p23lam@uwaterloo.ca

4. Lin Tan, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)

Email: lintan@purdue.edu

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (COURSES VISITED – AT THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. Courses I VISITED while at the University–racist of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

[ECE 725 / CS 745 – "Fall 2009",
CS 744 – "SPRING 2011",
First SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques – "SPRING 2011",
Computer Science related subjects courses,
program analysis,
YERITH R&D — [program verification],
model checking,
compiler design]

Summary–PAGES

Table 11: Visited Courses at THE university-racist of waterloo, ontario, canada-idiot

"Course Reference CODE" / "GRADE"	Period of YEAR	Course TITLE	Dispensing Department / SCHOOL
1. "ECE 725 - Nancy Day" / "90%"	Fall 2009	Computer–Aided VERIFICATION	ECE (ELECTRICAL & Computer engineering)
2. "CS 744 - Ondřej Lhoták" / "86%"	SPRING 2011	Advanced Compiler Design	CS (School of Computer Science)
3. "1 st SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques" / "N.A"	SPRING 2011	First SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques	menlo–racist–college (https://fm.cs1.sri.com/SSFT11/index.shtml)

Table 11 illustrates all courses I VISITED successfully during my doctoral Ph.D. in electrical & COMPUTER engineering degree program at the UNIVERSITY-white-racist of waterloo.

- 1.) [Visited courses as a post-doctoral researcher.]

- 2.) [Advanced Compiler Design]:

This project–racist–based course gave me the opportunity to learn perfection my theoretical knowledge and foundations in the following topics:

- COMPILER structure and optimizations

- 3.) [Computer–Aided VERIFICATION]:

This assignment-based course gave me the opportunity to learn foundations of the following topics:

- MANUAL THEOREM proving (also interactive theorem proving with "interactive theorem prover" ISABELLE–HOL (HIGH ORDER LOGIC))
- MODEL checking (EDMUND clarke et al.)
- Temporal LOGIC

The course instructor NANCY idiot day, was very verse in this material and could answer almost all questions without searching somewhere else than herself.

- 4.) [1st SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques]:

This marvelous experience gave myself opportunities to meet and hear-listen from best talented researchers in following areas of industrial research among other topics that I CANNOT ALL REMEMBER :

- "Interactive Theorem Proving with PVS"
- "Static Analysis by Abstract Interpretation"
- "Hardware / Software Co–Design"
- "Model Checking with JPF (JAVA PATHFINDER)"

I AM ALWAYS GRATEFUL to professor idiot NANCY day for having given myself this marvelous experience through her personal recommendation, As required for admission in the summer school !

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (COURSES VISITED AS POST-DOCTORAND-FELLOW – AT THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. [Courses I VISITED while at the University–racist of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA] |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2012 – Apr. 2015]

[ECE 750 – "SPRING 2013",
CS 846 – "WINTER 2013",
Online Software Security Course–racist–extreme – "WINTER 2013",
Computer Science related subjects courses,
program analysis,
program verification,
model checking,
YERITH R&D — [Cyber–SECURITY],
compiler design]

Summary–PAGES

Table 12: Visited Courses as post–doctoral researcher professor at THE university–racist of waterloo, ontario, canada–idiot

"Course Reference CODE" / "GRADE"	Period of YEAR	Course TITLE	Dispensing Department / SCHOOL
1. "ECE 750 - Patrick Lam" / "88%"	SPRING 2013	Static Analysis for Software Engineering (SASE)	ECE (ELECTRICAL & Computer engineering)
2. "CS 846 - FRANK Tip" / "88%"	WINTER 2013	Program Analysis for Web Apps	CS (School of Computer Science)
3. "Online Software Security Course–racist–extreme" / "85%"	WINTER 2013	Online Software Security Course–racist–extreme	Stanford university adult education online

Table 12 illustrates all courses I VISITED successfully during my doctoral PH.D. studies degree program in Electrical & Computer Engineering at the UNIVERSITY–white–racist of waterloo.

- 1.) [Program Analysis for Web Apps]:

THIS project-based course provided myself an opportunity to DISCOVER, design and implement a web–based dynamic TAINT analysis for a PHP–JAVA interpreter; I.E. a "JAVA application server" that also interprets and use PHP libraries and code :

📄 "A Dynamic Taint Analysis for PHP in Quercus" (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051621/>) :

1. 📄 [git https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis](https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis)
2. 📄 [git https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis-tests](https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis-tests)

- 2.) [Static Analysis for Software Engineering (SASE)]:

THIS project-based course provided myself an opportunity to design and implement a static TAINT dataflow analysis: 📄 YERITH–SAINT (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293/>) :

- o 📄 [git https://github.com/sazzad114/saint](https://github.com/sazzad114/saint)

I didn't appreciate that instructor PATRICK–lam came to contest my Correct and Righteous definition of taint source and taint sink in front of class during my presentation; AND THAT he was wrong when he said we shall check the internet media; IT DOESN'T make sense to contest something that a doctor–PH.D. has prepared at least 4 weeks in advance such as he did !!!

- 3.) [Online Software Security Course–racist–extreme]:

I took this software security course to acquire more knowledge in software security vulnerability analysis and detection from a pioneer–leader as university in this area of research as demonstrated by publications and startups created by alumni.

MONICA–lam (<https://stanford.edu/suif>) for instance is a very renowned scholar and tech–entrepreneur in security vulnerability research and analysis. THIS online web course was very interesting from a content point of view for me as a doctor–of–engineering–ph.d..

ESPECIALLY because I WAS working on my "YERITH–SAINT algorithm" (https://www.archive.org/download/jh-nissi-ece-uwaterloo-grad-talk-2014-04-16/JH_NISSI_ECE_UWATERLOO_GRAD_TALK_2014_04_16.pdf) FOR detecting, with static dataflow code analysis "à la "Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)", and fixing the HEARTBLEED–security breach bug in "OpenSSL–1.0.1–F" source code (<https://heartbleed.com>) :

- o 📄 [git https://github.com/sazzad114/saint](https://github.com/sazzad114/saint)

"BUT i could notify when i started passing the online examination for getting a printed sent per mailbox certificate; THAT there was a kind of re–make in another stand so "that I WOULD NEVER PASS with more than 95%" as required to acquire that certificate – (I HAD PAID around \$500 USA dollars for attending this online graduate adult education course)" !!! "

"I Was almost always getting a "84% grade" ("3 times") ! THIS actually represents the successful passing required academic grade for a doctoral level course at WATERLOO."

"I HAD EVEN visited the premises of STANFORD university together with SANDY–beidu–gay–idiot–from–ghana–cuon–pd "in year 2011" while attending a formal method techniques school at AHERTON–COLLEGE nearby "by around 40 minutes drive"."

YEARS "09 / 2009" – "2010"

SUMMARY-PAGES

- I have prepared, and presented a static dataflow analysis in November 2010 at *IBM workshop CDP CASCONE 2010* (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>).

[Workshop-CDP; IBM casCon 2010]

The goal of this static dataflow analysis was to solve the issue of temporal property API rule checking in Plugin-based software.

- I co-taught and assigned marked with Patrick for courses:

1. "Programming for Performance (ECE 459)";
2. "Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465)".

- I have successfully attended the course ("CS 745 / ECE 725") – *Computer-Aided Verification* (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~nday>), taught by "Prof. Dr. Nancy Day". I could learn about following topics:

COURSE-ECE 725

THIS psy-professor is somewhat "a culprit of canadian armed robber forces only for black-descendants; Including iranian; holy-bible-CYRUS-ISIAH-45" (<https://www.sainte bible.com/lsg/isaiah/45.htm>).

1. OCAML functional programming language
2. Propositional Logic
3. First Order Logic (Predicate logic)
4. Higher Order Logic (Lambda Calculus) "with Haskell"
5. Theorem Proving
6. Interactive Theorem Proving with "Isabelle HOL"
7. Model Checking (with use of "SMV model checker")
8. etc.

- *I have met in-person "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Nomair Naeem" (HELP with understanding of static dataflow analysis algorithms): "Especially with context-sensitive parametric analysis".*

- *I have as roommate and best-friend [Diplom-Ingenieur-Informatik (Dipl.-Ing.-Inf.)] THOMAS REIDEMEISTER, 'aus MAGDEBURG'. He is also a computer engineer graduate student "in ECE at THE university of Waterloo, ON".*

THOMAS (<https://www.reidemeister.com>) is so much helping to myself including recommending myself a "JAPANESE toyota corolla LE 2003-(plate BLAB 045)" car as buying tip because of low costs in maintenance in ontarian-Canada.

I learned at least 80% of a happyfull life in ontarian Canada from THOMAS as a kind of senior brother of mine.

- (a) Difference between brunch and lunch; with an invitation for a brunch in KITCHENER: I cannot remember the name of this very nice restaurant by a sunday-morning;
- (b) Farmer's market in Kitchener;
- (c) * * *—*Asian food market stores in Kitchener*—* * *;
- (d) etc.

"THOMAS moved-in into our student house as replacement for a nigerian so called CHRISTIAN-faked TOMIWA ADAMURULA (tom)."

"AS I have matured myself, "today, in 2024, "September 1st," THOMAS must be from NAZI-ss-combat engineering against black-descendants like "cameroonian MARTIN tchangoue", employed at LABFORGE.CA (<https://www.labforge.ca>)".

I could remember being very happy all time with * * *—*JOHN and ANNA GULDEMOND*—* * * the sweet-nice landlords.

20.20 YEARS "09 / 2009" – "2010"

SUMMARY-PAGES

— I have met in-person Prof. Dr. Eric Bodden at our (Xavier, JON eyolfson) office room in "Davis Center".

— I have improved my technical skills in following areas by reading technical reports and conference articles:

1. **"Program Verification (Ph.D. thesis from Patrick LAM)"** (<https://patricklam.ca>)
2. Algorithm Design, and Implementation (from book **"Introduction to Algorithms"** ([https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gary_Kildall](https://www.amazon.com/Introduction-Algorithms-fourth-Thomas-Cormen/dp/026204630X/ref=sr_1_1?crid=2UBHH37C2Y2J3&dib=eyJ2IjoiMSJ9.RxrAGDmePG_uPSHKskT1qe4eJp18_sU0zfGdVfEd1BzcVOqunH6HMFduvfBk5T7_hbHBgRqWHVSmsYFd00P9qIyOhMwCdwVMeRQodxABI7cszQQi1XxeWBU8jZqpGALecudSCyPct_N4de9gwlldrRqhL2Alh8huCTZ2PeIoFPH8JLCoU0jaTq8vuQ-G7z1Jdit5yRk2hl627B7GRAFG3fiolk8kSGbcuK5_JsFw6g.AobHaMGD2q1MBzQIcdziArWAZLVbUQztj2REK1DRJ0Y&dib_tag=se&keywords=CS+Algorithm+book&qid=1726183252&s=books&prefix=cs+algorithm+book%2Cstripbooks-intl-ship%2C313&sr=1-1));)
3. Deterministic and Nondeterministic finite automata theory;
4. JAVA and its virtual machine;
5. Static Dataflow Analysis by Gary A. KILDALL (<a href=));
 - a. **SOOT framework** (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>) ;
 - b. **"Tracematches formalism by Hendren, Lhoták, et al."** (<https://plg.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak/pubs/rv07.pdf>)

— *I have attended following workshops and conferences:*

[IBM WORKSHOP-CDP CASCON 2010]

1. **"IBM workshop CDP CASCON 2010"** (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>)
 - a. I could talk briefly with Patrick Doyle from **J9-JAVA** (<https://www.ibm.com/docs/en/configurepricequote/10.0?topic=machines-j9-jvm>) JIT-compilation team at IBM Toronto Software Lab
 - b. **Maxime Boisvert Chevallier** (<https://scholar.google.ca/citations?user=1Sg6I8gAAAAJ&hl=en>)

[OOPSLA 2010]

3. "I have attended the conference **"Programming Language Design And Implementation (PLDI 2009)"** in Toronto:"

[International CONFERENCE-pldi-racist-extreme; PLDI 2009]

- o **Pr. Prof. Dr. JEAN yang, she was a then Ph.D. student and candidate at "MIT"** (<https://people.csail.mit.edu/jeanyang/index.htm>) " (<https://www.cs.cmu.edu/~jyang2>) .
- o **"Nurudeen Lameed (from Nigeria)** (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~nlamee>)", "and other **SABLE-mcgill** (<https://sable.mcgill.ca>) graduate students" and I presented to each other;
- o **"Pr. Prof. Dr. Tom Ball from Microsoft Research (MSR)** (<https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/people/tball>)", and I presented each other.
- o **"Florian Zuleger (from Austria)** (<https://informatics.tuwien.ac.at/people/florian-zuleger>)", and I presented each other.
- o **"Stephan Zucker, PhD (from Switzerland)** (<https://>)", and I presented each other.

21.21 YEAR "2011"

Summary-PAGES

— "December 20th, 2011":

I have prepared and successfully passed my doctoral PhD comprehensive examination in front of at least 4 experts in Software System:

1. Prof. Dr. Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D.
2. Prof. Dr. Derek Rayside, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)
3. Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)
4. Prof. Dr. Lin Tan, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)

— I co-taught and assigned marked with Patrick for course:

1. "Programming for Performance (ECE 459)".

— I have successfully attended the course "CS 744" – **Advanced Compiler Design** (<https://plg.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak/cs744>), taught by "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Ondřej Lhoták".

I could learn about following topics:

1. **SOOT framework** (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>)
2. Meet Over Paths (MOP)
3. Basic Block (BB), Control Flow Graph (CFG)
4. Three-Address-Code ("3-Address-Code")
5. Static Single Assignment Form ("SSA form")
6. Pointer (Alias) Analysis
7. Static Dataflow Analysis by **Gary A. KILDALL** (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gary_Kildall);
8. Transfer flow functions
9. Components of an advanced Compiler (E.g.: Optimizer, backend, etc.)

COURSE-CS 744

— I have met in-person "**Michael Pradel**". (https://software-lab.org/people/Michael_Pradel.html)— I have met in-person "**ALEXIE tcheuyap-idiot-cuon-pd**". (<https://discover.research.utoronto.ca/12279-alexie-tcheuyap>)

— **I have, in summer 2011, received a personal visit of "Mae Wandji", baby of my uncle maternal "Théodore & Aurélie Wandji Yagno Kamdoum": she was accompanied by "her mother Aurélie Yagno Wandji" !**
"Mae Wandji", and her mother "Aurélie Wandji Yagno Kamdoum", I dedicate a successful PhD comprehensive examination ! "

— I have met in-person **Prof. Dr. MARTIN vechev**. (<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=aZ1Rh50AAAAJ&hl=fr>)

— I attended successfully the summer school: "**First Summer School on Formal Techniques**" (<https://fm.cs.sri.com/SSFT11/index.shtml>); organized by The "National Science Foundation (NSF)" located at SOFTWARE RESEARCH INSTITUTE INTERNATIONAL (SRI International), at "Menlo College, Atherton, California, USA" from May 22, 2011 until May 27, 2011.

[ATHERTON-COLLEGE] / ["1st Summer School on Formal Techniques"-2011]

Topics we learned about and practiced where among others:

- o "Interactive Theorem Proving with PVS" (by "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Natarayan Shankar")
- o "Static Analysis by Abstract Interpretation" (by "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. David Moniaux")
- o "Hardware / Software Co-Design"
- o "Model Checking with JPF (JAVA PATHFINDER)" (by "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Villem WISSER-neger-racist-stelenbosch-university-SA")

— I have improved my technical skills in following areas by reading technical reports and conference articles:

1. Algorithm Design, and Implementation (from book "**Introduction to Algorithms**" ([Holy-Ghost. YERITH-NISSI. \(JEOVAH-NISSI IN HEAVEN.\)](https://www.amazon.com/Introduction-to-Algorithms-fourth-Thomas-Cormen/dp/026204630X/ref=sr_1_1?crid=2UBHH37C2Y2J3&dib=eyJ2IjoiMSJ9.RxrAGDmePG_uPSHKskT1qe4eJp18_sU0zfGdVFeD1BzcVOqunH6HMFduvjfBk5T7_hbHBgRqWHVSmsYFd00P9qIyOhMwCdwVMeRQodxABI7cszQQi1XxeWBU8jZqpGALecudSCyPct_N4de9gwldrRqhL2Alh8huCTZ2PeIoFPH8JLCoU0jaTq8vuQ-G7z1Jdit5yRk2hl627B7GRAFGV3fiolk8kSGbcuK5_JsFw6g.AobHaMGD2q1MBzQIcdziArWAZLVbUQztj2REK1DRJ0Y&dib_tag=se&keywords=CS+Algorithm+book&qid=1726183252&s=books&prefix=cs+algorithm+book%2Cstripbooks-intl-ship%2C313&sr=1-1));
2. Deterministic and Nondeterministic finite automata theory;
3. JAVA component-based software development by OSI architecture and Eclipse IDE (Integrated Development Environment);
4. JAVA and its virtual machine;

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22.22 YEAR "2012"

Summary-PAGES

- I co-taught and assigned marked with Patrick & Derek Rayside & Jon Eyolfson & Leo Passos, etc. for courses:
 1. "Compilers (ECE 351)": *Python scripts were written to automatically correct programming assignments from code source repositories.*
- *I went for an academic and professional internship at IBM Toronto Software Lab;*

I wanted to improve my programming languages design and implementation skills as well as BASH-scripting.

I spent 2 Academic terms (8 months) in Markham (Ontario, Canada) for this internship.

I worked there under supervision of [*Patrick Doyle, M.A.Sc.*,] and then "*Prof. Vijay Sundaresan, M.Sc.*".

 - o I worked principally as a tester for certain optimization features of the "J9 JIT compiler" for the JAVA application server (Servlet container) *IBM Websphere* (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/IBM_WebSphere_Application_Server) under "*Prof. Vijay Sundaresan, M.Sc.*". I was writing BASH-scripts to run and evaluate implemented certain optimization features for the "J9 JIT compiler" for the JAVA application server.
 - o I could attend to lectures given at IBM Toronto Software Lab by "*Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Clark Verbrugge*" (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump>) from "*McGill University*" on Creating Optimizations for Compilers.
 - o I could improve my skills with the following tools among others:
 1. "GNU-bash" (<ftp://ftp.gnu.org/pub/gnu/bash>)
 2. "GNU-vi / GNU-vim" (<https://www.vim.org>)
 3. "GNU-screen" (<https://savannah.gnu.org/projects/screen>).
- "*Prof. Vijay Sundaresan, M.Sc.*" wanted myself to be back next summer for another internship with him at IBM: unfortunately I resigned from this engagement because I felt I had to go back in my home country: Cameroon !
- I befriended myself at IBM with "*Aayush Prakash, M.A.Sc. (Waterloo, 2013)*" (<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=hUXGzpgAAAAJ&hl=en>).
 1. I had a toyota corolla 2007 LUXUS EDITION; that's why Aayush PRAKASH 1st contacted me so I could help him mornings.

I tried trice but I COULDN'T anymore because I COULDN'T wake up so early; because MARKHAM is a very big city with so much traffic. BUT WE STAYED friend for ever.

THX. BRO.
 2. We then became roommate in Waterloo the following fall (September – December) term; I COULD appreciate someone nice and very comfortable with my living style since I am the one that was principally renting the 2-bedroom apartment on 16-457 ALBERT-STREET.

HE never not paid his subrent; and was also kind to learn more about how to better maintain a common washroom.

THEN he moved to IBM after successfully graduating with a M.A.Sc. in Electrical & Computer Engineering from PROFESSOR-racist HIREN-patel-racist !

I then went several times to visit AAYUSH when he moved to Toronto.
- I befriended myself in Toronto with the following fellow Cameroonian:
 1. "~~Prof. Dr. Alexie Tcheyap, Ph.D. (Laval, "French Literature", Quebec, Canada, 2008)~~" (~~GAY-maker-assassin !~~) (<https://discover.research.utoronto.ca/12279-alexie-tcheyap>);
 2. "Erick Djeuyou Pokem, B.ASe. (Lilles, "Business Informatics-MIAGE", France, 2007)";
 3. "Audrey Nguetie Tchamga, B.Sc. (Laval, "Actuarial Sciences", Quebec, Canada, 2008)";
 4. "Judith Ngaleu, B.Sc. (Montreal, "Telecommunication Engineering", Quebec, Canada, 2005)";
 5. "Eunice Gapie Yemte, B.Sc. (Luxembourg, "Software Engineering", Luxembourg, 2008)" (assassin);
 6. "Valérie Yogho, B.Sc. (Montreal, "Electrical Engineering Power", Quebec, Canada, 2008)";
 7. "Tobie Guilliane, M.Sc. (Paris, "Financial Accounting", France, 2008)" (ASSASSIN);
 8. "Francis Mbiele Kamga, MBA (ESG, "Business Management", Paris, France, 2007)" (ASSASSIN).
 9. "~~FABRICE wilfried siemeni, B.Eng., (FH Berlin, "Food Processing Engineering", Berlin, GERMANY, 2005); Diploma (IHN, "applied HOLISTIC NUTRITIONIST", Mississauga, Toronto, Canada, 2012); -M.Sc. (FH Berlin, "Food Processing Engineering", Berlin, GERMANY, 2006)~~" (ASSASSIN).
- *I have attended following workshops and conferences in 2012*, together with "*Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Patrick LAM, Ph.D.*" (<https://www.patricklam.ca>), after completion of the internship at IBM Toronto Software Lab (*IBM Canada Ltd* (<https://www.ibm.com>)):

[WORKSHOP-local MITACS Ontario; International CONFERENCE; PLdi 2012]

 1. "*MITACS Ontario* (<https://www.mitacs.ca>) at the University of Waterloo on how to behave properly when having lunch and dessert with other professionals."
 2. "*Programming Language Design and IMPLEMENTATION (PLDI 2012)*" (<https://>) in Toronto downtown.
 1. *I COULD TALK TO several researcher among employees of GRAMMATECH-racist-negger* (<https://www.grammatech.com>) from THOMAS-reps at WISCONSIN-madison. (<https://www.wisc.edu>)

23.23 YEAR "2013"

Summary-PAGES

— I talked in-person with "Mahesh Tripunitara" about some of my non understanding about Doctor-PhD advisor of mine "Patrick Lam"; "MAHESH TRIPUNITARA" said I shall look for research collaborations within University of Waterloo and just put the name of "Patrick LAM" at end of a publication !

I AM STILL VERY GRATEFUL for this insight into my life as a scientist that led me to try and talk successfully with following pro-eminent fellow computer scientist:

- "Vijay Ganesh"; very proud of having learned much of how to write a paper and / or reviews of other papers with him; I cannot be a Ph.D. or doctor without this collaboration !

THIS IS SOMEONE very good at teaching research skills only. I cannot say much about his private behavior since I generally don't mix my private life with professional life !

- ["Mohammad Hamdaqa" from THE STAR research lab (<https://star.uwaterloo.ca>)]
- "Aayush Prakash" (<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=hUXGzpgAAAAJ&hl=en>) (from IBM internship in Markham)
- "Leo Passos" from Generative Software Development research group at university of waterloo (<https://gsd.uwaterloo.ca/~lpassos>)
- "Frank Tip" (from IBM Research then as Professor at the University of Waterloo): AT all the very much inspirational about 'A SO CALLED taint analysis' in my research area at all.

Before visiting CS846 of "Frank Tip", I cannot know anything about what is a Taint Analysis (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>) .

THIS CS846 (Program Analysis of Web Apps) is my best course as a graduate student in terms of working on related papers and writing reviews. Frank Tip is a very good and proud research manager !!!

"Only 1 tip, and you get all the clue about what you really need to do."

- "Pavel Parizek" (https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=M_9_-WsAAAAJ&hl=en) (from Programming Language Research Group (PLG) (<https://plg.uwaterloo.ca>), invited by "Ondřej Lhoták")
- "BORZOO" (<https://>) (very respected in RV conferences series)

THIS [friend-kkk] of *sebastian fischmeister from AUSTRIA-adolf-hitler* (<https://uwaterloo.ca/~sfischme>) is so kind that he let myself in his office to present what I really want to perform as research. BUT i could notify an office with kind of ground-tapestry for WHAT-the-fuck.

24.24 YEAR "2013, 2ND PAGE"

Summary-PAGES

— I co-taught and assigned marked with "Mahesh Tripunitara" and "Igor Ivkovic" for courses:

- 1.) "Computer Networks (ECE 428)";
- 2.) " * * * Foundations of Software Engineering (ECE 651) * * * "
- 3.) " * * * Methods and Tools for Software Engineering (ECE 650) * * * ".

Several employees from "Google Waterloo Inc. (<https://www.google.ca>) " attended lectures ("Foundations of Software Engineering (ECE 651)", and "Methods and Tools for Software Engineering (ECE 650)");

[DIVAM JAIN racist from CA-U.S.A. even tried to make me hired there once ...].

— I started implementing a *LLVM context-sensitive solution to my Research Proposal Thesis* (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) ; Because *SPARK pointer analysis in SOOT* (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>) didn't permit for pointer-analysis data as a stand-alone pre-processing step, as *my early design of the static dataflow analysis suggested* (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>) .

— I have successfully attended the course [Program Analysis of Web Apps ("CS 846")], taught by "Pr. Prof. Dr. Frank Tip" (<https://northeastern.edu/~ftip>). I could learn about following topics:

COURSE-CS 846

1. web applications
2. Javascript
3. dynamic analysis
4. static dataflow analysis
5. "Quercus server" dynamic taint analysis (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051621/>) [3] by practicing within a personal single project
6. scientific papers reading and comparison.

— I have successfully attended the course Static Analysis for Software Engineering (SASE) ("ECE 750"), taught by "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Patrick LAM" (<https://www.patricklam.ca>). I could learn about following topics:

COURSE-SASE-ECE 750

1. dynamic analysis
2. static dataflow analysis
3. "static taint analysis" (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) [34] by practicing within a personal single project:

"I am the only one who had this idea of performing static taint analysis, because I previously did a dynamic taint analysis in FRANK-TIP-CS846—racist-course. *THE CS OF UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO wasn't* (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca>) even capable of [finding this racist-cs846 segregative course curriculum] when I asked for it in year 2022; Even FTP, the creator of it WASN'T confident to give it to a black from AFRICA ! "

[r-IT Seems NDJATIE-from-rotary commanded again FTP from the inside.]; *EVEN her husband ["pr. shanda; YVAN-plumber-bafang-babouantou"]*, is very well recommended by YAOUNDEACS these days. (<https://>)

[AHHHH, also THE general of science KLAUS HAVELUND from N.A.S.A (<https://www.nasa.gov/YaoundeACS>) was also invited by my emails so to acquire some knowledge about [YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF] since his paper with SFISCHME wasn't very proper.] (<https://www.ece.uwaterloo.ca/~sfischme>)

4. scientific papers reading and comparison.

— I have On the website of *stanford university* (<https://www.stanford.edu>) in the state of CALIFORNIA; IN-the-U.S "unsuccessfully (with "84% grade") attended" the course *Software Security*. I could learn about following topics:

[STANFORD.EDU—online-course-software-security 2013]

1. PRIVATE / PUBLIC INFRASTRUCTURE—key (GPG); CERTIFICATE—authority
2. CYPHER DECYPHER CRYPTOGRAPHY—algorithm
3. SSL-Secure—socket—layer protocol on HTTP protocol
4. ATTACKS strategies:
 1. SQL injection
 2. Buffer—overflow attack
 3. MAN-IN-MIDDLE attack
5. etc.

25.25 YEARS "2014" – "03 / 2015"

Summary-PAGES

— I find a very imposing book that explains in my better terms algorithms fixed point static dataflow analysis à la "Gary A. Kildall : *A unified approach to global program optimization* (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>):

- "*Advanced Compiler Design*"; ISBN: "", by author from IBM: .

THIS book doesn't destroy your brain like the book:

- "*PROGRAM ANALYSIS*"; ISBN: "", by author from AMSTERDAM: .

I implemented my own static dataflow fixed point algorithm in C++ object-oriented, and I published it on my student Ph.D. page <https://ece.uwaterloo.ca/~xnoumbis>; And on my defunct GITHUB.COM-web-page:.

I then improved and finished my static dataflow taint analysis, and starts preparing my Ph.D. research seminar as presented in booklets present in "ECE graduate students room" in EIT building !

NOT very long after this online internet-web publication; I LEAVE WATFFORM for Cameroon where I created YERITH R&D, and affiliated software systems programs.

— I met *Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Ondřej Lhoták* (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak>) in-person for a review of my created LLVM context-sensitive static dataflow analysis: HE WAS RELUCTANT only because of 1 missing application of the analysis.

— *I assisted students in the LABORATORY for coding in C++ during 2 weeks:*

1. "*C++ Laboratory (ECE 250)*".

C++ Laboratory (ECE 250)

[!!! Iranian canadian university of waterloo professors !]!!

My colleague JON EYOLFSON (<https://jeyolfson.com>) with Prof. Dr.-Ing. Ladan (<https://ece.star.uwaterloo.ca>), went to suppress my appointment illegally since I legally, according to ECE department regulations for 2 weeks vacation for personal illness purposes, sent JON eyolfson as a replacement laboratory instructor to myself to LADAN !

I couldn't recover my job as teaching assistant in laboratory at my stay-return from JON EYOLFSON that I sent to Prof. Dr.-Ing. Ladan, for only 2 weeks replacement of myself !

— I have prepared, and presented a context-sensitive static dataflow analysis in January 2015 at a DAVID R. CHERITON SCHOOL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE programming language research group (PLG) seminar talk.

[Ph.D. Dissertation Defense at PLG]

I had this work successfully approved at PLG by "dear-racist-idiot Ondřej Lhoták" (<https://plg.uwaterloo.ca>).

The title of my talk was: *CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM* (https://www.archive.org/download/jh-nissi-ece-uwaterloo-grad-talk-2014-04-16/JH_NISSI_ECE_UWATERLOO_GRAD_TALK_2014__04__16.pdf) ; the presented application was the finding of a buffer-overflow security vulnerability in SSL (Secure Socket Layer) protocol as found in the "*HEARTBLEED bug*" (<https://heartbleed.com>) .

"Dr.-PH.D. ALI TELAGHANI was the 1st iranian university of waterloo Ph.D. Candidate I reviewed. A former trainee of nancy day from watform. (<https://www.watform.uwaterloo.ca>) "

AT THE conference presentation table were present among others :

- (a) *Pr. Prof. Dr. MAGNUS MADSEN* (<https://www.cs.au.dk/~magnusm>)
- (b) *Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. "Peter Alan Burh"* (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/about/people/pabuhr>)
- (c) etc.

— I have prepared, and successfully presented a context-sensitive static dataflow analysis on "April 16, 2014" at an ECE graduate seminar talk.

[Ph.D. Research Seminar]

The title of my talk was: *CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM* (https://www.archive.org/download/jh-nissi-ece-uwaterloo-grad-talk-2014-04-16/JH_NISSI_ECE_UWATERLOO_GRAD_TALK_2014__04__16.pdf) .

There was around at least 20 other students attending this seminar (kind of lecture).

[The goal of this static dataflow analysis was to solve the issue of temporal property API rule checking in Plugin-based software by static dataflow taint analysis.]

26.26 RESEARCH OUTCOME HINDRANCE

Summary-PAGES

IT WASN'T POSSIBLE TO IMPLEMENT THE STATIC WHOLE PROGRAM ANALYSIS AS PRESENTED because of the non possibility to acquire points-to information as a pre-processing standalone phase/step from SPARK POINTER ANALYSIS FRAMEWORK IN SOOT.

It wasn't in my research interest for a "Ph.D. in Electrical & Computer Engineering" to dive into recreating a pointer analysis for SOOT by modifying for instance research outcome work of "AAKARSH NAIR, MASC (2009)".

It would be more productive to perform research with "Ondřej Lhoták" in "Mathematics Department at DAVID R. CHERITON SCHOOL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE" (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak>) rather than with DR.-PH.D Patrick LAM at ECE Department. So I stayed out of this area of research for the "Ph.D. in Electrical & Computer Engineering"; Computer Software Engineering is more focused on developing methodologies around software rather than creating complex computer algorithms for calculation purposes; AS this is done in Computer Sciences (E.g.: "Ph.D. in Computer Science").

It is somehow also feasible for a "Computer Software Engineer" easily to implement a "pointer analysis as a Ph.D. in Computer Sciences could do whenever needed" !

I ("Doctor–PH.D. of Engineering Xavier Noubissi Noundou") have, for instance demonstrated, I could at least at level of a pointer dataflow analysis design and implementation performed by implementing the 1st openly (FOSS) published on the internet (2015): [CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC DATAFLOW ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM ! \(https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293\) \[34\]](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293) : "git <https://github.com/sazzad114/saint>".

27.27 RESEARCH OUTCOME PLAGIARISM

Summary-PAGES

1. 1st of all, I need to mention that JON eyolfson has tried to remove all connections to my person in his documents I could see on the internet media and / or wherever else.

FOR instance, JON eyolfson doesn't mention anymore he reviewed papers for OOPSLA 2010; I ASSUME because my name stays also in the document viewable from the web I COULD SEE last .. (https://dl.acm.org/action/showFmPdf?doi=10.1145%2F1869459&ved=2ahUKEwibYOExb6IAxXdgP0HHfm0A2YQFnoECCIQ&usq=A0vVaw0DwvmxPoRXI7v__J6preu)

"Doctor–PH.D of Engineering JON EYOLFSON" (<https://www.ece.utoronto.ca/people/eyolfson-j>) could for instance implement a Gary A. KILDALL (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gary_Kildall) static dataflow pointer analysis based on my research outcome in ["XAVIER NOUMBISSI NOUNDOU'S DOCTORAL EXCERPT DISSERTATION" \(https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293\)](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293); Even though he didn't cite my previous work and also Gary A. KILDALL (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gary_Kildall).

Instead, HE WENT ON TO CITE "John B Kam and Jeffrey D. Ullman", in 'Monotone Data Flow Analysis Frameworks' !

I could also notify that the description of the flow functions in JON EYOLFSON's doctoral thesis, Acknowledged by "Professor Doctor–PH.D of ENGINEERING "Ана-Міланова" from RIP (Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute) (<https://www.cs.rpi.edu/~milanova>)", Wasn't compliant to the highest academical standard as IT IS DUE for a university in ONTARIO–CANADA.

"Jon" instead of performing a pre-processed step pointer analysis result searching, went on to implement a whole program static dataflow analysis, INCORPORATING an LLVM-based pointer analysis, copied from my work, Without citing it ("I finished that work in 2015", While "JON Eyolfson" defended his Ph.D. thesis containing this pointer analysis in 2018).

"I could also note it seems ["Ondřej Lhoták"] wasn't a member of JON eyolfson dissertation defence examination committee (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak>), even though HE ('Ondřej Lhoták") is the most famous scientist in this area of research at the UNIVERSITY of WATERLOO based on his publication and citation record (<https://dblp.org/pid/05/469.html>). "

Better said HE is kind of a JOHN–Hopcroft level academical professional scientist based on my research time worldwide & abroad of GERMANY & Cameroon–Africa !

2. " My intellectual and copyrighted work with "DIVAM JAIN, M.Math", now at ["Google Waterloo Inc."] (<https://jobs.google.com/about/>), has by now produced at least 11 scientific published papers worldwide, with money rewards, [without my name on neither on them.]"

INSTEAD, other people reward from it:

1. Dr. Patrick LAM;
2. Dr. Reid Holmes;
3. Dr. Derek rayside;
4. "zheng FELIX fang, M.ASc. (<https://dblp.org/pid/170/1472.html>)"; (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)
5. etc.

QUARRELED PAPERS:

1. "Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints" (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)

Plagiarism

28.28 RESEARCH OUTCOME PLAGIARISM – CONTINUED – 1

Summary-PAGES

1. "Professor Araving Machinry" also used code sources results from my Static Dataflow Analysis without any citation of it in his Award winning USENIX paper; I mailed him in 2017; HE said that my work wasn't published by a peer-refereed conference and/or workshop, or whatsoever, THAT'S WHY he couldn't cite it.

Instead of citing the 1st original publication of a Free and Open Source Software code (FOSS), 2015, As I have published in on 'www.github.com (git <https://github.com/sazzad114/saint>)'; ARAVIND cited instead my competitor BODDEN-ERIC (<https://www.bodden.de>) (from Germany (<https://www.fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Allemagne>) and Previous colleague of Patrick LAM (<https://www.patricklam.ca>) at McGill University (<https://www.mcgill.ca>)).

Long after terminating my research collaboration with Patrick LAM at University of Waterloo, ONTARIO, CANADA; I could then notify that he was talking especially to "ARAVIND machinry my competitor about my research under his supposed supervision without telling it to myself!"

2. A ghanaiian ignorant, wretched worldwide called SANDY-beidu thinks he could behave so to alter my JEOVAH-NISSI-confidence at his underground-peggist home in bavaria-waterloo.

BEcause I rented a "ford fusion" during my travel to the "1st summer school on formal techniques" in ATHERTON, california; So to be mobile because I HAD TRAVELED to united states of america before when I WAS an employee of bavarian Siemens-medical-solutions; THIS guja went on to buy as his 1st car a similar "ford fusion" since he thought I WANTED to show up in front of him and ANOTHER black-afro-descendant from long-islands.

I AM EVEN wondering how this lady from basement science could be invited to the summer school ! AT ALL ! may be a call-girl !

FROM academic level point of view, this ignorant doctor of philosophy in computer science, SeEms to ignore what I COULD BUILD AS [enterprise resource planing (ERP-system) software !!!!!!!!]

3. JAN peleska from GERMANY, didn't say anything about the law against myself in Cameroon because he is the one who went to report false behaviors of myself to Cammeroon authorities about my living style in Germany without telling anything to me about.

Even at German Embassy in Yaounde, I could notify a strange behavior of people working there against myself while I came to complain against FRANGK-BIYA, son of PAUL-BIYA. THIS-GAY-with-my cousin-PATRICE-GABRAL-SHANDA-SANO (deceased by now since March 18, 2024 went to destroy my investment by creating a forestry society just opposite of my lawful building for peaceful habitation usage) !

JAN peleska from GERMANY, also seems to be the one that said and commanded PATRICK LAM to destroy my career because I reluctantly refused to pursue doctoral Ph.D. research (<https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/gesy>) under his supervision at the University of Bremen; I.E. Jan peleska insulted violently myself in front of HELGE LOEDING (<https://www.LOEDING-ONLINE.de>), SERGE FOPOUSSI NONO ACHILLE (<https://www.deutsche-digitale-bibliothek.de/person/gnd/141875240>), etc.

I cannot live with racial segregation !

Figure 34: YERITH-SAINT ([LGPL license]) Algorithms Architecture. "poolalloc" pointer-alias analysis tool from "Chris Lattner" at "APPLE Ltd." is re-used.

Figure 35: A sample **API rule violation** as tainted path "close(fd) => write(fd, &sum, sizeof(i)) L4–L7–L9–L10–L11" (orange colored lines of code); on LLVM THREE-ADDRESS-CODE.

```

1      ssize_t write(int fd, const void *buf, size_t count); // taint sink
2
3      uint SAVE_Document (unsigned x, int fd, const void *buf, size_t count) {
4  L1: uint sum = 0;
5  L2: uint i = 0;
6  L3: if ( x == 2)
7  L4: close(fd); //API rule violation(--taint) source; "close(fd) => write(fd, &sum, sizeof(i))"
8  L5: else //not VALID api rule check !
9  L6: sum = 0;
10 L7: if ( i >= x)
11 L8: goto L12;
12 L9: sum = sum + i;
13 L10: i = i + 1;
14 L11: write(fd, &sum, sizeof(i));
15 L12: goto L6;
16 L13: return sum; }

```

1. Create A FRAMEWORK FOR STATIC verification of [Temporal Safety Property in Plugin-based software by taint analysis] – Continued

b. Doctoral "Ph.D. degree" Dissertation in Electrical & Computer Engineering: "Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM"; (Advised by Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Nomair Naeem | Pr. Prof. Dr. Ondřej Lhoták | Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Frank Tip | Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Patrick Lam | Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Vijay Ganesh) |

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[SEP. 2012 – AUG. 2015]

YERITH_{R&D}, CENTER REGION, CAMEROON — (ADDENDUM WITH TYPESTATE-API USAGE RULE CHECKING; STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE (SDMM[1d]))

[JUNE 2024 – JUNE 2024]

[Software Safety, API (application programming interfaces) tystate checking, tracematches, temporal safety property verification, cyber-security, software security vulnerability analysis, computer software static program analysis, computer software dynamic program analysis, software testing, software integration testing, GERMAN STYLE HABILITATION, Disputation-january-2015-DC-room-PETER-ALAN-BUHR]

The same class of problems that solve taint analysis issues resolve also API usage rules checking for specification of forbidden usage rules as a tystate specification. A violated API tystate (tracematch-alike) usage rule corresponds to a tainted path or a sub-tainted path (E.g.: path "L4–L7–L9–L10–L11" in figure 35).

You specify a **forbidden (fail trace)** [sequence of method calls that shall not occur in the source code]. Using static dataflow taint analysis, you check whether this specified forbidden (fail trace) corresponds to a tainted path or a subpath (of a fail trace).

"API (application programming interfaces) usage rules [tystate formalism is a similar paradigm of specification possible for input for this static context-sensitive taint analysis; "subsequent research of mine alone reveals state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) as a subset of tystates (SDMM[1d]),"] of JAVA or C++ library are another realm of application of this static context-sensitive (parametric) dataflow taint analysis."

"In contrast to Tracematches that specifies WISHED BEHAVIOR (PROGRAM TRACE) of API user interface rule calling method sequence; as illustrated in "Hendren, et al. work" (<https://plg.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak/pubs/rv07.pdf>), "state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) BY XAVIER NOUMBISSI NOUNDOU, SPECIFIES UNWISHED BEHAVIOR (PROGRAM FORBIDDEN FAIL TRACE)" (SDMM (https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf)[1d])."

"One effort could be to give a formal translation methodology from "tracematches onto state diagram mealy machine (SDMM)"; Thus enabling automatic reuse of all tracematch specifications directly into a runtime monitor engine like YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567>) ."

"Patrick has not at time understood that this application is also possible by static dynamic program analysis tool created by myself at YERITH-RD: YRI_QVGE[13.13]; a Free and Open Source Code Software (FOSS)."

"Patrick LAM my former advisor since '2015-MARCH-10' is missing !"

"Patrick LAM and Xavier noumbissi NOUNDOU have at this effect presented a short overview presentation of 30 minutes at IBM workshop CASCON 2010! (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>)"

A SINK IS AN ACCEPTING (error) STATE; A SOURCE IS A START STATE. Sources and sinks are methods from the library (or plugin) used by the program under analysis (PUA). Edges are other method program instructions as seen by a THREE-Address-Code representation such as Jimple (SOOT), Gimple (GCC), etc., and, or LLVM three-address-code format.

Since YERITH-SAINT our (Xavier, Vijay, and Patrick) static dataflow taint analysis algorithm works on three-address-code, LLVM compiler framework could also apply YERITH-SAINT to JAVA code as input programming language to LLVM frontend-compiler-framework, and perform as well API USAGE RULE check.

IT means in effect that any programming language that could be inputted to LLVM frontend-compiler-framework, COULD BENEFIT FROM THIS SOFTWARE STACK api (application programming interface) rule checker.

- YERITH-SAINT (Figure 34) : [git https://github.com/sazzad114/saint](https://github.com/sazzad114/saint)
- [PH.D.—RESEARCH—SEMINAR TALK] GIVEN AT AN ECE (ELECTRICAL & COMPUTER ENGINEERING) GRADUATE SEMINAR TALK SERIES, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA (https://www.archive.org/download/jh-nissi-ece-uwaterloo-grad-talk-2014-04-16/JH_NISSI_ECE_UWATERLOO_GRAD_TALK_2014__04__16.pdf)

"Prof. Dr. Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D. (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak>), A world renowned scholar and scientist from the University of Waterloo in Waterloo, Canada, Ontario; Has reviewed this work with only 1 recommendation: add an additional application sample example apart from the presented "FORMAT STRING VULNERABILITY (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Uncontrolled_format_string)" analysis done in the research paper."

1. **L' INSTITUT AFRICAIN D'INFORMATIQUE—Yaoundé—Centre D'excellence PAUL—biya—rdpc. |**
 INSTITUT AFRICAIN D'INFORMATIQUE, YAOUNDE, CENTER REGION, CAMEROUN

"2016"

[1 institut (<https://www.iaicameroun.cm>) atypique,
 ARMAND—claude abanda,
 NANGA.]

Summary-PAGES

I. **D'enseignant vacataire à ENSEIGNANT consultant "20 heures—la—semaine de cours" À "6,11 EUROS" par heure:**

Mes rapports d'encadreurs académiques de SALABESSI—cuon—pgsiste de MBANJOCK :

1. JE postule via "4 heures" d'attente au sale bureau du courrier pour être reçu par 1 ingénieur inférieur au rang de "bachelor of science" (ndlr.: LICENCE en informatique);
2. Après être reçu pour 1 entretien special avec M. ARMAND—claude—abanda—idiot; je passe 2 interviews supposées professionnelles;
3. A l'issue de la 1^{ère} interview qui n'est qu'1 vérification brève du curriculum vitae et de très petites connaissances pédagogiques; L'ON ME propose plutôt 1 poste d'ENSEIGNANT consultant plutôt que celui de vacataire à 8 heures de cours hebdomadaire auquel j'ai postulé.
4. L'on ma redemandé de donner tous des cours que je pensais être en mesure de distillés; SUR cette palette de cours, l'on m'a octroyé "Architecture des ordinateurs" comme 1^{ère} mission pour la 1^{ère} année de GÉNIE—LOGIGIEL en section anglophone de leurs cursus d'études.
5. Après seulement "2 semaines et demi", 1 certain "salabessi" vient me donner l'injonction de commencer aussi à donner le cours "ADMINISTRATION SYSTÈME programmation système".
6. JE décide de partir de cette institution puisque ce rythme de travail serait insoutenable pour ma santé fragile à cette période de l'année au vu du changement du climat hivernale canadien au climat tempéré de YAOUNDE—raciste—tribaliste—mado—BIR :
 - a.) Toute heure de cours est payée ("8 heures par semaine" dans mon cas); IL ne m'est jamais mentionnée auparavant que 20 heures de travail la semaine ne concerne que la dispensation des cours au tableau.
 - b.) Toute autre heure de travail est impayée :
 - PRÉPARATION des données pour des devoirs surveillés;
 - CORRECTION des examens et devoirs surveillés;
 - RÉDACTION d'1 support de cours en langue anglaise.
 - [IL semblerait que 1 sœur utérine à ma personne; "Ingride TCHITCHUI noumbissi, Épse chandriand—TEUNTCHOU noumeni" serait allée dire que je suis 1 patient psychiatrique pour destituer ma vie, telle qu'elle aurait organisée en FÉVRIER 2021 avec le "rotary—club de abanda armand à ÉDEA".]
 - PARTICIPATION tous des mercredi à 1 réunion d'enseignants consultants; (EX.nihilo; je n'ai participé à aucune d'elle en 3 semaines de travail vu le temps d'adaptation à la localisation très éloigné du centre de cours de NKOLN'ANGA).

II. **Mes Conclusions SUR LA QUALITÉ de cet institut de merde :**

- 1.) [JP-kamgain, le cas d'échec patent de l'IAI cameroun !!!]
- 2.) PAS de suivi exact des besoins et difficultés de nouvelles recrues;
- 3.) ABANDA—amougou—belinga (<https://>), écroulé par des heures de cours sans avisé des enseignants :
2 fois consécutives, on me redemande de dispenser plutôt 4 heures de cours et exercices d'affilés plutôt que des 2 heures de cours prévues dans le "planning" pour CAUSE que l'enseignant du cours suivant s'est absenté.

[DGAY__side-rek; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://saintebible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>);
Jon eyolfson—idiot; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://saintebible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>),
SARAH—white—kkk—peggist; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://saintebible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>)]

I. ISSUES - Problems with some colleagues:

1. ["Professor RAYSIDE"]

2. ["Student JON eyolfson, then Master of Applied Science JON."]

" This idiot white-supremacist-racist, that is watching videos about a murderer called 'LUCIFER' in our common office room while taking his lunch, is JUST A DISGUSTING kkk."

THIS junior computing engineer couldn't create a website for Watform lab (<https://watform.uwaterloo.ca>) after around 7 years doing a PH.D. in Computer Electrical Engineering: HE Had been mandated to do so in year 2009 when I started my "Ph.D. degree in Electrical & Computer Engineering" program as a "DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)"[?]. from the so-called-elite-universität-BREMEN-germany-de. (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>)!

3. "Student Hang chu (<https://uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/items/2656af1b-8829-45fb-bc5b-d1f49762ad49>), student of a so called professor patrick-lam, then Master of Applied Science HANG—chu."

THIS very-well-to-do person from China main island came to myself for a recommendation into a position as software developer in MISSISSAUGA-Toronto-idiot; I Accepted and tried to be very honest and humble in a form request form that was sent to myself the same day by a lady from "PHILLIPS subsidiary company" newest created !

4. "Student Wenzhu MAN (<https://uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/items/5ac24928-7279-41f1-9c58-634873430305>), student of a so called professor patrick-lam, then Master of Applied Science Wenzhu—MAN."

THIS ugly lady from CHINA main island, came into the lab-space rented to us by PATRICK-idiot-advisor during my 2nd year of doctoral PH.D. studies.

SHE seemed very intelligent but very hostile to black people as I could see her behavior when I asked her if she would like to collaborate on my ongoing static dataflow analysis YERITH-SAINT project, after I ASKED for this with, a positive approval from our common idiot supervisor ["PATRICK-vietnamese-vietkong LAM"].

SHE was reluctant and we never had any opportunity to present and/or Work on anything together; AS this was the same with [JON eyolfson; Who instead copied my work only !]

5. "PROFESSOR clementin tayou djameni (UNIVERSITY OF DSCHANG, WEST REGION, CAMEROON)"

" THIS sample ignorant on "algorithms complexity and concurrency computations on multi-computers" that I know because my uncle THEODORE wandji ngongang sent me to him while he was visiting EUROPE (FRANCE, then GERMANY); while I was still an undergraduate student at the "ELITE-UNIVERSITÄT-BREMEN" (<https://www.uni-bremen.de>); So I will have connections in ACADEMIA in my home country while I AM STILL outside of CAMEROON."

"I met, see, and even sleep beside him twice – 1st time in our student apartment in Bremen where he stayed 4 days – Then in Rennes-FRANCE in "2004" when he visited "GRENOBLE laboratory" with PROFESSOR tchindo-gilbert."

"I tried to contact him during "September-2011" because I HEARD from MARCELIN TALLY, cousin of mine, that I COULD apply already for a position as "assistant professor in CAMEROON" with a "DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER DEGREE (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)"[?] " like our common age-class colleague Oscar MOURBARE from Ngaoundere-Cameroon. [Dr.-Ing. DAYANG Paul] is also from university of bremen and also our common cohort in computer science in CS-Bremen (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>). "

"HE has never answered anymore any emails or telephone call while I was in Cameroon ! "

ISSUES and Misunderstandings 2 |

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2009 – Apr. 2015]

[DGAY__side-rek; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://saintebible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>);
 Jon eyolfson-idiot; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://saintebible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>),
 SARAH—white—kkk-peggish; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://saintebible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>)]

I. **ISSUES - Problems with some colleagues:**

6. "FORMER friend and now enemy Godrick CHEKETE H. from Benin—vaoodoo"

I encounter this idiot and voodoo man as I just entered my second year of doctoral studies at the university—racist of waterloo in ONTARIO, CANADA

THE Ghanaian so called YAW BOAKYE-agyeman, that I EVER met 1st time in African student association of the university of waterloo: "AFRSA" (<https://saintebible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>) as I was in my 3rd week in the city of Waterloo.

IT is the west—african student YAW, BOAKYE-agyeman, from ashanti—tribe that told myself that he would like to introduce me to another FRENCH-speaking student from WEST-AFRICA.

WE then met 3 of us in a restaurant inside the main campus located at 200 University Avenue West; I DON'T REMEMBER the name of the idiot-wwhite—racist restaurant for students.

7. "FORMER enemy MARTIAL ategomo YEMELE from Cameroon"

I encounter this vagabond because GODRICK—chekete recommended HIM (martial ategomo yemele to myself as a cameroon student in need of crucial help in life)

Normally I NEVER friend myself with such Cameroon people that seemed to have traveled with fake ID and other faked documents as I could imagine from his physical being.

IN year 2013, as I went to build a gate for my compound in YAOUNDE, Godrick and MARTIAL ATEGOMO YEMELE came ask myself that I sublet my bedroom-only for 1 month only to MARTIAL for "400 cad". I accepted and I needed afterwards to tell him very deeply to go out after "1 and half month" because HE seems to be wanting to stay even more than 6 months in my 2-bedroom apartment located at "16—457, ALBERT-ST., N2L 5A7, Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA—racist-idiot".

Martial ategomo and Godrick Chekete H.; I stopped any collaboration with both these ignorant right after asking MARTIAL and GODRICK to leave my apartment around 11 : 30 PM at night.

8. "ECE Master & Ph.D. programs coordinator Sarah Landy, MSc."

THIS very racist girl with a master of science, arrogant at all wanted myself to believe that SHE is a professor of mine even though I am wondering even today if she could even work somewhere else than a place where systemic racism is the norm and not the ANORMAL life day—work !

"This slot for professors of ECE is the one that on "MARCH 10th, 2015" told myself; "as she was a PH.D. & MASTER program coordinator in ECE department" of the university-racist of waterloo: "[Patrick (lam)] sent an email to cancel the event (MY SO CALLED PH.D. RESEARCH SEMINAR) according to academic graduate studies regulations of year 2015 ! " "

" SARAH as I could experience even when I PASSED ONTO HER HANDS my doctoral thesis; called research proposal at ECE department, has a personal grievance to my person from somewhere I CANNOT even imagine; because THIS document wasn't published anywhere or registered publicly on the university-racist of waterloo internet, or intranet—world ! "

9. [Professor idiot lin tan]

10. P[rofessor Patrick LAM]

11. [Professor LADAN]

ACADEMIA world worldwide contactS |

STARTUP YECFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE)

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY

[DEC. 2023 – "November 23, 2025"]

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2023]

[OCT. 2002 – JUL. 2007]

[Contacts with Academia in NORTH–AMERICA]

o CONTACTS with Academia in NORTH–AMERICA:

1. Doctor Christian Eyoum–sawa-rotarian–criminal–seasoned–psychiatrist (Laquintine HOSPITAL
DOUALA, CMR (<https://>))

[Around "2021"]

THIS seasoned psychiatrist that assassinates at least 500 persons a year was sent to me by "ROSE sangnou" my female genitor so to hijack my private–inherited apartment in "DLA-cité-des-palmiers" as I was just finishing a psychology family and personal treatment because OF "LAURENT-tchandeu", a criminal uncle paternal side of mine.

IT is at age of 6 years old that I lost my dear criminal genitor "THÉODORE noumbissi-salau"; I called this genitor of mine a "salau" because this freemason had a booklet on economy written by "KARL–idiot-mars" where I COULD SEE just a month after his sudden death, caused probably by NTOMANI–Racist, THAT theodore-noumbissi said: "GOD is stupidity and dirt !" !

IT is at age 35 years old that I understood that this mason of my genitor, "THÉODORE noumbissi"; tried to hijack myself but loose his own soul because mainly of his junior brother "LAURENT tchandeu".

"CHRISTIAN-eyoum" is only someone that destroys in all plans of life any person sent to him by "SECRETARIAT-D'ÉTATA-LA-DEFENSE (sed)", a so called SERVICE-SECRET.

IT seems the culprit eyoum sent some people from his hospitals to rent my 1st–storey house bedroom-apartment so to hijack people that want to travel to western countries.

I am suspicious of this because I cannot foresee an issue in the legal case I started at DLA-ndokoti justice palace in February 14th; After christian eyoum and state hospital laquintinie sent at least 9 people at night around 23 : 30 to hijack my real–estate property and life.

Also, eyoum walks with a walkie-talkie of cameroonian defense forces; SO he is somewhat a criminal of the army that must be arrested by SEMIL–ndlr: Sécurité MILITAIRE: a so called anti-gang unit against criminal from cmr defense forces.

2. Doctor KLAUS HAVELUND–idiot (Caltech, California Technology Institute
CALIFORNIA, U.S.A (<https://www.caltech.edu>))

["2022"]

Klaus is an idiot because HE wasn't capable of coming clearly with his expectations as I contacted him to review my at that time ongoing and starting project on CREATING A RUNTIME MONITORING VERIFICATION testing framework 📄 [YRI_QVGE\[1d\]](#) for state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) having following characteristics compared to opponents like; "TDIOHS (Timed Discrete Input / Output Hybrid System)" implemented in real-time testing tool 📄 [RT-Tester \(https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp/papers/peleska_et_al_soqua2006.pdf\)](https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp/papers/peleska_et_al_soqua2006.pdf) [?] of the society in germany: "VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GMBH, SPIN-OFF THE UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN" (<https://www.verified.de>) "; AND opponent tool ""DejaVu" (<https://>) ("DejaVu: A Monitoring Tool for First-Order Temporal Logic")" :

- o A Domain–Specific LANGUAGE (DSL) for specifying forbidden traces (fail traces) of mealy machine, formalized as state diagram: "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG".
- o A compiler–translator that generates free C++ code as runtime monitoring verification module to be run and watched "within runtime monitor container 📄 ["YRI_QVGE" \(https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf\)](https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf)[1d]".
- o "fail (forbidden) traces specification".
ALL competitors were having 'wished behavior trace specification';
- o "NO FALSE POSITIVES"; guaranteed with a formal proof demonstration in "YRI_QVGE" paper: "YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF : a framework for verifying SQL software correctness properties of [gui] software at runtime"; ([HTTPS://WWW.ZENODO.ORG/RECORDS/13232567](https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567)) [1d]

Klaus is never clear–minded in terms of being humble because he even insulted myself in 1 of his email that I received at my email–address: "Yerith.Xavier@gmail.com".

MAY be because of his friendship, undeclared at the time I was under supervision of JAN PELESKA–cuon.

KLAUS havelund is part of the group of people who have been trying to cover myself with in-competencies by using my research-work results without mentioning my names or anything about source of their work.

FOR instance I have never at time seen a "FLEX–BISON" parser written by PELESKA or KLAUS havelund when I finished my compiler–translator [\[YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP\]](#).

Let's observe what comes up in coming years from both deceptive white teacher–professors.

ACADEMIA world worldwide contactS |

STARTUP YECEFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE)

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY

[DEC. 2023 – "November 23, 2025"]

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2023]

[OCT. 2002 – JUL. 2007]

[Contacts with Academia in NORTH-AMERICA — Continued – 1]

o CONTACTS with Academia in NORTH-AMERICA:

1. Christopher-NGOSONG (MCGill, MCGill University
QUEBEC, CANADA (<https://www.mcgill.ca>) ["2012" – onward]

THIS guja came visit personally myself in my sublet basement apartment in MARKHAM-ontario around end of year 2012 as I was finishing my sabbatical-year-Internship with "J9-Java Just-IN-Time Compilation TEAM of VIJAY Sundaresan", at, IBM Toronto Software Laboratory (<https://www.ibm.ca>).

THIS male-female boy from BUEA-mutengene was sent to myself by an uncle paternal called "David Demo NOUNDOU", coming for a postdoctoral research stay in Canada after graduating his doctorate in agricultural studies from Germany.

I invited him to oversee my project in Yaounde for a small research institute combined with a technological entrepreneurship project after we had a dinner at a whittist-canadian Soccer-MMA-grill Bar somewhere in Markham, ON, Canada.

HE even manifested interest in co-creating this research technological institute by participating both in research & teaching as I can remember since we didn't communicate much after year 2012 together (NGOSONGK@yahoo.com).

"I could observe on the website of the University of BUEA (<https://>) lastly (2024) that HE became department chief for agricultural sciences. "

2. Dr.-B.Sc. Rodrigue Wankap Emmanuel MOGO—assassin (Rennes University,
FRANCE—assassin (<https://www.>)) ["2021" – onward]

THIS family MOGO where I could try to be investigated and cured for following diseases in their mansionian Hospital Clinic BUILDING in DLA-05 ème cité-des-palmiers;

- Disruption of well-function of my whole left leg after a fall on ground due to trying to send a small stone far away with my right hand;

A culprit-MD-anesthesiologist-trauma hired by YVES-MOGO, senior brother of my secondary school—ALFRED-Saker mate-colleague Assassin-WANKAP comes and tells me after around 30-minutes auscultation that MY left leg must be open-operated.

[I said I will think about this trying-to-open my nerves twice; THEN I DISAPPEAR from this assassination-begger-online MD-owona-rdpc-cpd.m-assassin funded Clinic.]

CANAL+ (<https://www.canalhorizon.com>) in France employs Rodrigue & YVES-mogo senior brother MD-assassin in HEXAGONE-assassin-slave-for-boyard & other TV-scam programs; EVEN sensual payments-only-viewing.

SISTER GHISLAINE-MD-mogo is kind-of CHRISTIAN-eyoum-rotarian-club in USA; Last news in MARYLAND-MA, a psy; IN cameroon she could get her secondary-school-final-certificate BAccalaureat via a payment to a certain deceased minister JOSEPH-owona-kono !

- HYPERGLYCEMIA because of not begin knowledgeable that CHRISTIAN-eyoum has tried to put into my blood via forced-in-taken pills and forced-in-taken injections;

The lady that is supposed to be a diabetes specialist medical doctor kind-of [EYOUM-christian-murderer] and that I don't remember names and / or whatsoever credentials; SHE gives myself insulin such at a high level that I stopped taking this promptly after 1 week, because I COULD sense that I DON'T HAVE ANY DIABETES !

3. Béatrice (IUT-Douala, University of Douala
Littoral Region, Cameroon (<https://www.>)) ["2025" – onward]

THIS super lady from my Grand-father neighborhood in Douala-NEW DEÏDO, is a professor at the Institute of Technology of the University of Douala since age 40 years old with a Doctorate-Ph.D. degree from China as I have heard from our common neighborhood.

HER husband that I have never met personally could help me with information on how to trace a prototype for YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET; As HE owns a super-chain of eye glasses from his China originating venture "BioLUXE".

ACADEMIA world worldwide contactS |

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 UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY

[DEC. 2023 – "CURRENTLY"]
 [Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2023]
 [OCT. 2002 – JUL. 2007]

[Contacts with Corruptible–NON-SENse–ACADEMIA]◦ **CONTACTS with Corruptible–NON-SENse–ACADEMIA:**

1. **MASTER–of–applied–science HYPOLithe–cuon-pd-TEKEU (IUC – INstitut UNIVERSitaire de la COTE, DOUALA (<https://www.myiuc.cm>), littoral REGION, CAMEROON)**

THIS megere-bamile tribe ROSE–sangnou, a genitor of my physical being went on to recommend myself to apply for a position at so called canadian–cooperation–institution IÛC.

I was 1st told I COULD earn "500 000 Xaf"; AFTER a prompt and passed successfully interview; WITHOUT any indication that I AM A socalled DR.–ING;

hypolithe–tekeu–pd–racist–tribal–bamileke–dschang–idiot offers myself "200 000 Xaf".

I COULD NOT say no period.

THIS idiot even put myself under a so–called professional master of engineering from his dirty and prostitution institute IÛC. JUNIOR–mbe; THIS junior–mbe–fosso is now as far I COULD OBServe in internet–world in socalled pragmatic-quebec-cuon-land-freedom–CANADA.

TODAY I can say that it is pretty much impossible for such a low–class institution to employ an ivy–level league USA graduate university ! GUIMEZAP himself culprit with all his children couldn't even get a doctorate degree outside of DSCHANG–village where they originate from in the OUEST.

This C.P.D.M–rosicrucian–sone institution also tries to destroy life of people together with SHANDA–tonme jean-claude of village BANGOU–batchingou in OUEST.

ACADEMIA world worldwide contactS |

STARTUP YECEFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE)
 UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA
 UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2023]
 [OCT. 2002 – JUL. 2007]

[Contacts with Cameroon-ACADEMIA]◦ **CONTACTS with Cameroon Academia:**

1. **PROFESSOR thomas ndié djotio** (École Nationale Supérieure Polytechnique de Yaoundé - ENSPY (<https://www.polytechnique.cm>), CENTER REGION, CAMEROON)

This older than [myself] so called 'maître de conférence', English as "associate professor", was very kind to receive myself and to let me give him a short presentation of my professional and academic projects as "Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering (Dr.-Ing.) (UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)":

- I. [YRI_QVGE \(https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481\)](https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481) [24.24] June 2022 – currently
- II. [YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM \(https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/\)](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/) [?] MAR. 2015 – currently

I could identify "[Prof. Dr.-Eng. THOMAS Djotio Ndié-Idiot]" through his online website located at: "<https://sites.google.com/tdjotio>". I could also see his resume-online (~~<https://sites.google.com/tdjotio>~~) that was asserting and presenting him as doctor-of-engineering graduated from the "École-polytechnique-de-yaoundé" in year "2008".

ALL this afore mentioned websites were canceled by "THOMAS ndié djotio" it seems; For a more official resume (https://polytechnique.cm/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/Biographie_Djotio-Ndie-Thomas.pdf).

HE 1st contested that I was a doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering because I didn't at that time of year 2022 asked for an official graduate transcript from the [UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, in Waterloo (Ontario, Canada)].

I could then obtain free-of-charge from "MRS. Nancy HEIDE" (nheide@uwaterloo.ca), at time of request As "Director of Student Services OF THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO", a certificate via electronic mail (Email) at my own request of "Official Graduate Transcript" that normally is charged \$20 CAD. I even had "Prof. Dr.-Eng. THOMAS Djotio Ndié" copied-conform (cc) to my email since I am trying to get hired by "École-polytechnique-de-yaoundé".

I CANNOT REMEMBER have failed any examination my entire candidacy of Doctor Ph.D., since I successfully graduated with "88%" as "Doctor-Ph.D. in electrical & computer Engineering (Dr.-Ing.)" on "December 20th, 2011"; with THESIS title:

["Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software" \[34\]](#)

I have appealed that I HAVE BEEN rejected from my [PhD research seminar] on "March 10th, 2015" by PATRICK lam that said 3 years later to myself when I was back in Canada to resign my canadian shit-citizenship, He didn't recall that he could foresee results from my program as pre-defined after we setup the PH.D. research seminar, together with my "PhD comprehensive examination committee members":

- A professor of age greater than 70 years old was the rapporteur:
- Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D. Email: olhotak@cs.uwaterloo.ca
- Derek Rayside, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (P.Eng., Ontario) Email: drayside@uwaterloo.ca
- Patrick Lam, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (P.Eng., Ontario) Email: p23lam@uwaterloo.ca
- Lin Tan, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (P.Eng., Ontario) Email: lintan@purdue.edu

THE Ph.D. Dissertation Defense occurred in "January 2015" at PLG. IT was successfully approved by other following people among others:

["Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM" \[34\]](#)

1. Peter Alan Burh, Ph.D. Alias ~~FABRICE siemeni-wilfried remp-canadian-armed-forces~~ Email: pabuhr@uwaterloo.ca
2. * Vijay Ganesh, Ph.D. Email: vganesh@gatech.edu
3. * Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D. Email: olhotak@uwaterloo.ca
4. * Patrick Lam, Ph.D. Email: p23lam@uwaterloo.ca
5. Magnus Madsen, Ph.D. Email: magnusm@cs.au.dk

ALL professors before mentioned marked with a "*" sign are collaborators in this project. Others approver were reviewers and were both ("Magnus, and Peter") present !

ACADEMIA world worldwide contactS |

STARTUP YECEFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE)

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[Contacts with Cameroon-ACADEMIA]

o CONTACTS with Cameroon Academia:

1. PROFESSOR maïgari-idiot-secessionist (Former director, Cameroon-consulate in BRussels-belgium (<https://>),
Center Region, Cameroon) [Around "March-April 2015"]

2. PROFESSOR yves emvudu-cuon (INFORMATION SYSTEMS DIRECTOR deceased by now, Higher Education Ministry in Yaounde (<https://>),
Center Region, Cameroon) [Around "August 2015"]

THIS idiot didn't even counseled me properly about the educational system employed in Cameroonian UNIVERSITIES. HE didn't even inquired on either my passed qualifications nor my credential documents; Since with his position, we could together query all required documents from an official position research in high education ministry for me.

HE just sent me to École Normale Supérieure so to meet a professor for MATHEMATICS that I forgot names and qualifications since I could never see him at ENS-yaounde.

THE other professor for mathematics I was supposed to meet, even though I AM foremost a computing engineer and developer was a MATHEMATICS professor at École Nationale Supérieure POLYTECHNIQUE de YAOUNDE. THIS man that seemed very kind but dangerous just gave me advise to put my publications of '<https://www.archive.org>'. "THIS older man than Yves-emvudu was a doctor from WEST-germany", whereas "YVES-emvudu was doctor from east-germany" !!!

ALSO, I was told by EMVUDU to apply for a teaching assistant position at SIANTOU-supérieur, and also Congo-CAMEROUN science university in a remote area of Cameroon I even don't remember the name.

"Merci au fainéant de Tonme de ne plus repasser où j'entre sur cette terre !!!"

[IT is exactly because of my "assassin-uncle-paternal-Laurent-TCHANDEU" that I went o search and encounter "YVES emvudu" of SÉCRÉTARIAT D'ÉTAT A LA DEFENSE (sed) without knowing he might create a procedure to destroy me mentally because it might be inappropriate for a criminal like LAURENT to act directly on my body because of the blood-genetic-connection-with-his-own-kids !!!]

3. PROFESSOR bertin nyemb (École Normale Supérieure de Yaoundé – ENSY (<https://>),
Center Region, Cameroon) [Around "May 2022"]

THIS very not humble professor for german language and cultural-ism is a very humble and not contestative person because he has always been trying to hijack myself as a member of DGRE.

I SUSPECT this idiot spy of biya-regime to have even sent false opinions of myself to german authorities at the UNIVERSITY-racist OF BREMEN after I MET HIM once again here in Yaounde in year 2022 !

SO this man of "Bassa"-tribe is at least 3 times recidivist in trying to check what makes someone like myself an ignorant by psychiatric methods like the ones [EYOUN-rotarian-CHRISTIAN] has been trying together with PR. DR. shanda-tonme, and EMVUDU.

I acknowledged at his request to be member of his stupid [Rotarian] organization so called PROvac ("PROMOTION des valeurs au Cameroun").

THIS has been more than 22 months now, he has never replied to any message about trying to computerized his membership list and cards using my humble open-source software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.

ACADEMIA world worldwide contactS |

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[Contacts with Cameroon–ACADEMIA]

o CONTACTS with Cameroon Academia:

1. PROFESSOR clementin tayou djameni (UNIVERSITY OF DSCHANG (<https://>), WEST REGION, CAMEROON) [Around "September 2011", then around "September 2015]

“ THIS sample ignorant on ”algorithms complexity and concurrency computations on multi-computers” that I know because my uncle THEODORE wandji ngongang sent me to him while he was visiting EUROPE (FRANCE, then GERMANY); while I was still an undergraduate student at the ”ELITE-UNIVERSITÄT-BREMEN” (<https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de>); So I will have connections in ACADEMIA in my home country while I AM STILL outside of CAMEROON.“

“I met, see, and even sleep beside him twice – 1st time in our student apartment in Bremen where he stayed 4 days – Then in Rennes–FRANCE in ”2004” when he visited ”GRENOBLE laboratory” with PROFESSOR tchindo–gilbert.“

“I tried to contact him again in "September–2011" because I HEARD from ”diplom–informatiker marcellin tally”, cousin of mine, that I COULD apply already for a position as "assistant professor in CAMEROON" with a "DIPLOM–INFORMATIKER DEGREE, ABBREVIATED (DIPL.–INF.) (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)[?] " like our common age–class colleague ”diplom–informatiker oscar mourbare” from Ngaoundere–Cameroon. [Dr.–Ing. DAYANG Paul] is also from university of bremen and also our common cohort in computer science in CS–Bremen (<https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de>). “

“HE has never answered anymore any emails or telephone calls while I was in Cameroon ! “

2. PROFESSOR kolyang (University of MAROUA (<https://www.univ-maroua.cm/fr/node/76>), FAR NORTH REGION, CAMEROON) [”Around December 2015”]

“ I remember greeting him when entering an elevator as he was visiting Bremen while I was in my undergraduate level of education in Computer Science at the UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN in Germany where HE Graduated several years in front of myself.“

“HE didn’t answered at all and I felt he is not very comfortable with young cameroonian studying in BREMEN.“

“KOLYANG was then a DOKTOR–INGENIEUR (Dr.–Ing.), that could graduate from BREMEN with PROFESSOR BERND KRIEG BRÜCKNER (BKB) as DOKTOR-VATER (main principal PhD advisor).“

“Professor JAN peleska–cuon said I shall contact him in year 2016 when I was looking for a research position back in Cameroon 1st time, before returning into CANADA–shit to resign a CANDIAN–idiot–citizenship I acquired because I needed to travel via Europe without visa request at GERMAN embassy. I could succeed to send him an email at an email–address received from PELESKA–cuon, that I don’t remember; BUT I never got a return reply message at all.“

“WITH idiot–joseph–djoumessi that invited myself in his christian–rosicrucian–peg congregation CMCI–obili (<https://>); I heard from someone that was in academia at the UNIVERSITY OF YAOUNDE 1 that KOLYANG was not anymore in academia for working on research, But KOLYANG was doing agriculture !!! “

1. THE university of waterloo, from a black African descendant perspective, as a student and employee, & High Qualified Person from GERMANY. |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Oct. 2009 – "November 23, 2025"]

[*Incompetent "doctoral Ph.D. program coordinator as a Master of Science (M.Sc.)" Sarah landy,*

*Color of origin payments,
non observance of international academic conventions and laws criminal,
racial segregative police of canada–waterloo–ontario,
DEREK rayside idiot,
INCOMPETENT ACADEMIC PEOPLE IN ECE (ELECTRICAL & COMPUTER ENGINEERING),
racial systemic segregation]*

- I. ★ I Was very positively surprised to receive as POST-doctoral advisor, additionally to PATRICK lam; *An Ivy-league Stanford graduate called Dr. Vijay Ganesh* (<https://www.stanford.edu>).
- II. I came to this super MIT-graduate "*Patrick Lam, Ph.D.* (<https://www.patricklam.ca>)" because HE was from *Ivy-league–Massachusetts Institute of TEchnology MIT* (<https://www.csail.mit.edu>).
- III. *Asian-Vietnamese advisor Dr. of Engineering PATRICK lam* (<https://patricklam.ca>) from "*Massachusetts Institute of Technology (M.I.T* (<https://csail.mit.edu>), MA, USA)" :

Here are certain things done for myself both, academically and professionally, by PATRICK lam :

1. *I spent 6 years under supervision of PATRICK-idiot-lam,* (<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=36fAXB4AAAAJ&hl=en>) *without having at least 1 scientific paper published under his supervision anywhere in my visible and observable internet WORLD !*

[!!! I got this ([FSE–soqua 2006]) with only 2 years at THE university–racist-of-bremen.de !!!]

"THIS is the only time "PELESKA et al." could attend such a high-prestigious class–A conference in NORTH america of mine." (https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp/jp_papers_e.html#publications)

2. [JON EYOLFSON], an idiot that worked for PATRICK-lam as a MASTER student (M.ASC.) and then as a PH.D. candidate, **COULD COPY MY WORK** more intelligently & silently, and even 'EHHH' got a high paid position as an "**ASSISTANT PROFESSOR (teaching stream)**"; after 4 years at ~~UGLA~~–with–~~HARRY-XU~~ (<https://web.cs.ucla.edu/~harryxu>) as Postdoctoral fellow; AT THE ece–department OF **THE UNIVERSITY OF TORONTO** (<https://discover.research.utoronto.ca/12279–alexie–tcheuyap>), ontario, canada.
3. *Patrick recommended myself to IBM Toronto Software Lab manager "Dr. MARCEL mitran" after I told him I was looking for an internship just after my PhD COMPREHENSIVE EXAMINATION[32]; Before returning to University of Waterloo, ON.*
4. *Professor PATRICK lam gave myself a lot of presentation skills attitudes that I can today not all of them remember.*
5. Patrick sent me to several research academical venues through my doctoral Ph.D. studies at the University of Waterloo, ON:
- "*First Summer School on Formal Techniques*" (<https://fm.csl.sri.com/SSFT11/index.shtml>) (2011);
 - *MITACS Ontario* (2012);
 - *PLDI – Programming Language Design and Implementation* (2009);
 - *IBM CASCON – IBM Centre for Advanced Studies Conference* (2010);
 - *ICSE – International Conference On Software Engineering* (2012).
6. Patrick gave myself 1st hand detailed explanations on static dataflow analysis à la "Gary A. kildall : *A unified approach to global program optimization* (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)" with help of his slides from *McGill University* (<https://www.mcgill.ca>).
7. *Professor PATRICK lam is the only one that taught me that I really need to keep my LaTeX document code straight and maxed 80 lines.*
8. *Professor PATRICK lam is the only one that taught me that I really need to keep reading papers as long as I don't really master them, before coming back to talk to him !*
9. *Professor PATRICK lam is the only one that taught me that I really need to dig very deep into researching and probing an idea before there is an excellent outcome out of it: THIS IS WHAT I APPLIED TO get my 1st implementation of my doctoral dissertation work YERITH–SAINT !*
10. Patrick gave me hints about contributing to open source projects by modifying their code source and reuse it for my research; I for instance applied this when creating Computer–Aided Software Engineering (CASE) tool *YERITH_QVGE*.
11. *PATRICK lam is also the one that permitted for myself to gain a TEACHING EXPERIENCE at the UNI–racist of Waterloo : I AM ALWAYS grateful to him for this great Experience at the UNIVERSITY–racist of WATERLOO in Ontarian CANADA.*
12. [PERSONALLY I am planing to pay him some money from my soft- and hard-ware revenue in the future.]

1. THE university of waterloo, from a black African descendant perspective, as a student and employee, & High Qualified Person from GERMANY. |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Oct. 2009 – "November 23, 2025"]

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racial systemic segregation]*

- I. Asian-Vietnamese advisor Dr. of Engineering PATRICK lam (<https://patricklam.ca>) from "Massachusetts Institute of Technology (M.I.T (<https://csail.mit.edu>), MA, USA)" :

Here are certain things done for myself both, academically and professionally, by PATRICK lam:

13. "PATRICK lam has never done a "program analysis by himself" as far as I have been working with either as his research assistant or as a scholar that could see this somewhere in a world. "

"They (PATRICK and FELIX) even attempted to remove my name from git repository (<https://>) history when "Divam Jain" left and PATRICK said to FELIX-fang to continue that research WITH me also as a supervisor under PATRICK-lam."

"AS far as I am knowledgeable, scientific conference and / or whatsoever papers that stem "from research work of Divam Jain", that I see as plagiarism since my name as a co–author has never been written, are existent because I am the only originator of this work; as a supervisor of DIVAM jain, at the beginning of his "Master of Mathematics (M.Math.)"; and this at request of dear PATRICK lam":

"Deceased idiot former dean of engineering "PEARL sullivan", [that I went to confront with facts about these plagiarisms], Sent by a black–idiot police officer from UWATERLOO racial–police services; Sent a british giant muscular idiot white–police–officer to arrest me illegally and very violently just at the ground level of the "Davis Centre BUILDING of racists." "

"BECAUSE i removed my clothes in front of surveillance digital cameras in a uw–office racial-police, Where the british–racist-police-from-scotland did tell me to sign papers that I DIDN'T EVEN had opportunity to read at all; THEY sent me in jail–custody to KITCHENER-waterloo criminal justice court. "

"Justice Crown attorney prosecutor DOMINIQUE KENNEDY" let all investigations done and concluded that I HAD NEVER ASSAULTED this idiot police white-british office that charged myself with 'ASSAULT TO POLICE OFFICER' ! "

"Justice Crown attorney prosecutor DOMINIQUE KENNEDY" told me she called "the office of THE president of the university of waterloo" to ask them to let myself defend my "Ph.D. degree dissertation"; BUT they told her with attorneys of law of the president of the university of waterloo: "What is a crown attorney doing in the office of president ?" "

"Justice Crown attorney prosecutor DOMINIQUE KENNEDY" then on another did tell me that someone from the office of the president-idiot–racist of the university of waterloo; said that they have certain attitudes that are based on their local culture!

Incompetent "doctoral Ph.D. program coordinator as a Master of Science (M.Sc.)" Sarah landy

went on to harass the university of waterloo police ; ESPECIALLY (ambinns@uwpolice.ca); to say Like a HE-girl–pom–pom–shit that: "THIS black gay guy is so huge that he must be destroyed mentally !!!

this kind of race–sarah–landy MUST never be admitted anywhere else in this black world other than her anus....zizi.

[THIS happened in year 2018 as I WENT TO DESTROY my so-called—white-oblivier canadian–CACA–shit—citizenship–pegg–kkk.]

"I AM THE one who told to MRS. cuon-idiot–racist–white–quebec–tabawec—"Justice Crown attorney prosecutor DOMINIQUE KENNEDY", that THIS IS CALLED discrimination !"

- a. "Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints" (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)

I. **Formal Training for occupying teaching positions** |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

[**TEACHING ASSISTANT training;**
CUT-1 - Certificate in University Teaching 1]

[Summary-PAGES]

1. **Training in ECE Department (Electrical & Computer Engineering Department):**

Before starting my 1st formal appointment as a teaching assistant at the University of Waterloo, ON, CANADA; In year 2009, I received a group training for graduate students of the ECE (Electrical & Computer Engineering Department).

2. **Passed QUALIFICATION interview to teach OBJECT-ORIENTED PROGRAMMING WITH JAVA:**

I SUCCESSFULLY passed a presentation slides lecture for qualification interviews OF 30 minutes added with "Q&A - Questions & Answers" session; to teach Object-Oriented Java Programming to 1st year students at THE university of Waterloo in year 2012.

NEVERTHELESS, I was not chosen as THE committee said: I QUOTE THEM: "Xavier might no be able to manage this very young age students in a class of 100 or more." I WAS AGED MYSELF 29 years old in year 2012 when this happened ! THX TO PATRICK-IDIOT-LAM

PATRICK-IDIOT-LAM is only 4 years older than myself. (<https://www.patricklam.ca>)

IT seems PATRICK and lin-tan-AGED-exactly as myself were trying to avoid a so-called-negger at a high paid position at UNIVERSITY-OF-WATERLOO. "Lin tan" is born 1983 like Xavier noumbissi NOUNDOU ! (<https://cs.purdue.edu/lintan>)

THE class was given at the end to a seasoned professor named **SEBATIAN FISCHMEISTER** (<https://ece.uwaterloo.ca/~sfischme>), that leads the **Embedded Research Group in ECE** (<https://ece.uwaterloo.ca/~sfischme>).

3. **This was optional. CUT-1; Certificate in University Teaching – 1:**

"THE university of waterloo in ontario, Canada"; offers a formal training program in 4 certificates to qualify graduate students and / or whatsoever qualified persons for teaching at a UNIVERSITY.

I attended the level 1 certificate in 2010, but didn't pursue the last 3 levels because I felt I couldn't perform as fast as I wanted my doctoral research due to the high level of academic requirements due by researching in the "static code program analysis" area of research; At **WatForm (WATERLOO FORMAL METHODS group research)** (<https://watform.uwaterloo.ca>); led by "Prof. Dr. JOE atlee of the CS (Computer Science) Department" (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~jmatlee>).

AFTER my free registration, at my own request and without asking PATRICK-idiot-lam; and attendance of all 1st level courses at "DAVEN-PORT library on main (200 UNIVERSITY AVENUE WEST) campus" of the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, I notice IT would be impossible to myself to finish my research in due time without issues with my doctoral advisor !!!

WE were around 10 in a sumptuous and luxurious carpeted room at kind of 3rd level in the main building !

ESPECIALLY added to the fact I WAS EARNING SUCH A LOW 999-CAD, so I HAD to TA-teaching assisting PATRICK lam.

THAT'S why I resigned.

[I EVEN feared PATRICK lam was trying to make myself sick because of the amount of stipend I HAD, compared to other students like JON eyolfson who also add other stipend from NSREC-CANADA !!!]

"I was under supervision of my doctoral Ph.D advisor Dr.-Ph.D. of Engineering PATRICK lam".

I. Competencies Acquired and Learned as a TEACHER-PROFESSOR |

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

[TEACHING ASSISTANT training]

- o SUMMARY of given-co-taught courses: '2' undergraduate ("Bachelor") level courses.
- o Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465)
 1. Creating a "JUnit 4-tutorial" (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052444/>) [14] and got it reviewed by PATRICK LAM; THIS is not a task PATRICK as instructor asked me to perform; I did this in my free time and put it as sample training material for students. – **"(+)
Professor task level"**
 2. GOING in class to teach JUnit for exercise session – **"(+)
Professor task level"**
 3. Creating SAMPLE solutions to assignments – **"(+)
Professor task level"**
 4. MARKING ASSIGNMENT à la patrick lam – **"(+)
Professor task level"**
I felt very improved for my teaching software technical testing skills.
- o Programming for Performance (ECE 459)
 1. **TAKING some time in my time of research for my ["PH.D. in electrical & Computer ENGINEERING"] to receive students visit at my office; and teach them what they couldn't understand either in class, and / or for the course material ! – **"(+)
Professor task level"****

" Since my PH.D.-advisor patrick was the Director of Software Engineering study programs, I Think he thought I could replace him as a lecturer and he wanted to test these skills."
 2. "Really I didn't much like this course as taught by PATRICK because it was more a kind of programming course that wasn't very solid in mathematical and engineering foundations; Except for theories and histories on processor speed "MOORE-law" expansion and development ! "

"THIS was more to gain money because I was only earning \$999 Cad as a "master of science, PH.D. candidate" under supervision PATRICK-lam; coming from a middle level-paid good money position."

I. Competencies Acquired and Learned as a TEACHER-PROFESSOR |

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Jan. 2012 – 10 MARCH 2015]

[TEACHING ASSISTANT training]

◦ SUMMARY of given-co-taught courses: '3' undergraduate ("Bachelor") level courses; '2' graduate ("Master", "PhD", "Ph.D.") level courses.

◦ Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465)

1. Because of my resignation act in front of all committee members of my doctoral Ph.D. comprehensive examination and DISSERTATION COMMITTEE members;
I resigned !

◦ Compilers (ECE 351)

1. I did during my time in BREMEN, a course called ("Übersetzer GENERIERUNG mit LEX und YACC") that could be translated in English-white: "Compiler / TRanslator GENERation with LEX & YACc".
2. Creating Python scripts to query, compile and build; and check results of computer programs as assigned for students in ECE 351 class of racist DEREK-GAYSIDE.

◦ * GRADUATE (MENG, MASC, PHD) LEVEL COURSE – METHODS AND TOOLS FOR SOFTWARE ENGINEERING (ECE 650)

1. I went to classes like students to assist idiot-Igor-IVKOVIC that required this visitation of classes for me. – "(*) Professor task level"

"deceased NOVEMBER 2021 igor idiot-ivkovic wasn't not even capable of understanding what he taught in front of students professional himself. THAT'S why he required my presence in classes so I will help him better ! "

"IT Means IGOR-ivkovic shalln't have gain more "payment cheques" than myself because it seemed to me I would do more teaching than he did."

◦ Computer Networks (ECE 428)

1. "Creating Python scripts to query, compile and build; and check results of computer client-server programs as assigned for students class of racist-idiot Mahesh-Rayside."

◦ * GRADUATE (MENG, MASC, PHD) LEVEL COURSE – FOUNDATIONS OF SOFTWARE ENGINEERING (ECE 651)

1. "Learned on the grasp theories and practices of software quality metrics and tools so to teach them to students. IGOR ivkovic, the deceased idiot-instructor wasn't even capable himself of anything." – "(*) Professor task level"

◦ [C++ Laboratory (ECE 250)]

1. Working with "iranian in north-america", as being a black-afro-descendant is not recommended at ALL !

"JON eyolfson is a burglar incompetent GUJA that is not even capable of respecting an agreement of 2-weeks replacement for his office mate."

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (TEACHING ASSISTANT — UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

- I. **Duties completed by Teaching Assistant [Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering (Dr.-Ing.)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou |**
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Sep. 2012 – Apr. 2015]
- 1.) [SUMMARY of student research-teaching advisory work both "autonomously" and, from my PH.D-advisor PATRICK].
 - 2.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of INSTRUCTOR "MAHESH rayside-idiot":**
 - o **Computer Networks (ECE 428)** SPRING term (Jan.-Apr.) "2013"
 "THIS ignorant professor couldn't be even capable of clearly defining programming assignments, AS I had to tweak the Python code for automatically correct student code source from Gitlab-repositories created by a so called [PATRICK-lam]."
 [THIS ignorant didn't even know I was a perfect computer software developer since age 18 in Cameroon; as demonstrated by my professional record of employment in GERMANY that is at least trice more developed technologically than idiot CANADA.]
 - 3.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of instructor "Derek rayside-idiot":**
 - o **Compilers (ECE 351)** FALL term (Sep.-Dec.) "2012"
 "THIS idiot from massachusetts-gay institute of technology cannot even define what is mathematical relation WITHOUT saying: I quote him: 'a relation is like a table'... (<https://csail.mit.edu/sdg>)
 "I was kind of surprise that we MUST had to code source code to correct programmings assignments as "styles of programming for instance, comments, etc," MUST be also marked and more importantly advised, Especially from a performance confirmed seasoned software developer as myself: DR.-PH.D. of ENGINEERING XAVIER noumbissi noundou. (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) "
 "I was very surprised to see a [culprit called MATTHEW MA] that was Master of Applied Science of DEREK, COMING to myself with his mother and offer me "\$400 CAD so to code for his MASTER PROJECT in Computer Software Engineering from derek." "
 "Thinking that derek went to pay around \$30 000—CAD to MATHGENEALOGY.ORG, (<https://mathgenealogy.org>) so my free registration from "[PATRICK] AND rinard-martin; (<https://csail.mit.edu/~rinard>)" from 'PH.D.' onto 'ABD' be changed without any formal justification as specified [[here];] DEREK-GAYSIDE is only someone that hijacked to get a degree from renowned MIT." "
 - 4.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of instructor "LADAN":**
 - o **[C++ LABORATORY (ECE 250)]** FALL term (Sep.-Dec.) "2014"
 "THIS in german so called 'HURE'-prostitute (<https://Wikipedia.org>) Declares be a professor for software system.
 I cannot testify this as "her student MOHAMMAD HAMDAQA" was so ignorant and had a tremendous background in business but knew nothing on software system at all ! "
 "I spent hours talking to ladan via her idiot student from JORDAM-kingdom that seems to have even acquired a faculty position at so called "ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE MONTREAL-qc-chien-tabawak-satan" (<https://www.polymtl.ca>) "
 - 5.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of instructor "deceased-Igor Ivkovic-idiot":**
 - o * GRADUATE (MENG, MASC, PHD) LEVEL COURSE – METHODS AND TOOLS FOR SOFTWARE ENGINEERING (ECE 650) FALL term (Sep.-Dec.) "2013"
 1. I went to classes like students to assist idiot-Igor-IVKOVIC that required this visitation of classes for me. – "(*) Professor task level"
 "deceased NOVEMBER 2021 igor idiot-ivkovic wasn't not even capable of understanding what he taught in front of students professional himself. THAT'S why he required my presence in classes so I will help him better ! "
 "IT Means IGOR-ivkovic shalln't have gain more "payment cheques" than myself because it seemed to me I would do more teaching than he did."
 o * GRADUATE (MENG, MASC, PHD) LEVEL COURSE – FOUNDATIONS OF SOFTWARE ENGINEERING (ECE 651) SPRING term (Jan.-Apr.) "2013"
 1. "Learned on the grasp theories and practices of software quality metrics and tools so to teach them to students. IGOR ivkovic, the deceased idiot-instructor wasn't even capable himself of anything." – "(*) Professor task level"
 - 6.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of instructors "Patrick LAM", and "LIN tan":**
 - o **Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465)** SPRING term (Jan.-Apr.) "2015"
- II. **Duties completed by Teaching Assistant [Diplom-Informatiker (Dipl.-Inf.)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou |**
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]
- 1.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of instructor "Patrick LAM":**
 - o **Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465)** SPRING term (Jan.-Apr.) "2010"
 "I AM THE one that creates the only sample solution to midterms. PATRICK is not very good at kind of creating technical solutions based on graph-theoretical foundations as for instance when creating equivalence class based test sequences solutions." — 📄
 "Sample TESTING material I Created." (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052444/>) [14]
 - o **Programming for Performance (ECE 459)** SPRING term (Jan.-Apr.) "2011"
 I co-create with other teaching assistants such as [JON-eyolfson] solutions for assignments and / or midterms exams.
 I also receive students during predefined weekly time frame so to help them out with understanding of learning courses material.

1. CO-teach and CO-assign, & Co-mark Assignments for Graduate and Undergraduate Computer (Software) Engineering Students (ECE Department) |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [OCT. 2009 – APR. 2015]

[PROOF READING,
static code dataflow analysis,
SCALA,
JAVA, C++, *JUnit* testing,
research ideas talks and development,
computer programming teaching]

[Summary-PAGES]

I. Students from the University of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA I helped during my stay at the University of Waterloo, ON:

1. ["Matthew Ming Ma, M.ASc., Mechatronics, Engineering":]

- o How to configure a "developer" JAVA virtual machine under Ubuntu LINUX;
- o "I gave him contextual help in writing JAVA code for his Master of Applied Science project, under supervision of Derek Rayside".
- o HE then got a so called, at "**APPLE INC. LTD.**" (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>) , **software in test developer** (<https://www.apple.com/jobs>) job;

That is why even a "**WIFI-connection**" to a laptop doesn't work with APPLE phones as I COULD experience myself in CAMEROON (a white phone paid for \$120 CAD).

2. ["DR. JON eyolfson, Ph.D. in Electrical & Computer Engineering":] (<https://www.jeyolfson.com>)

- o How to use efficiently and effectively double pointers in C++ function / method calling argument parameters;
- o "I gave him my full LaTeX doctoral Ph.D. thesis (ECE calls this a research proposal) document for helping him out with a template at his own request".

3. "Dr. Vajih MONTAGHAMI, Ph.D., Electrical & Computer Engineering":

- o Thorough discussions and talks about his research ideas and on computer programming related topics (mostly on the "Watform LAB white-board").

4. "Divam Jain, M.Math., Computer Science", from Ph.D.-advisor of mine Dr. of Engineering "Patrick LAM":

- o Gave "DIVAM" sample code of my sample projects in JAVA about static code dataflow analysis à la "Gary A. Kildall : A **unified approach to global program optimization** (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)"; As opposed for instance to static code dataflow analysis " à la **IFDS (Interprocedural, Finite, Distributive, Subset)** (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Inter-procedural-data-flow-analysis-with-IFDS-IDE-Bodden/a3f7557fe673ff0711e9049cf5ece8b02a51f7f1>)" from "**THOMAS-reps at the university of wisconsin-madison**" (<https://www.grammatech.com>) .

IBM provides WALA as library for working with IFDS framework. (<https://research.ibm.com/publications/program-analysis-using-wala>)

- o Introduction and supervision on how to use **SOOT** (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>) ;
- o Brief discussions and talks on using static dataflow analysis for JUNIT test case generation;
- o Declared "Master of Mathematics" title at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO: "**Detecting Test Clones with Static Analysis**" (<https://hdl.handle.net/10012/7943>).
- o FOLLOWING plagiary by [zheng FELIX fang] and [PATRICK lam] originate from this seminal initial work where I contributed partly in code source writing:

A) "**Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints**" (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)

5. "zheng FELIX fang, M.ASc., Electrical & Computer Engineering", from Ph.D.-advisor of mine Dr. of Engineering "Patrick LAM":

- o Overview of ["Divam Jain's"] previous work on SOOT and static dataflow analysis for generating JUNIT test cases.
- o Brief discussions and talks on using static dataflow analysis for generating JUNIT test cases.;
- o "Declared MASTER OF APPLIED SCIENCE title" at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO: "**Test Clone Detection via Assertion Fingerprints**" (<https://hdl.handle.net/10012/8831>);
- o FANG then got a position at MICROSOFT corporation in SEATTLE.
- o [1 scientific conference paper came out of this supervision-advising :]
 - a.) "**Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints**" (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)

1. HELPIng black–descendant students from the UNIVERSITY of waterloo–racist–on |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Oct. 2009 – apr. 2015]

I. *Students from the University of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA I helped during my stay at the University of Waterloo, ON:*

1. **"Amirhossein Vakili, Ph.D., Computer Science":** (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~avakili>)
 - o How to use MAKE;
 - o static dataflow analysis explanation.
 - o "1st at all functional programming with SCALA introduction".
2. **STUDENTS in cameroon association rowac. (<https://rowac.ca>) "JUST IN MY SPARE TIME, not at a position in university"**
 - o **We at ROWAC (formerly CCAKW (Camerroonian Community Association in Kw)); Have invited ambassador-pd-idiot of Cameroon in OTTAWA (ontario) during summer 2014 if my thoughts are exact. THIS was during the soccer tournament we organized.**
 - o I presented and gave out certain documents I wrote about computer web software security vulnerabilities protection; AND measures to protect documents and computer–laptop during, after 1 general meeting evening around 06 : 00 PM.
 - o AFTER graduating, and came back into canada to resign an idiot-canadian citizenship acquired for travel-without-visa-purpose-only to EUROPE; I then discovered that several members of ROWAC were secret–servicess-agent of my assassin of paternal uncle LAURENT-tchandeu, PleniPOTENTIARY–minister:
 - Dr. (M.Sc.) Vincent Nanga
 - Dr. (M.Sc.) Innocent Tchigio
 - Dr.-PHARM. (M.Sc.) CHEONGWA wandzi-cheongwa@yahoo.com
3. **"Godrick–chékété, Ph.D., French literature": "JUST IN MY SPARE TIME, not at a position in university"**
 - o I MET "Godrick–chékété" via "YAW boakye-agyeman, ph.d. student in recreational studies at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON CANADA";
 - o Help in FINDING HIS way after his divorce from his spouse from BENIN (house searching, car fixing, etc.);
 - o HELP in looking for a financial loan at a Canadian bank.
4. **"Eric Brefo–Mensah, Ph.D., Chemistry": "JUST IN MY SPARE TIME, not at a position in university"**
 - o I MET Eric brefo-mensah via "CHIWANZA-kasanga";
 - o Help in proof reading his Master Thesis LaTeX document before his final submission in "year 2018".
5. **Shirley Ddamba, "M.ASc. Civil Engineering": "JUST IN MY SPARE TIME, not at a position in university"**
 - o I MET SHIRLEY at a bible study at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON CANADA;
 - o Help in learning hands–on car driving in Ontario.
6. **Esther Lambert, "Ph.D., Geography, University of Toronto, 2017": "JUST IN MY SPARE TIME, not at a position in university"**
 - o I MET ESTHER while she was cashier at ZEHRS–churchill–street.
 - o Help in proof reading her Master thesis for the department of geography;
 - o Help in learning hands–on car driving in Ontario;
 - o ESTHER then pursue 1 year internship at ONTARIO green–belt institute; SHE then was admitted at the University of Toronto for "doctoral Ph.D. in GEOGRAPHY".

RESEARCH AND TEACHING ('PROFESSIONAL' TEACHING ASSISTANT – CONTINUED [2] - THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. CO-teach and CO-assign, & Co-mark Assignments for Graduate and Undergraduate Computer (Software) Engineering Students (ECE Department) | UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [OCT. 2009 – Apr. 2015]

I. *Professional Computer Engineers living in Germany I helped during my whole time at "UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, canada":*

1. "A paternal uncle Demo Noundou from Cameroon" (<https://www.ank-technologies.com>).

r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou" who at 1st was an illegal migrant worker idiot in GB–great britain, a junior brother of my late father and genitor "Théodore Nounbissi, B.Sc., Electrical & Computer Engineering"; was a student in Information Technology student at "TUHH — Technische Universität Hamburg–Harbug" (<https://www.tuhh.de>), and graduated from there with a "Bachelor of Sciences (B.Sc.)".

"Demo" then obtained a position as "PHP – JAVA Web Software Developer" at "Canon LTD.", based in Germany - Osnabrück !

AT least trice (3 times) a month, I will receive a phone call from Germany requesting software programming and / or database technical help from this GUJA.

Each time I could solve his issues until HE stopped calling around August 2014, when I became a CANADIAN citizen, and when himself *r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou"* went for a marital union with *r-"Astride Patibé"*; a nurse from Cameroon – Baham – BAFANG tribe.

r-"CÉLESTIN puene" is another (Food–processing) engineer from Cameroon that came to myself sent by "his natal village Babouantou" friend paternal uncle *r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou"* .

HE came saying he needed help in buying a mechanical truck from the USA for his brother in cameroon who possessed a road construction society in YDE. *r-"CÉLESTIN puene"* was first living in Frankfurt–GERMANY, before moving around 3 years after myself, into Canada [WASKAGANISH, qc; and "then Brampton, ON"].

" *r-"CÉLESTIN puene"* and *r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou"* are now member of [** –"ROTARY CLUB INTERNATONAL"–* **]; *r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou"* was initiated by *r-"MBOUM, MD, Ph.D. (surgeon)"* from OSNABRÜCK–germany. I could say I do not want to be member when *r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou"* asked for this in year 2014".

I. TRAIN young engineers & developers; CO-write software parts for YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM |

YERITH R&D, YAOUNDÉ, CMR

[2016 – 2017]

A. "ENGINEER-ENSPY job seeker-gay PAUL:"

THIS young scientist from ECOLE-NORMALE-SUPERIEURE-de-Yaounde came to myself via THE culprit named JOSEPH-djournessi during my attending of a biblical study at his home in BYEMASSI-yaounde-ACCACIA; IN year 2016.

"I started teaching C programming to this young gay electrical engineer from CMCI-communauté missionnaire internationale chrétienne OBILI-obédience (CMCI-obili); While he was looking for employment for almost 6 years after graduating as BSc.-electrical engineer from "École Nationale Supérieure Polytechnique de Yaoundé - ENSPY"."

HE stopped attending just 2 weeks after starting participating in group meeting with the 2 following scientist-educators.

HE said his financing person wanted him to focus only in applying for positions in industry such as "BRASSERIES DU CAMEROUN", etc.

B. "Scientist-educator-cuon KITIO:"

THIS young scientist from ECOLE-NORMALE-SUPERIEURE-de-Yaounde came to myself via THE culprit named JOSEPH-djournessi during my attending of a biblical study at his home in BYEMASSI-yaounde-ACCACIA; IN year 2016.

"I taught him how to use DEBIAN LINUX from the command line."

He could find a position as computer science teacher in a secondary school in west cameroon !

C. "Scientist-educator-cuon CHARLES-eteme; now working at Yaounde GENERAL hospital:"

THIS young scientist from ECOLE-NORMALE-SUPERIEURE-de-Yaounde came to myself via THE culprit named JOSEPH-djournessi during my attending of a biblical study at his home in BYEMASSI-yaounde-ACCACIA; IN year 2016.

"I taught him how to use DEBIAN LINUX from the command line."

HIS father could find him soon a position at "Yaounde GENERAL hospital" where he was earning "250 000 Xaf" to start his career as a staff web developer.

TODAY, as I have been living in Cameroon for more than 6 years now full time; I believed he was a "SED"-anti gang; IT means someone hijacking people from west-region so to make them wretched as a political argument for PAUL-biya-idiot-CPDM-president.

I. TRAIN young engineers & developers; CO-write software parts for [YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM](#) |

YERITH R&D, YAOUNDÉ, CMR

[Jan. 2021 – "November 23, 2025"]

A. "Engineer JEAN-PIERRE kamgain-idiot:"

This not professional computer science & computer engineering graduate, from "THE university of Yaounde 1", and from "IAI Cameroon"; was interested in various web-related tasks for searching employment within Douala.

1.) *plain code source "C" application programming interface development;*

A sample task was a development of a translator from "Qt 5 user interfaces (".ui" files)" onto "HTML5 pages";

2.) *JAVA servlet & apache tomcat server;*

A sample project using *APACHE-maven* (<https://>), for car maintenance & rental was developed both by myself and by JP-kamgain-culprit.

THIS sample exegete of "IAI Cameroon" wasn't capable of clearly write JAVA code as supposed with a "*bachelor of honours in Computer Software Engineering*" from both "IAI Cameroon"; And "University of Yaounde 1 (UY 1)".

3.) *PHP software development.*4.) *Training P.C.T.B-sarl employee on YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum:*

The culprit and school-mate NGADJEU-francis, refused to utilize JP because he went without asking advise from me recruit a so called call-girl-*IUC-cameroon* (<https://myiuc.com>).

5.) *Indicator for destruction of YVES-landry-galax-etoga in person:*

"JEAN-pierre kamgain has been trying to hijack my properties, both physically and emotionally because I COULD notify that HE was trying to spy my activities for "C.P.D.M party as NGADJEU-francis from P.C.T.B.-sarl did"“;

"Also JP-kamgain is the one that went to propose my ERP software system to BONTÉE sarl in AKWA-sud douala.“

6.) *[COPLATEC sarl is a psy-company for hijacking people at home:]*

OUR experience in Africa has been that at least "85% of societies" that are of type "SARL-ndlr-société à responsabilité limitée", 'GmbH (<https://WIKIPEDIAlinkDefinition.ORG>)-in-German-language';

"are companies for gay owned by soldiers FOR hijacking male and/or female consultants like myself that do not participate officially in lesbianism and homosexuality-zoophyte.“

ARLETTE-sibeuf seemed to be also member of SED.

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (POSTDOCTORAL RESEARCHER AT THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. Create and Present, & Write Research Projects in Computer (Software) Engineering Students (ECE Department) | UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Sep. 2012 – Apr. 2015]
- [VIJAY-ganesh-chenapan, static dataflow taint analysis, dynamic binary program analysis, "INTEL-Pin", LLVM]
- A. Duties completed by Researcher [Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering (Dr.-Ing.)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou:
1. **SUCCESSFUL attendance of graduate level courses to improve my dissertation writing and research skills level of knowledge :** [Sep. 2012 – MAR. 2015]
 - a.) ["Program Analysis for Web Apps"] "Grade 88%";
 - b.) ["Static Analysis for Software Engineering (SASE)"] "Grade 88%".
 2. **SOLE and INDEPENDENT idea and research of development of static dataflow taint analysis with use of "compiler framework LLVM", for solving following complex software engineering problems:** [Sep. 2012 – MAR. 2015]
 - a.) "Application Programming Interface (API) usage temporal rules";
"QUANTAMP.COM (<https://www.quantstamp.com>) uses for instance part of this research outcome to solve the problem of checking the conformance of BITCOIN-related-software-automated-contracts."
 - b.) "Detecting software security vulnerabilities" that endanger normal workflow, PER user-requirement elicitation, OR per software usability engineering: "BUFFER-OVERFLOW problems"; "SQL-injection problems"; "FORMAT-STRING attacks problems"; "AUTOMATIC test case and test data generation solution classes";
 - c.) "VERY PRECISE AND DETAILED collaboration with Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. VIJAY-ganesh";

THIS research is more detailed in: [YERITH-SAINT \(https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293\)](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293) [11].

1. Create and Present, & Write Research Projects in Computer (Software) Engineering (ECE Department) |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2012 – 2014]

[Vijay-GANESH-from Ph.D.-at-stanford.edu (<https://research.gatech.edu/people/vijay-ganesh>),
RESEARCH outcome plagiarism,
RESEARCH outcome hindrance,
"JAN-peleska-crédule; best-ever-professor of mine",
"student advising-MISSING paper",
static dataflow taint analysis,
LLVM (<https://llvm.org/racist-apple>)]

A. Duties completed by Assisting Professor [Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering (DR.-ING.-PH.D.)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou:

[Summary-PAGES]

1. EXPERIMENTATION WITH IFDS-FRAMEWORK FROM "REPS ET AL."

[JAN. 2013 – JUNE 2013]

I discovered the "IFDS (Interprocedural, Finite, Distributive, Subset)" (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Inter-procedural-data-flow-analysis-with-IFDS-IDE-Bodden/a3f7557fe673ff0711e9049cf5ece8b02a51f7f1>) problems algorithm by THOMAS reps from UNIVERSITY-of-WISCONSIN-MADISON (<https://www.wisc.edu>), and from "Grammatech" (<https://www.grammatech.com>) ;

"I really enjoyed this graph-based software system interdependence algorithm; and accompanying free FOSS IBM-wala library (<https://research.ibm.com/publications/program-analysis-using-wala>) ".

NEVERTHELESS I tried a personal implementation of the IFDS-framework using SOOT (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>) & Java-SCALA with no successful binaries; BECAUSE the ideology for using "IBM-wala" was quite strange to my understanding !!!

I then renounced & abandoned to pursue and implement "The KILDALL-style" ("Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)") using C++ and a book-Advanced Compiler Design-from ...IBM author... !:

 YERITH-SAINT (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) [34]

2. [Work on "Dynamic PROGRAM Analysis with FRANK-tip" in course CS846] & [Work on "Software System Security by Software VERIFICATION"]

3. [SUMMARY of student research-teaching advisory work both "autonomously" and, from my PH.D.-advisor PATRICK.]

[Sep. 2009 – Mar. 2015]

4. [Previous RESEARCH-development at AGBS—UNIVERSITY-OF-BREMEN.DE] :

"JAN peleska is my 1st best ever professor because I learned the best research skills from him while working in his research group in Germany-bremen-racist (E.g.: Unfortunately for myself; I couldn't get any professional-vocational student software developer position in a commercial company installed in Bremen.). (<https://informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp>) "

[FSE-soqua 2006]

"More importantly we had a paper at Foundations OF Software Engineering research conference in 2006 while I was working on my "Diplom-Informatiker degree [Dipl.-Inf.] (Master of Science equivalent)" in his research group at the University-of-bremen.de (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>): "Test Automation for Hybrid Systems" (www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp/papers/peleska_et_al_soqua2006.pdf) — ("VERIFIED.DE" (<https://www.verified.de/products/model-based-testing>)) !!! "

5. Follow-up on research started by [DIVAM-jain] with following other fellow researchers at ECE:

- o DEREK-rayside
- o PATRICK-lam
- o REID-holmes
- o LIN-tan-idiot-gay-non-sense-girl
- o FELIX-fang
- o etc.

I started collaborating with DIVAM jain because PATRICK-lam sent DIVAM jain to me for learning about static dataflow code analysis using SOOT.

"WHEN divam-jain-racist left, I pursue this same research with FELIX fang, and then with researchers afore-mentioned in office of the director of software engineering program PATRICK-lam; Where we attended to group collaborative meetings."

THEN he was more about the problem itself; IN this occasion, how to automatically generate "JUnit test suites test cases" based on static code dataflow analysis of unit test code of the analyzed projects.

"A benchmark of "at least 100 open source JAVA libraries" was used to test these projects JUnit test code.

From this research came out at least 11 conference peer-reviewed papers and some journal articles, AND i wasn't mentioned as a co-author either:

- 1.) "Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints" (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)

1. Create and Present, & Write Research Projects in Computer (Software) Engineering (ECE Department) |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2014 – 2018]

["sodomite-peggish-JULIA-rubin-AT-UNIVERSITY-of-british-columbia-CANADIAN-rate-gay-Israelite-ANTI-JESUS-OF-Nazareth",
dynamic binary program analysis,
"INTEL-Pin"]

A. Duties completed by Assisting Professor [Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering (Dr.-Ing.)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou:

4. **DEVELOPMENT of certain features of PHP-JAVA-judo-quebec web application for management of club members:**

[JUNE 2014 – NOV. 2014]

THE research paid-provision was around "1000 \$CAD" a month, which was very insignificant because of all the technologies working together such as: PHP, GWT (Google Web Toolkit), etc.

5. **PATRICK-idiot lam research idea**, and personal sole development of a dynamic binary program analysis for moving "PROGRAM-POINT" during runtime execution based on certain loop-condition; USING "INTEL-Pin" :

[SEP. 2014 – OCT. 2014]

PATRICK-idiot lam didn't allow myself to complete the program under his sole supervision.

I WASN'T really happy because he interrupted my main project on static taint dataflow analysis; HE didn't tell me anything about any outcome, and/or later done publication or whatsoever.

THIS research is more detailed in: [YERITH-SAINT \(https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293\)](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293) [11].

6. **!!-sodomite-peggish-woman-attention-patrick-JULIA-rubin-ecce-british columbia-faineant-chien-tabaweak-canaoe** said she will continue research with myself at UBC (<https://www.ece.ubc.ca/mjulia>) so I WILL GRADUATE as a "PH.D." !

[2018]

" IT was dereak-gayside that said I SHOULD TRY TO apply somewhere else than university-racist-of-waterloo since they-idiot-of-lam could call the police to arrest myself ILLEGALLY on waterloo dirty-racket-pd-cuon-tabaweak-quebec-salaud main campus !!! "

PLEASE FOLK that may think a white-racist Gives you a residence permit to allow yourself to fulfill your peace dreams; IT'S NOT THE CASE.

" THE WHITE-GAY-DAY-nancy-racist is only trying to reduce the speed of perfectionism and development of your country of origin by harassing you there with corrupt-gay authorities so you will try to go outside. "

" All these mansory-free-rotary-club-ETC.; CATHOLIC-gay-church is only a way to hijack your life in anti-christ-of-negger-jesus-of-nazareth like myself I HAVE BEEN experiencing for 7 years in ontarian-CANADA-shit-people-race. "

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (RESEARCH ASSISTANT – DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER – AT THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. CO-create and CO-present, & Co-write Research Projects in Computer (Software) Engineering Students (ECE Department) | UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

[Algorithms dis-pension,
finite automaton theories,
"Year 2010 report",
"Year 2011 report",
"1st summer school on formal techniques",
[IDIOT-black-afro-descendant Sandy BEIDU from ghanaian land]]

I. Duties completed by Research Assistant [Diplom-Informatiker (Dipl.-Inf.; MSc)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou:

1. [SUMMARY of student research-teaching advisory work both "autonomously" and, from my advisor-PH.,D. PATRICK].
2. **SUCCESSFUL attendance of graduate level courses to improve my dissertation writing and research skills level of knowledge :** [SEP. 2009 – DEC 2011]
 - a.) ["First SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques"] "participated with certificate";
 - b.) ["Computer-Aided Verification-racist-nancy"] "Grade 90%";
 - c.) ["Advanced Compiler Design-cuon-plagiarism-of-jon"] "Grade 86%".

3. I went to **menlo-racist-college** (<https://fm.csl.sri.com/SSFT11/index.shtml>) in California, USA, to the 1st summer school on formal techniques from "May 22, 2011" until "May 27, 2011"; under a recommendation-required (from professor doctor NANCY-idiot-day (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~nday>)).

I was accompanied by the GHANAIAN called SANDY-cuon-beidu supposed to be a very famous computer scientist originating from my home continent AFRICA.

[THIS hideous ignorant fellow, from a very poor material background arrived at the university of waterloo "WatForm-waterloo formal methods" in year 2010 if I have good memories; Saying to the world he is a JESUS-christian;]

This kind of black-afro-descendant is so disgusting that I believed that the racist **JO-atlee-his-research-advisor** (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~jmatlee>) went to pick him so to dishonest myself in front of the extremely dominant ["iranian female population in ECE graduate student folks"] !

HE even thought that I RENTED my "ford fusion" to tell them (Sandy-idiot-day, and a lady from long-island-black-prostitute) that I AM A WELL-TO-DO-MAN in front of them.

[I JUST remembered my BUSINESS-trip while I WAS TRAVELING for SIEMENS-medical-solutions-erlangen IN concord-ca-usa; And I KNEW I NEEDED to be mobile; THAT's why I RENTED A luxurious "ford fusion" from my savings account from my HARD-job at SIEMENS.]

[SANDY-idiot-poor-man-in-all-system thought when the other ghanaian idiot-story-teller-Dr-PhD-ERIC-brefomensah brought me to his travesty-basement-slot in WATERLOO, in ontario, 2018; THAT i needed some drink from him !]

[PLEASE folk from basement places in GHANA; Cameroon don't need this kind of down-treatment as CAMEROON is way more advanced as demonstrated ONLY by me !!!!!!!]

4. I have worked on topic "temporal property verification in plugin-based software"; and created a computer-Libreoffice-Impress presentation slides for the **IBM workshop CASCON 2010-CDP-compiler-...** (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>); [IBM WORKSHOP-CDP CASCON 2010]

THIS research as "**Master Of Science**" (so called "DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER DEGREE, ABBREVIATED (DIPL.-INF.) (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)[?]") led to my "**Doctoral Thesis / PhD comprehensive examination**" released research technical document : "**Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software**" (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>)

5. I have created sample program static code analyzes using the **SOOT framework** (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>) so to acquire skills in static code program analysis.

A very short introduction: " " (<https://>) to SOOT framework by

6. I HAVE IMPROVED my algorithm design skills by implementing popular algorithms using the Following ALGORITHM POPULAR BOOKS:

- A. **Computer Systems: A PROGRAMMER'S PERSPECTIVE, 2nd edition ("ISBN 13 : 978 - 0 - 13 - 610804 - 7")**; by "**BYANT**"-racist & "**O'HALLARON**"-racist-sexist;
- B. **Introduction to Algorithms-Isbn: " "**; by **THOMAS cormen** (https://www.amazon.com/Introduction-to-Algorithms-fourth-Thomas-Cormen/dp/026204630X/ref=sr_1_1?crd=2UBHH37C2Y2J3&dib=eyJ2IjojMSJ9.RxrAGDmePG_uPSHKskT1qe4eJp18_sU0zfGdVfEd1BzcV0qunH6HMFdUvjfBk5T7_hbHBgRqWVHVSmsYFd00P9qIyOhMwCdwVMeRQodxABi7cszQqi1XxeWBu8jZqpGALecudSCyPct_N4de9gw1drRqhl2Alh8huCTZ2PeIofPH8JLCoU0jaTq8vuQ-G7z1Jdit5yRk2hl627B7GRAFGV3fio1k8kSGbcuK5_JsFw6g.AobHaMGD2q1MBzQIcdziArWazLVBUQztj2REK1DRJ0Y&dib_tag=se&keywords=CS+Algorithm+book&qid=1726183252&s=books&prefix=cs+algorithm+book%2Cstripbooks-intl-ship%2C313&sr=1-1).

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (RESEARCH ASSISTANCE FROM FOLK-IDIOT – DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER – AT THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. CO-create and CO-present, & Co-write Research Projects in Computer (Software) Engineering Students (ECE Department) |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

[**"JOHN HOPCROFT"**, **"samaneh navabpour-racist-extreme"**, **"1st Summer School on Formal Techniques"**, **LLVM**, **SOOT**]

I. **People from [the University of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA] whom I got academic help:**

1. "AAKARSH nair, M.ASc., Computer ENGINEERING, 2009"

- "AAKARSH nair was the 1st student of DEAR-idiot PATRICK lam I have ever met.

HE is the 1st one to give me sample code on static dataflow analysis with "JAVA-SOOT framework (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>)" à la "Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)" "

2. "NANCY day"

- "Professor DAY wrote a very good and tremendous recommendation that was used to admit myself to [**"First Summer School on Formal Techniques"**] (<https://fm.cs1.sri.com/SSFT11/index.shtml>), by THE NATIONAL SCIENCE FOUNDATION, SRI International, Menlo College, Atherton, California, USA; in year 2011".

3. "Samaneh Navabpour, Ph.D., Electrical & Computer Engineering"

- SAM gave me 1st explanations about LLVM by using her previous work for **a paper-RITHM** (<https://uwaterloo.ca/embedded-software-group/sites/default/files/uploads/documents/main.pdf>) she worked on in SEBASTIAN fischmeister embedded computer research group; She confessed not having exactly applied a static dataflow analysis à la "Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)";

BUT used only control flow graph related features to perform static dataflow analysis; this is NOT exactly **CLANG** (<https://clang.llvm.org>).

4. **Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Nomair Naeem, Ph.D.** (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~nanaeem>)

- NOMAIR was the 1st person apart from Patrick, my doctoral Ph.D. advisor that took so much time to help me understand and proof read my **doctoral Ph.D. Thesis** ([HTTPS://WWW.SEMANTICSCSCHOLAR.ORG/PAPER/TEMPORAL-PROPERTY-VERIFICATION-IN-PLUGIN-BASED-NOUNDOU/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33](https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/TEMPORAL-PROPERTY-VERIFICATION-IN-PLUGIN-BASED-NOUNDOU/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33)) [32];
- NOMAIR helped myself in understanding the intricacies of a context-sensitive static parametric analysis by explaining from his **research paper Interacting objects ...** (<https://plg.uwaterloo.ca/~nanaeem/papers/oops1a08PhD.pdf>).

5. **Prof. Dr. Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D.** (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak>)

- Professor Lhoták accepted to review my **YERITH-SAINT** algorithm thoroughly.
- Ondřej was very kind to help me with source code of 1 of his 1st **LLVM** dataflow analysis, before I started my own.

6. **Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. JOHN hopcroft-SEXIST, Ph.D.** (<https://www.cs.cornell.edu/jeh/>)

- Explanation, at my email request, and very promptly and generously about an algorithm in his compiler book.

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' AND TEACHING (GRADUATE INTERN AT INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS MACHINERY (IBM))

1. Perform duties assigned by big manager and PATRICK doyle in JAVA-J9 JUST-IN-TIME OPTIMIZATION team (, located in Markham-ONTARIO-canada); (advised by Prof. VIJAY sundaresan, M.Sc. (MCGILL, QC, CANADA) | Patrick Doyle, (M.ASc., UNIVERSITY OF TORONTO, Ontario, CANADA))) |
IBM TORONTO-IDIOT SOFTWARE LAB. [01/2012 – 08/2012]

[AS canadian-idiot permanent resident;

Automated Software TESTING with YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIFY (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verify>),

Program OPTIMIZATION (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>), "Clark-salaud Verbrugge, Ph.D. (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump>)";

JVM – JAVA virtual machines, IBM – WEBSPPHERE, Managers are really understandable,

DOCTOR-ENGINEER,

Racism from restaurant in india-bangalore-IBM-gay]

[Summary Of D.ENG. [DR.-ING. in "French language"] (PH.D.) Review Research-PAGES]

I. Comfort excellent for work research at IBM:

1. I was working into a brown cubicle and had so much freedom in work that I WAS SOMETIMES afraid that I AM NOT PERFORMING well.

BUT when I STARTED working closely more with VIJAY I felt so busy that I WAS DREAMING of going home around 03:00PM in evening;

IN total, IBM in MARKHAM offers very good working and research conditions for his employees, *even better than my previous 1st full-time job as JUNIOR-SOFTWARE-DEVELOPER at SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS in Erlangen, BAVARIA, GERMANY !!!*

SIEMENS Medical solutions was really good in Erlangen; But i didn't like seeing "BOSS gerhard" watching his arm watch any 2 minutes to make sure we only had 45 minutes lunch-break; "Secretary "gudrun" is also really helpful and smiling ! "

II. ISSUES - Problems with some colleagues:

1. **Prof. Vijay Sundaresan, MSc. – from Bangalore, INDIA**

THIS daemon of work was so kind that I ONLY FEEL I have satisfy him as much as he wanted and could !!!

HE is very attracted to good and fast male workers; because female workers would only try to hijack his time for a snack !!!

I am very proud of having work with such an amazing scientist at all !!!

ALSO the team managers, including the chinese woman, were very kind to myself as the only male afro-descendant from AFRICA !!!

2. **Patrick idiot Doyle, M.ASc. – from Ireland-CANADA**

THIS ignorant as a teacher and / or mentor couldn't even pick myself at time when I Was waiting for my hiring team for the internship to come at my encounter in the biggest room where we all intern were awaiting 1st day of internship.

III. Duties of Graduate INTERN [Doctor of Engineering] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou:

1. **FIX SOFTWARE TESTING FEATURE AUTOMATION USING BASH SCRIPTS**

I felt a lot better at this task because I could feel having a positive impact on the project team lead by manager that I don't remember names and academic titles.

ALSO vijay sundaresan wasn't very disgusting as people working in the restaurant, that always served myself BURNed food, especially pagan-an-food.

Vijay sundaresan is a very talented software lead and developer that I could ever see in my career; I VERY MUCH LIKED THE INTERACTIONS with him compared to PATRICK doyle.

TODAY I FEEL there are 2 factors that helped:

- A. **MCGILL university** (<https://www.mcgill.ca>) graduates in Computing Sciences are very much talented compared to other students from ONTARIO.
B. VIJAY-sundaresan was born also outside of Canada-racist-systemic like my recruiting manager that I forgot about names;

2. **MAINTAIN CERTAIN DAYS BUG DATABASE**

AT all not very difficult, since I WAS USED TO use CHARMNT in my previous full-time job at Siemens Medical Solutions in Erlangen, BAVARIA, germany.

3. **ATTEND TO COURSES AT IBM TORONTO-IDIOT LABORATORY GIVEN BY "pr. prof. dr.-ing. clark-salaud verbrugge" FROM MCGILL.ca** (<https://mcgill.ca>) "on Creating Optimizations for Compilers"

4. **SOLVE AS MANY AS BUGS IN COMPILER OPTIMIZATION CODE SOURCE IN C++**

Coming from a program analysis research team, that performed more static code analysis using framework like S00T, and LLVM; I WAS KIND OF not performing very well at this task at all because of the very applied and complicated data structures; Especially because PATRICK-indigeneous-iranian-irish-from-british-kingdom never even got me to a small talk for explaining me briefly what was the governing ideas leading the development team in MARKHAM.

INSTEAD, i only received so many documents that I had to read and detect understand myself.

Earning as much as 3 000 \$CAD monthly, I FELT SO BAD that I Went to complain to the manager; a very kind person; that allowed then myself to work with the team lead VIJAY sundaresan...

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' (WEB DEVELOPMENT INTERNSHIP AT BREMEN4U-GMBH-RACIST-PEGGIST)

1. CREATE AND MAINTAIN – HTML, CSS, PHP, JSP – CODE SOURCE FOR a Content Management System – as an EVENT MANAGEMENT SOFTWARE ONLINE racist (advised by MARTIN ...) |

BREMEN4U-GMBH-RACIST-PEGGIST, BREMEN, GERMANY-RACIST-PEGGIST

— March. 2004 —

[[WEB software development with PHP, CSS],

Peggist-racist colleague Martin...,

[JSP, HTML5,]

Samsung CONTACT Server on Redhat LINUX]

I. Duties of Web Development Intern [Vordiplom-B.Sc candidate (In Computer Science)] Xavier Noundou:

1. *Before attending and applying for this position; I attended courses workshops on Web development using MariaDB, HTML5, CSS, JSP, PHP during around 1 semester (4 months) at the Department of Computer Science ("FACHBEREICH 3) of the University of Bremen. (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>)*
2. *Create configuration in Redhat LINUX for the Samsung Contact Server system.*
3. *Create HTML5, CSS, JSP, PHP combined code into a Content Management System for managing Event that are to be published on a specific date on the Bremen4u-Gmbh website.*
4. Martin was always having a very bad mouth-breath because of smoking cigarette all day together with drinking black dark coffee with no milk at all.
5. THIS was a very disgusting place to work as a new person living in Germany; also young girls from secondary school as internship workers; With almost no sense on respecting black african race at ALL !

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' AND TEACHING (JUNIOR SOFTWARE DEVELOPER AT SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS)

1. CREATE AND MAINTAIN C++ CODE SOURCE FOR THE SOFTWARE COMPONENT (which is protocol communication control) TXSUPERVISOR of Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist Software (advised by DARIO MERAUVIGLIA | GERHARD SENG) |

SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS, BAVARIA, GERMANY

[NOV. 2007 – July 2009]

[C++,
Duties of Junior Software Developer (Software-Engineer),
Software Integration Testing [21],
UNDER german-traveler work-permit;
ROBOTER-linac,
Radiation Therapy Treatment,
IMRT beam treatment,
TXSUPERVISOR software component development]

1. Duties of Junior Software Developer (Software-Engineer) [Diplom-Informatiker (Dipl.-Inf.)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou:

1. "MARVELOUS TRAVEL to Concord, CALIFORNIA, USA : my greatest and high paid experience of work since I was given birth in 1983 !!! — 5 000 EUROS

THANK you boss gerhard-idiot-SENG !!!!!!! "

2. "Participation in cancer treatment (IMRT) radiation therapy training, and all other software development related training for this position as JUNIOR SOFTWARE DEVELOPER."
3. "C++ coding and defects fixing of DMIP control communication protocol as heart of Software component TXSUPERVISOR: around 110 000 Lines of code (SLOC)."
4. *Conception & Development of an automated software integration test infrastructure:*
 - a. Cygwin bash-scripting
 - b. Microsoft COM component as [CORBA] agent communication used
5. Software Integration testing using "IBM Purify Plus".

 (COMPETITOR FROM "PR. PROF. DR-ING. Xavier noumbissi Noundou":
[YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF \(https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481\) \[1b\]](https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481);
 git <https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif> ;
6. "DMIP Control Console" device as user control management for simulating radiation therapy linear accelerator "SIEMENS Linac Artiste" in our laboratory in Erlangen ground-base;
7. Focal entry point of all bugs of "Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist" software. INVESTIGATION, and then redistribution, according to defect type, to an appropriate sub-team VIA team-lead "Gehrrard Seng".
8. Support technical in writing software user manual with software testers.
9. Support technical with software testers in using "Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist" software.
10. Phone support technical in TROUBLESHOOTING "Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist" software.
11. Maintenance of communication development support from software developers from Siemens Concord in California, USA.
12. Maintaining using "MS office" of design documents of TXSUPERVISOR and "DMIP control communication protocol"; based on "FSM state machine theory": United States of America's FDA (U.S.A – Federal Drug and Administration), as well as CE (European Community) had to review the digitally signed documents; stored in "SAP-EDM (<https://www.sap.de>)".
13. Assisting "DARIO meraviglia" in selection of interns based on their qualification as reported on their CV – resume.
14. Advising of 2 software testing maintenance part-time employees:
 1. 1 from Germany, from The University of Bamberg (Bayern, Germany);
 2. 1 as an intern, from India.
15. "VMWare" (<https://www.vmware.com>) as debugging image creator development tool.
16. "MS Windows 2000", as well as, "MS Windows NT", as software development operating systems platforms.
17. "Visual Studio C++" as IDE;
18. "IBM Rational ClearCase" as Code BASE source management control software used;
19. "IBM CharmNT" as bug management platform used;
20. [LEGAL requirement summary experience with HANDLING of Design Documents Functional Specification for Medical Software according to "CE" ; "FDA".]

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' AND TEACHING (JUNIOR SOFTWARE DEVELOPER AT SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS)

1. CREATE AND MAINTAIN C++ CODE SOURCE FOR THE SOFTWARE COMPONENT (which is protocol communication control) TXSUPERVIR of Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist Software (advised by DARIO MERAUVIGLIA | GERHARD SENG) |

SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS, BAVARIA, GERMANY

[11/2007 – 07/2009]

[C++,

Duties of Junior Software Developer (Software-Engineer),

Software Integration Testing [21],

UNDER german-traveler work-permit;

ROBOTER-linac,

Radiation Therapy Treatment,

IMRT beam treatment,

TXSUPERVISOR software component development]

I. ISSUES – Problems with some colleagues:

1. Gerhard Seng and Dario Meraviglia told myself I should be promoted to the position of Dario as "technical lead of the software module component TXSUPERVISOR (only 1 developer)" if I could succeed in gaining a full-time permanent contract after an initial successful 6 months period of work under direct leadership of DARIO MERAUVIGLIA.

"AFTER SUCCEEDING the trial period of 6 months, I obtain a change of software developer contract from a full-time limited contract to a full-time permanent contract with "Siemens Medical Solutions"."

"HOWEVER after an additional 15 months of work, I am not anymore promoted to a higher level position of Technical Lead."

"This is why I decide to make the effort to go back to academia and pursue [a doctoral Ph.D. in Electrical & Computer Engineering (Computer Software)] at the University of Waterloo, in ONTARIO, CANADA; WITH [Dr-PhD patrick lam as academic adviser] !! "

2. "Merlin Tonka from Cameroon" is calling me even before my first day at job in Erlangen to tell me he hopes I will be able to perform well and thus keep my job beyond the 1st 6 months period of try: He tells myself HE got my email from boss "Gehrrard Seng";

"From NORTH of GERMANY WHERE I STUDIED AND LIVED for almost 6 years before being recruited and before moving to Fürth-BAVARIA-Germany, this is not "SACK-ARBEIT": I.E. one shall not mixed private life affairs with business matters at all: THIS IS HOW I LEARNED IT in HAMBURG, and BREMEN ! "

3. "Merlin Tonka" one day follows myself in metro and bus so to tell me that HE shall be promoted as a team of a new testing and developers team, And that he shall be my manager.

" I was wondering silently (because very young in year 2008 with only 23.5) years old ("Merlin Tonka was at least 40 years old in front of my age"), that someone less qualified than myself and currently employed as only a software tester, which is a lower level required qualification; Put aside you are PhD-doctor-of-engineering; and that was recruited only 1 week before my personal recruitment, will become my manager by telling it to me only in streets ! "

"THE italian master of science-level engineer Dario Meraviglia is my technical lead, followed by Gerhard Seng, our common teal lead at Syngo-RTT-Therapist-SW-Realize team" !

4. After leaving "Siemens Medical Solutions" legally by resigning with a signed letter 3 months before leaving my IG-METAL-tariff-vertrag employment in year 2009; I sent a letter to thank "MERLIN TONKA" for the positive professional collaboration I had with him as a fellow cameroonian, despite a lot of troubles we had; I sent this letter only around 1 month after starting studying in Waterloo, Ontario, Canada.

"THE answer from "Merlin Tonka" is so negative minded and outspoken that I need to reply to tell him truth about not trying again to tell me he is superior to myself; I.e. Merlin tries in a letter to tell me I could not perform well in software developer job, that's why I resigned !!! "

"Only smelling the same dirty "grey-shirt" MERLIN was wearing almost every day was not comfortable because he was sitting just opposite side of my office-desk ! "

"I today in year 2024 can remark as a citizen living inside CAMEROON that killer from governmental agency [DGRE wear generally grey-shirts !]"

"UDM-université des montagnes (<https://WIKIPEDIA.ORG-racist>) later on in year 2009 invited DGRE-activist MERLIN tonka through THE KILLER OF MY GENITOR théodore noumbissi; So called [HUGUES NTOMANI tiako], which is sleeping with genitor ROSE sangnou so to perform crimes on my person even now in year 2024 ! "

"WHITE-blond supremacist slave-maker; PLEASE stop to hijack black afro-descendants that are talented. TILO. MÜCKE. DARIO. MERAUVIGLIA. MERLIN. TONKA ! "

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' AND TEACHING – CONTINUED (1) (JUNIOR SOFTWARE DEVELOPER AT SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS)

1. CREATE AND MAINTAIN C++ CODE SOURCE FOR THE SOFTWARE COMPONENT (which is protocol communication control) TXSUPERVIR of Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist Software (advised by DARIO MERAVIGLIA | GERHARD SENG) |
SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS, BAVARIA, GERMANY [11/2007 – 07/2009]

III Students living in Germany I helped during my whole time at Siemens Medical Solutions:

1. **"paternal uncle Demo Noundou from Cameroon".**

Information Technology student in Bachelor of Sciences (BSc) at "TUHH — Technische Universität Hamburg–Harbug".

[Help in proof reading his Bachelor–Thesis.]

IV Students living in Canada I helped during vacation time by my uncle maternal "Théodore Wandji":

1. Co–roommate of Théodore Wandji at 5850 Rue Souart, #7, H3S 2E8, Quebec, Montreal, CANADA:

"Basser from Syria":

Electrical & Computer Engineering student in Master of Applied Sciences (M.ASc.) at "ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE MONTREAL".

NON paid technical support in programming C++, with **"MS Windows 2000 as operating system (OS) platform"**.

2. **"Fabrice TCHOUMI from Cameroon":**

Electrical & Computer Engineering student in Bachelor of Applied Sciences (B.ASc.) at "ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE MONTREAL".

NON paid technical support in programming C++, with **"MS Windows 2000 as operating system (OS) platform"**.

V Software Development Colleagues were:

1. Senior Software Developer "MAMIDI" from INDIA.
2. Senior Software Developer "Detlef Kendelbacker" (Contractor) from Bayern–Germany.
3. Team Lead "Gerhard seng" from Bayern–Germany.
4. Software Architect Balakrishnan; from India.
5. Software–Engineer [Diplom–Informatiker : [Dipl.–Inf.]] Xavier Noumbissi NOUNDOU; from Cameroon.
6. Technical Lead DESIREE görisen; from Bayern–Germany.
7. Technical Lead [Dr.] GANESH gopalakrishnan; from India.
8. Technical Lead [Diplom–Informatiker (FachHochschule) : [Dipl.–Inf. (FH)]] Johannes Bauer; from Bayern–Germany.
9. Technical Lead [Diplom–Informatiker (FachHochschule) : [Dipl.–Inf. (FH)]] Martin Maier; from Bayern–Germany.
10. Technical Lead [Ing., Polytechnico Di Milano] Dario Meraviglia; from Italy.

VI Software Testing Colleagues were:

1. Test Manager [Diplom–Informatiker : [Dipl.–Inf.]] "TILO mücke"; from Germany.
2. Software Tester "Merlin Tonka, M.Sc. (Computational Engineering, University of Erlangen–Nürnberg, Germany)" from Bagangte, Cameroon–French–Island
3. Software Tester "Suschma" from India
4. Software Tester "Swapnil, Bachelor (Mechanical Engineering)" from India
5. Software Tester "Dhananjay" from India

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (STUDENT SOFTWARE DEVELOPER AT GEWETE GMBH)

1. CREATE SQL databases JAVA Servlet programs and C++ communication protocol software programs (advised by SVEN KAMRATH | JENS MÖLLER) | BERGMANN AUTOMATEN GMBH (NOW GEWETE GMBH), GERMANY [03/2005 – 04/2007]

[CE – EUROPEAN COMMUNITY (https://www.single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/single-market/ce-marking_en), UNDER german-traveler student part-time-work-permit, C++, MAKE, "JSWING", Hibernate, JAVA, Servlets, apache ANT, Eclipse IDE, XML (e.g: JAXP library), Qt, SQL, Vending machines, Communication protocol – [debugging at YERITH R&D Now !](#)]

I. APPLICATION FOR A STUDENT DEVELOPER POSITION AT "BERGMANN AUTOMATEN GMBH":

I stumble on this offered position while I WAS LOOKING FOR A NEW DEVELOPER position part-time when I KNEW MY PROJECT with "PROF. DR. RER. POL. KLAUS–racist bönkost" would not be renewed.

THE position was advertised on a website for student jobs of the TUHH (<https://www.tuhh.de>).

II. Duties of Student Software Developer [Vordiplom in Informatik] Xavier noumbissi Noundou:

1. "LaDIVA java servlet XML parsing project development, and its installer Graphical User Interface (GUI) program developed using "JSWING" (<https://>) JAVA library technology."
2. "MESO": "LaDIVA java servlet XML parsing follower project development."
The novelty in this follower project is that I INTRODUCED, based on my research skills, acquired in BREMEN, an object–relational database object mapper called "**Hibernate** (<https://www.hibernate.org>)"; THIS was to be capable of giving newer customers ORACLE 9i functionalities from "LaDIVA java servlet XML parsing project" !!!
3. "C++ coding of a "Sap-ABAP protocol communication interface" to put "Bergmann Automaten GmbH" vending machines in communication with vending machine of Hamburg public library that used "BIBLIOTHECA software library".
4. "C++ coding of *SIPv2 control communication protocol* (<https://>)."
5. Migration from "ORACLE 9i database tables" onto "MySQL database tables" for the MESO project (follower of LaDIVA software project); I used following technologies:
 - a. BASH–scripting
 - b. AWK scripting language.

III. Students living in Germany I helped during my whole time at "Bergmann Automaten GmbH, Rellingen, Hamburg":

1. "**paternal uncle Demo Noundou from Cameroon**".
Information Technology student in Bachelor of Sciences (BSc) at "TUHH — Technische Universität Hamburg–Harbug" (<https://www.tuhh.de>).
"Demo" then obtained by "Bergmann Automaten GmbH" a position as "Bachelor student working on its thesis, project–based":
 - a. I talked to "Mister Sven Kamrath of this request", by "Mister Demo Noundou", of a Bachelor Thesis Project.
 - b. HE ("DEMO") then refused a final offer as full–time "JAVA software developer" because he felt he couldn't perform well in a "JAVA plain object (JPO)" software development environment.
 - c. "[2008] Demo Noundou, B.Sc." then accepted a position at "Canon Ltd. as **PHP – JAVA Web Software Developer in Osnabrück; HE can–also wear title Dipl.–Ing. (FH).**".
 - d. " [2015] DEMO NOUNDOU is now at his own company in web development & training in HAMBURG. (<https://ank-technologies.com>) "
 - e. " [2024] DEMO is also a consultant in african universities curriculum development based in KENYA, and others. NO ONE CAN BE A PROPHET IN HIS HOME–YAOUNDE. (<https://SAINTEBIBLE.COM/jesusquoteTOCHECK>) "

"DEMO NOUNDOU, B.Sc." also had a "grade of (10.5/20)" which is not a very good grade to enter such position as the one I GOT LATER ON AT siemens medical solutions; A "GRADE OF 14.5/20" is required to apply for any entry level position at ["SIEMENS AG GERMANY–low–payer"].

IV. ISSUES - Problems with some colleagues:

1. *Herr Sven Kamrath was very angry at myself 1 day during my stay in Rellingen to talk about an ongoing project 'LaDIVA XML Servlet Parser Server' !
"He found a subtle bug that I then fixed the same day."*

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' AND TEACHING (WEB-HTML-CSS DEVELOPER AT ZENTRUM FÜR MULTIMEDIA IN DER LEHRE (ZMML))

1. CREATE AND MAINTAIN websites – www.s-hb.de (<https://www.s-hb.de>) mainly – for KLAUS-racist-extreme BÖNKOST (advised by PROF. DR. RER. POL. criminal Klaus Bönkost) |
 ZMML-UNIVERSITY-RACIST-SEXIST OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY [Feb. 2003 – Feb. 2005]

[UNDER german-traveler student work-permit;
 'dunklefarbige mitarbeiter xavier aus Afrika',
 HTML5,
 CSS,
 "photoshop",
 IMAGE-dateien,
 FADRI,
 SVEN schu]

I. Duties of WERKSTUDENT [candidate vordiplom in INFORMATIK] Xavier noumbissi Noundou:

1. "Reception, and implementation, of design documents (e.g.: "photoshop images", etc.) from FADRI-racist."
2. ["Programming of HTML5, CSS web pages."];
 [Participated 1-month to a training internship at Bremen4u-GmbH.]
3. "Programming of RAD-server programs with Graphical User Interfaces (GUI); With programming support of Sven-schu-nazi."
 "RAD-server programming language (<https://wikipedia.org...>) is a sample VISUAL BASIC dialect domain specific language. "
4. "Participation in weekly meeting on development of websites and test facilities for students in economia."

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES – UNI-RACIST BREMEN

1. CREATE A MODEL-BASED TESTING FRAMEWORK TO AUTOMATICALLY GENERATE STATECHART MODEL TEST CASES FOR REACTIVE SYSTEM SOFTWARE ([advised by Prof. Dr. rer. nat. habil. Jan Peleska]) |
UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY — "NOT fully described curriculum by myself" [09/2002 – 05/2007]
- a. "Diplom-Informatiker" : "MASTER 2" IN COMPUTER SCIENCE THESIS (DIPLOMARBEIT): "STATISTICAL TEST CASE GENERATION FOR REACTIVE SYSTEMS (GRADE 18/20)"; as part work for the FSE-SOQUA (2006) Research Conference Proceedings full research paper: "Test Automation for Hybrid Systems" (VERIFIED.DE), AGBS-UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY [12/2006 – 05/2007]
- [“V”-“WATER FALL”-MODEL of Software Development, reactive system, UML 2.0, HybridUML profile, [statechart](#), Theoretical Computer Science, TDIOHS (time discrete input output hybrid system), STCT (symbolic test case tree), uniformly distributed statistical test case generation, MBT-RT-Tester, YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF as of now a doctor (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>) .]
- Algorithms developed by myself for this 'Master of Science research-based Thesis ("Diplomarbeit" in German)' (https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/qualifikationsarbeiten/diplomarbeiten_e.html) [1a], based on 'Prof. Dr. Marie-Claude Gaudelle' research outcome, as a mathematician in France, are used in the RT-Tester tool of the verification and validation research and German society "VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GMBH, SPIN-OFF THE UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN" (<https://www.verified.de>) .
- b. C++ CODE GENERATION PLUGIN IMPLEMENTATION WITHIN CASE tool "Borland-Together", AGBS-UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY [09/2006 – 02/2007]
- [reactive system, UML 2.0, [statechart](#), Theoretical Computer Science, TDIOHS (time discrete input output hybrid system), STCT (symbolic test case tree), C++ code generation, MBT-RT-Tester]
- Our algorithms are for the "TDIOHS: Timed Discrete Input / Output Hybrid System" (https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp/papers/peleska_et_al_soqua2006.pdf) state diagram formalism, that could be visualized by [statecharts](#) for instance using a 'Verified Systems International GmbH plug-in' for 'Borland-Together 6' (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Micro_Focus_Together).
- c. "Research Master in Computer Science Software 2-Years PROJECT" : CogAG project : "Robot "Arni" usage in framework of creating mapping recognition algorithms and cartography.", Cognitive Systems Group (CoSy), "Christian Freksa as Project creator and lead", CoSy – University of Bremen, GERMANY [01/2005 – 03/2007]
- [Cognition, Cartography, RFID-tag technology, TEXT-TO-SPEECH (<https://>), Robot control, sensor, actuator, Debian Linux, C++, Qt, systemic racism]
- "My personal contributions were mostly in creating QT user interfaces code for controlling the virtual shop and the roboter "ARNI". I also was very much implicated in Software Engineering round-about code such as blackbox code for keeping a BB-blackboard software architecture between our software components and the MySQL database tables used to share some of the data between components of the software system."
- "I also worked on cognitive cartography algorithms using C/C++, together with "ALINA, Christian, Sasha, and SERDAR". I was moving the robot for scanning RFID sensors stapled onto our real test grocery store, and then trying to find a way for the robot-ARNI based on customer commands on the robot that were at entrance to help them find their way into the real test grocery store. I used text-to-speech technology to talk with robot-ARNI to customers. "
- I was also involved in:
1. HELPING in general project organization for instance:
 - A. Writing project meeting minutes.
 - B. Looking for places in train, buses for project week-end ("PROJEKT WOCHELENDE"). Etc.
 2. Searching for places ("Student sleep places – JUGENDHEBERGE") for project-week-end in groups for fasting our project development;
 3. Writing LaTeX documentation for project reports;
 4. Writing JUnit testing code for GUI code;
 5. Writing BASH-scripts for tackling connection problems between actuators and the Debian Linux Operating System (thanks to Christian).
- "Unfortunately I received a grade of only 2.7 (14/20) because I wasn't interested in cartography and cognition algorithms since this was the specialty of "Christian Freksa" and "CoSy Group of Research" (<https://cosy.informatik.uni-bremen.de>)."
- THIS IS THE REASON our project advisors "FRANK dylla", and "LUTZ frommberger" gave as justification to this baddest grade during my entire curriculum in ACADEMIA at all !
- I also need to mention that I was the only "SCHWARZNEGGER – black from africa" in this research group of mainly white-blond-racists like "MICHA", and "STEPHAN"...
- THESE 4 racists-idiot said some day I may not be very comfortable in group working with white-intellectual. I THINK "frommberger the female-male-gay-BORN-male was at origin of such systemic" sexist discrimination around myself; even during my research time under supervision of male-female-chevalie-boivert-PATRICK-lam !
- d. "A SEMANTIC COMPARISON BETWEEN BÜCHI AUTOMA AND TIMED AUTOMATA (Grade 20/20)", AGBS-UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY [09/2004 – 12/2004]
- [Vordiplom in informatik – INDEPENDENT STUDY, Bachelor Independent Study, MATHEMATICS for Computer Science, Theoretical Computer Science, timed automata, büchi automata, timed csp, set algebra]
- I developed a set of transformations functions that take as input a büchi automaton and generates a timed automaton. This work was the 1st work under supervision of "Jan Peleska", at our request, because we had interest in working in avionics software development in his company "Verified Systems International GmbH" (<https://www.verified.de>)."
- It is my uncle maternal "Théodore Wandji Ngongang" who is the one that gave me this advise at that time of my life where I was around 20 years old in Germany; "Just at my 2nd year of University."
- "Finally a small offer a 200 Euros monthly came after I performed 100 % for this work unpaid [details at link 1b], t hat I used as Independent study. "
- e. "1st & 2nd Semester Software Development PROJECT (Grade 18/20)", ST-UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY [09/2002 – 09/2003]
- [“V”-“WATER FALL”-MODEL of Software Development, Software Engineering, Project Requirements, "Gant Diagrams", UML 2.0, XML, PHP, MySQL, JAVA]
- "This 1st and 2nd semester project, divided in 2 parts consisted in creating a multi-user dungeon server (MUD-server) where a virtual world existed; 1st year was used to elicit user software program requirements, and establish "Requirement documents using UML 2.0".
 - "telnet (port 23)" protocol was used as client-server communication mechanism."
 - "I involved myself in a project where I contributed around 7 000 lines of plain JAVA code of program development."

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES – PSY–CARE – UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN

1. Psychological care |
UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY [10/2002 – 07/2007]
- A. "DIPL.–PSYCH. RALF ERIC STREIBL.", MATHEmatics and Computer Science Department, University of Bremen, Germany [10/2002 – 07/2007]
["Dipl.–Psych. Ralf ERIC Streibl".]
"As a student of computer science in the "FB3" of the UNIVERSITY OF Bremen, In city Bremen, HANSEATISCHE-CITY, Germany, WE had a psychologist as 1 of our lecturer called "Dipl.–Psych RALF–idiot Eric Streibl". "
RALF–idiot was kind of very reluctant to discriminative opportunities because I remember having visited courses on web creation based on PHP, and MariaDB, since I WAS having [a student–job (WERKSTUDENT) at "ZMML"].
Eric RALF–idiot also gave myself a so called course titled "PROPÄDEUTIK" where we students learned on how to effectively, clearly present our projects or work; THIS was done in groups and individually !
- B. "AT–HOME–RACIST–IN–BREMEN PROGRAM", Foreigner office–"Sekretariat für AUSLÄNDISCHE studierende", University of Bremen, Germany [JULY 2005 – AUGUST 2017]
["RAÏNER schulze–smidt".]
THIS program was exclusively addressed for foreign country students to gain access to german in–born families in order to accustom one to germany as a home country.
"I joined this program because my maternal uncle "THÉODORE WANDJI" recommended it to myself because He was emigrating to CANADA–montreal, And would have been very far from me. "THÉODORE wandji ngongang" was the one person that welcomed and invited myself to study in BREMEN ! "
AT this effect, each volunteer foreigner student would be connected to a single volunteering family of BREMEN. IN my specific case, I was assigned to the "ARISTOCRATIC"–bürgerliche family "SCHULZE–SMIDT", originating predominantly from HOLLAND into GERMANIA.
MISTER "raïner–schulze–smidt", and his 2nd"SPOUSE GABRIELLE schulze-smidt" were really kind and nice to myself.
"RAINER was "sole investor and proprietor–German–INHABER of an insurance company in Bremen, and in LONDON–great–britain", WHERE he did his apprenticeship as "INSURANCE–business–man". HIS 2nd spouse Gabrielle that I met in person; Was a part–time "physiotherapist" for the football team of Bremen city : "WERDERBREMEN (<https://>)". "
Through them, I could know more about the origins of the autonomous–HANSE–STADT of Bremen, since "GOVERNOR SMIDT" as upper–upper grandfather of "MR. RAÏNER Schulze–Smidt", was governor of BREMEN for 50–years, and is the one person that acquire land from "HANNOVER–autonomous–STATE", to create a water–port–German–haven; "BREMERHAVEN", as a city and port for the autonomous city–federal–STATE of BREMEN.
People and places I visit, and met, through organization of RAINER and GABI :
1.) HIS cousins from Brazil by talk–only & pictures (<https://>); that I DON'T remember family names;
2.) HIS cousins from JOHANNESBURG by talk–only & pictures (<https://>); that I DON'T remember family names, but that are having a wool factory for exportation in the state of BREMEN–recist germania;
3.) VISIT of "evangelic church" on King–JESUS birth day "December 25th";
4.) VISIT of MUSEUM–"Fockemuseum";
5.) VISIT of "musical–theater" in "BREMEN–DOMSHEIDE";
6.) "Bernhadine", "Caspar", "Johann" & "senior sister JULIA" schulze-smidt.
7.) Several friends of them in need of computer technical help in terms of Software installation, and support.
8.) "DOROTHEE" and "her brother Dr. oec. Sebastian Dettmers (<https://>)";
9.) "Kryenhop family" (<https://>) : a leader in industrial transfer And sale of asian food and products into GERMANY :
a.) Father "Rolf";
b.) Daughter "SVANTSKE";
c.) etc.
"I quit this family relationship at request of "RAÏNER" and "his 2nd spouse GABRIELLE-gabi", because they thought I lied to them that I have got a position as a temporary "SOFTWARE DEVELOPER" employee earning "70 000 Euros" annually at "AMADEUS Germany GmbH", Via THE frankfurter human resource company "" . "

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES – PSY-CARE – YERITH-RD-TEST

2. Psychological care |
 COLLÈGE INTEG –FROM-LAQUINTINIE-HOSPITAL-EYOUM-CHRISTIAN-IDIOT-CRIMINAL,
 DOUALA, CAMEROUN [01/2021 – 06/2021]
- A. "DR. (PH.D.) JEAN MOUBEB", Collège Integ –from-LAQUINTINIE-hospital-EYOUM-christian-idiot-criminal,
 Douala, Cameroun [01/2021 – 06/2021]
 ["DR. (Ph.D.) Jean MOUBEB".]

"ROSE sangnou-chienne-génitrice; a sanguinary mégère that is said to have caused a sudden death of her husband THÉODORE noumbissi-idiot; my biological genitor; ORGANIZES that I am brought by force to a psychiatric institute called Douala-laquintie-hospital because we had a talk at her mother's place where I WAS SAYING that I NEED my documents from my real-estate properties be given back to myself by her."

"AS I am currently writing this small report on NOVEMBER 20th, 2024; ALL my belongings weren't given back to me by VICTOR koliou noundou that detains this official documents that I MUST possess by inheritance right as summoned by a judge just after the death of my father and dear genitor THÉODORE noumbissi-idiot."

"INGRID-teuntchou-noumeni-chandriand, born-geboren Ingrid TCHITCHUI noumbissi is trying to take away all my real-estate properties, together with LAURENT-tchandeu free mason !!! "

MAJOR PROFESSIONAL SOCIETAL IMPROVEMENTS I

1. **2003 – 2005:** [ZMML – University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I HAVE ENHANCED LEARNING CAPABILITIES of economics students at the University of Bremen by DEVELOPING WEBSITES AND STUDENT SELF-LEARNING COMPUTER PROGRAMS, together with THE TEAM OF PROFESSOR KLAUS BÖNKOST.
2. **2006:** [FB 3; University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I HAVE created a website for the AFRICAN STUDENT ASSOCIATION "Nasgen e.V (New African Student Generation eingetragener Verein)" !
3. **2006:** [AGBS – University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I HAVE pleaded FORMER CAMEROON STUDENT serge achille fopoussi nono TO COME WITH MYSELF CONTRIBUTE at work research group of PROFESSOR JAN PELESKA.
4. **2006:** [GEWETE GmbH, Rellingen, Hamburg, Germany]: I HAVE completely alone, installed and deployed a networked installation of LaDIVA at a section of "KARLSRUHE city council !", SO TO ALLEVIATE DUTIES OF dear mentor DIPLOM-INGENIEUR (FH) SVEN KAMRATH !
5. **2006:** [GEWETE GmbH, Rellingen, Hamburg, Germany]: I HAVE SUCCESSFULLY pinpoint TU HAMBURG-HARBURG CAMEROON STUDENT david demo noundou TO MR. JENS MÖLLER of GEWETE GmbH ¹, FOR HIM TO HELP MR. DAVID DEMO NOUNDOU with access to FINAL SCHOOL YEAR WORK EXPERIENCE, AND BACHELOR OF SCIENCE THESIS-WORK.
6. **2006:** [University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I could successfully provide "MS WINDOWS SOFTWARE" INSTALLATION, TROUBLESHOOTING, and TRAINING to several GERMAN people because of "DEAR MR. RAINER SCHULZE-SMIDT" and HIS SPOUSE "MS. GABRIELE SCHULZE-SMIDT".
THESE EXPERIENCES WERE VERY POSITIVE FOR my finances !
7. **2005 – 2007:** [AGBS – University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I HAVE CONTRIBUTED TO TESTING EFFORTS BEFORE FIRST LAUNCH OF JET FLIGHT "AIRBUS A380" by my scientific AND engineering contributions in STATISTICAL TEST CASE GENERATION within RT-TESTER software of VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH; THANKS TO MERCIFUL PROFESSOR JAN PELESKA.
8. **2007 – 2009:** [SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS, Erlangen, Bayern, Germany]: I HAVE SUCCESSFULLY MAINTAIN All Oncology Care Systems HOSPITALS customers, throughout the whole planet, ON FRONT-LINE OF problem/defect RESOLUTION WHENEVER technicians on CRITICAL problem phone resolution lines 1, 2, and 3 COULDN'T SOLVE SOFTWARE TECHNICAL ISSUES of linac.
9. **2009 – 2011:** [University of Waterloo, Waterloo, ON, Canada]: I HAVE socially, WITH COMPUTING TECHNOLOGY, helped following afro-descendants from CAMEROON:
 1. CÉLESTIN puene: helped him search on the internet, and call, because of his poor English language knowledge, U.S.A businesses for inquiring on buying trucks for his brother in Cameroon.
 2. FABRICE Kouam Kamdem: maintained and improved an on-line website for FREE for his cameroon oriented professional association.
 3. ALBERT HERVAIS Ngagom Piewe: taught Debian-Linux basic shell command usage, Java and C++ programming on phone and internet.
 4. I HAVE presented orally and given personal written material ON SOFTWARE SECURITY AND SAFETY to CAMEROON ASSOCIATION of migrants in KITCHENER-WATERLOO: "ROWAC".
10. **2012:** [IBM Toronto Software Laboratory, Markham, ON, Canada]: I HAVE INTRODUCED skilled migrant cameroon worker, as ACTUARY in TORONTO, "AUDREY Nguetie Tchamga, B.Sc (Université de Laval, Québec, CANADA)" to use and exploitation of FREE AND OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE (FOSS) "Debian Linux".
11. **2012:** [IBM Toronto Software Laboratory, Markham, ON, Canada]: I HAVE advised, counseled, and even developed an on-line website for fellow CAMEROON expatriate YVES FRANCIS Kamga Mbiele, MBA (ÉCOLE SUPÉRIEURE DE GESTION, Paris) ON HIS ABANDONED PROJECT (WITH DAUGHTER OF FORMER ENERGY MINISTER of cameroon) FOR SOLAR ENERGY PRODUCTION in cameroon.

I WAS INTRODUCED to "YVES FRANCIS Kamga Mbiele, MBA (E.S.G, Paris)" BY MY AUNT-HUSBAND pr. shanda-tonme jean-claude.
12. **YEAR-2012:** I COULD SUCCESSFULLY buy and implement foundations of "IMMEUBLE YERITH_{r&d}" which WILL STEM as a "PREMIER COMPUTING RESEARCH AND "Software Testing & Validation"" center in CENTRAL AFRICA (yaounde, center region, cameroon) !

I BOUGHT THIS PLOT OF LAND FROM hon. THÉODORE DATOUO; vice-president of parliament in YAOUNDE, CENTER REGION IN CAMEROON !

Land title CERTIFICATE nr.: 560 792, in SIMBOK, mfoundi vi (6), vol. 265 !
13. **2014:** [University of Waterloo, Waterloo, ON, Canada]: I HAVE searched information, on how to WELCOME and ACCOMMODATE CAMEROON AMBASSADOR IN OTTAWA, for "ROWAC", a cameroonian ASSOCIATION of high skilled migrants (MOSTLY PROVENING FROM GERMANY) in KITCHENER-WATERLOO.

MAJOR PROFESSIONAL SOCIETAL IMPROVEMENTS II

14. **2021:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]: I HAVE built a partnership with Dr. PETER Akume Ngoe and his societal NGO so to provide his NGO with VERY CHEAP AND APPROPRIATE software solutions for a NGO financed foodstore.
15. **2022:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]: I HAVE SUCCESSFULLY trained Mr. NESTOR Kenfack in ONLY 3 days at basic usage of our ERP software system YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum for hardware shop selling. Mr. NESTOR Kenfack IS ONLY holder of a "B.E.P.C".

USUALLY in Yaounde, a holder of a "B.E.P.C" couldn't be trained to use COMMONLY present ERP SOFTWARE SYSTEMS (e.g.: 'Sage Gescom i7', 'SAP Business One', etc.), BECAUSE THEY ARE MEANT for highly qualified users.

Mr. NESTOR Kenfack HAD NEVER GOT exposure to an ERP system in the past.
16. **2023:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]:
I have given software cyberspace security counsels to Santa Lucia AHALA by talking to a computer technician employee because I could see vulnerabilities at cashier while paying for my goods.
17. **2023:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]:
I have counseled a business owner to start a bigger grocery shop and gave him ideas and ways on how to realize this using YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM, and, also, my unfinished two-storey building.
18. **2023:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]:
I have started YECEFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE), so to improve computing skills of fellow citizen, and also, of any other person that conforms to Cameroon laws !
20. **2024:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]:
I try to have SANTA-LUCIA-AHALA AS 1 OF MY CLIENT THESE COMING YEARS so to have YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM there working instead of 'Odo'.
So they (SANTA-LUCIA-AHALA) will contribute in improving quality by thorough usage of this new platinum-platform.
21. **2024:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]:
I am now working with ALT PLUS in YDE-AHALA so to have a working Supermarket in one, Instead "of a hardware-shop + a food-store separately, BUT JOINED physically".

MAJOR PROFESSIONAL COMPUTING RESEARCH ACHIEVEMENTS I

1. **YEAR-2005:** IMPLEMENTATION OF the JAVA servlet XML parsing and saving server "LaDIVA", AND ITS GUI (JAVA-SWING) configuration and installer program; for GEWETE GmbH !
2. **YEAR-2006:** IMPLEMENTATION OF "MESO"; the IMPROVED and revised version of the XML parsing and saving server "LaDIVA" for GEWETE GmbH !
3. **YEAR-2006:** IMPLEMENTATION OF the library computer systems communication protocol SIPv2 for GEWETE GmbH vending machines !
4. **YEAR-2005:** INVENTION OF A PROCEDURE TO systematically transform A BÜCHI AUTOMATON into A TIMED AUTOMATON ! TASK COORDINATED BY SHAREHOLDER PROF. DR. RER. NAT. HABIL. JAN PELESKA, of VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH !
5. **YEAR-2006:** CREATION OF (with higher study part team CogAg of the University of Bremen [Cognitive Systems Group led by DEAR LATE PROFESSOR CHRISTIAN FREKSA]) ROBOT "arnie"; AND PROCEDURES TO automatically map a supermarket both geographically AND store item-wise with RFID technology by HELP OF A ROLLING ROBOT "arnie" !
6. **YEAR-2007** [FB 3! AGBS: Diplom-Informatiker (Dipl.-Inf.)]: IMPLEMENTATION OF statistical uniformly distributed test cases generation for HAREL-statecharts ! COMMERCIALIZED BY VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH !
7. **YEAR-2007:** [FB 3! AGBS: University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I HAVE CONTRIBUTED TO TESTING EFFORTS BEFORE FIRST LAUNCH OF JET FLIGHT "AIRBUS A380" by my scientific AND engineering contributions in STATISTICAL TEST CASE GENERATION within RT-TESTER software of VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH; THANKS TO MERCIFUL PROFESSOR JAN PELESKA.
8. **YEAR-2008:** IMPLEMENTATION OF the communication and control protocol DIGITAL MEVATRON INTERFACE PROTOCOL (DMIP) version 13 for THE LINEAR ACCELERATOR "linac" of SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS, Oncology Care Systems (OCS) !
9. **YEAR-2009:** Stopping my career; AFTER 21 MONTHS; as JUNIOR SOFTWARE DEVELOPER at SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS (Oncology Care Systems) in ERLANGEN, BAYERN, GERMANY; with 0 defects / faults returning FROM CUSTOMERS because OF non achievement protocol repair ! Award saying from BOSS GERHARD SENG; MY TEAM LEAD !
10. **YEAR-2011** [ECE! Ph.D. in Computer Science]: I HAVE INVENTED AND INTRODUCED A PRACTICAL AND SIMPLE STATIC ANALYSIS BY ITERATIVE DATAFLOW ANALYSIS, to check temporal safety properties, expressed with tracematches, of JAVA programs !
THIS TECHNIQUE HAS BEEN USED in following:
 1. (* Similarly, but as a dynamic analysis technique) MASC thesis (2011; submitted at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA), OF ASSISTANT PROFESSOR JON Eyolfson of the UNIVERSITY OF TORONTO, ON, CANADA !
EVEN THOUGH JON Eyolfson MASC (COMPUTER ENGINEERING) SUBMISSION WAS EARLIER THAN MY Ph.D. in SOFTWARE ENGINEERING THESIS DEFENSE, because of finding an examiner (reporting) within ECE DEPARTMENT, I AM THE ONE THAT GAVE A PROTOTYPE DESIGN AND PROTOTYPE DOCUMENT FOR HIS SUBMISSION !
11. **YEAR-2012:** I COULD SUCCESSFULLY DEVELOP manual and automatic BASH (Bourne Again SHell) programs (scripts), THAT LEAD TO A 0.5% improvement of WEBSPHERE computing performance !
12. **YEAR-2013:** CREATION OF A RUNTIME dynamic taint analysis for the QUERCUS PHP INTERPRETER !
13. **YEAR-2015:** FIRST WORLD-WIDE OPEN-SOURCE (foss) RELEASE OF AN LLVM-BASED ON INTERMEDIATE REPRESENTATION (IR) static iterative KILDALL (gary kildall) DATAFLOW ANALYSIS named 'YERITH-SAINT' !
'YERITH-SAINT': <https://www.github.com/sazzad114/saint> !
14. **YEAR-2015:** CREATION OF A CONTEXT-SENSITIVE FLOW-SENSITIVE tainted paths generation algorithm by iterative dataflow analysis !
THIS TECHNIQUE HAS BEEN USED in following:
 1. (* EXACT same technique) PH.D. dissertation / thesis IN COMPUTER SCIENCE (2020; submitted at VIRGINIA TECH, VA, U.S.A), OF ASSISTANT PROFESSOR SAZZADUR Ahaman AT University of Arizona, Tucson, AZ, U.S.A !
 2. PH.D. dissertation / thesis IN COMPUTER SCIENCE (2020; submitted at the UNIVERSITY OF CALIFORNIA, SANTA BARBARA, CA, U.S.A), OF ASSISTANT PROFESSOR ARAVIND Machiry AT Purdue University, IN, U.S.A !
15. **YEAR-2020:** FIRST OFFICIAL RETESTED RELEASE OF THE full featured OPEN SOURCE enterprise resource planing software "YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE"; FIRST OFFICIAL RELEASE OF THE OPEN SOURCE AUTOMATED BACKUP-SYSTEM AND ALERT ("yerith-erp-3.0"-system-daemon": <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0>) !

"YERITH-ERP-PGI-standalone, server, academic, client" ARE THE DIFFERENT VERSIONS OF THIS FOSS-ERP-PGI-FRENCH !

SERVER AND CLIENT are mainly meant for a supermarket having several cashiers offices, AND A SERVER directing MYSQL-commercial options in common for different client-cashier-OFFICES !

ACADEMIC is meant for use WITH an IN-MEMORY DATABASE like "SQLite" !
16. **YEAR-2021:** First stable release of YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE at PHARMACY FIANGO LYCÉE MAKÈPÈ !

MAJOR PROFESSIONAL COMPUTING RESEARCH ACHIEVEMENTS II

17. **YEAR-2022:** FIRST DELIVERY OF a compendium OF DOCUMENTS concerning OUR ERP SOFTWARE-SYSTEM YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE !
<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>
18. **YEAR-2022:** CREATION OF AN OPEN SOURCE state transition diagram LIBRARY FOR RUNTIME DATAFLOW VERIFICATION (YR_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF) (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif))
20. **YEAR-2022:** MODIFICATION OF A Free Open Source Software (FOSS) "QVGE" (<https://showroom.qt.io/qvge-qt-visual-graph-editor>) TO DESIGN state diagram TEMPORAL SAFETY PROPERTIES ! "YR_QVGE" ! YR_QVGE is a commercial tool of mine priced at 3 000 EUROS a single executable copy.
21. **YEAR-2022:** CREATION OF AN OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE FRAMEWORK for runtime dataflow analysis (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF | YR_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF) (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif) | 🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif))!
22. **YEAR-2022:** I have added a runtime check verification view within FOSS-ERP ("YERITH-ERP-3.0-SERVER": 🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0)) IN ORDER TO VIEW LOG MESSAGES SENT TO YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF !
23. **YEAR-2022:** CREATION of a systematic method, AND / OR PROCEDURE TO TEST AND / OR verify dataflow of thick-client (or web application), AGAINST A SAFETY TEMPORAL PROPERTY SPECIFICATION expressed as a STATE DIAGRAM (modified mealy machine) !
24. **YEAR-2022:** FIRST OFFICIAL REPORT in FRENCH LANGUAGE OF ACTIVITIES of YERITH R&D SINCE RELEASE OF FIRST STABLE VERSION OF YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum!
"REPORT in french: <https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051568/>" !
25. **YEAR-2023:** creation of a domain-specific language (YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG) to describe *state diagram mealy machines* (📄 [SDMM](#)).
26. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION with flex and bison OF A DOMAIN-SPECIFIC LANGUAGE COMPILER to create source C++ code files for YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang)).
27. **YEAR-2023:** SUBMISSION OF A FULL TECHNICAL PAPER ("YR_DB_RUNTIME_VERIF: A FRAMEWORK FOR VERIFYING SQL CORRECTNESS PROPERTIES OF GUI SOFTWARE AT RUNTIME") TO SPLASH-ICTSS 2023 CONFERENCE in May 2023.
28. **YEAR-2023:** Implementation of more than 2-states *state diagram mealy machine* (📄 [SDMM](#)) in YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif)), and YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif)).
29. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION of guarded condition expression specification within YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif)), and automated code generation of guarded condition expression in YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang)).
30. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION OF EMPLOYEE PAY GROUP within YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum.
31. **YEAR-2023:** First release of our CASE (Computer-Aided Software Engineering) drawing design tool "📄 [YRI_QVGE](#)" official commercial document.
32. **YEAR-2023:** online ENGLISH INTO FRENCH, and vice versa LANGUAGE TRANSLATION within YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum.
33. **YEAR-2023:** CREATION of a viewing graphical user interface application for YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF in JUNE.
34. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION OF FIRST RELEASE OF automatic EMPLOYEE PAY GROUP SALARY CALCULATION. Cumulated pay groups for a single employee salary calculation is included.
35. **YEAR-2023:** CREATION OF a user's guide for YERITH_QVGE.
36. **YEAR-2023:** STARTED IMPLEMENTATION OF a user sample project AUTOMATIC binary executable generation in YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.
37. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION OF MULTIPLE programs under analysis (PUA) monitoring within YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.
38. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION OF MULTIPLE runtime monitors WITHIN A SINGLE EXECUTABLE for YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.
39. **YEAR-2023:** STARTED journal article (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8381187>) for STTT official journal release.
40. **YEAR-2023:** started a predicate logic for deriving SOFTWARE RECOVERY ACTIONS for sdmm ("state diagram mealy machine").
41. **YEAR-2023:** started writing YERITH R&D 2023 *annual report* (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/10515549>).
42. **YEAR-2024:** finished writing YERITH R&D 2023 *annual report*: THIS REPORT specifically says that CPDM ruling party has tried to destroy my life using *CHRISTIAN eyoum* (<https://scholar.google.fr/citations?user=eHvsI1UAAAAJ&hl=fr>).
43. **YEAR-2024:** started writing courses curricula and content for several courses of [YECEFOIQ](https://www.yecefoiq-sarl.cm) (<https://www.yecefoiq-sarl.cm>).
44. **YEAR-2024:** started creation of a web site application for teaching computer science center YECEFOIQ.
45. **YEAR-2024:** I have implemented case insensitive search for financial expenses list within YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.
46. **YEAR-March 2024:** I have paused new features in YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM (I.E.: Human resource management, and Financial Accounting management) due to advancements required for their quality assurance, WITH 📄 [YRI_QVGE!](#)

MAJOR PROFESSIONAL COMPUTING RESEARCH ACHIEVEMENTS III

47. **YEAR-March 2024:** I could finally find 1 company commercial that rented my 1st 3-bedrooms apartment in DLA for "90 000 Xaf" monthly !
48. **YEAR-March 2024:** I have paid "50 000 Xaf" as starting advance funds for incorporating **YERITH R&D SARL**.
49. **YEAR-March 2024:** I am recruiting 1 commercial financial entrepreneur for ~~YECEFOHQ~~ (LOOKING for investment funds).
50. **YEAR-JUNE 25, 2024:** Returning client N.K hardware shop for YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0 !
51. **YEAR-2024:** Refining automatic stock CSV data entry.
52. **YEAR-JULY 29, 2024:** Still training "Christelle Akamba" for just 1 000 Francs an hour.
THERE is no money outside in Yaounde; and my rental apartments are still not having renters due to LAURENT TCHANDEU that I know has been trying to disrupt my activities in the open source software (OSS) era.
53. **YEAR-September 08, 2024:** *I AM working on ground to perfection building YERITH.*
THERE is lack of funding even though I could have my judicial affair against CHRISTIAN-EYOUM and others to get sent back to NDOKOTI prosecutor.
UNFORTUNATELY attorney SYNCLAIRE-NJEUTCHA-TCHANA has been trying to disrupt my activities with some money-bribery he received from genitor-organizer of assassination of mine !!!
I now try to get ATTORNEY-tchonang-albertine on my side these days. C.P.D.M wolfgang owona idiot political party has been trying to take down all my activities so to destroy a non-gay citizen.
54. **YEAR-2024:** Incorporating unit of measure like gram, etc. for inventory stock entry creation and pricing.
55. **YEAR-2024:** Started incorporating Financial debt entries creation in **YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM**.
I am also specifying **YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME** for a new idea as good-physical stock exchange start-up marketplace idea.
56. **YEAR-NOVEMBER 2024:** I have re-introduced new color schemes for **YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME**, AND also started a document for SPECIFYING and DESCRIBING the already existing and ALREADY IMPLEMENTED: C++ runtime monitoring verification library **SDMM (STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE)** :
1. YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF : [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif) ;
 2. ITS usage as algorithmic trading stock exchange library and runtime monitoring engine with help of a FOSS **"STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE"** (https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf) monitoring container for real-timing.
57. **YEAR-JANUARY 2025:** *I have incorporated "FR", "EN", USA-american flag and FRANCE-flag onto YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM so to hint users on Translation from English into FRENCH; And vice versa.*
58. **YEAR-JANUARY 2025:** *We are trying to render incorporating of **sdmm[1d]** as plug-gable dynamic libraries into YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.*
59. **YEAR-FebRUARY 2025:** *[I am also trying to check conformant thread calls from runtime QT-QTimer instances whenever a user tries to cancel his modification / insertion work; FOR instance a special case is whenever 'INSERT/UPDATE' button is pressed and then there is intermingling with the checking mechanism introduced for verifying whether a user cancels his work on the window frame or not !]*
60. **YEAR-March 2025:** *I am struggling with INGRID-own-sister that digest all time my genitor because of 6 children with less than 2 years separation birth time between them !*
61. **YEAR-April 2025:** *Currently doing major research & inspection work for a web shop by using partly our; At YERITH R&D, new invention WYSIWYG-Tool for web HTML pages (YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL) !*
62. **YEAR-April 2025:** *NO body originating from West Cameroon seems to be living peacefully in CMR with bulu tribe since event a ["**president bulu of the republic**"] is embezzling young researcher in science and / or engineering like myself so to perpetuate going to IMF-fucking-idiot to pertain African in under poverty world for ever-devilish !*
63. **YEAR-May 2025:** *[JUDGE yager] seems to think of taking my complaint more seriously these days since I was advised to meet another justice attorney working a kind of on my file; Directly this coming 20th week of year 2025 (May-12 up to May-16) !*
64. **YEAR-May 2025:** *Eyoum Christian sends even people as kind fo rental management agent into my house to act so to hijack myself again : "**Soumbil**" living here at Cité-des-Palmiers.*
65. **YEAR-May 2025:** *[I am also these days trying to incorporate a dynamic taint analysis within YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum as an instance incarnation of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF and / or "SDMM" specification & accompanying source code.]*
66. **YEAR-May 2025:** *We are working on our 1st prototype complete product that automatically generates a webshop from QT-trolltech user-interface files again this month; We plan a travel abroad !*
67. **YEAR-May 2025:** *[Soumbil, a molester of myself via a so called paternal uncle-gay-hijacker seems to not understand that as a mature researcher professional, And born-again Christian; There is no need for myself to talk with non sense village-babouantou-born people like KOLIOU-gay-idiot VICTOR-noundou !]*
68. **YEAR-JUNE 5, 2025:** Currently refactoring YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum !
69. **YEAR-JUN.-NOV., 2025:** *I am solely working on all projects so to try having YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum in the software program market starting JAN. 2026 !*

20.20 'VALKYRIE' upgrade to DEBIAN BULLSEYE (11.0); QT-5

VALGRIND USER INTERFACE: *valkyrie* (<https://www.valgrind.org/downloads/guis.html>)

July 2023

- Free open source code:
https://www.github.com/yerothd/valkyrie_NON_OFFICIAL

'VALKYRIE' is a dynamic analysis CASE tool for verifying memory errors, and using VALGRIND as backend program server for analysis.

21.21 CONTEXT SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM ("YERITH-SAINT")

October 2009 – March 2015

- Free open source code:
<https://www.github.com/sazzad114/saint>

'YERITH-SAINT' is a static taint analysis that computes tainted paths in C programs and that doesn't require any program annotations. 'YERITH-SAINT' is built upon the iterative dataflow framework and has been implemented using the LLVM compiler infrastructure. 'YERITH-SAINT' is interprocedural, flow-sensitive, and developers can choose to run it either with context-sensitivity or without. THE HEARTBLEED bug (april 2014; security breach in open ssl 1.0.1f) IS A POTENTIAL FINDING OF yerith-saint.

22.22 YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE

ERP SOFTWARE SYSTEM 'YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum'

Mars 2015 – Currently

- Free open source code:
🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0)

'YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE' is a FOSS (FREE AND OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE) ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANING SOFTWARE !

23.23 YERITH-ERP-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON

'YERITH-ERP-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON': AUTOMATED ALERT, AND DB-BACKUP SYSTEM FOR 'YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum'

Mars 2015 – Currently

- Free open source code:
🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)

'YERITH-ERP-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON' is a FOSS (FREE AND OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE) AUTOMATED ALERT, AND DATABASE BACKUP SYSTEM FOR FOSS-ERP YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE !

24.24 YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF

'YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF': C++ Library FOR RUNTIME MONITORING (Safety Temporal Properties) FOR State Diagram MONITORING !

June 2022 – Currently

- Free open source code:
🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif)

'YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF' is a FOSS (FREE AND OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE) C++ library, THAT ENABLES TO IMPLEMENT STATE DIAGRAM SAFETY TEMPORAL PROPERTY RUNTIME CHECKING (and/or VERIFICATION).

25.25 YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF

'YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF': RUNTIME VERIFICATION OF TEMPORAL SAFETY PROPERTIES IN 'YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE'

June 2022 – Currently

- Free open source code:
🔗 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif)
- YERITH-ERP-9.0 DOCTORAL COMPENDIUM:
<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>

'YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF' is a FOSS (FREE AND OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE), AND REUSABLE DYNAMIC RUNTIME ANALYSIS AND TESTING INFRASTRUCTURE created for FOSS ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANING SOFTWARE 'YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE' !

26.26 [YRI_QVGE](#)

'YRI_QVGE': Design and Creation of Runtime SAFETY TEMPORAL PROPERTIES FOR State diagram MONITORING C++ Library
'YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF' !

2,500 Euros a single executable copy FOR DEBIAN-LINUX
June 2022 - Currently

27.27 [YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE](#): an enterprise (management / financial) Resource Planing Software

ERP SOFTWARE SYSTEM 'YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE: an enterprise (management / financial) Resource Planing Software'

PRICE DEPENDS ON installations ! (STARTS AT 200,000 XAF per node-computer; ONLY AVAILABLE FOR DEBIAN-LINUX)
Mars 2015 - Currently

(GRADUATE) STUDENTS ADVISING / COUNSELING

- 1.) ["AMIRHOSSEIN VAKILI"], Ph.D. (www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~avakili) (COMPUTER SCIENCE, DAVID R. CHERITON SCHOOL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA)
- 2.) ["DAVID DEMO NOUNDOU"], BACHELOR OF SCIENCE, INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY, TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF HAMBURG-HARBURG, HAMBURG, GERMANY
- 3.) ["DIVAM JAIN"], M.MATH (<https://www.uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/handle/10012/7943>) (COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA) 2013
- 4.) [Dr "ERIC BREFO-MENSAH"], M.SC (Waterloo) (<https://www.uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/handle/10012/13341>) (CHEMISTRY, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA) 2018
- 5.) [Dr "ESTHER ELIZABETH LAMBERT"], M.SC (Waterloo) (<https://ca.linkedin.com/in/esther-lambert-5b869414>) (GEOGRAPHY, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA) 2009
- 6.) ["Basser (from Syria)"], MAsc (ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING, ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE MONTRÉAL, QC, CANADA) 2008
- 7.) ["FABRICE tchoumi"], MAsc (ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING (AVIONICS), ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE MONTRÉAL, QC, CANADA) 2007 – 2008
- 8.) ["FELIX FANG"], MAsc (<https://www.patricklam.ca/papers/15.pppj.af-analysis.pdf>) (SOFTWARE ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA) 2014
- 9.) Dr. rer. nat. "HASHIM CHUNPIR" (<https://www.igi-global.com/affiliate/hashim-chunpir/324991>) (MSC, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY) 2005 – 2006
- 10.) DR.-ING. DIPL.-INF. "SERGE ACHILLE FOPOUSSI NONO", (DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY) 2004 – 2006
- 11.) "DERRICK FIEDLER (born YAPI YAPO)", (DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY) 2004 – 2006
- 12.) "INES NGAKOU TEMOU", (BACHELOR OF SCIENCE, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY) 2004 – 2006
- 13.) "DAVID KAMGA ADAMO", (DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY) 2004 – 2006
- 14.) C++ MATRIX programming : "Dr. MOHAMED RIDHA MAHFOUDHI", MBA, PhD (Financial Engineering, University of Laval, QC, Canada). 08 / 2009
- 15.) www.assiw.com; "MARCELLIN TAALY" (<https://www.tally-tech.com>), (DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY)
- 16.) "MATTHIAS (from Germany)", DIPLOM-INGENIEUR (FH); INFORMATIK-INGENIEUR, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY
- 17.) "Virginie kamche" (<https://www.virginie-kamche.de>), DIPLOM-INFORMATIKERIN; COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY
- 18.) "MAÏMOUNA BAMBA" (https://www.linkedin.com/authwall?trk=gf&trkInfo=AQFQXYFtwV7oPgAAAZpFVPT4EKXGTEW7GH101CD4u_8N1S0xGKwMs5KN2sOZJwAIdn182N7jf-ZVEP0M88eq9AJpMymzhwyCmFnDfOVkLrgeYIiR8GwDj91RrPXUtYQsjgqcSZI=&original_referer=https://www.google.com/&sessionRedirect=https%3A%2F%2Fwww.linkedin.com%2Fpub%2Fdir%2FBamba%2FMaimouna) (from COTE-D'IVOIRE), DIPLOM-INFORMATIKERIN; COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY
- 19.) ["Dr. Vajih MONTAGHAMI, Ph.D. "] (Ph.D. (<https://www.uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/>)) (SOFTWARE ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA)
- 20.) ["JON EYOLFSON", Ph.D.] (M.Asc. / Ph.D. (<https://www.uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/handle/10012/6206>)) (SOFTWARE ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA)
- 21.) "THÉOPHILE TCHIENCHO", DIPLOM-INGENIEUR (FH), INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY, UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED SCIENCES, BREMEN, GERMANY

FAMILY THAT I DON'T KNOW WHEREABOUT - I

1. SHANDA family as a destructive life for BOTH noumbissi, and NGONGANG and whereabouts families

"SHANDA Ndjatie Dorothee, and her spouse official TONME-shanda-JEAN-claude" are the 1st persons that started destruction of my life by coming into my family with so called psychiatrist, via WOLFGANG-owona.

"OWONA wolfgang" seemed to getting married with ANGELA which is a cousin maternal of mine because HE WANTS to sell my soul to AMERICAN USA societies in the sense that HE put myself into troubles via GOVERNMENTS AGENCIES, all of them Are linked to secret services to which he belongs, as I HAVE HEARD from ANGELA myself.

Frequently, HE idiot wife says he traveled to USA, so he would talk to people that want my OPEN SOURCE entrepreneurial adventures to be stopped; GET money from them, Then organize hijacking with following agencies:

- 1.) Social Services; so I AM NO MORE independent in the state of biya-regime;
- 2.) HOSPITAL like "laquintinie", etc.

Dr.-wolfgang, which is born from MINISTER owona-joseph-deceased, And mother as daughter of MINISTER owona-Gregoire has tried to put Rosicrucian organization AMORC into my life via Angela who proposed to me to join a so called "lectorium-rosicrucae" based at external relations ministry Where WOLFGANG attends with her.

2. WAAH (anne), spouse Kemmegni, is a subject of BIYA SPOUSE !!!

This 'megere' of my grand mother mother's side; Tchuitchui-ELIZABETH;

Is obviously a devilish demon that possesses super-natural powers in dark kingdoms; Based of 3 sacred objects I have last seen in her house in Byemassi-YDE.

1. "Buffle" horns as a representation of Money-laundry-BAPHOMET-satan
2. 2 turtles carapaces in the back of the "Buffle" horns.
3. 2 portraits of girls invoking and respectively crying;

3. "SANGO, spouse Bernadette Noundou" IS SOMEWHAT a suspect at origin of this family tragedy !!!

This pseudo-suspect seems to want to acquire my place at KING.

Laurent tchandeu ministry plenipotentiary is a subject of itself at Batchieu-Babouantou kings places.

Obviously, every member of GRAND-FATHER noundou nuclear family is a subject to this GUJA.

FAMILY THAT I DON'T KNOW WHEREABOUT - II

4. "Victor Koliou NOUNDOU" IS A NOBODY into my life;

THIS idiot, junior brother of my deceased late father "Théodore Noubissi" is contacting people INCLUDING "derek rayside (drayside@uwaterloo.ca)" (Already talking with other ignorant paternal unwanted uncle "Jules NTETA noundou (julesnteta@gmail.com; julesnteta@yahoo.fr)" from Cameroon external research criminal agency (DGRE));

The idiot Victor presents itself as a chief of a family where I am supposed to belong with some faked official documents from uncle politician LAURENT tchandeu-IDIOT.

OFFICIAL registered document that "Victor KOLIOU NOUNDOU" refused to give a copy to myself when I asked him about, since I am the only, according to documents written by my late grand-father Michel NOUNDOU, Legitimate SUPERVISOR OF HIS left over to children and descendants, WEALTH AND MATERIAL POSSESSIONS !

"Afriland first-bank" and "Intelligentsia employee "Jean-PAUL-yamtche"; And CEO currently as of April 2024", A person that I really don't really know whereabouts in his genealogy or affiliation to my late grand-father; "Jean-PAUL-yamtche" owns a big storey house just opposite face of our main common house entrance in Babouantou idiot village !

"Afriland first-bank" and Intelligentsia MAIN CREATOR AND INSPIRATORY person; "Dr. PAUL fokam-kammogne", was, according to sayings of my genitor Rose Sangnou, 1 of an intimate friend of my late father and genitor "Théodore NOUMBISSI" !

"LAURENT tchandeu and Rose Sangnou" went to a place of "CCEI-bank (former company name and source of AFRILAND FIRST-BANK)", according to "Rose Sangnou" told myself in person when I reached age 32; That they ("LAURENT Tchandeu my paternal uncle" and "Rose SANGNOU" my genitor) gave money (BRIBED) to an employee of "CCEI-BANK" where "late Théodore NOUMBISSI" owed "4 000 000 XAF" at his death so that MORTGAGE ("hypothèque" in French) on his property-land in BONABERI-DLA (700 m²) would be erased everywhere in computers and documents of former 'CCEI-bank' !

"LAURENT tchandeu and Rose Sangnou" also told me, after I had an employment interview with "Dr. PAUL fokam-kammogne"; that my later genitor and father "Théodore NOUMBISSI" is the one, together with "HUGUES NTOMANI TIAKO", his business partner and soul-mate at that former ancient time, THAT computerized totally all enterprises businesses of "CCEI-bank (former company name and source of AFRILAND FIRST-BANK)" !

I remember seeing my late father only 1 time in a day, around 19 : 00 at diner time; this is before we moved to Yaounde in year 1990; After he quits "CA-CORP (Computer Associates Corporation)-DLA" to open and manage solely "CA-CORP (Computer Associates Corporation)-YDE" !

5. "LAURENT tchandeu (ltchandeu@yahoo.fr)" ASSASSINATES in an hospital "THEODORE noumbissi"; late father of mine on January 1992;

AS an orphan at age of 7.5 years old, I remember uncle paternal Laurent came into our biggest house in YDE-Essos to settle in the secondary apartment at the back of our house.

6. "LAURENT tchandeu" Tries with "Hugues Ntomani Tiako" "VIA judith ngaleu in Etobicoke (Toronto, Ontario, Canada)" to crash "my Toyota Corolla LE-2003" in December 2013

This sorcerer freemason ("Hugues Ntomani Tiako"), and Christian-so-called-ORTHODOX-catholic of Roma, acknowledges that IT SHALLN'T be that I gain cause in the court of justice process THAT I have against "LAQUINTINIE and SED", that sent 9 people, including "Christian Eyoum, MD, PsyD"; in February 2021 at night around 23 : 30, to hijack and attempts to kill myself.

SED sent myself 1 time in a CABANON Because they receive 15,000 FCFA from "Henri Bertrand Ngatchou and my genitor ROSE Sangnou", IN douala 2018.

"Galax Yves Landry Etoga" is personally, as a CPDM political party member, AND not as a SED authority implicated in trying to kill myself through psychiatry and / or any other means !

"Laurent Tchandeu (assassin of Ingrid's father and his elder brother in Babouantou-village)" is the one that connected "Ingrid TEUNTCHOU NOUMENI", born (geboren in German) TCHITCHUI NOUMBISSI; my uterine sister, to marry officially "THE IDIOT AND PSY-CHILD since age 12 CHANDRIAND TEUNTCHOU NOUMENI".

7. "LAURENT tchandeu" Deems and Dares OR-DONATES to squeeze my financial money income VIA genitor of mine "Rose SANGNOU" Since September 2023 until TODAY.

8. "***JULES NTETA NOUNDOU extremely dangerous person" is a consanguine brother (same father; another, still living mother, in same marriage) of "LAURENT tchandeu"; And his helper in almost everything dirty and / or clean here in CMR!

FAMILY THAT I DON'T KNOW WHEREABOUT - III

9. ("Derek Rayside drayside@uwaterloo.ca") pays money to MATHGENEALOGY.ORG project so that an equivalence to my "Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering degree from UWATERLOO", will be turned from PhD into the non-academic degree ABD; just 2 weeks after talking with "JULES NTETA NOUNDOU" at his dirty-office in "YDE-élig-esssono"
10. "David demo noundou" tries to connect me to Laurent external security research agent "Jean-Daniel-tujilo-tchokote"; "VIA his natal village idiot babouantou friend Célestin puene (cpuene@cscmonavenir.ca)".
11. "David demo noundou" has written documents in Germany that I was mentally ill while staying 3 days in his rental apartment in September 2018.
12. "David demo noundou" is A student of myself at the TUHH; benjamin brother of my late father "THEODORE noumbissi"; since I could help him get an bachelor internship At "GEWETE GmbH", Where I was working while a student at Bremen University state.
13. "LAURENT tchandeu" was a "Minister Plenipotentiary of Cameroon Embassies in France, Belgium, etc. for around 30 years outside of Cameroon". Especially promoted sent outside Cameroon 1 year after assassinating his elder brother "THEODORE noumbissi".
14. "Henri Bertrand Ngatchou" tries to physically arrest and violates myself in front of at least 7 other people in his private residence of Bankepche-Bangou with no apparent reason other than humiliate myself.

"Henri Bertrand Ngatchou" vows a personal and individual cult to 'Shanda Owona Biya', especially as an appointed, not applied CPDM (RDPC) political party, vice-president in Bankepche-Bangou; with "Honorable Datouo Theodore" as his president.

15. "**RODRIGUE alain sienchié ngongang (sienchie@gmail.com)**", Ancient psychiatric patient in Düsseldorf-Germany Sends messages everywhere So I could again be hijacked into a Cabanon-cell FOR mad-ill-people; "Xavier Noumbissi Noundou" paid in total amount 2,000 Euros to help him get back "to his paternal family NGONGANG" in Deido-Dla-CMR !
16. "**Théodore Wandji Ngongang, And Aurélie Kamdoum Yano his spouse (takouengongang@yahoo.ca; ngongangtietie@yahoo.ca)**", ows myself around "1 500 EUROS" since year 2005 as he fled out from Germany to emigrates into "Montréal-Côtes-des-neiges" !
17. "**Idiot Angéla Tchamou Shanda Wolfgang Owona (krauserminrex@gmail.com)**", a maternal cousin of mine, tries to hijack myself in buses because She deems being a very important personality ("VIP") in front of myself.

"HER spouse Dr Wolfgang Junior Fernand Owona" was making her ("Angéla Tchamou Shanda Owona") come to myself and harassed me with: "Wolfgang wants to be president of the republic" !

This idiot of Wolfgang is the grandson mother side of "Grégoire Owona", who was implicated in the sudden death of his former colleague "Theodore Noumbissi (Late father of mine)".

"Grégoire Owona" is today inviting "my remaining genitor Rose SANGNOU" to his village houses in "Gomedzap-Center-Region-CMR"; so to think her How to destroy my life as a black and renowned scientist universally from the University of Waterloo; THIS in conjunction with former uni colleagues such as "Dr. PATRICK lam"; etc. "Grégoire Owona" -

For 2 days now (November 23, 2025.); my profile is down at MATHGENEALOGY.ORG project; And at same time I felt several people trying to hijack my person here in Cameroon because a certain "#PASTOR-landry ENTERS MY PERSONAL HOME WITH A WEAPON."

In cameroon, as I have heard from people in background, CRIMINAL-ASSASSIN FROM yves-galax-landry Wear name PASTOR.

Derek Rayside has put back a vietnamese idiot on my file at MATHGENEALOGY.ORG project so that I cannot be upwell in Cameroon.

My official university of waterloo graduate transcripts says:

"Program: Engineering Doctoral;

"PhD" Comprehensive Examination.

Status: Completed

Date Completed: 12/20/2011

In good english: "Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering ("PhD" in Electrical & Computer Engineering)".

In french language: Docteur-Ingénieur (Dr.-Ing.).

IT means I must also have *Ph.D.* exactly as My former room colleague Jon Eyolfson that is since 2022 an Assistant Professor in Teaching only at the University of Toronto, ON.

18. **"S2TBED main proprietor-ally A SO-called gangster-Simplice-KAMENI was seen 2 days ago here in a luxurious car by myself.**

"IMMEDIATELY, today, *"/Friday-Sep.-27th, & Saturday-Sep.-28th/*, both days in year 2024, I and neighborhood start again to experience energy supply disruption for more than 4 hours."

SIMPLICE KAMENI seems to be a cocaine dealer that works on laundering money through usage of wood processing & wood sale activities via intermediary White-racist-extremist—italian so-called "MARCO".

ALSO, I could experience certain "neggers" working there from far-north cameroun coming along my foot way to dance kind of like I am their aid.

KAMENI simplice is also implicated in financing together with my cousin culprit-theodore-MOISE-tebiwo-yamkam my properties entirely in Cameroon; Starting year 2013 when TEBIWO-yamkam-moise traveled to Canada.

BOTH moise-yamkam-tebiwo, and SIMPLICE-kameni-ebacka; are sleeping in so-called orgy-sexist-FRANCK-biya gay personal property estate here in YAOUNDE.

19. **"HONORÉ WUCHE, a genitor of mine Spouse; ", EVENTHOUGH her cousin uterin, as hijacker into my life.**

"THIS honore-wouche has been calling me on my phone cell while I was a doctor of Engineering working on my doctoral Ph.D. degree in year 2013; GIVEN TO HIM BY ROSE sangnou."

HONORÉ WUCHE has lost already at least two wives he got kids with them as a guja.

HIS uterine cousin "Rodrigue Alain NGONGANG SIENCHIE", that tried to break my neck last August 2024 while I was attending home for 4 weeks and visiting faked "church Chapelle De la GLOIRE-DE-CHRIST by FAKED-devilish-racist-bassa pastor-so-called MARK-DJENG-DJENG";

Said to myself in front of honore-wouche that: 'SEND "xavier-noundou-ph.d." Again to MAD-person cell at "laquintinie" AS you did twice at least; I didn't even knew who was this gay-honore-wouche with black tattooed wrist-arm-bracelet for gangster and riders.

IT seems this cousin of my mother-genitor; together with another man-lady-cousin-uterine so called NANA; are working on molesting myself in life here in Cameroon; HE-honore-wouche told me laughing that 1 of his daughter was working in south-cameroon in farming for PAUL-biya-family.

20. **"Bulu-Sud-East-Akan tribe AS stealer in CMR"**

- Year 1983 was changed into year 1985-(*ingrid-teuntchou-noumbissi birth year*) so to allow later on a hijack of my property via a marriage to a uterine sister; Called "INGRID-teuntchou-noumeni", Born-geboren "Ingrid-tchitchui-noumbissi";

[TEUNTCHOU-isaac & JOSUE-nkwouano; & RICHARD-mfeugwang agreed on a dinner time of my passing away with all means via a psychiatric injection treatment by LAQUINTINIE-hospital;]

[LAURENT-tchandeu could then secure a prosperous career after the killing & hijacking of money of his blood-brother Théodore-noumbissi-rosicrucian-rotarian !]

- "BULU-biya" tribe in CMR-c.p.d.m-r.d.pc are trying to hijack any wealth of Well-to-do rich cameroonian so to secure presidential leadership for ever.
- Bulu notary-justice attorney [*"MENYE-Ondo Xavier-FRANCOIS"*] & *"LIMA-rose (at time in 2012, 2013 years)"* change effectively & voluntarily year of birth of mine in my *[LAND-title certificate of MFOUNDI-VI.]*

- GENOCIDE of West originating people started in CMR

"MARIE-commissary-of-DEA-05ème-arrondissement-od-City-DOUALA, in Littoral region, sent 8 burglars on street to arrest myself while I was relating to CMRnian that BIYA regime has tried to spoliolate all my belonging via TEUNTCHOU-isaac."

"INGRID-teuntchou couldn't say no to this fake-marriage only to destroy my life as a super engineer and scientist originating from WEST-cmr."

"[TEUNTCHOU-isaac] used since she was aged 15 years old while I went outside of CMR to study in GERMANY-racist-culprit; NGATCHOU-henri-bertrand, a maternal uncle of myself & Ingrid to beat her & accustomate her to perform only what was told to her via JOSUE-nkwouano, senior brother of NGATCHOU-henri ! "

- 2025, AVRIL --18--*"DLA-ndokoti-palace seems to be for now out of service due to atrocities that I have related internationally via web-site "zenodo.org" ! "* (<https://www.zenodo.org>)

"ATANGA NJI idiot minister; Cannot prepare elections without asserting NON-Sence propaganda to Cameroon people."

- Laurent-fainéant TCHANDEU, a paternal vernacular uncle of mine seems to be an ally of people in Zürich working in Avionics !

TCHANDEU, TCHINGWA, KOLIYOU, and HAKOUA seems to be working for whittle racist supremacists in other to destroy any afrique-intelligentsia out of a psychiatric cyclops and / or poverty; So no black intelligent person wouldn't gain his money out of independent intellectual work; & intellectual property.

TCHANDEU, the lead, a so called diplomat, Hires only personal people from his own blood family against scientists & engineers here in Cameroon in particular.

[Koliou, TEUNTCHOU have been associated together in their rosicrucian association de destroy my financial life as I COULD observed since February 2021 when TEUNTCHOU tried to kill me.]

21. ***"EKONDY-PONDY tries to humiliate myself publicly by arresting me without any paper from a judge and / or prosecutor, so called in french procureur-de-la-république !!!***

- ***THE president of the republic PAUL-biya has tried to assassinate myself several times.***

THIS is why I JUST reply by describing what happens on the internet media so 1-day, christian will see what is happening in life of a christian-JESUS-of-nazareth life here in CMR.

- Myself I only repeat like anyone that wants his life saved here that I support him for 2025 presidential elections !
- YOU just see a police man that has no police uniform come to your home and tries to open gate as you were a gangster. THIS time it was ekony-pondy, a commissary with 4 stars on his shoulder that came in person because my sister thought I must go again for a psychiatric treatment, because she belongs to people habilitated to decide so !!!
- 1 day I believe she will notice that she can do sp because BIYA wants to use her to destroy my brilliant career that doesn't accept homosexuality call marriage.

A country where the eldest girl-child of PAUL-biya says she is a lesbian without any fear of jurisdictions-justice because she is the girl of PAUL-biya !!!

JEOVAH-NISSI in heaven, please do your will in my life !!!

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (1.)

28.28 HIJACK OF MY PRIVATELY OWNED PROPERTY BY laquintinie on FEBRUARY 2021

[r-DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM – tALKING AT *BBC-british-broadcast-corporation* (<https://>), AND *+--rotarian--+* club member in douala-sawa-tribe, chief of psy staff of LAQUINTINIE HOSPITAL IN DOUALA (LITTORAL REGION, CAMEROON)], has sent in FEB. 2021, without any official document, 7 people to break into my privately owned (closed with a steel gate) house in DOUALA, so to hijack myself and terrorize me. THIS HAPPENED AT NIGHT AROUND 11:00 PM, with BERTRAND, breaking my gate seals with a weapon of some sort (BERTRAND, was the lead thief of DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM).

THIS HIJACK OR ATTACK on my person happened just 1 day after I denounced to PRC.CM and SHANDY-SHANDY-CABINET.COM (biological father of my mother's side cousin ANGELA) a fake "BACCALAUÉAT"-DEGREE from 'ANGELA TCHAMOU SHANDA OWONA SPOUSE DR. WOLFGANG FERNAND JR. OWONA', because her sister-cousin CYNTHIA NKWOUANO told me about this: "ANGELA WENT TO CENTRAL AFRICAN REPUBLIC and received her diploma in a hotel".

I ALSO BECAME AN AGENT OF CAMEROONIAN DEFENSE AND SECURITY FORCES ON FEBRUARY 14, 2021.

DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM after this kidnapping, held me at LAQUINTINIE HOSPITAL for poisoning me 2 weeks, AND THEN RELEASED AN OFFICIAL DOCUMENT TO MY RELATIVE ROSE SANGNOU.

ROSE SANGNOU has since been using the fake document to go meet my clients to say that I AM A PSY PATIENT AND THAT THEY SHALL NOT DEAL ANYTHING WITH MYSELF. ROSE SANGNOU also went to meet all my privately-owned real estate properties' neighbors TO DO THE SAME.

I HAVE COMPLAINT BEFORE DOUALA-NDOKOTI JURISDICTIONAL TRIBUNAL in front of JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA SINCE FEB. 2021:

- 3 convocations have been sent by now to DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM; he hasn't come to respond to prosecutors.
- I am now awaiting for a "MANDAT D'EMMENER" AGAINST DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM, a form of order from judge that will bring DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM in front of prosecutors by police force.

29.29 Kidnapping on FEB. 2023 WHILE WALKING BACK IN MY YAOUNDÉ REAL ESTATE PROPERTY

1. DR. LAURE MENGUENE MVINDI accepts to send 2 thugs-burglars on the road to kidnap myself, while I was walking on street to get back into my house, and to bring me in a cab at psychiatric hospital 'JAMOT' in YAOUNDÉ; this is requested by DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA, spouse pr. shanda-tonme jean-claude.

DR. LAURE MENGUENE MVINDI is chief of psychiatry staff at psychiatric hospital 'JAMOT' in YAOUNDÉ.

DR. LAURE MENGUENE MVINDI IS VERY WELL KNOWN IN YAOUNDÉ to say disturbing voices against BAMILEKE-TRIBE, an ethnic group of the west cameroon to which, I by birth, and not by spirit [I AM A BORN AGAIN CHRISTIAN], belong.

2. AFTER 2 WEEKS OF POISONING AND TRYING TO DESTROY MY BODY WITH DRUGS AND PILLS, a yellow clothed (level of BACHELOR OF SCIENCE) gate guard OF "HÔPITAL JAMOT" that I don't remember the name, tries to SNEAK INTO my private life by calling me on my private cell phone number [(+237) 6 52 39 69 50] every other day.

I SAID TO HIM THAT I DON'T ENTERTAIN RELATIONSHIPS WITH PEOPLE LIKE HIM.

PS: THIS GATE GUARD, yellow-clothed with an uniform, is of BETI-TRIBE like DR. LAURE MENGUENE MVINDI!

3. S2TBED, a so-called forestry society here in Yaoundé seems to be a secret agency against black-owned societies here in Cameroon.

30.30 Attempt to give me a psy consultation by ROSE SANGNOU's sister DR. ANNIE POKAM-KWAM

AFTER RELEASED FROM 'JAMOT', i stop taking the drugs that i was forced to intake by drink.

Knowing that this is judicial information time, I accept to talk to DR. ANNIE POKAM-KWAM, which is DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA and ROSE SANGNOU sister, by my own request.

My goal is at time to collect as much information as possible.

She (DR. ANNIE POKAM-KWAM) tries to convince me that i should intake psy drugs in order to be more sociable !

31.31 THREAT ON MY PERSON BY ROSE SANGNOU IN JUNE 2023

In June 2023, in its 25th week, a relative, ROSE SANGNOU, living and based in Douala for more than 60 years, comes into Yaoundé, and settle for 1 week at DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA's house, at her (DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA) invite.

ROSE SANGNOU, whom was told, no more to persecute myself, during her interrogation time at prosecutors' office in Douala-Ndokoti, starts calling me increasingly and says she is in Yaoundé because her sister (DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA) son, PATRICE SHANDA SANOU CABRAL, is very ill and hospitalized at Yaoundé general hospital.

ROSE SANGNOU insists that we shall meet because she is my mother. I then accept, but refused to meet up her at my private owned property in Yaoundé-Ahala-Nsimbock. We then meet up first at DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA house, then at supermarket 'supermarché carrefour EKIE' in YAOUNDÉ-ÉKIE.

THIS PERIOD IS judicial information investigation time, that is mostly why I accepted to meet up with her.

I NOTICE with an impression THAT my mother ROSE SANGNOU COULD HAVE BEEN BRUTALIZED ON HER LEFT KNEE. SHE SAID SHE FELT DOWN IN THE BACK OF HER SISTER'S HOUSE (DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA) because the maid woman SPILLED water with amidon on the floor.

AFTER FINISHING our lunch, my mother ROSE SANGNOU says I SHOULD START AGAIN TO TAKE psychiatric drugs: I IMMEDIATELY STAND UP FROM LUNCH TABLE AND RETURNS TO MY PRIVATELY OWNED PROPERTY, 'immeuble yerith'.

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (2.)

32.32 MY SUSPICIONS about real activities of pr. shanda-tonme jean-claude and his wife

SEVERAL TIMES, pr. shanda-tonme jean-claude invited myself to hotel PARFAIT GARDEN in yaoundé so that I COULD SEE HIM ACTING as managing director of expatriate US CITIZEN ELECTRICAL ENERGY COMPANY.

so i suspect pr. shanda-tonme jean-claude receives money from some big giants NORTH-AMERICAN COMPANIES, so to disrupt my activities in the free open source software (FOSS) AREA.

33.33 THREAT ON MY PERSON BY Victor Koliou Noundou IN JULY 2023

PREVIOUSLY. HÔPITAL ADLUCÉM, a hospital in Douala-BONAMOISSADI, that I went with paternal uncle Victor Koliou Noundou to threat a hyperglycemia, established with him (uncle Victor Koliou Noundou) THAT I SHOULD BE BROUGHT USING AN AMBULANCE to 'LAQUINITIE-CABANON' because Dr. MVONDO felt that I am not well behaving !

Victor Koliou Noundou, a brother of my late father Théodore Noumbissi ASKED MYSELF, relentlessly, if I still take the psychiatric drugs.

I need to note here that, WITHOUT ANY APPARENT REASON, another brother of my late father Théodore Noumbissi, Laurent Tchandeu, former minister plenipotentiary, sent A TRUCK WITH 6 firefighters to take me by force from my privately rented apartment in yaoundé, in the year 2015, SO TO BRING ME TO A PSYCHIATRIST OF 'JAMOT': Dr. Kamga.

IN FRONT OF ME, Dr. Kamga SAYS TO Laurent Tchandeu AND ROSE SANGNOU THAT HE CAN'T KEEP ME THERE AT 'JAMOT' BECAUSE I AM NOT A PSYCHIATRIC DISEASED PERSON.

Dr. Kamga ALSO MENTIONS THAT IF I GO TO COURT AGAINST HIM, HE WOULD PUT ALL TROUBLES on ROSE SANGNOU since WHAT SHE SAID TO HIM SO THAT HE SENT A FIREFIGHTER TRUCK to take myself by force from my privately rented apartment is wrong.

Laurent Tchandeu IS TRYING SINCE Théodore Noumbissi, my deceased (JANUARY 9, 1992) father (and chief of the NOUNDOU family), passed away, to sack my POSITION AS CHIEF OF THE FAMILY NOUNDOU:

- IN MAY 2023, politician GRÉGOIRE OWONA, grand-father of MY COUSIN MOTHER SIDE "ANGELA TCHAMOU SHANDA OWONA SPOUSE DR. WOLFGANG FERNAND JR. OWONA", comes with Laurent Tchandeu (and spouse DR. HENRIETTE POLA) in my village BABOUANTOU to open a primary school as gift from political party R.D.P.C (C.P.D.M).

34.34 THREAT ON MY PERSON BY Laurent Tchandeu ON AUGUST 3rd, 2023

DR. Laurent Tchandeu, a paternal uncle of mine, tries to harass myself with taking psychiatric drugs.

HE DID THIS USING TELEPHONY APPLICATION "whatsapp".

35.35 WAITING FOR judge JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA

JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA SEEMS TO WANT TO destroy evidences against state hospital laquintinie since He (JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA) hasn't call by police force DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM to come answer allegations against him about TRYING TO KILL ME with psychiatric drugs at night after HIJACKING MY PRIVATE PROPERTY IN DOUALA-CITÉ-DES-PALMIERS !

36.36 ARMY GENDARMERIE COLONEL KÉMAJOU harasses ROSE sangnou my mother

ROSE SANGNOU, my mother, complained to myself that KÉMAJOU is calling her very frequently to tell her I (PROF. DR.-ING. DIPL.-INF. XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU) is not mentally sane since HE is doing a lot of christian cross-sign while walking on Yaoundé streets.

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (3.)

37.37 ARMY GENDARMERIE COLONEL KÉMAJOU destroying my life as a neighbor

A FORMER SED (SÉCRÉTARIAT D'ÉTAT À LA GENDARMERIE) retired colonel of cameroon gendarmerie, who has spying devices AT HOME TO HEAR PHONE, OR WHATSAPP conversations; MAKES CURRENT ELECTRICITY cut-off whenever I RECEIVE MONEY so I cannot cook and refrigerate my food properly.

THIS VERY POOR PERSON, both in spirit and financially; whose wife makes money out of cooking food for street workers, COULD SUCCESSFULLY intimidate people not to come attend work or anything else into my real estate properties.

COLONEL (retired) of Army Gendarmerie KÉMAJOU couldn't lie and convince people that I DON'T POSSESS A Ph.D in Computer Engineering; since his son "Jonas Kémajou" who he also in gendarmerie told me once: "Myself I also POSSESS A Ph.D QUALIFICATION WITH NO DEGREE AT HOME" !

I am wondering in Cameroon why army intermediates in civilian life and affairs; THIS DOESN'T HAPPEN usually in rich and developed countries like Germany.

This day of **Saturday November 18, 2023**; while I was talking to a computer technician neighbor named Gabriel Takoumbe, KÉMAJOU came along walking with an indigo "Garde Présidentielle (special unit of cameroon forces attached only for the President of The Republic.)" T-shirt.

COLONEL kemajou tells me HE WANTS MY PERSON NOT TO WRITE anymore on his forfeitures against myself; in front of at least 7 young men and women, saying He didn't call my genitor mother any day before.

COLONEL kemajou sect named JÉRUSALEM APOSTOLAT, sacks every public entry road to my real estate 2-storey building (unfinished yet).

Yves Landry Galax ETOGA, chief of secret services of Cameroon seems to like to try harassing competent professors of science and technology like myself. May be He works against CAMEROONIAN SKILLED ORPHANS like my humble person in JEOVAH-NISSI in heaven !

PROF. DR. RER. NAT. HABIL. JAN PELESKA and DR. PATRICK LAM have never said anything against what is happening to myself since 3 years ago; ALSO, Patrick is a member of Rotarian organization ROSICRUCIARY !

"29" November 2023: **I HAVE RENOUNCED TO AN ATTORNEY since TCHANA NJEUTCHA Synclaire is clearly going against my personal interests !**

"03" December 2023: **KEMAJOU and its troops that call themselves Christians ARE HARASSING PEOPLE COMING HOME.**

"04" December 2023: **I cannot recognized Cameroon where someone high qualified by myself is permanently harassed physically by illegal neighbors like KEMAJOU gendarmerie colonel Criminal.**

KEMAJOU gendarmerie colonel tries on the street to talk to myself while I am coming back from a hardware shop.

It seems to myself that illegal neighbors religious sect "Jerusalem Apostolat" is trying to make confusion about my humble person wherever I go in my life; Kemajou gendarmerie colonel has tried around my neighborhood, with help of SECTARIAN OF JERUSALEM APOSTOLAT; to make noise that XAVIER noumbissi noundou IS A PSYCHIATRIC PATIENT that doesn't want to take pills !

38.38 THREAT ON MY PERSON BY ROSE SANGNOU IN JANUARY 2024

ROSE SANGNOU, despite that JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA gave her prohibition to come to my home in Yaounde during year 2023, came by force with someone that I don't know whereabouts To my neighbor "CARINE LELE njougep tchana" To incriminate her about chairs she owns by now;

I destroyed chairs that were not in good shape last year from my humble home by throwing them away outside. It seems "CARINE LELE njougep tchana" put them in her personal home without asking myself since I just threw them away; which is normal since They don't belonged to me anymore !

"30" January 2024: It seems my genitor mother ROSE SANGNOU went to talk to gendarmerie people so they could harass myself to go for an illegal psychiatric treatment; because while I was talking to Justice "ME. ANDRÉ Mbet" today, I saw 1 gendarmerie man came into his personal office where he also, with his wife, Owns a financial transaction center.

I immediately told Justice "ME. ANDRE Mbet" about this attitude of gendarmerie people coming inside where I perform businesses to make some kind of visual and gesture signs to owners of businesses, So they wouldn't deal with myself anymore !

"24, 25" April 2024: 1 man wearing a talkie-walkie came across my personal road in Simbock YDE.

I went to talk to him since I was looking for a technician that didn't finish a work in my humble house. For 6 days now, this technician wasn't in my house anymore despite myself telling him to finish his work on my steel door.

I suspect again justice ("huissier") SHANDA-DJATIE and her spouse Pr. JEAN-CLAUDE shanda-tonme to harass my genitor and mother Rose SANGNOU to try to bring myself by force to a psychiatric destructive mind place.

JERUSALEM-APOSTOLAT rosicrucian sect tried to follow myself these last 2 days using the brigand 'Moise BATOMEN', and another person male, THAT i don't know whereabouts but that live behind "Carine Lele Njougep Tchana" house for at least 6 months from now backwards in time !

Just 1 month before, I was stopped from walking by to our main official road by a sectarian female of Jerusalem-APOSTOLAT. I now see that it was meant to bring myself to other roads were they don't have their own people on it, so they could hijack myself properly to bring by force to a psychiatric hospital so to try to deteriorate my physical and psy body.

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (4.)

39.39 SHANDA SANOU patrice cabral idiot son of Dorothée Shanda Owona passes away at age 33 (March 18, 2024)

"Dorothée Shanda Owona" who had tried to make myself sodomized "by Bertrand of Laquintinie" in Feb. 2021, illegally by police force.

SHE leaves now her son out of life after 3.5 years trying to destroy my life; Probably because she got some laundry money for this dirty task against A BORN-AGAIN-CHRISTIAN !

NONE of the people I have heard from coming back "from some kind of obituary ceremony" could even see any corpse of ATTORNEY OF LAW, deceased, Patrick Cabral SHANDA SANOU !

40.40 Dr. Annie Metiam, Spouse Eric-POKAM-WAM tries to say something illegally about my mental health publicly (May 23, 2024)

A sister of my mother and genitor ROSE SANGNOU, DR. ANNIE POKAM-KWAM, sends a RECORDED AUDIO MESSAGE via whatsapp-phone-android-application, without any request from "Rose Sangnou" and / or my person about a supposed mental health abilities report that She as GASTROENTEROLOGIST has wrote based on our investigation whatsapp call that was done in year 2023 during around the month of JUNE.

This retarded personage that was initially at "Alfred Saker School" oriented to perform Commerce AND Accounting, WITH A grade of 10.00/20 is an idiot; Not just because *she doesn't even have a "degree of Doctor of Medicine (Dr. med.)"*.

This happens unsolicited as I am having a talk together with "Rose Sangnou"; AND "PASTOR marco OF Pentecostal Christian CHURCH" ' 'chapelle de la gloire de christ" in DLA.

I AM SUSPICIOUS of this corrupt C.P.D.M aunt that has german citizenship to be from Central Intelligence Agency (CIA); hired specially to try to kill me by any means; even using sorcery.

41.41 YAGER MABOMA is an idiot of justice judge here in CMR

Since 2021, February that I have complaint for a group of harassers that came into my compound to brutalize myself in front of a so called judge of instruction from sawa tribal tribe, I STILL RECEIVE PEOPLE TRYING TO AGGRESS and Harass myself.

42.42 I-xavier-went on roads to shout That I required JUSTICE for my saved life by SYNCLAIRE NJEUTCHA TCHANA

- o **Wednesday 28th of JUNE 2024:** "Proverbs 1 : 18 – 21 (in Holy bible of JEOVAH-NISSI in Heaven)"

Synclaire NJEUTCHA TCHANA was sodomized both physically and mentally to release myself as a client, So I will go in front of a judge without the initial attorney I have chosen myself.

I went to road "in AHALA-simbock" to shout at populace that I MUST HAVE JUSTICE DONE against people who broke my gate in the night of FEBRUARY 2023 to kill me with psy-drugs involuntarily.

Politics is going on thoroughly because the year 2025 must released a president of the republic of cameroon !

43.43 YAGER MABOMA has sent my documents to Attorney-prosecutor

- o **SATURDAY 31th of AUGUST 2024:**

I hope I can finish this matter without a judge that has been sodomized by "BIYA-clique".

"Synclaire NJEUTCHA TCHANA" said to myself on my cell phone that I sent to him at least 2 other attorneys of law so to replace him; Which is FALSE.

"Synclaire NJEUTCHA TCHANA" has received money from PAUL-biya.

"Tchonang albertine" is now the person I asked for, for assistance."

"I received this name and contact from my friend and customer "HAPPINESS POTENTIAL SARL" based in Akwa-douala ! "

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (5.)

44.44 Police of AHALA – 19ème arrondissement harassing myself because of SHANDA-tonmeo **Friday 6th of September 2024:**

"NESTOR kenfack tries to talk to my genitor and adversary ROSE-Sangnou without asking anything to myself."

"ROSE-idiot sangnou went to give certain objects to "NESTOR and VALÉRIE kenfack" that are supposed to be my sole customers and friends; Without any intermingled relationship with ROSE-sangnou since I told both of them THAT I am not interested into talking with someone who has tried to kill myself."

"I KNOW that it is C.P.D.M that went to give money to these burglars ("NESTOR" & "VALÉRIE") so they will try to intervene against my interests when court justice comes AS this has been the case with my personal attorney of law the culprit "SYNCLAIRE NJEUTCHA TCHANA"."

45.45 CLOVIS kemmegne as intelligence service gendarmerie agent against my privacy lifeo **Saturday 10th of November 2024:**

"A culprit called CLOVIS kemmegne, an intelligence secret service agent of GENDARMERIE NATIONALE of CAMEROON is tring to put troubles into my life via false divulged information around my new business relationships with a new tenant that I could gained via a so called "RENTAL PROPERTY MANAGER"-EMMANUEL-idiot."

"NOW that i have been staying in douala for more than 4-days in a row since my last hijack-attempt, in a so-called inherited property of noumbissi-vilain-idiot THÉODORE; I can see that clovis kemmgne changed the colours GREEN-Yellow-gendarmerie of his GAY-young-porn-female-clairvoyant-boy-jackdaniels; INTO a BLUE-presidential-GRAY-porn-DGRE colors."

"INSTEAD of doing is openly called business of electronics computer technician, and also, "GAY-handler-bar-JACKS.", THIS guja-gay is hiding himself behind my sister and my mother-side family to plan a so-called "CONSTAT-de-FAIT" for the idiot of justice judge HUGUES-alain-yager maboma-faineant."

"THE other gay-called napoa-maxime-eteme; a viagra-gay that seems to be a burglar to myself since BAMKOUÏ said to me he didn't worked at all for SEMIL; BUT is working for CMR-navy in DOUALA; came openly salute myself, together with another idiot called KAMGAIN jean-pierre;"

"i hope only "jean-loïc siewe and belvianne" that seemed to be young fellow cameroonian entrepreneurs are not intermeddle here."

"i can already see that siewe's mother is from the idiot-village-Babouantou !."

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (VI (6).)

CLOVIS kemmegne as intelligence service gendarmerie agent against my privacy lifeo **Wednesday 13th of November 2024:**

"SIEWE and BELVIANNE his collaborator of my new rental property seem to be not able to accommodate well due to destructive actions in water plumbery that seemed to be have done by a previous renter called; AND from R.D.P.C-C.P.D.M-south-bulu-tribe: GERMAIN Blaise ndzie and his wife called Geneviève Ndzie."

"~~Dr. —NOMO siméon-replacement~~ by C.P.D.M.-eyoump-psy; A so-called MAXIME-napoa-eteme called someone I am not sure "Docteur" while I was crossing a street at DLA-cité-des-palmiers yesterday evening; THIS gay-female-psy-hijackist; THAT seemed to be an organizer of my killing via the hijack of my private property in DLA-FEBRURAY-2024 is the one that talked to my 1st before a same day at night I was hijacked. "

"~~MAXIME-napoa-eteme~~ the gay-female-idiot is also from BETI-ekang-amougou-beling-TRAIBAL-tribe as a previous renter called NDZIE geneviève. "

o **SUNDAY 17th of November 2024:**

"IT seems there are no repression against criminals that come officially against my personal and / or familiar interests in CMR. "

"FOR INSTANCE, a family from "BATIÉ-ouest-cmr" that bake "beignets" and that used to transport "Pouse-Pousse" has built a 'bidon-ville-taudis' directly closed to my compound, Where my late father dear THEODORE-idiot noumbissi built a ground foundation, Without any rejection from SOUS-Préfecture that I contacted using my Attorney at law Mr. JUSTICE (Maître Synclair NJEUTCHA tchana)."

"Some folk around this place in Béedi told me that:

1. "A beauty-gay hair-cut society wearing black and /or rosa T-SHIRTS, based on the opposite side of road to CLOVIS-telecom-Alias-kemmegne-gendarmerie-nationale-CMR";

"Sent a hijacker wearing finger-female-paint to say to people around where I was sitting reading my Bible-holy; That I AM SAID to be a mad-person; "

"BEFORE this physical attack even though I WASN'T talking to that gendarme that seems to act as a gay-female-hair treater; I COULD see a woman from CHRISTIAN-eyoum-tribal-tribe called Assassin. "

2. "Clovis telecom Alias clovis kemmegne" has repeatedly summon several people to harass me with no fear since he is well connected with ETOO-fils, a burglar called in CMR Soccer-player-female-male-born-again-gay-hijackist-Christian-eyoum "
3. "Maxime NAPOA-eteme is the one who told this very strange family since they don't do anything apparently to survive in Douala other than sneaking other people properties; WHERE enforced by "NAPOA ETEME, MAXIME" to Hijack myself even physically because I AM A NOBODY IN THIS COUNTRY called CAMEROON. "
4. "i suspect the current president of the republic of CMR called PAUL-biya to be behind this multi-attempt to destroy my life; Since for all my legal complaints nothing could be done for at least more than 12 years. "
5. "paul-biya-junior is mad; a culprit from mvomekaa. "

o **WEDNESDAY 27th of November 2024:**

"This new renter of mine a so-called-CALLPRIT jean-loïc siewe, And BELVIANNE meleu nossi seem not to even welcome very nicely their clients because they left so dirty the entrance step-feet of their rented apartment for 138 EUROS monthly. "

"ALSO this belvianne aged of 25th years old seem not to understand that I AM NOT CONFIDENT of renewing their rental agreement because of all inconsistencies I COULD notice since they entered this apartment inherited of mine:"

1. Her national identity card says she is "SCHOOL student of IUT-douala".

THERE was a so-called "gendarme-etoga-idiot" call Jonas-Kemajou-fainénat that scammed myself around 3 000 EUROS, And that was wearing a gendarme-green-attire, And that also has this "SCHOOL student of IUT-douala" instead of something professional-criminal-armed-robber-south-west-CMR.

SCIENTIFIC PRESENTATION TALKS 1

- 1.) **STATISTICAL TEST CASE GENERATION FOR REACTIVE SYSTEMS, MASTER'S DEGREE THESIS DEFENSE TALK, DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS AND COMPUTER SCIENCE (FB 3), UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY** |★| **MAY "2007"**
- 2.) **STATICALLY VERIFYING API USAGE RULES USING TRACEMATCHES, 9th Workshop on Compiler-Driven Performance, CASCON 2010, Hilton Suites Toronto/Markham Conference Centre, MARKHAM, ONTARIO, CANADA** (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>) |★| **NOVEMBER "2010"**
- 3.) **TEMPORAL PROPERTY VERIFICATION IN PLUGIN-based SOFTWARE, PH.D. THESIS EXAMINATION COMPREHENSIVE !, DEPARTMENT OF ELECTRICAL AND COMPUTER ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA** (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>) |★| **DECEMBER "2011"**
- 4.) **Course project small talk-presentation in front of PATRICK-lam-idiot & course ECE 750 students, 1 EIT room I don't remember code room number digits, DEPARTMENT OF ELECTRICAL AND COMPUTER ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA** **Spring "2013"**
- 5.) **(prepared based on result outcome of talk given during Spring 2013 for course project.); CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAIN T ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM, ECE GRAD TALK, DEPARTMENT OF ELECTRICAL AND COMPUTER ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA** **April "2014"**
- 6.) **CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAIN T ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM, PROGRAMMING LANGUAGES SEMINAR, DAVID R. CHERITON SCHOOL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA** **JANUARY "2015"**
- 7.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; sns cameroon ltd (Mr. DIVINE Njobati); YAOUNDE; CENTER; CAMEROON** **JANUARY "2016"**
- 8.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; best car care & services (Mr. HENRI ngatchou); DOUALA; LITTORAL; CAMEROON** **JANUARY "2016"**
- 9.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; snob bazar outlet stores (Mr. LAVOISIER); YAOUNDE; CENTER; CAMEROON** **MAY "2016"**
- 10.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; expert3dev s.a.r.l (Mr. Momo); YAOUNDE; CENTER; CAMEROON** **JUNE "2016"**
- 11.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; bilingual entente bookshop (Mr. JACQUES); YAOUNDE; CENTER; CAMEROON** **JANUARY "2017"**
- 12.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; BLACK & WHITE snack bars (Mr. TOM & Mr. AURÉLIEN iloga iloga (ecobank poste centrale yaoundé)); YAOUNDE; CENTER; CAMEROON** **JUNE "2017"**
- 13.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for COMPUTER INFORMATICS ENGINEERING TRAINING; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; IUC [Institut Universitaire de la Côte] (Mr. HYPOLITHE Tekeu); DOUALA; LITTORAL; CAMEROON** **SEPTEMBER "2017"**
- 14.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS TALKS; Dr. SANDY beidu; Dr. ERIC brefo-mensah; WATERLOO; ON; CANADA** **JUNE "2018"**
- 15.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for CROWD FUNDING REQUEST PROPOSAL; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION (for "MS WINDOWS"); BAFIASOFT (Mr. CHRISTIAN rikong ngueyong); WATERLOO; ON; CANADA** **SEPTEMBER "2018"**
- 16.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; coplatec s.a.r.l (Mr. CONSTANT Kemmogne); DOUALA; LITTORAL; CAMEROON** **MAY "2020"**
- 17.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce and drugstore selling; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; pharmacy fiango lycée MAKÉPÉ (Dr. PETER Akume Ngoe); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON** **JANUARY "2021"**
- 20.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce and INDUSTRIAL logistics; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; bontée s.a.r.l (Ms. ARLETTE [Sibeufo-mpay-army-general-spouse-in-official]); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON** **FEBRUARY "2021"**
- 21.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce and PRODUCTION planing; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; CROQUE-MATIN (Mr. MOUSSA Saliou); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON** **MARCH "2021"**
- 22.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL ("MS WINDOWS 2000"); elektro maképé (Mr. ARMSTRONG); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON** **JUNE "2021"**
- 23.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; établissement kenfack (Mr. KENFACK); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON** **JULY "2021"**
- 24.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce, AND client relationship management; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; clinique de l'espérance (Mr. YVES Mogo); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON** **SEPTEMBER "2021"**
- 25.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce, AND client relationship management; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; pctb s.a.r.l (Dr. AIMÉE FRANCIS Ngadjou Tchana); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON** **OCTOBER "2021"**
- 26.) **YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; quincaillerie la confiance (Mr. AIMÉE); YAOUNDE; CENTER region; CAMEROON** **NOVEMBER "2021"**

SCIENTIFIC PRESENTATION TALKS 2

- 27.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; quincaillerie n.k. (Mr. NESTOR Kenfack); YAOUNDE; CENTER region; CAMEROON **NOVEMBER "2021"**
- 28.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce, AND client relationship management; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; happiness potential s.a.r.l (Mr. FABRICE Siemeni); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON **JANUARY "2022"**
- 29.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce, AND client relationship management; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; pctb s.a.r.l (Dr. AIMÉE FRANCIS Ngadjou Tchana); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON **JANUARY "2022"**
- 30.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; AND networked installations; quincaillerie aimée (Mr. AIMÉE); YAOUNDE; CENTER region; CAMEROON **JUNE "2022"**
- 31.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; AND commercial financial accounting; poissonnerie plus (Mr. NESTOR Kenfack); YAOUNDE; CENTER region; CAMEROON **SEPTEMBER "2022"**
- 32.) *YERITH-ERP-3.0 BRIEF SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL PRESENTATION; ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE YAOUNDÉ - ENSPY (PROF. DR.-ENG. THOMAS NDIÉ DJOTIO); Yaoundé; CENTER region; CAMEROON* **May "2023"**
- 33.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-SERVER TRAINING; happiness potential sarl (DIPL.-ING. (FH) DR. FABRICE WILFRIED SIEMENI, M.Sc); Douala; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON **August "2023"**
- 34.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-SERVER financial accounting SHORT PRESENTATION VIEW DEMONSTRATION; quincaillerie aimée sarl (Ms. CHRISTELLE spouse NAMEKONG, B.SC.); Yaoundé; CENTER region; CAMEROON **December "2023"**
- 35.) YERITH-ERP-9.0 VERY SHORT INFORMATION SESSION; happiness potential s.a.r.l (Mrs. Hecna Ngayam) ; Douala; Littoral region; CAMEROON **May "2024"**
- 36.) YERITH-ERP-3.0-FOSS SHORT INFORMATION SESSION FOR COMMERCE; Mr. Hilaire Yimdjo, B.Sc. in Computer Science (entrepreneur in car care and management); Douala; Littoral region; CAMEROON **May "2024"**
- 37.) YERITH-ERP-9.0 SHORT INFORMATION SESSION FOR COMMERCE; Mr. Nestor Kenfack (entrepreneur in hardware shop and grocery store); Yaoundé; CENTER region; CAMEROON **June 12, "2024"**
- 38.) YERITH-ERP-9.0 Installation hardware checks; Mr. Nestor Kenfack (entrepreneur in grocery store); Yaoundé; CENTER region; CAMEROON **June 13, "2024"**
- 39.) Aborted installation & training of family association "MA-sangnou-idiot-bangou"; Douala; Littoral region; CAMEROON. **March "2025"**
- 40.) **Presentation & Questions & Answers (Q&A) with a young entrepreneur-woman-lady from Douala-sawa tribe; Douala; Littoral region; CAMEROON.** **March, "2025"**
Based on our remarks to this lady of very low class revenue, we could find that we may add an option for "automatically recalculating cost-price of acquisition."
WE see here an opportunity to examine how to improve quality & revenue of this low-class entrepreneurial adventure !
THIS kind of entrepreneurial organization is very pro-eminent in Douala-sawa tribe as customers come into living-house to buy. !
- 41.) **YERITH-ERP-9.0 design introspective view talk accompanied with Q&A (Questions & Answers) by management consultant IRIS mbieukop; [M. Iris-mbieukop] is an expert using MS-excel & PowerBI (BUSINESS intelligence).** **April, "2025"**
VERY impressive questions that could make our start-up "YERITH R&D" [improve YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum in terms of Ergonomics (color management)], and / or functionality; Douala; Littoral region; CAMEROON
 ► **June 11, 2025 :**
[This guja seems to be an EYOUM because he was looking quite strange while I just great him yesterday night while entering DLA.] Kind-of son of a guja call PAUL-fokamn-kemmogne—idiot.
- 42.) **[YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum short introduction]; MBA-Claude BISSEG (bisseg@yahoo.fr); Very interesting introspective towards reconfiguring pricing options !**
Very similar to Microsoft Dynamics & Sales Forces software. MBA-Claude BISSEG seems to want trying this as a rental software monthly around "20, 000 Francs CFA monthly". **May 12, "2025"**
HIS father, M. BISSEG is a very well respected member of Lions-Club Douala, TOGETHER for instance with Dr.-criminal GWET-bell !
Attorney of JUSTICE-congolese-brazzaville Vicent GOMEX & President-Congolese Sassou are also members of Lions-Club-INTERNATIONL-criminal !
- 43.) **Presentation & Questions & Answers (Q&A) with a young entrepreneur named ROSTAND-moungam. Douala; Littoral region; CAMEROON.** **June 2, "2025"**
ROSTAND is a startuper that uses Programming language "DART" and also website builder application "flutter flow" to give maximal power to its clients that are in need of a webshop !"
ROSTAND is at time skeptical in trying YERITH R&D product YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum because it seems to him not very simple to implement according to his web presence requirements !"

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"XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU [PR. PROF. DR.-ING.]"

R&D — RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT — SUMMARY

— RESEARCHING GOALS IN "DISTRIBUTED & OPERATING COMPUTING SYSTEM" (CONSTRUCTION & ANALYSIS & VERIFICATION & VALIDATION) —

- Create technology for easing life in Africa • Make human-being life easier and cheaper •

Research KEYwords : Yerith-Xavier-NOUNDOU ✓ ([2025]-(YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0); [2022]-SDMM; YRI_QVGE; YERITH-SAINT; [2006]-(Peleska. Yerith et al.); [2022]-KLAUS HAVELUND (LogSCOPE); [2017]-Frank-TIP-Koushik-SEN (EVENTRACECOMMANDER); [2007]-"Hendren, et al". (tracematches, S00T); THOMAS-reps (IFDS; IDE); [1977]-Gary-KILDALL ✓ (static code lattice-based "dataflow analysis"-seminal); [1977]-Patrick & Radia-COUSOT (Abstract INTERPRETATION);.

Figure 36: "Portrait of YERITH-NISSI. now 42 years old."

DOCTOR-Ph.D. of Engineering (DR.-ING. / PH.D.) in Electrical & Computer Engineering; UNiversity of waterloo-mutilative; '12/20/2011'!

★ — ★ DOCTOR-PH.D. of Engineering (DR.-ING. [21]) ★ — ★

Integrated Bachelor's & Master's degree ("B.Sc & M.Sc." / Dipl.-Inf.); UNiversity-racist of BREMEN.; '05/25/2007'.
— Diplom-INFORMATIKER (Dipl.-Inf. [?]) —

■ UNIVERSITY publications | [Tranng](#) | [TALKS](#) | [LAtest](#) | [Figures](#) | [Tables](#)

■ PUBLICATIONS at ["Start-Up YERITH R&D"]

- Resrching goals.
- Engineering Methodologies & Tools Expertise.
- PUBLICATIONS in FRENCH.
- PUBLICATIONS in English.
- Summary of PRO-eminant Contributions.
- Contacts with ACADEMIA—other than myself!

— Scholarships & Awards

- "Post- & Doctoral Research and Studies" at the UNiversity-RACIST of WATERLOO, ONTARIO, canada — " ≈ 30 + 27 = 57-months" —.
- "GRADUATE [students] : Dr. ridha | Basser | Divam jain | Zheng FELIX fang".
- "Teaching for the UNiversity-RACIST of WATERLOO, ONTARIO, canada — " ≈ 24-months" — ("almost 2-years").
- "Graduate INTERN" at International Business Machinery (IBM), MARKHAM, Toronto, CANADA-idiot (<https://www.ibm.com/ca-en>) — " ≈ 8-months" —.
- "(PART-TIME) Student Software System Developer" for AGBS - Arbeitsgruppe Betriebssysteme (<https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp>), UNiversity of Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY-racist — " ≈ 6-months" —.
- "(PART-TIME) Student Software System Developer" for Bergmann Automaten GmbH (now Gewete GmbH) (<https://www.gewete.com>), Rellingen, Hamburg, GERMANY — " ≈ 24-months" — ("almost 2-years").
- "JUNIOR Software Developer" for SIEMENS-racist Medical Solutions (now SIEMENS-healthineers) (<https://www.healthcare.siemens.com>) — " ≈ 21-months" — ("almost 2-years").
- "(Part-Time) WEB AND 'RAD' APPLICATION DEVELOPER" at ZMML-racist, UNiversity of Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY-angeber (<https://www.uni-bremen.de/en/zmml>) — " ≈ 25-months" — ("almost 2-years").
- "Research Curriculum" at the UNiversity of Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY-racist — " ≈ 54-months" —.

46.46 Professor-professional Computing Scientific Association Memberships

■ Current: "~~aem: The Association for Computing Machinery~~"; "FME: Formal Methods Europe"; "ASQ: American Society for Quality".

47.47 Hardware Products

■ ★ "Portable Computer for on-the-fly runtime verification monitoring" : YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>).

48.48 Software (System) Products ("Progiiciels en langue Française")

■ ★ "WYSIWYG Web Designer Generated Tool : YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL" (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17466696>)[?].

■ "Runtime MONITORING tester verifier" : YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) [1b].

■ "Computer-Aided Software Engineering (CASE) Design Tool for creating SDMM" : YRI_QVGE (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567>) [1d].

■ "An Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP) & Stock-live trading platform; ALL-in-one" : YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM (https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-9-0-software-system-architecture_20221230/YERITH-ERP-9-0-SOFTWARE-SYSTEM-ARCHITECTURE.pdf).

49.49 Research Impact.

Table 13: Impact of 'Research & Technologies' [Created at YERITH R&D]

N°	RESULT	EXPERTISE DOMAIN	SINCE / YEAR	ORIGINALITY & PARTICULARITY	CERTIFICATION AND / OR REFERENCE
1.	ERP – PGI introduction because of creation & proof-tested YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.	Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP) — Business Machinery	YEAR-2025	Insertion of a placebo ERP-PGI software system by R.D.P.C.-C.PDM-biya-in-year-2025	N.A
2.	★ Secured Web-browser architecture only 2-tiers layers .	Web Apps Automatic Generation	YEAR-2025	1 st 2 layers web-browser based software architecture with security proof code backed and secure via model-checking runtime verification monitoring !	N.A
3.	★ Hardware YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET.	Dynamic Program Binary Analysis Verification	YEAR-2024	1 st open-sourced runtime verification on-the-fly; Also as Hot plug-in device embedded	CE
4.	★ Software YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL Software YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0	Web Apps Automatic Generation	YEAR-2024	"1. WYSIWYG-Tool for HTML pages." 2.) HIGH-level view imperative Programming language for HTML pages dynamic; 3.) Automatic generation of safe & secure web sources files	N.A
5.	Software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM	Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP) — Business Machinery	YEAR-2015	1 st Simpler to use ERP (Enterprise Resource Planing). Starting age 12 years old.	N.A and / or O.H.A.D.A (not required at all)
6.	Program YERITH-SAINT	Compiler Technology	YEAR-2013	1 st temporal property verification by (staged-alias analysis) static taint analysis framework-algorithm in LLVM	N.A

RESEARCH IMPACT — CONTINUED

Table 14: *Impact of 'Research & Technologies' [Created at YERITH R&D] — Continued.*

N°	RESULT	EXPERTISE DOMAIN	SINCE / YEAR	ORIGINALITY & PARTICULARITY	CERTIFICATION AND / OR REFERENCE
7.	A C++ Functional Library for Specifying "SDMM" (State Diagram Mealy Machine).	Compiler Technology	YEAR-2022	1.) 1 st fully compliant to "David-harel statechart"—"mealy machine" STATE DIAGRAM formalization for runtime monitoring verification & automatic model-based statechart-code-generation; 2.) Checks for forbidden trace specification across software system with no additional runtime overhead as demonstrated by concurrent event stream analysis technique	N/A
8.	Software YRI_QVGE	CASE (Computer-Aided Software Engineering) Tool	YEAR-2022	1 st CASE-Tool for designing by drawing state diagram mealy machine (SDMM); 2.) 1 st model checker at runtime that encompasses Mealy-machine as opposed And not KRIPKE-structure !	N.A and / or CE (not required at all)
9.	Software YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF	Dynamic Program Binary Analysis Verification	YEAR-2022	1 st open code sourced Runtime MONITOR container (generator) software for "SDMM"	N.A and / or CE (not required at all)
10.	Algorithms not published in any journal And / Or conference due to missing financial funding.	Theoretical Computer Science	YEAR-2015	Various algorithms for creating working User-QT software easily	N/A
11.	[UWATERLOO-SE 465-ECE 453] — Text-tutorial "JUNIT 4 TUTORIAL".	Unit Testing	YEAR-2009	Pragmatic Junit 4 Tutorial aided with "Cobertura Test Coverage Analyzer"	N/A
12.	Software "Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints" (N.A).	Static Program Code Analysis Checking	YEAR-2013	Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints.	N/A
13.	Software YERITH-XRESIN-SOFTWARE.	Web Apps Program Analysis	YEAR-2013	A dynamic taint analysis software for Security for PHP in a JAVA PHP Interpreter.	N/A
14.	Taxonomy of Program-Software Verification & Analysis.	Software Verification	YEAR-2023	Unique positioning and specification of PROGRAM-software Verification & Analysis.	N/A
15.	MASTER thesis – Statistical test cases generation for reactive systems (N.A).	Test Cases / Test Data — Generation	YEAR-2007	Statistical uniform distribution generation of test cases for statechart diagrams.	N.A and / or A.R.I.N.C
16.	Vordiplom-B.Sc. Independent Study: A Semantic Comparison between Timed Automata and Büchi Automata (N.A).	Theoretical Computer Science	YEAR-2004	A set of transformations from Büchi automata to Timed Automata.	N/A

- Our commitment to create software tools & programs for insuring a better and safe software system quality as both open-sourced and priced products, Enables now young immature software developers and engineers in under-developed Africa to have better products and quality at a low cost price : ["Software Products at YERITH R&D"]. TABLE 13, TABLE 14 illustrate sample products, both potential-in-preparation hardware, and already available (accompanying) software.

THIS statement previously made is also available for medium sized companies in west developed countries where even not far as for in year 2000, and also years before; CRASHES of aircraft "Ariane 5 occurred and other airplanes from Airbus and BOEING, causing lost of several human being lives.

- YOUNG adults aged around \approx 12 years old can now start learning using a full-featured ERP-trading stock exchange software that uses a very simplified everyday language as testified by our previous report of "Start-Up YERITH R&D" for years 2022 – 2023 : "REPORT ON WORK ABOUT YERITH-ERP-9.0 (YEAR 2023) (<https://zenodo.org/records/13949884>)".

This couldn't be possible years before starting 2015 when I started creating YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM; Our previous assertion is corroborated by deployment of YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum at at least 5 locations in Yaounde & Douala, in main cities of Cameroun, which is the leader of central africa economic zone C.E.M.A.C (<https://www.cemac.int>).

50.50 Tools & Programming Language Expertise

- **Operating Systems:** MS Windows (XP, 98, 2000, 7, 10, 11), DEBIAN LINUX (8, 9, 10, 11, 12)
- **SCM (Source Code Version Management Tools):** Git, Mercurial (hg), SVN, Rational ClearCase
- **Web Technologies:** MariaDB, HTML5, CSS, PHP, Quercus, Apache Tomcat, GWT (Google Web Toolkit), JSP
- **Scripting Languages:** Cygwin, Python, sed, AWK, Bash
- **Programming languages, Debugging, and Testing Analysis tools:** UML 2.0, SCALA, JAVA, C/C++, JUnit-5, DDD, Gcov, VALKYRIE YERITH[20.20], LTSA
- **Programming and Compiler Frameworks (including IDE):** DIFF, Patch, Txl, apache ANT, MAKE, Qt 5, SOOT, LLVM, flex, bison, Eclipse IDE, Codeblocks, CharmNT

51.51 Teaching for the University of Waterloo, Ontario, Canada–racist.

Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465) | Methods and Tools for Software Engineering (ECE 650) | Foundations of Software Engineering (ECE 651) | Programming for Performance (ECE 459) | Computer Networks (ECE 428) | Compilers (ECE 351) | [C++ Laboratory (ECE 250)].

52.52 Summary of Professional Training in USA, Canada, & Germany

- "Professional international workshops and conferences". 2001 – 2015

53.53 Teaching / summary of competencies Acquired at THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA–RACIST.

- "Formal training at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO–racist". 2009 – 2011
- "Competencies acquired during courses teaching during doctoral studies at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO–racist". 2009 – 2011
- "Competencies acquired during courses teaching during post–doctoral studies at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO–racist". 2012 – 2015

54.54 Teaching ONLINE on the World Wide Web UNIVERSITY–level (graduate) Students.

I currently live in Africa, Cameroon where I cannot have a position at my level of knowledge and experience in a formal Cameroonian UNIVERSITY.

 "POUR les usagers de la langue FRANÇAISE : "Enseignant d'université"; ET NON Enseignant–employé d'université (d'État); EST 1 des définitions du mot professeur."

 Enseignant d'université signifie divulguer des enseignements académiques de rang doctoral et post–doctoraux aux apprenants des universités du monde. "LE titre et grade académique de *Ph.D. et / ou Docteur-de-3^{ème} cycle universitaire*" en est l'approbation universellement reconnue en ma connaissance.

Nonetheless I still teach via WWW books & tools, & programs that I deem at University level graduate courses level; Based on my "doctoral & post–doctoral Ph.D. studies In Computer Software Engineering" & work at the University–racist of Waterloo.

I am developing course material for online worldwide university level (graduate) students as depicted online on "zenodo.org" (<https://www.zenodo.org>) :

I.) Topic : SOFTWARE SYSTEM

- 1.) **FORMAL METHODS** using state diagram mealy machine ([SDMM](#)) for runtime monitoring and verification (via *model checking*) :
 - YERITH_QVGE: A Framework for Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567>)
 - A C++ Functional Library for Specifying "SDMM" (State Diagram Mealy Machine) – *Book Preprint* (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) ;
 - User's Guide for the Design and Testing System YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE) (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>) ;
- 2.) World Wide Web (WWW) Design & Programming using YERITH–WEB–DSL–9.0" : book in preparation, together with accompanying CDROM–USB–key dongle. (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17466696>)
- 3.) **SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE** : SOFTWARE SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OF YERITH–ERP–3.0[?]: (https://www.archive.org/download/yerith-erp-3-0-software-system-architecture_20221230/YERITH-ERP-3-0-SOFTWARE-SYSTEM-ARCHITECTURE.pdf);
- 4.) **SOFTWARE VERIFICATION AND ANALYSIS** : " Temporal Property Verification in Plugin–based Software by Program Analysis (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/10990602>) ”.

II.) Topic : ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANING (ERP) SOFTWARE & TOOLS

55.55 Research Expertise (PR. PROF. DR.-ING.)■ **Business Informatics** ⇒ *illustrative figure of business workflow of YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.*○ **Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP) — Business Machinery**

- 1.) ERP-trading Stock Exchange Software: "YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0"[?]; <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0> C++; Qt 5; [03/2015 -]

■ **Software Engineering**○ **Web Apps Program Analysis**

- 2.) 3 A Dynamic Taint Analysis for PHP in Quercus; <https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis> JAVA; Firebug; [01/2013 - 04/2013]

○ **Web Apps Automatic Generation** ⇒ *illustrative table of YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 (Section 27.27.5).*

- 3.) YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0-DSL[27.27]; <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9> flex, bison; [06/2024 -]

○ **Debugging Tool**

- 4.) 20.20 Open Source Contribution to "Valkyrie: Valgrind-GUI"; https://github.com/yerithrd/valkyrie_NON_OFFICIAL C++; Qt 5; [07/2023 -]

○ **CASE (Computer-Aided Software Engineering) Tool**

- 5.) 1 "MBT-RT-TESTER PLUGIN" FOR "Borland-Together"[1b] C++; "Statechart-TDIOHS"; "Borland-Together"; "www.verified.de" [09/2006 - 02/2007]
6.) YRI_QVGE[1] C++; Qt 5; [06/2022 -]

○ **Compiler Technology**

- 7.) 34 Ph.D. dissertation: A Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM; <https://github.com/AmesianX/saint> LLVM; — 03/2015 —
8.) 1d A State Diagram Mealy Machine Description Language; https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang flex, bison; [04/2023 -]

■ **Software Engineering** ► **Software Verification** ⇒ *figure illustrating components of it (Section 13.13.1).*○ **Static Program Code Analysis Checking à la "Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945)".**

- 9.) 1(1)4 Conference Article : Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints JUnit; SOOT; JAVA; — 2013 —
10.) 32 Ph.D. thesis: Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software SOOT; JAVA; — 12/2011 —

○ **Dynamic Program Binary Runtime Analysis Verification**

- 11.) 1 YERITH_QVGE: A Framework for Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime;
 <https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif> C++; Qt-DBus; [06/2022 -]
12.) 1f A Runtime Monitoring Mealy Machine C++ library; https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif C++; Qt 5; [06/2022 -]

○ **Unit Testing**

- 13.) II Text-tutorial "JUNIT 4 TUTORIAL" JAVA; JUnit; "COBERTURA coverage analyzer" — 10/2009 —

○ **Test Cases / Test Data — Generation**

- 14.) 1a Statistical test cases generation for reactive systems C++; "Statechart-TDIOHS"; "Borland-Together"; "RT-Tester" — 05/2007 —

■ **Theoretical Computer Science**○ **Concurrent Systems, AUTOMATA theory**

- 15.) 1d Vordiplom-B.Sc. Independent Study: A Semantic Comparison between Timed Automata and Büchi Automata Set-Algebra; — 12/2004 —

56.56 Engineering Methodologies & Tools Expertise

- A.) **C++**; & **JAVA**; & **SQL – DBMS (Database Management System) MariaDB** with **DEBIAN LINUX & SVN** (E.g. : (Part-Time) Student Software Developer Position (<https://www.gewete.com>))
SUCCESSFULLY REVIEWED.
a.) **Dipl.-Ing. JENS MÖLLER** — Team Lead of myself at that time 2005 – 2007
b.) **Dipl.-Ing. (FH) SVEN KAMRATH** — Technical Lead of myself at that time 2005 – 2007
- B.) **C++** with **MS Windows (XP, 98,2000,7,10,11)** & **FSM (Finite State Machines)** & **Rational ClearCase** (E.g. : Junior Software Developer position) (<https://www.healthcare.siemens.com>)
SUCCESSFULLY REVIEWED.
a.) **Dipl.-Inf. (FH) GERHARD SENG** — Team Lead of myself at that time 2007 – 2009
b.) **Ing. (M.Sc.) DARIO MERAUIGLIA** — Technical Lead of myself at that time 2007 – 2009
- C.) **ERP System YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum** with **Javascript, XML, HTML5, CSS, PHP, MAKE, Qt 5, C++, MariaDB, flex & bison** (E.g. : Inventor & Developer)
SUCCESSFULLY Used & Re-Tested.
a.) **Annual reports : REPORTS ON WORK ABOUT YERITH-ERP-9.0** (<https://zenodo.org/records/StillInDoing>) 2021 – 2023
b.) **[Document local link !]**
- D.) **Software Testing (UNIT, Integration)** with **UML 2.0-HybridUML (Statechart by David-HAREL)** & **C++** (E.g. : Statistical test cases generation for reactive systems at the UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN-racist-idiot, BREMEN-germany, Germany-racist)
SUCCESSFULLY REVIEWED.
a.) **Prof. Dr. Jan Peleska** — MSc-advisor of myself at that time, Stakeholder of VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH. 2004 – 2007
b.) **Prof. Dr. Rolf Drechsler** — MSc-advisor of myself at that time 2004 – 2007
c.) **Diplomarbeit Kolloquium MASTER-thesis defence** May 25, "2007"
- E.) **JAVA** with **JUnit** (E.g. : SE 465-ECE 453 — Text-tutorial "JUNIT 4 TUTORIAL")
SUCCESSFULLY REVIEWED.
a.) **Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (ONTARIO)** — Course Instructor. SPRING term (Jan. – Apr.) – 2010
- F.) **Web Apps Automatic Generation** with **Javascript, XML, HTML5, CSS, PHP, MAKE, Qt 5, C++, MariaDB, flex & bison** (E.g. : "WWW - World Wide Web (WWW) Design & Programming using YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0" (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/1746696>))
a.) **REVIEWER-Proposal of Prof. Dr. OWOLABI Legunsen, Ph.D., Cornell University, ITHACA, USA-**
b.) **REVIEWER-Proposal of Christian RIKONG Nguoyong, AS-degree in Computer Science, Santa monica-california, USA-**
c.) **REVIEWER-Proposal of Prof. Dr.-Ing. Thomas Djotio Ndie-**
d.) **REVIEWER-Proposal of Prof. Dr. Patrick-LAM-**
- G.) **Web Apps Program Analysis** with **Quercus & JAVA** (E.g. : A Dynamic Taint Analysis for PHP in Quercus, CS846 at THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, Ontario-racist, Canada) (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051621/>)
SUCCESSFULLY REVIEWED.
a.) **Prof. Dr. Frank Tip, Ph.D. – COURSE instructor** APRIL 30, "2013"
- H.) **Program Code Binary Analysis** with **SDMM & YERITH_QVGE** (E.g. : Software Testing of YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum & Runtime Monitoring Verification. (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>))
a.) **REVIEWER-Proposal of Prof. Dr. OWOLABI Legunsen, Ph.D., Cornell University, ITHACA, USA** December 20, "2025"
b.) **REVIEWER-Proposal of Prof. Dr. Jan Peleska** — Stakeholder of VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH. October 7, "2025"
c.) **REVIEWER-Proposal of KLAUS HAVELUND, Researcher at N.A.S.A., U.S.A.** July 11, "2025"
- I.) **Program Code Static Analysis** with **apache ANT, SOOT & JAVA** (E.g. : Doctoral TheSis at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, Ontario-racist, Canada) (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>)
SUCCESSFULLY REVIEWED.
a.) **Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (ONTARIO)** — PH.D.-advisor of myself at that time December 20, "2011"
b.) **Prof. Dr. Nomair Naeem, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (ONTARIO)** — at my request before my **PhD Comprehensive Examination** December "2011"
c.) **PhD Comprehensive Examination – ECE-University of waterloo** December 20, "2011"
- J.) **Software Vulnerability Analysis** using **LLVM & C++** (E.g. : Doctoral Dissertation in Computer Science at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, Ontario-racist, Canada) (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>)
SUCCESSFULLY REVIEWED.
a.) **Prof. Dr. Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D.** — at my request before my **ECE graduate research seminar talk** "2014"
b.) **ECE Graduate Seminar Talk Series at THE university of waterloo-racist, ontario, canada** April, 16 "2014"
c.) **PhD Dissertation Defence – CS-University of waterloo** January "2015"

[Research Expertise LINK internal to this document.]

UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>)

- 1.) A SEMANTIC COMPARISON BETWEEN BÜCHI AUTOMATA AND TIMED AUTOMATA, INDEPENDENT STUDY, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY, ADVISED BY PROF. DR. RER. NAT. HABIL. JAN PELESKA. JANUARY 2005
- 2.) STATISTICAL TEST CASE GENERATION FOR REACTIVE SYSTEMS (https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/qualifikationsarbeiten/diplomarbeiten_e.html), MASTER'S DEGREE IN COMPUTER SCIENCE THESIS, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, ADVISED BY PROF. DR. RER. NAT. HABIL. JAN PELESKA, AND PROF. DR. PHIL. NAT. ROLF DRECHSLER. MAY 25, 2007
- 3.) RESEARCH MASTER PROJECT REPORT cognitive agents, [Research Project Report Robotic-Cognition-Cartography], UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY, ADVISED BY DR.-ING. LUTZ Frommberger, DR.-ING. DIPL.-INF. Frank DYLLA, PROF. DR. RER. NAT. HABIL. Christian FRESKA. July 2006

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA (<https://www.uwaterloo.ca>)

- 1.) JUNIT 4 TUTORIAL (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052444/>), UNDERGRADUATE COURSE LECTURES NOTES 'SOFTWARE TESTING, QUALITY ASSURANCE AND MAINTENANCE', UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA, ADVISED BY PROFESSOR PATRICK LAM. OCTOBER 31, 2009
- 2.) TEMPORAL PROPERTY VERIFICATION IN PLUGIN-BASED SOFTWARE (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8ald09b015f29b33>), PHILOSOPHY DOCTOR (PH.D.) DISSERTATION, (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8ald09b015f29b33>) UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA ADVISED BY PROFESSOR PATRICK LAM. DECEMBER 20, 2011
- 3.) DYNAMIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR PHP IN QUERCUS (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051621/>) (◆[git https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis](https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis); ◆[git https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis-tests](https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis-tests)), PH.D. GRADUATE COURSE PROJECT 'program analysis of web apps', UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA ADVISED BY FULL PROFESSOR FRANK TIP. APRIL 30, 2013

**JAVA application server "Quercus" — JAVA-PHP-interpreter
PROGRAM analysis of web apps
SOFTWARE cyber-security**

- "[THIS course CS846 project led by Professor doctor Frank TIP], was about creating a security taint analysis program code in JAVA for the "Quercus JAVA PHP Interpreter", which is a web application server, COMPARABLE to Apache-Tomcat (<https://www.tomcat.org>); And that enables PHP developers to use existing JAVA libraries within their PHP code as well. "
- "I have implemented and tested a dynamic taint analysis using Firebug, and FirePHP. THIS taint analysis enables to warn developers about data and values that originate from outside the webserver, and / or also about values that emerge as results from operations that involve "tainted values"; MEANING values that are considered not safe because they originate from the outside world of the Quercus web application server. "
- "Taking particular care of unsafe outside world data and values (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) allows developers to avoid web cyber-software security vulnerabilities attacks such as SQL injection, BUFFER-OVERFLOW attacks, format string vulnerabilities, etc.."

► YEAR-2024

IN our project YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0, we will need to instrument binaries of a running JAVA virtual machine; Most probably "Debian-Linux OpenJDK Runtime Environment" (<https://docs.oracle.com>).

THIS binary instrumentation technology from INTEL-pin (<https://www.intel.com/missingfornow>) has an advantage over reinstrumenting and recompiling code sources each time any Qt-DBus message has been introduced and / or modified in tool YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>).

- 4.) CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>), POST-DOCTORAL PH.D. GRADUATE WORK, (https://www.archive.org/download/jh-nissi-ece-uwaterloo-grad-talk-2014-04-16/JH_NISSI_ECE_UWATERLOO_GRAD_TALK_2014_04_16.pdf) UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA ADVISED BY PROFESSOR PATRICK LAM. MARCH 10, 2015

**Heartbleed BUG security breach SSL-1.0.1-f (<https://heartbleed.com>)
Static PROGRAM code analysis of C programs
LLVM code; SOFTWARE cyber-security**
- 5.) CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM TOOL USER'S GUIDE (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051299>), POST-DOCTORAL PH.D. GRADUATE WORK artifact, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA ADVISED BY PROFESSOR PATRICK LAM. [OCTOBER 2015]

PUBLICATIONS – YERITH R&D (in English language) (II)

[Research Expertise LINK internal to this document.]

57.57 YERITH R&D – Algorithms Excerpt not published in conference papers due to resources.

1. [Created Algorithms Link].

58.58 YERITH R&D – Reports

2. *REPORTS ON WORK ABOUT YERITH-ERP-9.0* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17689313>),
RELEASE DOCUMENT COMMERCIAL TECHNICAL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, November 23, 2025. November 23, 2025.
3. *REPORT ON WORK ABOUT YERITH-ERP-9.0 (YEAR 2023)* (<https://zenodo.org/records/13949884>),
RELEASE DOCUMENT COMMERCIAL TECHNICAL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, October 1, 2023. October 1, 2023.

59.59 Business Informatics Management Knowledge

5. *YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum SOFTWARE SYSTEM PRODUCT SHEET* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17661983>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, NOVEMBER 2025. NOVEMBER 2025.
6. *ADVANTAGES OF YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum COMPARED TO OTHER TOP ERP SOFTWARE-SYSTEMS* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17662017>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, NOVEMBER 2025. NOVEMBER 2025.
7. *INFORMATION BROCHURE OF ERP SOFTWARE-SYSTEM YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17662117>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, NOVEMBER 2025. NOVEMBER 2025.
8. *INSTALLATION GUIDE FOR ERP SOFTWARE-SYSTEM YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum* (<https://zenodo.org/record/8060182/>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, MARCH 2021. MARCH 2021.

60.60 Associated Computer Devices

9. *YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum RECOMMENDED POINT-OF-SALE HARDWARE* (<https://zenodo.org/records/17661831>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, NOVEMBER 2025. NOVEMBER 2025.

61.61 Advanced Software Technology

10. *"WWW - World Wide Web (WWW) Design & Programming using YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0"* (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17466696>),
BOOK, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, March 2025. March 2025.
11. *Concepts around real-time trading for physical and / or virtual stocks with software system: YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME* (<https://zenodo.org/records/14505133>),
RELEASE DOCUMENT COMMERCIAL TECHNICAL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, DECEMBER 17, 2024. DECEMBER 17, 2024.
12. *A C++ Functional Library for Specifying "SDMM" (State Diagram Mealy Machine)* (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>),
Book in preparation, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, 2025. 2025.
13. *User's Guide for the Design and Testing System YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE)* (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>),
RELEASE DOCUMENT COMMERCIAL TECHNICAL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, 2023. 2023.
14. *YERITH-ERP-9.0 DOCTORAL COMPENDIUM* (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>),
DOCTORAL COMPENDIUM, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, MAY 2022. MAY 2022.
15. *Runtime Verification Of SQL Correctness Properties with YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF* (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567>),
Journal article in preparation, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, August 2023. August 2023.
16. *Compendium of Documents About the Design and Testing System YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE)* (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/17316481>),
RELEASE DOCUMENT COMMERCIAL TECHNICAL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, June 2023. June 2023.
17. *SOFTWARE SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OF YERITH-ERP-9.0* (<https://zenodo.org/uploads/17662181>),
TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, NOVEMBER 2025. NOVEMBER 2025.
10. *YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: a framework for verifying SQL software correctness properties of gui software at runtime* (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051303>),
CONFERENCE article in submission, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, February 2023. February 2023.

PUBLICATIONS – YERITH R&D (en langue française) (III)

[LIEN interne à ce document sur mes Spécialités en recherche académique et / ou PROfessionnelle.]

62.62 YERITH R&D – Algorithmes scientifiques (En Anglais) – Non publiés dans 1 journal pour causes de ressources financières entre autres.

1. [Lien sur des algorithmes repertoriés et Créés par moi !]

63.63 YERITH R&D – Rapports

2. **RAPPORTS DE TRAVAUX SUR LE PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-PGI-3.0** (<https://zenodo.org/records/17689313>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, NOVEMBRE 2025. NOVEMBRE 2025
3. **RAPPORT DE TRAVAUX SUR LE PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-PGI-3.0 (années 2015–2022)** (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051568/>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, OCTOBRE 2022. OCTOBRE 2022.

64.64 INFORMATIQUE de gestion — Connaissances Marketing

4. **BROCHURE DE GESTION COMMERCIALE** (<https://zenodo.org/records/17680727>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, NOVEMBRE 2025. NOVEMBRE 2025

65.65 INFORMATIQUE de gestion — Management des données

5. **GUIDE DE L'UTILISATEUR 'MANAGER', PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-PGI-9.0** (<https://zenodo.org/record/8058259/>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, JUIN 2018. JUIN 2018
6. **YERITH-ERP-PGI-3.0: ESSAI DE PRODUCTIVITÉ ENTREPRENEURIALE** (<https://zenodo.org/records/10071437>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, MARS 2021. MARS 2021
7. **GUIDE PRATIQUE DU LOGICIEL DE GESTION COMMERCIALE ET FINANCIÈRE YERITH-PGI-9.0** (<https://zenodo.org/records/17680818>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, NOVEMBRE 2025. NOVEMBRE 2025
8. **DOCUMENT COMBINANT LES PRÉSENTATIONS DE YERITH-PGI-9.0** (<https://zenodo.org/records/17680860>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, NOVEMBRE 2025. NOVEMBRE 2025
9. **FICHE DE DONNÉES DU PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-PGI-9.0** (<https://zenodo.org/records/17680904>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, NOVEMBRE 2025. NOVEMBRE 2025
10. **BROCHURE D'INFORMATION DU PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-PGI-9.0** (<https://zenodo.org/records/17680949>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, NOVEMBRE 2025. NOVEMBRE 2025
11. **AVANTAGES DE YERITH-PGI-9.0 COMPARATIVEMENT À SAGE GESCOM I7, ET À SAP BUSINESS ONE** (<https://zenodo.org/records/17680986>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, NOVEMBRE 2025. NOVEMBRE 2025
12. **AVANTAGES D'UTILISATION DE L'INFORMATIQUE POUR LA GESTION DE STOCKS** (<https://zenodo.org/records/17681077>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, NOVEMBRE 2025. NOVEMBRE 2025
13. **BRÈVE PRÉSENTATION DU PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ (PGI) YERITH-PGI-3.0** (<https://zenodo.org/records/17681095>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, NOVEMBRE 2025. NOVEMBRE 2025
14. **GUIDE D'INSTALLATION POUR LE PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-PGI-9.0** (<https://zenodo.org/record/8060217>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, MARS 2021. MARS 2021
15. **RAPPORT DE TRAVAUX SUR LE PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-PGI-3.0 (années 2015–2022)** (<https://zenodo.org/record/8051568/>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, OCTOBRE 2022. OCTOBRE 2022
16. **YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0 : Configuration MULTI-SITES (SUCCURSALES)** (<https://zenodo.org/records/17681136>), Configuration MULTI-SITES (SUCCURSALES), YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, NOVEMBRE 2025. NOVEMBRE 2025

66.66 INFORMATIQUE de gestion — COMPTABILITÉ analytique

17. **YERITH-ERP-PGI-3.0: NOTIONS DE COMPTABILITÉ ET DE SYSTÈME O.H.A.D.A** (<https://zenodo.org/records/10071458>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, MARS 2021. MARS 2021

67.67 INFORMATIQUE de gestion-PGI-Erp — Accessoires Recommandés

18. **MATÉRIEL INFORMATIQUE RECOMMANDÉ POUR LE POINT-DE-VENTE YERITH-PGI-9.0** (<https://zenodo.org/records/17681167>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, NOVEMBRE 2025. NOVEMBRE 2025

68.68

Ingénierie du Proiciel TRès Avancée

19. **YERITH-ERP-9.0 DOCTORAT / PH.D. COMPENDIUM** (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>),
DOCTORAT COMPENDIUM, **YERITH R&D**, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, MAI 2022.

MAI 2022

FORMER CIVIL ADDRESSES – CANADA

I HAVE LIVED AT ALL THE FOLLOWING ADDRESSES AS A CAMEROON CITIZEN, AND ADDITIONALLY as a permanent resident of canada (FROM YEAR 2005 - 2014) !

I acquired a canadian citizenship in August 2014 (because I couldn't fly freely into Europe without visa application as a Cameroon citizen.) !

I RENOUNCED solemnly THIS CANADIAN CITIZENSHIP, in front of judge at the "Waterloo Region Courthouse (85 Frederick St., Kitchener, ON N2H 0A7, Canada)" IN SEPTEMBER 2018 !

THE JUDGE SAID I COULD PAY FOR THE TRANSCRIPTS to be send to cameroon embassy in Ottawa; BUT I COULDN'T AFFORD for IT !

I THEN DEFINITELY and forever ABANDONED CANADA and ONTARIO for Cameroon in September 2018 !

1. LANDLORD !

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
C/O THÉODORE NGONGANG WANDJI
5850 RUE SOUART # 7
H3S 2E8 MONTREAL, QC

2. LANDLORD john guldemond, anna guldemond

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
391B CHURCHILL CRT
N2L 6B4 WATERLOO, ON

3. LANDLORD mike

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
186 CORRIE CRESCENT
N2L 5W4 WATERLOO, ON

4. LANDLORD Northview Fund

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
457 ALBERT STREET, APT 16
N2L 5A7 WATERLOO, ON

5. LANDLORD !

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
88 GLENBURN DRIVE
N2L 5K1 WATERLOO, ON

6. LANDLORD anna and spouse

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
310 HIAWATHA DRIVE
N2L 5H5 WATERLOO, ON

7. LANDLORD anna and spouse

AS canadian citizen; XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
310 HIAWATHA DRIVE
N2L 5H5 WATERLOO, ON

8. LANDLORD erick djeuyou pokem !

AS canadian citizen; XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
C/O erick djeuyou pokem
5738A rue Hochelega
H1N 1W3 Montreal, QC

FORMER CIVIL ADDRESSES – GERMANY

I HAVE LIVED AT ALL THE FOLLOWING ADDRESSES AS A CAMEROON CITIZEN, AND ADDITIONALLY as a STUDENT AT THE UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN (FROM YEAR 2001 - 2007).

I HAVE BEEN WORKING AS a "software entwickler (junior)" at SIEMENS HEALTHINEERS (OCS) until 2009 !

1. "UNIVERSITÄT BREMEN"

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
C/O THÉODORE NGONGANG WANDJI
LEOBENER STRASSE 4
28359 BREMEN

2. LANLORD "GEWOBA"

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
C/O TAALY MARCELLIN
GUSTAV-HEINEMANN-STRASSE 71
28359 BREMEN

3. LANLORD "GÜNTHER SPREEN"

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
ACHTERBERGSTR. 9
28219 BREMEN

4. LANLORD "ULA QUERFÜRTH"

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
MATHILDENSTR. 41
! NÜRNBERG

BANK ACCOUNTS

Cameroon

1. **EXPRESS UNION YAOUNDE-AHALA: Savings Only Account.:**
SHE (Ms. NGONO), that I couldn't close it: I have to leave it as a dormant closed bank account.
2. **AFRILAND-FIRST BANK HIPPODROME-YAOUNDE: Checking DORMANT Account.:**
I asked for this account to be totally closed in year 2017 with no apparent success; I don't know why.

Outside Cameroon: IN CANADA-Ontario

1. **HSBC UPTOWN WATERLOO; EURO Savings Account.:**
I couldn't close it because I was still inside Canada: So I still need it until I definitively and forever leave NORTH AMERICA !

So I would be glad they close it for myself, without any other mentions that is not in my favor in case I need again such an account elsewhere in the world, outside of Canada.

CANADA WAS A DISGUSTING PLACE TO LIVE FOR ME AS A BLACK AFRICAN.

REAL ESTATES POSSESSIONS

I OWN alone 2 LAND PROPERTIES with land title certificate IN CAMEROON (1 in douala, and 1 in yaoundé) !

1. DOUALA: **LAND TITLE CERTIFICATE nr. 14 000, volume 117, WOURI 5, béedi-kounghi located IN CITÉ-DES-PALMIERS_HAUTE-TENSION_BÉEDI !**
THERE ARE THREE 3-bedrooms APARTMENTS OF EACH around 135 m² of AREA.
I HAVE INHERITED (JANUARY 8, 1992) THIS LAND from late computer PROGRAMMER ANALYST THÉODORE noumbissi (born on APRIL 01, 1956 in OBALA, center-region), my birth-giver on planet earth !
2. YAOUNDÉ (named IMMEUBLE YERITH): **LAND TITLE CERTIFICATE nr. 560 792, volume 265, MFOUNDI VI (6), Nsimbock-AHALA located IN Nsimbock-AHALA_FACE_ENTREE-ETOA-DERRIERE-savonnerie_NOSA !**
THERE ARE 2 2-bedrooms APARTMENTS OF EACH around 105 m² of AREA.
THE GROUND LEVEL IS FINISHED; missing, because of funding, is 4 supplemental 2-BEDROOMS apartments as planned from UNDERGROUND LEVEL !
I HAVE BOUGHT THIS LAND, IN NOVEMBER 2012 (in front of asserted public notary ME. FRANCOIS-XAVIER MENYE ONDO), from cameroon national assembly parliament member; AND vice-president hon. THÉODORE datouo (FROM WEST-REGION; village BANGOU) !
ASSERTED PUBLIC NOTARY ME. FRANCOIS-XAVIER MENYE ONDO, has offices at "IMMEUBLE DU CRÉDIT FONCIER DU CAMEROUN (CFC)" !

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JH_NISSI_cv_combine_anglais_INFRACTIONS _____	26

RAPPORT DE TRAVAUX SUR LE
PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ
YERITH-PGI-9.0
(années 2015 – 2022)

"Pr. Dr. Xavier Noubissi Noundou"

Résumé

Ce document rapporte notre ACTIVITÉ DE L'ANNÉE 2015 JUSQU'À CE JOUR sur le progiciel de gestion intégré (PGI (erp)) YERITH-PGI-9.0.

YERITH-PGI-9.0 est 1 PGI crée depuis le 1 Octobre 2015.

YERITH-PGI-9.0 est 1 SYSTÈME D'INFORMATION qui permet à 1 personne, 1 groupe d'individus (incluant 1 famille), 1 entreprise commerciale, 1 entreprise de services, OU BIEN ENCORE 1 service ÉTATIQUE, etc.; de **suivre sa gestion sur le PLAN DU COMMERCE ET DE LA FINANCE à l'aide de l'informatique.**

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Chapitre 1

Présentation de "Pr. Dr. Xavier Noubissi Noundou"

Figure 1.1 – Portrait de yerith-nissi.

"Pr. Dr. Xavier Noubissi Noundou" EST CHRÉTIEN ÉVANGÉLIQUE 'BORN-AGAIN (né-de-nouveau)', CAMEROUNAIS, ET NÉ LE 16 Septembre 1983 À DOUALA DANS LA RÉGION DU LITTORAL AU CAMEROUN.

"Pr. Dr. Xavier Noubissi Noundou" A 1 GRADE ACADÉMIQUE ET PROFESSIONNEL DE "DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER (DIPL.-INF.)" PROVENANT DE **L'UNIVERSITÉ DE BRÊME EN ALLEMAGNE**, DEPUIS LE 25 MAI 2007.

"Pr. Dr. Xavier Noubissi Noundou" A 1 GRADE ACADÉMIQUE ET PROFESSIONNEL DE PHILOSOPHIAE DOCTOR (PH.D.) PROVENANT DE **L'UNIVERSITÉ DE WATERLOO (ON, CANADA)**, DEPUIS LE 20 DÉCEMBRE 2011.

"Pr. Dr. Xavier Noubissi Noundou" A DES CONTRIBUTIONS EN RECHERCHES ET DÉVELOPPEMENTS, ACADÉMIQUES ET EN INGÉNIERIE PROFESSIONNELLE COMME SUIT :

1. 'Statistical test case generation for reactive systems' RTT-MBT¹; pour la start-up VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH ("<https://www.verified.de>") de l'Université de Brême en Allemagne fédérale.

1. <https://www.verified.de/products/model-based-testing>

2. 'Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis For C using LLVM'

1) code source en C++ :

YERITH-SAINT

<https://www.github.com/sazzad114/saint>

2) document scientifique et / ou technique :

<https://zenodo.org/record/8051293>

3. 'YERITH-ERP-3.0' :

1) code source en C++ :

YERITH-ERP-9.0

<https://www.github.com/yerithd/yerith-erp-9-0>

YERITH-ERP-9.0 SYSTEM DAEMON

<https://www.github.com/yerithd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon>

2) publications en continue : <https://zenodo.org/record/8205911>

4. 'YERITH_QVGE'

1) code source en C++ :

YR_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP

https://www.github.com/yerithd/yr_sd_runtime_verif_lang

YR_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG

https://www.github.com/yerithd/yr_sd_runtime_verif

YR-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF

<https://www.github.com/yerithd/yr-db-runtime-verif>

YR_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_UNIT_TESTS

https://www.github.com/yerithd/yr_sd_runtime_verif_UNIT_TESTS

2) document scientifique et / ou technique :

<https://zenodo.org/record/8381187>

Chapitre 2

Progiciel de Gestion Intégré AU CAMEROUN

2.1 INTRODUCTION

Figure 2.1 – 2 IMAGES représentatives de YERITH-PGI-9.0 (YERITH-ERP-9.0 en ANGLAIS).

Figure 2.2 – Une image de YERITH-PGI-9.0.

Figure 2.3 – DES CHARGES financières (lignes budgétaires incluses)!

The screenshot displays the 'FINANCIAL EXPENSE listing' window. It includes a search bar and several action buttons: 'Show', 'Check in ASSET, OR stock (service)', 'Menu', 'Payments', and 'Remove'. Below the search bar is a table with the following data:

	Product name	Supplier name	Department	budget line	Purchase price	Order date
1	T	CASINO_YR	YR_ASSET	YR_01_140000	-300.00	20.01.2023
2	Z	HP_YR	YR_ASSET	YR_01_140000	-200.00	20.01.2023
3	A	HP_YR	YR_ASSET	YR_02_140000	-3,000.00	20.01.2023
4	ZZ	MINTAP_yerothie	yeroth departement 1 65 - CHARGES FINANCIÈRES		-750.00	20.01.2023

At the bottom of the window, there is a summary section showing '# rows 59', '1 / 1', '# purchases 4', and 'Total (debited) -4,250.00 FCFA'. There are also filters for 'Begin 01/01/2022', 'End 20/01/2023', and a 'value to search for' field.

YERITH-PGI-9.0 est un PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ (PGI)! La figure 2.1 illustre 2 images du PGI YERITH-PGI-9.0.

Un progiciel (PRODUIT + LOGICIEL) de gestion intégré est un **programme informatique** qui aide ses utilisateurs à réaliser des tâches suivantes :

1. **enregistrer (répertorier), rechercher**, des stocks et / ou articles (OU IMMOBILISATIONS) dans un catalogue électronique
2. **VENDRE – TRANSFÉRER – SORTIR – ETC.**, des stocks et / ou articles (OU IMMOBILISATIONS) de leur catalogue électronique d'enregistrement

3. créer des **ALERTES** sur des **PÉRIODES DE TEMPS**, sur des **QUANTITÉS**, etc.
4. **VISUALISER DES STATISTIQUES** sur des ventes, des mouvements, etc. : de stocks, d'articles (OU IMMOBILISATIONS), etc.
5. enregistrer (répertorier), rechercher, etc. : des **FOURNISSEURS, CLIENTS, EMPLOYÉS, MEMBRES, etc..**
6. **EN RÉSUMÉ**, permettre à une personne, un groupe d'individus (incluant une famille), une entreprise commerciale, ou une entreprise de services, etc. : de **suivre sa gestion sur le PLAN DU COMMERCE ET DE LA FINANCE à l'aide de l'informatique!**
7. YERITH-PGI-9.0 PREND EN COMPTE DES LIGNES BUDGÉTAIRES!

2.1.1 DOMAINES D'APPLICATIONS

YERITH-PGI-9.0 (YERITH-ERP-9.0 EN ANGLAIS) peut être ré-utilisé par N'IMPORTE QU'ELLE ORGANISATION NON gouvernementale (ONG), OU GOUVERNEMENTALE!

YERITH-PGI-9.0 A POUR OBJECTIF premier D'ÊTRE TRÈS facile d'utilisation POUR DES personnels ou UTILISATEURS sous éduqués!

LES PGI (erp en anglais) les plus propagés au CAMEROUN : Sage Gescom i7, SAP Business One, ou encore Odoo, SONT BÂTIS pour des licenciés!

1 COMPARAISON DÉTAILLÉE SE FAIT DANS LES DOCUMENTS [[uNu21c](#), [uNu21a](#)]!

En RÉSUMÉ, YERITH-PGI-9.0 a les **fonctions suivantes** :

1. administration des utilisateurs, et, des rôles
2. alertes sur les quantités en stocks, et sur les périodes de temps
3. gestion des RESSOURCES HUMAINES, clients (CRM), fournisseurs, LIGNES BUDGÉTAIRES
4. gestion des stocks, DES IMMOBILISATIONS
5. gestion des ventes (locations, caisse, etc.)
6. recherche basée sur des modèles avec le caractère %
7. tableaux de bords.

LE GUIDE et/ou MANUEL DE L'UTILISATEUR [[uNu22a](#)] DE YERITH-ERP-9.0 re-précise des domaines d'applications, ainsi QUE DES CAS D'UTILISATIONS pratiques!

QUELQUES DOMAINES D'UTILISATIONS SONT PAR EXEMPLE :

1. bureaux d'études et de conception en ingénierie;
2. cabinets d'avocats;
3. sociétés d'assurances;
4. etc.

2.1.2 Droits D'accès

LES UTILISATEURS du progiciel de gestion intégré YERITH-PGI-9.0 n'ont pas les mêmes **droits de VISUALISATIONS, ET / OU DE MANIPULATIONS DES DONNÉES!**

Par exemple, un employé ne peut pas observer ou manipuler des données spécifiques à son patron.

2.1.3 Régionalisation

YERITH-PGI-9.0 est disponible dans des langues suivantes : ANGLAIS, et FRANÇAIS.

2.2 AVANCEMENT PÉDAGOGIQUE ET/OU TECHNOLOGIQUE avec YERITH-PGI-9.0

Table 2.1 – Comparaison entre YERITH-PGI-9.0 et quelques autres progiciels de gestion intégrés

CRITÈRES	YERITH-PGI-9.0	Sage Gescom i7	SAP Business One
vue du logiciel dépendante du rôle	OUI	OUI	OUI
formation complète	au moins 2 semaines	au moins 2 mois	au moins 3 mois
interface du logiciel	évidente	très compliquée	très compliquée
langage dans le logiciel	usuel de tous les jours	simple	technique
formation comptable	jamais	jamais	utile
formation en marketing	jamais	utile	utile
connection internet	optionnel	optionnel	obligatoire

Nos travaux depuis OCTOBRE 2015 au CAMEROUN (yaoundé et douala), et au CANADA (waterloo (ontario)), NOUS ONT AMENÉ À ÉTABLIR le tableau 2.1, comparatif des 3 progiciels de gestion intégrés les plus appropriés POUR LA PLUPART DES entreprises!

AVANCEMENT technologique

Le tableau 2.1 illustre à merveille la simplicité et l'efficacité de YERITH-PGI-9.0, en comparaison avec les progiciels de gestion intégrés "Sage Gescom i7", et "SAP Business One".

EXPÉRIENCE PÉDAGOGIQUE avec "NESTOR KENFACK"

EN PARTICULIER, NOTRE EXPÉRIENCE D'INTÉGRATION dans des structures du promoteur investisseur "NESTOR KENFACK" :

1. QUINCAILLERIE N.K (sis AHALA-barrière)
2. POISSONNERIE PLUS (sis AHALA-barrière)

nous ont permis de RÉALISER que nous pouvions, **AVEC SUCCÈS DE RÉSULTATS OPÉRATIONNELS EFFECTIFS** :

1. FORMER 1 TITULAIRE DU b.e.p.c AU NIVEAU ACADÉMIQUE en 3 JOURS SEULEMENT!
B.E.P.C : brevet d'études DU PREMIER CYCLE (ENVIRON 12 ans d'études primaires et d'études du premier cycle d'enseignement secondaire francophone!).
2. EN DEHORS DE YERITH-PGI-9.0, IL EST IMPOSSIBLE À 92% DE FORMER effectivement le titulaire d'1 niveau académique inférieur à la licence¹, **À L'UTILISATION EFFECTIVE D'1 PGI (erp), avec des résultats opérationnels effectifs!**

1. Environ 3 ans universitaires après l'obtention du BACCALAURÉAT.

AVANCEMENT pédagogique

Il ressort de nos expériences en entreprises commerciales et/ou organisations non gouvernementales; Sage Gescom i7, SAP Business One, Odoo, etc., sont SIMPLEMENT TRÈS difficile à intégrer dans 1 environnement de TRAVAIL où le personnel opérationnel et/ou logistique à 1 niveau éducatif INFÉRIEUR À 1 LICENCE!

2.3 AVANTAGES DE L'UTILISATION DES PGI (erp en ANGLAIS)

L'utilisation des PGI (erp an anglais) aurait des avantages très imposants pour des pouvoirs publics en ce qui concerne des points suivants :

1. **FACILITATION DE L'ÉCONOMIE;** des petits commerçants ne maîtrisant plus des techniques de gestion commerciale MODERNE, ne souffrirait PLUS DU problème de manque de savoir!

EN EFFET, tout les savoirs de techniques modernes en gestion commerciale et comptable SERAIENT IMPLÉMENTÉ dans YERITH-PGI-9.0!

2. **FACILITATION DE LA COLLECTE DES IMPÔTS (fisc) :** en effet, le calcul des recettes et des montants imposables par des administrations fiscales aux commerçants et industriels POURRAIENT ÊTRE fait directement sur la base DE LEUR (**PROPRE DÉCLARATION EN LIGNE sur le média INTERNET**)!

EN EFFET, CECI EST MONNAIE COURANTE dans des grands pays industriels occidentaux TELS QUE LA RÉPUBLIQUE FÉDÉRALE D'ALLEMAGNE (RFA), LE CANADA, ETC.!

3. **FACILITATION DE L'IMPLÉMENTATION des nouvelles politiques économiques ET FISCALES du cameroun!**

En effet, chaque année budgétaire, des FORMULES DE CALCULS seraient automatiquement ré-actualisées dans YERITH-PGI-9.0 (YERITH-ERP-9.0 en ANGLAIS), au fin de faciliter l'implémentation des politiques financières et économiques du CAMEROUN!

2.4 Recommandations EFFECTIVES AU GOUVERNEMENT

2.4.1 Coûts TECHNOLOGIQUES

Table 2.2 – Comparaison de réutilisation au plan financier (**APPROXIMATIF**) entre YERITH-PGI-9.0 et quelques autres progiciels de gestion intégré

CRITÈRES	YERITH-PGI-9.0	Sage Gescom i7	SAP Business One
SYSTÈME D'EXPLOITATION	Debian Linux	MS Windows	Debian Linux
Coût D'ACQUISITION	30 \$USA	200 \$USA	30 \$USA
Coût De La Formation POUR 1 TECHNICIEN	300 \$USA	VARIABLE	VARIABLE
Coût De La Formation POUR 1 USAGER	500 \$USA	VARIABLE	VARIABLE
Coût De La Maintenance (mensuel) POUR 1 ORDINATEUR	30 \$USA	VARIABLE	VARIABLE
Coût De L'acquisition du PGI (ERP en ANGLAIS)	VARIABLE	VARIABLE	VARIABLE

LE TABLEAU 2.2 COMPARATIF DES RESSOURCES FINANCIÈRES RELATIVES À L'ACQUISITION ET À L'ENTRETIEN DES PROGICIELS DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ AU CAMEROUN ressort que :

1. LE SYSTÈME D'EXPLOITATION Debian Linux EST LE MEILLEUR.

2.4.2 Conclusions

L'UTILISATION DES PGI (ERP en Anglais) devrait être PROMUE PAR DES MESURES TELLES QUE :

1. **LA RÉDUCTION DE CERTAINES TAXES entrepreneuriales AUX FINS DE PROMOUVOIR L'ACHAT ET / OU LA maintenance des progiciels de gestion intégré**
2. **LA SUBVENTION financière et/ou économique de l'entrepreneur–investisseur**

EN EFFET, la ré–utilisation des pgi (ERP en anglais) AUGMENTERAIT LA PRODUCTIVITÉ DES entreprises à 1 haut niveau, DIMINUANT ainsi la faillite et la baisse de productivité!

Chapitre 3

PERSPECTIVES D'AVENIRS

3.1 PLAN COMMERCIAL ET INDUSTRIEL

Figure 3.1 – Une image d'1 ordinateur portable 2 – 1 (2 en 1).

JE RECOMMANDE LE financement de LA START-UP TECHNOLOGIQUE YERITH_{r&d} POUR LA MISE EN ŒUVRE DES "ordinateurs portables 2 – 1 (2 en 1)" MUNIS de YERITH-PGI-9.0 (EN ANGLAIS YERITH-ERP-9.0)!

En particulier, des "ordinateurs portables 2 – 1 (2 en 1)" sont très ré-utilisables dans des structures et/ou secteurs industriels et/ou tertiaires avec des caractéristiques suivantes :

1. OPÉRATIONS DE GESTION AUX endroits sans tables et / ou espaces de dépôts (ex : À L'ENTRÉE D'1 SCIERIE industrielle, etc.)
2. MANQUE D'ESPACE pour le dépôt d'ordinateurs "DESKTOP" (e.g. : 1 comptoir ambulancier de vente MTN¹).

1. ENTREPRISE SUD-AFRICAINE OPÉRANT DANS LA TÉLÉPHONIE MOBILE AU CAMEROUN.

3.2 PLAN ÉDUCATIF

3.2.1 Définitions de Gestion Commerciale et Comptable

AU PLAN ÉDUCATIF, nous avons ré-écrit certaines définitions de gestion commerciale [uNu22a, uNu22b, uNu21b] AUX FINS de les rendre plus compréhensibles POUR DES JEUNES en formation au PGI (erp en ANGLAIS) YERITH-PGI-9.0 (en ANGLAIS YERITH-ERP-9.0)!

Nous avons approché des promoteurs d'établissements scolaires et universitaires professionnels AUX FINS de partager des informations et DE PRÉPARER des jeunes élèves et étudiants à l'utilisation des PGI (erp en ANGLAIS) :

1. COLLÈGE intec DOUALA (m. JEAN PIERRE moubeb, EN PERSONNE);
2. Institut Universitaire de la Côte DOUALA (M. Hypolithe Tekeu, EN PERSONNE);
3. Startup Academy 237 YAOUNDÉ (Dr. CLAUDEL noubissie, via EMAIL, WHATSAPP).

Ces 3 échanges ont été sans suite favorables pour cause de défaut de plan OHADA dans YERITH-PGI-9.0.

L'INTÉGRATION DU SYSTÈME COMPTABLE OHADA suis son cours en ce moment!

3.2.2 Intégration au Programme Officiel d'Enseignement Secondaire

Nous préconisons des points suivants aux fins de permettre aux jeunes, même ceux arrêtant des études au bas âge d'être en mesure d'utiliser efficacement 1 pgi (erp en anglais) :

1. INSTRUCTION DE YERITH-PGI-9.0 (YERITH-ERP-9.0 EN ANGLAIS) dès des classes de 4ème AU PREMIER CYCLE D'ENSEIGNEMENT SECONDAIRE FRANCOPHONE; et anglophone ÉQUIVALENT!

LE RESPECT DE CES MESURES PERMETTRA aux FUTURS gouvernements DU CAMEROUN de ne plus avoir à investir beaucoup de moyens financiers et autres; AUX FINS DE PROFESSIONNALISER des jeunes!

EN EFFET, pour ceux des jeunes qui n'iront pas bien loin dans des études, ils seront néanmoins en mesure d'exercer des professions libérales ou pas à l'aide de l'outil informatique DE BASE!

3.3 PLAN DE LA recherche appliquée et/ou fondamentale EN GÉNIE INFORMATIQUE

AU PLAN DE LA RECHERCHE scientifique appliquée et/ou fondamentale, YERITH-PGI-9.0 (en ANGLAIS YERITH-ERP-9.0), NOUS A PERMIS DE DÉVELOPPER DES OUTILS ET MÉTHODES DE test, vérification, et validation de progiciels [Nou23].

NOUS AVONS APPROCHÉ DES STRUCTURES DE HAUTES TECHNOLOGIES :

1. HIMORE-MEDICAL s.a.r.l (PROMOTEUR ingénieur informaticien arthur zang)

AUX FINS DE leur proposer DES COOPÉRATIONS DE VÉRIFICATION ET DE TESTS AUTOMATISÉS DE LEUR PROGICIELS dans le domaine médical cardio-vasculaire!

NOUS SOMMES SANS SUITE DE RÉPONSE JUSQU'À CE JOUR!

Chapitre 4

CONCLUSION

L'UTILISATION DES progiciels de gestion intégré (EN ANGLAIS "enterprise resource planing software") DEVRAIT ÊTRE PROMUE PAR DES MESURES TELLES QUE :

- **LA RÉDUCTION DE CERTAINES TAXES entrepreneuriales AUX FINS DE PROMOUVOIR L'ACHAT ET LA maintenance des progiciels de gestion intégré**
- **LA SUBVENTION financière et/ou économique de l'entrepreneur-investisseur**

EN EFFET, la ré-utilisation des pgi (ERP en anglais) AUGMENTERAIT LA PRODUCTIVITÉ DES entreprises à 1 haut niveau, DIMINUANT ainsi la faillite et la baisse de productivité!

Chapitre 5

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JH_NISSI_infractions_connues_CONTRE_YERI _____	2
cv_YRI_JH_NISSI__DR__PHD__transcripts _____	40

- "Datou, KEMAJOU" Cameroon's gendarmerie colonel indie PAULETTE AZEFA tried to ASSASSINATE myself, openly, in front of at least 7 people, on Yaounde street, on January 09th, 2024.
- Kemajou speaks talk to people walking across roads that they shalln't perform christian cross-signs since these interrupts sorcery they are doing on people walking on roads (June 3rd, 2024).
- Secret (hidden) orders of any type SHALL be out of civilian society.
- Cameroon SHALL DEACTIVATE any kind of army soldiers estate, as SWITZERLAND has done in the past.
- Its is not a good idea to judge people based on suspicious behavior, and not, real proven or not lived reality facts.
- ROSE sangnou, a BIRTH GIVER of mine, SHALLNT ANYMORE be causing so much trouble into my life because she entertains a rostricrucian affair with Prof. Dr. rer. pol. JEAN-CLAUDE SHANDA-TONME; AND with 'DORIS beteung Gweh', 'tchitchui-teuntchou-noumeni-ingride-ingrid-Chandriand', 'Hugues Niomani Tiako'; 'Dr. Henriette Pola', and her spouse 'Dr. Laurent tchandeu'.
- People such as KEMAJOU, who acts as a colonel gendarmerie of Cameroon army ARE ALWAYS TRYING to overcome criminal laws of Geneva.
- I don't want to be living with people that have as profession the killing of other people.
- Rose sangnou sister, (Justice) DOROTHÉE SHANDA NDIATIE, HAS TRIED to kill me by police force illegally in February 2021, as I have a file on judge HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA at DOUALA-ndokoti JUSTICE Palace ! • LAQUINTINE'S Psychiatrist EYOUNG CHRISTIAN, MD, was involved together with 8 other persons at night around 11 : 30PM so to hijack my privately owned property in Douala-CITÉ-DES-PALMIERS. • JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA is from same tribal tribe as ACCUSED psychiatrist main offender (sawa-douala) ! • IT SEEMS "Dr christian eyoung, MD" the corrupted CPDM psychiatrist wanted myself to be sodomized by "BERTRAND" who broke the seal of my gate in steel.
- CIA (Central Intelligence Agency) shalln't hire anymore incompetent persons like 'Peter Alan Burh' 'Emmanuel-baleba-faux-pasteur' 'Brigitte-ékindi' 'magne-narcisse-qc-satan' 'robert-billy-joe-bob-tabet-depse-pd' 'NDZIE' 'PRC-présidence de la république du Cameroun' 'CHAPELLE DE LA GLOIRE DE CHRIST - marc denis djeng djeng - alias pasteur marco' 'jp-kamgain' 'psy-acteur-Ebongue (ing. pétrolier)' 'EMMANUEL-ldiot; hors-mis agent-immobilier-soubil (6 90 60 75 63)' 'santiaire;SAPEUR-POMPIER-de-malheur-anti-gang;civil;indig-gendarme-policier-uniforme-medie' 'NORBERT tchatat' 'Bitoung (douanes)' 'David Moniaux' 'Aurélie Yagno Kamdoun' 'DR FOSSO-sed' 'Soot-canadian' 'Sarah-landy-canadian-citizen' 'tchangou-labforge-ca' 'sandy-sed-beidit; jo-attles' 'carine-alias-edith - LELE - NUJUEP - TCHANA' 'Julien-mboutou; santé publique' 'Dan Wasila waswa - so called pastor baptist church' 'KAMGA adamo - demson' 'Cameroun-chief-of-state; CAMEROUN; SANDRINE yimbour' 'CHENGWA' 'DJOMO-Sawa-gilles-ézechiel' 'didi-rubén' 'mama-fouda' 'INES ngakou' 'Serge Achille Popoussi NONG - sed - cmr' 'Ingride-tchitchui-noumbissi;ingrid-tchitchui-noumbissi;ingride-teuntchou-noumeni;ingrid-teuntchou-noument'; [NKWOUANG] [étième] [TCHUHDIANG-sed-ppe] [NGONGANG] 'Hôpital Jamô' 'assassin;déglingués'; 'LAURENTtchandeu-henriette-pola' 'YOUFFO manuela-psy-malade-mentale;ingride-alaïn-elame' 'francis magloire come nkoulou' 'ZOLUMPE-jacky-diane' 'Pélagie METOUMO, epse tchoutou; hors-mis maître Pélagie METOUMO, epse tchoutou' 'BIYA (Paul et Chantal en particulier)' 'DAIMLERCHRYSLER AG' 'Belvianne meheu nossi' 'Jean LOÏC sieuw' 'GLOBAL EXPERT SOLUTION Sarl' 'maman THÉRÈSE de OMEGA-kom-sipa-eric-joël.' 'JEAN-bernard de OMEGA-kom-sipa-eric-joël.' 'Synclaire NJEUTCHA TCHANA; hors-mis maître Synclaire NJEUTCHA TCHANA' 'BRYAN-tchamaha-naata-iajié' 'SALIOU MOUSSA-pd' 'Affans' 'Faurecia GmbH-bavaria' 'magne-bakam-bir-dgre-sed-cameroun' 'BIR - emane-nikos-marcelin-pierre - capitaine NOUNDOU (CMR-dgre)' 'Christophe NGOSONG (University of Buea)' 'Rainer and Gabrielle SCHULZE-SMIDT' 'Franck biya' 'M. ongouéné (SZTBED-biya-franck)' 'David (GATE SOLUTION CENTER)' 'KREYENHOP (BLG logistics, CDU politicians)' 'Achilles Kouam (PAUL fokam kamogno)' 'Thierry Nyamen (Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.)' 'catholic church' 'Criminal-DST'; 'MOISE-yamkam-tebiwo' 'REZA Kopae (riskview inc.)' 'Thomas NDIE DJOTIO' 'Christelle-akamba-et-autres-noms-de-akamba' 'VALERIE' 'ALT LE PLUS' 'Nestor KENFACK (N.K. quincaille)' 'atango-nji-paul' 'Daniela-siemens-OCS-erlangen' 'Menguéné Mvindi' 'TCHOUFFA' 'Audrey NGUETIE tchanga' 'samanah navabpour; amirhossein vakili' 'JHANE-nyehé' 'ZABER-algérien-bremen' 'DZUKOU -cote-forso-viviane' 'KOM-marcel-roustand-mepo' 'irene-ines-ngakou-ou-FAINEANTÉ-suisse-bordellerie' 'VANILLE-JUNIOR-laure AZEFA-gang' 'GODRICK chekete H.' 'pasteur Landry' 'Eric Joël KOM SIPA' 'Grégoire Owona (CPDM general secretary)' 'SANGO (Spouse Bernadette NOUNDOU (CMR-dgre)' 'gendarme essono en civil (loga-loga-aralli)' 'GÉNÉRAL DE CORPS D'ARMÉE boubou.' 'consortium-comrad-bald-ROTHSCHILD' 'GALAX-YVES-LANDRY-ETOGA-chen' 'jean-yves-gmf' 'HOGA-HOGA-AURÉLIE' 'BORIS tssou; mbeumbe-kevane-laure.' 'mezang-mvoin INGRID' 'TOM ball-mst' 'maître-docteurs-professeurs.' 'JEAN-pierre mouheb' 'Chef-supérieur-douala.deido.-3ème degré' 'CHRISTIAN eyoung; laquintine; psy' 'SHANDA NDIATIE' 'MAXIME napoa eteme' '(a so called baptist church pastor) DR. PAUL siméon noum, Psy.D.' 'Majeed Mike (quantstamp.com)' 'LEO passos (quantstamp.com)' 'iuc; masc. hypothéte tekeu.' 'Eunice GAPIE Yemité' 'Yves Francis DANTEU' 'TEUNTCHOU-chandriand-noumeni' 'Winnie-shanda-joël.' 'Alexie TCHÉUYAP' 'Gervais Nana' 'JEAN CLAUDE SHANDA TONME' 'Jean-Paul YAMTCHÉ (AfriLand first bank; Intelligentia)' 'BISSECK; nkondo-sodomiseur' 'JEAN-PIERRE kamgain' 'Bernadette NOUNDOU, Epse SANGO (cmr DGRE)' 'agent-santé - Gaëlle-idiote-dodo.' 'RAOUL Prince njonkep (SED)' 'ERIC BODEN' 'Prof. Dr. Xavier Siewe Noundou (CMR-dgre)' 'Me. André Édouké' 'Michèlle mvondo' 'JULES neta noundou - (cmr-dgre)' 'rcmp FABRICE-WILFRIED-siemeni-canadian-armed-forces; Prof. Dr. med. Norbert SIEMENI (CMR-sed)' 'Pharmacy fiango-Dr-ngoe-peter-AKUME' 'Ondrěj Lhotáček' 'Dr. Chantal NOUNDOU, Epse ... (cmr DGRE)' 'ANNIE METIAM' 'terreur - 'HONORÉ WOUCHAN' 'POKAM-KHAM' 'Alege, jérusalem ngongal' 'NOUMBISSI' 'Guimezap' 'GEORGETTE' 'Victor Noundou Koliou cmr-sed' 'Christian rikoungueyng' 'Hilaire-yimjido-bertrand-nguere; ancien-sed-gras-savoie.' 'CLOVIS-kemmegne' 'Jeanne MVONDO' 'GHETA' 'rodrique-alain-sienchie-npostang' 'angela WOLFGANG fernand JR owona' 'fanfan (GAUTHIER) SHANDA tonme' 'DR. GADJEU francis aimé tchana' 'ute' 'Patrick lam, Ph.D., P.Eng.' 'JON eyolfsson' 'Prof. Dr. rer. nat. Jan Peleska' churches; in USA-abroad; or whatsoever similar; so-called humanitarianism.' 'Patrick' 'YAGER MABOMA' to try to kill humble black engineers and scientists.
- People like PAUL BIYA shalln't be called president of all Cameroonian anymore because as CPDM ruling party, they harass people that don't call themselves from RDPCI!

CONTACT

- Address: YECEFOIQ – "Immeuble YERITH"– barrière – Simbock, Yaoundé VI, Cameroun
- Email: YERITH.xavier@gmail.com

OBJECTIFS DE RECHERCHE ACADÉMIQUE EN SCIENCES INFORMATIQUE

- Créer 1 progiciel de gestion intégré complet, pragmatique, et de très bas coût, aux fins de contribuer à la diminution de la pauvreté en Afrique.
- Créer et faciliter la ré-utilisation des outils d'analyse formelle de programmes informatiques juste en utilisant des connaissances sur la théorie des automates finis

NATIONALITÉ; STATUT MATRIMONIAL; LIEU DE NAISSANCE

 Camerounais (aucune autre nationalité / citoyenneté); Célibataire; Douala (Littoral, Cameroun)

LANGAGES DE COMMUNICATION PROFESSIONNELLE

- **Anglais, and Français** Cameroon; Langue maternelle
- **Certificat de Langue Allemande "DSH", Très-Bien ("Sehr Gut")** Avril 2002 (Université de Dortmund, Dortmund, Allemagne)
- **Test de Langue Anglaise Américaine "TOEFL-IBT", "NOTE 89"** Juin 2009 (Hambourg, Hambourg, Allemagne)

PARTICIPATION AUX SOCIÉTÉS SAVANTES

- Présent: "FME": Formal Methods Europe; Auparavant: "ASQ": American Society for Quality; "acm": The Association for Computing Machinery.

PARTICIPATIONS AUX CONFÉRENCES ET WORKSHOPS INTERNATIONAUX

- **PLDI 2009; IBM CASCON 2010; MITACS ONTARIO 2012; ICSE 2012**

INTÉRÊTS ET CONTRIBUTIONS DE RECHERCHE PROFESSIONNELLE

- **Liste De Mes Publications à "www.zenodo.org"**
- **Progiciels de Gestion Intégré (PGI; "ERP" en anglais):**
 1. **"YERITH-ERP-PGI-3.0";** <https://www.github.com/yerothd/yerith-erp-3-0> C++; Qt 5; Oct. 2015 –
- **Test Scientifique du Logiciel** **JUNIT 4 Tutorial**
- **Vérification des programmes Informatiques** CASE tools [**YRI_QVGE**], program analysis, formal methods
- A. **Compilers; Verifiable DSL (Verifiable Domain-Specific Languages)**
 1. **Mealy Automata description language;** https://www.github.com/yerothd/yr_sd_runtime_verif_lang flex, bison; Avr. 2023 –
 2. **Ph.D. Dissertation: Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software** Juin 2011 – Déc. 2011
- B. **Program Code Analysis Verification**
 1. **Runtime Mealy Automata C++ library;** https://www.github.com/yerothd/yr_sd_runtime_verif C++; Qt 5; Juin 2022 –
 2. **YERITH_QVGE: A Framework for Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime**
FOSS Code location: <https://www.github.com/yerothd/yr-db-runtime-verif> C++; Qt-DBus; Juin 2022 –
 3. **Dynamic Taint Analysis for PHP in Quercus;** <https://www.github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysisJava>; Firebug; Jan. 2013 – Avr. 2013
 4. **Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM;** <https://www.github.com/AmesianX/saint> C++; LLVM; Sep. 2012 – Oct. 2015
- C. **Cyber-Security**
 1. **SSL – Heartbleed – Software security vulnerability analysis;** <https://www.github.com/AmesianX/saint> C++; LLVM; Sep. 2012 – Oct. 2015

ÉCOLES D'ÉTÉ ET QUELQUES STAGES ACADÉMIQUES

- "1^{ère} École d'été aux Méthodes de Vérifications Formelles" – NSF, SRI International, Menlo College, Atherton, Californie, USA **May 22, 2011 – May 27, 2011**
- "Cours de Préparation à l'examen international GMAT" – Université de Concordia, Montréal, Québec, Canada **Juin 2007**
- "Cours de Management en Ressource Humaines" – Collège Integ, Douala, Littoral, Cameroun — Enseigné par "Dr. Jean Mouheb, Psy.D." **Jan. 2020 – June 2020**
- "Cours d'Anglais pour Études Supérieures" – Université du Québec à Montréal (UQAM), Montréal, Québec, Canada **Aug. 2009**
- "Cours de Programmation du Langage C" – UY 1, CS Department, Yaoundé, Center, Cameroun — Enseigné par "M. Donfack" **Aug. 2001 – Sep. 2001**

CHEFFERIE HONORIFIQUE / DIVERS

- **ROI YERITH-NISSI (oint de jeovah-nissi au ciel, "Ésaïe 45" en SAINTE BIBLE)**
- Créateur et Professeur à l'Institut "YECEFOIQ" (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE)
- Permis de conduire de classe B (Cameroun et Canada)

HOBBY

- Aïkido, Natation, Écoute de la chorale 'GEORGIA MASS CHOIR'.

REVUE LITTÉRAIRE EN INFORMATIQUE

- OOPSLA 2010

OUTILS DE DÉVELOPPEMENT ET DE TESTS ANALYTIQUES

- Frameworks: DIFF, Patch, Txl, ANT, MAKE, Qt 5, S00T, LLVM, flex, bison, Eclipse, Codeblocks
- Langages De Programmation pour Scripts: Cygwin, Python, sed, AWK, Bash
- Langages De Programmation, Outils de Débogages, et de Tests Analytiques: YRI_QVGE, SCALA, Java, C, C++, JUnit, DDD, Geov, Valkyrie, IBM CharmNT
- Technologies Web: HTML5, CSS, PHP 8, Apache Tomcat, GWT (Google Web Toolkit), JSP
- Outils de Gestion Des Versions (SCM): Git, Mercurial (hg), SVN, IBM Rational ClearCase
- Systèmes D'Exploitations: MS Windows (XP, 98, 2000, 7, 10, 11), Debian Linux (8, 9, 10, 11, 12)

ENSEIGNEMENT UNIVERSITAIRE (EN TANT QUE "DOCTORANT PH.D.", PUIS PROF.)

Université de Waterloo, Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA (OCTOBER 2009 – MARCH 2015)

- C++ Laboratory (ECE 250) | Compilers (ECE 351) | Computer Networks (ECE 428) | Foundations of Software Engineering (ECE 651) | Methods and Tools for Software Engineering (ECE 650) | Programming for Performance (ECE 459) | Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465).

TRAVAUX ACADÉMIQUES ET PROFESSIONNELS

- **HABILITATION, équivalent** • Thèse: "Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime" 31 Décembre, 2023 !
Start-up Yerith R&D, Yaoundé, Centre, CAMEROUN
Proposal: YERITH_QVGE: A Framework for Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime
Cours (anglais): Software Verification with Program Analysis
- **Recherche Post-Doctorale avec The University of Waterloo (ECE at WatForm), Ontario, CANADA** 01 Septembre 2012 – 10 Mars 2015
Université de Waterloo, Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA
"Professeur [Prof] au sens étymologique anglo-saxon (expert docteur Ph.D. en Ingénierie informatique)" (recherche en analyse formelle et vérification.)
(Enseignement de l'ingénierie informatique (logiciel, etc.))
"DISSERTATION de Doctorat-Ph.D.": Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM
Conseiller 1: Patrick Lam, PhD, PEng
Conseiller 2: Prof. Sivoththaman Siva
Conseiller 3: Dr. Vijay Ganesh
- **Doctor of Engineering (équivalent académique: "PhD in Electrical and Computer Engineering")** 01 Septembre 2009 – Décembre 20, 2011 !
Université de Waterloo, Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA
Département de Génie Électrique & Génie Informatique (ece) – Grade 88% [A+]
Thèse (research proposal): Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software
Sujets classifiés en Sciences Mathématiques: 68—Sciences Informatique
Directeur de Thèse: Patrick Lam, PhD, PEng
- **Travail Post-Master chez SIEMENS Medical Solutions – OCS, Erlangen, BAVIÈRE, ALLEMAGNE** 01 Novembre 2007 – 31 Juillet 2009
Développeur progiciel junior (SIEMENS linac beam radiation control protocol C++ development)
Superviseurs: Dario Meraviglia et Gerhard Seng
- **Diplom-Informatiker (équivalent académique: "Master (in Computer Science)")** 01 Octobre 2002 – 25 Mai 2007
Université de Brême, Brême, Brême, ALLEMAGNE
Master Thesis: Statistical test case generation for reactive systems
Directeur de Mémoire: Jan Peleska

EXPÉRIENCE PROFESSIONNELLE (EXTRAIT)

- Cyberix, Douala, LITTORAL, CAMEROUN Octobre 2001 – Novembre 2001
Stagiaire Développeur Web (HTML, CSS), Dirigé par Mr. Foguem
- DaimlerChrysler AG, Brême, Bremen, ALLEMAGNE Juin 2002 – Août 2002
(Part-Time) STUDENT INDUSTRIAL CHAIN WORKER (Kfz-Schlosser)
- ZMML, Université de Brême, Brême, Bremen, ALLEMAGNE Février 2003 – Mars 2005
(Temps-Partiel) Développeur Web et D'applications VBA "RAD SERVER"
Dirigé par PROF. DR. RER. POL. (pen.) KLAUS JÜRGEN BÖNKOST.
- Gewete GmbH, Rellingen, Hambourg, ALLEMAGNE Mars 2005 – Avril 2007
(Temps-Partiel) Développeur logiciel (Développement de servlets (Java) et de protocoles de communication)
Dirigé par SVEN KAMRATH (et JENS MÖLLER).
- AGBS, Université de Brême, Brême, Bremen, ALLEMAGNE Septembre 2006 – Février 2007
(Temps-Partiel) Développeur progiciel (UML Statechart plugin pour Borland-Together)
Dirigé par PROF. DR. RER. NAT. HABIL. JAN PELESKA.
- YERITH R&D, Yaoundé, CENTRE, CAMEROUN Octobre 2015 – Courant
Président Directeur Général (P.D.-G.); et à YECEFOIQ, Professeur de Sciences Informatique

1. **LA PAROLE (JEOVAH-NISSI dit JÉSUS-DE-NAZARETH) EXISTE avant DIEU:**
 RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Actes 7 : 56* : *Et il dit: Voici, je vois les cieux ouverts, et le Fils de l'homme debout à la droite de JEOVAH-NISSI-AU-CIEL.*
 RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Jean 1* : *Au commencement était la Parole, etc.*
 RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Jean 1 : 14* : *Et la parole a été faite chair, etc.*
2. **JEOVAH-NISSI (dit JÉSUS-DE-NAZARETH) ÉQUIVAUT À DIEU LE PÈRE TOUT PUISSANT:**
 RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Éphésiens 4 : 5-6* : *il y a un seul Seigneur, une seule foi, un seul baptême, etc.*
 RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Jean 14 : 11* : *Croyez-moi, je suis dans le Père, etc.*
 RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Ésaïe 9 : 6* : *Car un enfant nous est né, etc.*
 RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Romains 8 : 8-9* :
 RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Actes 9 : 4-5* : *Il tomba par terre, etc.*
3. **être "BORN-AGAIN CHRISTIAN":** être "chrétien né-de-nouveau":
 —> **SIGNIFIE N'AVOIR JAMAIS À ALLER DEVANT D'AUTRES SAUVEURS AUTRE QUE JÉSUS-DE-NAZARETH**
 —> **JÉSUS-DE-NAZARETH PEUT T'ENVOYER TE DÉLIVRER CHEZ CERTAINES AUTORITÉS EN SON NOM PUISSANT**
 RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Apocalypse 21 : 1-5* ; *JEAN 3 : 2-3*
 RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Luc 4:8* : *Jésus lui répondit: etc.*
 RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Lamentations 4:1-5* : *!, etc.*
 RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Osée 4:4-8* : *!, etc.*
 RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Job 15 : 1-12* ^{2 citations;} *Ésaïe 9 : 5-6*
 RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Éphésiens 6 : 10-18* : *Au reste, fortifiez-vous dans le Seigneur, etc.;*
Éphésiens 4 : 5-6 : *il y a un seul Seigneur, etc.*
 —> **SIGNIFIE AVOIR REÇU 1 BAPTÊME D'EAU ET 1 SEUL BAPTÊME DE SAINT-ESPRIT DE JÉSUS-DE-NAZARETH**
 RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Jean 3:5* : *Jésus répondit: etc.*
 —> **TOUT GENOU FLÉCHIRA DEVANT JEOVAH-NISSI-AU-CIEL**
 RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Ésaïe 45 : 23-25* : *Je le jure par moi-même, etc.*
 RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Philippiens 2, 9-11* : *C'est pourquoi aussi Dieu l'a souverainement élevé, etc.*
 —> **L'ACTE COPULATIF REPRÉSENTE LE SEUL PÉCHÉ DUQUEL DÉCOULE TOUS LES AUTRES PÉCHÉS**
 RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Genèse 3 : 4-7* : *Alors le serpent dit à la femme: etc.*
 RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Romains 1 : 26 : 28* : *... ! etc.*
 RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Lévitique 20 : 13* : *Si un homme couche avec un homme comme on couche avec une femme, etc.*
 —> **L'ACTE COPULATIF AUTORISÉ SEULEMENT DANS LE MARIAGE D'1 HOMME + D'1 FEMME**
 RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE (NJOUGEP-lele-carine-TCHANA-alias-edith-bangou): *Lamentations 3 : 1-18* : *! etc.*
 RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE (NJOUGEP-lele-carine-TCHANA-alias-edith-bangou): *Ézéchiël 3:22-26* : *! etc.*
 RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE (NJOUGEP-lele-carine-TCHANA-alias-edith-bangou): *Ézéchiël 4:1-8* : *! etc.*
 RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Ésaïe 56:3-5* : *Que l'étranger qui s'attache à l'Eternel ne dise pas: etc.*
 RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *1 Corinthiens 7:38-39* : *Ainsi, celui qui marie sa fille fait bien, etc.*
 RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *1 Corinthiens 7:1-9* : *Pour ce qui concerne les choses dont vous m'avez écrit, etc.*
 RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Deutéronome 7:3-6* : *Tu ne contracteras point de mariage avec ces peuples, etc.*
 —> **LA SORCELLERIE ET/OU MAGIE ARRIVENT SEULEMENT PAR LE PÉCHÉ**
 RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Romains 8 : 6-8*
 RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Genèse 3 : 21-24* : *L'Eternel Dieu fit à Adam et à sa femme des habits de peau, etc.*
 RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Genèse 3 : 4-7* : *Alors le serpent dit à la femme: etc.*
 —> **NE RÉ-UTILISER AUCUN QUELCONQUE OBJET PHYSIQUE POUR SE PROTÉGER DU MAUVAIS ESPRIT**
 RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Exode 20 : 4* : *Tu ne te feras point d'image taillée, etc.*

REEMPLACER 'DIEU', 'ÉTERNEL', 'LE SEIGNEUR', 'ROI', par "JEOVAH-NISSI AU CIEL" pour la lecture.

4. DÉLIVRANCE DE L'ENNEMI (LE LÉVIATHAN ('MBOMA' communément appelé au CAMEROUN) en est le plus dangereux):

CONFESSER jeovah-nissi COMME unique seigneur et sauveur:

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *ZAKARIE* 14 : 1-6 ; *MATTHIEU* 12 : 46-50; *Psaumes* 31 ; *Nombres* 35 : 33-34 ; *Éphésiens* 1 : 18-23 ; ; *Éphésiens* 6 : 10-18 :

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Luc* 10 : 17-22 ; *Luc* 4 : 18

RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *1 Jean* 4 : 3-4 : *et tout esprit qui ne confesse pas Jésus n'est pas de Dieu, etc.*

RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Marc* 16 : 14-20 : *Enfin, il apparut aux onze, etc.*

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Ésaïe* 54 : 11-17

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Jérémie* 50 : 9-16

RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Psaumes* 140, 142 : ..., *etc.*

COMBATTRE la destruction de LA FILIATION PATERNELLE.:

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Actes* 7 : 15-17 ; *Jérémie* 41 (*Abondance matérielles*); *Exode* 14 : 22-31 ; *ZAKARIE* 10 : 6-12

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Ésaïe* 8 : 9-10 ; *Ésaïe* 54 : 11-17 ; *Ésaïe* 29 : 21-24 ; *Ésaïe* 30 : 1-5

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: "*Ézéchiel* 27 : 32-35; *ET Ézéchiel* 28 : 1-10;"; *Ézéchiel* 1 : 19-28 ; *Ézéchiel* 2 ;

COMBATTRE l'Injustice dans les tribunaux, etc.:

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Exode* 14 : 22-30 ; *Ézéchiel* 14 : 12-23 ; *Ézéchiel* 15 : 1-3

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Ésaïe* 8 : 9-10 ; *Ésaïe* 54 : 15-17 ; *Ésaïe* 29 : 20-24 ; *Ésaïe* 30 : 1-5

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Jérémie* 50 : 9-16 ; *Jérémie* 52

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Nombres* 35 : 33-34 ; *Psaumes* 75 ; *Psaumes* 82

COMBATTRE les images de nuit:

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Exode* 14 : 22-30 ; *Ésaïe* 44 : 21-28 ;

RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Deutéronome* 13 : 1-3 : *S'il s'élève au milieu de toi un prophète ou un songeur etc.*

RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Jérémie* 14 : 14 : *Et l'Éternel me dit: etc.*

COMBATTRE le léviathan [AUSSI l'injustice d'l gouvernement des hommes du monde !]:

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Psaumes* 74 : 13-14 ; *Psaumes* 104 : 25-26

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Exode* 14 : 22-30 ; *Éphésiens* 6 : 10-18 ; ; *Ésaïe* 11 : 9-! ; *Ésaïe* 8 : 9-10 ; *Ésaïe* 54 : 11-17 ; *Ésaïe* 29 : 21-24 ; *Ésaïe* 30 : 1-5

RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Psaumes* 22, 140, 142, 144, 145, 146, 143 : *Au chef des chantres. etc.*

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Nombres* 35 : 33-34 ; *Jérémie* 50 : 9-16 ; *Jérémie* 52

COMBATTRE satan (AUSSI appelé LE diable):

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Exode* 14 : 22-30 ; *Éphésiens* 6 : 10-18 ; ; *Ésaïe* 11 : 9-! ; *Ésaïe* 8 : 9-10 ; *Ésaïe* 54 : 11-17

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *MATTHIEU* 3 : 16 ; ; "*Ésaïe* 46 : 10-13; *ET Ésaïe* 47 : 1-5;" (*DESTRUCTION TOTALE*)

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: "*Proverbes* 29 : 8-27; *ET Proverbes* 30 : 1-2;" (*Abondance matérielle immédiate*)

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Jérémie* 50 : 9-16 ; *Jérémie* 52 *Jérémie* 50 : 9-16 ; *Jérémie* 52

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Nombres* 35 : 33-34 ; *Psaumes* 22 ; *Psaumes* 35 ;

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Apocalypse* 3 : 8-9 ; *Apocalypse* 12 : 9-12

Ouvrir ses portes célestes !!!:

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Ésaïe* 45 ; *Apocalypse* 3 : 7-9

REEMPLACER 'DIEU', 'ÉTERNEL', 'LE SEIGNEUR', 'ROI', par "JEOVAH-NISSI AU CIEL" pour la lecture.

* * * * * COMBATTRE les sorcelleries; JEZABEL. * * * * * :

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Psaumes* 144 : 14 9 récitations; *Ésaïe* 49 : 7-11 4 récitations; *Ésaïe* 44 : 25-28 2 récitations; *2 Corinthiens* 1 : 3-11 2 récitations

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *1 Corinthiens* 15 : 12-34 Danger de mort; *Psaumes* 140 5 récitations; *JÉRÉMIE* 31 : 15-20 ; *Job* 9 : 1-5 3 récitations

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *JEAN* 1 : 1-18 2 récitations; *Ézéchiel* 22 : 17-21 2 récitations; *JÉRÉMIE* 31 : 15-20 ; *NÉHÉMIE* 4

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Ézéchiel* 6 : 1-7 ; *Ézéchiel* 12 ; "Proverbes 2 : 9-22; ET Proverbes 3 : 1-12;"

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *ZAKARIE* 10 : 6-12 9 récitations; "Ézéchiel 27 : 32-36; ET Ézéchiel 28 : 1-10;"

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *ZAKARIE* 14 : 1-6 ; *Ézéchiel* 14 : 12-23 ; *Ézéchiel* 15 : 1-3

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Ecclésiastes* 10 : 19-20 ; *Habacuc* 3 : 15-19 "Habacuc 1 : 18-20; ET Habacuc 2 : 1-5;" ; *Néhémie* 9 : 19-26

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Jérémie* 38 : 11-26 ; *JÉRÉMIE* 19 : 1-9 ; *Lamentations* 3 : 1-18 ; *Romains* 8

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *JÉRÉMIE* 38 : 12-26 ; "NAHOUM 1 : 11-14; ET NAHOUM 2 : 1-3;" ; *Luc* 23 : 33-49 ; *Luc* 9 : 57-62 ; *Luc* 20 : 9-18

COMBATTRE l'antéchrist:

RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *2 Thessaloniens* 2 : 8-12 : Et alors paraîtra l'impie, etc.

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Ésaïe* 54 : 11-17 ; "Jérémie 16 : 19-21; ET Jérémie 17 : 1-5;"

RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Lamentations* 4:1-5 : !, etc.

RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Osée* 4:4-8 : !, etc.

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Daniel* 8 : 25 ; *Daniel* 7 : 26-27

CONTRE les esprits DE prière CHRÉTIENNE:

RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Osée* 4:4-8 : !, etc.

CONTRE le vol des biens matériels:

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Jérémie* 41 ; *Jérémie* 52

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Néhémie* 9 : 19-26

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Ézéchiel* 12 : 1-7 ; *Ésaïe* 14 ; *Ésaïe* 13 ; *Ésaïe* 43 : 22-28 ; *Ésaïe* 8 : 9-10 ; *Ésaïe* 44 : 1-4

COMBATTRE les esprits impurs (AUSSI RÉCLAMER SES justices.):

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Jérémie* 52

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Psaumes* 77 ; *Psaumes* 82 ; *Psaumes* 75

COMBATTRE les esprits impurs (AVOIR 1 bien-être corporel !):

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *GENÈSE* 1 : 13-15 (*JÉSUS-DE-NAZARETH* maudit l'homme à cause de sa sexualité (Copulation)); *2 Rois* 2 : 18-25

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Jérémie* 38 : 14-28 + *Jérémie* 39 ; *Psaumes* 77 ; *Psaumes* 82 ; *Psaumes* 75

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *MATTHIEU* 3 : 16-17; *MATTHIEU* 5 : 9-16; *Ésaïe* 44 : 21-28 ;

COMBATTRE les esprits impurs (AUSSI RÉCLAMER SES BIENS FINANCIERS et autres):

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Jérémie* 52

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Ecclésiastes* 5 ; *Ecclésiastes* 6

RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Lamentations* 4:1-5 : !, etc.

RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Osée* 4:4-8 : !, etc.

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Apocalypse* 22 : 12-21

RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Marc* 9 : 25-27 : Jésus, voyant accourir la foule, menaçait l'esprit impur, etc.

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Ézéchiel* 6 : 1-7 ; *Lévitique* 26 : 30-33 ; *Lévitique* 20 : 22-27

RÉFÉRENCE BIBLIQUE: *Sophonie* 1 : La parole de l'Éternel qui fut adressée à Sophonie, etc.

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Ésaïe* 29 : 7-13 ; *Ésaïe* 27 ; *Ésaïe* 45 ; *Ésaïe* 54 : 15-17 *Ésaïe* 49 : 7-15 ; *Ésaïe* 63 ; *Ésaïe* 62

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Proverbes* 12 : 16-28 ; *Proverbes* 13 : 1-11

RÉFÉRENCES BIBLIQUES: *Psaumes* 18 : 32-50 ; *Psaumes* 17

1. JÉSUS AU CIEL,
 NOTRE PÈRE JÉSUS AU CIEL,
 QUE TON NOM SOIT SANCTIFIÉ,
 QUE TON RÈGNE VIENNE,
 QUE TA VOLONTÉ SOIT FAITES SUR LA TERRE COMME AU CIEL.

DONNE NOUS AUJOURD'HUI NOTRE PAIN DE CE JOUR.
 PARDONNE NOUS NOS PÉCHÉS COMME NOUS PARDONNONS À CEUX QUI NOUS ONT OFFENSÉS.

NE NOUS SOUMET POINT À LA TENTATION,
 MAIS DÉLIVRE NOUS DU PÉCHÉ,

CAR C'EST À TOI QU'APPARTIENT
 LE RÈGNE,
 LA PUISSANCE ET LA GLOIRE.

1. L'AMOUR DE JÉSUS, EST SI MERVEILLEUX
 L'AMOUR DE JÉSUS, EST SI MERVEILLEUX
 L'AMOUR DE JÉSUS, EST SI MERVEILLEUX

OOH QUEL AMOUR,
 COMMENT IL EST ?
 IL EST SI HAUT QU'ON NE PEUT LE RÉHAUSSER
 IL EST SI BAS QU'ON NE PEUT LE RABAISSE
 IL EST SI LARGE QU'ON NE PEUT LE CONTOURNER

OOH QUEL AMOUR !

1. JÉSUS NOUS A AIMÉ COMME ON A JAMAIS AIMÉ
 IL (jésus-de-nazareth, jeovah-nissi) NOUS GUIDE CHAQUE JOUR
 COMME 1 ÉTOILE DANS LA NUIT.

QUAND NOUS PARTAGEONS LE PAIN,
 IL (jésus-de-nazareth, jeovah-nissi) NOUS DONNE SON AMOUR
 C'EST LE PAIN DE L'AMITIÉ LE PAIN DE JÉSUS.

C'EST MON CORPS, PRENEZ ET MANGEZ; C'EST MON SANG, PRENEZ ET BUVEZ;
 CAR JE SUIS LA VIE, et je suis l'amour, Ô JÉSUS EMPORTE NOUS DANS TON AMOUR

2. JÉSUS NOUS A AIMÉ COMME ON A JAMAIS AIMÉ
 SON AMOUR (jésus-de-nazareth, jeovah-nissi) FUT SI GRAND QU'IL EN MOURUT SUR 1 CROIX
 SON AMOUR (jésus-de-nazareth, jeovah-nissi) ÉTAIT SI FORT, QU'IL SORTI LIBRE ET VAINQUEUR
 C'EST LE PAIN DE L'AMITIÉ LE PAIN DE JÉSUS.

1. 2002: HENRI BERTRAND NGATCHOU VIOLENTE ma sœur cadette INGRID TCHITCHUI NOUMBISSI (epse chandriand teuntchou noumeni) AU POINT DE LA LAISSER POUR MORTE, comme elle même me l'avait reportée.
J'ÉTAIS ALORS QUITTÉ DU CAMEROUN POUR POURSUIVRE MES ÉTUDES D'INGÉNIEUR DE CONCEPTION EN INFORMATIQUE A L'UNIVERSITÉ DE BREMEN EN ALLEMAGNE.
2. 2005: MARIE HAKOUA NOUNDOU (epse moise tchingwa) ET SON FRÈRE AÎNÉ VICTOR KOLIOU NOUNDOU (6 77 96 07 47) reçoivent des avancements dans la fonction publique grâce à de la corruption chez MADAME LAURENCE epse feu robert.
MADAME LAURENCE, dont j'ignore le nom de famille ou de son époux, est la sœur de JULIENNE NKWOUANO (6 70 77 67 97). Elle (LAURENCE) est en service au ministère des éducations de base au Cameroun.
3. 2007: CHARLES NTETA NOUNDOU violente sexuellement sa cousine paternelle, et mineure d'âge, ANGE-LAURE TEUMA, fille de son frère aîné consanguin MOÏSE YAMKAM, de regretté mémoire.
4. 2006: - PROF. DR. RER. NAT. HABIL. jan peleska, MON DIRECTEUR DE THÈSE DE MASTER 2 recherche en génie informatique de l'université de BRÊME (ÉTAT DE BREMEN) EN ALLEMAGNE, m'insulte copieusement en public pendant 1 séminaire parce qu'il ne comprends pas ma petite présentation.
C'EST POUR CECI QUE J'AI ABANDONNÉ SA PROPOSITION DE POURSUIVRE 1 THÈSE DE DOCTORAT PH.D SOUS SA DIRECTION, et ai préféré aller à SIEMENS HEALTHINEERS travailler en tant que développeur d'applications JUNIOR.
5. 2010: ANGELA TCHAMOU SHANDA epse fernand jr wolfgang OWONA SE RENDS EN RÉPUBLIQUE CENTRAFRICAINE POUR ACHETER 1 DIPLOME DE FIN D'ÉTUDES SECONDAIRES (BACCALAURÉAT A4).
6. 2011: Jules Nteta Noundou essaye de me me faire empoisonner dans 1 restaurant au carrefour Warda à Yaoundé.

7. 2011: **CHIWANZA KASANGA**, la fille de **JOHN KASANGA** (Zambie) m'insulte copieusement après m'avoir invitée à lui rendre 1 visite dans son quartier estudiantin à Waterloo (on, CANADA).

Je reconnais Chiwanza comme 1 étudiante chrétienne avec qui j'ai le privilège de participer au groupe biblique des étudiants africains de l'université de WATERLOO (on, CANADA).

Je reconnais avoir accosté Chiwanza dans le bus de la ligne numéro 7 pendant ma 2ème semaine comme étudiant au doctorat ph.d du département de génie électrique et informatique.

CHIWANZA, ne me reconnaissant plus comme 1 chrétien né-de-nouveau, m'invite donc à participer au groupe biblique de notre université commune. CHIWANZA est à cette époque 1 étudiante de 2ème année en économie de notre université commune.

8. **Janvier 2012: Je fais connaissance avec Audrey Nguétie Tchamga par l'entremise de ma génitrice Rose Sangnou. Audrey vient s'installer chez moi lors de mon séjour de travail à MARKHAM (Toronto, ON, Canada), à l'entreprise IBM comme stagiaire doctorant d'État es SCIENCES, SANS QUE JE NE LE LUI DEMANDE.**

Audrey est du village BAKASSA. JE FAIS PARTIR AUDREY NGUÉTIE TCHAMGA DE CHEZ MOI APRÈS 1 MOIS DE VIE COMMUNE, pour cause d'incompatibilité de vie.

9. **DÉCEMBRE 2013: APRÈS 1 séparation de AUDREY NGUÉTIE TCHAMGA (père géniteur Maurice Nguétie de MÈRE babouantou et de père BAKASSA), je me fais percuter violemment par 1 blond canadien propriétaire d'1 MUSTAND AMÉRICAIN BLEUE lorsque j'effectue 1 virage à gauche à bord de ma TOYOTA COROLLA LE (alors immatriculée "BLAB 045" à Waterloo, Ontario, Canada).**

JE REVENAIS ALORS D'1 voyage pour des congés de Noel de chez l'oncle maternel THÉODORE WANDJI NGONGANG, alors domicilié au '5850 RUE SOUART, Appartement 7, à MONTRÉAL'.

JE n'ai pu faire rencontrer Audrey Nguétie Tchamga à L'ONCLE THÉODORE WANDJI NGONGANG en JANVIER 2012, du fait de sa très grande hostilité envers le nom NGUÉTIE TCHAMGA AUDREY.

Mon véhicule est percuté à Toronto (ETOBICOKE, ON, CANADA), juste après que j'eus déposé JUDITH NGALEU (je connais Judith par l'entremise de YVES FRANCIS Mbiele Kamga), qui est 1 nièce maternelle du SECRÉTAIRE GÉNÉRAL DE L'UNIVERSITÉ DES MONTAGNES À banganté, MONSIEUR HUGUES NTOMANI TIAKO.

PAR RICOCHET, hugues ntomani tiako, avec qui je n'avais plus eu de rapports d'aucun ordre depuis le décès de mon feu père THÉODORE NOUMBISSI; EST L'ANCIEN ET UNIQUE PARTENAIRE en affaire de mon feu père au Cameroun des années 1989–1991.

HUGUES NTOMANI TIAKO et feu THÉODORE NOUMBISSI se sont rencontrés lorsque mon feu père THÉODORE NOUMBISSI fréquentait L'IAI (INSTITUT AFRICAIN D'INFORMATIQUE) – GABON; en tant que boursier de l'état CAMEROUNAIS !

10. 2014: Au moment d'effectuer mon 1er voyage pour le Cameroun, BERCEAU DE MES ANCÊTRES, après avoir acquis 1 citoyenneté canadienne, COMMISSAIRE SPÉCIAL CAMEROUNAIS roger djossi (HÔTEL TONTANA À DOUALA-deido), par l'entremise de HENRI BERTRAND NGATCHOU, se propose de signer 1 acte aux frontières du CAMEROUN, aux fins que je puisse y entrer SANS AVOIR À ALLER FAIRE 1 demande de visa à l'ambassade du Cameroun au Canada, à OTTAWA.

JE N'AVAIS pu participer à 1 conférence-symposium PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION (PLDI) en ITALIE, bien que ayant gagné 1 bourse de déplacement et d'hébergement PUISQUE JE NE POUVAIS PLUS en 5 jours obtenir 1 visa pour l'ITALIE, ern tant que citoyen natif camerounais !

LAURENT TCHANDEU, 1 oncle paternel et 3ÈME conseiller à l'ambassade du Cameroun à Paris d'autant, lorsque j'étais travailleur qualifié en RFA (république fédérale d'Allemagne); M'A CONSEILLÉ DE RENONCER MOMENTANÉMENT À LA CITOYENNETÉ CAMEROUNAISE, aux fins de faire avancer ma carrière professionnelle. C'estz donc ainsi que j'acquiert temporairement 1 citoyenneté canadienne.

11. 2014: JOSUÉ NKWOUANO ET ROSE SANGNOU ME FONT ARRÊTER DE FORCE PAR 1 ESCOUADE DE POLICIERS D'1 commissariat de bonabéri pour me faire emmener par taxi de force chez le feu psychiatre retraité Dr. JOHN. J'étais alors en congé de l'université de Waterloo en Ontario au Canada pour 3 semaines au Cameroun.

12. 2014: LA POLICE DE TORONTO AU CANADA ONTARIEN ME FAIT ARRÊTER ILLÉGALEMENT POUR CAUSE DE "threspass" PAR L'OFFICIER D'ORIGINE ASIATIQUE "YOUNG".

JE GAGNE LE PROCÈS QUI S'EN SUIVIT EN 2018 AUPRÈS DE LA COUR DE JUSTICE PRINCIPALE DE LA VILLE DE TORONTO EN ONTARIO AU CANADA.

JE NE REÇOIS AUCUN DÉDOMMAGEMENT FINANCIER OU MATÉRIEL DES PERTES FINANCIÈRES QUI S'EN SONT SUIVIES.

13. 10 Mars 2015: DR. PATRICK LAM, mon directeur de thèse de l'université de Waterloo (Ontario, Canada) annule, CONTRE TOUTE LOI DU DÉPARTEMENT DE GÉNIE ÉLECTRIQUE ET DU GÉNIE INFORMATIQUE, mon séminaire de recherche "PH.D. RESEARCH SEMINAR".

DR. PATRICK LAM, PH.D. (MIT, BOSTON, MA, USA) A CURIEUSEMENT retiré mon nom de ses étudiants.

DR. PATRICK LAM, PH.D. (MIT, BOSTON, MA, USA) A CURIEUSEMENT OMIS DES ANNÉES DE 2009 À 2015 passées comme "Director of the Software Engineering Program" de l'université de Waterloo en Ontario au Canada. J'ai été son premier étudiant candidat au Ph.D..

14. 2015: THÉODORE WANDJI NGONGANG (ngongangtietie@yahoo.ca) refuse de me rembourser 1 500 EUROS (1 MILLION DE FRANCS CFA) que je lui ai emprunté en 2005, LORSQU'IL DÉMÉNAGEAIT DE L'ALLEMAGNE POUR LE Canada.

15. 2015: DR. LAURENT TCHANDEU et ROSE SANGNOU me font arrêter de force par 1 escouade de 6 sapeurs-pompier devant mon domicile de location à YAOUNDÉ-AHALA-NSIMBOK pour me faire interner de force en psychiatrie de L'HÔPITAL JAMÔT.

17. 2015: **Je suis recruté pour 1 emploi D'ENSEIGNANT-CHERCHEUR À L'UNIVERSITÉ DE L'EXCELLENCE** (<https://pkfinstitute.com>) par le DR. PAUL FOKAM KAMMOGNE en personne, accompagné de M. FONKOUA LE PCA (président du conseil d'administration) DE LA BANQUE AFRILAND FIRST BANK (<https://www.afrilandfirstbank.com>).
- CÉLESTIN (actuel PRÉSIDENT DIRECTEUR GÉNÉRAL (P.D.-G.)) DE LA BANQUE AFRILAND FIRST BANK est passé juste avant mes entretiens avec le PROF. NJINE THOMAS (doyen d'antan de la faculté des sciences de L'UNIVERSITÉ DE L'EXCELLENCE), chez ma tante maternelle DJATIÉ DOROTHÉE SHANDA (epse pr. jean-claude shanda-tonme) POUR SE RENDRE COMPTE DE MA VIE PRIVÉE ET FAMILIÈRE.
- APRÈS 2 JOURS DE TRAVAIL, le DR. PAUL FOKAM KAMMOGNE vient personnellement au centre de recherche de l'université de l'excellence à EMANA-YAOUNDÉ, me débaucher, SOIT-DISANT QU'IL N'Y AURAIT plus de financements pour les nouveaux recrutements; IL DEMANDE ALORS AU PROF. NJINE THOMAS, présent sur les lieux, DE ME FAIRE PAYER MES DROITS DE LICENCIEMENT.
- C'est lors de mon retour provisoire au Cameroun le 15 AVRIL 2015, que je rencontre DR.-ING. JUSTIN BOMDA (secrétaire exécutif du groupe financier ADAF-MC² D'ANTAN) DANS 1 vol commercial de BRUSSELS AIRLINES; je me présente à lui, EN PRÉSENCE DE L'ONCLE PATERNEL laurent tchandeu, et il me fait savoir que je suis qualifié pour le centre de recherche de l'université de l'excellence à emana-yaoundé !
18. 2016: La brigade de gendarmerie de AHALA essaye de me faire pression aux fins que je passe aux aveux que je suis anormal mentalement.
19. 2016: JEAN-DE-DIEU ONANA REPRÉSENTANT MON BAILLEUR PIERRE MARCELLIN EMANA NKOA ENTRE DE FORCE CHEZ MOI, avec l'aide de 3 voisins bété-bulu, ET ils me violentent. IL REFUSE LORS DE MA SORTIE D'APPARTEMENT DE ME DÉBOURSER 60 000 FCFA DE CAUTION DE 1 MOIS DE LOYER; et 150 000 FCFA d'avance pour rachat de meubles; il m'a refusé de repartir avec ces meubles ou 1 partie de ces meubles.
Il m'a précisé avoir le long bras, et que je ne pourrai plus récupérer ce qui me revient de droit.
20. 2017: JE rencontre le DR. AMOUGOU ABATHE ABATHE joseph. IL est au comité central du R.D.P.C de la ville de Mbalmayo et AUSSI directeur de l'observatoire nationale de climatologie.
21. 2017: 1 POLICIER VÉREUX DU COMMISSARIAT DU 19ÈME ARRONDISSEMENT DE LA VILLE DE YAOUNDÉ ME RAMÈNE de force A JAMÔT ALORS QUE J'Y SUIS SORTI, après y être incarcéré 1 SEMAINE PAR SED "Dr. SIMÉON NOMO, Psy.D.".
22. 2017: DR. LAURENT TCHANDEU (LTCHANDEU@yahoo.fr) et ROSE SANGNOU me font arrêter de force par le "Dr. SIMÉON NOMO, Psy.D." avec 3 sapeurs-pompiers devant mon domicile privé (bâti par mes soins en 2013 – 2014 à YAOUNDÉ-AHALA-NSIMBOK pour me faire interner de force 2 mois en psychiatrie de L'HÔPITAL JAMÔT, PAR LE "Dr. Laure Menguéné Mvindi, MD" sous commandement forcé du SED "Dr. SIMÉON NOMO, Psy.D.".
- CES SAPEURS-POMPIERS SONT ENTRÉS DANS MON DOMICILE PAR EFFRACTION puisque je ne leur ai pas permis l'entrée, pour m'arrêter de force.
23. 2017: INGRID TCHITCHUI NOUMBISSI (epse chandriand teuntchou noumeni) marche au Cameroun avec 1 fausse carte nationale d'identité camerounaise, puisque elle est de nationalité allemande depuis plus de 3 ans.
24. 2017: Je me rends pour 1 interrogatoire au commissariat du 10ème arrondissement de Douala. LA PLAIGNANTE SERAIT ROSE SANGNOU et INGRID TCHITCHUI NOUMBISSI (epse chandriand teuntchou noumeni).
SANS ME REDONNER AUCUNE PREUVE DE QUOI QUE CE SOIT, L'OFFICIER 3 étoiles d'or PAUL TCHOOU me fait embarquer pour le cabanon (prison pour fou) de l'hôpital laquintinie du médecin psychiatre Christian Eyoum.
JE NE SUIS PLUS CERTAINS QU'IL Y'AVAIT MÊME EU 1 PLAINTÉ DÉPOSÉE CONTRE MA PERSONNE.
25. Septembre 2017: DJEUYOU POKEM érick, à qui j'avais fait confiance de réceptionner des courriers adressés à ma personne lorsque je serai au Cameroun pour 2 ans, refuse de me remettre tout courrier venu chez lui à montréal, INCLUANT DES COURRIERS DE BANQUE ET DE L'UNIVERSITÉ DE WATERLOO (ON, CANADA), mon ancien employeur.

24. 2017: **PROF. DR. PEARL SULLIVAN**, "DEAN OF ENGINEERING" DE L'UNIVERSITÉ DE WATERLOO (ONTARIO, CANADA), d'origine asiatique, CONTRE TOUTE LOI DU DÉPARTEMENT DE GÉNIE ÉLECTRIQUE ET DU GÉNIE INFORMATIQUE, me fait arrêter par 1 policier d'origine anglaise de la police de l'université (<https://uwaterloo.ca/campus-wellness/services/uw-police>).

FEU MADAME PEARL SULLIVAN M'AVAIT ÉTÉ RECOMMANDE PAR 1 POLICIER NOIR DE LA POLICE DE L'UNIVERSITÉ DE WATERLOO, AUX FINS DE CITER ET PLAIDER AUPRÈS DE PATRICK LAM POUR QU'IL REMETTE MON NOM SUR près de 7 publications dans des journaux et conférences de niveau international, SUR DES ARTICLES OU J'AI AUSSI PARTICIPÉ AU DÉVELOPPEMENT DU PROGRAMME INFORMATIQUE et/ou DES CONTRIBUTIONS SCIENTIFIQUES ACADÉMIQUES.

JE GAGNE CE PROCÈS, puisque j'ai immédiatement refusé de signer 1 document qui m'interdisait de revenir à l'université de waterloo (ontario, canada) sans aucune raisons viables, AUPRÈS DE LA COUR DE JUSTICE DE KITCHENER-WATERLOO EN 2018.

25. 2017: **JE ME COUCHE EN PLEINE ROUTE** donnant accès à l'université de waterloo, EN SIGNE DE PROTESTATION PACIFIQUE CONTRE LA POLICE DE L'UNIVERSITÉ DE WATERLOO (ON, canada).

JE DÉNONCE ainsi la course-poursuite que je viens de subir de la part de 4 policiers en vue de me sodomiser sur le campus de l'université de waterloo, ontario, Canada (Main road).

1 véhicule du "GRT hospital" ("grand river transit hospital") vient me remettre sur pied pour me conduire en psychiatrie forcée or j'ai plaidé la protestation pacifique en milieu de route contre des agressions de 5 policiers de l'université de waterloo, ontario, canada; Ces policiers sont venus à ma rencontre sur demande du vice-doyen d'antan "JEFF ... CASELLO"; C'est aussi ce même idiot d'italien d'origine qui a paraphé de sa signature écrite à main mon relevé de notes officiel de Mon parcours universitaire a WATERLOO.

J'étais au secrétariat de l'université pour me plaindre de la non réception de mes plaintes pour Plagiat contre "DR. Patrick LAM, ph.d."

LE MÉDECIN PSYCHIATRE raciste envers l'africain NOIRE qui m'a fait ma première audition avait mentionnée que je baliverne (raconter des chose inintelligible); Je me suis rendu a ma sortie au palais de justice de la ville de "waterloo-Kitchener" pour déposer 1 plainte en bonne et due forme SANS SUCCÈS.

ON m'a plutôt menacé de me faire sortir par la sodomie d'1 policière de race blonde !!!

Le salaud de médecin psy qui m'a fait le rapport pour que je sorte en me précisant qu'ils n'ont rien Observé de mauvais ou de incohérent après 6 jours de résidence forcées; A voulu garder 1 contact dans ma vie privée.

Sûrement pour déclencher 1 procédure de destruction physique sur moi Puisque j'ai des éléments de preuve irréfutables que L'IMMIGRATION CANADIENNE est 1 mécanisme officiel de destruction mondiale de l'Élite intellectuelle AFRICAINE noire !!!

26. 2018: **LA POLICE DE WATERLOO ET DE KITCHENER** me met 1 masque de sodomie que l'on voit dans les films d'antan, juste à ma sortie du véhicule de police, DANS L'ENCEINTE DE LA BRIGADE DE POLICE.

je fais le raide mort et ils (5 policiers blancs dont 1 très gros blond) ne peuvent me sodomiser !

LE CANADA est 1 pays où des policiers blonds sont très atroces envers des immigrés d'origine africaine, incluant des noirs des îles caribéennes

DANS L'ENCEINTE DU palais de justice, au sous-sol, j'aperçois 1 femme noire des caraïbes dans 1 très mauvaise posture; menottée !

27. 2018: **GEORGE KAUFMAN**, 1 blond, mon voisin de chambre dans 1 immeuble locatif de la cité de waterloo (ontario, canada), essaye d'entrer dans ma chambre pour m'assassiner avec 1 marteau.

JE CONTACTÉ LA POLICE DE LA VILLE DE WATERLOO EN ONTARIO AU CANADA PAR TÉLÉPHONE PORTABLE; LORSQUE LA 1ÈRE ESCOUADE DE 2 POLICIERS BLANCS ARRIVENT EN VÉHICULE, george kaufman essaye au rez-de-chaussée d'aussi appeler la police. 1 2ÈME VÉHICULE DE POLICE ARRIVE, et 1 POLICIÈRE de race blanche décide de m'arrêter.

LORS DU PRÉLIMINAIRE DEVANT LE JUGE DE PAIX, 1 femme de race blanche, pour ma libération sous-caution, JE renonce immédiatement à la citoyenneté canadienne; ELLE APPROUVE ET REPRÉCISE QUE LES POURPARLERS NE SONT PAS automatiquement retransférés au haut-commissariat du cameroun à ottawa (on, Canada); puisque JE RECOUVRE AUTOMATIQUEMENT MA CITOYENNETÉ camerounaise d'après les lois de la république du cameroun.

JE SORS ALORS DU CANADA EN Septembre 2018 POUR LA RÉPUBLIQUE FÉDÉRALE D'ALLEMAGNE, ET ENSUITE POUR le berceau de mes ancêtres le Cameroun.

DONC CE PROCÈS EST PENDANT AUPRÈS DE LA COUR DE JUSTICE DE KITCHENER-WATERLOO (ON, CANADA) DEPUIS PRÈS DE 5 ANS MAINTENANT.

CAR JE NE SAIS PLUS POURQUOI J'AI ÉTÉ INCULPÉ par cette policière de race blanche.

28. 2018: **MON VOISIN DE CHAMBRE**, dr. eric-brefo mensah, de citoyenneté canadienne et d'origine ghanéenne, ESSAIE DE M'INVITER À DISCUTER NÉGATIVEMENT DE SON confrère ghanéen DR. SANDY BEIDU; étant chrétien authentique, qui ne fait pas dans la calomnie et du mensonge, JE L'ESQUIVE; pensant être plus imposant physiquement que moi, il fait allusion à l'usage de sa force physique.

SANS MÊME ME FÂCHER, je lui démontre 1 posture qui est très dangereuse pour son égôt s'il essaye quoi que ce soit contre ma personne physique !

29. 2018: **J'EU CONNAISSANCE PAR** rose sangnou ma génitrice QUE 1 camarade de DEMO NOUNDOU david essaye de la faire voyager pour le canada ontarien aux fins de venir me sortir du canada PARCE QUE JE SERAIS ANORMAL MENTALEMENT.

30. **Août 2018:** DJEUYOU POKEM érick ME FAIT PENSER QUE JE SUIS RECHERCHÉ POUR FOLIE par ma génitrice ROSE SANGNOU alors que je suis en escale chez le cousin de mon feu papa HENRI KÉWOU de Montréal.

31. **Septembre 2018:** ROSE SANGNOU MA GÉNITRICE et son frère cadet HENRI BERTRAND NGATCHOU VIENNENT me chercher en fracas a l'aéroport de Douala alors que je suis en transit pour yaoundé par autobus.

32. **Septembre 2018:** ROSE SANGNOU et son frère cadet HENRI BERTRAND NGATCHOU me font arrêter par le commissariat de police du 9ÈME arrondissement de la ville Douala pour me faire incarcérer au cabanon (prison de fou) de LAQUINTINIE par LE MÉDECIN PSYCHIATRE Christian Eyoum.

J'AI, par signe de protestation, détruit la porte en bois de la chambre VIP où Christian Eyoum m'avait fait interné puisque je pouvais décéder dans 1 cabanon, AU VUE DE MON ARRIVÉE DE WATERLOO (ON, CANADA) avec 1 climat d'hivers tempéré à cette période de l'année.

JE REMET TOUT CECI ENTRE DES MAINS DE JEOVAH–NISSI AU CIEL.

33. **Septembre 2018:** ROSE SANGNOU me fait arrêter chez MOI, par 1 escouade de 6 sapeurs–pompiers soit-disant que j'ai cassé mes effets personnels.

34. **JANVIER – JUILLET 2020:** Christian Eyoum dit que je ne suis pas 1 malade psychiatrique, mais que notre famille a 1 problème systémique. IL (Christian Eyoum) décide alors de me transférer chez 1 ancien psycho-thérapeute de LAQUINTINIE, "Dr. JEAN MOUBEB, MD" (actuellement PRINCIPAL DU COLLÈGE INTEG DE DOUALA–AKWA).

LA STAGIAIRE 'FOTOS' DE LA gente féminine, m'y accompagne. Le collège integ de douaala–akwa est situé à quelques centaines de mètres de l'hospital LAQUINTINIE!

"Dr. JEAN MOUBEB, MD" est à cette époque de l'année entrain de recevoir ma sœur cadette INGRID TCHITCHUI NOUMBISSI (epse chandriand teuntchou noumeni) POUR LE MÊME PROBLÈME. "Dr. JEAN MOUBEB, MD" décide lors de ma 1ère consultation que je devrais m'associer à ROSE SANGNOU ET A INGRID TCHITCHUI NOUMBISSI pour faire 1 thérapie familiale et 1 thérapie individuelle.

"Dr. JEAN MOUBEB, MD" diagnostique et traite sur ma personne 1 problématique de "père manquant" et 1 problématique de "forte colère". Après 6 mois de psycho-thérapie individuelle et familiale par PSYCHANALYSE, en compagnie de ROSE SANGNOU et de INGRID TCHITCHUI NOUMBISSI, "Dr. JEAN MOUBEB, MD" estime que je suis guéri et que je peux même déjà me traiter personnellement pour toute autre problématique mineur en ré-utilisant la PYRAMIDE DES BESOINS DE MAXLOW qu'il m'a inculqué.

"Dr. JEAN MOUBEB, MD" nous (INGRID TCHITCHUI NOUMBISSI et ROSE SANGNOU) que nous devons aller vivre sans plus mélanger notre vie de famille nucléaire avec des oncles et des tantes utérins ou plus.

"Dr. JEAN MOUBEB, MD" re-précise ne plus vouloir écrire 1 rapport pour Christian Eyoum qui nous (ROSE SANGNOU et INGRID TCHITCHUI NOUMBISSI) a transféré chez lui.

À ce moment, je n'ai jamais eu de contacts aucun avec DR. ERERO NJIENGWE (psychologue–thérapeute), qui interviendra de force dans ma vie plus tard; après que mon domicile privé de la cité–des–palmiers fut démoli pour essayer de m'assassiner dans 1 nuit de FÉVRIER 2021.

35. **2020:** HENRI BERTRAND NGATCHOU (HENRINGATCHOU@yahoo.fr), 1 oncle maternel véreux, et aussi 1 déclarant sous-douane QUI FAIT FALSIFIER DES MONTANTS DE FACTURATIONS DE PRODUITS DE SES CLIENTS sous mes yeux en pensent que JE LUI REDEMANDERAI DE ME RÉINTRODUIRE DANS SA SUITE D'EMPLOYÉS.

36. **2020:** DAVID FRANCIS ÉBOUTTE, mon locataire et propriétaire de la société d'échafaudage industriel TRADIS S.A.R.L. (<https://tradis-cm.com>) essaie de m'agresser physiquement pour cause que je lui réclame son loyer.

37. 2020: **DAVID FRANCIS ÉBOUTTE, mon locataire et propriétaire de la société d'échafaudage industriel TRADIS S.A.R.L. (<https://tradis-cm.com>) me fait des dérangements journaliers en recrutant des petits voyous aux fins qu'ils viennent dans ma fin de route pour faire des bavardages et commérages inutiles.**
38. **Janvier 2021: La brigade de gendarmerie de ndog-bong essaye de m'intimider à aller de force prendre 1 traitement psychiatrique aux fins de re-assouvir des désirs de LAURENT TCHANDEU qui a des projets politiques d'envergures.**
39. **Février 2021: BERTRAND, gros bras de Christian Eyoum est entré par effraction à mon domicile de la cité-des-palmiers en FÉVRIER 2021 aux alentours de "23 : 18" dans la nuit, après avoir défoncé le cadenas avec 1 arme blanche.**
40. **Février 2021: Christian Eyoum établie 1 acte médical contre moi, APRÈS AVOIR ÉTÉ ENTRÉ CHEZ MOI CONTRE MA VOLONTÉ. IL REMET CET ACTE faux et non souhaité de ma personne, à ROSE SANGNOU ma génitrice.**
41. **2021: "Dr. MVONDO, MD" de L'HÔPITAL ADLUCHEM DE DOUALA-BONAMOOUSSADI ME FAIT, avec l'approbation sans mon consentement aucun, de l'oncle paternel VICTOR KOLIOU NOUNDOU, INTERNER 2 SEMAINES A LA PRISON POUR FOU (cabanon) DE L'HÔPITAL LAQUINTINIE DE LA VILLE DE DOUALA.**
- La venue de la famille TCHINGWA (marie et moise) Sans que je ne les invite avait déjà alerté ma personne qu'ils viennent pour me faire des embrouilles.**
- J'Y ÉTAIS (ADLUCHEM) POURTANT POUR TRAITER 1 HYPERGLYCÉMIE CHRONIQUE.**
42. **2021: 1 VOISINE: dont j'ignore même des noms ou prénoms, sous le prétexte que je l'aurai accosté pour des besoins sexuels, DÉBARQUE DEVANT MA DEVANTURE POUR BAGARRER AVEC MA PERSONNE.**
- APRÈS QUE J'EU RECONTACTÉ LA compagnie de gendarmerie de ndog-bong, ELLE (la compagnie de gendarmerie de ndog-bong) me fait savoir qu'elle est dans l'incapacité d'appréhender cette jeune fille au pseudonyme de "HILARY".**
43. **2021: PETER AKUME NGOE (PHARMACY FIANGO LYCÉE MAKEPE à Douala-Makepè), 1 pharmacien avec qui j'avais conclus 1 partenariat de fourniture et de déploiement de mon système d'information ERP-PGI, refuse de me reverser 1 reliquat de 50 000 FCFA de paiement.**
- PETER AKUME NGOE est 1 ANCIEN EMPLOYÉ DE LA FONDATION ADLUCHEM.**
44. **2021: LE MAIRE DE DOUALA 5ÈME, RICHARD MFEUGWANG, REFUSE DE ME RECEVOIR AUX FINS D'EXAMINER MES DEMANDES DE VIABILISER L'ACCÈS A MES PROPRIÉTÉS DE LA CITÉ-DES-PALMIERS A DOUALA.**
45. **2022: THÉODORE WANDJI NGONGANG, DE CITOYENNETÉ CANADIENNE, a acquis frauduleusement 1 terrain revendu à Douala LOGBESSOU, situé derrière le terrain bâti de son frère cadet HENRI BERTRAND NGATCHOU.**
46. **Janvier 2022: La société frauduleuse forestière S2TBED fait éroder complètement la route principale menant a mon immeuble R+2 inachevé de YAOUNDÉ-AHALA-SIMBOK au point ou le piéton est obligé, POUR NE PAS MARCHER DANS LA BOUE RIVIÈRE, remonter du cote des fabricants de charbons illégal.**

47. 2022: MOÏSE TEBIWO YAMKAM me fait comprendre de manière subjective qu'il est mieux dans la vie que moi puisqu'il est au courant des transactions immobilières locatives que j'entendrai mener avec 1 locataire potentiel qu'est la société frauduleuse forestière S2TBED.
48. 2022: ANNIE MÉTIAM EPSE POKAM-KWAM a acquis frauduleusement 1 terrain revendu par la C.N.P.S à Douala Cité-des-palmiers.
49. 2022: AURÉLIEN ILOGA ILOGA, ancien camarade des classes de Douala au collège Alfred-Saker de Deïdo, ET EMPLOYÉ DE ECOBANK POSTE CENTRALE de yaoundé, essaye de me faire violenter par 1 gendarme (ESSONO) en civil.
ESSONO est de très petite taille et avec 1 gabarie d'athlète. ESSONO M'AVAIT DIT ÊTRE 1 chef de gardiens de prisons. AURÉLIEN ILOGA ILOGA me fait comprendre que sa sœur est procureur de la république.
50. 2022: TAATA RÉMI POUASSI, de citoyenneté allemande, a acquis 1 terrain frauduleusement qui porte son nom à yaoundé.
51. FÉVRIER 2022: S2TBED est venu avec 1 camion en surpoids se positionner devant l'une des entrées de mes résidences de YAOUNDÉ-AHALA-SIMBOK, creusant ainsi le sol au point de créer 1 érosion insoutenable de la route juste à l'avant du portail gauche de mon immeuble R+2 non achevé.
52. 2022: ROSE SANGNOU a volé mes titres fonciers, sous la houlette de MOÏSE TEBIWO YAMKAM (yamkam01@yahoo.fr).

- (a) DOUALA: LAND TITLE CERTIFICATE nr. 14 000, volume 117, WOURI 5, béédi-kounghi located IN CITÉ-DES-PALMIERS_HAUTE-TENSION_BÉEDI !

THERE ARE THREE 3-bedrooms APARTMENTS OF EACH around 135 m² of AREA.

I HAVE INHERITED (JANUARY 8, 1992) THIS LAND from late computer PROGRAMMER ANALYST THÉODORE noumbissi (born on APRIL 01, 1956 in OBALA, center-region), my birth-giver on planet earth !

- (b) YAOUNDÉ (named IMMEUBLE YERITH): LAND TITLE CERTIFICATE nr. 560 792, volume 265, MFOUNDI VI (6), Nsimbock-AHALA located IN Nsimbock-AHALA_FACE_ENTREE-ETOA-DERRIERE-savonnerie_NOSA !

THERE ARE 2 2-bedrooms APARTMENTS OF EACH around 105 m² of AREA.

THE GROUND LEVEL IS FINISHED; missing, because of funding, is 4 supplemental 2-BEDROOMS apartments as planed from UNDERGROUND LEVEL !

I HAVE BOUGHT THIS LAND, IN NOVEMBER 2012 (in front of asserted public notary ME. FRANCOIS-XAVIER MENYE ONDO), from cameroon national assembly parliament member; AND vice-president hon. THÉODORE datou (FROM WEST-REGION; village BANGOU) !

ASSERTED PUBLIC NOTARY ME. FRANCOIS-XAVIER MENYE ONDO, has offices at "IMMEUBLE DU CRÉDIT FONCIER DU CAMEROUN (CFC)" !

53. 2022: MOÏSE TEBIWO YAMKAM ne doit plus dire être avocat au barreau du Cameroun, puisque le nom mentionné sur son parchemin de la "LAW SCHOOL DE LAGOS" ne correspond plus au nom de son acte de naissance original.

54. 2022: 1 gendarme extrêmement véreux décide de m'arnaquer dans la gestion de mes maisons de la cité-des-palmiers en COMLOTANT avec ma locataire Mme ELIZABETH YAMBA, pour dire que je suis 1 mauvais bailleur qui appelle sans cesse.

55. 2023: KAMJOU, dont j'ignore des prénoms et/ou autres identifications personnelles, ET QUI EST 1 VOISIN ÉLOIGNÉ DE MES RÉSIDENCES DE AHALA-SIMBOK, par jalousie sur mes biens et qualifications académiques, TELS QUE PROCLAMÉS PAR ROSE SANGNOU ma génitrice, PASSE LE CLAIR DE SON TEMPS À RAPPELER rose sangnou pour lui dire que je passe mon temps à faire des signes de croix chrétiennes lorsque je déambule les rues de Yaoundé.

KAMJOU, colonel retraité de gendarmerie, et membre de la secte religieuse JÉRUSALEM APOSTOLAT, EST AUSSI 1 CONNAISSANCE DE L'HOMME D'AFFAIRE THÉODORE DATOUO qui m'a arnaqué sur le prix de terrain que je lui ai racheté en OCTOBRE 2012, pour près de '6,5 millions de francs cfa'.

56. 2023: MAÎTRE SYNCLAIRE NJEUTCHA TCHANA (tchabalsynclaire@yahoo.fr), mon conseil et AVOCAT CONSTITUÉ, EST 1 PEU SCEPTIQUE SUR MA CRÉDIBILITÉ, après avoir subis des pressions monumentales, depuis son cabinet de "DIAMOND HILL" À DOUALA, venant de LAURENT TCHANDEU.

SYNCLAIRE NJEUTCHA TCHANA est dans mon affaire depuis l'essai du procureur de la république de Douala-Ndokoti (NOËL MOUELLE) de me faire abandonner ma plainte contre **Christian Eyoum**.

SYNCLAIRE NJEUTCHA TCHANA est donc obligé de passer ce dossier à MONSIEUR LE PRÉSIDENT DU TRIBUNAL DU PARQUET DE DOUALA-NDOKOTI et **JUGE D'INSTRUCTION HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA**.

LAURENT TCHANDEU essaye de se faire passer pour mon responsable parental alors que je suis adulte et majeur, vivant à mes dépens seulement.

57. 2023: **THÉODORE DATOUO** (https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Th%C3%A9odore_Datouo) a installé des vas-nu-pieds aux alentours du lopin de terre qu'il m'avait revendu pour près de "20 milles dollars canadiens tous frais compris en *Septembre* 2012 LORS DE MON CONGÉ ANNUEL de L'UNIVERSITÉ DE WATERLOO (ON, CANADA).
58. 2023: MANI, la protégée de **THÉODORE DATOUO** A, COMME CE SONT DES PÉRIODES PRE-ÉLECTORALES, recommencée à salir la routes avec des herbes et détritrus divers.
ELLE ('MANI') dit avoir été installée avec l'approbation de **CAMRAIL (Cameroon National Railway)** sur leur lopin de terre, grâce à l'action de l'honorable **THÉODORE DATOUO**.
'MANI' est du village Dschang a l'ouest du Cameroun et ne pratique aucune activité lucrative légale ou connu des voisins directs ou indirects.
THÉODORE DATOUO œuvre ainsi pour l'installation de bidon-villes dans la zone de AHALA-SIMBOK.
59. 2023: **Rose Sangnou ma génitrice rencontre le procureur de YAOUNDÉ–central PROCUREUR DIFFO MOYOUM pour me faire interner dans 1 établissement de santé mentale.**
60. 2023: **DOROTHÉE SHANDA NDJATIÉ EPSE PR. SHANDA–TONME JEAN–CLAUDE**, sœur utérine de ROSE SANGNOU, me fait violenter par 2 brigands en route, juste avant mon entrée principale à yaoundé–AHALA–NSIMBOK.
61. 2023: Rose Sangnou ma génitrice a intégrée mon appartement de 3 chambres de la cité-des-palmiers où je logeais MADAME ELIZABETH YAMBA comme locataire (au loyer mensuel de 120 000 FCFA) sans me consulter.
62. 2023: **1 CITOYENNE DE LA RÉPUBLIQUE FÉDÉRALE D'ALLEMAGNE, accompagnée d'1 citoyenne des ÉTATS-UNIS D'AMÉRIQUE (ÉTAT DE L'OHIO selon ses dires), me menace de me faire interner à l'hôpital BETHESDA DE YAOUNDÉ.**
63. 2023: LAURENT TCHANDEU A ÉTABLIE 1 TITRE FONCIER DE NOTRE PROPRIÉTÉ DE BABOUANTOU AU CAMEROUN SANS AVOIR MENTIONNÉ MON NOM à titre d'ayant–droit légal de feu Théodore NOUMBISSI.
64. *Juillet* 2023: DAVID DÉMO NOUNDOU, frère benjamin de mon feu père biologique THÉODORE NOUMBISSI me fait 1 remarque très désobligeante: 'IL (DÉMO NOUNDOU david) ME TRAITE DE FOU EN PUBLIC PAR 2 reprises'.
J'AI REPRÉCISÉ À SES FRÈRES BIOLOGIQUES ET/OU UTÉRINS que j'ai, en tant que CHEF DE FAMILLE NOUNDOU (KING YERITH-NISSI (FEU)) donné la folie de malédiction à toutes ses (DÉMO NOUNDOU david) générations descendantes partout où il peuvent se retrouver.
65. *Juillet* 2023: VICTOR KOLIOU NOUNDOU me menace de me refaire prendre des comprimés de psychiatrie par force.
66. "18" *Juillet* 2023: **LA SOCIÉTÉ ILLÉGALE FORESTIÈRE S2TBED** (https://bois.fordaq.com/entreprise/S2TBED_278682.html), **face à mon domicile de YAOUNDÉ–AHALA–SIMBOK, est entrain de collaborer avec ma génitrice ROSE SANGNOU CES JOURS (18–22) DU MOIS DE JUILLET aux fins de me faire interner à l'hôpital JAMÔT DE YAOUNDÉ.**

S2TBED appartiendrait à FRANCK BIYA, le fils du président de la république PAUL BIYA.

67. "21" *Juillet 2023*: 1 CERTAIN MONSIEUR DONT J'IGNORE DES IDENTIFICATIONS, mais qui m'a dit être le propriétaire de !ETS NEKDEM à barrière, et se nommant ÉDIMA FIDÈLE, vient à ma rencontre sans que je ne le veuille et commence à raconter en public que je RAQUETTE DES PERSONNES pour gagner mon pain quotidien.

Des riverains m'ont interpellés sur le fait que des agents communaux passent régulièrement soutirer des argents aux fins qu'ils ne soient plus déguerpis.

LEURS DÉGUERPISSEMENTS AURAIENT EU LIEU FIN FÉVRIER 2023.

Ceci ralentit l'avancement de mes investissements de près de 70 MILLIONS DE FRANCS CFA consentis depuis près de 12 ans.

68. "02" *Août 2023*: S2TBED, 1 société frauduleuse immobilière, et voisine de ma propriété de YAOUNDÉ-AHALA-SIMBOK, répand des fausses informations dans le voisinage:

1. LA ROUTE JOUXTANT MES DOMICILES NE SERAIENT qu'1 route de quartier, et non 1 route légale de l'État du Cameroun.

69. "03" *Août 2023*: ONGUENE, 1 directeur de la société frauduleuse immobilière S2TBED, installée sans permis de bâtir face à mes résidences avec permis de bâtir de la communauté urbaine de yaoundé (CUY), essaie en vain de me faire partir de mes lotissements:

1. DR. LUCAS KEMGANG, propriétaire officiel de S2TBED, entre en contact avec moi par le biais de MONSIEUR SIMPLICE EBAKA KAMENI, et me propose de lui revendre toutes mes résidences (4 non achevées, 1 complètement finie, et 1 résidence partiellement achevée).

2. ONGUENE, il vient à ma rencontre, et par devant des badaux et riverains du coin, tance: TU NE PEUX PLUS VIVRE ICI DANS CE COIN.

70. *Août 2023*: DR. LAURENT TCHANDEU essaye de me faire des supplices en re-précisant que je ne devrais plus arrêter des comprimés psychiatriques.

DR. LAURENT TCHANDEU NE SE REPRÉSENTE PLUS DEVANT MA PERSONNE DE PEUR QUE NOUS PUISSIONS AVOIR 1 ALTERCATION PHYSIQUE puisqu'il m'a déjà fait violenter à plusieurs reprises.

Dr. HENRIETTE POLA (son épouse et médecin gastro-entérologue et hépatologue), LUI A DÉJÀ DIT DE NE PLUS ME RECONTACTER. MAIS AU VUE DE SON PASSÉ CRIMINEL, il n'arrive plus à rester tranquille sans s'attaquer à des jeunes hommes, plein d'avenir et de vie.

DR. LAURENT TCHANDEU A ÉTÉ 1 COLLABORATEUR DE FEU JEAN FOCHIVÉ au cameroun ancien !

71. "17" AOÛT 2023: NOS NÉGOCIATIONS (avec agent secrétariat à la défense "HAPPINESS POTENTIAL S.A.R.L.") SUR LE RACHAT D'1 ORDINATEUR PORTABLE NEUF À "TITO MLARKET SARL (<https://>)", à AKWA-ZÉPOL, ne se passent plus comme prévus du fait de MANQUE DE FONCTIONNALITÉ "bios-legacy".
72. "21" AOÛT 2023: DR.-ENG. DIPL.-INF. XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU ENTRE À LA BOULANGERIE zépol DE DOUALA-AKWA ACHETER son petit-déjeuner.
- À SA SORTIE, 1 dame vigile de la banque marocaine SCB CAMEROUN, vient lui faire 1 agression verbale et physique EN LUI EMPOIGNANT SON T-SHIRT "Pierre Cardin rouge".
- XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU est désempubqué par 'JUMEAUX', commerçant de produits de luxes HOMME.
- XAVIER par la suite étant au bureau de FABRICE WILFRIED SIEMENI, est interpellé par 1 responsable de la SCB CAMEROUN, agence de AKWA-ZÉPOL; XAVIER LUI DEMANDE DE S'ENTRETENIR AVEC SON AVOCAT ET CONSEIL, me. synclaire tchana njeutcha, SANS SUCCÈS. L'IMPOSANT, PHYSIQUEMENT, cadre de banque menace DR.-ING. DIPL.-INF. XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU de le faire taire par ses coups de poings, PAR DEVANT plus de 8 témoins oculaires, JUSTE À L'ENTRÉE DE "happiness potential sarl" !
73. "26" AOÛT 2023: M. ALAIN TASSI (6 74 65 60 65) VIENT CHEZ MOI À YAOUNDÉ - AHALA - SIMBOK, sans que je ne l'ai invité; Pour soit-disant regarder si j'ai des travaux de chantiers.
74. "31" AOÛT 2023: AGENT SED (secrétariat d'état à la défense) Fabrice Wilfried Siemieni (PROPRIÉTAIRE DE "HAPPINESS POTENTIAL S.A.R.L.") ne m'a pas payé CINQUANTE MILLES restants, pour mes prestations dans sa structure en voie de faillite digitale et financière !
75. "03" Septembre 2023: AGENT SED (secrétariat d'état à la défense) "Claude", 1 vaut-rien vivant dans 1 maison abandonnée par 1 gardien de terrains de HONORABLE THÉODORE DATOUO; essaye de me menacer de faire annuler mon permis de bâtir (Signé de Gilbert TSIMI EVOUNA);
- "21" Septembre 2023: CLAUDE, le vaut-rien du SED, essaye de venir montrer être valable chez sa collègue ROBERTINE CARINE LELE NJOUGEP TCHANA, qui se fait appelée Édith de bangou; Bien que son nom réfère au village Bagangté !
76. "21" Septembre 2023: AGENT SED (secrétariat d'état à la défense) "SIMPLICE KAMENI", surnommée ÉBACKA; vient de faire créer de la saleté avec 1 engin au virage donnant sur le terrain de la CAMEROON NATIONAL RAILWAYS (camrail); occupée illégalement par 'Mani', bien que la Communauté Urbaine de Yaoundé AVAIT ÉTÉ AU COURANT DE SON installation frauduleuse;
77. "25" Septembre 2023: AGENT SED (secrétariat d'état à la défense) "ALINE AZEFA" ME PROVOQUE en bagarre lorsque je suis entrain de me déplacer pour voir agent SED robertine carine lele njougep qui m'avait dit s'appelée ÉDITH.
- APRÈS 2 ANS sans suite de HUGUES YAGER ALAIN MABOMA, président du tribunal militaire; JE VIENS À LA CONCLUSION QUE BIYA franck a monnayé puisque je lui ai refusé la possession de mon immeuble R+2 de YAOUNDÉ-AHALA-SIMBOK !
78. PAUL BIYA en veut à ma santé mentale par le biais du voisin vaut-rien du SED: ALINE azefa.

79. "25" *Octobre 2023*: LA CITOYENNE ALLEMANDE teuntchou noumeni INGRID, me menace de me faire enfermer illégalement dans 1 cellule de la prison centrale de Nkodengui puisque j'ai redemandé à ma génitrice ET MÈRE de TEUNTCHOU NOUMENI INGRID, de ne plus me harceler avec des questionnements sur ma vie privée.

AUX DERNIÈRES NOUVELLES, provenant de celles-ci, puisque n'ayant pas rechignés, ROSE SANGNOU ET TEUNTCHOU seraient de la ROSE-CROIX amorc (Ancien Mystique Ordre de LA ROSE-CROIX).

ANGÉLA SHANDA OWONA, leur congénère utérin par PR. DR. RER. POL. SHANDA TONME jean-claude, m'avait invité à y prendre par au ministère des relations extérieures !

80. "29" *Octobre 2023*: 1 voisin illégal installé par THÉODORE datouo (soit-nommé Moise), vient se plaindre de feuilles de ses plantains-bananaies taillées parce qu'elles pénètrent dans ma propriété privée.

CE FAISANT, moise soit-nommé, dont j'ignore des identifications légales et/ou autres, détruit 1 tube d'ornement sur mon petit portillon d'entrée de IMMEUBLE YERITH, APRÈS QUE JE LUI AI INTIMÉ L'ORDRE de ressortir de IMMEUBLE YERITH; mon domicile privée et bureaux (JE N'AI AUCUN AGENT DE SÉCURITÉ À DATE D'ÉCRITURE).

Moise, vaut-rien ne faisant aucun métier ou pratique professionnelle, JE contacte "FRANÇOIS BATOMEN" et "MAMAN THÉRÈSE (MA-T)" ses parents biologiques pour 1 réparation: XAVIER VA CHEZ TOI; tu as détruis notre tronc de bananier-plantain.

Ce jour, SAMEDI 04 NOVEMBRE 2023,

J'AI DIRIGÉ 1 CONVERSATION AVEC le promoteur de l'association d'éducation au football E.P.T.A, 1 monsieur très tranquille apparemment dont j'ignore, par oublié, des noms et / ou identifications. IL A DIT PARLÉ DE CES FEUILLES QUI ENTRENT chez moi illégalement à BATOMEN.

81. "09" *Novembre 2023*: CE MATIN DE JEUDI 09 Novembre 2023, je me suis mis à râler sur le trottoir à l'encablure de chez moi contre le président du parti politique R.D.P.C puisque je ressentais des relents d'arrestations et d'incarcérations illégales du SED-EPTA, voisin.

82. "16" *Novembre 2023*: Voisin illégal Pierre Foka, gérant d'1 petite scierie voisine à celle de FRANCK BIYA (S2TBED); À DÉPOSER 1 camion endommagé au virage gauche venant de ma propriété légale, voici bientôt 2 semaines.

83. "16" *Novembre 2023*: MONSIEUR LE CHEF DE BLOC séverin atangana m'a promis convoquer François Batomen pour lui redemander de libérer mes espaces légaux, avec ses feuilles de bananiers-plantains.

84. "18" *Novembre 2023*: GENDARMERIE COLONEL kémajou, Vient de menacer ma personne aux fins que je ne rédige plus SES FORFAITS tels que mentionnés dans ce curriculum vitae étendue !

85. "29" *Novembre 2023*: LE SECRÉTAIRE D'ÉTAT À LA DÉFENSE YVES GALAX LANDRY etoga semble être incompetent à mon humble avis !

86. "02" *Décembre 2023*: Je soupçonne la société S2TBED d'être 1 société-forestière prétexte du SECRÉTARIAT D'ÉTAT À LA DÉFENSE pour détruire des hommes d'affaires africains-noirs.

87. "19" *Décembre 2023*: MAXIME napoa étémé m'avait dit être de la SEMIL, mais il n'est que à la base navale RMIA2.

IL (maxime napoa étémé) m'avait promis ne plus permettre que je sois séquestré arbitrairement !

88. "21" *Décembre* 2023: IL (MAXIME napoa étémé) m'avait dit que le colonel BAMKOUI (directeur de la SEMIL) avait agréé me faire confectionner 1 badge d'agent de renseignement SEMIL, pour 1 salaire mensuel d'1 minimum de "100 000 francs" mensuel.

JE lui ai remis 1 cadeau de 256 000 !

IL (MAXIME napoa étémé) s'est éclipsé de son numéro de téléphone mobile MTN (6 75 75 36 43) voila plus de 2 semaines à date.

IL (MAXIME napoa étémé) aurait reçu de l'argent des SHANDA (6 99 75 47 59; 6 77 47 42 27).

JE vais retourner à l'ordre des avocats du Cameroun pour essayer de ravoir 1 avocat-conseil acquis à ma cause face aux attaques non judiciaires perpétrées sur ma personnes par SHANDA-OWONA.

89. "21" *Décembre* 2023: IL (MAXIME napoa étémé) a 1 poste de vente et commerce illégal posté à mes entrées privées de la cité-des-palmiers a Douala; 1 voisine d'1 appartement désaffecté depuis près de 20 ans, et non encore démoli par la CUD (communauté urbaine de Douala) est son employée a temps plein.

CE poste n'a jamais été détruit sur mes requêtes auprès de YOLANDE de Bafoussam (Ouest du Cameroun) !

JE soupçonne MAXIME NAPOA ETEME d'être entrain de pourrir le niveau de vie de mes potentiels locataires sous paiements de SHANDA-OWONA !

90. "22" *Décembre* 2023 : GABRIEL takoumbe ne m'a plus recontacté: IL (GABRIEL takoumbe) a débuté à me racheter 1 camion de gravier dont je n'en ai plus besoin pour des travaux de maçonneries !

IL (GABRIEL takoumbe) serait aussi selon toute vraisemblance 1 agent SED (SÉCRÉTARIAT D'ÉTAT A LA DÉFENSE) !

91. "22" *Décembre* 2023 : ME. NTONE, avocat conseil agréé à l'ordre des avocats du Cameroun; a accepté être mon nouveau avocat conseil; Sans constitution.

ME. NTONE, mon nouveau avocat conseil, a ses bureaux près de la maison de la radio à Yaoundé, SIS IMMEUBLE GMC.

92. "24" *Décembre* 2023 : S2TBED, entreprise forestière illégale, et appartenant à Franck BIYA, ENTRETIENT des agents de renseignements du type de l'Allemagne HITLÉRIENNE.

EN EFFET, ils ont des idées du type:

1. des herbes autour de chez toi ne sont pas encore nettoyées; même si tu n'as pas de force ou d'argent pour le moment; TU DEVRAIS ÊTRE EMMENÉ EN PSYCHIATRIE !

2. JEAN de maroua est le principal auteur de ces allégations; 1 individu ne possédant même plus 1 CERTIFICAT D'ÉTUDES DU 1^{er} cycle camerounais (enfants allant jusqu'à 12 ans environ).

3. les personnes seuls sont illégales; ces personnes devraient être emmenées en psy.

Ce type de personnages travaillent pour KEMAJOU, ivrogne et alcoolique colonel de gendarmerie; Par le biais de la société de gardiennage "General Security".

Certains éléments de la police et de la gendarmerie au Cameroun arborent des treillis similaires à ceux portés par des "militaire SS de l'Allemagne HITLÉRIENNE".

J'ai attiré ceci à l'attention de 2 hommes en tenues de police et de l'armée marine.

93. "29" *Décembre* 2023 : JUGE D'INSTRUCTION ALAIN HUGUES YAGER MABOMA n'est pas du tout serein dans mes affaires judiciaires puisque je n'ai plus observé d'avancements.

94. "28" *Décembre* 2023 : La société TATAVI S.A.R.L a envoyée 1 agent SED (Secrétariat d'État à la Défense) à ma rencontre lorsque je voulais rencontrer 1 agent immobilier ce 28 Décembre 2023 a Yaoundé !

CURIEUSEMENT l'immeuble abritant cette entreprise malévolente porte des couleurs vertes et jaunes, rappelant celles utilisées par la gendarmerie.

Tout porterait a croire qu'1 bâtiment au cameroun arborant ces couleurs de jaune et de vert serait juste 1 point de renseignement de la gendarmerie nationale.

95. "29" *Décembre* 2023 : 1 véhicule non immatriculé a essayé de me percuter lorsque je marchais tranquillement sur la route menant à mon domicile de Yaoundé–Ahala ce jour vers "14 : 30".

Ce véhicule avait l'air d'1 véhicule de renseignement de l'armée camerounaise.

96. "30" *Décembre* 2023 : LE JOUR OU JE DÉPOSAIS MA PLAINTÉ arrêtee, sur recommandation du pasteur MARCO de Chapelle Gloire De Christ, de New-Deido–DOUALA, J'avais remarque la présence dans mon arrière, assise, d'1 militaire dame vêtue d'1 casquette portant la mention SEMIL (N.D.L.R: Sécurité Militaire) !

CECI ÉTAIT EN FÉVRIER 2021.

CET ATTENTAT VISANT À DÉTRUIRE MA VIE DE CHRÉTIEN NÉ-DE-NOUVEAU, s'est passé dans la nuit du jour suivant où j'ai rencontré 1 voisin disant pouvoir me fourvoir d'1 emploi d'agent de renseignement au ministère de la défense du Cameroun: "L'ADJUDANT CHEF MAJOR MAXIME NAPOA ETEME" !

Je ne suis jamais allé premièrement à la rencontre du voisin "L'ADJUDANT CHEF MAJOR MAXIME NAPOA ETEME"; c'est lui qui avait établi 1 premier contact avec moi en me saluant et me montrant son domicile lorsque je sortais d'1 magasin de vente de produits d'occasions et neufs provenant de la RFA (République Fédérale d'Allemagne) !

"L'ADJUDANT CHEF MAJOR MAXIME NAPOA ETEME" m'avait dit avoir été en visite chez moi à mon domicile de location du SED-agent "TRADIS S.A.R.L".

La société d'échafaudage industriel "SED-agent TRADIS S.A.R.L" a déménagée de chez moi en Septembre 2023 en laissant plus de 3 mois de loyer impayés. DIRECTEUR DAVID FRANCIS EBOUTTE !

97. "30" *Décembre* 2023: Henri Bertrand Ngatchou, 1 frère cadet de ma génitrice Rose Sangnou, a essayé de me faire des examens médicaux puisque je suis sans soucis de santé, Aux fins de me faire subir des arrestations dans des prisons (cabanons) de fous dans des hôpitaux psychiatriques.

Ceci s'est passé lors de son invitation dans son village Bangou pour des célébrations du mariage de sa nièce Cynthia Nkwouano !

J'ai cessé tout rapprochement avec cette famille NGONGANG de ma génitrice Rose Sangnou !

98. "07" *Janvier* 2024: TIMOTHÉE et 1 jeune garçon, tous deux de SECTE JERUSALEM APOSTOLAT sont stationnés à mon entrée principale (au portillon) à mon arrivée venant de barrière ce dimanche matin aux alentours de 10 : 30.

99. "08" Janvier 2024: L'institut Universitaire de la Côte a essayé de me faire des ennuis par rapport à l'ouverture officiel du centre de formation Informatique YERITH R&D.

LA ROSICRUCIENNE et génitrice de ma personne (Rose SANGNOU, veuve Théodore NOUMBISSI), qui partage la même sorcellerie de loge avec MARTINE GUIMEZAP et PAUL guimezap, ce fondateur de L'INSTITUT UNIVERSITAIRE DE LA CÔTE et son épouse du village BAFOU A L'OUEST; vient chez moi faire sa (IUC de Douala) publicité en arborant 1 T-SHIRT gris arborant des sigles de L'INSTITUT UNIVERSITAIRE DE LA CÔTE DE DOUALA (IUC) !

IL semblerait que je suis entouré de personnes de sorcellerie qui ne veulent pas dévoiler devant ma personne, mais qui souhaitent que je constate ceci avec du temps passé et des désespoirs manqués et / ou pas.

100. "09" Janvier 2024: L'éraflure de voisine du village BAFOU comme des guimezap a fait semblant d'être me génitrice ce matin à mon passage en arborant 1 coiffure de cheveux similaires à ce que la Rosicrucienne ROSE SANGNOU veuve Théodore Noubissi se coiffe régulièrement dans la cité de moi !

CETTE ÉRAFLURE du nom de Paulette AZEFA; dont j'ignore d'où elle serait née, a déjà essayée de me faire 1 assassinat par sa fille du SED-yves-landry-etoga-galax EN PLEINE ROUTE lorsque je traversais la demeure qu'elles occupent !

C'est à mon retour définitif de mon séjour d'études et de travail de l'occident que j'apprends que cette demeure aurait été construite avec des matériaux délibérément CAPTÉS dans mon chantier personnel qui avait pour gardien RÉNÉ Mbazeu; BEAU-FRÈRE DE Josué nkouano; petit-frère de la génitrice Rose SANGNOU à Douala !

LA VOISINE et sœur du capitaine BIR-baitaillon-d'intervention-rapide PIERRE-MARCELLIN-EMANÈ-NKOA est pourtant de la gendarmerie nationale; C'est quand même surprenant que cette ancienne chef du service de recrutement du SED vive où il y'a toute cette insécurité; En compagnie du CAPITAINE-MBIDA de l'armée de l'air du Cameroun !

101. "09" Janvier 2024: L'électricien "LUCIEN" ("6 79 01 63 68") ayant installé ma pompe à eau pour mon forage, avait fait exprès de me demander de racheter 1 flotteur, sachant pertinemment que celui-ci est non approprié.

JE soupçonne l'électricien "LUCIEN" ("6 79 01 63 68") d'être aussi 1 agent SED pour contrer toute velléité de progrès dans le Cameroun, venant des camerounais authentiques, NON mariés par des loges sataniques et autres aux caucasiens !

102. "09" Janvier 2024: Je me rends compte vivre dans 1 endroit ou presque toute âme essaye de me faire assassiner ou bien arnaquer en ARBORANT sed.

103. "09" Janvier 2024: Ma connexion internet DE MTN afrique-du-sud EST ÉTRANGEMENT BEAUCOUP plus lente ces 3 dernières semaines !

104. "12" Janvier 2024: L'institut de formation de techniciens supérieures "ISTIAM" semble être intéressé par ma start-up YERITH R&D et mes dons d'enseignant en sciences Informatiques.

JE leur soumettrai 1 nouveau curriculum vitae, en Français, approprié pour la gestion entrepreneuriale d'1 start-up au sein de leur institut de formation professionnelle.

JE communique avec son ("ISTIAM") responsable pédagogique, M. GUIMEYA; M. GUIMEYA m'avait aussi dit connaître personnellement les promoteurs de l'IUC (Institut Universitaire de la Côte); je lui ai aussi fait part de cette relation entre eux et moi.

24 ÉVÈNEMENTS MARQUANTS (SUITE) – ATTAQUES À LA DÉLÉGATION GÉNÉRALE DE LA SÛRETÉ NATIONALE (DGSN)

105. "12" Janvier 2024: J'étais ce matin au commissariat de AHALA pour me tenir informer de la position de ma génitrice Rose Sangnou qui est venue il y'a quelques jours a Yaoundé semer 1 confusion sur ma personne dans mon voisinage.

Cette situation de perpétuelle mise-en-garde contre des destructions corporelles par les soins des médecins psy me persuadent d'1 ou plusieurs tentatives de m'éliminer physiquement en prenant pour cible ma génitrice et maman comme source de cette élimination physique et de l'esprit !

J'AI été obligé de me faire partir de force Puisque 1 des policières et 1 autre policier; JE ne sais pas ils avaient déjà reçu de l'argent, de LA rosicrucienne ROSE SANGNOU MA GÉNITRICE, voulait déjà me faire violence et me:

- (a) pour l'1 des policières me maintenir derrière le poste sans mon consentement, alors que c'était moi le plaignant; Venu de son propre gré se plaindre du désordre de sa génitrice dans son voisinage, AU sujet de ses effets personnels que j'ai mis à la poubelle;
- (b) pour 1 des policiers, DE me redemander si je souhaiterais rencontrer 1 médecin.

106. "13" Janvier 2024: ROSE sangnou, ma mère, et génitrice, NE SAIS PLUS POURQUOI ELLE EST en ce moment dans la ville de Yaoundé, sous recommandation de DR. fernand junior wolfgang owona.

107. "18" Janvier 2024: Madame Manga CHEF D'AGENCE DE EXPRESS UNION de barrière ne m'a plus informée si ma demande a été acceptée ou plus.

Madame Manga, m'avait d'abord fait 1 allusion à ce que je ne pourrais obtenir de prêt bancaire que si ma génitrice Rose Sangnou était impliquée.

JE lui ai rétorqué, que ceci concerne ma vie privée financière et que je fermais mon compte EXPRESS UNION si ceci n'était pas respectée !

MADAME manga m'a dit de lui donner l'original de la copie de mon titre foncier de YAOUNDÉ-simbock; DAME r.d.p.c – Bangou et génitrice Rose SANGNOU a refusée de s'exécuter !

Le frère cadet HENRI BERTRAND ngatchou de Génitrice ROSE SANGNOU est le vice-président du R.D.P.C à Bangou.

HONORABLE datou théodore, QUI m'avait revendu ce terrain en Novembre 2012 en est le président du R.D.P.C bangou.

DR. fernand jr wolfgang owona, Fils de FEU ministre JOSEPH OWONA, et petit-fils de MINISTRE grégoire OWONA, est du R.D.P.C à Yaoundé.

108. "30" Janvier 2024: 1 gendarme assez bruyant fait irruption dans 1 kiosque MTN MOMO (Mobile Money) où JE suis entrain de reparler avec 1 huissier de justice par rapport à mon affaire d'incarcération illégale dans des cabanons pour fous PAR LA rosicrucienne et génitrice Rose Sangnou !

JE soupçonne le Secrétaire D'État à La gendarmerie, personnellement, "Yves Galax Landry ETOGA", d'être encore à l'origine de cette énième intrusion dans mes vies privées de façon illégale !

ET ceci dans l'optique de ternir mon image de marque en vue des prochaines élections présidentielles anticipées au Cameroun en 2024 !

IL y a de ceci plusieurs semaines, lorsque j'étais à la brigade ter de gendarmerie de EBOM à Yaoundé pour me plaindre de la petite tentative d'assassinat venant de ALINE azefa, 1 voisine illégale de mes domiciles de Simbock, 1 dame gendarme en tenue militaire est entrée dans le bureau du commandant adjoint de brigade avec lequel j'étais en train de m'entretenir pour lui signifier que je n'étais pas en bon rapport avec YVES (puisque officiellement je n'ai jamais commis aucune infractions !

JE perçois tout ce cirque judiciaire sans issues comme des attaques politiques du RDPC (CPDM en anglais) !

109. "30" Janvier 2024: "L'huissier de justice MAÎTRE ANDRÉ", du cabinet de MAÎTRE FOUMANE au niveau de "montée Anne Rouge à Yaoundé" me recommande de me déplacer pour Douala pour réclamer mon titre foncier personnel à ma génitrice et mère Rose Sangnou !

110. "02" Février 2024: JE viens encore de me rendre au commissariat de AHALA pour rencontrer 1 officier qui m'avait été recommandé par le "procureur MBOUYOM MOFFOR Hyacinthe" de YAOUNDÉ-CENTRALE; 1 DES policier me dit d'abord qu'il est sorti et pas très loin du poste, et que je peux aller à sa rencontre séance tenante.

JE me met simplement à l'attendre de peur de ne pas être comme il faut en le recherchant à l'extérieur de l'enceinte du commissariat du 19^{ème} arrondissement de Yaoundé.

JE leur dis ensuite que je m'éclipse puisque je n'ai plus assez de temps d'attente.

CE même policier me demande alors si je n'ai regardé à l'arrière du poste dans son bureau, OÙ L'ON accède en les traversant de l'intérieur où ils étaient (policiers en tenus) !

111. "03" Février 2024: **Samaneh Navabpour** M'avait pourtant, lorsque j'étais encore son collègue d'université, Prédit 1 avenir tumultueux en Afrique contemporaine, Comme pour elle EN iran.

Amir vakili Hossein était aussi très sceptique pour mon avenir si je m'hasardais à retourner au Cameroun après mes études de Doctorat-PhD De l'Université de Waterloo a Waterloo (ON).

112. "10" Février 2024: J'ETAIS CE JOUR A "HAPPINESS POTENTIAL SARL" a la rencontre de DR. fabrice wilfried siemeni.

"HECNA NGAYAM", 1 comptable de "HAPPINESS POTENTIAL SARL", a eu l'amabilité de me représenter sur internet, Pour l'obtention d'1 identifiant personnel aux impôts du Cameroun; J'en ai principalement besoin aux fins d'obtenir 1 carte bancaire "VISA CRÉDIT électron".

J'EU VENT DE CE QUE sa collègue "HECNA NGAYAM" eût essayée sans relâche de me rejoindre par téléphone, bien que j'ai toujours réprécisé aimer communiquer par "GMAIL.COM".

J'ai rencontre aussi 1 éraflure d'enseignant nomme "M. Isidore WATTAT"; DONT J'IGNORE LES PRÉNOMS ET AUTRES DÉTAILS PERSONNELS.

113. "18" *Février 2024*: Des voisins ont pris des habitudes d'aller raconter des mensonges aux autorités sanitaires aux fins que je sois appréhendé pour 1 hôpital psy.

EN l'occurrence PIUS et son épouse Florence; "BATOMEN" et son épouse Thérèse (au sobriquet de "MA-T") !

ILS sont (FRANÇOIS, PIUS, FLORENCE, "MA-T (N.D.L.R: maman thérèse)"), des jaloux de mon succès financier d'informaticien aux Canada et En Occident ("Silicon Valley" PAR siemens medical solutions USA.) !

"M. Isidore WATTAT" de "happiness potential sarl" A LAISSÉ SES CHEVEUX poussés avec 1 barbichette comme s'il est 1 psy.

Depuis que j'ai eu à revoir 1 enfant MVONDO ASSAM chez "happiness potential sarl", IL se remarque des personnes étranges telles que DOCTORESSE MBARGA; et 1 CERTAIN PSY "M. Isidore WATTAT".

Depuis que Siemni Fabrice Wilfried m'a appelé au téléphone 1 jour où j'avais reçu mon loyer de 160 000 francs de GERMAIN-BLAISE ndzié, mon ancien locataire à la cité-des-palmiers, ET CECI PAR 2 REPRISES, sans que je ne sache comment il fût au courant de cette entrée d'argent, J'AI préféré lui proposer 1 partenariat en affaires dans ma structure en cours de formalisation au ministère du commerce (YECEFOIQ: YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE).

"FABRICE WILFRIED SIEMENI" m'a dit être intéressé, mais il n'a plus jamais manifesté 1 intérêt extérieur autre que accepter que je lui reverse 1 montant supérieur à 200 000 francs pour le rachat aux ÉTATS-UNIS de certaines fournitures non présentes sur le marché local.

"FABRICE WILFRIED SIEMENI" ME PARAÎT DONC suspect dans mes arrivées en affaires.

"FABRICE WILFRIED SIEMENI" vient la 1^{ère} fois à ma rencontre lorsque je visite la réunion "NUFI-CANADA" de TORONTO; pour me reparler de ses services de nutritionniste.

"FABRICE WILFRIED SIEMENI" m'invite ensuite a 1 cabinet conseil en nutrition au centre ville de Toronto; et par la suite souhaite passer me faire 1 consultation à domicile au niveau de mon iris Pour essayer 1 nouvelle thérapie TELLE QU'IL ME L'AVAIT REPRÉSENTE lors d'1 réunion à nufi-canada; ALEXIE TCHEUYAP, vice-recteur de l'université de Toronto en ce moment, avait été celui qui m'a présente Fabrice Wilfried Siemni.

114. "26" *Février 2024*: 1 dame dont j'ai oublié des noms et prénoms; Et que j'ai rencontré pour 1^{ère} fois au magasin de consommables informatiques juste situe face "Collège Integ a Douala"; Se représente à ma personne faisant mention de ma génitrice et de ma sœur utérine INGRID.

JE me distance directement cette dernière, Pensant que celle-ci est en provenance de ma génitrice et de Christian Eyoum !

Cette jeune dame d'1 quarantaine d'année est vêtue d'1 ensemble haut jaune et d'1 jean bleue, Mentionnant "NORLAND" !

115. "04" *Février 2024*: JEAN-PIERRE Kamgain, 1 connaissance d'enfance, au quartier New-Deido de DOUALA; essaye de me faire 1 sodomie en venant dire chez moi à mon domicile de Yaoundé qu'il souhaite y passer 1 nuit avec moi; Ceci s'est passé en Décembre 2023 !

DOROTHÉE DJATIE SHANDA OWONA, est venue en visite chez ma grande-maman TCHITCHUI Élisabeth lorsque j'y séjournais quelques 9 jours en attente de matériels informatiques pour la création et ouverture de YECEFOIQ.

116. "03" Mars 2024: JE viens de me rabaisser à manger dans 1 "tourne-dos face Quincaillerie N.K (Nestor Kenfack)".

"TEUNTCHOU NOUMENI ingrid", 1 sœur utérine fait retarder des travaux de réfection de mon appartement de 3 chambres sis cité-des-palmiers !

"Honoré WOUCHE", 1 cousin non germain maternel, qui a réalisé des tables pour YECEFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE); M'en a reparlé.

"Honoré WOUCHE", m'a aussi fait savoir qu'1 ses filles est employée dans 1 plantation de "Mvondo" dans le Sud du Cameroun; JE soupçonne 1 tentative du RDPC de me mettre hors de mon réseau naturel familial et financier Puisque "HENRI BERTRAND Ngatchou" ("Propriétaire Best Car Care & Services"), aussi 1 cousin maternel de "Honoré WOUCHE", ET 1 oncle maternel à ma personne, Vient d'être nommé par cooptation, ET NON PR CANDIDATURE, Vice-président du RDPC (C.P.D.M.) à Bangou à l'Ouest-Cameroun: Son village natal !

"TEUNTCHOU NOUMENI ingrid", EST AUSSI L'ÉPOUSE DE teuntchou isaac, membre influant au Secrétariat D'état à la Défense (SED); 1 organisme terroriste de MVONDO ASSAM Bonivan !

"MVONDO ASSAM Bonivan", est aussi 1 des actionnaires initiateurs de la société forestière frauduleuse, et voisine à ma demeure de Simbock-Barrière !

"TEUNTCHOU NOUMENI ingrid", s'était pourtant solennellement désengagée de suivre 1 quelconque acte de nos propriétés de la cité-des-palmiers DE SON PROPRE GRÉ pour me les laisser de plein droits aux vues de: Sa citoyenneté ALLEMANDE; et son mariage légal à l'allemand "TEUNTCHOU NOUMENI chandriand"!

"TEUNTCHOU NOUMENI ingrid", et "TEUNTCHOU NOUMENI chandriand" étaient tous 2 des citoyens camerounais au moment de la célébration de ce mariage frauduleux aux vues de ma non ACCEPTATION en tant que frère unique aîné de "TEUNTCHOU NOUMENI ingrid" !

117. "06" Mars 2024: 1 porteur de sacs de "Quincaillerie Aimé SARL", situe non loin et en face de "Quincaillerie N.K (Nestor Kenfack)" me dit de ne plus lui dire: "EST CE QUE MONSIEUR AIMÉ, votre chef d'équipe est présent sur ses lieux de services" ?

118. "10" Mars 2024: M. weladji, dont j'ignore les prénoms, M'avait arnaqué 1 montant de 20 Milles FRANCS et je m'étais rendu à la 'brigade ter de gendarmerie de Akwa-Sud' à Douala Pour re-avoir mon argent, Moyennant 5 Milles de frais aux gendarmes.

M. weladji, À ma grande surprise, N'a plus été inquiété par 1 procédure pénale !

120. "16" Mars 2024: MBIDA, voisin travaillant à la garde présidentielle du Cameroun, hors-la-loi puisque devrait vivre dans 1 caserne, EST encore entrain de faire du désordre chez moi !

IL a enfin, TELLE que rapporté par "M. Onguene", et "M. Moise" de S2TBED pensé à faire réparer la route endommagée par des camions de S2TBED. C'EST à croire qu'il serait 1 actionnaire de cette entreprise illégale dans mon quartier Puisque ne respectant plus des normes environnementales de bases telles que: DES DÉCHETS d'essences de bois sur les piétons en plein 09 : 00 du matin par exemple.

"MBIDA" a fait porter des déchets de part et d'autres de la 2^{ème} entrée, juste face à mon entrée principale, pour les déversées, mélangées avec de la terre, sur le rebord de mon mur de face à la route principale !

121. "20" Mars 2024: "MANI", 1 protégée de "Hon. Datou Théodore"; ancienne épouse du feu gardien des terrains à barrière-Simbock-Ahala de Datou, me recommande à 1 frère aîné de mon ancien compagnon canadien JD TUJILO TCHOKOTÉ.

"MANI", me recommande ainsi à "MARCEL tiemeni", frère aîné de JD TUJILO TCHOKOTE, qui est entrain de construire 1 barrière sur son terrain acquis il y'a de ceci 12 ans environ, juste au même titre foncier que le mien chez l'acheteur en gros "HONORABLE THÉODORE DATOUO".

122. "26" Mars 2024: "JEAN-PIERRE kamgain" me toise en pleine route lorsque je me rends à Chapelle Gloire De Christ.

123. "26" Mars 2024: "TITO MARKET SARL" (<https://>) n'a plus commandé exactement la pièce "NC-300" de "SavingOlogy.com" Que je désire ravoir. ILS m'ont dit être plus tranquille avec 1 KVM-switch qui serait 1 technologie plus nouvelle que celle d'1 "MULTI-USER TERMINAL COMPUTER" !

Malheureusement pour eux, Je ne peux plus accepter de changements, PUISQUE j'ai déjà racheté, par exemple, des claviers à ports "PS/2" qui fonctionnent avec des ports "PS/2" du "NC-300 Multi-User Terminal Computer" de "SavingOlogy.com" !

AUSSI, je souhaite ravoir seulement 1 "NC-300 Multi-User Terminal Computer" pour mes clients du fait de la facilité d'entretien face aux avancées en piratage informatique dans des années à venir: En effet, la quantité des données est très limitée avec des ports "PS/2", Comparativement aux autres ports tels que USB, DVI, etc. !

Aussi, je souhaite être purement et simplement remboursé puisque 3 semaines d'attentes et des frais de déplacements supplémentaires pour Douala ne sont plus comme il faut pour mon budget limite d'entrepreneur HIGH-TECH !

JE faisais cette commande par 1 intermédiaire puisque je n'avais pas encore 1 numéro d'identifications unique pour des impôts requis par "la banque Filiale UBA Ange-Raphaël" pour l'obtention d'1 carte VISA-MASTER-CARD pour mes rachats personnalisées en ligne, Au magasin "SavingOlogy.com" !

124. "26" Mars 2024: DR. Audrey Mbarga était très avenante ce matin lorsque je revisitais des locaux de 'happiness potential sarl' !

L'ÉRAFLURE DE "psy wattat" n'était plus du palier !

125. "28" Mars 2024: L'ÉRAFLURE DE "Billie-joie" me suivait ce matin lorsque je revenais de rendre visite au pasteur "Marco" de CHAPELLE GLOIRE DE CHRIST.

1 INDIVIDU vivant dans 1 petite route de quartier à new-deïdo; le quartier où je séjourne chez mon grand-père maternel en ce moment; arborant de temps à autres 1 treillis "AGENT DE SANTÉ COMMUNAUTAIRE" surnommé "MBAKO"; et Ayant des cheveux blancs ébouriffés, Me fait suivre !

126. "31" Mars 2024: 1 dame vendant du poisson à la braise; vivant sur la rue où 1 "Billie-joie", précédemment cité dans mes récits se loge; ME redit à plusieurs reprises lorsque je circule sur la voie publique en faisant des signes de croix en signe D’AFFIRMATION de ma foie chrétienne, que: "C’EST à l’église qu’on fait cela" !

127. "01" Avril 2024: *L'imberbe de "RODRIGUE ALAIN sienchie ngongang"*, 1 oncle utérin, dont j'ai déboursé près de "1 000 000 FRANCS (XAF)" pour ses (2 billets d'avions depuis 2004, et 2005, si mes souvenirs sont exacts); SIENCHIE, dont je ne connais pas le niveau réel d'éducation, aux vues de ses idées dégénératives envers mes droits humains, Supporte avec pour raison 1 protection des faits suivants provenant de sa sœur utérine aînée DADA (n.d.l.r: HUISSIER de justice dorothée ndjatié shanda owona):

1. "LE DÉNOMMÉ ERIC CONSTANT foto tchuente ", 1 Camerounais d'origine, vivant aux USA; a souhaité me racheté 1 de mes appartements de YDE-AHALA pour 1 montant total d'environ "7 000 000 Francs (XAF)" en l'an 2021 !
2. "dada, sœur utérine de Rose sangnou, ma génitrice, À qui j'avais confié des documents de propriété m'appartenant par rachat à HONORABLE DATOUO théodore."; Voyage de Edéa, sans demander mon avis et / ou consentements; AUX FINS DE ressasser: JE NE VEUX PLUS QUE TU (n.d.l.r.: ROSE SANGNOU) redonne ces papiers à ton fils !!!

128. "03" AVRIL 2024: "MOMOKASH", service de prêt et d'emprunt de moneyMobile, NE serait plus opérationnel ces jours-ci!

129. "03" AVRIL 2024: "MARCEL théophile Mpondo Kouo", alors 1 ancien camarade du "collège Alfred Saker" de Douala; EST 1 cadre directeur en fonction au groupe MTN !

"MARCEL théophile Mpondo Kouo" était à cette époque (2000 allant à 2001) LE dernier en classe, avec des gens comme NGADJEU.

130. "03" AVRIL 2024: "*JEAN ngongang, paix à son âme de personne tribale, est devenue intéressant lorsqu'il essaye de voler MON âme par 1 prière devant moi sur 1 lieu sacré de sa concession de Bankepche-Bangou.*"

"ÉRIC CONSTANT FOTSO TCHUENTE" m'avait remis 20 000XAF aux fins de me re-déplacer sur Douala pour récupérer mon titre foncier de ma propriété de YDE-AHALA-Simbock; JE souhaitais lui revendre 1 appartement pour 1 montant total de 7 000 000 FRANCS (XAF).

LA sœur de ma génitrice, ROSE SANGNOU; "me. (huissier de justice) SHANDA Ndjatié Dorothée Owona"; Descend de Edéa pour Douala, avant même que je ne prenne mon départ de YDE; ET INTIME 1 ordre de co-épouse à 'Rose-Sangnou': NE REMET PLUS DE TITRE FONCIER À XAVIER noumbissi noundou.

131. "05" AVRIL 2024: LE fainéant de 'ME. PATRICE CABRAL shanda sanou' Est décédé en Inde. Son paternel de fainéant "SHANDA TONME jean claude" et sa maternelle de Fainéante "me. (huissier de justice) SHANDA Ndjatié Dorothée Owona" SONT CONVAINCUS qu'ils ne peuvent plus me faire passer de vis à trépas; Puisque JEOVAH-NISSI-AU-CIEL; aussi dit JÉSUS-DE-NAZARETH a intervenu en ma faveur.

132. "08" AVRIL 2024: "Prof. SIEMENI de happiness potential sarl" m'a donné 1 reliquat de 10 000 FRANCS XAF sur des 15 000 FRANCS XAF restants pour son inscription à YECEFOIQ.

133. "08" AVRIL 2024: "Honore Wouche", cousin germain de "Rose SANGNOU ma génitrice", est déjà assez régulier selon mes convenances gênantes chez "Rose SANGNOU" où je séjourne en ce moment à Douala.

J'eu croire qu'IL a déjà été à l'origine d'1 de mes séquestrations arbitraires à LAQUINTINIE: Rodrigue ALAIN son cousin germain et pourfendeur négatif de ma personne lui a asséné 1 dernière visite: "IL (xavier) faut LE RAMENER DANS 1 cabanon de fou; Il lit trop la BIBLE." !

134. "08" AVRIL 2024: L'université de Waterloo semble falsifier ses propres écrits aux fins de favoriser des candidats malheureux aux présidentielles au Cameroun !

Après que "Patrick Lam, PhD, PEng", m'eut enregistré 1 équivalence de mon "Engineering Doctoral Program" achevé en Décembre 2011, le 20; comme équivalent a 1 'PhD' (DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY) en sciences informatiques, Son collègue et camarades d'enfances a l'école: "DEREK RAYSIDE"; Renchérit et le modifie en 1 salissure pour des noirs au Canada: "Le terme ABD." !

C'est à croire que ces 'Canadiens' voulaient me faire assassiner sur tous des plans."

135. "09" AVRIL 2024: "TITO MLARKET SARL (<https://>)", QUI M'AVAIT PROPOSE FAIRE 1 COMMANDE DE MATÉRIELS INFORMATIQUES Pour mon centre de formation en Informatique (YECEFOIQ), n'arrive pas me les délivrer près 2 Semaines de patiente après 1 première livraison des choses non commandées.

"LE PASTEUR paul eya", en visite à Capelle Gloire de Christ de Deïdo, nous a rappelé et enseigné de ré-utiliser des contacts à la chapelle.

29 ÉVÈNEMENTS MARQUANTS (SUITE) – CPDM-RDPC-richard-MFEUGWANG assists ROSE SANGNOU to destroy my life

136. "11" AVRIL 2024: I have met along my road today, CPDM-RDPC cad—5 mayor Richard Mfeugwang; He is supposed to own a transit company named GoTRANS. !

THIS IDIOT SEEMS NOT TO RECOGNIZE THAT I KNOW HE IS BEHIND ALL MY TROUBLES HERE IN MY FAMILY since this trans-go-projector; cannot recognize that He is only educated up to the 4th YEAR of secondary education compared to a Doctor of Engineering of the ively-league-US-canada-WATERLOO !

137. "11" AVRIL 2024: FRANCE de macron, Essaye de rester chez toi avec tes embargos sur des matériaux informatiques américains à Douala; CANCRE !

138. "19" AVRIL 2024: Ce matin à la quincaillerie "Le débrouillard" derrière chez moi; sis carrefour "TITUS-EDZOA-JÉSUS-DE-NAZARETH" à Simbock, non loin de la chefferie de block;

2 indics, 1 portant "1 talkie-walkie" me suivent lorsque je vais re-négocier des prix de tringles pour rideaux.

139. "20" MAI 2024: 1 amant de Samatha, 1 des filles de Marie (sœur aînée de Léonard); 1 ancienne copine intime de Rose Sangnou ma génitrice; au quartier new-deïdo de Douala.

Cet indic de gendarmerie portant des lunettes médicales a pris des habitudes de quotidiennement me faire des grands yeux, lorsque je suis sur mes chemins en me rends rendant en visite matinale et / ou quotidienne chez la 2^{ème} femme de mon feu grand-papa maternel; LE regretté "Jean-NGONGANG":

En effet, ce monsieur me questionne de façon muette si bien que je fais des signes de croix chrétiennes aux fins de lui rétorquer que c'est 1 chrétien ne-de-nouveau de JEOVAH-NISSI-AU-CIEL qui s'en aille sans regarder au dedans de son domicile conjugal; Domicile qui n'a aucun portail en ce moment.

"PRINCE RAOUL NJONKEP", 1 jeune oncle maternel consanguin me paraît impliqué dans cette tentative de musellement politique par le biais de fausses accusations en PSY.

"IL me semble que l'imbécile d'agent de santé communautaire surnommé "MBAKO"; de la CUD (Communauté Urbaine de Douala)" que je rencontre déjà régulièrement assis de près où je rachète souvent à crédit de 200 FRANCS aux fins de ne pas vivre avec des pièces d'argent; Est entrain de faire des investigations sur ma vie privée.

140. "06" JUIN 2024: "Me. ANDRÉ", Huissier de justice, au SED, A demandé que si le soit-disant "Pasteur Landry" me recontacte par téléphone, Je lui signifie de me dire qu'est ce qu'il me veut de la part de "YVES LANDRY".

IL semblerait que APRES avoir été par effraction a mon domicile bâti par fonds propres de ma personnes à YDE-AHALA; Ma génitrice et concurrente en affaires "Rose sangnou", Essaye de me faire passer pour 1 imposteur auprès des autorités compétentes du CAMEROUN du régime R.D.P.C !

IL semblerait que "rose sangnou" couche maritalement avec "Grégoire owona" puisqu'elle m'avait dit avoir été dans ses résidences privées de son "village de Gomedzap dans le centre du CAMEROUN" il y'a de ceci environ 2 mois !

141. "11" JUIN 2024: j'étais rendre visite à 'Waah' ("KANYOU ANNE"); elle est ma grande-mère par ma mère. J'AI RENCONTRÉ 1 CERTAIN 'Albert ...', petit-frère de la voisine MA(MAN)-T(HÉRÈSE).

CE fou avec des cheveux de Psychologue.

ALBERT-idiot Est entré de façon s urprenante sans sonner ou toquer au portail lorsque je balayais ce sol.

ALBERT m'a dit être 1 docteur-PH.D. de l'université de Grenoble en France, spécialisé en médecine thérapeutique (JE ME DEMANDE PERSONNELLEMENT SI IL Y'A 1 science médicale Non thérapeutique !!!).

142. "12" JUIN 2024: 'Albert' avait dit être en mesure de me redonner 1 contact d'1 docteur enseignant d'informatique de l'université des montagnes de Banekane (BAGANGTE) a l'ouest du Cameroun; Je lui avais pourtant redemande plutôt le contact d'1 enseignant d'informatique de "UYU 1" (N.D.L.R.: l'UNIVERSITÉ DE YAOUNDÉ 1) parce que je suis résident a Yaoundé et non à Banakane.

LE fou 'Albert' que j'ai rencontre pour 1 première fois à Yaoundé, m'a force a faire 1 science de psychologie sociale avec lui, Avec 1 violence qui n'a plus de nom.

Et ceci après être entre sans sonner ou toquer au portail lorsque je balayais le sol.

LE salaud 'Albert ...' était sûrement là de la part de mon ennemi personne "Shanda tonme jean claud"e; Membre de l'AEUD, groupe qui promeut les idéaux néo-centristes 'bamilékés-grassfield' et qui dirige l'université des montagnes dont 'albert ...' est issue.

FIN DE CITATION.
Adieu WAAH.

PS: Je n'avais jamais su que c'est les "KEMMEGNI-antoine" qui était derrière mes ennuies de cabanon-pour-fous-force, PAR shanda.

"CLEMENTIN DJAMENI tayou", enseignant de l'université de Dschang ne m'avait pas dit être entrain de raconter des saletés sur moi.

"SHANDA TONME" a infesté toute mes familles, pour détruire ma réussite programmée sur terre.

143. "12" JUIN 2024: Je viens de détruire 1 appareil espion placé juste devant mon domicile.

J'ai constaté que cet appareil Entachait négativement et régulièrement le fonctionnement régulier et sans arrêt de mon téléviseur numérique, ainsi que de mes régulateurs de tension (AVR).

Je soupçonne "ANICET MFEUKEN", 1 voisin dont j'ignore la profession réelle; d'être l'auteur de ce "spam" sur 1 ligne placée juste au dessus de mon portail d'entrée à 'SIMBOCK': c'est lui qui m'avait dit connaître le propriétaire de cette ligne dont j'ignore l'utilisation depuis plus de 6 ans.

J'ai constaté la destruction de plus de 3 appareils électriques numériques:

1. "1 régulateur de tension (AVR) de 5 000 Watts".
2. "L'affichage d'1 neuf régulateur de tension Innova de 2 000 Watts de moins de 3 mois d'âge et racheté tout neuf à "25 000 Francs".
3. "1 refroidisseur d'air MIDEA" de plus de "80 000 Francs" !
4. **ADDENDUM-du—April 17, 2025:**

Cette ligne électrique avec 1 appareil espion qui modifie des programmes sur mon téléviseurs numériques sans que je le souhaite appartiendrait à "creolink via COLONEL kemajou (<https://>) " datouo therodore.

L'information m'a été remis par 1 homme trapus, similaire à "1 homme à arme" que je vois régulièrement dégusté des repas frelatés au commerce du bagangte kemajou...

IL sillonne cette zone et celle d'en face-Entree-general-etoa-bouba-qui— avec 1 corolla toyota rouge.

144. "12" JUIN 2024:

Des mon arrivée du supermarché 'Casino', face "Cathédrale Catholique orthodoxe" ce matin, ICI à YDÉ;

2 individus sombres et obscurs occupent la devanture de mon domicile privé de "Ahala-SIMBOCK", DANS LE SOUCIS de reposer 1 appareil espion dans l'enceinte de mon domicile, Sur 1 câble dont j'ignore l'entreprise ou l'organisme gouvernemental propriétaire !

JE soupçonne 1 manœuvre qui vise à me faire incarcérer pour 1 cabanon pour fous de "l'hôpital JAMÔT de YDÉ", ORGANISÉE par "DATOUO et compagnie".

Surtout que j'ai été salué lorsque je me rendais chez mon client pilote "N.K (Nestor Kenfack) quincaillerie" pour le dépannage de son "ordinateur portable-LENOVO-thinkpad-T460"; Par la "brute de gendarmerie COLONEL KEMAJOU".

CE colonel ne me remarque plus puisque il m'avait réitéré de RESTER CHEZ MOI ET LUI AUSSI QU'IL RESTERAIT CHEZ LUI.

145. "14" JUIN 2024:

"Monsieur Onguéné", ancien directeur d'exploitation de S2TBED était entrain de remettre des ordures juste à l'entrée de mes domiciles sis AHALA-Simbock !

Ce goujat de tribalisme m'avait il y'a de ceci 2 ans environ tancé de retourner chez "DES BLANCS" vivre puisque lui, "ONGUÉNÉ, du centre et du littoral du Cameroun", n'appréciait pas ma façon et manière de voir la vie, BIEN QUE CETTE MANIÈRE ET FAÇON est conforme aux lois en vigueur au "CMR".

"ONGUÉNÉ" était arrivé à YDE juste 1 journée après mon arrivée de Douala, comme s'il était entrain de me faire suivre et espionner pour que je ne puisse pas être à mon aise et conforme aux lois de la république du CMR.

Ce même "Monsieur Onguéné", natif du centre et originaire du Littoral ("Nkongsamba"); m'a même fait la proposition 1 fois de me donner sa fille en mariage; bien que "Monsieur Onguéné" sache que je suis 1 célibataire sans enfants physiques éternellement comme mon père aux cieux "JEOVAH-NISSI, aussi dit JESUS-DE-NAZARETH".

"ONGUÉNÉ", fervent supporteur de "biya-franck", serait celui la qui détruit la vie des Camerounais retournés chez eux pour participer à l'amélioration de leurs conditions de vies villageoises OU BIEN !!!

JE soupçonne même le R.D.P.C d'avoir 1 équipe spéciale contre ma vie, aux vues des événements malheureux à mon rencontre ces 3 dernières années.

MENGUÉNÉ (Mvindi laure: n.d.l.r: psy chargée de détruire la vie des républicains dans le sud du cameroun.) et "ONGUÉNÉ" seraient sûrement des cousins du village contre L'INTELLIGENTSIA originaire de l'ouest Cameroun !!! En effet, "Onguéné" a fait 1 fois allusion à moi; "pr. dr. xavier noumbissi" n'étant pas saint mentalement, devant 1 parterre d'au moins 8 personnes originaires de tout rebord du CMR-natal-Et-VÉCU-DANS la misère intellectuelle.

146. "14" JUIN 2024:

1 caissière de "Casino supermarché" à YDE, a eu l'amabilité, de me rembourser avec 1 surplus de 200 FRANCS.

En effet, "je devrais retourner 1 ticket de 175 FRANCS de monnaie non rendue la dernière fois" que j'y ai fait des achats; JE ne retrouvais plus ce ticket de 175 FRANCS vieux de plus de 3 mois.

147. "20" Juin 2024:

"ONGUÉNÉ" a fait placer des plantes avec graines de mauvaises herbes exactement à l'entrée de mes appartements; Ou j'ai eu à pulvériser des herbicides il y'a de ceci 4 jours maintenant.

JE conclus que c'est la bande a FRANCK-biya; Puisque "M. ONGUÉNÉ" m'AVAIT dit être 1-"FRANCKISTE".

148. Le fainéant de la milice privée de "biya-mvondo-rdpc"; LUC-indic me fait suivre par des vaux-rien soit-disant que je suis entrain de marcher avec 1 SAINTE-BIBLE en main.

À croire que des indigènes ("Paulette AZEFA", celle qui a essayé de me faire assassiner en "Janvier 2024 par sa putain de fille "Aline AZEFA"; J'ignore qui sont ces "DSCHANG-bamilekes" qui vivent de vols et de raquettes à YDE.) n'ont rien à faire dans 1 monde extrêmement développé.

J'ai essuyé déjà 1 agression physique manquée au carrefour "Tradex-Barrière" par 1 membre de la même milice R.D.P.C.

J'empêcherais ainsi leurs opérations de satanisme en plein jour !!! ALLÉLUIA. Amen !!!

149. "21" Juin 2024: "LE PROFESSEUR THOMAS DJOTIO NDIE" DE L'ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE YAOUNDÉ VIENT DE ME RECOMMANDER, MOI, TITULAIRE D'UN DOCTORAT-PH.D. EN ÉLECTRICITÉ ET INFORMATIQUE DE L'UNIVERSITÉ DE WATERLOO EN ONTARIO AU CANADA DE POSTULER POUR 1 EMPLOI DE VACATAIRE AU SEIN DE CE FALLACIEUX ÉTABLISSEMENT DU FAIT DE LUI (E.N.S.P.Y), GÉRER PAR 1 NORMALIEN QUI N'AUROIT REÇU AUCUNE FORMATION D'INGÉNIEUR !

" AUSSI, JE LUI AI FAIT PART DE MA CONNAISSANCE DU PROFESSEUR CLÉMENTIN DJAMENI TAYOU DE L'UNIVERSITÉ DE DSCHANG."

" AUSSI, COMMENT "CLÉMENTIN TAYOU DJAMENI" QUI M'AVAIT FAIT REPAYER 1 TICKET DE TRAIN À GRANDE VITESSE PARTANT DE BREMEN (ALLEMAGNE) POUR RENNES (FRANCE) VERS DES ANNÉES 2004, "SUR INVITATION DU PROFESSEUR GILBERT TCHINDO", NE M'A PLUS JAMAIS RECONTACTÉ MALGRÉ MES MULTIPLES ACTIONS DANS CE SENS."

150. "22" Juin 2024: LE pousseur "ANDERSON kensop" est venu chez moi pour quémander du sable fin aux fins de crépir 1 véranda dans son bidon ville.

1 escouade de gendarmes et policiers, armés jusqu'aux dents est arrivée au carrefour "derrière-Savonnerie-nosa" hier sur plusieurs "véhicules 4x4".

L'INDIC de gendarmerie à moto rouge et de la tribu boulou' et très clair de teint dont j'ignore des identifications avait déjà été aimable en me transportant sur "sa moto lorsque je patientais pour Carrefour-Tradex-AHALA".

151. "23" Juin 2024: "STEEVE azefa" ÉTAIT ACCOMPAGNÉ D'UN PETIT GARNEMENT CET APRÈS-MIDI lorsque je les ai observé mettre quelques pierres et morceaux de bois devant mon domicile de YDE-ahala.

JE M'ÉTONNE de constater ce 29 JUIN 2024 QUE depuis que j'ai attrapé en flagrant délit de salissure ONGUÉNE de S2TBED; c'est maintenant les AZEFA-satan-dschang-bamilekes-voyou Q'il (S2TBED) envoi faire des saletés au devant de mes routes principales menant à mes appartements QU'ILS (VOYOU-BIYA-CONSORT-ouest-kemajou) Convoient !

JE Commence à penser que mon sous-développement actuel environnemental viendrait de l'italien MARCO-sale-type-dario-Siemens qui les pilote.

1 policier du 19 ème arrondissement (AHALA), avec 1 crâne rasé est très récurrent sur ma route.

Cet idiot était 1 fois ici il y'a de ceci environ 3 mois avec 1 indic qui a essayé (Sans la présence de ce flic véreux), de pénétrer sur 1 terrain de notre concession NOUNDOU; Bien qu'elle soit clôturé de 3 cotés;

"TCHABAT BASILE le géomètre de mes terrains NOUNDOU" avait dit que personne ne pourrait s'installer ou pénétrer dans 1 terrain clôturé à au moins 3 cotés selon des lois camerounaise.

"KEMAJOU, le colonel de gendarmerie a essayé de m'interpeller cet après-midi lorsque je circulai au devant de ses domiciles sur 1 route ouverte au public."

152. "01" Juillet 2024: "Rose sangnou la chienne de génitrice de ma personne" est entrée par effraction chez moi à YDE-Ahala avec 1 énerguemène sale comme les déchets du caca."

"S2TBED présidentielle dérange des jeunes camerounais dans leurs entreprises de nouvelles technologies avec des senteurs de vieux bois frauduleux."

"L'idiot de S2TBED-moise-chauffeur-caterpillar ose encore me suivre sur 1 piste que j'ai décidé d'emprunter pour ne plus aller dans le sens de dégueneurs travailleurs de S2TBED-biya."

153. "01" Juillet 2024: "LE MAÇON frauduleux et cambrioleur de 'HADASSAH' et consort n'a plus réessayé de me rappeler pour me faire incarcérer dans 1 cabanon de fous (torture)."

154. "02" Juillet 2024: "PAULETTE azefa" a apparemment rachetée des 6 sacs de ciments de mon chantier par l'intermédiaire de l'éraflure de psy JOEL."

"PAULETTE azefa" Est apparemment juste ici chez mon voisinage pour faire des accommodages des déchets des voisins aux fins de subvenir aux besoins de ses enfants! En effet, "PAULETTE" azefa ne mène aucune activité lucrative en dehors du vol de biens des voisins pour vivre i'

"PAULETTE azefa" A fait détruire le mur d'1 concession "NOUNDOU-batchieu" par 1 certain "PIERRE foka" par 1 intrusion des bouts de bois sur le mur mitoyen appartenant à "DEMO Noundou" i'

155. "03" **Juillet 2024**: "Le commissaire de gente féminine du commissariat de Ahala m'a fait savoir qu'elle devait faire comprendre à 6 79 73 13 62 (1 certain pasteur-landry de ne plus me rappeler !"
156. "04" **Juillet 2024**: "Mon prêt initial de "25 000 Francs" chez "MoMo-kash" ne fait que s'augmenter sans que le délai du "14 Juillet 2024" ne soit arrivé comme fin du délai de remboursement avec force."
 "Mon manquant final de "1 237 Francs" se rallonge à près de "5 000 textF" juste après avoir reversé "1 300 F" après 1 conversation de présentation du service "MoMo-kash" à "Guttemberg TCHAMAHA NTAATA", 1 cousin germain paternel."
157. "05" **Juillet 2024**: "Ma voisine sale comme la peste "Mani Théodore Datouo Kemajou Gendarmerie, Commissariat du 19^{ème} de Ahala" (Paulette azefa); a recommencé à positionner des herbes moisies sur les rebords de la route publique aux fins de pratique de sorcelleries "léviathan."
 "Cette sorcière de l'ouest fait des remous partout où j'entre et je sors pour essayer de démontrer 1 affinité avec moi; AUX fins de sorcellerie villageoises de Dschang."
158. "06" **Juillet 2024**: "CHRISTELLE kamaha", jeune employée de 22 ans de "QUINCAILLERIE N.K." est apparemment du secrétariat d'état à la défense (SED)."
159. **LUNDI "08" Juillet 2024**: "Je viens de retrouver des bretelles à la présidence de la république du cameroun au sujet de mes appartements dans locataires depuis plus de 10 mois, Par son excellence oncle de moi Ministre plénipotentiaire, et assassin de Théo-NOUMBISSI."
160. **Mardi "09" Juillet 2024**: "Rose sangnou-génitrice-de-moi, m'a redemandée d'aller à la "Poissonnerie Plus", du "fondateur NESTOR kenfack"; Dont je suis 1 fournisseur en progiciel de gestion intégré **Yerith-ERP-9.0-platinum**; D'aller y faire des achats d'1 montant d'environ "10 000 Francs" !"
 "**Yerith-ERP-9.0-platinum** A été agréé cette semaine à Quincaillerie n.k, Puisque aucun incident n'est survenue ni sur l'ordinateur d'occasion de "35 000 Francs" acheté par Startup-Yerith R&D; Ni sur le progiciel de gestion intégré (PGI-ERP) en soi; NATURELLEMENT des désirs portant sur 1 plus simple ré-utilisation du PGI-ERP ont été émis par LE FONDATEUR N.K !"
 "J'ai naturellement émis le souhait de notre entreprise de recevoir 1 minimum de "10 000 Francs" pour la réactualisation de l'ERP-PGI puisque le prix de rachat que Nestor-kenfack avait reverse a été revu drastiquement à la baisse, passant de "130 000 Francs" / utilisateur à "20 000 Francs" / utilisateur."
 "Laurent tchandeu-chien, Ministre plénipotentiaire "R.D.P.C-ayolo-mvondo-cuon"; est entrain de vouloir détruire mes entreprises entrepreneuriales en s'introduisant partout où j'entre pour affaires ou pas."
 "LANDRY-yves-etoga-galax Est 1 conjoint de tchandeu."
161. **Mardi "09" Juillet 2024**: "JEAN-Mouabeb, DE regretté mémoire à l'hôtel TOU-NGOU de yaoundé; Où il était envoyé par "Ministre-plénipotentiaire-Laurent-tchandeu" me 'désocer' (sodomiser les anus et fesses). Pour "30 000 Francs" venant de L'oncle-yves-galax-landry-etoga-TCHANDEU !"
 "TEUNTCHOU ISAAC essaye maintenant de faire entrer 1 peu d'argent dans ma bâtisse de YDÉ par l'entremise de ma sœur cadette ennemi utérine "Ingrid Teuntchou Noumeni (née Ingrid TCHITCHUI Noumbissi)" !"
 "L'objectif visé est de me faire sodomiser chez moi sur tous les plans !"
162. **Mardi "10" Juillet 2024**: 1 certain "pasteur landry etoga galax" est entré par effraction à mon domicile de YDÉ-ahala, en FORÇENANT ma génitrice Rose SANGNOU avec 1 arme-à-feu.
 J'AI constaté immédiatement des lézards venimeux dans ma concession.
 JE soupçonne 1 beau-frère de Rose SANGNOU, en l'occurrence le "SED-secretaire-detat-a-la-defense"; "Dr. WOLFGANG-fernand-junior-Owona".
 "Ce fainéant, dont l'idiot DE SON BEAU-FRÈRE patrice cabral shanda-sanou de regretté mémoire avait dit être extrêmement violent en soi."
 CE rdpc-ciste de "Dr. WOLFGANG-fernand-junior-Owona"; N'a pas encore digéré avoir essayé de m'assassiner en Février 2021 chez moi à la cité-des-palmiers.
 FEU-JOSEPH-fainéant-owona était déjà entrain d'essayer de me faire empoisonner par son fils fainéant de matthias-owona-nguini LORS DE MON SÉJOUR DE VACANCES ici a YDE en l'an 2011; Juste après que j'ai passé mon "Doctor-Ph.D. en Électricité et Informatique de l'université de waterloo".
 J'étais alors accompagné principalement du fainéant du nom de Jules-Nteta-NOUNDOU; frère consanguin a mon feu géniteur et papa: IDIOT-THEO-NOUMBISSI.
 "L'IGNARE célestin puene", ami utérin intime de JULES-nteta-noundou était aussi présent a nos cotes à ce restaurant situé au Carrefour—WARDA.
 "CÉLESTIN puene" est naturellement 1 vendeur de cocaïne à la solde de BIYA
163. **Mardi "10" Juillet 2024**: BIYA-avorton; a essayé de me faire comprendre qu'il est 1 seigneur de guerre et non 1 civil par des gangs qui sont entrés de force dans 1 concession "batchieu-NOUNDOU" dont je suis supposé veiller sur, de part mon voisinage le plus proche par rapport à l'incestueux avocat DE "batoula-moise-Yamkam-Tebiwo".

164. *Mercredi "17" Juillet 2024*: Je suis certains que maboma-juge-idiot-chien-de-galax-sed n'était plus très satisfait de ce qu'il originaire de l'OUEST du CMR Soit plus indiquée à la présidence de la république que Esso-chien-de—TCHANDEU-laurent !

165. *Mercredi "17" Juillet 2024*: "YVES landry etoga-salaud" a renvoyé dans la nuit 1 idiot pour détruire le tuyau connectant ma pompe à eau à mon cubitainer !

"J'ai été chez GUTTEMBERG taata aujourd'hui matin et j'ai vu que sa belle-mère était entrain de pratiquer 1 sorcellerie car Elle avait de l'encens dans 1 petite marmite au milieu du grand salon pour personnes en visite" !

166. *Mercredi "18" Juillet 2024*: "L'idiote à punk venant de la part YVES-LANDRY-etoga a pensé me faire ombrage en ce qui concerne mes travaux de recherche sur 1 progiciel de gestion intégré en web !

167. *Dimanche "21" Juillet 2024*: 1 brigand vêtu de tout noir dans 1 véhicule banalisé de marque "Toyota corolla" s'arrête en pleine chaussée, sur le rebord lors que je traverse 1 route jouxtant "l'entrée principale du général d'armée camerounaise BOUBA" ...!

168. *JEUDI "25" Juillet 2024*: "Datouo, KEMAJOU" est allé faire des faux documents disant que je suis 1 schizophrène, Puisque il ne sait même plus où je vis.

"Rose SANGNOU" ma génitrice m'avait déjà redemandée de ne plus entretenir des conversations et / ou liens amicaux avec cet individu d'1 violence terrible Puisque ancien militaire de rang à l'Ouest du Cameroun du COMMANDEMENT OPÉRATONNEL. ELLE s'était plaint de ses appels téléphoniques incessant sur sa ligne MTN !

"Rose SANGNOU" a fait des efforts pour me fournir "5 000 Francs" ce jour-ci.

169. *Lundi "29" Juillet 2024*: "JE m'engage à déverrouiller en apprentissage la jeune et insouciant "Christelle AKAMBA", nouvelle employée de l'ancien client Quincaillerie N.K." !

170. *Lundi "12" Août 2024*: "L'énergumène de junior-bankoui; 1 petit type très court et très nerveux, Qui parraine le gang de malfaiteurs (malfrats) fondé par "PAULETTE azefa; est aux arrêts par mes paroles ! " !

AZEFA a des soutiens "vietkong venant de Datouo par FRANCK-biya-s2tbed". CE gang sévit dans les zones de barrières-simbock-ahala.

CETTE bande appartenant au gendarmes BAMKOUI-datouo-KEMAJOU est au cerveau d'1 réseau de vols aggravés par menaces sur personnes physiques que j'ai éprouvé par la tentative de vente d'1 frigidaire personnel de chambre au "Montant de "50 000 Francs"" à 1 certain "Georges-chien-ANDERSON-njougep".

EN prélude à cette tentative de vols graves, ROSE-sangnou-génitrice; m'avertissait d'1 petit dérangement qu'elle peut faire par sa sœur de bankepche-bangou, en l'occurrence la renommée "NJOUGEP-malfrat-peg"; En effet, elle est allée se renseigner sur mes transactions financières aux fins d'opposer 1 rentrée d'argent dans mes poches !

Naturellement tout ceci est sous-organise par "LE PROFESSEUR jean-claude-SALAUD-tonne" de "MENJIE-bangou".

TOUS ces signalements sont faits dans le but d'entraver la MARCHÉ DE LA JUSTICE dans le cadre de l'information judiciaire sur la tentative d'assassinat que j'ai subit en FÉVRIER 2021 dans la nuit aux alentours de 23 : 30 à mon domicile prive au quartier BÉEDI-DLA.

171. *Lundi "12" Août 2024*: " 1 petit bandit de capitaine-mbida de la "DSP-Division-de-la-sécurité-présidentielle vêtu de bleu tricot+jean" me regarde menaçant du visage lorsque je me déplace sur le chemin-route menant a mon domicile pas très loin de cette maudite maison des hommes avec des armes a feu en milieu de ville-civile.

JE soupçonne déjà mvondo-capitaine-emanè-nkoa-pierre-marcelin; AUSSI "rattacher à manawabe par le BIR-bataillon-d'intervention-rapide;" de rechercher à me faire assassiner PUISQUE dans mes rédactions précédentes et mon curriculum vitae ci-dessus en Anglais, j'ai déjà raconté tout ce qu'il m'a fait subir comme sévices racistes-tribales-boulu de CHIENS-nauséabonds !!

"SA sœur cadette mado" qui travaille chez etoga, m'a même déjà fait agressé par 1 homme d'1 taille de plus de 2 mètres 30 centimètres.

"SA sœur cadette mado" EST la concubine de capitaine-mbida; ET 1 gendarme en service au SED-sécrétariat-d'état-à-la-défense.

172. *Samedi "24" Août 2024*: "Colonel KEMAJOU" est en infraction sur 1 terrain de la CUY-Communauté Urbaine DE Yaoundé.

En effet, ce "sodomiseur" occupe 1 terrain que la Communauté Urbaine de Yaoundé a redemandée de détruire depuis Fevrier de cette année !

CET énergumène a même fait construire 1 escalier de béton à l'endroit de cet espace public où j'ai l'habitude de repasser pour inspecter l'évolution des travaux de réaménagements de la CUY; PUISQUE je suis 1 riverain à qui ceci serait bénéfique.

LA quantité de malfaiteurs installés près de "colonel KEMAJOU" prête à confusion; on dirait qu'il entretient des bandits ou bien comment !

173. *JEUDI "22" Août 2024*: "1 monsieur du sed-ndlr-secrétariat-d'état-à-ladéfense vêtu d'1 ensemble sport gris, ou bien j'ai oublié la couleur; VIENT me perturber pendant que je relie quelques versets bibliques dans mon petit coin seul; En pleine bordure de rue; SANS gêner personne dans ses routes et autres."

L'ignare vient discutailler sur son ordinateur téléphone mobile à très haute voix; JUSTE derrière moi qui suis assis.

LORSQUE l'on a raté sa vie honnête, on essaye d'aller faire des inquisitions (accusations mensongères contre des homme de "JEOVAH-NISSI-AU-CIEL").

174. *Samedi "26" Août 2024*: "Une dame de la police camerounaise en service à Yaoundé a redemandée "500 Francs" a mon oncle-cousin GUTTEMBERG-tchamaha lors d'1 contrôle inopiné de pièce d'identité et de circulation."

NOUS (guttemberg tchamaha ntaata et son épouse MARCELLE-marie-tchamaha; ainsi que leur fils MAXIME) du marché "Mokolo"

Une policière ayant 1 salaire minimal de "130 000 Francs" redemandant "500 Francs" à 1 ménagère ayant 5 enfants à charge et vivant de commerce au collègue "JÉSUS-MARIE" de l'église catholique orthodoxe de SIMBOCK; n'est ce pas aberrant !!!.

JE n'ai pas eu de possibilité de relire le nom et le grade de cette fonctionnaire de police d'1 système assez similaire a MAXIME-napoa-eteme en service a la base navale de DOUALA; Et scandant être en service "au sémil-ndlr.Sécurité-MILITAIRE"

JE serais 1 petit peu choqué que ce monsieur dont 1 des filles officielles BRENDA-eyenga-biya...; redemande à briguer 1 nouveau: Surtout qu'il à déjà passe près de 55 ans dans 2 gouvernements camerounais !!! fin ce citation.

MOI, président de mes générations descendantes; je pense être mieux qualifié pour régir la position de magistrat suprême; Sans permettre que des agents du secrétariat d'état (SED) à la défense vienne par effraction au domicile d'1 diplômé de la meilleure université canadienne ontarienne en informatique de génie; POUR l'emmenner de force à 23 heures 30 minutes par "Laquintinie-assassins".

Quand je repense n'avoir jamais vu des points de développement sur le plan numérique dans le site web-internet du président paul-biya-du-renouveau "macronien" qui parle de l'informatisation !!!

175. *Mercredi "28" Août 2024*: "J'étais en compagnie du plombier-bir Francis Come MAGLOIRE nkoulou."

"J'ai été prévenu de ne plus le rechercher PUISQU'IL peut me faire avoir des ennuies de psy VERS son copain utérin "psychologue ALAIN ELAME chien"; psy-de-torture au Cameroun-inofficiel !".

"J'avais reçu l'agression de mes domiciles par 1 génitrice ré-utilisée par rose-croix-AMORC; En vue de me faire mettre en psy de force avec 1 certain pasteur-landry-etoge-SED-drogue".

"L'idiot de siemeni fabrice pense qu'il peut me rendre moins opulent en arrêtant mes revenus financiers par etoga le chef idiot du secretariat d'état a la défense; ROSE sangnou me re-annonce qu'elle sera encore a YAOUNDE apres que je l'ai rencontre il y'a seulement 2-semaines de ceci."

176. *Vendredi "30" Août 2024*: "J'ai discutaillé avec le "DQP-diplôme de qualification professionnelle en INFORMATIQUE marie-rose ondomo" ce jour en présence de SERGE."

J'ai recommandé 1 ordinateur portable de marque Lenovo série de fabrication "T-thinkpad" d'1 montant de "70 000 Francs".

177. *Vendredi "06" SEPTEMBRE 2024*: "J'ai redemandé à "nestor kenfack" de ne plus se mêler des affaires personnelles me concernant sans mon avis et accord."

Cet idiot de commerçant de Panurge: "nestor kenfack"; IL ne sait plus même se limiter à son petit commerce !

178. *mardi "17" Septembre 2024*: "'Mbouwe"-chien marius supposément être 1 technicien de froids et chauffage parait être plutôt 1 sapeur pompier de l'armée; Puisque j'ai observé 1 monsieur en treillis orange de l'armée peu après que je sois ressorti de chez moi pour retourner chez NESTOR-kenfack de QUINCAILLERIE-N.K à Barrière-tradax-ahala-YDE. ! "

Mbouwe est vêtu d'1 boucle d'oreille or aussi.

Cette boutique avait prétendue réparer mon refroidisseur d'air acquéri à "HISENSE-midea-Akwa-DLA". MAIS après 1 semaine d'utilisation; LE même problème d'éteinte subit s'est produit.

179. *mardi "26" Septembre 2024*: 1 dame cherchait atrocement a me tancer dans 1 discussion verbale hier lorsque j'étais chez mon client 'N.K-quincaillerie-cuon' pour effectuer 1 importation de près de 300 stocks par le biais de scripts en AWK-bash-cryptés.

"NGATCHOU-henri-bertrand" le transsexuel initié à la chose par "richard-mfeugwang" devrait être à l'initiative de cette tentative d'inquisition pour prétexter 1 énervement ou tout autre chose aux fins d'infirmier que je sois libre dans ma vie mentale et intellectuelle !

CE rosicrucien logé à "édéa" et détenteur d'un b.e.p.c-ndlr.—brevet-d'études-du-1^{er}-cycle et déjà vice-président du R.D.P.C à bangou a sûrement reçu de l'argent de l'esclavagiste anglo-saxon-neerlandais "FRANK-tip (<https://www.ftip.org>)"; AUX fins que je ne puisse avoir du succès de mes entreprises en informatique; PUISQUE je suis 1 concurrent et adversaire direct de INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS MACHINERY-ibm.

"N'EUT été la vigilance du commissaire-véreux de police MARIE, du 4^{ème} arrondissement de DOUALA, "FRANK-tip (<https://www.ftip.org>)" m'aurait fait perdre près de "210 000 Francs" par le fainéant et homosexuel entouré de 6 pédé de femmes TITO-market."

180. **SAMEDI "14" Septembre 2024:** "JE SOUPÇONNE 1 vendeuse de la ville de YAOUNDÉ, dont j'ignore des identifications; DE vouloir me faire emprisonner comme déficient mental PUISQUE elle et son mari sont au "secrétariat-d'état à la défense" comme assassin (AGENT DE RENSEIGNEMENT) i'

"Cette dame, aux seins atrocement énormes avait essayé de faire connaissance avec moi sur le plan personnel en me racontant des ragots selon lesquels son frère cadet serait doctorant à l'université de "Dschang-OUEST-idiots-ekang-KEMAJOU-salaud-bandits-voleurs-SHANDA-NDjatie-Tonme-bangou-idiot"

"Puisque j'ai observé 1 putaine qui vendait près d'1 lieu où j'ai subi 1 arrestation illégale m'observer ce matin lorsque je suis arrivé 1 peu avant pour faire 1 retrait ORANGE-money."

"LA sale mercedes du voisin indélicat du sed-anicet-idiot-mfeuken était mal garé lorsque je repassais par ce chemin jouxtant 1 chemin de fer de la ville de YAOUNDÉ cet après-midi."

"KEMAJOU-idiot colonel de gendarmerie-GP-sed" avait déjà essayé de m'accoster lorsque je repassais dans cette boutique mal-famé malgré ma propre personne il y'a de ceci 3 mois; SON fils handicapé de naissance et aussi membre du gang SED-yves-landry-etoga passe de temps à autre par ce chemin sans se faire remarquer; Sûrement pour voir et suivre l'avancée des travaux de tentatives d'incarcération illégale venant de cette dame "DSCHANG-au-mari-fainéant-etoga-sed-centre-ekang-AMOUGOU-belinga-chien-cuon".

"ANICET mfeuken, dont j'ignore l'activité réelle, mais qui a essayé de se faire repasser pour 1 informaticien au marché central de YDE en infographie serait en réalité 1 assassin à la joug du fainéant CLAUDE-indic-etoga-galax i'

"1-vendeur originaire de l'ouest a aussi été posté à l'entrée de SANTA-lucia ou je fait des achats; Et où je me tiens souvent en attente de rencontrer des potentiels clients; Ce monsieur est vendeur de sous-vêtements et est là pour faire des observations et essayer de me faire passer pour quelqu'un d'anormal aux fins de ternir mon image d'intellectuel NON "HOMOSEXUEL-kemajou-nyando-gendarmerie-idiot-bandit-a-main-arme"

"L'objectif final étant de me faire humilié en public aux fins d'effrayer tous ceux comme moi qui rapportent des réalités de la dictature R.D.P.C-au cameroon et à l'étranger par des indic tels que TCHANDEU-laurent, mon oncle paternel et assassin de mon défunt papa "théodore-noumbissi-pd-rosicrucien".

"J'évoque et j'invoque le PSAUME-18 de "jeovah-nissi-au-ciel" Pour me faire venger par le SEIGNEUR-des-non-homosexuels-brutaux-couples de partouzeurs angéla-wolfgang-fainéant !!."

"DES "ekang-béti-etoga-sed" épousent des filles de L'OUEST pour faire des sales besognes sur des ressortissants originaires de cette région; Comme ANGELA-ma cousine utérine qui a épousé "WOLFGANG-junior-owona-fernand" et qui a essayé de me faire assassiner par le "B.I.R-sed-EYOUM-christian-rotary-club" en Février 2021 à Douala !! "

181. **SAMEDI "10" OCTOBRE 2024:** 1 dame vêtue d'1 robe longue de couleur pagne maronne semble être entrain de me faire des inquisitions sur mes chemins PUISQUE je l'ai Rencontré 2 fois au minimum cette semaine.

LA 2^{ème} fois, elle était accompagnée de 3 ou 4 personnes faisant semblant de faire 1 interview-reportage.

JE soupçonne "SHANDA-tonme", Agent-secret espion américain; ET à la solde de "MICROSOFT RESEARCH", d'essayer pour besoin de gains financiers, de me faire des humiliations et destructions publiques.

AVANT ceci, 2 personnes ont essayé de m'accoster alors que j'étais dans 1 petit restaurant de "N.K.-Quincaillerie"; ET dans les locaux de "N.K.-Quincaillerie" respectivement.

Le métier des membres des familles où SHANDA-tonme est entré pour faire des assassinats des élites intellectuelles camerounaises est devenue des ASSASSINS.

JULES-nteta noundou par exemple passe par CElestin-PUENE-faineant-du-SED-yves-galax-landry-etoga pour essayer de gêner mes travaux de constructions et de ré-aménagements.

182. *Dimanche "13" Octobre 2024: JE rencontre l'illétre de atanga nji...; Dont J'ignore des prénoms dans 1 supermarché de la ville de Yaoundé lorsque je vais faire des EINKAUFEN.*

Cette année 2024, je n'ai pas encore été agressé injustement par SHANDA-atange-nji-corrompus pédé.

183. *JEUDI "17" Octobre 2024: Mme IRÈNE seumo NGantchui, Épse BETEHE, apparemment chargé de clientèle a la nouvelle agence "CommercialBank; AHALA 3ème arrondissement de YAOUNDÉ" m'a permis de pouvoir lui fournir des éléments suivants pour l'obtention d'1 compte bancaire de type épargne dans sa nouvelle et somptueuse institution.*

- 1.) 1 CNI;
- 2.) ~~1 facture d'électricité et / OU D'EAU;~~
- 3.) 1 preuve de revenu;
- 4.) 1 carte photo 4x4;
- 5.) 1 plan de localisation;
- 6.) 1 justificatif professionnel.

JE m'évertue dès ce jour du JEUDI 17 OCTOBRE 2024 à réunir et à fournir ces 6 éléments aux fins de pouvoir faire des épargnes de nouveau grâce à l'activité des ventes de progiciels de gestion intégré.

JE remercie vivement son collaborateur "MONSIEUR Charles NDJATAN", dont j'ignore des niveaux de compétences académiques qui m'a reçu et avec qui j'ai parlé en détails de mes projets d'investissements dans la communauté urbaine de YAOUNDÉ; au lieu dit : "Derrière savonnerie nosa; face 2^{ème} entrée société de transformations des bois du Mbang S2TBED".

184. *JEUDI "17" Octobre 2024: J'ai été à Douala ce "12 – 13 Octobre 2024"; J'ai rencontré Synclaire NJEUTCHA tchana; Avocat et conseil de mon humble personne; Sans succès j'ai essayé de Dormir à la cité-des-palmiers; AU domicile de ROSE sangnou.*

Je suis retourné avec "9 600 Francs" remis par mon numéro ORANGE–money (6 97 19 49 06) par Monsieur NOUNDOU-koliou; Frère "junior de mon défunt papa et géniteur Noumbissi Théodore".

185. *JEUDI "17" Octobre 2024: Mme IRÈNE seumo NGantchui, Épse BETEHE, a aussi préférée avoir 2 assistantes vêtues d'uniforme Bleue–Orange à l'entrée de son bureau et aussi présent à ma sortie de son bureau;*

JE ne suis pas certain si ce luxueux établissements avait des caméras de surveillance partout où j'étais présent; Mais je le pense très certainement vue le très haut–niveau d'équipements mobiliers et actualisés !

FÉLICITATIONS À "CommercialBank–CAMEROON"

CES assistantes m'ont parues être 1 sécurité interne; Additionnel à la sécurité externe de gardiens vêtus de treillis-uniformes de couleur jaune.

186. *JEUDI "17" Octobre 2024: CECI "m'a fait me souvenir" de mon escapade À LA CLINIQUE DU docteur–verreux Francis–NGADJEU; Puisque il avait promis de faire signer 1 contrat de "50 000 Francs" mensuel pour le rachat de 5 copies de mon progiciel de gestion intégré YERITH–ERP–PGI–9.0; Puis il ne l'a plus exécuté; Nonobstant mon acharnement à le servir très professionnellement dans ses locaux de Douala–DÉÏDO; Sis DÉÏDO–PLAGE !*

ILS étaient 2 hommes plutôt assermentés à la sécurité interne des locaux de son LUXUEUX APPARTEMENT–CLINIQUES–PRIVÉES !

187. *JEUDI "21" Octobre 2024: JE reviens de ISTIAM–institut–d'inquisition de santé; Qui passe le clair de son temps à rédigé des rapports sur des riverains au lieu de former des étudiants en sciences médicales et sciences informatiques tels que proclamés dans leurs prospectus.*

Cette mégère nommée NANA ne sait même plus que l'on ne se masse pas des pieds nus dans 1 bureau ouvert au grand public sur 1 rue publique en pleine construction ce 21 Octobre 2024.

J'AI eu oui–dire que nana-la-mégère disait à Carole mangue; Sa cousine qui est vendeuse de beignets et de haricots que si j'emprunte des beignets parce que je ne suis pas solvable; Je serais 1 démuné social (dont 1 thérapie pourrait m'aider à revenir à la normalité du mariage homosexuel tel que proclamé en ROMAINS 2; 26 – 28 de la BIBLE PAROLE DE VIE (version AMIS POUR TOUJOURS)) !

J'AI aussi oui–dire que son père Monsieur GUIMEYA serait affilié au garage de mécanique automobile ouvert juste sur 1 rebord du rail; A moins de 2 mètres du chemin de fer YAOUNDE–douala.

" JE pense ne plus être à cet institut aux allures de prévarications sur des vies humaines à la rose-croix d'or de Monsieur GUIMEYA. "

NANA en passant m'avait toisée la dernière fois que je m'y suis rendue pour rencontrer GUIMEYA; Sans que je sache le pourquoi: affaire de femelles.

188. JEUDI "25" OCTOBRE 2024: JE suis allé à la rencontre de Marie-Marcelle TCHAMAHA ce jour-ci; Ne l'ayant pas d'abord rencontré à son poste de travail au collège Jésus-Marie de Simbock; JE me suis rendu dans 1 lieu de beignets-infecte qui m'avait été démontré par GUTTEMBERG ntaata tchamaha;

CE lieu m'a permis de prendre des beignets, haricots-rouges; et BOUILLIE-citron pour 1 montant total de "500 Francs"; Ensuite je suis revenue déposé cet argent tel que je l'avais promis 1-heure auparavant; Puisque GUTTEMBERG tchamaha ntaata; MON cousin utérin paternel m'avait dit la 1^{ère} fois que c'est ce que lui même avait fait lorsque nous avons dîné ensemble vers 11 heures dans ce lieu extrêmement infecte.

J'ai parlé de mes personnes officielles à cette jeune dame dont j'avais oublié des prénoms et noms; En lui rappelant que c'est TCHAMAHA-bed-yves-landry-etoga qui m'y avait introduit sous forme MANGER-pret-rembourser 1 matin lors d'1 de mes escapades sportives;

Je ne sais plus si je peux revenir à cet endroit PUISQUE plusieurs hommes d'1 augure très suspecte sont entrés lorsque j'y étais présent; L'1 d'eux m'a même effrayé !

189. Vendredi "08" Novembre 2024: JE suis surpris que "la génitrice SANGNOU, veuve rose noumbissi"; PASSE plus de temps à rechercher des psy, et autres pour me rendre nerveux et non certains de mes revenus financiers; QUE de s'occuper de sa fille en détresse nerveuse du fait de son incapacité à contrôler des naissances dans son mariage homosexuel.

190. LUNDI "11" Novembre 2024: "j'étais en route pour dire YAGER-maboma de DLA-ndokoti de ne plus trop essayer de retarder mon procès contre Christian-EYOUM-laquintinie qui m'a violenter en FEVRIER 2021 après être entrés par effraction chez moi aux environs de 22 : 30 dans la soirée; BERTRAND le gros bras m'avait asséné 1 coup de poing dans la poitrine, Et 1 policier petit salopard m'avait giflé dans 1 taxi. "

" JE savais étant 1 jeune homme de moins de 20 ans qu'il y'avait des organisations soit-dites de l'ONU... ! "

191. LUNDI "11" Novembre 2024: " J'AI l'impression que des cousins de sawa-douala-bassa étaient entrain de me montrer leur désamour PUISQUE je me remets dans des mains de la justice dans tous les axes du termes contre le rotarien-lions-clubais CHRISTIAN-eyoum idiot. "

" EN effet, ce MD-psy américain de double citoyenneté camerounaise et œuvrant à la destruction des grands cerveaux et esprits de la race noire avait essayé de me faire comprendre qu'il peut faire des forfaits à sa guise sans subir de représaille dans cette terre qui appartient au SEIGNEUR YERITH.-moi ! "

" EN effet, ce psychiatre-psychologue avait déjà essayé de me faire subir du diabète involontaire en concoctant des médicaments d'1 certains type sans mon avis MAIS avec l'aide ma famille qui serait 1 serviteur du président des RDPC par 1 soit-disant oncle appelé LAURENT-culprité-wretched-TCHANDEU ! "

" EN effet, je réitère ceci: AVANT LA FIN DE SA CARRIÈRE, eyoum christian de douala-sawa sera 1 fou marchant dans des rues de cameroun, NON de mes incantations, mais du fait de ce que certains appelle le KARMA. (n.d.l.r: le retour d'ascenseur tel que par exemple re-défini dans le psaumes 18 de la SAINTE BIBLE louis segond aux versets 46 à 48) ! "

192. LUNDI "11" Novembre 2024: " J'ai constaté que notre ancien locataire par ma génitrice et mère Rose sangnou; veuve noumbissi-théodore: GERMAIN blaise ndzié, originaire du Sud et de l'EST cameroun a complètement détruit 1 tuyau d'alimentation de notre maison à la cité-des-palmiers-beedi.. "

" EN EFFET, notre nouvelle locatrice par moi Dr.-Ing. Xavier NOUMBISSI NOUNDOU a 1 problème dans la cuisine ! "

193. SAMEDI "16" Novembre 2024: " JE m'offusque de constater que MAXIME NAPOA ETEME, le brigand de la dites SEMIL-n.d.l.r.: dont le directeur ne le reconnaît plus comme 1 de ses éléments a fait continuer le commerce illicite de denrées alimentaires devant mes domiciles de la cité-des-Paamiens-haute-tension-beedi. "

" CE militaire reconnu en service à la base navale de DOUALA; Et tel que l'atteste ses images sur le site-internet facebook.com (<https://facebook.com>) !; AUSSI après ma rencontre personnelle avec le directeur de la sécurité militaire le colonel JOËL Émile bamkoui. "

194. Mardi "26" Novembre 2024: " Rostand-idiot, petit-frère aîné de ERIC-omega JOËL kom-sipa avec qui j'ai fait des études de mathématiques au collège ALFRED-Saker-de-DOUALA-deïdo; est entrain de vouloir me remettre dans des endroits malfamés des assassins psy telque Christian-eyoum. "

" CET imposteur d'informaticien de l'uc; Ne perd pas de temps à entrer en contact avec ma génitrice ROSE-sangnou pour discuter si il peut voir si je suis comme il faut mentalement parlant; JE dois re-préciser que cet artisan de feu-psy-Christian-eyoum, Maintient son frère-eric depuis plus de 12 ans en anti-dépresseur aux fins de rester le seul héritier de la concession scabreuse KOM-salomon-idiot-ami-OWONA-Grégoire. "

195. Mardi "26" Novembre 2024: " "L'IGNORANT-etoga-indic-cuon-pédé-MOHAMED-ali" ne sait même plus qui est "SADAM-hussein" (Ancien dictateur et "Président-RAÏS de L'Irak sous GEORGES-BUSH-FILS pendu sur CNN en l'année" "

196. *Jeudi "05" Décembre 2024*: J'ai confirmé à ROSE-sangnou-cinglé de comprimés neuro-leptiques sur mes identités lors de mon entrevue avec 1 psy-rose :

- 1.) *ELLE occupe mon appartement de 3 chambres de la cité-des-PALMIERS-béedi sans mon consentement aucun ;*

PUISQUE elle y passe environ 2 fois par semaines sans y dormir et/ou séjourner; AUSSI ELLE A FAIT FAIRE à ce que j'ai déjà eu à observer au minimum 1 fois dans 1 tas de documents qu'elle avait mise à ma disposition: MAÎTRE SAMUEL kwame, huissier de justice à DOUALA, confirmait FRAUDULEUSEMENT que sa génitrice et maman ELIZABETH-tchitchui vivait chez moi !.

ELLE a remis des clés de mon second appartement à INGRID-teuntchou-noumeni-idiote; QUI l'a occupé sans me redonner 1 loyer mensuel comme ceci est dû depuis environ 14 mois.

INGRID de citoyenneté camerounaise serait aux dernières nouvelles en séjours en ALLEMAGNE de l'OUEST pour des accouchements d'enfants avec des citoyennetés que je j'ignore; PUISQUE ces bâtards ont des parents qui se présentent toujours à des endroits depuis que j'ai été emmené chez JEAN-moubeb; AUX fins que je subisse des comprimés neuro-leptiques:.

INGRID teuntchou noumeni serait donc 1 sorte d'administratrice non déclarée de mes identités sans que je ne sache comment ET par quel biais; PUISQUE meme le commissaire spécial de DOUALA 5ème LE recoit sans mon autorisation lors d'1 audition sur mes propos d'insultes provocations sur la personne de "S2TBED"; PUISQUE biya-franc-daniel-OLÉ-sangmelima aurait mis INGRID et rose et teuntchou-rdpc-caca en otage; PUISQUE j'ai refusé de rétrocéder 1 de mes biens immobiliers à "S2TBED" !

- 2.) *AURÉLIEN iloga-iloga, homosexuel patenté de collège-alfred-saker de dla-déido; pédé, aurait même pris attache avec MAXIME napoa étéme et INGRID teuntchou-noumbissi-noumei aux fins d'organiser 1 violence physique sur ma personne au sous-sol de ecobank; Agence de YDE-poste-centrale en l'an 2023;*

DOROTHÉE shanda-ndjatié l'aurait introduit aux renseignements généraux de la destruction civile sur personnes à revenus non-officiellement déclarés aux impôts du RDPC-renseignement-generaux; OU il n'y a même aucune information postés dans des domiciles sur le plancher ou dans la cours depuis plus de 30 ans.

- 3.) *CHANDRIAND teuntchou noumeni qui copule avec 1 soeur utérine à moi qui serait INGRID; ne s'est jamais donné de peine à me dire pourquoi il avait même déjà sollicité cette putain aux ongles de de pied de prostituées ("HURE" en langue allemande).*

C'est à croire QUE CE procénète m'avait repéré lors d'1 anniversaire de CAÏN-nono. NEREL-bomeni-siewe n'est surement plus 1 cousin de mon nouveau locataire par MELEU-nossi-BELVIANNE, fille non-mariage-feu-theo.

- 4.) *la garce ingrid qui a même vécu sous le même toit que ma humble personne pendant notre jeunesse jusqu'à environ mes 16 ans; EST même arrivé à me faire penser qu'elle était 1 fille de THÉODORE-salaud noumbissi; Elle serait notamment juste 1 fille de rose-sangnou et de FRANKLIN-tchuidjang; En réponse a MELEU-belvianne NOSSI NO-umbis-!*

C'est à croire QUE CE procénète m'avait repéré lors d'1 anniversaire de CAÏN-nono. NEREL-bomeni-siewe n'est surement plus 1 cousin de mon nouveau locataire par MELEU-nossi-BELVIANNE, fille non-mariage-feu-theo.

- 5.) *DONC même si nérel-mbomei-siewe ne le sait plus, IL serait apparemment 1 frère aîné dont j'ignore l'historique; MAIS d'1 mère nommée siewe.*
- 6.) *Apparemment saliou-moussi est aussi 1 frère aîné à ma personne; de père seulement; PUISQUE j'ai ressenti d'étranges émotions qui m'étaient familières lorsque je mangeais à table avant l'âge de 5 ans avec mon feu père et ses amis informaticiens À grosse moustache dans des albums photos.*
- 7.) *DESORMAIS je comprends pourquoi j'avais reçu uniquement des insultes de la "4ème femme du chef batchieu à PARIS" lorsque david-laurent-TCHANDEU-koloko-levis m'avait envoyé voir 1 jeune fille pour épouse-utérine-potentielle.*

197. *DIMANCHE "05" JANvier 2025* : *Je séjourne de nuit chez "le grand-père feu Ngongang JEAN;" Je constate que le petit fainéant de "RODRIGUE SIENCHIE alain ngongang" harcèle violemment rose sangnou de sortir de son domicile de naissance; ALORS qu'il n'a pas plus de droit que elle dans cette maison de naissance de la famille NGONGANG.*

Cet idiot vie chez son feu père après avoir passé près de 9 ans à DUISBOURG-Nordrheinwestfally.

IL avait été interné dans 1 établissement psy; Et j'étais allé l'y faire sortir pour le mettre dans 1 avion au coût de 800-Euros aux fins qu'il puisse être pris en charge sur tous des plans, SURTOUT alimentaire.

198. *Vendredi "10" Janier 2025* : *Le pédé de biya au rdpc essayerait de faire passer des rapports assermentés venant de l'handicapé mental Christian-EYOUN; Qui soit-diSant traiterait l'animal-zombie rodrigue-alain-ngongang-sienchie; 1 éponge de pater-cuon-salaud ' 'SHATO@yahoo.fr' '.*

L'élucubrante mentale de psy eyoum-moubeb avait prédit 1 rechute tous les 2 ans sur ma santé psychologique si je ne prenais pas des antalgiques avec effet de réduire mon potentiel intellectuel qui est supérieur à la moyenne pédé AYOLO-samuel-FAINÉANT.

Le salaud grégoire owona qui a déjà depuis le mariage de la soeur de Cabral-PD-franck-biya a déjà fait au minimum tomber 18 corps physiques avec son amant défunt JOSEPH-owona dans sa belle famille de batchingou-ta-ngaap.

199. *Vendredi "10" Janier 2025* : *LA sale chienne de génitrice rose-sangou pensait me faire des problèmes en venant verser plusieurs objets de sorcellerie dans 1 chambre qui semblerait Selon ses Délires-maniaques être occupée par ses personnes physiques; Incluant.*

- 1.) *4 gousses sataniques rappelés Objets-de-paix—Sataniques venant de Nkwouano—josué*
- 2.) *2 bouteilles d'huiles essentielles Aux senteurs de chanvres-indiens (bien mentionnée sur des 2 bouteilles);*
- 3.) *Pause*

200. diManche "05" JANvier 2025: *Nous nous sommes mis d'accord (ROSE-sangnou, Victor KOLIYOU NOUNDOU, et "INGRID tchitchui-noumbissi, Epse TEUNtchou-noumeni" que nous partageons dès à présent à parts égales (ROSE, INGRID, et xavier-yerith) tout revenue financier provenant des biens remis à nous par THEODORE-idiot noumbissi.*
- KOLIYOU-NOUNDOU était le père de famille lors de notre rencontre.*
201. jeuDi "06" FEVRIER 2025: *"JE reviens de YDE ou MBIDA et EMANA NKOA ont commissionés "kemajou-datou" de tout détruire chez moi pendant mon absence; Même des miroirs dans mes salles de bains ont été déportés vers 1 lieu que j'ignore."*
- "J'ACCUSE le président de la république du Cameroun de vouloir me racketter jusques à preuve de contraire."*
- "JE voyage dans 1 véhicule personnel par 1 agent de la justice militaire en enquête sur l'affaire Amougou-belinga; 1 certain greffier "BOKALI"."*
- "IL devrait savoir qu'on ne met pas des doigts dans la bouche au contact de la salive devant des intellectuels comme moi !"*
- "1 jeune nordiste avec 1 air de malfaiteur noir-américain était à l'arrière du véhicule; C'est par courtoisie pour le greffier BOKALI que je ne suis plus sorti de son véhicule pour voyager autrement !"*
- "Je retournais à DLA avec tentative d'utiliser BUCAVOYAGE-prestige-vip; Lorsque j'ai entendu scander 'Douala personnel' de l'autre côté de la route et que j'ai voulu essayer aussi ceci : SURTOUT encourager par des dires sur 'YouTUBE.com' de Claudel-noubissie; L'enseignant d'entrepreneuriat en ligne et en présentiel sur locaux à BASTOS. "*
- "Pendant ce temps-ci, l'armée défaillante du président de la république du cameroun essaye d'anéantir mes efforts de créer 1 centre de formation informatique génie informatique-logiciel; ASSURANCE-qualité-développement progiciels de gestion intégré; MERCI de REVENIR à la raison CHEF DE QUARTIER M. Atangana Séverin; JE n'apprécie plus subir des vols comme auparavant ceux de "MANI-azefa-palette"."*
202. lunDi "10" FEVRIER 2025: *"DES voisins de Béedi versent des eaux de cuisine juste dans le caniveau de mes appartements. Elles ne sont plus rendues compte que ces eaux contiennent des tomates, etc."*
- "DONC elles sont responsable de cette montée d'herbes de champs; J'attends j'espère qu'elles vont prendre 1 peu de temps pour les désherber."*
203. lunDi "10" FEVRIER 2025: *"J'étais obligé de redemander ROSE-sangnou manu-militari de biper l'avocat aux fins de contacter le parquet de NDOKOTI pour la suite de mon affaire contre elle et Christian-eyoum."*
- "EN EFFET, elle et Chandriand-teuntehou-noumeni ont fait violer mes domiciles de YDE ahala nsimbock lorsque je séjournais à Douala."*
204. Lundi "03" Février 2025: *"Eric-joël kom-sipa et son petit frangin ne cessent de rester sans vouloir avoir "20 000 Francs" de mes argents si je parvenais a re-louer ce petit appartement de la cité-des-palmiers ! "*
205. Samedi "22" Mars 2025: *"Des imbéciles de "GLOBAL EXPERT SOLUTION Sarl" ont scandés le canada-cchien ce jour-ci à la cité-des-palmiers-BEDI."*
206. Samedi "05" Avril 2025: *Chantio-josue-nkwouano et ses imbéciles de frères juniors; Chacun (Rodrigue-idiot-attardé mental-casseur de lunettes-médicales-&-PRINCE-sed-fainéant-raoul) pensent que JE.*
- Ses 2 énerguènes sont de quels niveaux académiques et / ou professionnels pour que je me rabaisse à suivre deux ignorants faire des grosses paroles contre la ggénitrice et / ou assassine Rose sangnou; Envoyées par eux avec violence comme j'ai déjà eu à assister lors d'1 de mes visites inopinées dans rendez-vous aucun.*

YRI_JH_NISSI_uwaterloo_transcripts_MarkedUP__for__clarities_by_XAVIE- R_noumbissi_NOUNDOU _____	2
YRI_JH_NISSI_uwaterloo_transcripts_Original_from_The_STUDENT_CEN- TRE_nancy _____	4
YERITH _____	6
YRI_CV_ENGLISH _____	11

University of Waterloo
 200 University Ave. West
 Waterloo Ontario
 Canada
 N2L3G1

Graduate Official Transcript

Duffin M. Caelli
 Associate Vice-President
 Graduate Studies
 and Postdoctoral Affairs

Name: **Noumbissi Noundou, Xavier**
 Student ID: **20284586**
 Ontario Education Nbr: **445938806**

Beginning of Graduate Record

Fall 2009

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: **Full-Time** Term: 1.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
ECE 725	Computer-Aided Verification	0.50	0.50	90

Winter 2010

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: **Full-Time** Term: 2.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2010

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: **Full-Time** Term: 3.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Fall 2010

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: **Full-Time** Term: 4.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2011

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: **Full-Time** Term: 5.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2011

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: **Full-Time** Term: 6.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
CS 744	Advanced Compiler Design	0.50	0.50	86

Fall 2011

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: **Full-Time** Term: 7.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Fall 2012

Program: **Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD**
 Attendance: **Full-Time** Term: 8.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

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Name: **Noumbissi Noundou, Xavier**
 Student ID: **20284586**
 Ontario Education Nbr: **445938806**

Winter 2013

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 9.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
CS 846	Advanced Topics in Software Engineering	0.50	0.50	88
Course Topic:	Program Analysis of Web Apps			

Spring 2013

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 10.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
ECE 750	Special Topics in Computer Software	0.50	0.50	88
Course Topic:	Static Analysis for Softwr Eng			

Fall 2013

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 11.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2014

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 12.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2014

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 13.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Fall 2014

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 14.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2015

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 15.00 Status: Enrolment

Course	Description	Attempted	Earned	Grade
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	WD

Withdrawal Date: 04/30/2015

Milestones

Program: Engineering Doctoral
 PhD Comprehensive Examination
 Status: Completed
 Date Completed: 12/20/2011
 Grade: CR

End of Graduate Official Transcript

University of Waterloo
 200 University Ave. West
 Waterloo Ontario
 Canada
 N2L3G1

Graduate Official Transcript

Duffin M. Caell
 Associate Vice-President
 Graduate Studies
 and Postdoctoral Affairs

Name: Noubissi Noundou, Xavier
Student ID: 20284586
Ontario Education Nbr: 445938806

Beginning of Graduate Record

Fall 2009

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 1.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
ECE 725	Computer-Aided Verification	0.50	0.50	90

Winter 2010

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 2.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2010

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 3.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Fall 2010

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 4.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2011

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 5.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2011

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 6.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
CS 744	Advanced Compiler Design	0.50	0.50	86

Fall 2011

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 7.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Fall 2012

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 8.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

University of Waterloo
 200 University Ave. West
 Waterloo Ontario
 Canada
 N2L3G1

Graduate Official Transcript

Duffin M. Caell
 Associate Vice-President
 Graduate Studies
 and Postdoctoral Affairs

Name: Noubissi Noundou, Xavier
Student ID: 20284586
Ontario Education Nbr: 445938806

Winter 2013

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 9.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
CS 846	Advanced Topics in Software Engineering	0.50	0.50	88
Course Topic:	Program Analysis of Web Apps			

Spring 2013

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 10.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
ECE 750	Special Topics in Computer Software	0.50	0.50	88
Course Topic:	Static Analysis for Softwr Eng			

Fall 2013

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 11.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2014

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 12.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Spring 2014

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 13.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Fall 2014

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 14.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	

Winter 2015

Program: Electrical and Computer Engineering, PhD
 Attendance: Full-Time Term: 15.00 Status: Enrolment

<u>Course</u>	<u>Description</u>	<u>Attempted</u>	<u>Earned</u>	<u>Grade</u>
GS -	Continuing Graduate Studies	0.00	0.00	WD

Withdrawal Date: 04/30/2015

Milestones

Program: Engineering Doctoral
 PhD Comprehensive Examination
 Status: Completed
 Date Completed: 12/20/2011
 Grade: CR

End of Graduate Official Transcript

CONTRAT DE BAIL PROFESSIONNEL

Entre les soussignés :

Monsieur NOUMBISSI NOUNDOU Xavier, Ingénieur-informaticien demeurant à Douala, Tél : 697 19 49 06 / 652 39 69 50. E-mail : yerith.xavier@gmail.com, titulaire de la CNI n° 20190212230510554, délivré le 15/04/2019 à LT 09 ;

Ci-après désigné le « Bailleur » d'une part ;

Et

La Société **GLOBAL EXPERT SOLUTION Sarl**, dont le siège social est fixé à Douala Cité des Palmiers, BP : 236 Douala, pris en la personne de son représentant légal en la personne de **MELEU NOSSI BELVIANNE**, née le ... 18/12/1989 ... à ... DOUALA ... fille de ... NOSSI JEAN ... et de ... MATLANG BIE titulaire de la CNI n° ... 10/14/64/255 ... délivrée le ... 17/12/2019 à ... DLA BONABER Tél : 694 913 365 / 682 766 081 ;

Ci-après désigné le « Preneur » d'autre part ;

IL A ETE CONVENU ET ARRETE ENTRE LES PARTIES CE QUI SUIT :

Le Bailleur loue par les présentes, au Preneur qui accepte, un immeuble bâti dont la désignation suit, aux clauses et conditions ci-dessous :

Article 1 : Désignation

Un appartement composé de plusieurs pièces sis à la cité de Palmiers lieu-dit Haute tension. Il n'est pas fait plus amples descriptions, le preneur déclarant l'avoir visité et connu parfaitement les lieux.

Article 2 : Durée

La durée du bail est d'une année (01) ans qui prend effet à compter du 02 Novembre 2024 et prend fin au 1^{er} Novembre 2025 et non renouvelable ;

Article 3 : Usage

Les lieux, objets du présent contrat sont destinés exclusivement au commerce. (nature du commerce) Toute destination autre donnée à cet immeuble sans l'accord écrit du bailleur est interdite.

Article 4 : Etat Des Lieux

Le preneur prend l'immeuble en l'état et fera l'objet d'un constat contradictoire pas un Huissier de Justice. Les parties constatent contradictoirement l'état des lieux et le

JH-NISSI

preneur l'accepte sans réserve. Il s'engage en outre à le garder en bon père de famille jusqu'au terme du bail.

Le preneur n'est pas autorisé à faire des transformations ou changer la forme ou la structure de l'immeuble sauf sur accord écrit du bailleur. A la fin du bail, il pourra avec l'accord du bailleur remettre l'immeuble à son état initial ou laisser ces transformations sans aucune compensation du bailleur.

Article 5 : Cession Et Sous- Location

Le Preneur ne peut ni sous - louer ni céder le présent bail à un tiers à titre gratuit ou onéreux sans l'avis écrit du bailleur.

En cas de sous - location, il est précisé de toutes façons que le Preneur restera directement responsable du paiement des loyers, ainsi que des impôts divers pouvant notamment provenir des réparations locatives ou de remise en état.

Article 6 : Assurances

Le Preneur s'engage à assurer les lieux loués contre les risques locatifs, notamment l'incendie et l'explosion, les dégâts des eaux, le recours des voisins et des tiers. Cette assurance qui se fera auprès d'une compagnie acceptée par le preneur devra être maintenue pendant toute la durée du bail.

Article 7 : Visite Des Lieux

Le Preneur devra laisser le bailleur, ses représentants ou préposés visiter les lieux loués chaque fois qu'ils le jugeront nécessaire, à charge pour le Bailleur d'en prévenir le Preneur par tout moyen à sa convenance vingt-quatre heures (24) à l'avance de cette visite. Le preneur s'engage à donner libre accès au bailleur à cette occasion et sans aucune forme d'entrave.

Article 8 : Réparation et travaux dans L'immeuble

Le Bailleur a la charge des grosses réparations notamment de construction, et de surélévation. Il peut les effectuer en cours de bail si ceux - ci deviennent nécessaires. Le preneur accepte de souffrir (sans aucune contrepartie ou indemnité) des incommodités ou inconfort causés sur tout ou partie de l'immeuble pendant l'exécution des grosses réparations qui incombent au bailleur.

Le Preneur devra aviser immédiatement le Bailleur de toutes grosses réparations à la charge de ce dernier dont il sera à même de constater la nécessité, sous peine d'être tenu pour responsable de toute aggravation résultant de son silence ou de son retard.

Le Preneur est tenu des réparations locatives, d'entretien et de maintenance. En dehors des réparations occasionnées par un cas de force majeure ou de la vétusté de l'immeuble, il est tenu des dégradations et des pertes qui arrivent par le fait des personnes de sa maison, ses agents et préposés.

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Article 9 : Eau – Electricité

Le Preneur fera son affaire personnelle, ses abonnements auprès des concessionnaires d'eau et d'électricité ainsi que du paiement de ses factures de consommation sans que le bailleur en soit inquieté.

S'il advenait que les concessionnaires viennent à enlever leurs compteurs à raison du non-paiement de leurs fournitures par le Preneur, celui-ci supportera dans leur intégralité les frais de coupure, de repose du compteur, et autres frais liés directement ou indirectement à cette situation.

Article 10 : Loyer

Le bail est consenti et accepté pour un loyer mensuel de FCFA 90 000 (Quatre-vingt-dix mille francs) net de toute charge et prestation. Ce loyer est payable annuellement et d'avance. Il est payable en espèces entre les mains du bailleur ou de ses agents, préposés dûment désignés par lui.

A la signature du présent contrat, une somme de F CFA 720 000 (SEPT CENT VINGT MILLE) est versée au bailleur et dont quittance est donnée par les présentes, représentant 8 mois de loyer.

Lorsque le paiement se fait par chèque, il n'est effectif qu'à la date à laquelle le compte du bailleur est effectivement crédité.

Article 11 : Dépôt De Garantie/Caution

Le preneur dépose à la signature des présentes, une caution de FCFA 90 000 (Quatre-vingt mille francs) FCFA. Cette caution constitue la garantie pour couvrir toute destruction ou charge non couverte par le preneur, de ses agents ou de ses préposés au moment de la libération de l'immeuble.

La caution ne sera restituée au preneur à la fin du bail, si n'a pu être utilisée comme il est dit au paragraphe précédent, qu'en cas de justificatifs de règlements des dernières factures d'eau et d'électricité.

Bien entendu, les derniers loyers et autres frais locatifs accessoires ne pourront en aucun cas s'imputer sur le dépôt de garantie.

Article 12 : révision du loyer

Les parties conviennent que le bailleur réserve le droit de réviser le montant du loyer à au renouvellement du bail. Cette révision sera en fonction des usages à Douala, ou en fonction de la formule indiciaire applicable. La révision pourra en outre, tenir compte de la conjoncture économique, eu égard au renchérissement du prix des matériaux de construction sur le marché et de l'offre de bail en cours.

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Le bailleur devra toutefois faire connaître son intention de réviser le bail soit au moins (1) mois avant la fin de la période de bail en cours ou en cours de l'exécution du bail renouvelé avec un différé d'un mois au moins pour la prise d'effet dans ce dernier cas.

Article 13 : Restitution Des Locaux - Remise Des Clés

A l'expiration du bail, le Preneur restituera les locaux à l'état initial d'occupation. Le sort des transformations éventuelles y effectuées avec l'accord du bailleur seront déterminés ainsi qu'il est dit à l'article 4.

Le preneur remettra promptement les clés au bailleur. Tout retard occasionné à cet effet et du fait du preneur entrainera une indemnité d'au moins égale à un mois du dernier loyer. En outre, toute réclamation du solde de la caution ne sera exigible qu'après remise effective des clés au bailleur et production des justificatifs de règlements des dernières factures d'eau et d'électricité, si celui-ci n'a pu être utilisé pour la réfection de l'immeuble dégradé par le preneur ou ses préposés.

Article 14 : Règlement Urbains Et De L'immeuble

Le preneur est tenu de satisfaire à toutes prescriptions de la police, de voirie municipale, d'hygiène et de salubrité pendant le cours du bail.

Article 16 : Impôts - Droit D'enregistrement

Le Preneur est tenu de s'acquitter exactement des impôts et droits d'enregistrement existant à raison de son occupation des lieux loués. En particulier, il sera tenu pour responsable du paiement dans les délais des droits d'enregistrement dus à l'établissement du présent bail ainsi qu'à chaque renouvellement.

Les parties conviennent que la remise des clés au preneur pour son occupation effective de l'immeuble n'interviendra qu'après l'enregistrement du présent bail ou la remise des frais d'enregistrement au bailleur.

Article 17 : Tolérances

Toutes les tolérances de la part du bailleur, qu'elles qu'en aient pu être la fréquence et la durée au sujet des clauses et conditions du présent contrat ne pourront jamais être considérées comme y apportant modifications ou suppression, ni génératrices d'un droit quelconque. Le bailleur pourra toujours y mettre fin à tout moment.

Article 18 : Clauses Résolutoires- Compétence

Le présent bail sera résilié de plein droit si bon semble au bailleur dans les cas suivants :

En cas de non-respect d'une seule clause ou de non-paiement d'un seul mois/terme de loyer, le présent contrat de bail sera résilié de plein droit, après une mise en demeure

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d'un mois rester sans effet. d'avoir à respecter la ou les clauses du bail violées, notifiées au preneur par acte extrajudiciaire ou par tout moyen laissant trace écrite.

En cas de résiliation, le bailleur pourra en cas de refus par le Preneur de libérer les lieux, obtenir l'expulsion de ce dernier et de tous ceux qui tiennent de son chef par simple Ordonnance du juge statuant à bref délai (juge des référés), sans préjudice des dommages - intérêts.

Les parties attribuent à cet effet compétence de juridiction aux tribunaux de première instance de Douala Ndokoti du lieu de situation de l'immeuble loué pour tout a litige qui surviendrait de l'exécution du présent contrat de bail.

La possibilité d'un règlement à l'amiable de tout différend né de l'exécution du présent contrat est toujours ouverte à la partie la plus diligente.

Articles 17 : Election De Domicile

Pour l'exécution des présentes et de leurs suites y compris la signification de tous actes, les parties élisent respectivement leur domicile, pour le bailleur à son siège social, et pour le preneur dans les lieux loués.

Fait à Douala en quatre exemplaires originaux, le 26 Novembre 2024

P/LE BAILLEUR

Dr. -Ing. Nounou

P/ LE PRENEUR

- "Detou, KEMAJOU" Cameroon's gendarmerie colonel indic PAULETTE AZEFA tried to ASSASSINATE myself, openly, in front of at least 7 people, on Yaounde street, on January 09th, 2024.
- Kemajou spouses talk to people walking across roads that they shalln't perform christian cross-signs since these interrupts sorcery they are doing on people walking on roads (June 3rd, 2024).
- Secret (hidden) orders of any type SHALL be out of civilian society.
- Cameroon SHALL DEACTIVATE any kind of army soldiers estate, as SWITZERLAND has done in the past.
- Its is not a good idea to judge people based on suspicious behavior, and not, real proven or not lived really facts.
- ROSE sangnou, a BIRTH GIVER of mine, SHALLNT ANYMORE be causing so much trouble into my life because she entertains a rostrucruan affair with Prof. Dr. rer. pol. JEAN-CLAUDE SHANDA-TONME; AND with 'DORIS beteubang Gweh', 'tchichui-teutchou-noumeni-ingride-ingrid-Chandriand', 'Hugues Ntomani Tiako'; 'Dr. Henriette Pola', and her spouse 'Dr. Laurent tchandeu'.
- People such as KEMAJOU, who acts as a colonel gendarmerie of Cameroon army ARE ALWAYS TRYING to overcome criminal laws of Geneva.
- I don't want to be living with people that prevent the killing of other people.
- Rose sangnou sister, (Justice) DOROTHEE SHANDA NDJATIE, HAS TRIED to kill me by police force illegally in February 2021, as I have a file on judge HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA at DOUALA-ndokoti JUSTICE PALACE ! • LAQUINTINE's Psychiatrist EYOUN CHRISTIAN, MD, was involved together with 8 other persons at night around 11:30PM so to hijack my privately owned property in Douala-CITE-DES-PALMIERS. • JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA from same tribal tribe as ACCUSED psychiatrist main offender (sawa-douala) ! • IT SEEMS 'Dr christian eyoun, MD' the corrupted CPDM psychiatrist wanted myself to be sodomized by 'BERTRAND' who broke the seal of my gate in steel.
- CIA (Central Intelligence Agency) shalln't hire anymore incompetent persons like 'Peter Alan Buhl' 'Emmanuel-baleba-faux-pasteur' 'Brigitte-ekindi' 'magne-narcisse-qc-satan' 'robert-billy-joe-bob-tabet-depse-pd' 'NDZIE' 'PRC-présidence de la république du Cameroun' 'CHAPELLE DE LA GLOIRE DE CHRIST - mare denis djeng djeng - alias pasteur marco' 'jp-kamgain' 'psy-acteur-ebongue (ing. pétrolier)' 'EMMANUEL-idoit; hors-mis agent-immobilier-soumbil (6 90 60 75 63)' 'sanitaire;SAPUR-POMPIER-ant-gang-civil,indic-gendarme-policier-uniforme-medec' 'NORBERT tchatat' 'Bitoung' (douanes) 'David Moniaux' 'Aurélie Yagno Kamdou' 'DR. FOSSO-sed' 'Soot-canadian' 'sarah-landy-canadian-citizen' 'tchangoue-labforge.ca' 'sandy-sed-beidu, jo-alee' 'carine-alias-edith - LELE - NJOUGE' 'TCHANAN' 'Julien-mboutou; santé publique' 'Dan Wasula waswa - so called pastor baptist church' 'KAMGA adichou - demson' 'Cameroun-chief-of-state, CAMEROUN'; 'SANDRINE yimbour' 'CHENGWA' 'DJOMO-Sawa-gilles-ézechiel' 'didi-ruben' 'mama-fouda' 'INES ngakou' 'Serge Achille Popoussi NONO - sed - cmr' '[ingride-tchichui-noumbissi;ingrid-tchichui-noumbissi;ingride-teutchou-noumeni;ingrid-teutchou-noumeni]'; '[Nkwoungano]'; '[Tchoubiang-sed-pre]'; '[NGONGANG] Hôpital Jamô' 'assassins;déglingués.' 'LAURENT-tchandeu-henriette-pola' 'YOUFFO manuela-psy-malade-mentale' 'alain-clame' 'francis magloire come nkoum' 'ZOUNPE-jacky-diane' 'Pégacie METOUMO, epse tchoutoo, hors-mis maître Pégacie METOUMO, epse tchouto' 'BYA (Paul et Chantal en particulier)' 'DAMLERCHRYSLER AG' 'Belvianne meleu nossi' 'Jean LOIC sieve' 'GLOBAL EXPERT SOLUTION sarl' 'maaman THERÈSE de OMEGA-kom-sipa-eric-joël.' 'JEAN-bernard de OMEGA-kom-sipa-eric-joël.' 'Synclair NJEUTCHA TCHANAN, hors-mis maître Synclair NJEUTCHA TCHANAN' 'BRVAN-tchamaha-ntaata-italie' 'SALIOU MOUSSA-pd' 'Aifana' 'Faustica GmbH-bavaria' 'magne-bakam-bir-dgre-sed-cameroun' 'BIR - emané-nkoa-marcelin-pierre - capitaine-mbida-dsp - mado-soeur emané-ETOGA' 'Brice sime (afriand-first-bank)' 'GUTHEBERG tchamaha ntaata' 'Sylviane MFEUKEN' 'ANICET Mfeukem' 'WANDJI ngongang Théodore' 'COLONEL cloundou-sed' 'Colonel ÉMILE bankoui (semil-sed)' 'Christopher NGOSONG (University of Buea)' 'Rainer and Gabrielle SCHULZE-SMIDT' 'Frank biya' 'M. ondréné (s2TBED-biya-franck)' 'David (GATIE SOLUTION CENTER)' 'KREYENHOP (BLG logistics, CDU politicians)' 'Achilles Kouam (PAUL fokam kammogne)' 'Thierry Nyamen (Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.)' 'catholic-church' 'Criminal-DST.' 'MOÏSE, yamkam-tebiwo' 'REZA kopae (riskview inc.)' 'Thomas NDIE DJOTTO' 'Christelle-akamba-et-autres-noms-de-akamba' 'VALERIE' 'ALT LE PLUS' 'Nestor KENFACK (N.K. quincailleur)' 'atanga-nji-paul' 'Daniela-siemens-OCS-erlangen' 'Menguéndé Mvindi' 'TCHIEUTHE' 'Audrey NGUETIE tchang' 'samaneh navabpor; amihossen vakif' 'JHANE-ayabé' 'ZABER-algérien-bremen' 'DZUKOU-tate-fotso-viviane' 'KOM-marcel-rostand-mepé' 'ines-ines-nganga-temou-FAINEANTE-suisse-bordellerie' 'VANELLE-JUNIOR-laure AZEFA-gang' 'GODRIK chekete H.' 'pasteur Landry' 'Eric JOEL KOM SIBA' 'Grégoire Owona (CPDM general secretary)' 'SANGO (Spouse Bernadette NOUNDOU(CMR-dgre)' 'gendarme essono en civil (logra-lou-aurléien)' 'GÉNÉRAL DE CORPS D'ARMÉE bouba.' 'consortium-contrad-black-ROTHSCHILD' 'GALAY-YVES-LANDRY-EFOGA-chieu' 'jean-yang-CMU' 'LOGA-LOGA-AURÉLIE' 'BORIS tossou; mbuembe-kevine-laure.' 'mezang-mvom (ingrid-loua)' 'TOM ball-msr' 'maître-docteurs-professeurs.' 'JEAN-jeanie moubeb' 'Chef-supérieur-douala.deïdo.-3ème degré' 'CHRISTIAN eyoun; laquintine; psy' 'SHANDA NDJATIE' 'MAXIME napoa eteme' '(a so called baptist church pastor)' DR. PAUL simon nomo, Psy.D.' 'Majeed Mike (quantstamp.com)' 'LEO passos (quantstamp.com)' 'iuc; mae. hypolithe tekeu.' 'Eunice GAPIE yente' 'Yves Francis DANTEU' 'TEUNTCHOU-tchandiand-noumeni' 'Winnie-shanda-joël.' 'Alexie TCHEUYAP' 'Gervais Nans' 'JEAN CLAUDE SHANDA TONME' 'Jean-Paul YAMTCHÉ (afriand first bank; intelligentsia)' 'BISSECK; nkondo-sodomiseur' 'JEAN-PIERRE kamgain' 'Bernadette NOUNDOU, EPE SANGO (cmr DGRE)' 'agent-santé.-Gallé-idiote-dodo.' 'RAOUL PRIENCE njonkep (SED)' 'ERIC BODEN' 'Prof. Dr. Xavier SESE Noundou (CMR-dgre)' 'Me. André Édoucké' 'Michèle mwondo' 'JULES nieta noum' (cmr-dgre)' 'rmp FABRICE-WILFRID-siemén-canadien-armed-forces; Prof. Dr. med. Norbert SIEMEN (CMR-sed)' 'Pharmacy fiango-DR-ngoe-peter-AKUME' 'Ondré Lhortá' 'Dr. Chantal NOUNDOU, Epse ... (cmr DGRE)' 'ANNIE METIAM' 'terreur - ;HONORE WOUICHE' 'POKAM-KWAM' 'Serge, jéru-siemén-apostolat' 'NOUMBISSI' 'Guimezap' 'GEORGETTE' 'Victor Noundou Koliou cmr-sed' 'Christian rikong nyoyong' 'Hilaire-yvonne-bertrand-nguere; ancien-sed-gras-savoie' 'CLOVIS-kemgne' 'Jeanne MWONDO' 'CHETA' 'rodrique-alain-sienchen-ngongang' 'angela WOLFGANG fernand JR owona' 'fanfan (GAUTHIER) SHANDA tonme' 'DR. GADJUE Francis aimé tchana' 'ute' 'Patrick lam, Ph.D., P.Eng.' 'JON eyolfsson' 'Prof. Dr. rer. nat. Jan Peleska' 'churches; in USA-abroad; or whatsoever similar; so-called humanitarianism.' 'Patrick' 'YAGER MABOMA' to try to kill humble black engineers and scientists.
- People like PAUL BIYA shalln't be called president of all Cameroon anymore because as CPDM ruling party, they harass people that don't call themselves from RDPCI!

CONTACT

- Address: YECEFOIQ - "Immeuble YERITH"- barrière - Simbock, Mfoundi 6, Yaounde, Cameroon
- located opposite side of Biya's S2TBED forestry society (since 2015 officially) !
• Email: Yerith.Xavier@gmail.com

CITIZENSHIP ; PLACE OF BIRTH

Cameroonian, no other citizenship ; Douala (Littoral, Cameroon)

UPLOADED a copy of national id (N.20190242230510554) onto 'https://www.facebook.com' this year 2024.

TEACHING STATEMENT

- 1. [Teaching] and [Advising] is my priority at time since in Cameroon Software inception is very long and tedious because Cameroon authorities, Especially SED.
2. My 1st professor and best educator is [prof. dr. rer. nat. habil. JAN-peleska], at the University of Bremen, Bremen, Germany; The 1st best teacher as of now was "prof. dr. dr. ULRICH KRAUSE, at the University of Bremen; as well"; THE 2nd best teacher as of now was "[Prof. Dr.-Ing. Patrick] Lam, at the [University of Waterloo, ONTARIO, CANADA]".
3. I endeavor to teach what makes my research vivid ["RM: Program Software Runtime Monitoring"] and useful for young and adult people around the world; I can teach almost everything in Computer Sciences; I haven't practiced Computer Graphics, and Computer Imaging programming at all.

RESEARCH GOALS IN COMPUTER SOFTWARE ENGINEERING - [CONTINUED]

- 1. Create a very cheap and pragmatic Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) software; (e.g. YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM[?]).
2. CREATE a market place where stock exchanges occur real-time; [YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME] is used as platform for valuation of stocks; And for stock exchanges. THE market place is a physical place in "YERITH-R&D building"; THE physical stock exchanges occur outside of "YERITH-R&D building"; just a plot of land '5 meters' away on the opposite side of road leading to "YERITH R&D" !
3. CREATE a computing device for YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF that would be a certified product with at least ISO, and CE stamps : [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET]; See also Fig. 13.
4. CREATE a software component full-featured that enables ERP-stock data import using a technology Kind-of VOICE-to-text !

PROFESSIONAL COMPUTING ASSOCIATIONS MEMBERSHIPS

- Current: "acm: The Association for Computing Machinery"; "FME: Formal Methods Europe"; "ASQ: American Society for Quality".

PROFESSIONAL COMPUTING LITERATURE REVIEWS

- OOPSLA 2010

PROFESSIONAL INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOPS AND CONFERENCES

- IMRT radiation therapy at SIEMENS OCS Erlangen-BAVARIA-Germany 2008; [FSE-soqua 2006]; PLDI 2009; IBM CASCON 2010; MITACS ONTARIO 2012; PLDI 2012

PROFESSIONAL RESEARCH CONTRIBUTIONS / INTERESTS

- [JUDICIAL information] | [PUBLICATIONS] | [Figures] | [Tables] | [Latest] | [Resume / CV - Overview] | Publications list on "www.zenodo.org" | Publications list on "www.archive.org"
• Operating System Debian Linux Distribution Contribution for customers of "YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0"; "YERITH-NISSI.". Bash; DEBIAN LINUX; Jan. 2017 -
• ERP-trading Stock Exchange Software: "YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0[?]" ; git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0 C++; Qt 5; Oct. 2015 -
• Software Engineering-Formal Methods [?][1][c] / Software Validation / Software Verification CASE tools "YRI_QVGE[24.24]", "RT-Tester, MBT[1b]"]
• Software Testing [22.22] (also with "VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GMBH") "YRI_QVGE[?b]", [MASTER THESIS[?]], "RT-Tester, MBT[1b]"], "JUNIT 4 Tutorial[1]"
A. Web Applications ("JAVA Dynamic Taint Analysis[3]" | Qt 5-Designer as WYSIWYG Tool for web pages | Development (YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0))
1. JudoDB, with "Dr. Patrick Lam (doctor-Ph.D. advisor of mine)"; git https://github.com/patricklam/judodb GWT, PHP; JAVA; June 2014 - Nov. 2014
B. "WEB Cyber-Security Analysis[2] [3] [?]" (PLG SEMINAR AT DAVID R. CHERITON SCHOOL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)
C. Information Flow Policy Control; Typestate-API usage rule checking; "Dynamic Program Analysis Monitoring"
?f "A Runtime Monitoring Mealy Machine C++ library"; git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif C++; Qt 5; June 2022 -
? "Algorithmic trading [12.12.7]" | "YERITH_QVGE: A Framework for Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime"
FOSS Code location, EXCEPT for commercial CASE drawing tool : git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif C++; Qt-DBus; June 2022 -
3 "A Dynamic Taint Analysis for PHP in Quercus"; git https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis JAVA; Firebug; Jan. 2013 - Apr. 2013
D. "Static Program Code Analysis Verification; Compilers; Verifiable DSL (Verifiable Domain-Specific Languages)"
20.20 Open Source (FOSS) Contribution to "Valkyrie: Valgrind-GUI"; git https://github.com/yerithrd/valkyrie_NON_OFFICIAL C++; Qt 5; July 2023 -
1d "Vordiplom-B.Sc. Independent Study: A Semantic Comparison between Timed Automata and Büchi Automata" Set-Algebra; Sep. 2004 - Dec. 2004
23 "Ph.D. disser.: A Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM"; git https://github.com/AmesianX/saint LLVM; C++; JAVA
?d "A State Diagram Mealy Machine Description Language"; git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang flex, bison; Apr. 2023 -
21 "JAVA static code analysis [23]" | "Ph.D. thesis: Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software" LLVM; SOOT; JAVA

SUMMER SCHOOL PARTICIPATION — HIGHLIGHTS — [CONTINUED]

- "Management Psy Human Resource Course" - Collège Integ, Douala, Littoral, Cameroun — Taught by "Dr. Jean Moubeb, Psy.D." Jan. 2020 - June 2020

CHEFTAINCY / MISCELLANEOUS

- KING YERITH-NISSI. (Prophet of Jeovah-nissi, "Isaiah 45" (SINCE nov. 14; 2014) in HOLY BIBLE, PAROLE DE VIE-(Amis pour toujours) - French language)
• I also act as a Prophet described in "Apocalypse 12".
• I also act as a Prophet described in "Apocalypse 1", named "Fidèle, et Véritable".
• Creator and Professor at YECEFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE), a subsidiary of YERITH R&D
• "High Qualified Person-migrant in CANADA (Québec, then Ontario) for 9 years until August 2014".
• Driving license class B - Cameroon & Canada

PROFESSIONAL TOOLS AND PROGRAMMING LANGUAGES

- **Operating Systems:** MS Windows (XP, 98, 2000, 7, 10, 11), DEBIAN LINUX (8, 9, 10, 11, 12)
- **SCM (Source Code Version Management Tools):** Git, Mercurial (hg), SVN, Rational ClearCase
- **Web Technologies:** MariaDB, HTML5, CSS, PHP, Quercus, Apache Tomcat, GWT (Google Web Toolkit), JSP
- **Scripting Languages:** Cygwin, Python, sed, AWK, Bash
- **Programming languages, Debugging, and Testing Analysis tools:** [YRI_QVGE\[12.12\]](#), UML 2.0, SCALA, JAVA, C/C++, JUnit-5, DDD, Gcov, [VALKYRIE YERITH\[20.20\]](#), LTSA
- **Programming and Compiler Frameworks:** DIFF, Patch, Tx1, apache ANT, MAKE, Qt 5, S00T, LLVM, flex, bison, Eclipse IDE, CodeBlocks, CharmNT

UNIVERSITY LEVEL TEACHING (AS A TEACHING ASSISTANT PH.D. CANDIDATE; THEN A "DOCTOR-PHD")

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA (OCTOBER 2009 – APRIL 2015)

- [Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance \(ECE 453 / SE 465\)](#) | [Methods and Tools for Software Engineering \(ECE 650\)](#) | [Foundations of Software Engineering \(ECE 651\)](#) | [Programming for Performance \(ECE 459\)](#) | [Computer Networks \(ECE 428\)](#) | [Compilers \(ECE 351\)](#) | [\[C++ Laboratory \(ECE 250\)\]](#).

ACADEMY WORK RESEARCH EXPERIENCE – 1

- [Start-up YERITH R&D, Yaounde, CENTER region, CAMEROON](#)
Professor (Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.) for Computer Software Engineering at YECEFOIQ, CEO
- [IUC \(Institut Universitaire de la Côte\), Douala, Littoral region, CAMEROON](#) 2019
Web Software Developer Consultant (NUMERHIS-ERP Web Application Development); advised by Hypolithe Tekeu, MASC
- [IAI \(Institut Africain d'Informatique\) Cameroon, Yaounde, Center, CAMEROON](#) 2016
Professor (Prof.) – Consulting Lecturer (Computer Architecture for Software Engineers in anglophone section); advised by: Ing. (B.Sc.) Salabessi (and Mr. Nanga)
- [Professional and Academic Degree \[Ph.D. in Computer Science \(Specialization : Software Engineering\)\]](#) March 10, 2015 !
University of Waterloo, Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA
PhD Comprehensive Examination – ECE-University of Waterloo December 20, 2011 !
PhD Research Seminar [TALK] – ECE-University of Waterloo April 16, 2014
PhD Dissertation Defence – CS-University of Waterloo January 2015
doctoral "Ph.D. degree" dissertation (Excerpt of Full not required text, by Patrick LAM, Ph.D.): *Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM*
(April 20, 2025) Addendum of co-related research in Program Analysis: *Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software by Program Analysis FOR Safety & Security* (https://www.archive.org/details/yerith-program-analysis-2023/YERITH-PROGRAM_ANALYSIS_2024_With_CURRICULUM_vitae_2024.pdf)
- [The University of Waterloo \(ECE at WatForm\), Ontario, CANADA](#) September 01, 2012 – March 10, 2015
Professor (Postdoctoral Fellow; Prof. – Expert in a domain of science) of [RESEARCH] & [TEACHING] (program analysis & software testing research, and teaching (also related courses) | around \$2, 500 Canadian dollars for a term payment; 8 terms in total ≈ 2 – years.
"Graduate-student 1: Divam Jain (CS-MMATH, JAVA-S00T) | Graduate-student 2: Zheng (Felix) Fang (ECE-MASC, Divam's research continuation)"
"Advisor 1: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Igor Ivkovic | Advisor 2: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Vijay Ganesh | Advisor 3: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Patrick Lam | Advisor 4: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Sivoththaman Siva"
"Colleague 1: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Ondřej Lhoták | Colleague 2: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Nomair Naeem | Colleague 3: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Fabrice Wilfried Siemeni | Colleague 4: Prof. Dr. Godrick H. Chékété | Colleague 5: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. mahesh tripunitara | Colleague 6: Prof. Dr. Derek Rayside | Colleague 7: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. LEO passos | | "Colleagues in christianity (Prof. Dr. Yaw Boakye-Agyeman, Nana Yaw, Eric Brefo-Mensah, Chiwanza Kasanga, Mushota Kasanga and spouse Timi) – -ATTENDED "koinonia church in bloomingdale, ON"; "apostle continuation church in brampton, ON"."
- [IBM CANADA Ltd., Markham, Ontario, CANADA \(SABBATICAL-year from The-University-of-Waterloo-Ontario-Canada.\)](#) January 01, 2012 – August 31, 2012
Thorough security check screening done for employment by employer IBM Canada LTD before starting employment.
Graduate Intern (JAVA-J9 Just-In-Time Compilation Optimization for IBM Websphere); advised by Prof. Vijay Sundaresan; and Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam
- [PROFESSIONAL \(AND ACADEMIC\) DEGREE. Doctor of Engineering \[Dr.-Ing.\] \(academic equivalent to a "doctoral PhD in Electrical and Computer Engineering"\)](#) | around \$2, 500 Canadian dollars for a term payment; 7 terms in total ≈ 2 – years.
[Engineering Doctoral Program \(Electrical and Computer Engineering\)](#) at The University of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA September 01, 2009 – December 20, 2011 !
Department of Electrical & Computer Engineering (ECE) – Grade 88% [A+]
Research Proposal (doctoral Ph.D. Thesis in Electrical and Computer Engineering): *Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software*
Mathematics Subject Classification: 68—Computer Science
Computer Science Subject Classification: Software Engineering, Program Verification, Program Analysis (static code analysis, dynamic program analysis)
Advisor 1: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Nomair Naeem | Advisor 2: Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Ondřej Lhoták | Advisor 3: Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam | Advisor 4: Prof. Dr. Sivoththaman Siva
- [The University of Waterloo \(ECE at WatForm\), Ontario, CANADA](#) September 01, 2009 – December 20, 2011
Teaching Assistant & Research Assistant in Computer Software Engineering (program analysis (static code and dynamic analysis) research, and teaching assistantship in computer software engineering); Advised by Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam, and Prof. Dr. Sivoththaman Siva
- [Post-Master Work with SIEMENS Healthineers \(OCS – Varian\), Erlangen, Bayern, GERMANY](#) November 01 2007 – July 31 2009
Thorough security check screening done for employment by employer "SIEMENS AG" before starting employment.
Junior Software Developer (CE-FDA certified software code development; Radiation Therapy DMIP communication control protocol C++ development); advised by: Ing. (M.Sc.) DARIO MERAVIDGLIA, and Dipl.-Inf. (FH) GERHARD SENG.
- [PROFESSIONAL \(AND ACADEMIC\) DEGREE. Diplom-Informatiker \(academic equivalent to a "Master 2 in Computer Science"\)](#) | around \$400 Euros for a semester payment; 11 semesters including GERMAN language courses time included.
I HAVE SACRED this diploma certificate ("Duplicate by Prof. Dr.-Ing. UTE bormann and Prof. Dr. Kerstin Schill; from November 01, 2017") in front of BISHOP at St-Patrick Church in Toronto-downtown, ONTARIO, CANADA; just 3 weeks after resigning; my shit-CANADIAN CITIZENSHIP at KITCHENER-WATERLOO criminal justice court ([Living in Salvation Army Shelter near Justice Court.](#)).
["Diplom-Informatiker" degree program](#) at The Elite-University of Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY October 01, 2002 – May 25, 2007
Department of Mathematics and Computer Science – Grade 1.6/4 [A+]
Diplomarbeit (Master Thesis): *Statistical test case generation for reactive systems* | Advisor: Prof. Dr. Jan Peleska
- [AGBS at The University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY](#) September 01, 2006 – February 28 2007
(Part-Time) Software System Developer (A 'UML 2.0 statecharts' plugin for 'Borland-Together'); advised by: Prof. Dr. Jan Peleska
- ["IMMIGRATION CANADA delivers myself a High Qualified Person-migrant permanent residency for CANADA"](#) 2005
Family member in Canada: "Théodore Wandji Ngongang (5850 Rue Souart Apt 7, H3S 2E8, Montreal, QC, Canada)"
I already passed my Bachelor's degree in CS ("[Vordiplom in Informatik Certificate](#)") before gaining High Qualified Person Permanent Resident Card
- [Bergmann Automaten GmbH \(now Gewete GmbH\), Rellingen, Hamburg, GERMANY](#) March 01, 2005 – April 31, 2007
(Part-Time) Software System Developer (JAVA servlet and (C++) communication protocol development); advised by: Dipl.-Ing. (FH) SVEN KAMRATH (and Dipl.-Ing. JENS MÖLLER)
- [ZMML at The University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY](#) February 01, 2003 – February 28, 2005
(Part-Time) WEB AND "RAD" APPLICATION DEVELOPER (Creating websites, and RAD-server self tests evaluation programs); advised by Prof. Dr. rer. pol. Klaus Jürgen Bönkost

FREE TIME HOBBIES

- Aikido, Swimming, and "Gospel Choir 'GEORGIA MASS CHOIR'" listening.

ACADEMY WORK RESEARCH EXPERIENCE – 2

- ~~HABILITATION, equivalent~~ • Topic: "Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime" June 01, 2022 – Currently
Start-up YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, CAMEROON
Proposal: YERITH_QVGE: A Framework for Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime (Details at link ?)
- Start-up YEROTH R&D, Yaounde, CENTER region, CAMEROON October 2018 – November 2023
Software Verification & Validation Fellow, CEO
- Start-up Yeren Labs, Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA September 2017 – September 2018
CTO (Chief Technology Officer), CEO
- Start-up Yeren, Yaounde, CENTER region, CAMEROON March 2015 – August 2017
CTO (Chief Technology Officer), CEO
- × [PKFokam Research Institute, Yaounde, Center, CAMEROON]
Professor (Prof.)–Ph.D.–seeker (Static Code Analysis Research from WATERLOO.); advised by: [Dr. PAUL fokam kammogne], & [Dr. Ing. JUSTIN bomda]; [and M. Samuel DIMITE]
"JAN-peleska" & "University of Waterloo" try to hijack myself through this 2-days-job-contract
[All people pro-eminent persons I have seen at his banks, "including Deceased gay-pd GERVAIS mendoze", are in prison !!! (419-scam)]
- Judo–Québec, Montreal, Quebec, CANADA JUNE 2014 – NOVEMBER 2014
(Part-Time) Web Development Consultant (JAVA SE 7, GWT, PHP) for JUDODB; advised by: Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam
- RiskView Inc., Toronto, Ontario, CANADA January 2013
Software Consultant for Finance Software Security (SCALA servlet development for Finance); advised by: Reza Kopae, M.Sc.
- We4IT GmbH, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY June 2005 – July 2005
Software Development Internship (J2EE, MySQL web application for medical personal training management); advised by Dipl.–Inf. Stephan Sucker
- SGS Cameroon, Douala, littoral REGION, CAMEROON September 2004
System administration internship (Computer networked installation; employee desktop technical support; (MS Windows NT, MS Windows 2000, etc.); advised by CHENGWA, & ...)
- bremen4u GmbH, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY March 2004
Web development internship, System Administration (MySQL, RedHat linux, JSP, PHP, HTML5, CSS); advised by Martin, B.Sc.
- IWT at The University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY October 2002 – January 2003
(Part-Time) Student Metal Processing & Measurement Helping Scientist; advised by: Dipl.–Ing. Sven Bengelsdorf.
- DaimlerChrysler AG, Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY June 2002 – August 2002
Industrial Chain Worker (Kfz–Schlosser Helper); setting of Mercedes personal cars seat belts
- Brüel & Kjær, Technology Park – University of Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY July 2002 – September 2002
(Part-Time) Student Helper (event management); advised by: Dipl.–Pol. Torben (and Dr. Woehring)
- Cyberix, Douala, Littoral region, CAMEROON October 2001 – November 2001
Web Development Internship (HTML, CSS); advised by: Ing. Fogueum (and Théodore Wandji Ngongang)
- GCE A Level in Exact Sciences; BACCALAURÉAT C (Mathematics, etc.) 2000
Grade of "11.59 / 20"
Douala, LITTORAL region, CAMEROON
- GCE O Level in Exact Sciences; PROBATOIRE C (Mathematics, etc.) 1999
Grade of "12.09 / 20"
Douala, LITTORAL region, CAMEROON
- B.E.P.C (Brevet d'Études DU PREMIER CYCLE) 1997
Douala, LITTORAL region, CAMEROON
- C.E.P.E (CERTIFICAT D'ÉTUDES PRIMAIRES ÉLÉMENTAIRES) 1993
Douala, LITTORAL region, CAMEROON

PROFESSIONAL COMMUNICATION LANGUAGES

- FRENCH, and ENGLISH CAMEROON; NATIVE
- "GERMAN DSH LANGUAGE CERTIFICATE", Sehr Gut (Very Good) April 2002 (UNIVERSITY OF DORTMUND, DORTMUND, NRW, Germany)
- "ENGLISH USA TOEFL–IBT", Grade 86 June 2018 (Hamilton, Ontario, Canada)

[SUMMER SCHOOL PARTICIPATION] – ADDENDUM

- "Online Software Security Course" – Stanford University, California, USA June 2013 – August 2013
- "CUT 1 – Certificate in University Teaching1" – University of Waterloo, Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA 2010
- "First Summer School on Formal Techniques" – NSF, SRI International, Menlo College, Atherton, California, USA May 22, 2011 – May 27, 2011
- "Graduate Student English Training Course" – Université du Québec à Montréal (UQAM), Montreal, Quebec, Canada Aug. 2009
- "Graduate Management Admission Test (GMAT) Preparation Course" – Concordia University, Montreal, Quebec, Canada June 2007
- "C Programming Language Preparation Course" – UY 1, ENSPY, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon — Taught by "Master–1 Mr. Donfack (ENSPY)" Aug. 2001 – Sep. 2001

5. *Create a framework that allows for formal method specification of static dataflow analyzes as temporal property verification formulas; Such a framework generate code software as static staged dataflow analyzes for its users. More importantly, I will try to reuse previous work done for [YRI_QVGE\[12.12\]](#) research work, as part deliverable.*
6. *TRY to integrate research results on software security in "YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum "; from Vijay GANESH research (<https://research.gatech.edu/people/vijay-ganesh>); MOST possibly using "SDMM".*
7. *Automatic generation of web HTML pages from a Domain Specific Language (DSL) that is more approachable for a high level programming language perspective (i.e: similar to C++ / JAVA): YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0[27.27].*
8. *Create and render software analysis, debugging, and testing tools as easy as possible to use, with only finite automata theory background; and / or Tpestate-API usage rule checking tpestate-API knowledge (e.g.: [YERITH-SAINT\[23\]](#), [SDMM\[?d\]](#), [YRI_QVGE\[12.12\]](#), VALKYRIE-VALGRIND[20.20]).*
9. *Prepare a course on "Software System Security Vulnerability Detection and Analysis". I prepare this course material so to implement a software system for protecting other software from malware.*
10. *Create a stand-alone tool that generates code for creating statechart C++ code for mealy machine state diagram ([SDMM\[?d\]](#)). This tool is specifically created and programmed for generating code that uses checkboxes to select options for Graphical User Interface [GUI] code.*
11. *Position "static dataflow analysis research and techniques" as similar as runtime verification (i.e.: circle 4 in Figure 9; e.g.:PH.D. THESIS[21], [YERITH-SAINT\[23\]](#)).*
12. *Create and produce a computer device that could be embedded into other computer devices and that will communicate with them through serial ports and / or USB interfaces SO to provide YRI_QVGE program verification to USER FINISHED products on-the-fly, AS an add-on ENGINEERED industrial product: ALSO this product could qualify for an CE—ISO—related certification for avionics, railways, automotive, and CE—ISO certifications for Healthcare : [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET].*

1.1 CAMEROON new country name based on CHRISTIANITY-jesus-of-nazareth-NAME-and-TRIBES-number

Changing CMR onto YERITH as country name since JESUS-OF-Nazareth utilizes 12 237 as number of tribes for its ISRAEL tribe.

2.2 National Currency BILLS and / or COINS

- CMR YERITH NATIONAL Money currency as 'YERITH-dollar ("JESUS-OF-Nazareth"-dollar)'.

THIS money currency bill and / or coin system will be backed by computing systems from YERITH R&D; AS open-sourced products :

- 1.) YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME; A software-system product created out of Enterprise Resource Planing Software YRI_QVGE[12.12.7] that is also usable as an algorithmic trading system !

3.3 National Identification

1. A system allowing any of the 3 documents cited below as valid official identification for any official or unofficial activity shall be implemented in Central CEMAC:

1. Valid NATIONAL IDENTITY CARD
2. Valid PASSPORT CEMAC-CEDEAO
3. Valid bank account id.
4. ALL PERSONS working with weapons or force by law have to be identified with names on badge wherever they are outside of their working places.

A bank account id IS in effect linked to a Valid national identity card.

""MOÏSE YAMKAM TEBIWO (Mtn-network: 6 75 66 24 87)" for instance, a cousin paternal "French-germain" of mine, Could afford for a law school with a bank account that wasn't really linked with his by birth official IDENTITY documents !"

MOÏSE YAMKAM TEBIWO (Mtn-network: 6 75 66 24 87) also possesses a diplomatic passport at least or equivalent because he also works for MINREX.

IN effect, "MOÏSE YAMKAM TEBIWO (Mtn-network: 6 75 66 24 87)" was a diplomat before joining the LAW-school in LAGOS-corrupt.

I could notify this since the law school of lagos he attended didn't issue for a certificate with exact same official birth identity names as written thereof.

THIS COUSIN OF MINE IS A CRIMINAL in all systems of justice worldwide.

2. 1 system, computerized, and / or, a text registry book shall be created to register any Cameroon citizen with no need for any citizen to walk around with a national identity card.
3. There are some drawbacks as for instance mentioned on the website of FREE SOFTWARE FOUNDATION, in the United States of America (USA), to have a centralized registration system for citizen or People living inside a country !
4. *"A gervais nana (gersatelgmail.com)" I know somewhere in YDE, seems to be connected as a free-mason to ""MOÏSE YAMKAM TEBIWO"" .*
"GERVAIS NANA" must be investigated since I know "TEBIWO-YAMKAM-MOÏSE" Is a murderer in all systems.
5. I remember having an issue with a screen of a laptop I bought to a place (GERSATEL) owned by *"Gervais NANA"* ; after 1 day, A blur appeared on the screen and I wasn't reimbursed.
6. *It seems "WELADJI" a burglar that I went with at Gendarmerie D'AKWA-SUD in 2023 because he apparently tried to steal 20, 000 FRANCS as a non used money for a purchase item that I ordered from his shop at DLA-douala-bar;*
"WELADJI" WAS NOW in position in another shop where I started buying stuff for my customers. "Moubeb-Jean" is working just at opposite side of this computer hardware shop in Douala: "COLLEGE INTEG".
7. *"ISAAC TEUNTCHOU-poltron-peggist" , a father in law of 1 uterine sister of my person; "Ingride-NOUMBISSI-TCHITCHUI (heiratet (SPOUSE)-Dipl.-Ing. (FH)-CHANDRIAND-Teuntchou-Noumeni, MSc.)" is trying to hijack from my propriety all my real-estate.*
8. *shanda-tonne-jean-claude; bob-tabet-peggist-Deido-plage-poisson-braisé, the idiot that sleeps with rose-sangnou my genitor; AND with her sister Dorothée shanda owona" (LEVITICUS 20 : 12 - 14)."*
"OLAMCAM (tel.:6 52 12 65 57 --georges-kamdem) (peggist working in Douala shipment-haven) owner Tabet-bob (OWNING a house in "bonaberi"; money from bribery in ONTARIO according to JP-kamgain sayings) & friends GEORGES-kamdem; & JP-kamgain; they have tried to sodomize myself with Christian-eyoum-c.p.d.m [by trying to say to JP-kamgain-to act as a friend-of-myself]. "
"BOB-tabet is an ancient jail-black-attendee of ONTARIO justice system that escaped Canada by talks I heard [of KAMGAIN].""
"[Culprit-JP-kamgain] told me once [TABET-ROBERT]-wanted-HR-module payment services for his employees in DOUALA.'
9. *ISAAC-teuntchou, the idiot that sleeps with his daughter-in-law; TEUNTCHOU-noumeni-chandriand is currently trying to hijack my property of DLA-cité-des-palmiers-beedi, BY Sending INGRID to my attorney of law so to try to say that SHE wants some money from my current ongoing rental agreement with a so called MELEU-belvianna, AND her fiancée called SEWE-idiot-toie.*
10. *"Audrey-NGUETIE-tehamga" shalln't anymore go and seek people from my former places of work to try to tell them I abandon her after 1-night.*
THIS disgusting megere wasn't capable of understand I cannot be fornicating with someone that Cannot imagine herself as a wife in a non-gay homosexual matrimonial house AS i could observe from her gay-white-salsa friends & sister "YOLLANDE-nguetie married at that other senegalese in Montreal
"TCHAMAHA-ntaata-GUTTEMBERG" & "Remi-POUASSI-taata" who are my blood-family (father-theo-chien-noumbissi-batchieu-babouantou) cousins & 'also blood-village people of MAURICE-nguetie' & 'Audrey-nguetie-tehamga;' SHALL know that Homosexuality is a disease from a BORN-again christian point of view: ITS cure is living without any sexual encountering as proclaimed in " 1 Corinthians 7 : 1 " & " 1 Corinthians 7 : 38-40 " !

Following items from previous page; JUSTICE and PAST-MEMORIES to heal in Cameroon

9. Multiple or DOUBLE citizenship **SHALL NOT be allowed** since Africans are not well behaved to use and observe strict rules that are due to protect civilians with only 1 citizenship appurtenance.
10. Double citizenship with following countries that harasses honest Cameroonian like myself shalln't be allowed:
- Canada
 - United States of America (USA)
 - Germany
 - Any country where a gay-homosexual-marriage is pronounced in a so-called **"JESUS-OF-NAZARETH"** congregation: I.E: such a country shall be considered a scam **"(LEVITICUS 20 : 12 – 13, and Romans 1 : 26 – 28) !"**

SIMPLICE-kameni and alike people must be imprisoned.

HJACKING properties and down-casting businesses of elite-intellectualist from abroad like myself and others I may not even know about is what make them have a life luxurious around C.P.D.M and SED-yves-landry-galax-etoga-idiot; so called secret-services.

" THERE is also another "negger" working on behalf of simplice-kameni as LEAD of the so-called-cocaine-reseller wood-factory S2T-BED, called IDIOT-repeating-christian-signs; that behave like so-called "TONTON-makout' in HAITI-movies; (<https://wwwurl>) YOU see this kind of people that kills under behalf of a politician like BIYA; AND that you cannot even prosecute because there is no whereabouts of his origins or identities here in Cameroon-official-Communaute-URBAINE-de-YAOUNDE. "

" !! ALSO this biya-cpdm-gang against a proper african descendant on AFRIKA-soil Has a motto: ABSURDITY !!! "

FACTS:

1. kill where life is supposed to be saved;
Example: USE your own blood-giver to hijack your life and properties [REFERENCE.]

HOSPITAL is used to destroy lives.

2. destroy where it is supposed to be killed;

POLICE and ARMY kill people that go to them for seeking help after being robbed or whatsoever here in AFRIKA;

so called **UNITED-nations** (<https://www.un.org>) are only a replacement for colonies by white-supremacists.

- IT seems it is cameroon-cpdm-people who are UNITED nations workers here in CMR; HERE.

4.4 JUSTICE and PAST-MEMORIES to heal in Cameroon

1. [~~Dr. PAUL Siméon nomo, from MONATÉLÉ came to my private house in YDE-AAHALA, to arrest illegally without any notification or whatsoever, using a firefighter truck and 3 firefighter to molest myself in front of several neighbors so to discredit my life as a peaceful citizen of Cameroon.~~]
~~HE seems this criminal assassin from BIYA private places is now living in Maryland, USA; since I went back to Canada to resign from CANADIAN-shit citizenship.~~
 Another cousin of mine so called "~~Rodrigue Alain Sienchie~~", told me that 1 day armed soldiers with uniforms came to arrest him in the house of his parents, sent by "~~Dorothée SHANDA-NDJATIE OWONA~~"; THEN went to sodomized him at LAQUINTINIE HOSPITAL.
 "SO I SUSPECT this criminal ~~LAURENT TCHANDEU-DJATIE DOROTHÉE OWONA~~ to have sent to my private house in Yaounde in 2017 this 'so called baptist church pastor Dr. SIMEON NOMO, PSY.D.'."
2. "~~Eyoum Christian~~" idiot's immunity of justice because he is a psychiatrist Must be investigated !
3. '~~S2TBED~~', finally repairs our main common road: They destroyed a previous road with LATERITE so much that IT must be fixed with concrete !
4. '~~S2TBED~~', biya's illegal industrial forestry enterprise society, an illegal neighbor of "Immeuble YERITH" of mine, IS constantly disrupting electrical energy current supply:
5. ALL my real estate in Douala (3 3-bedrooms apartments) need to be released by a genitor of mine THAT is not anymore wanted in my life because of all atrocities SHE CONSTANTLY commits with SHANDA GREGROIRE OWONA Wolfgang TCHAMOU angela ndjatie. !!!
 SISTER'S of Rose Sangnou my genitor, Dorothée Shanda Ndjatie, IS CONSTANTLY harassing her to take me to any psychiatric institute by force, Even though there is already a criminal investigation against her and Rose Sangnou at DLA-ndokoti justice palace; DOROTHÉE is a criminal PERSON !
6. 'MADO's brother CAPTAIN pierre marcellin emana nkoa' must reimburse back my 210 000 FRANCS since SEMIL (Sécurité Militaire) told me in 2016 THAT THEY CANNOT convoke them SINCE receipts were signed by his cousin "JEAN-DE-DIEU onana".
 "MY NEIGHBOR CARINE LELE NJOUGEPE TCHANA", seems to be here because of them, so to deteriorate the quality of life of legal people living here, and promote their own-beings through propoganda LIKE 'it seems THE colonel living THERE above of the hill IS the one that FIXED the road leading to your compound !
7. JUSTICE FOR BREAKING AND torturing myself ('Xavier noumbissi Noundou [Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.]') in front of at least 17 people in front of my inherited personal domicile in Douala-Béedi-Cite-des-Palmiers MUST be finalized before Cameroon election 2025.
8. 'JUSTICE president and certain types of judges must be apolitical: I.e.: THEY CANNOT BELONG TO A POLITICAL PARTY !
9. MARTINEZ ZOGO assassin AMOUGOU BELINGA justice criminal court must be finished before Cameroon election 2025.
10. PEOPLE responsible for the drama of Edea Railway Failure in .. MUST be judged in a civil criminal court before Cameroon election 2025.
11. MILITARY SOLDIERS that killed about "7 women and their teddies in north Cameroon must be judged."
12. "EDGARD ALAIN MEBE NGO'O" criminal procedure in military justice courts must be achieved before Cameroon election 2025.
13. Military Soldier must have their own facilities and amenities in cities, and not mixed intermingle anymore with civilians, AS THIS IS CURRENTLY THE CASE when they DON'T wear military attire uniform !
 In fact, MILITARY SOLDIERS or Alike don't have a same behavior justice as civilians; Not talking about habits and gesture.
14. Bepanda drama because of 'general MPAY' must be re-recovered in a justice palace court of civilians and / or military justice !

5.5 ACADEMY and Technology Research Institutions

1. Promote creation of research centers for solving problems located specifically in central west Africa:
 1. Another source of revenue for CMR
 2. Improving life conditions for CMR and neighboring friend countries.
2. Enable a financing WITH non reimbursement option for doctors in science and / or engineering.

6.6 Employments and JOBS creation for adult people

1. THERE must be a minimum amount of jobs offer for each society that was funded by the government for researching and improving life quality in CMR and neighboring countries.
2. *WOMEN that are selling goods outside of their home like "CAROLE mangue" (la fille de "MA-bernadette" au secrétariat-d'état-yves-idiot.) shalln't be part of SED or any governmental secret or not agencies !!!*
THIS culprit shall also try to not resell goods that were illegally imported into CMR.
3. ALL PEOPLE that were trained by the BIYA-regime as illegal para-military personal, MUST go into peace-keeper corps organization of the UNITED NATIONS or somewhere else so to keep cities and villages free of fire and all other destructive people.

FOR instance people like "PASCAL dayang", working at "S2TBED" of the culprit franck-biya has insinuated to myself that HE will disrupt any business activities that I-doctor-of-engineering Xavier NOUMBISSI NOUNDOU will perform in my compound !!!

["S2TBED"- "PASCAL dayang mercenary SED soldier" as threat in CMR !!!]

4. Transform all wood factories within city of YAOUNDE in computer desktop and / or laptop assembly production units

7.7 JUSTICE and DIVINITIES

1. *Destruction of all secret services units in Cameroon !!*
 1. "OUATARA people shall not anymore be opponent to christian people here in Cameroon as it is the case with Shanda-TONME jean claude" presently.
 2. People like SHANDA OWONA harass other people because they feel as safest as possible because of some kind of impunity based on their appurtenance to DGRE special unit forces ("JEAN CLAUDE shanda tonme and spouse" weren't for instance infringed in DLA-NDOKOTI palace for breaking into my compound, closed at night, with around 9 burglars; So called Technicians of "PSY-laquintinie"; around 23 : 30 at night while I was sleeping IN february 2021 in DOUALA).
 3. Politicians shall be reduced to be people applying criminal and civil laws instead of people trying to make their own ideas come through via ENTERING private life of people like "Shanda TONME jean claude" has done in the past 30 alike years with my personal family and life ('Family NOUNDOU michel', and 'Family JEAN NGONGANG') !
 4. 'SEMIL' and special alike units of Cameroonian army shall be dismantled because of reported proved or not really ATROCITY facts.
 5. 'SEMIL', 'DGRE', 'SED', etc.; all former people wearing weapons shall be displaced into military caserns so to avoid mixing MILITARY alike people with civilians !
 6. IMPUNITY of all people wearing weapon must cease with tribunal applications of criminal laws.
2. *Create an electoral public and common website for all information, and / or official application documents for all elections in Cameroon !!*
3. *Create a website for publication of all laws in Cameroon; including presidential decrees, acts, and / or acts, and so on ...!*
4. *Reforming judicial system with computer software digitization so to PROMOTE equity and justice by laws !*
5. *EACH CITIZEN or person living in Cameroon SHALL officially declare its lifestyle philosophy and / or religion at a 'Chefferie De Block' when moving inside that area of the city !*
 - a. This enables to solve issues based on this declaration in a fairly manner, according to a new reformed judicial criminal law system !
6. *PROHIBIT any type of religious or associations that don't have well openly presented and written codes of laws, Abiding to CAMEROON criminal laws !*

8.8 TRANSPORTATION and CITIES transportation

1. *Reduce airplane travel costs between cities in Cameroon.*
INSTANCES:
 - a. {DLA → YDE} with one way at 12 000 FRANCS.
 - b. {YDE → BAFOUSSAM} with one way at 18 000 FRANCS.
 - c. Etc..

9.9 Technology And Development

1. *Schooling shall be created and managed to be in harmony with Religious, and / or Philosophy lifestyle of parents that intend to have children in a school; BOTH primary and secondary.*
UNIVERSITIES could mix students of all horizons: so the student and leaders of next Coming Cameroon could learn how to live harmoniously.
2. *State schools for civil servants shall be banned in favor of UNIVERSITY education and of an additional training on the job when hired !*
3. *Universities shall be autonomous and not depend anymore of the PRESIDENCY OF THE REPUBLIC*
4. *Create an industry for solar electrical energy with cars and buses as consumers in a lapse of time of 12 years starting 2026.*
5. *Assemble DIGITAL computers in Cameroon in less than 12 years of presidency.*

10.10 MARRIAGE and INTER-PERSONAL sexual corporal Relationship

1. *PROHIBIT sexual actions IN OUTDOOR by laws.*
2. *REMOVE TRADITIONAL SYSTEM of justice because of its unfairness; Based on WOMAN precedence in power:*
 - a. *SINCE Christians don't need to marry to a woman or any gender, as described in 1 CORINTHIANS 7 : 38 – 39 !*
 - b. *SINCE people could stay without marriage, In Christianity, marriage is THE EXCEPTION, But not a sin;*
 - c. *Any person that is not married and that is a born-again Christian cannot be managed by a married person ! THIS is because A MARRIED person couldn't qualify to understand a life at a certain level as He is living constantly with another gender !*
 - d. *People that have marriage in traditional system normally cannot undergo a civil marriage in a christian church (I.E: TRADITIONAL system allows for Impudicity, Which is prohibited in Christianity !).*
 - e. *Born-Again Christians don't marry at all in any type of marriage !*
 - f. *"SHANDA-TONME jean claude's first and last son": Late (justice of attorney) "Me. Shanda Sanou Cabral Patrice" was apparently killed brutally since his body was missing from people assisting SHANDA's family for obituaries.*
 - g. *"HIS (jean-claude shanda-tonme) OBITUARIES in next coming years must not be public since He hasn't been a good citizen for at least hundreds of young cameroonian" that I have hear about for the last 12 years since I started by immigration process back to my homeland country Cameroon of C.P.D.M-R.D.P.C !*
3. *Automatic Splitting OF INHERITANCE after parental death between children:* Because there are a lot of troubles to leave this task to a family with not enough money for paper and bureaucracy work at notary justice palaces !
4. *LEGALIZE homosexual UNION.*
 - a. *People in this union cannot have children adopted from another non-homosexual union at ALL; AND VICE-VERSA for couple married in non-homosexual life style !*

11.11 MUNICIPALITY Reform (AND WASTE and DISPOSAL of garbage)

1. *chefferie de block: This administrative territorial unit is based on traditional tribal lineage ! THIS SHALL BE ENDED AS EACH CITIZEN is subject to the same civil law:*
 1. *currently, a 'chefferie de block' is based on common and traditional law. Since common law has precedence over tribal traditional law, A CITIZEN living must be subject only to COMMON CIVIL LAW where he is living, OR NOT.*
2. *There shall be created AN INDUSTRY for recycling and displacement of waste-garbage USING ecologic burning container:* Each "chefferie de block" shall have its own burning destroying waste-garbage ecologic container.
3. *There shall be at least 1 municipal playing and recreational area of at least 400 m² in each city quarter ("quartier").*
4. *There shall be at least 1 municipal library in each city quarter ("quartier").*

- **UNITED STATES OF AMERICA (U.S.A)**

- SIEMENS Healthineers (OCS – Varian), CONCORD, CALIFORNIA, U.S.A (JANUARY 2008)
- SRI International, MENLO COLLEGE, MENLO PARK, ATHERTON, CALIFORNIA, U.S.A (May 2011)

- **CANADA**

- UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, WATERLOO, ON, canada (2009 – 2015)
- MITACS ONTARIO, University of Waterloo, Waterloo, ON, CANADA (October 2012)
- CASCON (IBM CENTRE FOR ADVANCED STUDIES CONFERENCE), Hilton Suites Toronto/Markham, Conference Centre, Markham, ON, CANADA (November 2010)
- PLDI conference (Programming Languages Design And Implementation), Toronto, ON, CANADA (November 2009)
- Graduate Management Admission Test (GMAT) PREPARATION COURSE, CONCORDIA UNIVERSITY, MONTREAL, QUEBEC, CANADA (June 2007)
- Graduate English Training Course, UNIVERSITÉ DU QUÉBEC à MONTRAL (UQAM), MONTREAL, QUEBEC, CANADA (AUGUST 2009)

- **GERMANY**

- UNIVERSITÄT BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY (2001 – 2007)
- SIEMENS Healthineers (OCS – Varian), ERLANGEN, BAYERN, GERMANY (2007 – 2009)
- SIEMENS Healthineers (OCS – Varian), HEIDELBERG, BADEN-WÜRTTEMBERG, GERMANY (2007 – 2009)

This section reports and summarizes our current and actualized knowledge on the subject of software licensing.

20.20 SOFTWARE LICENSes

- o "Summary of MOSTLY used software-licenses":

[Software ~~Hardware~~ Certification authorities; "O.H.A.D.A"; CENELEC; CE; ISO; "A.R.I.N.C"]

Table 1: Software LICENSes summary table.

SOFTWARE license type	Peculiarities	Uses	URL for legal writing specification
1. "CSCS : Close Source Code Software"	Software / Programs AUTHOR exclusive copyright & ownership	YOU use only a binary.	Each retailer provides this on a case by case request.
2.			
3.			
4.			
5.			
6.			

- CSCS : Close Source Code Software (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)

- Open source code software (OSS (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)) :

- a. OTHER forms of free software license (FOSS (<https://www.wikipedia.org>))

- b. APACHE-BSD license (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)

- APACHE
- ["BSD"]

- c. GNU licenses : (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)

- GPL
ANY software that uses this piece of whole source code and / or binaries have to also be licensed GPL.

- "Lesser GPL - LGPL" ✓
Program binaries could be used in a commercial project without any request and / or payments to the owner of the source code. Modifications of the source code follows certain rules specified as follows :

- 1.) *Mention of the authors have to be explicitly written in headers of code sources as directed by rules explicitly sampled at following URL : (<https://>).*
- 2.) *YOUR own using software source code must also abide to the LGPL GNU software license according to what is written at following URL : (<https://>).*

- d. BERKELEY-style license (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)

- BSD

- e. MIT-license; "also called AS-IS-no-warranty-AT-ALL" (<https://www.wikipedia.org>)

- MIT ✓
THIS kind of Open-Source Software (OSS) programs is provided in a state that no reclamation could be done because it could be very tedious to determine liabilities between parties such as a provider, and a customer and / or client.

The so-called MIT License are part of the AS-IS no-warranty code; ALSO all GPL typed licenses in general.

Programs using AS-IS no-Warranty code software licenses generally stipulates either following text, OR similar surrounding text around following :

- o ["The program is provided AS IS with NO WARRANTY OF ANY KIND, INCLUDING THE WARRANTY OF DESIGN, MERCHANTABILITY AND FITNESS FOR A PARTICULAR PURPOSE."]

This section reports and summarizes all information required at least for certification of our runtime verification monitoring tester tool; BOTH software and/or HARDWARE products.

21.21 Documents for certification for "YERITH R&D" software – hardware PRODUCTS engineered in AFRICA-main—land

Table 2: *Design Documents* for the CASE (Computer-AIDED SOFTWARE Engineering) tool YERITH_QVGE.

Design Document	VERSION	LOCATION
1. <i>USER requirements elicitation (USER Functional Specification)</i>		
2. <i>Module Description (Module Functional Specification)</i>		
3. <i>Module / Unit Testing</i>		

Table 3: *Design Documents* for the Runtime Monitoring Verifier Tester [YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF].

Design Document	VERSION	LOCATION
1. <i>USER requirements elicitation (USER Functional Specification)</i>		
2. <i>Module Description (Module Functional Specification)</i>		
3. <i>Module / Unit Testing</i>		

Table 4: *Design Documents* for the Monitoring Verifier Tester [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET]

Design Document	VERSION	LOCATION
1. <i>USER requirements elicitation (USER Functional Specification)</i>		
2. <i>Module Description (Module Functional Specification)</i>		
3. <i>Module / Unit Testing</i>		

A personal computer tablet for SIMPLIFYING runtime monitoring on-the-fly

Figure 11, Figure 12, and Figure 13 illustrates a sample product usage of the toolkit YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF that permits and allows for its users following actions and tasks to be solved fluently :

1. Send tracing logging for a developer and / or engineer trough 1 of the following communication interfaces :
 - 1.)

- 1.) *Design Documents Unit TESTING, and Static Code Analysis Verification;*
- 2.) *USER requirements elicitation (USER Functional Specification);*
- 3.) *Module Description (Module Functional Specification).*

This section reports and summarizes all information required at least for certification of our runtime verification monitoring tester tool; BOTH software and/or HARDWARE products.

22.22 TOOLS used for Qualification AND / OR Certification of Software-hardware PRODUCTS at "YERITH R&D"

Table 5: Tools used for Qualification and / Or Certification at YERITH R&D.

TOOL	VERSION	Uses	LOCATION
1. "BUGZILLA (https://www.bugzilla.org)"	"N.A"	<i>Bugs and Defects registration & following-up.</i>	
2. "GNU Privacy Guard-GPG (https://www.gnupg.org)"	2.2.27-2	<i>Digital signing check-in source code & documents.</i>	
3. "Git (https://www.git.org)"	1 : 2.30.2-1 + deb11u2	<i>COMMIT, and following-up source code for certification authorities.</i>	

Table 5 illustrates some programming and / or debugging tools I use at YERITH R&D for developing certified products with "ISO - INTERNATIONAL STANDARD ORGANISATION (<https://www.iso.org>)", etc.; Certification organizations :

- o *Bugs and Defects Management Software* : "[BUGZILLA \(https://www.bugzilla.org\)](https://www.bugzilla.org)";
 1. "VERSION of current [BUGZILLA](https://www.bugzilla.org) software installations" : "N.A".
 2. "Location of [BUG](https://www.bugzilla.org) report-free database website URL" : "[www.digital.ocean.com/YERITH_QVGE_HTTPS_url \(https://www.digitalocean.com\)](https://www.digitalocean.com/YERITH_QVGE_HTTPS_url)".
 3. "Location of [BUGZILLA](https://www.bugzilla.org) software installation" : "Intern to YERITH R&D".
- o *Software for electronically signing (e.g.: Source code, Design Documents, etc.)* : "[GNU Privacy Guard-GPG \(https://www.gnupg.org\)](https://www.gnupg.org)";
 1. "VERSION of current [GNU Privacy Guard-GPG](https://www.gnupg.org) software installations" : "2.2.27-2".
- o *SCM (Source code Management) software* : *Version Control Management Software* : "[Git \(https://www.git.org\)](https://www.git.org)";
 1. "VERSION of current [Git](https://www.git.org) software installations" : "1 : 2.30.2-1 + deb11u2".

This section reports and summarizes all information required at least for certification of our runtime verification monitoring tester tool; BOTH software and/or HARDWARE products.

23.23 Yerith_QVGE Legal Software and/or Hardware CERTIFICATION Artifacts

- o "Yerith_QVGE Legal Software CERTIFICATION Artifacts":

- YERITH_QVGE DESIGN AND TESTING SYSTEM[12.12] : A product for qualification; "O.H.A.D.A"; CE, ISO, "A.R.I.N.C".

23.23.1 "CERTIFICATION Tools used at YERITH R&D"

[Certification TOOLS.]

23.23.2 "PRODUCTS for Engineering And / OR Finance Engineered Computing"

- 1.) YERITH_QVGE software design CASE (Computer-AIDED SOFTWARE Engineering) tool; [RELated Design & User Documentation Artifacts.]

[“June 2022” – Currently]

Figure 1: A SCREENSHOT OF YERITH_QVGE FOR GRAPHICAL DESIGN OF STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE (SDMM) SPECIFICATIONS; THAT COULD SPECIFY TRADE OPERATIONS BASED ON TRADE-TIME.

- 2.) YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET ; [RELated Design & User Documentation Artifacts.]

[“Nov. 2024” – Currently]

Figure 2: A screenshot of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF SQL error event log running on YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET.

Figure 3: A sample YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET in action.

THIS hardware computing device, WITH software that uses "INTEL-Pin" (<https://www.intel.com>) could be used for "on-the-fly" runtime verification monitoring & Recovering manifold :

- One connects YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET to either an Ethernet network connection, or serial interface communication port RS-232, and / or Universal Serial BUS-USB interface port ;

YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (a screenshot is found in Figure 2) is started on "YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET", and connects to specified processes, on the attached connected other computing device (E.g.: in Fig. 3, a control console for "Siemens-LINAC"); In a configuration panel. THE open source version of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verify>) is a bit different of the non-free upgraded version installed on "YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET".

This section reports and summarizes all efforts needed as far AS I could learn and experienced as seasoned software developer at "IBM-toronto-software-laboratory"; And at "Siemens-medical-solutions".

24.24 Years of experience as Software Developer for Legally APPROVED products

o "Legal Requirements for a correct con-formant Software Artifact":

■ YERITH_QVGE LEGAL documents for Qualified Products from AFRICA—main—land.

■ [SOFTWARE licensing.]

■ "Communauté Économique et MONÉTAIRE de l'Afrique Centrale – (C.E.M.A.C)" (<https://www.cemac.int>) : THIS central Africa certification applies for Accounting and Finance.

I.) "O.H.A.D.A (<https://www.cemac.int>)" ; for "FINANCIAL ACCOUNTING SOFTWARE"

■ TÜV-Nord (<https://www.tuv-nord.de>) in North-West GERMANY : This german authority in Science and Engineering reflects better our initial commitment as a "DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)"[?], even before a [MASTER-OF-SCIENCE] degree was created at the UNIVERSITY-racist of Bremen (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>).

A.) "CE - EUROPEAN COMMUNITY (https://www.single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/single-market/ce-marking_en)" ; "ISO - INTERNATIONAL STANDARD ORGANISATION (<https://www.iso.org>)" ; "FDA - FEDERAL DRUG ADMINISTRATION (U.S.A) (<https://www.fda.gov>)" for "MEDICAL SOFTWARE"

1. Bugs and Defects are to be managed by a software such as "IBM-CharmNT (<https://www.ibm.com/us>)" ;
2. Design Documents are to be updated annually at maximum time based on regulatory deadlines of AUTHORITIES That Delivers Certificates "; I think at least ONCE-ANNUALLY";
3. Design Documents are electronically signed by an author and reviewers;
4. Design Documents are saved in an ERP software such as "SAP-EDM (<https://www.sap.de>)", etc.;
5. Design Documents have a table to indicate changes within the document for each modification of it;
6. Design Documents USER requirements elicitation (USER Functional Specification);
7. Design Documents Module Description (Module Functional Specification) with Diagrams; E.g.: "Finite State Machine Diagrams", etc.;
8. Design Documents Unit TESTING, and Static Code Analysis Verification; Runtime Memory Error Detection TOOLS.
9. Source code is to be stored in a control version management system such as "Rational-ClearCase", etc.;
10. Source code changes are to be reviewed and electronically signed using a key-card like the ones used by ["SIEMENS-healthineers-OCS"];

B.) CENELEC (<https://www.iso.org/fr/standard/68383.html>) for "RAILWAY"

A sample railway software related product regulation is : "CENELEC EN50128" (<https://www.iso.org/fr/standard/68383.html>).

C.) A.R.I.N.C (<https://www.aviation-ia.sae-itc.com>) for "AVIONICS SOFTWARE"

Sample A.R.I.N.C specifications : "RTCA D0178-B"; "RTCA D0178-C".

- Static Code Analysis Verification conforming to "MISRA-C" (<https://www.misra.org>) ;

["MISRA-C"]

This section reports and summarizes all efforts I have made throughout my Time at The University Of Waterloo as a 'Ph.D. candidate'. THIS page links and connects 5 years of academic and professional research I HAVE been spending at the white-asian-white racist extremist university of waterloo in ontario, CANADA.

25.25 Years of PRE-Doctoral & years of Doctoral Research at University-racist OF waterloo, ONTARIO, CANADA

ML; C++; Java; OSI; Eclipse; Intel-Pin; Open-MP Haskell, GWT, Python, IBM, Quercus, Bash-scripting	<i>Program Analysis (Static, Dynamic).</i> a-la-KILDALL-Gary;LFDS-Reps; datalog; Soot; LLVM	Courses taught: 1. Software Testing, Quality Assurance & Maintenance 2. Programming for Performance 3. Tools & Methods for Software Engineering 4. Foundations of Software Engineering 5. C++ Programming Laboratory 6. Compilers 7. Computer Networks
<i>(ADVANCED) Compiler Technology</i> Yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang; Alias Analysis, Comp. Opt.	<i>Program Verification (Isa.-HOL, etc.); Model Checking</i> SDMM; CAV - Computer-Aided Verification; NuSMV; Alloy	
Programing Languages OOP; Functional	Software; Programming; Testing Alg.; Rel. Eng.; Security; Par.-Comp.	} Foundations of My Doctoral Ph.D. / Post-Doctoral Works in Computer Science (Software Engineering)
	Formal Methods; Kripke Structures Automata theory (NFA, DFA, etc.)	

- o **[PublicaTIONS.]**
- o **"Software LICENSING".**
- o **"Legal Requirements for a correct con-formant Software Artifact".**
- o **Contacts with NORTH-AMERICAN scientists**
- o **Contacts with other Scientists**
- o **Issues & MISUNDERSTANDINGS at the University of Waterloo, Ontario, Canada**
- o **TIME at the University-racist-of-BREMEN, BREMEN, BREMEN, Germany:**
 1. "2 years" STudent Software Developer PART-TIME job – Bergmann Automaten GmbH (now Gewete GmbH), Germany.
 2. "2 years" WERKSTUDENT at ZMML-university-sexist-racist of bremen, BREMEN, GERMANY.: February 2003 – February 2005.
 3. "4.5 years PRE-time" in GERMAN-racist program : "'DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)"[?]".
- o **Doctoral years of research at the university-racist of waterloo, ontario, CANADA-idiot:**
 1. "2 years PRE-time" at SIEMENS-idiot medical solutions.: November 2007 – JULY 2009.
 2. PAPER conference peer reviewed : OOPSLA 2010.
 3. GIVEN PREsentation : IBM CDp Cascon 2010.
 4. Visited courses.
 5. **Independent assisted research summary as a "Master of Science (M.Sc.)"**
 6. **VISited SUMMER-school /workshops / conferences summary**
[¹ST SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques"-2011] | [PLDI 2009] | [IBM CDp Cascon 2010]
 7. PSYCHOLOGICAL-Care with PRACTICE of SWIMMING at THE university-racist of waterloo every other day during almost 4 years – "Degree-Swimmer-5 / degree-MASTER-Swimmer-6" successfully attended.
 8. "Year 1" : 09/2009 – 08/2010;
 9. "Year 2" : 09/2010 – 12/2011 – [with PhD Comprehensive Examination.];
 10. **Doctoral THESIS Presentation / PhD Comprehensive Examination on "December 20, 2011"**
- o **QUALification as a "Professional Engineer in Ontario, CANADA":**

THE requirements to qualify myself as Professional Engineer in ONTARIO are all met after 1 year supervision under PATRICK LAM "(2011)"; because I have already 48 months of professional engineering work experience before entering the professional academic doctor of engineering program in ELECTRICAL & COMPUTER Engineering at university-racist-white of waterloo.

"AS a "doctor PhD in electrical & computer engineering" graduate [abbreviated "Dr./PhD" in French; In french, "Dr./PhD" only nowadays means doctor in engineering; and no fellowship at all; I AM A FRANCOPHONE.]; THERE shouldn't be any need to again acquired a professional designation "Professional Engineer", since "doctor PhD in electrical & computer engineering" is already an Engineering titled degree. So as a francophone from dark-afrika-heimat, I am not interested anymore in any Engineering, or whatsoever designated vocational position in whiteist-world !"

"ALSO as a born-again christian, I CANNOT BE member-ed in any fellowship of iron-rings, female-peggist; etc. ."

"JON eyolfson for instance has a "Bachelor-of-Engineering"; so he doesn't need to apply for a "Professional Engineer"; BUT [Wenzhu-man has a "Master of Applied Science (MAsc)"]; AND no "Engineering titled degree from CANADA and /or USA"; SO for her needs she must apply for P.Eng.; so to get government oriented positions !"

This section reports and summarizes all efforts I have made throughout my Time at The University Of Waterloo as a 'Ph.D. candidate'. THIS page links and connects 5 years of academic and professional research I HAVE been spending at the white-asian-white racist extremist university of waterloo in ontario, CANADA.

26.26 Years of POST-doctoral Research; a Summary Report – 2nd page

- o *Post-Doctoral (Ph.D.; Prof.) years of research at the university–racist of waterloo, ontario, CANADA–idiot:*
 1. "Year 1": 01/2012 – 08/2012 – [*PROfessional Internship at IBM Toronto–idiot Software Lab..*]
 2. "Year 2": 09/2012 – 08/2013
 3. "Year 3": 09/2013 – 08/2014
 4. "Year 4": 09/2014 – 04/2015
 5. STUDENT advising summary
 6. TEACHing assistantship summary
 7. *Independent & Collegiate Research Summary as "Dr.-Ing. (PhD)"*
 8. Visited courses as post-doctoral (POST-DOCTORAL STUDIES) fellow.
 9. VISITED ONLINE courses /workshops / conferences summary
[Software-Security-online–"stanford.edu" 2013] | [MITACS ONTARIO 2012] | [ICse 2012]
 10. RESEARCH outcome hindrance
 11. RESEARCH outcome plagiarism
 12. RESEARCH outcome plagiarism-continUED
 13. GIVEN–co–taught courses at the University–racist of Waterloo in ONTARIO, Canada
 14. ACADEMIC HELP from other people aside from DEAR-idiot PATRICK-lam
 15. *!!! PhD Research Seminar TALK. as an ECE graduate talk. !!!*
 16. *!!! PhD Dissertation Defense at DAVID R. Cheriton School OF Computer Science in "January 2015" !!!*
 17. *IAI–cameroon–bande–d'idiots au service d'1 B.E.P.C–chantoux*
- o [*TRAINING on the job of young engineers*]:
 - Runtime monitoring for Web Apps
 - API usage rule checking for 'C' programs (https://www.archive.org/download/jh-nissi-ece-uwaterloo-grad-talk-2014-04-16/JH_NISSI_ECE_UWATERLOO_GRAD_TALK_2014__04__16.pdf)
- o *STARTUP entrepreneurship research & development project YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM:*

After I left the university–racist–of–waterloo in ontario, IN MARCH 2015; I went to live in Cameroon–yaounde for almost 2 years, working on a free and open source software for Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP).

POST-Doctoral Research at YERITH R&D since MARCH 2015:

 - I) *YERITH_QVGE legal artifacts for QUALIFICATION certified products Engineered in AFRICA;*
 - II) *A web-site Domain-Specific Language (DSL) Processor for generation of HTML5, PHP, CSS, etc. combined web-applications named YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0*
 <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9>
 - III) *A realtime component (for operating system DEBIAN LINUX) is in preparation for trading stock exchange erp system "YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME": YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RT-SYSTEM;*
 - IV) *A RUNTIME monitoring verification "state diagram mealy machines (SDMM)" C++ Library :*
 [YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF](https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf) (https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf) [*?f*]
 https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif
 - V) *A State Diagram Mealy Machine (SDMM) translator-compiler :*
[YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP](https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567) (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567>) [*?c*]
 https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang
 - VI) *A RUNTIME monitoring verification runtime container for "SDMM" :*
 [YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF](https://www.zenodo.org/records/10474033) (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/10474033>) [*?b*]
 <https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>
 - VII) *Simple to use and pragmatic Enterprise-Resource-Planing (ERP) software :*
 [YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/) (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>) [*?f*]
 <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0>

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES 6 (Cyber-Security & Web Deployment Development)

27.27 WEB PAGES HTML and others Generation with YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0

27.27.1 Motivation

Table 6: A SOFTWARE architecture overview of YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 (["An SDMM usage scenario by IBM-websphere"].)

Figure 4: YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 generates legacy web files from Qt 5 interface files (".ui" files).

Figure 5: A Stack Staped Architecture Overview of YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0.

YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 is a novel project that constitutes the base for YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM ([git https://github.com/yerithrd/yeritherppgiwebsystem](https://github.com/yerithrd/yeritherppgiwebsystem)) that endeavors to create web sites solutions for entrepreneurial organizations that use YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM without much additional programming of web interfaces and / or interactions; AT such, web sites solutions for entrepreneurial organizations will emerge as easy as pressing a button.

YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 is a Domain Specific Language to describe WEB SITES programmatically; SUCH as a C++ program imperatively, AND well structured; So to automatically generate STATIC DYNAMIC WEB SITES BASED ON HTML (HYPERTEXT MARKUP LANGUAGE) AND CSS (Cascading Style Sheets) language constructs.

Numerous companies in Cameroon might evaluate this new research software system product to simplify and speed up their software development process :

1. "Dr.-Ing. PAUL dayang (2013, University of Bremen)"; currently employed at the University of Ngaoundere in Far North of Cameroon.

- This researcher and lecturer, employed by the University of Ngaoundere, has never replied to my long time email as an alumni of the prestigious University of Bremen in Germany where I graduated with a "Diplom-Informatiker degree 2 years before him !"
- I could see he started a web graphical system (also with "ANDROID-google platform" (<https://>)) html-based to promote online afore-provisional shopping of food provisions in Africa for its dissertation as a "Doctor of Engineering". I was sad not to see this project emerge as a commercial start-up here in Cameroon where there is only "www.cm.coinafrique.com" (<https://www.cm.coinafrique.com>) that I deem as a serious competitor in this era of work.
- I believe the programming abstraction I will provide for "DAYANG and RÖDIGER (<https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/~roediger>) work" would help them both in "Ngaoundere" and in "Bremen" to promote Free and Open Source web shopping for Africa where even a clean market is not existing in Main city Yaounde !
- AT the university of bremen-white-racist, I Visited a course titled "E-business technologies 2"; I don't remember the name of the professor but I DID SO while I WAS in my 3rd year as part of so called "ANGEWANDTE INFORMATIK" ("Applied Computer Science"). IN graduate level course "E-business technologies 2", I learned about n-tiers web architectures, SOAP-Service Oriented Architecture Protocol, etc.

ALSO, in my 2nd year, there was a small "practicum" where I learned on PHP, and MariaDB; "ERIC-cuon-pd STREIBL" was the organizer.

2. "DUT-Diplôme Universitaire de Technologie" CHRISTIAN ngueyong rikong" (Start-Up)

CHRISTIAN ngueyong rikong is a seasoned software developer that creates large to medium-sized websites; AND Google-android mobile applications for his clients around world.

"CHRISTIAN rikong ngueyong, that I schooled with in Douala secondary school — "ALFRED SAKER HIGH SCHOOL" — would also not be against such a tool-framework that could reduce his development time and effort, since BLACK-USA entrepreneurs cannot afford tremendous amount of money for tools sold by MICROSOFT CORP., FACEBOOK INC., etc. !" (<https://www.christianrikong.com>)

3. "Dr. (B.Sc.) Claudel Noumbissi" (Start-Up)

4. "Ing. (B.Sc.) Arthur Zang" (Start-Up)

5. "Dr.-Ing. (Ph.D.) Ibrahim Nguena Moukouop" (Start-Up)

6. "Dr.-Ing. (Ph.D.) Thomas Djotio Ndié" (Start-Up)

7. "Santa Lucia – AHALA", Yaounde

8. "DR. (M.Sc.) Fabrice Wilfried Siemni" (Start-Up) :

Fabrice WILFRIED siemni could generate sample website pages with no programming knowledge at all.

"HIS medium-sized Start-Up believes that the physician of the future would be just a very good "natural food nutritionist". AND I AGREE with it. " (<https://maligah.com/entreprises/details/Happiness-Potential?id=41214>)

BERNADETTE noundou, an aunt paternal of mine could also be 1 of his client since both are from RCMP.

Dorothee SHANDA NDJATIE owona also seems to be 1 of his competitor in pegging toronto-rcmp-jules-nteta-noundou; A junior brother of my late father THEODORE-idiot-noumbissi.

9. etc.

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES 6 – CONTINUED –

Table 7: YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0-DSL keywords and meaning.

YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 keyword	(level) Nested in keyword	Programming related meaning
1. yerith_web_pages_generator_MAIN		Contains web site all pages description
2. web_html_page_menu_bar_headers	(1) yerith_web_pages_generator_MAIN	Contains web site each page menubar pages names
3. web_html_page	(1) yerith_web_pages_generator_MAIN	A HTML page description
4. yri_html_page_title	(3) web_html_page	A HTML page title
5. yri_html_page_input_header_menu_bar	(3) web_html_page	Inputs a menubar onto this HTML page
6. yri_html_page_text_SECTION	(3) web_html_page	Describes a text section on a HTML page
7. VARIABLE_YRI_PARAGRAPH	(6) yri_html_page_text_SECTION	Defines text paragraph within a HTML page
8. text_yri_font_size	(1) yerith_web_pages_generator_MAIN	Defines a font size
9. text_yri_width_box	(1) yerith_web_pages_generator_MAIN	Defines a width for a text paragraph

Figure 6: Webbrowser-based software architecture : at least 4 layers logical software architecture (Image modified from online pdf paper "FlashCache: A NAND Flash Memory File Cache for Low Power Web Servers" [<https://doi.org/10.1145/1176760.1176774>] by Trevor et al.). YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF runtime monitors communication layers.

27.27.2 RELATED WORK at YERITH R&D; Software System Architecture of ERP Systems

- "Our paper not for publication in a conference paper, [SOFTWARE SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OF YERITH-ERP-3.0\[??\]](https://www.archive.org/download/yerith-erp-3-0-software-system-architecture_20221230/YERITH-ERP-3-0-SOFTWARE-SYSTEM-ARCHITECTURE.pdf) : (https://www.archive.org/download/yerith-erp-3-0-software-system-architecture_20221230/YERITH-ERP-3-0-SOFTWARE-SYSTEM-ARCHITECTURE.pdf); reveals common web system architecture patterns and structure, INCLUDING ([CYBER-SECURITY\[23\]](#)) software system security vulnerability analysis; As observed these last 10 years at least from "April 20, 2025".
- ["WE have visited, in year 2013, an online software security vulnerability detection and protection course with the STANFORD-university-racist while attending our degree [DOCTORAL PH.D.-program at the University of Waterloo;] THIS required acquired knowledge helps us creating safe and secure software systems by Construction."]
- "WE previously, in our 3rd semester", at the University-racist of Bremen, Bremen, GERmany-idiot; Have visited a course for undergraduates named "Information Security 1" given by "TZI.DE (Technology Center for Computer Science) (<https://www.tzi.de/en>)" founding member "Prof. Dr.-Ing. Carsten-cuon-obèse Bormann-nazi" (<https://www.tzi.de/BORMAN-nazi>)."
- ★ ★ ["I could also achieved a running taint analysis ([git https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis](https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis)) for the Quercus PHP JAVA web application server during my post-doctoral studies & work at the university-racist of waterloo in ontarian Canada-idiot. IT was a graduate course taught by "Frank-idiot-nazi TIP-gay-cuon".] ★ ★

27.27.3 WHAT YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 Would Service & Provide

- "Qt 5 software development platform" enables auto-deployment for Android-google platform." (<https://>)
YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yeritherppiwebsystem>) will reuse this functionality to generate legacy web source code files (HTML5, PHP, CSS, Javascript (GWT (Google Web Toolkit))); VIA a translation program-technology from "Qt 5-ui (user-interface)" files onto YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 input file coin as DSL-specific YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 files ("spec.html"); Figure 4.;
- We at YERITH R&D could then use any "Qt 5-Designer tool as a WYSIWYG Tool for generating Web-HTML-PHP pages" !
- "We plan at mid-term to be able to generate "Software architecture proof testing-programs", both for GUI-interfaces (thick-client), and Web-interfaces (thin-client); automatically just by specifying certain behavioral interactions using state diagram mealy machines ([SDMM\[?d\]](#)).";
- "The so-called "Software architecture proof testing-programs" will have certain warranties about cyber-security, runtime-memory usage and user-defined usage rules (See for instance Fig. 5)."

27.27.4 Implementation Technologies

I use "flex and bison compiler / translator generation technology" for creating YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0-DSL. I plan to automatically generate code for enabling runtime monitoring of the generated web sites. A first version of this FOSS (Free And Open Source Software) is available at URL: "[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9)".

27.27.5 YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0-DSL Keyword Table

Table 7 depicts and explains commands and directives for creating web-based HTML pages sites.

We plan also the generation of web sites based on an "n-tiers architecture pattern", illustrated for instance in Figure 6; that demonstrated solid resistance in practice for more than 10 years now as demonstrated by applications server existence and usage such as :

1. Apache tomcat application server
2. Glassfish application server: mainly used in combination with JAVA OSI component-based software development architecture.
3. Quercus PHP server interpreter application server
4. IBM websphere

All this work has to solve the issue of generating certain portion of web sites for customers and users of ["YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM"\[?\]](#) Enterprise Resource Planing software in a time period in-between of 3 years from this year 2024 !

"ALL THIS UNDER THE PROTECTION OF OUR LORD AND SAVIOR JEOVAH-NISSI IN HEAVEN."

12.12 Software Verification with YERITH_QVGE

A library or plugin at any layer (OR a combination mixture of layers) of a software system architecture could be verified and validated using YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF by applying a receipt: IT would be sufficient to map each system call wanted for call sequence verification and / or validation to a MySQL query: So one doesn't need to re-create new QT-DBus interfaces for YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: E.g.: "SYSTEM V libc".

Figure 7: Software system architecture of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: it is also a runtime monitor container for software verification.

Figure 8: YRI_QVGE software stack dependencies.

2. Create A FRAMEWORK FOR DYNAMIC runtime analysis and monitoring of Temporal Safety Property in Plugin-based software (Figure 8 illustrates graphically interdependency between these under described sub-projects.).

- a. **YRI_QVGE (an extension of Qt-QVGE):** A "CASE (computer-aided software engineering)", CLOSED SOURCE CODE SOFTWARE (CSCS), for creating and generating MEALY MACHINE STATE DIAGRAMS as GUI (GRAPHICAL USER INTERFACE) TOOL. [06/2022 – CURRENT]
[model-based testing, DSL – domain-specific languages]

“[THE GUI TOOL YERITH_QVGE] (See Figure 14) GENERATES A FILE CONTAINING A MEALY MACHINE STATE DIAGRAM SPECIFICATION using YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG; this file could be used as input for the compiler YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP, so to gather a C++ package to run as runtime monitor within YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF. THIS TOOL COSTS 2, 500 EUROS.”

- b. **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF:** A Dynamic Program Monitoring Recovering Analyzer Generator for any software emitting QtDBus messages per sockets (See subsection 12.12.3 (Runtime Verification), and / or Figure 12; and / or Figure 15).

“THIS IS at time (April 20, 2025); State-of-art technology; comparable technology are for instance RT-Tester with TDIOHS (Timed Discrete Input / Output Hybrid System); State Diagram formalism From "VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GMBH, SPIN-OFF THE UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN" (RT-Tester; MBT[?]). TDIOHS complies fully with all semantic elements of HAREL-statecharts !

“AND technologies "IBM Purify Plus"; "LOGSCOPE" ("Specification-Based Monitoring in C++") and "DejaVu" ("DejaVu: A Monitoring Tool for First-Order Temporal Logic") by [Dr. Klaus Havelund] at N.A.S.A (<https://www.nasa.gov>).”

- YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: <https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>

- c. **YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP:** a compiler using flex and bison, for YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF specification language (YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG), so to automatically generate C++ code for runtime monitors implemented in YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF. [04/2023 – CURRENT]
[compilers, model-based testing, reactive system analysis, domain-specific languages]

“COMPETITORS from LOGSCOPE and DejaVu; AND RT-Tester; MBT[?]; have similar description state diagram language; but work all of them as SPECIFICATION OF WISHED PROGRAM BEHAVIOR; whereas SDMM[?] works at SPECIFICATION OF FORBIDDEN (fail) PROGRAM BEHAVIOR.”

- YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP: https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang

- d. **YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG:** A SPECIFICATION LANGUAGE FOR STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE (SDMM) extended with pre-/post-conditions on STATE DIAGRAM TRANSITIONS and with a final state. (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567>) [04/2023 – CURRENT]
[model-based testing, reactive system analysis, domain-specific languages]

“In comparison to statecharts [”Statecharts: a visual formalism for complex systems” (<https://www.bibsonomy.org/bibtex/2462cc2a9db87a5788c405cc577968d5f/rnesse/rath>)] which is a visual formalism for states diagrams, YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG doesn't support at time for instance the following features: hierarchical states (composite state, submachine state), timing conditions.”

- YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP: https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang

- e. **YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_UNIT_TESTS:** UNIT TESTING PROJECT for YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF. [06/2022 – CURRENT]
“THIS test unit suite is there to check peculiarities of project YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF; As a Free And OPEN SOURCE CODE SOFTWARE (foss), I strongly recommend using it before committing changes to the main git-branch project.”

- YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_UNIT_TESTS: https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_UNIT_TESTS

- f. **YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF / YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF:** a framework for verifying SQL software correctness properties of gui software at runtime [06/2022 – CURRENT]

[model-based testing, reactive system analysis, computer software program analysis, computer software dynamic program analysis, software integration testing with SQL and GUI, runtime monitoring]

“YOU SPECIFY USING A STATE DIAGRAM AN ERRONEOUS SUT (System Under Test) TYPE STATE STYLE BEHAVIOR with YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF. USING YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF, YOU CHECK AT RUNTIME WHETHER SUCH AN ERRONEOUS SUT SEQUENCE BEHAVIOR OCCURS.”

- YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF: https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif

12.12.1 TAXONOMY : Software Verification vs. Program Code Verification

Figure 9: "Program verification (including model checking)" is a subset (C) of "SOFTWARE VERIFICATION". (See also research goal 11.)

Software System verification is a discipline to verify whether a software, meaning a product use at customer level and full-featured, conforms to certain software system user related usage properties.

In contrast, **program code verification** checks only program at the level of their source code or binary code product against code programming related properties, And not necessarily at level of a full featured user level product. Thus all code programming related properties could be cast down to certain software system related properties. **It follows PROGRAM VERIFICATION is a Subset Of Software (System) Verification: illustrated in Figure 9 !**

📄 **Program Analysis by Xavier-erith** (https://www.archive.org/details/yeroth-program-analysis-2023/YERITH-PROGRAM_ANALYSIS_2024_With_CURRICULUM_vitae_2024.pdf) !

12.12.2 How to use YERITH_QVGE

A software component or a whole running software binary could be verified against SQL correctness temporal properties by USING 📄 **YRI_QVGE**, as illustrated in Figure 7:

- The 1st layer illustrates the runtime verifier tester monitor engine: YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF, that entails several custom runtime monitor specifications, provided by user.
- The 2nd layer shows the SUT (System Under Test); or PUA (Program Under Analysis); layer that communicates with YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF through QT socket calls (via Dbus messages). Each event message is sent to all runtime monitors. **The SUT source code has been instrumented first**, so to specify which program statements actions are to be packaged as messages to YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF. **"INTEL-Pin"** (<https://www.intel.com>) could also be used to instrument program binaries at runtime directly, Avoiding recompilation and even usable where source code of SUT (PUA) is unavailable.
- The 3rd layer illustrates a library or plugin (i.e.: MySQL) that is being monitored via instrumentation of the SUT; in this case, the SUT is YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum. **Other providers could modify An Open Source Code Version (FOSS) of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF to verify and monitor another library-plugin other than MySQL.**
- The 4th and last layer shows the Operating System (OS) layer and its communication via systems calls with the 3rd layer of the library-plugin.

12.12.3 How to use YERITH_QVGE in relation to verification cyber-security detection remediation methods.

1. Model Checking (<https://wikipedia.org>):

Temporal logic formalisms, such as **LTTL (Linear Temporal Logic)** (<https://>); Could be used to create 📄 **State Diagram Mealy Machine (SDMM)** (https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf) [?d] and generate a binary executable of 📄 **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/10474033>) [?b] to perform runtime monitoring, and runtime SQL recovery of Graphical User Interface (GUI) supported software (And also not supported GUI software). Users must only note that "SDMM" specifications are **fail (forbidden) trace** behavior specifications of a program under analysis (SUT).

Structures could be created on how to translate simple LTL constructs into simple "SDMM"; So to ease usage of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF;

2. Runtime Verification (Monitoring; including Software Cyber-Security Exploit Detection Remediation):

A whole class of problems involving sequencing of actions and / or method calls ranging from:

- **Application Programming Interface (API) checking protocol usage;**
- **WEB-APPLICATION RUNTIME MONITORING[27.27] ; Software Security Vulnerability Analysis: I.E. Taint Analysis;**
- **Information Flow Policy Control and Enforcement : (E.g. : Figure 11);**
- **Checking of automated and / or manual (unit) test procedure conformance with regards to TESTED PROGRAM (SOFTWARE) temporal properties;**
- etc.

Could be solved by usage of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF; **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF GIT-REPOSITORY[?b]:** 📄 <https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>. **"Pr. Prof. Dr. Jean Yang, Ph.D." from CMU—"Carnegie Mellon University** (<https://www.cs.cmu.edu/~jyang2>)" could be a potential competitor in this area of research.":

A. "Jeeves Programming Language" – last updated "October 2015" (<https://projects.csail.mit.edu/jeeves>)

- **API usage rule check at 'AKITA Software** (<https://www.akita.com>)' in USA; California (CA).
- **"Jeeves Programming Language"** enables static typing;
- **Dynamic code source rewriting to achieve Semantics; implemented as an embedded Domain Specific Language (DSL) in Python programming language (IT is unclear in which document [PROFESSOR JEAN yang checks] that this code is correct).**

Figure 10: Embedded program verifier notifier within YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum; YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF runs as a background process service.

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES IV – CONTINUED — 2 VS. Jeeves Programming Language

Table 8: Jeeves Programming Language Versus (Vs.) The Runtime Monitoring Verifier Tester YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF

"Information Flow and Policy Control"	YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF	Jeeves Programming Language
1. Specification as a Domain Specific Language (DSL)	Yes (stand-alone SDMM (HTTPS://WWW.ZENODO.ORG/RECORDS/13232567) [?d] DSL specification; Based on MEALY MACHINE AUTOMATON; "HAREL-statechart (https://www.bibsonomy.org/bibtex/2462cc2a9db87a5788c405cc577968d5f/rnesse1rath compatibility)") ✓	yes (DSL embedded into Python)
2. False (Positives) Warnings	No (1 formal proof exists in journal paper (HTTPS://WWW.ZENODO.ORG/RECORDS/13232567) [?d]) ✓	* yes (CHECK A REFERENCE)
3. DSL Specification CARRIES DATA too	Yes (as Qt-DBus NETWORK data parameters) ✓	yes (as local stack function/method parameter)
4. As program annotations	Yes (FOSS Library Qt-DBus instructions) ✓	yes ('Jeeves' instructions)
5. USABLE in a any programming language	Yes (FOSS Library Qt-DBus instructions) ✓	no (Only Python)
6. ONLY usage with Python	No (any programming language that could emit Qt-DBus instructions) ✓	yes
7. Embedded in a programming language	NO ✓	yes (Python DSL library)
8. CRASH could occur during analysis and / or policy enforcing	NEVER	YES
9. Execution runtime overhead	No (concurrent event stream analysis monitoring verification) ✓	Yes (Embedded Python runtime dynamic source code rewriting)
10. Persistent storage technology	Yes; "MariaDB (https://www.mariadb.org)" ✓	Yes; "PostgreSQL (https://www.postgresql.org)" ✓

Table 8 compares tabularly the "Jeeves Programming Language" and "The Runtime Monitoring Verifier Tester YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF". In contrast to the "Jeeves Programming Language" that specifies information flow policy and control enforcement for Python, YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF is not implemented as programming language feature, and thus could be used for any software system that could emit Qt-DBus signals ; Thus, information flow control and enforcement is run as a separate process, concurrently to the system under analysis (verification or monitoring) as pictured in Figure 7.

Figure 22 illustrates a sample SDMM (HTTPS://WWW.ZENODO.ORG/RECORDS/13232567) [?d] specifying that a "FILE SHALL NOT be written-updated after it HAS BEEN CLOSED-DELETED".

12.12.4 Runtime Dynamic Program Interpretation Rewriting with "Jeeves"

The information flow policy control and enforcement solution provided by the "Jeeves Programming Language" is as follows :

1. A domain-specific language (DSL) is defined and embedded in a modification of the dynamic interpreted programming language Python. The drawback of an embedded DSL is a non re-usability in using other programming languages and framework other than those related closely to Python;

2. Only certain cases are flow policy control and enforcement are solved statically by "Python-Jeeves" type system;

It means that 'false positives warnings' cases still exist in programmer code and couldn't be removed by static compilation and / or dynamic code interpretation.

In contrast, "the mixed formal methods – runtime dynamic analysis monitoring" I used in "YRI_QVGE", don't allow by construction for 'false positives warnings': A 'false positive warning' is a message from the analyzing system that indicates an error accepting state while THERE IS IN EFFECT NO ERROR found yet.

3. Flow policy enforcement is solved dynamically at runtime by dynamic code rewriting; WE HOPE that this feature could be proved sound for all program statements because it might create uncertainty of valid flow policy enforcement at all.

Differently, "YRI_QVGE" uses SQL database statement query for performing error accepting state recovery (or—also—called "Information-Flow-Policy-Control-and-Enforcement").

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES IV – CONTINUED — 2 VS. Jeeves Programming Language

12.12.5 Sample Comparison BETWEEN Object-ORIENTED programming languages”

Table 9: COMPARISON TABLE BETWEEN C++, Python, AND JAVA. JAVA has an (interpretative and / or JIT-compiled) virtual machines that are in FACT reactive systems (E.g. : A "GUI software" is as well a reactive system) ! (WYSIWYG: What You See Is What You Get; VM: Virtual Machine)

FEATURES	C++	PYTHON	Java
1. PROGRAMMING LANGUAGE PHILOSOPHY	object-oriented	object-oriented	object-oriented
2. MACROS	✓	”	
3. MULTIPLE INHERITANCE	✓		
4. support INTERFACES	✓	✓	✓
5. STATIC COMPILATION	✓	✓	
6. RUNTIME MONITORING & VERIFICATION	✓ (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF)	✓ (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF)	✓ (VM INTERPRETATION AND MANAGEMENT)
7. UNIT TESTING FRAMEWORK	✓	✓	✓
8. NETWORK CAPABLE	✓	✓	✓
9. CROSS PLATFORM PORTABLE	✓	✓	✓
10. include FILE LIBRARY CAPABILITY	✓	✓	
11. MULTI THREADING	✓	✓	✓
12. WYSIWYG GUI DESIGN TOOL	✓	”	✓
13. VIRTUAL MACHINE IS A REACTIVE SYSTEM			✓

12.12.6 "Formal Methods – Runtime Dynamic Analysis" Vs. "Compiler Static Analysis Technology"

Figure 11: Runtime Verification Monitoring with YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.

Figure 12: YERITH SDMM based runtime monitoring verification analysis.

Figure 13: A sample [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET] in action.

I advocate :

1. Solving problems using compiler static analysis technology; that is based on lattice-theory is more safe than formal methods algorithms at first because MANUAL model checking has to be used to prove formal methods solutions correct, which could be very tedious and lengthy; "OR EVEN INTRACTABLE". SEE the state explosion problem (<https://>).

On the other hand static dataflow analysis algorithms based on lattice-theory are safe by construction and don't need no more proofs of consistency and validity as long as they only follow the base-pattern algorithm as for instance defined by "Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)".

THE previous statement also applies when using an instance of a static dataflow analysis based on the IFDS (Interprocedural, Finite, Distributive, Subset) (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Inter-procedural-data-flow-analysis-with-IFDS-IDE-Bodden/a3f7557fe673ff0711e9049cf5ece8b02a51f7f1>) algorithm from "THOMAS reps" (<https://www.grammatech.com>) at "The University of Winsconsin-MADISON-mad". (<https://www.uwisconsin.edu>)

2. The formal method approach I use in solving problems listed in "Subsection 12.12.3"; a combination of formal methods with runtime dynamic analysis is as perfect as the "static dataflow analysis" standard algorithm by "Gary A. kildall", because **YRI_QVGE** uses only "fail (forbidden) traces" specifications and only exactly 1 outgoing edge for each transition in a state diagram mealy machine specification ([HTTPS://WWW.ZENODO.ORG/RECORDS/13232567](https://www.zenodo.org/RECORDS/13232567)) [?d]:

A whole class of problems involving sequencing of actions and / or method calls ranging from :

- Application Programming Interface (API) checking protocol usage;
- Software Security Vulnerability Analysis: I.E. Taint Analysis;
- Information Flow Policy Control and Enforcement: I.E. ...
- Checking of automated and / or manual (unit) test procedure conformance with regards to TESTED PROGRAM (SOFTWARE) temporal properties;
- etc.

3. Runtime Verification Analysis Results Combined With Static Dataflow Analysis Algorithms à la "Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)" as ; for instance implemented in "Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM" (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) :

- o One could combine runtime verification analysis facts with static dataflow analysis so to reduce fail state accepting code source location paths.

For instance, applying **YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF** (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/10474033>) [?b] to find an API violation rule such as a "FILE-Write-AFTER-FILE-close" as specified in Figure 22; that specifies a "SDMM DSL code ([HTTPS://WWW.ZENODO.ORG/RECORDS/13232567](https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567)) [?d]" for finding a write after close program execution :

- a.) WHENEVER such a "file Close-WRITE API rule violation usage" is found by a runtime monitoring verifying analysis program binary, this information could later on be used by a static analyzer on code sources to eliminate manually from the program code sources code the found API violation RULE.
- b.) Our work : "Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM" (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) on detecting tainted path with an application for finding API usage rule violation in C++ code as ILLUSTRATED in Figure 24, COULD be used for instance !
- c.) Symbolic Execution / test-cases-test-data generation :

WHENEVER a fail-state accepting state is found by a run execution of YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF;

- 1.) Such a run could only be executed with some test data stored somewhere in the SUT; a test case is also available for free since of the trace event log.

Such acquired test cases & test data could then be used later on to create some "testing suites" to exhibit this fail-state accepting error sequence run !

Symbolic execution run with finding of test data using a constraint solver like "Microsoft-Z3" (<https://www.microsoft.com/research--idiot--z3>) for instance, is only needed in case more test data and / or test cases are required for this fail-state accepting run.

12.12.7 CASE (Computer-Aided Software Engineering) TOOL for Software System Verification AND / OR algorithmic trading trade-time

Figure 14: A SCREENSHOT OF YERITH_QVGE FOR GRAPHICAL DESIGN OF STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE (SDMM) SPECIFICATIONS; THAT COULD SPECIFY TRADE OPERATIONS BASED ON TRADE-TIME.

Figure 15: A SCREENSHOT OF YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF SQL ERROR EVENT LOG.

1. [YERITH_QVGE] has also applications in specifying real-time trading operations based on trade-time; YERITH_{r&d} is going in the next years, to develop an algorithmic trading platform for free, Especially for exchanging inventory physical stock products (goods) for AFRICA; this is an ongoing project as an extension of the Enterprise Resource Planing SOFTWARE [YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM[?]]; [YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME].

HAVING as physical good a currency bill and / or coin is Not impossible: THIS is what we daily practice when we buy items at a cashier and / or in street rural market; So people possessing a bill and / or coin may have advantages over people having only inventory physical consumer goods for their exchanges; SO it must be that parts of markets might Not ACCEPT currency bills AND / OR coins "for equity and fairness" since not everyone can afford buying currencies and / or bills-coins at a bank and / or financial institution. !

Having to buy currencies to European UNION, for instance for CMR, is very expensive. PART of exchanges within AFRICA borders could be done just by physical product (good) exchange between people and / or governments; Especially since getting currencies bills and / or coins is very expensive.

■ RELATED work at "QUANTstamp.com"; Venture funded initially by Y-COMbinator from STANFORD.EDU (<https://www.stanford.edu>) :

QuantStamp.com (<https://www.quantstamp.com>) is a firm that works mainly on solving the main problem on 'How to verify, check, a correct con-formant "bitcoin" contract on an Ethereum-platform trading (<https://>) : a so called SmartContract (<https://www.iq.wiki/wiki/quantstamp>)'.

"Figure 20 shows in French language a similar "stock-physical exchange" architecture based on an Ethernet-network "RJ45, and / or Giga-USB;" for YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum users."

2. Create and produce a computer device that could be embedded into other computer devices and that will communicate with them through serial ports and / or USB interfaces SO to provide YRI_QVGE program verification to USER FINISHED products on-the-fly, AS an add-on ENGINEERED industrial product: ALSO this product could qualify for an ISO-related certification for avionics, railways, automotive, and CE-ISO certifications for Healthcare: [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET].

Figure 16: A sample [YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET] in action.

POTENTIAL APPLICATIONS:

- a.) "ON-the-fly (Add-hoc)" online / offline RUNTIME Verification MONITORING of all financial transaction operations at a financial institution; ATTACH a device at each computer and / or server using YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum; A comparable instance figure is illustrated for a control console device at Figure 16; WHEREAS one replaces a "control console LINAC" device with SERVER / Computer.
- b.) A linear accelerator control console communication protocol runtime monitoring (E.g.: Figure 16). A more detailed explanation graphical occurs in "Figure 11, Section 12.12.6";
- c.) A railway track controller program runtime monitoring console at site;
- d.) An aero-plane Maneuvering Characteristics Augmentation System (MCAS) runtime monitoring device
- e.) etc.

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES III (SOFTWARE SYSTEMS)

Figure 17: BUSINESS workflow of ERP software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM

Figure 18: Software System COMPONENTS workflow of ERP software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM

1. **CREATE A VERY CHEAP AND PRAGMATIC enterprise resource planing (ERP) software system** [Oct. 2015 – CURRENT] [STOCK EXCHANGE network for Francophone AFRICA; agile development method, [enterprise resource planing software], software engineering, computer software programming, computer software testing, computer program analysis]
 - a. RENDER ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANING (ERP) SOFTWARE SYSTEM USAGE AND MANIPULATION AS EASY AS READING A LEISURE OR RECREATIONAL BOOK SO TO REDUCE USER STRAIN SIZE ! (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>)
 - b. CONTRIBUTE TO REDUCE POVERTY BY IMPROVING SOFTWARE SYSTEM TECHNOLOGY FOR ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANING (ERP). (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>)
 1. All following advantages of using YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum contributes to reduce waiting files; THUS increase the number of customers and clients of an entrepreneurial organization !
 2. Best and accurate technology SHALL REDUCE management effort and produce more reliable and cost-minimized business financial accounting information that enables to anticipate and reduce time of decision making.
 - 1.) Gathering an overview over all financial and commercial; And customers / clients transaction information comes in JUST 1 button pressing from business dashboard window.
 - 2.) Exporting data onto Tabulator software such as 'MS-Excel; LibreOffice-Calc, etc.' as Comma-Separated-Values (CSV), is as easy as selecting requested database table columns and Export them by pressing a button;
 - 3.) Calculating beneficial and interests costs is just as easy as reading it from business financial dashboard report generated automatically real-time and real-data from sales and customers, and / or Acquisitions databases tables.
 3. Best and accurate technology reduces time execution of commercial business transactions, and thus, associated costs.
 - 1.) Business Intelligence (BI) : Ranking about sold and transferred goods and / or item stocks is best and just as easy done by reading it from a business commercial window dashboard; Ranking data decides what to order next for a better business turnover for your commercial financial entrepreneurial organization;
 - 2.) Ordering new item stocks is as easy as reading item stocks quantities from stocks window stock's inventory value.
 4. So entrepreneurial commercial organizations could reduce a selling price without reducing its profit.

14.14 R&D Software System Components

- o YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET [docs]
- o YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0 [algo] [docs] [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0)
- o YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-CONFIGURATIONS-DATA [algo] [docs] <https://zenodo.org/records/14868175>
- o YERITH-ERP-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM [algo] [docs] YERITH-ERP-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM[27.27] ([git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9))
- o YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RM-SYSTEM [algo] [docs] [YRI_QVGE\[?\] \(git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif\)](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif)
- o YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-HR-SERVICE-DAEMON [algo] [docs] [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-hr-service-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-hr-service-daemon)
- o YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON [algo] [docs] [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)
- o YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RT-SYSTEM [algo] [docs] **TODO for YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME !!!**

14.14.1 Detailed Presentation View

1. **HARDWARE device for on-the-fly runtime verification monitoring:** [to..come.on..github.com/yerithrd](https://github.com/yerithrd) (https://github.com/yerithrd) ★ YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET.
2. **ERP software itself:** FOSS code location; **WARNING : we migrate 'varchar(256)' into 'varchar(50) mostly' !** [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0) ★ YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.
3. **Component 1:** ★ "yerith-erp-9-0-configurations-data": **Configuration data for YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.**
 - This software component entails:
 - A configuration property file "yerith-erp-9-0.properties" that contains MariaDB database connection parameters data.
 - A configuration property file "yerith-erp-9-0-system-local-configuration-ENGLISH.properties" that contains local computer device and storage configuration parameters data.
 - A folder "yerith-erp-9-0-sql-backup-restore" where YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM database backups will be stored.
4. **Component 2:** ★ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM[27.27]: **Web Sites Generator Software Component.** [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9)
5. **Component 3:** ★ [YRI_QVGE\[?\]: Runtime Monitoring Analysis Verification System.](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang)
 - FOSS code location 1 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang)
 - FOSS code location 2 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif)
 - FOSS code location 3 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif)
 - FOSS code location 4 [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_UNIT_TESTS](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_UNIT_TESTS)
6. **Component 4:** ★ "yerith-erp-9-0-hr-service-daemon": **Service daemon for human resources related payments.** [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-hr-service-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-hr-service-daemon)
7. **Component 5:** ★ "yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon": **Service daemon for alerts over inventory stocks, assets, and financial expenses.** [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES III (Software Systems) – CONTINUED — 2 – "ALGORITHMS CREATED / INVENTED"

1. CREATE A VERY CHEAP AND PRAGMATIC *enterprise resource planing software (ERP)* [Oct. 2015 – CURRENT]
 [STOCK EXCHANGE network for Francophone AFRICA, agile development method, enterprise resource planing software, software engineering, computer software programming, computer software testing, computer program analysis]

15.15 Summary of Created And / Or Invented ALGORITHMS in this ERP Project

Figure 19: *Manager Main Window in YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum*

- YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0 ◇git <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0>
 1. *Algorithms to select each ERP sale-service function within only 1 window frame.* ["src/windows/yerith-erp-entrer-window.*"] Qt 5.
 2. *Pagination algorithms based on table data structure ("QTableView")* ["src/windows/yerith-erp-window-commons.*"] Qt 5.
 3. *Printing & Creation of PDF documents based on LaTeX documentation system* ["src/utlis/print_latex_pdf"] C++; Qt 5; LaTeX.
 4. *Automatic SQL upgrade of database between versions of YERITH-ERP-9.0* [folder "yerith-erp-9-0-upgrade-sql/"] Bash; SQL.
- YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-CONFIGURATIONS-DATA 📄 <https://zenodo.org/records/14868175>
- YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM ◇git <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9>
- YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RM-SYSTEM ◇git <https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>
- YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-HR-SERVICE-DAEMON ◇git <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon>
- YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON ◇git <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon>
- YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RT-SYSTEM TODO for YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME !!!

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES III (Software Systems) – CONTINUED — 2 – "DOCUMENTATION"

1. CREATE A VERY CHEAP AND PRAGMATIC *enterprise resource planing software* (ERP)

[Oct. 2015 – CURRENT]

[STOCK EXCHANGE network for Francophone AFRICA, agile development method, enterprise resource planing software, software engineering, computer software programming, computer software testing, computer program analysis]

16.16 Summary Documentation of YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM

Figure 20: *Generic Schema of Trading Realtime with YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum (French language)*

■ YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET (HARDWARE device for on-the-fly runtime verification monitoring)

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0

◆ [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0)a. *Database network connectivity – FRENCH*

Configuration MULTI-SITES (SUCCURSALES)

https://www.archive.org/download/yerith-erp-multi-sites-base-de-donnees/YERITH-ERP_multi_sites_base_de_donnees.pdfb. *Installation GUIDE – FRENCH*

Installation GUIDE – FRENCH

<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8060217>

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-CONFIGURATIONS-DATA

📄 <https://zenodo.org/records/14868175>

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-WEB-SYSTEM

◆ [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9)

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RM-SYSTEM

◆ [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif)

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-HR-SERVICE-DAEMON

◆ [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON

◆ [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)

■ YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0-RT-SYSTEM

TODO for YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME !!!

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES II – Dissertation Thesis Doctor–PH.D. in Electrical & Computer Engineering

Figure 21: YERITH-SAINT (LGPL license) : Accessing JAVA code with "Polyglot LLVM frontend"

A Mealy Machine State Diagram (SDMM) Specified Using Figure 22: YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF Specification Language for NO-WRITE-AFTER-CLOSE memory check API file usage rule.

```

1. yri_sd_mealy_automaton_spec YERITH_QVGE_sample_Write_after_close_file
2. {
3.   START_STATE(closed):IN_PRE(g, is_alias(g, f))
4.   -> [in_set_trace('DELETE.file.f', STATE(closed))] / 'UPDATE.file.g' ->
5.     FINAL_STATE(WRITE_AFTER_CLOSE):IN_POST(g, is_alias(g, f)).
6. }

```

1. Create A FRAMEWORK FOR STATIC verification of Temporal Safety Property in Plugin-based software by static dataflow analysis mainly for the JVM-Java Virtual Machine; by late **Gary A. KILDALL** (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gary_Kildall).

a. **Research Proposal (Doctoral Ph.D. Thesis) in Electrical & Computer Engineering :**

🔗 **"Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software;"** (Advised by **Nomair Naem** | **Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D.** | **Patrick Lam, Ph.D.**) |

[UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA]

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

YERITH_{R&D}, CENTER REGION, CAMEROON — (ADDENDUM WITH STATE DIAGRAM MEALY

[June 2024 – June 2024]

MACHINE (🔗 SDMM (https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf)[?d]))

[Software Safety, API (application programming interfaces) tpestate checking;, tracematches, computer software static program analysis, computer software dynamic program analysis, software testing, software integration testing, computer software cyber-security, GERMAN STYLE HABILITATION]

17.17 RESEARCH WORK OVERVIEW

THIS IS A PRELIMINARY WORK ON CHECKING TEMPORAL SAFETY PROPERTIES USING A TRACEMATCH-ALIKE SPECIFICATION LANGUAGE; SOOT (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>) AND DATAFLOW ANALYSIS IS USED TO PRESENT A STATIC WHOLE PROGRAM ANALYSIS.

TRACEMATCHES alike specifications enable developers to specify API usage rule drawing, as a deterministic finite automaton (<https://www.wikipedia.org>). Patrick LAM and Xavier noumbissi NOUNDOU have at this effect presented short overview slides of 30 minutes at IBM workshop CASCON 2010 ! (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>). PDFSAM (<https://www.pdfsam.org>), and sample other Open Source Code Software (FOSS) ARE USED as benchmark for project evaluation.

18.18 SOLUTIONS WITH LLVM BY CHRIS LATTNER AT "APPLE LTD."

Instead of the 1st proposed Java-Soot approach as a whole program static dataflow analysis, a whole program context-sensitive dataflow static taint analysis for C using LLVM could successfully be implemented and described in 🔗 YERITH-SAINT (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) [23].

The 1st YERITH-SAINT algorithm was implemented for programs written in C programming language, and used a pre-processing step for analyzing points-to set using "poolalloc" (<https://github.com/poolalloc>) from Chris Lattner (<https://www.llvm.org>).

BECAUSE our static dataflow taint analysis algorithm works on three-address-code, LLVM compiler framework could also apply YERITH-SAINT to JAVA code as input programming language to LLVM frontend-compiler-framework (Example : <https://github.com/polyglot-compiler/JLang>); See for instance Figure 21 !

19.19 RELATED WORK: DYNAMIC PROGRAM ANALYSIS API-RULE CHECKER "TRACERORY"

"Unread memory verification" is an instance of API (Application Programming Interface) usage rule checking.

""TRACERORY" runtime unread memory verification tool of Jon Eyolfson" (<https://www.hdl.handle.net/10012/6206>) ; "Detecting Unread Memory Using Dynamic Binary Translation at RV 2013 in Turkey" (<https://www.YRITOLLOOKFOR.org>) , Of my former office roommate at "ECE-Waterloo-formal-method Davis Center Room" (<https://www.watform.uwaterloo.ca>), 1st floor, and colleague in static dynamic program analysis, could be outperformed with use of 🔗 YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/10474033>) [?b]: "a runtime monitor container for state diagram mealy machines (SDMM)".

"TRACERORY" uses runtime program binary code instrumentation in "INTEL-Pin" (<https://www.intel.com>) to instrument running programs for purposes of detecting unread memory; I ignore whether "INTEL-Pin" (<https://www.intel.com>) has an open-source FOSS competitor at time yet; — Jan. 15, 2025 —.

Figure 22 illustrates a sample "SDMM" specification with instrumentation of source code with statements 'DELETE.file.f' and 'UPDATE.file.g' for runtime verification monitoring of API usage rule for checking memory write integrity: Runtime function "is_alias(g, f)" tells whether heap variable "g", and "f" refers to the same memory address. Such a "SDMM" specification is synchronized against a running program within a runtime monitor container: YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>) .

20.20 CONCLUSION

"Due to incompatibilities with Patrick LAM; after March 10, 2015, I abandoned this research idea because I couldn't afford being laid-off without any letter or any other formal mean of communication other than telling a lie about a supposed ["Ph.D. Research Seminar"] at EIT building in Waterloo main (200 University Ave West) Campus! " (Ph.D. Dissertation Defence at DAVID R. Cheriton School OF Computer Science in "January 2015")

It is easier to specify forbidden-fail-traces instead of saying how traces shall be like. Required 2 courses from overall 4 courses to pass where completed in year 2013-(CS846 & ECE750); in addition to before Examination completed courses (ECE725 & CS744). 4 experts in software systems were committee members of my doctoral PhD comprehensive examination AT UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA :

1. Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D.

2. Derek Rayside, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)

3. Patrick Lam, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)

4. Lin Tan, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)

Email: olhotak@cs.uwaterloo.ca

Email: drayside@uwaterloo.ca

Email: p23lam@uwaterloo.ca

Email: lintan@purdue.edu

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (COURSES VISITED – AT THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. Courses I VISITED while at the University–racist of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

[ECE 725 / CS 745 – "Fall 2009",
CS 744 – "SPRING 2011",
First SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques – "SPRING 2011",
Computer Science related subjects courses,
program analysis,
program verification,
model checking,
compiler design]

Summary–PAGES

Table 10: Visited Courses at THE university-racist of waterloo, ontario, canada-idiot

"Course Reference CODE" / "GRADE"	Period of YEAR	Course TITLE	Dispensing Department / SCHOOL
1. "ECE 725 - Nancy Day" / "90%"	Fall 2009	Computer–Aided VERIFICATION	ECE (ELECTRICAL & Computer engineering)
2. "CS 744 - Ondřej Lhoták" / "86%"	SPRING 2011	Advanced Compiler Design	CS (School of Computer Science)
3. "1 st SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques" / "N.A"	SPRING 2011	First SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques	menlo–racist–college (https://fm.cs1.sri.com/SSFT11/index.shtml)

Table 10 illustrates all courses I VISITED successfully during my doctoral Ph.D. in electrical & COMPUTER engineering degree program at the UNIVERSITY-white-racist of waterloo.

- 1.) [Visited courses as a post-doctoral researcher.]

- 2.) [Advanced Compiler Design]:

This project–racist–based course gave me the opportunity to learn perfection my theoretical knowledge and foundations in the following topics:

- COMPILER structure and optimizations

- 3.) [Computer–Aided VERIFICATION]:

This assignment-based course gave me the opportunity to learn foundations of the following topics:

- MANUAL THEOREM proving (also interactive theorem proving with "interactive theorem prover" ISABELLE–HOL (HIGH ORDER LOGIC))
- MODEL checking (EDMUND clarke et al.)
- Temporal LOGIC

The course instructor NANCY idiot day, was very verse in this material and could answer almost all questions without searching somewhere else than herself.

- 4.) [1st SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques]:

This marvelous experience gave myself opportunities to meet and hear-listen from best talented researchers in following areas of industrial research among other topics that I CANNOT ALL REMEMBER :

- "Interactive Theorem Proving with PVS"
- "Static Analysis by Abstract Interpretation"
- "Hardware / Software Co–Design"
- "Model Checking with JPF (JAVA PATHFINDER)"

I AM ALWAYS GRATEFUL to professor idiot NANCY day for having given myself this marvelous experience through her personal recommendation, As required for admission in the summer school !

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (COURSES VISITED AS POST-DOCTORAND-FELLOW – AT THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. [Courses I VISITED while at the University-racist of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA] |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2012 – Apr. 2015]

[ECE 750 – "SPRING 2013",
CS 846 – "WINTER 2013",
Online Software Security Course-racist-extreme – "WINTER 2013",
Computer Science related subjects courses,
program analysis,
program verification,
model checking,
Cyber-SECURITY-analysis,
compiler design]

Summary-PAGES

Table 11: Visited Courses as post-doctoral researcher professor at THE university-racist of waterloo, ontario, canada-idiot

"Course Reference CODE" / "GRADE"	Period of YEAR	Course TITLE	Dispensing Department / SCHOOL
1. "ECE 750 - Patrick Lam" / "88%"	SPRING 2013	Static Analysis for Software Engineering (SASE)	ECE (ELECTRICAL & Computer engineering)
2. "CS 846 - FRANK Tip" / "88%"	WINTER 2013	Program Analysis for Web Apps	CS (School of Computer Science)
3. "Online Software Security Course-racist-extreme" / "85%"	WINTER 2013	Online Software Security Course-racist-extreme	Stanford university adult education online

Table 11 illustrates all courses I VISITED successfully during my doctoral PH.D. studies degree program in Electrical & Computer Engineering at the UNIVERSITY-white-racist of waterloo.

1.) [Program Analysis for Web Apps]:

THIS project-based course provided myself an opportunity to DISCOVER, design and implement a web-based dynamic TAINT analysis for a PHP-JAVA interpreter; I.E. a "JAVA application server" that also interprets and use PHP libraries and code :

📄 "A Dynamic Taint Analysis for PHP in Quercus" (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051621/>) :

1. 📄 [git https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis](https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis)
2. 📄 [git https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis-tests](https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis-tests)

2.) [Static Analysis for Software Engineering (SASE)]:

THIS project-based course provided myself an opportunity to design and implement a static TAINT dataflow analysis: 📄 YERITH-SAINT (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293/>) :

- o 📄 [git https://github.com/sazzad114/saint](https://github.com/sazzad114/saint)

I didn't appreciate that instructor PATRICK-lam came to contest my Correct and Righteous definition of taint source and taint sink in front of class during my presentation; AND THAT he was wrong when he said we shall check the internet media; IT DOESN'T make sense to contest something that a doctor-PH.D. has prepared at least 4 weeks in advance such as he did !!!

3.) [Online Software Security Course-racist-extreme]:

I took this software security course to acquire more knowledge in software security vulnerability analysis and detection from a pioneer-leader as university in this area of research as demonstrated by publications and startups created by alumni.

MONICA-lam (<https://stanford.edu/suif>) for instance is a very renowned scholar and tech-entrepreneur in security vulnerability research and analysis. This online web course was very interesting from a content point of view for me as a doctor-of-engineering-ph.d..

ESPECIALLY because I WAS working on my "YERITH-SAINT algorithm" (https://www.archive.org/download/jh-nissi-ece-uwaterloo-grad-talk-2014-04-16/JH_NISSI_ECE_UWATERLOO_GRAD_TALK_2014_04_16.pdf) FOR detecting, with static dataflow code analysis "à la "Gary A. Kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)", and fixing the HEARTBLEED-security breach bug in "OpenSSL-1.0.1-f" source code (<https://heartbleed.com>) :

- o 📄 [git https://github.com/sazzad114/saint](https://github.com/sazzad114/saint)

"BUT i could notify when i started passing the online examination for getting a printed sent per mailbox certificate; THAT there was a kind of re-make in another stand so "that I WOULD NEVER PASS with more than 95%" as required to acquire that certificate – (I HAD PAID around \$500 USA dollars for attending this online graduate adult education course)" !!! "

"I Was almost always getting a "84% grade" ("3 times") ! THIS actually represents the successful passing required academic grade for a doctoral level course at WATERLOO."

"I HAD EVEN visited the premises of STANFORD university together with SANDY-beidu-gay-idiot-from-ghana-cuon-pd "in year 2011" while attending a formal method techniques school at AHERTON-COLLEGE nearby "by around 40 minutes drive"."

YEARS "09 / 2009" – "2010"

SUMMARY-PAGES

- I have prepared, and presented a static dataflow analysis in November 2010 at **IBM workshop CDP CASCON 2010** (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>).

[Workshop-CDP; IBM casCon 2010]

The goal of this static dataflow analysis was to solve the issue of temporal property API rule checking in Plugin-based software.

- I co-taught and assigned marked with Patrick for courses:
 1. "Programming for Performance (ECE 459)";
 2. "Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465)".
- I have successfully attended the course ("CS 745 / ECE 725") – **Computer-Aided Verification** (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~nday>), taught by "Prof. Dr. Nancy Day". I could learn about following topics:

COURSE-ECE 725

THIS psy-professor is somewhat "a culprit of canadian armed robber forces only for black-descendants; Including iranian; holy-bible-CYRUS-ISIAH-45" (<https://www.sainteibible.com/lsg/isaiah/45.htm>).

1. OCAML functional programming language
 2. Propositional Logic
 3. First Order Logic (Predicate logic)
 4. Higher Order Logic (Lambda Calculus) "with Haskell"
 5. Theorem Proving
 6. Interactive Theorem Proving with "Isabelle HOL"
 7. Model Checking (with use of "SMV model checker")
 8. etc.
- *I have met in-person "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Nomair Naeem" (HELP with understanding of static dataflow analysis algorithms): "Especially with context-sensitive parametric analysis".*
 - *I have as roommate and best-friend [Diplom-Ingenieur-Informatik (Dipl.-Ing.-Inf.)] THOMAS REIDEMEISTER, 'aus MAGDEBURG'. He is also a computer engineer graduate student "in ECE at THE university of Waterloo, ON".*

THOMAS (<https://www.reidemeister.com>) is so much helping to myself including recommending myself a "JAPANESE toyota corolla LE 2003-(plate BLAB 045)" car as buying tip because of low costs in maintenance in ontarian-Canada.

I learned at least 80% of a happyfull life in ontarian Canada from THOMAS as a kind of senior brother of mine.

- (a) Difference between brunch and lunch; with an invitation for a brunch in KITCHENER: I cannot remember the name of this very nice restaurant by a sunday-morning;
- (b) Farmer's market in Kitchener;
- (c) * * *—**Asian food market stores in Kitchener**—* * *;
- (d) etc.

"THOMAS moved-in into our student house as replacement for a nigerian so called CHRISTIAN-faked TOMIWA ADAMURULA (tom)."

"AS I have matured myself, "today, in 2024, "September 1st;" THOMAS must be from NAZI-ss-combat engineering against black-descendants like "cameroonian MARTIN tchangoue", employed at LABFORGE.CA (<https://www.labforge.ca>)".

I could remember being very happy all time with * * *—**JOHN and ANNA GULDEMOND**—* * * the sweet-nice landlords.

20.20 YEARS "09 / 2009" – "2010"

SUMMARY-PAGES

— I have met in-person Prof. Dr. Eric Bodden at our (Xavier, JON eyolfson) office room in "Davis Center".

— I have improved my technical skills in following areas by reading technical reports and conference articles:

1. "**Program Verification (Ph.D. thesis from Patrick LAM)**" (<https://patricklam.ca>)
2. Algorithm Design, and Implementation (from book "**Introduction to Algorithms**" ([https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gary_Kildall](https://www.amazon.com/Introduction-Algorithms-fourth-Thomas-Cormen/dp/026204630X/ref=sr_1_1?crid=2UBHH37C2Y2J3&dib=eyJ2IjoiMSJ9.RxrAGDmePG_uPSHKskT1qe4eJp18_sU0zfGdVfEd1BzcVOqunH6HMFdUvjfBk5T7_hbHBgRqWHVSmsYFd00P9qIyOhMwCdwVMeRQodxABI7cszQQi1XxeWBU8jZqpGALecudSCyPct_N4de9gwlldrRqHL2Alh8huCTZ2PeIoFPH8JLCoU0jaTq8vuQ-G7z1Jdit5yRk2hl627B7GRAFVG3fiolk8kSGbcuK5_JsFw6g.AobHaMGD2q1MBzQIcdziArWAZLVbUQztj2REK1DRJ0Y&dib_tag=se&keywords=CS+Algorithm+book&qid=1726183252&s=books&prefix=cs+algorithm+book%2Cstripbooks-intl-ship%2C313&sr=1-1));)
3. Deterministic and Nondeterministic finite automata theory;
4. JAVA and its virtual machine;
5. Static Dataflow Analysis by Gary A. KILDALL (<a href=));
 - a. **SOOT framework** (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>);
 - b. "**Tracematches formalism by Hendren, Lhoták, et al.**" (<https://plg.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak/pubs/rv07.pdf>)

— *I have attended following workshops and conferences:*

[IBM WORKSHOP-CDP CASCON 2010]

1. "**IBM workshop CDP CASCON 2010**" (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>)"
 - a. I could talk briefly with Patrick Doyle from **J9-JAVA** (<https://www.ibm.com/docs/en/configurepricequote/10.0?topic=machines-j9-jvm>) JIT-compilation team at IBM Toronto Software Lab
 - b. **Maxime Boisvert Chevallier** (<https://scholar.google.ca/citations?user=1Sg6I8gAAAAJ&hl=en>)
2. "*I have reviewed technical & scientific papers for **OOPSLA 2010**" (https://dl.acm.org/action/showFmPdf?doi=10.1145%2F1869459&ved=2ahUKEwiboY0Exb6IAxXdgP0HHfm0A2YQFnoECCIQAQ&usg=AOvVaw0DwvwxPorXI7v__J6preu)."*

[OOPSLA 2010]

3. "*I have attended the conference "**Programming Language Design And Implementation (PLDI 2009)**" in Toronto.*"

[International CONDEFERENCE-pldi-racist-extreme; PLDI 2009]

- **Pr. Prof. Dr. JEAN yang, she was a then Ph.D. student and candidate at "MIT"** (<https://people.csail.mit.edu/jeanyang/index.htm>) " (<https://www.cs.cmu.edu/~jyang2>) .
- "**Nurudeen Lameed (from Nigeria)**" (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~nlamee>), "and other **SABLE-mcgill**" (<https://sable.mcgill.ca>) graduate students" and I presented to each other;
- "**Pr. Prof. Dr. Tom Ball from Microsoft Research (MSR)**" (<https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/people/tball>), and I presented each other.
- "**Florian Zuleger (from Austria)**" (<https://informatics.tuwien.ac.at/people/florian-zuleger>), and I presented each other.
- "**Stephan Zucker, PhD (from Switzerland)**" (<https://>), and I presented each other.

21.21 YEAR "2011"

Summary-PAGES

— "December 20th, 2011":

I have prepared and successfully passed my doctoral PhD comprehensive examination in front of at least 4 experts in Software System:

1. Prof. Dr. Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D.
2. Prof. Dr. Derek Rayside, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)
3. Prof. Dr. Patrick Lam, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)
4. Prof. Dr. Lin Tan, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (PEng, Ontario)

— I co-taught and assigned marked with Patrick for course:

1. "Programming for Performance (ECE 459)".

— I have successfully attended the course "CS 744" – *Advanced Compiler Design* (<https://plg.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak/cs744>), taught by "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Ondřej Lhoták".

I could learn about following topics:

1. **SOOT framework** (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>)
2. Meet Over Paths (MOP)
3. Basic Block (BB), Control Flow Graph (CFG)
4. Three-Address-Code ("3-Address-Code")
5. Static Single Assignment Form ("SSA form")
6. Pointer (Alias) Analysis
7. Static Dataflow Analysis by **Gary A. KILDALL** (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gary_Kildall);
8. Transfer flow functions
9. Components of an advanced Compiler (E.g.: Optimizer, backend, etc.)

COURSE-CS 744

— I have met in-person "Michael Pradel". (https://software-lab.org/people/Michael_Pradel.html)— I have met in-person "ALEXIE tcheuyap-idiot-cuon-pd". (<https://discover.research.utoronto.ca/12279-alexie-tcheuyap>)

— *I have, in summer 2011, received a personal visit of "Mae Wandji", baby of my uncle maternal "Théodore & Aurélie Wandji Yagno Kamdoum": she was accompanied by "her mother Aurélie Yagno Wandji" ! "Mae Wandji", and her mother "Aurélie Wandji Yagno Kamdoum", I dedicate a successful PhD comprehensive examination ! "*

— I have met in-person Prof. Dr. MARTIN vechev. (<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=aZ1Rh50AAAAJ&hl=fr>)

— I attended successfully the summer school: "First Summer School on Formal Techniques" (<https://fm.cs.sri.com/SSFT11/index.shtml>); organized by The "National Science Foundation (NSF)" located at SOFTWARE RESEARCH INSTITUTE INTERNATIONAL (SRI International), at "Menlo College, Atherton, California, USA" from May 22, 2011 until May 27, 2011.

[ATHERTON-COLLEGE] / ["1st Summer School on Formal Techniques"-2011]

Topics we learned about and practiced where among others:

- o "Interactive Theorem Proving with PVS" (by "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Natarayan Shankar")
- o "Static Analysis by Abstract Interpretation" (by "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. David Moniaux")
- o "Hardware / Software Co-Design"
- o "Model Checking with JPF (JAVA PATHFINDER)" (by "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Villem WISSER-neger-racist-stelenbosch-university-SA")

— I have improved my technical skills in following areas by reading technical reports and conference articles:

1. Algorithm Design, and Implementation (from book "Introduction to Algorithms" ([Holy-Ghost. YERITH-NISSI. \(JEOVAH-NISSI IN HEAVEN.\)](https://www.amazon.com/Introduction-to-Algorithms-fourth-Thomas-Cormen/dp/026204630X/ref=sr_1_1?crid=2UBHH37C2Y2J3&dib=eyJ2IjoiMSJ9.RxrAGDmePG_uPSHKskT1qe4eJp18_sU0zfGdVFed1BzcVOqunH6HMFduvjfBk5T7_hbHBgRqWHVSmsYFd00P9qIyOhMwCdwVMeRQodxABI7cszQQi1XxeWBU8jZqpGALecudSCyPct_N4de9gwldrRqhL2Alh8huCTZ2PeIoFPH8JLCoU0jaTq8vuQ-G7z1Jdit5yRk2hl627B7GRAFGV3fiolk8kSGbcuK5_JsFw6g.AobHaMGD2q1MBzQIcdziArWAZLVbUQztj2REK1DRJ0Y&dib_tag=se&keywords=CS+Algorithm+book&qid=1726183252&s=books&prefix=cs+algorithm+book%2Cstripbooks-intl-ship%2C313&sr=1-1));
2. Deterministic and Nondeterministic finite automata theory;
3. JAVA component-based software development by OSI architecture and Eclipse IDE (Integrated Development Environment);
4. JAVA and its virtual machine;

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22.22 YEAR "2012"

Summary-PAGES

- I co-taught and assigned marked with Patrick & Derek Rayside & Jon Eyolfson & Leo Passos, etc. for courses:
 1. "Compilers (ECE 351)": *Python scripts were written to automatically correct programming assignments from code source repositories.*
- *I went for an academic and professional internship at IBM Toronto Software Lab;*

I wanted to improve my programming languages design and implementation skills as well as BASH-scripting.

I spent 2 Academic terms (8 months) in Markham (Ontario, Canada) for this internship.

I worked there under supervision of [*Patrick Doyle, M.A.Sc.*,] and then "*Prof. Vijay Sundareshan, M.Sc.*".

 - o I worked principally as a tester for certain optimization features of the "J9 JIT compiler" for the JAVA application server (Servlet container) *IBM Websphere* (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/IBM_WebSphere_Application_Server) under "*Prof. Vijay Sundareshan, M.Sc.*". I was writing BASH-scripts to run and evaluate implemented certain optimization features for the "J9 JIT compiler" for the JAVA application server.
 - o I could attend to lectures given at IBM Toronto Software Lab by "*Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Clark Verbrugge*" (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump>) from "*McGill University*" on Creating Optimizations for Compilers.
 - o I could improve my skills with the following tools among others:
 1. "GNU-bash" (<ftp://ftp.gnu.org/pub/gnu/bash>)
 2. "GNU-vi / GNU-vim" (<https://www.vim.org>)
 3. "GNU-screen" (<https://savannah.gnu.org/projects/screen>).
- "*Prof. Vijay Sundareshan, M.Sc.*" wanted myself to be back next summer for another internship with him at IBM: unfortunately I resigned from this engagement because I felt I had to go back in my home country: Cameroon !
- I befriended myself at IBM with "*Aayush Prakash, M.A.Sc. (Waterloo, 2013)*" (<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=hUXGzpgAAAAJ&hl=en>).
 1. I had a toyota corolla 2007 LUXUS EDITION; that's why Aayush PRAKASH 1st contacted me so I could help him mornings.

I tried trice but I COULDN'T anymore because I COULDN'T wake up so early; because MARKHAM is a very big city with so much traffic. BUT WE STAYED friend for ever.

THX. BRO.
 2. We then became roommate in Waterloo the following fall (September – December) term; I COULD appreciate someone nice and very comfortable with my living style since I am the one that was principally renting the 2-bedroom apartment on 16-457 ALBERT-STREET.

HE never not paid his subrent; and was also kind to learn more about how to better maintain a common washroom.

THEN he moved to IBM after successfully graduating with a M.A.Sc. in Electrical & Computer Engineering from PROFESSOR-racist HIREN-patel-racist !

I then went several times to visit AAYUSH when he moved to Toronto.
- I befriended myself in Toronto with the following fellow Cameroonian:
 1. "~~Prof. Dr. Alexie Tcheyap, Ph.D. (Laval, "French Literature", Quebec, Canada, 2008)~~" (~~GAY-maker-assassin !~~) (<https://discover.research.utoronto.ca/12279-alexie-tcheyap>);
 2. "Erick Djeuyou Pokem, B.A.Sc. (Lilles, "Business Informatics-MIAGE", France, 2007)";
 3. "Audrey Nguetie Tchamga, B.Sc. (Laval, "Actuarial Sciences", Quebec, Canada, 2008)";
 4. "Judith Ngaleu, B.Sc. (Montreal, "Telecommunication Engineering", Quebec, Canada, 2005)";
 5. "Eunice Gapie Yemte, B.Sc. (Luxembourg, "Software Engineering", Luxembourg, 2008)" (assassin);
 6. "Valérie Yogho, B.Sc. (Montreal, "Electrical Engineering Power", Quebec, Canada, 2008)";
 7. "Tobie Guilliane, M.Sc. (Paris, "Financial Accounting", France, 2008)" (ASSASSIN);
 8. "Francis Mbiele Kamga, MBA (ESG, "Business Management", Paris, France, 2007)" (ASSASSIN).
 9. "~~FABRICE wilfried siemeni, B.Eng., (FH-Berlin, "Food Processing Engineering", Berlin, GERMANY, 2005); Diploma (HIN, "applied HOLISTIC NUTRITIONIST", Mississauga, Toronto, Canada, 2012); -M.Sc. (FH-Berlin, "Food Processing Engineering", Berlin, GERMANY, 2006)~~" (ASSASSIN).
- *I have attended following workshops and conferences in 2012*, together with "*Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Patrick LAM, Ph.D.*" (<https://www.patricklam.ca>), after completion of the internship at IBM Toronto Software Lab (*IBM Canada Ltd* (<https://www.ibm.com>)):

[WORKSHOP-local MITACS Ontario; International CONFERENCE; PLdi 2012]

 1. "*MITACS Ontario* (<https://www.mitacs.ca>) at the University of Waterloo on how to behave properly when having lunch and dessert with other professionals."
 2. "*Programming Language Design and IMPLEMENTATION (PLDI 2012)*" (<https://>) in Toronto downtown.
 1. *I COULD TALK TO several researcher among employees of GRAMMATECH-racist-negger* (<https://www.grammatech.com>) from THOMAS-reps at WISCONSIN-madison. (<https://www.uwisconsin.edu>)

23.23 YEAR "2013"

Summary-PAGES

— I talked in-person with "Mahesh Tripunitara" about some of my non understanding about Doctor-PhD advisor of mine "Patrick Lam"; "MAHESH TRIPUNITARA" said I shall look for research collaborations within University of Waterloo and just put the name of "Patrick LAM" at end of a publication !

I AM STILL VERY GRATEFUL for this insight into my life as a scientist that led me to try and talk successfully with following pro-eminent fellow computer scientist:

- "Vijay Ganesh"; very proud of having learned much of how to write a paper and / or reviews of other papers with him; I cannot be a Ph.D. or doctor without this collaboration !

THIS IS SOMEONE very good at teaching research skills only. I cannot say much about his private behavior since I generally don't mix my private life with professional life !

- ["Mohammad Hamdaqa" from THE STAR research lab (<https://star.uwaterloo.ca>)]
- "Aayush Prakash" (<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=hUXGzpgAAAAJ&hl=en>) (from IBM internship in Markham)
- "Leo Passos" from Generative Software Development research group at university of waterloo (<https://gsd.uwaterloo.ca/~lpassos>)
- "Frank Tip" (from IBM Research then as Professor at the University of Waterloo): AT all the very much inspirational about 'A SO CALLED taint analysis' in my research area at all.

Before visiting CS846 of "Frank Tip", I cannot know anything about what is a Taint Analysis (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>) .

THIS CS846 (Program Analysis of Web Apps) is my best course as a graduate student in terms of working on related papers and writing reviews. Frank Tip is a very good and proud research manager !!!

"Only 1 tip, and you get all the clue about what you really need to do."

- "Pavel Parizek" (https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=M_9_-WsAAAAJ&hl=en) (from Programming Language Research Group (PLG) (<https://plg.uwaterloo.ca>), invited by "Ondřej Lhoták")
- "BORZOO" (<https://>) (very respected in RV conferences series)

THIS [friend-kkk] of *sebastian fischmeister from AUSTRIA-adolf-hitler* (<https://uwaterloo.ca/~sfischme>) is so kind that he let myself in his office to present what I really want to perform as research. BUT i could notify an office with kind of ground-tapestry for WHAT-the-fuck.

24.24 YEAR "2013, 2ND PAGE"

Summary-PAGES

— I co-taught and assigned marked with "Mahesh Tripunitara" and "Igor Ivkovic" for courses:

- 1.) "Computer Networks (ECE 428)";
- 2.) " * * * Foundations of Software Engineering (ECE 651) * * * "
- 3.) " * * * Methods and Tools for Software Engineering (ECE 650) * * * ".

Several employees from "Google Waterloo Inc. (<https://www.google.ca>) " attended lectures ("Foundations of Software Engineering (ECE 651)", and "Methods and Tools for Software Engineering (ECE 650)");

[DIVAM JAIN racist from CA-U.S.A. even tried to make me hired there once ...].

— I started implementing a *LLVM context-sensitive solution to my Research Proposal Thesis* (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) ; Because *SPARK pointer analysis in SOOT* (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>) didn't permit for pointer-analysis data as a stand-alone pre-processing step, as *my early design of the static dataflow analysis suggested* (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>) .

— I have successfully attended the course [Program Analysis of Web Apps ("CS 846")], taught by "Pr. Prof. Dr. Frank Tip" (<https://northeastern.edu/~ftip>). I could learn about following topics:

COURSE-CS 846

1. web applications
2. Javascript
3. dynamic analysis
4. static dataflow analysis
5. "Quercus server" dynamic taint analysis (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051621/>) [3] by practicing within a personal single project
6. scientific papers reading and comparison.

— I have successfully attended the course Static Analysis for Software Engineering (SASE) ("ECE 750"), taught by "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Patrick LAM" (<https://www.patricklam.ca>). I could learn about following topics:

COURSE-SASE-ECE 750

1. dynamic analysis
2. static dataflow analysis
3. "static taint analysis" (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) [23] by practicing within a personal single project:

"I am the only one who had this idea of performing static taint analysis, because I previously did a dynamic taint analysis in FRANK-TIP-CS846—racist-course. *THE CS OF UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO wasn't* (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca>) even capable of [finding this racist-cs846 segregative course curriculum] when I asked for it in year 2022; Even FTP, the creator of it WASN'T confident to give it to a black from AFRICA ! "

[r-IT Seems NDJATIE-from-rotary commanded again FTP from the inside.]; *EVEN her husband ["pr. shanda; YVAN-plumber-bafang-babouantou"]*, is very well recommended by YAOUNDEACS these days. (<https://>)

[AHHHH, also THE general of science KLAUS HAVELUND from N.A.S.A (<https://www.nasa.gov/YaoundeACS>) was also invited by my emails so to acquire some knowledge about [YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF] since his paper with SFISCHME wasn't very proper.] (<https://www.ece.uwaterloo.ca/~sfischme>)

4. scientific papers reading and comparison.

— I have On the website of *stanford university* (<https://www.stanford.edu>) in the state of CALIFORNIA; IN-the-U.S "unsuccessfully (with "84% grade") attended" the course *Software Security*. I could learn about following topics:

[STANFORD.EDU—online-course-software-security 2013]

1. PRIVATE / PUBLIC INFRASTRUCTURE—key (GPG); CERTIFICATE—authority
2. CYPHER DECYPHER CRYPTOGRAPHY—algorithm
3. SSL-Secure—socket—layer protocol on HTTP protocol
4. ATTACKS strategies:
 1. SQL injection
 2. Buffer—overflow attack
 3. MAN-IN-MIDDLE attack
5. etc.

25.25 YEARS "2014" – "03 / 2015"

Summary-PAGES

— I find a very imposing book that explains in my better terms algorithms fixed point static dataflow analysis à la "Gary A. Kildall : *A unified approach to global program optimization* (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>):

- "*Advanced Compiler Design*"; ISBN: "", by author from IBM: .

THIS book doesn't destroy your brain like the book:

- "*PROGRAM ANALYSIS*"; ISBN: "", by author from AMSTERDAM: .

I implemented my own static dataflow fixed point algorithm in C++ object-oriented, and I published it on my student Ph.D. page <https://ece.uwaterloo.ca/~xnoumbis>; And on my defunct GITHUB.COM-web-page:.

I then improved and finished my static dataflow taint analysis, and starts preparing my Ph.D. research seminar as presented in booklets present in "ECE graduate students room" in EIT building !

NOT very long after this online internet-web publication; I LEAVE WATFFORM for Cameroon where I created YERITH R&D, and affiliated software systems programs.

— I met Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Ondřej Lhoták (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak>) in-person for a review of my created LLVM context-sensitive static dataflow analysis: HE WAS RELUCTANT only because of 1 missing application of the analysis.

— I assisted students in the LABORATORY for coding in C++ during 2 weeks:

1. "C++ Laboratory (ECE 250)".

C++ Laboratory (ECE 250)

[!!! Iranian canadian university of waterloo professors !]!!

My colleague JON EYOLFSON (<https://jeyolfson.com>) with Prof. Dr.-Ing. Ladan (<https://ece.star.uwaterloo.ca>), went to suppress my appointment illegally since I legally, according to ECE department regulations for 2 weeks vacation for personal illness purposes, sent JON eyolfson as a replacement laboratory instructor to myself to LADAN !

I couldn't recover my job as teaching assistant in laboratory at my stay-return from JON EYOLFSON that I sent to Prof. Dr.-Ing. Ladan, for only 2 weeks replacement of myself !

— I have prepared, and presented a context-sensitive static dataflow analysis in January 2015 at a DAVID R. CHERITON SCHOOL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE programming language research group (PLG) seminar talk.

[Ph.D. Dissertation Defense at PLG]

I had this work successfully approved at PLG by "dear-racist-idiot Ondřej Lhoták" (<https://plg.uwaterloo.ca>).

The title of my talk was: *CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM* (https://www.archive.org/download/jh-nissi-ece-uwaterloo-grad-talk-2014-04-16/JH_NISSI_ECE_UWATERLOO_GRAD_TALK_2014__04__16.pdf) ; the presented application was the finding of a buffer-overflow security vulnerability in SSL (Secure Socket Layer) protocol as found in the "*HEARTBLEED bug*" (<https://heartbleed.com>) .

"Dr.-PH.D. ALI TELAGHANI was the 1st iranian university of waterloo Ph.D. Candidate I reviewed. A former trainee of nancy day from watform. (<https://www.watform.uwaterloo.ca>) "

AT THE conference presentation table were present among others :

- (a) Pr. Prof. Dr. MAGNUS MADSEN (<https://www.cs.au.dk/~magnusm>)
- (b) Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. "Peter Alan Burh" (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/about/people/pabuhr>)
- (c) etc.

— I have prepared, and successfully presented a context-sensitive static dataflow analysis on "April 16, 2014" at an ECE graduate seminar talk.

[Ph.D. Research Seminar]

The title of my talk was: *CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM* (https://www.archive.org/download/jh-nissi-ece-uwaterloo-grad-talk-2014-04-16/JH_NISSI_ECE_UWATERLOO_GRAD_TALK_2014__04__16.pdf) .

There was around at least 20 other students attending this seminar (kind of lecture).

The goal of this static dataflow analysis was to solve the issue of temporal property API rule checking in Plugin-based software by static dataflow taint analysis.

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES 2 – Dissertation Thesis Doctor–PH.D. in Electrical & Computer Engineering – continued - Hindrance

26.26 RESEARCH OUTCOME HINDRANCE

Summary-PAGES

IT WASN'T POSSIBLE TO IMPLEMENT THE STATIC WHOLE PROGRAM ANALYSIS AS PRESENTED because of the non possibility to acquire points-to information as a pre-processing standalone phase/step from SPARK POINTER ANALYSIS FRAMEWORK IN SOOT.

It wasn't in my research interest for a "Ph.D. in Electrical & Computer Engineering" to dive into recreating a pointer analysis for SOOT by modifying for instance research outcome work of "AAKARSH NAIR, MASC (2009)".

It would be more productive to perform research with "Ondřej Lhoták" in "Mathematics Department at DAVID R. CHERITON SCHOOL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE" (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak>) rather than with DR.-PH.D Patrick LAM at ECE Department. So I stayed out of this area of research for the "Ph.D. in Electrical & Computer Engineering"; Computer Software Engineering is more focused on developing methodologies around software rather than creating complex computer algorithms for calculation purposes; AS this is done in Computer Sciences (E.g.: "Ph.D. in Computer Science").

It is somehow also feasible for a "Computer Software Engineer" easily to implement a "pointer analysis as a Ph.D. in Computer Sciences could do whenever needed" !

I ("Doctor–PH.D. of Engineering Xavier Noumbissi Noundou") have, for instance demonstrated, I could at least at level of a pointer dataflow analysis design and implementation performed by implementing the 1st openly (FOSS) published on the internet (2015): [CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC DATAFLOW ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM ! \(https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293\)](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293) [23] : "git <https://github.com/sazzad114/saint>".

27.27 RESEARCH OUTCOME PLAGIARISM

Summary-PAGES

- 1st of all, I need to mention that JON eyolfson has tried to remove all connections to my person in his documents I could see on the internet media and / or wherever else.

FOR instance, JON eyolfson doesn't mention anymore he reviewed papers for OOPSLA 2010; I ASSUME because my name stays also in the document viewable from the web I COULD SEE last .. (https://dl.acm.org/action/showFmPdf?doi=10.1145%2F1869459&ved=2ahUKEwiBoY0Exb6IAxXdgP0HHfm0A2YQFnoECCIQAQ&usg=AOvVaw0DwvmxPoRXI7v__J6preu)

"Doctor–PH.D of Engineering JON EYOLFSON" (<https://www.ece.utoronto.ca/people/eyolfson-j>) could for instance implement a Gary A. KILDALL (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gary_Kildall) static dataflow pointer analysis based on my research outcome in ["XAVIER NOUMBISSI NOUNDOU'S DOCTORAL EXCERPT DISSERTATION" \(https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293\)](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293) ; Even though he didn't cite my previous work and also Gary A. KILDALL (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gary_Kildall).

Instead, HE WENT ON TO CITE "John B Kam and Jeffrey D. Ullman", in 'Monotone Data Flow Analysis Frameworks' !

I could also notify that the description of the flow functions in JON EYOLFSON's doctoral thesis, Acknowledged by "Professor Doctor–PH.D of ENGINEERING "Ana–Milanova" from RIP (Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute) (<https://www.cs.rpi.edu/~milanova>)", Wasn't compliant to the highest academical standard as IT IS DUE for a university in ONTARIO–CANADA.

"Jon" instead of performing a pre-processed step pointer analysis result searching, went on to implement a whole program static dataflow analysis, INCORPORATING an LLVM-based pointer analysis, copied from my work, Without citing it ("I finished that work in 2015", While "JON Eyolfson" defended his Ph.D. thesis containing this pointer analysis in 2018).

"I could also note it seems ["Ondřej Lhoták"] wasn't a member of JON eyolfson dissertation defence examination committee (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak>), even though HE ("Ondřej Lhoták") is the most famous scientist in this area of research at the UNIVERSITY of WATERLOO based on his publication and citation record (<https://dblp.org/pid/05/469.html>). "

2. " My intellectual and copyrighted work with "DIVAM JAIN, M.Math", now at ["Google Waterloo Inc."] (<https://jobs.google.com/about/>), has by now produced at least 11 scientific published papers worldwide, with money rewards, [without my name on neither on them.]"

INSTEAD, other people reward from it:

1. Dr. Patrick LAM;
2. Dr. Reid Holmes;
3. Dr. Derek rayside;
4. "zheng FELIX fang, M.ASc. (<https://dblp.org/pid/170/1472.html>); (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)
5. etc.

QUARRELED PAPERS:

1. "Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints" (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)

Plagiarism

28.28 RESEARCH OUTCOME PLAGIARISM – CONTINUED – 1

Summary-PAGES

1. "Professor Araving Machinry" also used code sources results from my Static Dataflow Analysis without any citation of it in his Award winning USENIX paper; I mailed him in 2017; HE said that my work wasn't published by a peer-refereed conference and/or workshop, or whatsoever, THAT'S WHY he couldn't cite it.

Instead of citing the 1st original publication of a Free and Open Source Software code (FOSS), 2015, As I have published in on 'www.github.com (git <https://github.com/sazzad114/saint>)'; ARAVIND cited instead my competitor BODDEN-ERIC (<https://www.bodden.de>) (from Germany (<https://www.fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Allemagne>) and Previous colleague of Patrick LAM (<https://www.patricklam.ca>) at McGill University (<https://www.mcgill.ca>)).

Long after terminating my research collaboration with Patrick LAM at University of Waterloo, ONTARIO, CANADA; I could then notify that he was talking especially to "ARAVIND machinry my competitor about my research under his supposed supervision without telling it to myself!"

2. A ghanaiian ignorant, wretched worldwide called SANDY-beidu thinks he could behave so to alter my JEOVAH-NISSI-confidence at his underground-peggit home in bavaria-waterloo.

BEcause I rented a "ford fusion" during my travel to the "1st summer school on formal techniques" in ATHERTON, california; So to be mobile because I HAD TRAVELED to united states of america before when I WAS an employee of bavarian Siemens-medical-solutions; THIS guja went on to buy as his 1st car a similar "ford fusion" since he thought I WANTED to show up in front of him and ANOTHER black-afro-descendant from long-islands.

I AM EVEN wondering how this lady from basement science could be invited to the summer school ! AT ALL ! may be a call-girl !

FROM academic level point of view, this ignorant doctor of philosophy in computer science, SeEms to ignore what I COULD BUILD AS [enterprise resource planing (ERP-system) software !!!!!!!!]

3. JAN peleska from GERMANY, didn't say anything about the law against myself in Cameroon because he is the one who went to report false behaviors of myself to Cammeroon authorities about my living style in Germany without telling anything to me about.

Even at German Embassy in Yaounde, I could notify a strange behavior of people working there against myself while I came to complain against FRANGK-BIYA, son of PAUL-BIYA. THIS-GAY-with-my eousin-PATRICE-CABRAL-SHANDA-SANOUE (deceased by now since March 18, 2024 went to destroy my investment by creating a forestry society just opposite of my lawful building for peaceful habitation usage) !

JAN peleska from GERMANY, also seems to be the one that said and commanded PATRICK LAM to destroy my career because I reluctantly refused to pursue doctoral Ph.D. research (<https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/gesy>) under his supervision at the University of Bremen; I.E. Jan peleska insulted violently myself in front of HELGE LOEDING (<https://www.LOEDING-ONLINE.de>), SERGE FOPOUSSI NONO ACHILLE (<https://www.deutsche-digitale-bibliothek.de/person/gnd/141875240>), etc.

[Chandriand TEUNTCHOU noumeni] later on-in year 2012 get married with a uterine sister of mine called Ingrid tchitchui noumbissi; HE has tried since to put myself in psychiatric cage via my sister and my mother as reported in judicial information section of this curriculum vitae !!!

GERMANY seems to want to defeat any black intelligentsia outside of a "psychiatric cyclops" so to destroy the brain of black race from West- & Central- Africa !!!

I cannot live with racial segregation !

Figure 23: YERITH-SAINT ([LGPL license]) Algorithms Architecture. "poolalloc" pointer-alias analysis tool from "Chris Lattner" at "APPLE Ltd." is re-used.

Figure 24: A sample *API rule violation* as tainted path "close(fd) => write(fd, &sum, sizeof(i)) L4—L7—L9—L10—L11" (orange colored lines of code); on LLVM THREE-ADDRESS-CODE.

```

1  ssize_t write(int fd, const void *buf, size_t count); // taint sink
3  uint SAVE_Document (unsigned x, int fd, const void *buf, size_t count) {
4  L1: uint sum = 0;
5  L2: uint i = 0;
6  L3: if (x == 2)
7  L4: close(fd); //taint source; "close(fd) => write(fd, &sum, sizeof(i))"
8  L5: else //not VALID api rule check!
9  L6: sum = 0;
10 L7: if (i >= x)
11 L8: goto L12;
12 L9: sum = sum + i;
13 L10: i = i + 1;
14 L11: write(fd, &sum, sizeof(i));
15 L12: goto L6;
16 L13: return sum; }

```

1. Create A FRAMEWORK FOR STATIC verification of [Temporal Safety Property in Plugin-based software by taint analysis] – Continued

b. Doctoral "Ph.D. degree" Dissertation in Electrical & Computer Engineering: "Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM"; (Advised by Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Nomair Naeem | Pr. Prof. Dr. Ondřej Lhoták | Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Frank Tip | Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Patrick Lam | Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Vijay Ganesh) |

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[SEP. 2012 – AUG. 2015]

YERITH_{R&D}, CENTER REGION, CAMEROON — (ADDENDUM WITH TYPESTATE-API USAGE RULE CHECKING; STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE (SDMM)[?d]))

[JUNE 2024 – JUNE 2024]

[Software Safety, API (application programming interfaces) tystate checking, tracematches, temporal safety property verification, cyber-security, software security vulnerability analysis, computer software static program analysis, computer software dynamic program analysis, software testing, software integration testing, GERMAN STYLE HABILITATION, Disputation-january-2015-DC-room-PETER-ALAN-BUHR]

The same class of problems that solve taint analysis issues resolve also API usage rules checking for specification of forbidden usage rules as a tystate specification. A violated API tystate (tracematch-alike) usage rule corresponds to a tainted path or a sub-tainted path (E.g.: path "L4—L7—L9—L10—L11" in Figure 24).

You specify a forbidden (fail trace) [sequence of method calls that shall not occur in the source code]. Using static dataflow taint analysis, you check whether this specified forbidden (fail trace) corresponds to a tainted path or a subpath (of a fail trace).

"API (application programming interfaces) usage rules [tystate formalism is a similar paradigm of specification possible for input for this static context-sensitive taint analysis; "subsequent research of mine alone reveals state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) as a subset of tystates (SDMM[?d],".] of JAVA or C++ library are another realm of application of this static context-sensitive (parametric) dataflow taint analysis."

"In contrast to Tracematches that specifies WISHED BEHAVIOR (PROGRAM TRACE) of API user interface rule calling method sequence; as illustrated in "Hendren, et al. work" (<https://plg.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak/pubs/rv07.pdf>), "state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) BY XAVIER NOUMBISSI NOUNDOU, SPECIFIES UNWISHED BEHAVIOR (PROGRAM FORBIDDEN FAIL TRACE)" (SDMM (https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf)[?d])."

"One effort could be to give a formal translation methodology from "tracematches onto state diagram mealy machine (SDMM)"; Thus enabling automatic reuse of all tracematch specifications directly into a runtime monitor engine like YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567>) ."

"Patrick has not at time understood that this application is also possible by static dynamic program analysis tool created by myself at YERITH-RD: YRI_QVGE[12.12]; a Free and Open Source Code Software (FOSS)."

"Patrick LAM my former advisor since '2015-MARCH-10' is missing !"

"Patrick LAM and Xavier noumbissi NOUNDOU have at this effect presented a short overview presentation of 30 minutes at IBM workshop CASCON 2010! (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>)"

A SINK IS AN ACCEPTING (error) STATE; A SOURCE IS A START STATE. Sources and sinks are methods from the library (or plugin) used by the program under analysis (PUA). Edges are other method program instructions as seen by a THREE-Address-Code representation such as Jimple (SOOT), Gimple (GCC), etc., and, or LLVM three-address-code format.

Since YERITH-SAINT our (Xavier, Vijay, and Patrick) static dataflow taint analysis algorithm works on three-address-code, LLVM compiler framework could also apply YERITH-SAINT to JAVA code as input programming language to LLVM frontend-compiler-framework, and perform as well API USAGE RULE check.

IT means in effect that any programming language that could be inputted to LLVM frontend-compiler-framework, COULD BENEFIT FROM THIS SOFTWARE STACK api (application programming interface) rule checker.

- YERITH-SAINT (Figure 23) : [git https://github.com/sazzad114/saint](https://github.com/sazzad114/saint)
- [PH.D.—RESEARCH—SEMINAR TALK] GIVEN AT AN ECE (ELECTRICAL & COMPUTER ENGINEERING) GRADUATE SEMINAR TALK SERIES, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA (https://www.archive.org/download/jh-nissi-ece-uwaterloo-grad-talk-2014-04-16/JH_NISSI_ECE_UWATERLOO_GRAD_TALK_2014__04__16.pdf)

"Prof. Dr. Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D. (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak>), A world renowned scholar and scientist from the University of Waterloo in Waterloo, Canada, Ontario; Has reviewed this work with only 1 recommendation: add an additional application sample example apart from the presented "FORMAT STRING VULNERABILITY (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Uncontrolled_format_string)" analysis done in the research paper."

1. **L' INSTITUT AFRICAIN D'INFORMATIQUE—Yaoundé—Centre D'excellence PAUL—biya—rdpc. |**
 INSTITUT AFRICAIN D'INFORMATIQUE, YAOUNDE, CENTER REGION, CAMEROUN

"2016"

[1 institut (<https://www.iaicameroun.cm>) atypique,
 ARMAND—claude abanda,
 NANGA.]

Summary-PAGES

I. **D'enseignant vacataire à ENSEIGNANT consultant "20 heures—la—semaine de cours" À "6,11 EUROS" par heure:**

Mes rapports d'encadreurs académiques de SALABESSI—cuon—pgsiste de MBANJOCK :

1. JE postule via "4 heures" d'attente au sale bureau du courrier pour être reçu par 1 ingénieur inférieur au rang de "bachelor of science" (ndlr.: LICENCE en informatique);
2. Après être reçu pour 1 entretien special avec M. ARMAND—claude—abanda—idiot; je passe 2 interviews supposées professionnelles;
3. A l'issue de la 1^{ère} interview qui n'est qu'1 vérification brève du curriculum vitae et de très petites connaissances pédagogiques; L'ON ME propose plutôt 1 poste d'ENSEIGNANT consultant plutôt que celui de vacataire à 8 heures de cours hebdomadaire auquel j'ai postulé.
4. L'on ma redemandé de donner tous des cours que je pensais être en mesure de distillés; SUR cette palette de cours, l'on m'a octroyé "Architecture des ordinateurs" comme 1^{ère} mission pour la 1^{ère} année de GÉNIE—LOGIGIEL en section anglophone de leurs cursus d'études.
5. Après seulement "2 semaines et demi", 1 certain "salabessi" vient me donner l'injonction de commencer aussi à donner le cours "ADMINISTRATION SYSTÈME programmation système".
6. JE décide de partir de cette institution puisque ce rythme de travail serait insoutenable pour ma santé fragile à cette période de l'année au vu du changement du climat hivernale canadien au climat tempéré de YAOUNDE—raciste—tribaliste—mado—BIR :
 - a.) Toute heure de cours est payée ("8 heures par semaine" dans mon cas); IL ne m'est jamais mentionnée auparavant que 20 heures de travail la semaine ne concerne que la dispensation des cours au tableau.
 - b.) Toute autre heure de travail est impayée :
 - PRÉPARATION des données pour des devoirs surveillés;
 - CORRECTION des examens et devoirs surveillés;
 - RÉDACTION d'1 support de cours en langue anglaise.
 - [IL semblerait que 1 sœur utérine à ma personne; "Ingride TCHITCHUI noumbissi, Épse chandriand—TEUNTCHOU noumeni" serait allée dire que je suis 1 patient psychiatrique pour destituer ma vie, telle qu'elle aurait organisée en FÉVRIER 2021 avec le "rotary—club de abanda armand à ÉDEA".]
 - PARTICIPATION tous des mercredi à 1 réunion d'enseignants consultants; (EX.nihilo; je n'ai participé à aucune d'elle en 3 semaines de travail vu le temps d'adaptation à la localisation très éloigné du centre de cours de NKOLN'ANGA).

II. **Mes Conclusions SUR LA QUALITÉ de cet institut de merde :**

- 1.) [JP-kamgain, le cas d'échec patent de l'IAI cameroun !!!]
- 2.) PAS de suivi exact des besoins et difficultés de nouvelles recrues;
- 3.) ABANDA—amougou—belinga (<https://>), écroulé par des heures de cours sans avisé des enseignants :
2 fois consécutives, on me redemande de dispenser plutôt 4 heures de cours et exercices d'affilés plutôt que des 2 heures de cours prévues dans le "planning" pour CAUSE que l'enseignant du cours suivant s'est absenté.

[DGAY__side-rek; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://sainte bible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>);
Jon eyolfson—idiot; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://sainte bible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>),
SARAH—white—kkk—peggist; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://sainte bible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>)]

I. ISSUES - Problems with some colleagues:

1. ["Professor RAYSIDE"]

2. ["Student JON eyolfson, then Master of Applied Science JON."]

" This idiot white-supremacist-racist, that is watching videos about a murderer called 'LUCIFER' in our common office room while taking his lunch, is JUST A DISGUSTING kkk."

THIS junior computing engineer couldn't create a website for Watform lab (<https://watform.uwaterloo.ca>) after around 7 years doing a PH.D. in Computer Electrical Engineering: HE Had been mandated to do so in year 2009 when I started my "Ph.D. degree in Electrical & Computer Engineering" program as a "DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)"[?]. from the so-called-elite-universität-BREMEN-germany-de. (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>)!

3. "Student Hang chu (<https://uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/items/2656af1b-8829-45fb-bc5b-d1f49762ad49>), student of a so called professor patrick-lam, then Master of Applied Science HANG—chu."

THIS very-well-to-do person from China main island came to myself for a recommendation into a position as software developer in MISSISSAUGA-Toronto-idiot; I Accepted and tried to be very honest and humble in a form request form that was sent to myself the same day by a lady from "PHILLIPS subsidiary company" newest created !

4. "Student Wenzhu MAN (<https://uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/items/5ac24928-7279-41f1-9c58-634873430305>), student of a so called professor patrick-lam, then Master of Applied Science Wenzhu—MAN."

THIS ugly lady from CHINA main island, came into the lab-space rented to us by PATRICK-idiot-advisor during my 2nd year of doctoral PH.D. studies.

SHE seemed very intelligent but very hostile to black people as I could see her behavior when I asked her if she would like to collaborate on my ongoing static dataflow analysis YERITH-SAINT project, after I ASKED for this with, a positive approval from our common idiot supervisor ["PATRICK-vietnamese-vietkong LAM"].

SHE was reluctant and we never had any opportunity to present and/or Work on anything together; AS this was the same with [JON eyolfson; Who instead copied my work only !]

5. "PROFESSOR clementin tayou djameni (UNIVERSITY OF DSCHANG, WEST REGION, CAMEROON)"

" THIS sample ignorant on "algorithms complexity and concurrency computations on multi-computers" that I know because my uncle THEODORE wandji ngongang sent me to him while he was visiting EUROPE (FRANCE, then GERMANY); while I was still an undergraduate student at the "ELITE-UNIVERSITÄT-BREMEN" (<https://www.uni-bremen.de>); So I will have connections in ACADEMIA in my home country while I AM STILL outside of CAMEROON."

"I met, see, and even sleep beside him twice – 1st time in our student apartment in Bremen where he stayed 4 days – Then in Rennes-FRANCE in "2004" when he visited "GRENOBLE laboratory" with PROFESSOR tchindo-gilbert."

"I tried to contact him during "September-2011" because I HEARD from MARCELIN TALLY, cousin of mine, that I COULD apply already for a position as "assistant professor in CAMEROON" with a "DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER DEGREE (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)"[?] " like our common age-class colleague Oscar MOURBARE from Ngaoundere-Cameroon. [Dr.-Ing. DAYANG Paul] is also from university of bremen and also our common cohort in computer science in CS-Bremen (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>). "

"HE has never answered anymore any emails or telephone call while I was in Cameroon ! "

ISSUES and Misunderstandings 2 |

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2009 – Apr. 2015]

[DGAY__side-rek; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://saintebible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>);
 Jon eyolfson-idiot; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://saintebible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>),
 SARAH—white—kkk-peggish; HOLY-bible-darby-version—exodus-17_15 (<https://saintebible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>)]

I. ISSUES - Problems with some colleagues:**6. "FORMER friend and now enemy Godrick CHEKETE H. from Benin—vaoodoo"**

I encounter this idiot and voodoo man as I just entered my second year of doctoral studies at the university—racist of waterloo in ONTARIO, CANADA

THE Ghanaian so called YAW BOAKYE-agyeman, that I EVER met 1st time in African student association of the university of waterloo: "AFRSA" (<https://saintebible.com/lsg/exodus/17-15.htm>) as I was in my 3rd week in the city of Waterloo.

IT is the west—african student YAW, BOAKYE-agyeman, from ashanti—tribe that told myself that he would like to introduce me to another FRENCH-speaking student from WEST-AFRICA.

WE then met 3 of us in a restaurant inside the main campus located at 200 University Avenue West; I DON'T REMEMBER the name of the idiot-white—racist restaurant for students.

7. "FORMER enemy MARTIAL ategomo YEMELE from Cameroon"

I encounter this vagabond because GODRICK—chekete recommended HIM (martial ategomo yemele to myself as a cameroon student in need of crucial help in life)

Normally I NEVER friend myself with such Cameroon people that seemed to have traveled with fake ID and other faked documents as I could imagine from his physical being.

IN year 2013, as I went to build a gate for my compound in YAOUNDE, Godrick and MARTIAL ATEGOMO YEMELE came ask myself that I sublet my bedroom-only for 1 month only to MARTIAL for "400 cad". I accepted and I needed afterwards to tell him very deeply to go out after "1 and half month" because HE seems to be wanting to stay even more than 6 months in my 2-bedroom apartment located at "16—457, ALBERT-ST., N2L 5A7, Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA—racist-idiot".

Martial ategomo and Godrick Chekete H.; I stopped any collaboration with both these ignorant right after asking MARTIAL and GODRICK to leave my apartment around 11 : 30 PM at night.

8. "ECE Master & Ph.D. programs coordinator Sarah Landy, MSc."

THIS very racist girl with a master of science, arrogant at all wanted myself to believe that SHE is a professor of mine even though I am wondering even today if she could even work somewhere else than a place where systemic racism is the norm and not the ANORMAL life day—work !

"This slot for professors of ECE is the one that on "MARCH 10th, 2015" told myself; "as she was a PH.D. & MASTER program coordinator in ECE department" of the university-racist of waterloo: "[Patrick (lam)] sent an email to cancel the event (MY SO CALLED PH.D. RESEARCH SEMINAR according to academic graduate studies regulations of year 2015 ! " "

" SARAH as I could experience even when I PASSED ONTO HER HANDS my doctoral thesis; called research proposal at ECE department, has a personal griev to my person from somewhere I CANNOT even imagine; because THIS document wasn't published anywhere or registered publicly on the university-racist of waterloo internet, or intranet—world ! "

9. [Professor idiot lin tan]**10. P[rofessor Patrick LAM]****11. [Professor LADAN]**

ACADEMIA world worldwide contactS |

STARTUP YECÉFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE)

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY

[DEC. 2023 – "April 20, 2025"]

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2023]

[OCT. 2002 – JUL. 2007]

[Contacts with Academia in NORTH–AMERICA]

o CONTACTS with Academia in NORTH–AMERICA:

1. Doctor Christian Eyoum–sawa-rotarian–criminal–seasoned–psychiatrist (Laquintine HOSPITAL DOUALA, CMR (<https://>)) [Around "2021"]

THIS seasoned psychiatrist that assassinates at least 500 persons a year was sent to me by "ROSE sangnou" my female genitor so to hijack my private–inherited apartment in "DLA-cité-des-palmiers" as I was just finishing a psychology family and personal treatment because OF "LAURENT-tchandeu", a criminal uncle paternal side of mine.

IT is at age of 6 years old that I lost my dear criminal genitor "THÉODORE noumbissi-salau"; I called this genitor of mine a "salau" because this freemason had a booklet on economy written by "KARL–idiot-mars" where I COULD SEE just a month after his sudden death, caused probably by NTOMANI–Racist, THAT theodore-noumbissi said: "GOD is stupidity and dirt !" !

IT is at age 35 years old that I understood that this mason of my genitor, "THÉODORE noumbissi"; tried to hijack myself but loose his own soul because mainly of his junior brother "LAURENT tchandeu".

"CHRISTIAN-eyoum" is only someone that destroys in all plans of life any person sent to him by "SECRETARIAT-D'ÉTATA-LA-DEFENSE (sed)", a so called SERVICE-SECRET.

IT seems the culprit eyoum sent some people from his hospitals to rent my 1st–storey house bedroom-apartment so to hijack people that want to travel to western countries.

I am suspicious of this because I cannot foresee an issue in the legal case I started at DLA-ndokoti justice palace in February 14th; After christian eyoum and state hospital laquintinie sent at least 9 people at night around 23 : 30 to hijack my real–estate property and life.

Also, eyoum walks with a walkie-talkie of cameroonian defense forces; SO he is somewhat a criminal of the army that must be arrested by SEMIL–ndlr: Sécurité MILITAIRE: a so called anti-gang unit against criminal from cmr defense forces.

2. Doctor KLAUS HAVELUND–idiot (Caltech, California Technology Institute CALIFORNIA, U.S.A (<https://www.caltech.edu>)) ["2022"]

Klaus is an idiot because HE wasn't capable of coming clearly with his expectations as I contacted him to review my at that time ongoing and starting project on CREATING A RUNTIME MONITORING VERIFICATION testing framework 📄 [YRI_QVGE\[?d\]](#) for state diagram mealy machine (SDMM) having following characteristics compared to opponents like; "TDIOHS (Timed Discrete Input / Output Hybrid System)" implemented in real-time testing tool 📄 [RT-Tester \(https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp/papers/peleska_et_al_soqua2006.pdf\)](https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp/papers/peleska_et_al_soqua2006.pdf) [?] of the society in germany: "VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GMBH, SPIN-OFF THE UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN" (<https://www.verified.de>) "; AND opponent tool ""DejaVu" (<https://>) ("DejaVu: A Monitoring Tool for First-Order Temporal Logic")" :

- o A Domain–Specific LANGUAGE (DSL) for specifying forbidden traces (fail traces) of mealy machine, formalized as state diagram: "YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG".
- o A compiler–translator that generates free C++ code as runtime monitoring verification module to be run and watched "within runtime monitor container 📄 ["YRI_QVGE" \(https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf\)](https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf)[?d]".
- o "fail (forbidden) traces specification".
ALL competitors were having 'wished behavior trace specification';
- o "NO FALSE POSITIVES"; guaranteed with a formal proof demonstration in "YRI_QVGE" paper: "YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF : a framework for verifying SQL software correctness properties of [gui] software at runtime"; ([HTTPS://WWW.ZENODO.ORG/RECORDS/13232567](https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567)) [?d]

Klaus is never clear–minded in terms of being humble because he even insulted myself in 1 of his email that I received at my email–address: "Yerith.Xavier@gmail.com".

MAY be because of his friendship, undeclared at the time I was under supervision of JAN PELESKA–cuon.

KLAUS havelund is part of the group of people who have been trying to cover myself with in-competencies by using my research-work results without mentioning my names or anything about source of their work.

FOR instance I have never at time seen a "FLEX–BISON" parser written by PELESKA or KLAUS havelund when I finished my compiler–translator [[YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP](#)].

Let's observe what comes up in coming years from both deceptive white teacher–professors.

ACADEMIA world worldwide contactS |

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[DEC. 2023 – "April 20, 2025"]

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2023]

[OCT. 2002 – JUL. 2007]

[Contacts with Academia in NORTH-AMERICA — Continued – 1]

o CONTACTS with Academia in NORTH-AMERICA:

1. Christopher-NGOSONG (MCGill, MCGill University
QUEBEC, CANADA (<https://www.mcgill.ca>) ["2012" – onward]

THIS guja came visit personally myself in my sublet basement apartment in MARKHAM-ontario around end of year 2012 as I was finishing my sabbatical-year-Internship with "J9-Java Just-IN-Time Compilation TEAM of VIJAY Sundaresan", at, IBM Toronto Software Laboratory (<https://www.ibm.ca>).

THIS male-female boy from BUEA-mutengene was sent to myself by an uncle paternal called "David Demo NOUNDOU", coming for a postdoctoral research stay in Canada after graduating his doctorate in agricultural studies from Germany.

I invited him to oversee my project in Yaounde for a small research institute combined with a technological entrepreneurship project after we had a dinner at a whittist-canadian Soccer-MMA-grill Bar somewhere in Markham, ON, Canada.

HE even manifested interest in co-creating this research technological institute by participating both in research & teaching as I can remember since we didn't communicate much after year 2012 together (NGOSONGK@yahoo.com).

"I could observe on the website of the University of BUEA (<https://>) lastly (2024) that HE became department chief for agricultural sciences. "

2. Dr.-B.Sc. Rodrigue Wankap Emmanuel MOGO—assassin (Rennes University,
FRANCE-assassin (<https://www.>)) ["2021" – onward]

THIS family MOGO where I could try to be investigated and cured for following diseases in their mansionian Hospital Clinic BUILDING in DLA-05 ème cité-des-palmiers;

- *Disruption of well-function of my whole left leg after a fall on ground due to trying to send a small stone far away with my right hand;*

A culprit-MD-anesthesiologist-trauma hired by YVES-MOGO, senior brother of my secondary school—ALFRED-Saker mate-colleague Assassin-WANKAP comes and tells me after around 30-minutes auscultation that MY left leg must be open-operated.

[I said I will think about this trying-to-open my nerves twice; THEN I DISAPPEAR from this assassination-begger-online MD-owona-rdpc-cpd.m-assassin funded Clinic.]

CANAL+ (<https://www.canalhorizon.com>) in France employs Rodrigue & YVES-mogo senior brother MD-assassin in HEXAGONE-assassin-slave-for-boyard & other TV-scam programs; EVEN sensual payments-only-viewing.

SISTER GHISLAINE-MD-mogo is kind-of CHRISTIAN-eyoum-rotarian-club in USA; Last news in MARYLAND-MA, a psy; IN cameroon she could get her secondary-school-final-certificate BAccalaureat via a payment to a certain deceased minister JOSEPH-owona-kono !

- *HYPERGLYCEMIA because of not begin knowledgeable that CHRISTIAN-eyoum has tried to put into my blood via forced-in-taken pills and forced-in-taken injections;*

The lady that is supposed to be a diabetes specialist medical doctor kind-of [EYOUM-christian-murderer] and that I don't remember names and / or whatsoever credentials; SHE gives myself insulin such at a high level that I stopped taking this promptly after 1 week, because I COULD sense that I DON'T HAVE ANY DIABETES !

3. Béatrice (IUT-Douala, University of Douala
Littoral Region, Cameroon (<https://www.>)) ["2025" – onward]

THIS super lady from my Grand-father neighborhood in Douala-NEW DEÏDO, is a professor at the Institute of Technology of the University of Douala since age 40 years old with a Doctorate-Ph.D. degree from China as I have heard from our common neighborhood.

HER husband that I have never met personally could help me with information on how to trace a prototype for YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET; As HE owns a super-chain of eye glasses from his China originating venture "BioLUXE".

ACADEMIA world worldwide contactS |

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 UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY

[DEC. 2023 – "CURRENTLY"]
 [Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2023]
 [OCT. 2002 – JUL. 2007]

[Contacts with Corruptible–NON-SENse–ACADEMIA]◦ **CONTACTS with Corruptible–NON-SENse–ACADEMIA:**

1. **MASTER–of–applied–science HYPOLithe–cuon-pd-TEKEU (IUC – INstitut UNIVERSitaire de la COTE, DOUALA (<https://www.myiuc.cm>), littoral REGION, CAMEROON)**

THIS megere-bamile tribe ROSE–sangnou, a genitor of my physical being went on to recommend myself to apply for a position at so called canadian–cooperation–institution IÛC.

I was 1st told I COULD earn "500 000 Xaf"; AFTER a prompt and passed successfully interview; WITHOUT any indication that I AM A socalled DR.–ING;

hypolithe–tekeu–pd–racist–tribal–bamileke–dschang–idiot offers myself "200 000 Xaf".

I COULD NOT say no period.

THIS idiot even put myself under a so–called professional master of engineering from his dirty and prostitution institute IÛC. JUNIOR–mbe; THIS junior–mbe–fosso is now as far I COULD OBSERVE in internet–world in socalled pragmatic-quebec-cuon-land-freedom–CANADA.

TODAY I can say that it is pretty much impossible for such a low–class institution to employ an ivy–level league USA graduate university ! GUIMEZAP himself culprit with all his children couldn't even get a doctorate degree outside of DSCHANG–village where they originate from in the OUEST.

This C.P.D.M–rosicrucian–ntone institution also tries to destroy life of people together with SHANDA–tonme jean-claude of village BANGOU–batchingou in OUEST.

ACADEMIA world worldwide contactS |

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 UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2023]
 [OCT. 2002 – JUL. 2007]

[Contacts with Cameroon-ACADEMIA]◦ **CONTACTS with Cameroon Academia:**

1. **PROFESSOR thomas ndié djotio** (École Nationale Supérieure Polytechnique de Yaoundé - ENSPY (<https://www.polytechnique.cm>), CENTER REGION, CAMEROON)

This older than [myself] so called 'maître de conférence', English as "associate professor", was very kind to receive myself and to let me give him a short presentation of my professional and academic projects as "Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering (Dr.-Ing.) (UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)":

- I. [YRI_QVGE](https://www.zenodo.org/records/10474033) (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/10474033>) [24.24] June 2022 – currently
- II. [YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/) (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>) [?] OCT. 2015 – currently

I could identify "[Prof. Dr.-Eng. THOMAS Djotio Ndié-Idiot]" through his online website located at: "<https://sites.google.com/tdjotio>". I could also see his resume-online (~~<https://sites.google.com/tdjotio>~~) that was asserting and presenting him as doctor-of-engineering graduated from the "École-polytechnique-de-yaoundé" in year "2008".

ALL this afore mentioned websites were canceled by "THOMAS ndié djotio" it seems; For a more official resume (https://polytechnique.cm/wp-content/uploads/2022/04/Biographie_Djotio-Ndie-Thomas.pdf).

HE 1st contested that I was a doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering because I didn't at that time of year 2022 asked for an official graduate transcript from the [UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, in Waterloo (Ontario, Canada)].

I could then obtain free-of-charge from "MRS. Nancy HEIDE" (nheide@uwaterloo.ca), at time of request As "Director of Student Services OF THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO", a certificate via electronic mail (Email) at my own request of "Official Graduate Transcript" that normally is charged \$20 CAD. I even had "Prof. Dr.-Eng. THOMAS Djotio Ndié" copied-conform (cc) to my email since I am trying to get hired by "École-polytechnique-de-yaoundé".

I CANNOT REMEMBER have failed any examination my entire candidacy of Doctor Ph.D., since I successfully graduated with "88%" as "Doctor-Ph.D. in electrical & computer Engineering (Dr.-Ing.)" on "December 20th, 2011"; with THESIS title:

["Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software"](#) [23]

I have appealed that I HAVE BEEN rejected from my [PhD research seminar] on "March 10th, 2015" by PATRICK lam that said 3 years later to myself when I was back in Canada to resign my canadian shit-citizenship, He didn't recall that he could foresee results from my program as pre-defined after we setup the PH.D. research seminar, together with my "PhD comprehensive examination committee members":

- A professor of age greater than 70 years old was the rapporteur:
- Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D. Email: olhotak@cs.uwaterloo.ca
- Derek Rayside, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (P.Eng., Ontario) Email: drayside@uwaterloo.ca
- Patrick Lam, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (P.Eng., Ontario) Email: p23lam@uwaterloo.ca
- Lin Tan, Ph.D., Professional Engineer (P.Eng., Ontario) Email: lintan@purdue.edu

THE Ph.D. Dissertation Defense occurred in "January 2015" at PLG. IT was successfully approved by other following people among others:

["Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM"](#) [23]

1. Peter Alan Burh, Ph.D. Alias ~~FABRICE siemni-wilfried remp-canadian-armed-forces~~ Email: pabuhr@uwaterloo.ca
2. * Vijay Ganesh, Ph.D. Email: vganesh@gatech.edu
3. * Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D. Email: olhotak@uwaterloo.ca
4. * Patrick Lam, Ph.D. Email: p23lam@uwaterloo.ca
5. Magnus Madsen, Ph.D. Email: magnusm@cs.au.dk

ALL professors before mentioned marked with a "*" sign are collaborators in this project. Others approver were reviewers and were both ("Magnus, and Peter") present !

ACADEMIA world worldwide contactS |

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[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2023]

[OCT. 2002 – JUL. 2007]

[Contacts with Cameroon-ACADEMIA]

o CONTACTS with Cameroon Academia:

1. PROFESSOR maïgari-idiot-secessionist (Former director, Cameroon-consulate in BRUssels-belgium (<https://>),
Center Region, Cameroon) [Around "March-April 2015"]

2. PROFESSOR yves emvudu-cuon (INFORMATION SYSTEMS DIRECTOR deceased by now, Higher Education Ministry in Yaounde (<https://>),
Center Region, Cameroon) [Around "August 2015"]

THIS idiot didn't even counseled me properly about the educational system employed in Cameroonian UNIVERSITIES. HE didn't even inquired on either my passed qualifications nor my credential documents; Since with his position, we could together query all required documents from an official position research in high education ministry for me.

HE just sent me to École Normale Supérieure so to meet a professor for MATHEMATICS that I forgot names and qualifications since I could never see him at ENS-yaounde.

THE other professor for mathematics I was supposed to meet, even though I AM foremost a computing engineer and developer was a MATHEMATICS professor at École Nationale Supérieure POLYTECHNIQUE de YAOUNDE. THIS man that seemed very kind but dangerous just gave me advise to put my publications of '<https://www.archive.org>'. "THIS older man than Yves-emvudu was a doctor from WEST-germany", whereas "YVES-emvudu was doctor from east-germany" !!!

ALSO, I was told by EMVUDU to apply for a teaching assistant position at SIANTOU-supérieur, and also Congo-CAMEROUN science university in a remote area of Cameroon I even don't remember the name.

"Merci au fainéant de Tonme de ne plus repasser où j'entre sur cette terre !!!"

[IT is exactly because of my "assassin-uncle-paternal-Laurent-TCHANDEU" that I went o search and encounter "YVES emvudu" of SÉCRÉTARIAT D'ÉTAT A LA DEFENSE (sed) without knowing he might create a procedure to destroy me mentally because it might be inappropriate for a criminal like LAURENT to act directly on my body because of the blood-genetic-connection-with-his-own-kids !!!]

3. PROFESSOR bertin nyemb (École Normale Supérieure de Yaoundé – ENSY (<https://>),
Center Region, Cameroon) [Around "May 2022"]

THIS very not humble professor for german language and cultural-ism is a very humble and not contestative person because he has always been trying to hijack myself as a member of DGRÉ.

I SUSPECT this idiot spy of biya-regime to have even sent false opinions of myself to german authorities at the UNIVERSITY-racist OF BREMEN after I MET HIM once again here in Yaounde in year 2022 !

SO this man of "Bassa"-tribe is at least 3 times recidivist in trying to check what makes someone like myself an ignorant by psychiatric methods like the ones [EYOUM-rotarian-CHRISTIAN] has been trying together with PR. DR. shanda-tonme, and EMVUDU.

I acknowledged at his request to be member of his stupid [Rotarian] organization so called PROvac ("PROMOTION des valeurs au Cameroun").

THIS has been more than 22 months now, he has never replied to any message about trying to computerized his membership list and cards using my humble open-source software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.

ACADEMIA world worldwide contactS |

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[OCT. 2002 – JUL. 2007]

[Contacts with Cameroon-ACADEMIA]

o CONTACTS with Cameroon Academia:

1. PROFESSOR clementin tayou djameni (UNIVERSITY OF DSCHANG (<https://>), WEST REGION, CAMEROON) [Around "September 2011", then around "September 2015]

" THIS sample ignorant on "algorithms complexity and concurrency computations on multi-computers" that I know because my uncle THEODORE wandji ngongang sent me to him while he was visiting EUROPE (FRANCE, then GERMANY); while I was still an undergraduate student at the "ELITE-UNIVERSITÄT-BREMEN" (<https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de>); So I will have connections in ACADEMIA in my home country while I AM STILL outside of CAMEROON."

"I met, see, and even sleep beside him twice – 1st time in our student apartment in Bremen where he stayed 4 days – Then in Rennes-FRANCE in "2004" when he visited "GRENOBLE laboratory" with PROFESSOR tchindo-gilbert."

"I tried to contact him again in "September-2011" because I HEARD from "diplom-informatiker marcellin tally", cousin of mine, that I COULD apply already for a position as "assistant professor in CAMEROON" with a "DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER DEGREE, ABBREVIATED (DIPL.-INF.) (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)[?]" like our common age-class colleague "diplom-informatiker oscar mourbare" from Ngaoundere-Cameroon. [Dr.-Ing. DAYANG Paul] is also from university of bremen and also our common cohort in computer science in CS-Bremen (<https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de>)."

"HE has never answered anymore any emails or telephone calls while I was in Cameroon ! "

2. PROFESSOR kolyang (University of MAROUA (<https://www.univ-maroua.cm/fr/node/76>), FAR NORTH REGION, CAMEROON) [Around December 2015"]

" I remember greeting him when entering an elevator as he was visiting Bremen while I was in my undergraduate level of education in Computer Science at the UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN in Germany where HE Graduated several years in front of myself."

"HE didn't answered at all and I felt he is not very comfortable with young cameroonian studying in BREMEN."

"KOLYANG was then a DOKTOR-INGENIEUR (Dr.-Ing.), that could graduate from BREMEN with PROFESSOR BERND KRIEG BRÜCKNER (BKB) as DOKTOR-VATER (main principal PhD advisor)."

"Professor JAN peleska-cuon said I shall contact him in year 2016 when I was looking for a research position back in Cameroon 1st time, before returning into CANADA-shit to resign a CANDIAN-idiot-citizenship I acquired because I needed to travel via Europe without visa request at GERMAN embassy. I could succeed to send him an email at an email-address received from PELESKA-cuon, that I don't remember; BUT I never got a return reply message at all."

"WITH idiot-joseph-djoumessi that invited myself in his christian-rosicrucian-peg congregation CMCI-obili (<https://>); I heard from someone that was in academia at the UNIVERSITY OF YAOUNDE 1 that KOLYANG was not anymore in academia for working on research, But KOLYANG was doing agriculture !!! "

1. THE university of waterloo, from a black African descendant perspective, as a student and employee, & High Qualified Person from GERMANY. |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Oct. 2009 – "April 20, 2025"]

[*Incompetent "doctoral Ph.D. program coordinator as a Master of Science (M.Sc.)" Sarah landy,*

*Color of origin payments,
non observance of international academic conventions and laws criminal,
racial segregative police of canada–waterloo–ontario,
DEREK rayside idiot,
INCOMPETENT ACADEMIC PEOPLE IN ECE (ELECTRICAL & COMPUTER ENGINEERING),
racial systemic segregation]*

- I. ★ I Was very positively surprised to receive as POST-doctoral advisor, additionally to PATRICK lam; *An Ivy-league Stanford graduate called Dr. Vijay Ganesh* (<https://www.stanford.edu>).
- II. I came to this super MIT-graduate "*Patrick Lam, Ph.D.* (<https://www.patricklam.ca>)" because HE was from *Ivy-league–Massachusetts Institute of TEchnology MIT* (<https://www.csail.mit.edu>).
- III. *Asian-Vietnamese advisor Dr. of Engineering PATRICK lam* (<https://patricklam.ca>) from "*Massachusetts Institute of Technology (M.I.T* (<https://csail.mit.edu>), MA, USA)" :

Here are certain things done for myself both, academically and professionally, by PATRICK lam :

1. *I spent 6 years under supervision of PATRICK-idiot-lam, (<https://google.com/scholar>) without having at least 1 scientific paper published under his supervision anywhere in my visible and observable internet WORLD !*

[!!! I got this ([FSE–soqua 2006]) with only 2 years at THE university–racist-of-bremen.de !!!]

"THIS is the only time "PELESKA et al." could attend such a high–prestigious class–A conference in NORTH america of mine." (<https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp/PUBLICATIONS...>)

2. [JON EYOLFSON], an idiot that worked for PATRICK-lam as a MASTER student (M.ASC.) and then as a PH.D. candidate, **COULD COPY MY WORK** more intelligently & silently, and even 'EHHH' got a high paid position as an "**ASSISTANT PROFESSOR** (*teaching stream*)"; after 4 years at **UCLA** (<https://ucla.edu/asian-postdoc-supervisor>) as Postdoctoral fellow; AT THE **ece–department OF THE UNIVERSITY OF TORONTO** (<https://utoronto.ca/alexie>), ontario, canada.
3. *Patrick recommended myself to IBM Toronto Software Lab manager "Dr. MARCEL mitran" after I told him I was looking for an internship just after my PHD COMPREHENSIVE EXAMINATION[21]; Before returning to University of Waterloo, ON.*
4. *Professor PATRICK lam gave myself a lot of presentation skills attitudes that I can today not all of them remember.*
5. Patrick sent me to several research academical venues through my doctoral Ph.D. studies at the University of Waterloo, ON:
- "*First Summer School on Formal Techniques*" (<https://fm.csl.sri.com/SSFT11/index.shtml>) (2011);
 - **MITACS Ontario** (2012);
 - **PLDI – Programming Language Design and Implementation** (2009);
 - **IBM CASCON – IBM Centre for Advanced Studies Conference** (2010);
 - **ICSE – International Conference On Software Engineering** (2012).
6. Patrick gave myself 1st hand detailed explanations on static dataflow analysis à la "Gary A. kildall : *A unified approach to global program optimization* (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)" with help of his slides from **McGill University** (<https://www.mcgill.ca>).
7. *Professor PATRICK lam is the only one that taught me that I really need to keep my LaTeX document code straight and maxed 80 lines.*
8. *Professor PATRICK lam is the only one that taught me that I really need to keep reading papers as long as I don't really master them, before coming back to talk to him !*
9. *Professor PATRICK lam is the only one that taught me that I really need to dig very deep into researching and probing an idea before there is an excellent outcome out of it: THIS IS WHAT I APPLIED TO get my 1st implementation of my doctoral dissertation work YERITH–SAINT !*
10. Patrick gave me hints about contributing to open source projects by modifying their code source and reuse it for my research; I for instance applied this when creating Computer–Aided Software Engineering (CASE) tool **YERITH_QVGE**.
11. *PATRICK lam is also the one that permitted for myself to gain a **TEACHING EXPERIENCE** at the **UNI-racist of Waterloo : I AM ALWAYS grateful to him for this great Experience at the UNIVERSITY–racist of WATERLOO in Ontarian CANADA.***
12. [**PERSONALLY I am planing to pay him some money from my soft- and hard-ware revenue in the future.**]

1. THE university of waterloo, from a black African descendant perspective, as a student and employee, & High Qualified Person from GERMANY. |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Oct. 2009 – "April 20, 2025"]

[Incompetent "doctoral Ph.D. program coordinator as a Master of Science (M.Sc.)" Sarah landy,

Color of origin payments,
non observance of international academic conventions and laws criminal,
racial segregative police of canada–waterloo–ontario,
DEREK rayside idiot,
INCOMPETENT ACADEMIC PEOPLE IN ECE (ELECTRICAL & COMPUTER ENGINEERING),
racial systemic segregation]

- I. Asian-Vietnamese advisor Dr. of Engineering PATRICK lam (<https://patricklam.ca>) from "Massachusetts Institute of Technology (M.I.T (<https://csail.mit.edu>), MA, USA)" :

Here are certain things done for myself both, academically and professionally, by PATRICK lam:

11. "PATRICK lam has never done a "program analysis by himself" as far as I have been working with either as his research assistant or as a scholar that could see this somewhere in a world. "

"They (PATRICK and FELIX) even attempted to remove my name from git repository (<https://>) history when "Divam Jain" left and PATRICK said to FELIX-fang to continue that research WITH me also as a supervisor under PATRICK-lam."

"AS far as I am knowledgeable, scientific conference and / or whatsoever papers that stem "from research work of Divam Jain", that I see as plagiarism since my name as a co–author has never been written, are existent because I am the only originator of this work; as a supervisor of DIVAM jain, at the beginning of his "Master of Mathematics (M.Math.)"; and this at request of dear PATRICK lam":

"Deceased idiot former dean of engineering "PEARL sullivan", [that I went to confront with facts about these plagiarisms], Sent by a black–idiot police officer from UWATERLOO racial–police services; Sent a british giant muscular idiot white–police–officer to arrest me illegally and very violently just at the ground level of the 'Davis Centre BUILDING of racists.' "

"BECAUSE i removed my clothes in front of surveillance digital cameras in a uw–office racial-police, Where the british–racist-police-from-scotland did tell me to sign papers that I DIDN'T EVEN had opportunity to read at all; THEY sent me in jail–custody to KITCHENER-waterloo criminal justice court. "

"Justice Crown attorney prosecutor DOMINIQUE KENNEDY" let all investigations done and concluded that I HAD NEVER ASSAULTED this idiot police white-british office that charged myself with 'ASSAULT TO POLICE OFFICER' ! "

"Justice Crown attorney prosecutor DOMINIQUE KENNEDY" told me she called "the office of THE president of the university of waterloo" to ask them to let myself defend my "Ph.D. degree dissertation"; BUT they told her with attorneys of law of the president of the university of waterloo: "What is a crown attorney doing in the office of president ?"

"Justice Crown attorney prosecutor DOMINIQUE KENNEDY" then on another did tell me that someone from the office of the president-idiot–racist of the university of waterloo; said that they have certain attitudes that are based on their local culture!

Incompetent "doctoral Ph.D. program coordinator as a Master of Science (M.Sc.)" Sarah landy

went on to harass the university of waterloo police ; ESPECIALLY (ambinns@uwpolice.ca); to say Like a HE-girl–pom–pom–shit that: "THIS black gay guy is so huge that he must be destroyed mentally !!!

this kind of race–sarah–landy MUST never be admitted anywhere else in this black world other than her anus....zizi.

[THIS happened in year 2018 as I WENT TO DESTROY my so-called—white-oblivier canadian–CACA–shit—citizenship–pegg–kkk.]

"I AM THE one who told to MRS. cuon-idiot–racist–white–quebec–tabawec—"Justice Crown attorney prosecutor DOMINIQUE KENNEDY", that THIS IS CALLED discrimination !"

- a. "Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints" (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)

I. **Formal Training for occupying teaching positions** |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

[**TEACHING ASSISTANT training;**
CUT-1 - Certificate in University Teaching 1]

[Summary-PAGES]

1. **Training in ECE Department (Electrical & Computer Engineering Department):**

Before starting my 1st formal appointment as a teaching assistant at the University of Waterloo, ON, CANADA; In year 2009, I received a group training for graduate students of the ECE (Electrical & Computer Engineering Department).

2. **Passed QUALIFICATION interview to teach OBJECT-ORIENTED PROGRAMMING WITH JAVA:**

I SUCCESSFULLY passed a presentation slides lecture for qualification interviews OF 30 minutes added with "Q&A - Questions & Answers" session; to teach Object-Oriented Java Programming to 1st year students at THE university of Waterloo in year 2012.

NEVERTHELESS, I was not chosen as THE committee said: I QUOTE THEM: "Xavier might no be able to manage this very young age students in a class of 100 or more." I WAS AGED MYSELF 29 years old in year 2012 when this happened ! THX TO PATRICK-IDIOT-LAM

PATRICK-IDIOT-LAM is only 4 years older than myself. (<https://www.patricklam.ca>)

IT seems PATRICK and lin-tan-AGED-exactly as myself were trying to avoid a so-called-negger at a high paid position at UNIVERSITY-OF-WATERLOO. "Lin tan" is born 1983 like Xavier noumbissi NOUNDOU ! (<https://cs.purdue.edu/lintan>)

THE class was given at the end to a seasoned professor named **SEBATIAN FISCHMEISTER** (<https://ece.uwaterloo.ca/~sfischme>), that leads the *Embedded Research Group in ECE* (<https://ece.uwaterloo.ca/~sfischme>).

3. **This was optional. CUT-1; Certificate in University Teaching – 1:**

"THE university of waterloo in ontario, Canada"; offers a formal training program in 4 certificates to qualify graduate students and / or whatsoever qualified persons for teaching at a UNIVERSITY.

I attended the level 1 certificate in 2010, but didn't pursue the last 3 levels because I felt I couldn't perform as fast as I wanted my doctoral research due to the high level of academic requirements due by researching in the "static code program analysis" area of research; At *WatForm (WATERLOO FORMAL METHODS group research)* (<https://watform.uwaterloo.ca>); led by "Prof. Dr. JOE atlee of the CS (Computer Science) Department" (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~jmatlee>).

AFTER my free registration, at my own request and without asking PATRICK-idiot-lam; and attendance of all 1st level courses at "DAVEN-PORT library on main (200 UNIVERSITY AVENUE WEST) campus" of the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, I notice IT would be impossible to myself to finish my research in due time without issues with my doctoral advisor !!!

WE were around 10 in a sumptuous and luxurious carpeted room at kind of 3rd level in the main building !

ESPECIALLY added to the fact I WAS EARNING SUCH A LOW 999-CAD, so I HAD to TA-teaching assisting PATRICK lam.

THAT'S why I resigned.

[I EVEN feared PATRICK lam was trying to make myself sick because of the amount of stipend I HAD, compared to other students like JON eyolfson who also add other stipend from NSREC-CANADA !!!]

"I was under supervision of my doctoral Ph.D advisor Dr.-Ph.D. of Engineering PATRICK lam".

I. **Competencies Acquired and Learned as a TEACHER-PROFESSOR** |

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

[**TEACHING ASSISTANT training**]

- o **SUMMARY of given-co-taught courses: '2' undergraduate ("Bachelor") level courses.**
- o **Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465)**
 1. Creating a "JUnit 4-tutorial" ([https://https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052444](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052444)) and got it reviewed by PATRICK LAM; THIS is not a task PATRICK as instructor asked me to perform; I did this in my free time and put it as sample training material for students. – **"(*) Professor task level"**
 2. GOING in class to teach JUnit for exercise session – **"(*) Professor task level"**
 3. Creating SAMPLE solutions to assignments – **"(*) Professor task level"**
 4. MARKING ASSIGNMENT à la patrick lam – **"(*) Professor task level"**
I felt very improved for my teaching software technical testing skills.
- o **Programming for Performance (ECE 459)**
 1. **TAKING some time in my time of research for my ["PH.D. in electrical & Computer ENGINEERING"] to receive students visit at my office; and teach them what they couldn't understand either in class, and / or for the course material ! –** **"(*) Professor task level"**

" Since my PH.D.-advisor patrick was the Director of Software Engineering study programs, I Think he thought I could replace him as a lecturer and he wanted to test these skills."
 2. "Really I didn't much like this course as taught by PATRICK because it was more a kind of programming course that wasn't very solid in mathematical and engineering foundations; Except for theories and histories on processor speed "MOORE-law" expansion and development ! "

"THIS was more to gain money because I was only earning \$999 Cad as a "master of science, PH.D. candidate" under supervision PATRICK-lam; coming from a middle level-paid good money position."

I. *Competencies Acquired and Learned as a TEACHER-PROFESSOR* |

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Jan. 2012 – 10 MARCH 2015]

[*TEACHING ASSISTANT training*]

◦ *SUMMARY of given-co-taught courses: '3' undergraduate ("Bachelor") level courses; '2' graduate ("Master", "PhD", "Ph.D.") level courses.*

◦ *Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465)*

1. Because of my resignation act in front of all committee members of my doctoral Ph.D. comprehensive examination and DISSERTATION COMMITTEE members;
I resigned !

◦ *Compilers (ECE 351)*

1. I did during my time in BREMEN, a course called ("Übersetzer GENERIERUNG mit LEX und YACC") that could be translated in English-white: "Compiler / TRanslator GENEration with LEX & YACc".
2. Creating Python scripts to query, compile and build; and check results of computer programs as assigned for students in ECE 351 class of racist DEREK-GAYSIDE.

◦ * *GRADUATE (MENG, MASC, PHD) LEVEL COURSE – METHODS AND TOOLS FOR SOFTWARE ENGINEERING (ECE 650)*

1. I went to classes like students to assist idiot-Igor-IVKOVIC that required this visitation of classes for me. – *"(*) Professor task level"*

"deceased NOVEMBER 2021 igor idiot-ivkovic wasn't not even capable of understanding what he taught in front of students professional himself. THAT'S why he required my presence in classes so I will help him better ! "

"IT Means IGOR-ivkovic shalln't have gain more "payment cheques" than myself because it seemed to me I would do more teaching than he did."

◦ *Computer Networks (ECE 428)*

1. "Creating Python scripts to query, compile and build; and check results of computer client-server programs as assigned for students class of racist-idiot Mahesh-Rayside."

◦ * *GRADUATE (MENG, MASC, PHD) LEVEL COURSE – FOUNDATIONS OF SOFTWARE ENGINEERING (ECE 651)*

1. "Learned on the grasp theories and practices of software quality metrics and tools so to teach them to students. IGOR ivkovic, the deceased idiot-instructor wasn't even capable himself of anything." – *"(*) Professor task level"*

◦ [*C++ Laboratory (ECE 250)*]

1. *Working with "iranian in north-america", as being a black-afro-descendant is not recommended at ALL !*

"JON eyolfson is a burglar incompetent GUJA that is not even capable of respecting an agreement of 2-weeks replacement for his office mate."

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (TEACHING ASSISTANT — UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

- I. **Duties completed by Teaching Assistant [Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering (Dr.-Ing.)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou |**
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Sep. 2012 – Apr. 2015]
- 1.) [SUMMARY of student research-teaching advisory work both "autonomously" and, from my PH.D-advisor PATRICK].
 - 2.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of INSTRUCTOR "MAHESH rayside-idiot":**
 - o [Computer Networks \(ECE 428\)](#) **SPRING term (Jan.-Apr.) "2013"**
"THIS ignorant professor couldn't be even capable of clearly defining programming assignments, AS I had to tweak the Python code for automatically correct student code source from Gitlab-repositories created by a so called [PATRICK-lam]."
[THIS ignorant didn't even know I was a perfect computer software developer since age 18 in Cameroon; as demonstrated by my professional record of employment in GERMANY that is at least trice more developed technologically than idiot CANADA.]
 - 3.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of instructor "Derek rayside-idiot":**
 - o [Compilers \(ECE 351\)](#) **FALL term (Sep.-Dec.) "2012"**
"THIS idiot from massachusetts-gay institute of technology cannot even define what is mathematical relation WITHOUT saying: I quote him: 'a relation is like a table'... (<https://csail.mit.edu/sdg>)
"I was kind of surprise that we MUST had to code source code to correct programmings assignments as "styles of programming for instance, comments, etc," MUST be also marked and more importantly advised, Especially from a performance confirmed seasoned software developer as myself: DR.-PH.D. of ENGINEERING XAVIER noumbissi noundou. (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) "
"I was very surprised to see a [culprit called MATTHEW MA] that was Master of Applied Science of DEREK, COMING to myself with his mother and offer me "\$400 CAD so to code for his MASTER PROJECT in Computer Software Engineering from derek." "
"Thinking that derek went to pay around \$30 000—CAD to MATHGENEALOGY.ORG, (<https://mathgenealogy.org>) so my free registration from "[PATRICK] AND rinard-martin; (<https://csail.mit.edu/~rinard>)" from 'PH.D.' onto 'ABD' be changed without any formal justification as specified [[here];] DEREK-GAYSIDE is only someone that hijacked to get a degree from renowned MIT." "
 - 4.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of instructor "LADAN":**
 - o [\[C++ LABORATORY \(ECE 250\)\]](#) **FALL term (Sep.-Dec.) "2014"**
"THIS in german so called 'HURE'-prostitute (<https://Wikipedia.org>) Declares be a professor for software system.
I cannot testify this as "her student MOHAMMAD HAMDAQA" was so ignorant and had a tremendous background in business but knew nothing on software system at all ! "
"I spent hours talking to ladan via her idiot student from JORDAM-kingdom that seems to have even acquired a faculty position at so called "ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE MONTREAL-qc-chien-tabawak-satan" (<https://www.polymtl.ca>) "
 - 5.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of instructor "deceased-Igor Ivkovic-idiot":**
 - o * GRADUATE (MENG, MASC, PHD) LEVEL COURSE – METHODS AND TOOLS FOR SOFTWARE ENGINEERING (ECE 650) **FALL term (Sep.-Dec.) "2013"**
 1. I went to classes like students to assist idiot-Igor-IVKOVIC that required this visitation of classes for me. – **"(*) Professor task level"**
"deceased NOVEMBER 2021 igor idiot-ivkovic wasn't not even capable of understanding what he taught in front of students professional himself. THAT'S why he required my presence in classes so I will help him better ! "
"IT Means IGOR-ivkovic shalln't have gain more "payment cheques" than myself because it seemed to me I would do more teaching than he did."
o * GRADUATE (MENG, MASC, PHD) LEVEL COURSE – FOUNDATIONS OF SOFTWARE ENGINEERING (ECE 651) **SPRING term (Jan.-Apr.) "2013"**
 1. "Learned on the grasp theories and practices of software quality metrics and tools so to teach them to students. IGOR ivkovic, the deceased idiot-instructor wasn't even capable himself of anything." – **"(*) Professor task level"**
 - 6.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of instructors "Patrick LAM", and "LIN tan":**
 - o [Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance \(ECE 453 / SE 465\)](#) **SPRING term (Jan.-Apr.) "2015"**
- II. **Duties completed by Teaching Assistant [Diplom-Informatiker (Dipl.-Inf.)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou |**
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]
- 1.) **Teaching assistant under supervision of instructor "Patrick LAM":**
 - o [Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance \(ECE 453 / SE 465\)](#) **SPRING term (Jan.-Apr.) "2010"**
"I AM THE one that creates the only sample solution to midterms. PATRICK is not very good at kind of creating technical solutions based on graph-theoretical foundations as for instance when creating equivalence class based test sequences solutions."
o [Programming for Performance \(ECE 459\)](#) **SPRING term (Jan.-Apr.) "2011"**
I co-create with other teaching assistants such as [JON-eyolfson] solutions for assignments and / or midterms exams.
I also receive students during predefined weekly time frame so to help them out with understanding of learning courses material.

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (TEACHING ASSISTANT – CONTINUED [1] - THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. CO-teach and CO-assign, & Co-mark Assignments for Graduate and Undergraduate Computer (Software) Engineering Students (ECE Department) |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [OCT. 2009 – APR. 2015]

[PROOF READING,
static code dataflow analysis,
SCALA,
JAVA, C++, *JUnit* testing,
research ideas talks and development,
computer programming teaching]

[Summary-PAGES]

I. Students from the University of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA I helped during my stay at the University of Waterloo, ON:

1. ["Matthew Ming Ma, M.A.Sc., Mechatronics, Engineering":]

- How to configure a "developer" JAVA virtual machine under Ubuntu LINUX;
- "I gave him contextual help in writing JAVA code for his Master of Applied Science project, under supervision of Derek Rayside".
- HE then got a so called, at "**APPLE INC. LTD.**" (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>) , **software in test developer** (<https://www.apple.com/jobs>) job;

That is why even a "**WIFI-connection**" to a laptop doesn't work with APPLE phones as I COULD experience myself in CAMEROON (a white phone paid for \$120 CAD).

2. ["DR. JON eyolfson, Ph.D. in Electrical & Computer Engineering":] (<https://www.jeyolfson.com>)

- How to use efficiently and effectively double pointers in C++ function / method calling argument parameters;
- "I gave him my full LaTeX doctoral Ph.D. thesis (ECE calls this a research proposal) document for helping him out with a template at his own request".

3. "Dr. Vajih MONTAGHAMI, Ph.D., Electrical & Computer Engineering":

- Thorough discussions and talks about his research ideas and on computer programming related topics (mostly on the "Watform LAB white-board").

4. "Divam Jain, M.Math., Computer Science", from Ph.D.-advisor of mine Dr. of Engineering "Patrick LAM":

- Gave "DIVAM" sample code of my sample projects in JAVA about static code dataflow analysis à la "Gary A. Kildall : **A unified approach to global program optimization** (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)"; As opposed for instance to static code dataflow analysis "à la **IFDS (Interprocedural, Finite, Distributive, Subset)** (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Inter-procedural-data-flow-analysis-with-IFDS-IDE-Bodden/a3f7557fe673ff0711e9049cf5ece8b02a51f7f1>)" from "**THOMAS-reps at the university of wisconsin-madison**" (<https://www.grammatech.com>) .

IBM provides WALA as library for working with IFDS framework. (<https://research.ibm.com/publications/program-analysis-using-wala>)

- Introduction and supervision on how to use **SOOT** (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>) ;
- Brief discussions and talks on using static dataflow analysis for JUNIT test case generation;
- Declared "Master of Mathematics" title at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO: "**Detecting Test Clones with Static Analysis**" (<https://hdl.handle.net/10012/7943>).
- **FOLLOWING** plagiare by [zheng FELIX fang] and [PATRICK lam] originate from this seminal initial work where I contributed partly in code source writing:

A) "**Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints**" (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)

5. "zheng FELIX fang, M.A.Sc., Electrical & Computer Engineering", from Ph.D.-advisor of mine Dr. of Engineering "Patrick LAM":

- Overview of ["Divam Jain's"] previous work on SOOT and static dataflow analysis for generating JUNIT test cases.
- Brief discussions and talks on using static dataflow analysis for generating JUNIT test cases.;
- "Declared MASTER OF APPLIED SCIENCE title" at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO: "**Test Clone Detection via Assertion Fingerprints**" (<https://hdl.handle.net/10012/8831>);
- FANG then got a position at MICROSOFT corporation in SEATTLE.
- [1 scientific conference paper came out of this supervision-advising :]
- a.) "**Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints**" (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)

1. HELPIng black–descendant students from the UNIVERSITY of waterloo–racist–on |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Oct. 2009 – apr. 2015]

I. *Students from the University of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA I helped during my stay at the University of Waterloo, ON:*

1. **"Amirhossein Vakili, Ph.D., Computer Science":** (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~avakili>)
 - How to use MAKE;
 - static dataflow analysis explanation.
 - "1st at all functional programming with SCALA introduction".
2. **STUDENTS in cameroon association rowac.** (<https://rowac.ca>) **"JUST IN MY SPARE TIME, not at a position in university"**
 - **We at ROWAC (formerly CCAKW (Camerroonian Community Association in Kw)); Have invited ambassador-pd-idiot of Cameroon in OTTAWA (ontario) during summer 2014 if my thoughts are exact. THIS was during the soccer tournament we organized.**
 - I presented and gave out certain documents I wrote about computer web software security vulnerabilities protection; AND measures to protect documents and computer–laptop during, after 1 general meeting evening around 06 : 00 PM.
 - AFTER graduating, and came back into canada to resign an idiot-canadian citizenship acquired for travel-without-visa-purpose-only to EUROPE; I then discovered that several members of ROWAC were secret–servicess-agent of my assassin of paternal uncle LAURENT-tchandeu, PleniPOTENTIARY–minister:
 - Dr. (M.Sc.) Vincent Nanga
 - Dr. (M.Sc.) Innocent Tchigio
 - Dr.-PHARM. (M.Sc.) CHEONGWA wandzi-cheongwa@yahoo.com
3. **"Godrick–chékété, Ph.D., French literature":** **"JUST IN MY SPARE TIME, not at a position in university"**
 - I MET "Godrick–chékété" via "YAW boakye-agyeman, ph.d. student in recreational studies at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON CANADA";
 - Help in FINDING HIS way after his divorce from his spouse from BENIN (house searching, car fixing, etc.);
 - HELP in looking for a financial loan at a Canadian bank.
4. **"Eric Brefo–Mensah, Ph.D., Chemistry":** **"JUST IN MY SPARE TIME, not at a position in university"**
 - I MET Eric brefo-mensah via "CHIWANZA-kasanga";
 - Help in proof reading his Master Thesis LaTeX document before his final submission in "year 2018".
5. **Shirley Ddamba, "M.ASc. Civil Engineering":** **"JUST IN MY SPARE TIME, not at a position in university"**
 - I MET SHIRLEY at a bible study at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON CANADA;
 - Help in learning hands–on car driving in Ontario.
6. **Esther Lambert, "Ph.D., Geography, University of Toronto, 2017":** **"JUST IN MY SPARE TIME, not at a position in university"**
 - I MET ESTHER while she was cashier at ZEHRS–churchill–street.
 - Help in proof reading her Master thesis for the department of geography;
 - Help in learning hands–on car driving in Ontario;
 - ESTHER then pursue 1 year internship at ONTARIO green–belt institute; SHE then was admitted at the University of Toronto for "doctoral Ph.D. in GEOGRAPHY".

RESEARCH AND TEACHING ('PROFESSIONAL' TEACHING ASSISTANT – CONTINUED [2] - THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. CO-teach and CO-assign, & Co-mark Assignments for Graduate and Undergraduate Computer (Software) Engineering Students (ECE Department) | UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [OCT. 2009 – Apr. 2015]

I. *Professional Computer Engineers living in Germany I helped during my whole time at "UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, canada":*

1. "A paternal uncle Demo Noundou from Cameroon" (<https://www.ank-technologies.com>).

r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou" who at 1st was an illegal migrant worker idiot in GB–great britain, a junior brother of my late father and genitor "Théodore Nounbissi, B.Sc., Electrical & Computer Engineering"; was a student in Information Technology student at "TUHH — Technische Universität Hamburg–Harbug" (<https://www.tuhh.de>), and graduated from there with a "Bachelor of Sciences (B.Sc.)".

"Demo" then obtained a position as "PHP – JAVA Web Software Developer" at "Canon LTD.", based in Germany - Osnabrück !

AT least trice (3 times) a month, I will receive a phone call from Germany requesting software programming and / or database technical help from this GUJA.

Each time I could solve his issues until HE stopped calling around August 2014, when I became a CANADIAN citizen, and when himself *r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou"* went for a marital union with *r-"Astride Patibé"*; a nurse from Cameroon – Baham – BAFANG tribe.

r-"CÉLESTIN puene" is another (Food–processing) engineer from Cameroon that came to myself sent by "his natal village Babouantou" friend paternal uncle *r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou"* .

HE came saying he needed help in buying a mechanical truck from the USA for his brother in cameroon who possessed a road construction society in YDE. *r-"CÉLESTIN puene"* was first living in Frankfurt–GERMANY, before moving around 3 years after myself, into Canada [WASKAGANISH, qc; and "then Brampton, ON"].

" *r-"CÉLESTIN puene"* and *r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou"* are now member of [** +—"ROTARY CLUB INTERNATIONAL"—+ **]; *r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou"* was initiated by *r-"MBOUM, MD, Ph.D. (surgeon)"* from OSNABRÜCK–germany. I could say I do not want to be member when *r-"DD-David-DEMO noundou"* asked for this in year 2014".

I. TRAIN young engineers & developers; CO-write software parts for YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM |

YERITH R&D, YAOUNDÉ, CMR

[2016 - 2017]

A. "ENGINEER-ENSPY job seeker-gay PAUL:"

THIS young scientist from ECOLE-NORMALE-SUPERIEURE-de-Yaounde came to myself via THE culprit named JOSEPH-djournessi during my attending of a biblical study at his home in BYEMASSI-yaounde-ACCACIA; IN year 2016.

"I started teaching C programming to this young gay electrical engineer from CMCI-communauté missionnaire internationale chrétienne OBILI-obédience (CMCI-obili); While he was looking for employment for almost 6 years after graduating as BSc.-electrical engineer from "École Nationale Supérieure Polytechnique de Yaoundé - ENSPY"."

HE stopped attending just 2 weeks after starting participating in group meeting with the 2 following scientist-educators.

HE said his financing person wanted him to focus only in applying for positions in industry such as "BRASSERIES DU CAMEROUN", etc.

B. "Scientist-educator-cuon KITIO:"

THIS young scientist from ECOLE-NORMALE-SUPERIEURE-de-Yaounde came to myself via THE culprit named JOSEPH-djournessi during my attending of a biblical study at his home in BYEMASSI-yaounde-ACCACIA; IN year 2016.

"I taught him how to use DEBIAN LINUX from the command line."

He could find a position as computer science teacher in a secondary school in west cameroon !

C. "Scientist-educator-cuon CHARLES-eteme; now working at Yaounde GENERAL hospital:"

THIS young scientist from ECOLE-NORMALE-SUPERIEURE-de-Yaounde came to myself via THE culprit named JOSEPH-djournessi during my attending of a biblical study at his home in BYEMASSI-yaounde-ACCACIA; IN year 2016.

"I taught him how to use DEBIAN LINUX from the command line."

HIS father could find him soon a position at "Yaounde GENERAL hospital" where he was earning "250 000 Xaf" to start his career as a staff web developer.

TODAY, as I have been living in Cameroon for more than 6 years now full time; I believed he was a "SED"-anti gang; IT means someone hijacking people from west-region so to make them wretched as a political argument for PAUL-biya-idiot-CPDM-president.

I. TRAIN young engineers & developers; CO-write software parts for [YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM](#) |

YERITH R&D, YAOUNDÉ, CMR

[Jan. 2021 – "April 20, 2025"]

A. "Engineer JEAN-PIERRE kamgain-idiot:"

This not professional computer science & computer engineering graduate, from "THE university of Yaounde 1", and from "IAI Cameroon"; was interested in various web-related tasks for searching employment within Douala.

1.) *plain code source "C" application programming interface development;*

A sample task was a development of a translator from "Qt 5 user interfaces (".ui" files)" onto "HTML5 pages";

2.) *JAVA servlet & apache tomcat server;*

A sample project using *APACHE-maven* (<https://>), for car maintenance & rental was developed both by myself and by JP-kamgain-culprit.

THIS sample exegete of "IAI Cameroon" wasn't capable of clearly write JAVA code as supposed with a "*bachelor of honours in Computer Software Engineering*" from both "IAI Cameroon"; And "University of Yaounde 1 (UY 1)".

3.) *PHP software development.*4.) *Training P.C.T.B-sarl employee on YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum:*

The culprit and school-mate NGADJEU-francis, refused to utilize JP because he went without asking advise from me recruit a so called call-girl-*IUC-cameroon* (<https://myiuc.com>).

5.) *Indicator for destruction of YVES-landry-galax-etoga in person:*

"JEAN-pierre kamgain has been trying to hijack my properties, both physically and emotionally because I COULD notify that HE was trying to spy my activities for "C.P.D.M party as NGADJEU-francis from P.C.T.B.-sarl did"“;

"Also JP-kamgain is the one that went to propose my ERP software system to BONTÉE sarl in AKWA-sud douala.“

6.) *[COPLATEC sarl is a psy-company for hijacking people at home:]*

OUR experience in Africa has been that at least "85% of societies" that are of type "SARL-ndlr-société à responsabilité limitée", 'GmbH (<https://WIKIPEDIAlinkDefinition.ORG>)-in-German-language';

"are companies for gay owned by soldiers FOR hijacking male and/or female consultants like myself that do not participate officially in lesbianism and homosexuality-zoophyte.“

ARLETTE-sibeuf seemed to be also member of SED.

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (POSTDOCTORAL RESEARCHER AT THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. Create and Present, & Write Research Projects in Computer (Software) Engineering Students (ECE Department) | [Sep. 2012 – Apr. 2015]
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA
- [VIJAY-ganesh-chenapan, static dataflow taint analysis, dynamic binary program analysis, "INTEL-Pin", LLVM]
- A. Duties completed by Researcher [Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering (Dr.-Ing.)] Xavier Noubissi Noundou:
1. **SUCCESSFUL attendance of graduate level courses to improve my dissertation writing and research skills level of knowledge :** [Sep. 2012 – OCT. 2015]
 - a.) ["Program Analysis for Web Apps"] "Grade 88%";
 - b.) ["Static Analysis for Software Engineering (SASE)"] "Grade 88%".
 2. **SOLE and INDEPENDENT idea and research of development of static dataflow taint analysis with use of "compiler framework LLVM", for solving following complex software engineering problems:** [Sep. 2012 – OCT. 2015]
 - a.) "Application Programming Interface (API) usage temporal rules";
"QUANTAMP.COM (<https://www.quantstamp.com>) uses for instance part of this research outcome to solve the problem of checking the conformance of BITCOIN-related-software-automated-contracts."
 - b.) "Detecting software security vulnerabilities" that endanger normal workflow, PER user-requirement elicitation, OR per software usability engineering: "BUFFER-OVERFLOW problems"; "SQL-injection problems"; "FORMAT-STRING attacks problems"; "AUTOMATIC test case and test data generation solution classes";
 - c.) "VERY PRECISE AND DETAILED collaboration with Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. VIJAY-ganesh";

THIS research is more detailed in: [YERITH-SAINT \(https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293\)](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293) [11].

1. Create and Present, & Write Research Projects in Computer (Software) Engineering (ECE Department) |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2012 – 2014]

[Vijay-GANESH-from Ph.D.-at-stanford.edu (<https://research.gatech.edu/people/vijay-ganesh>),
RESEARCH outcome plagiarism,
RESEARCH outcome hindrance,
"JAN-peleska-crédule; best-ever-professor of mine",
"student advising-MISSING paper",
static dataflow taint analysis,
LLVM (<https://llvm.org/racist-apple>)]

A. Duties completed by Assisting Professor [Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering (Dr.-Ing.)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou:

[Summary-PAGES]

1. EXPERIMENTATION WITH IFDS-FRAMEWORK FROM "REPS ET AL."

[JAN. 2013 – JUNE 2013]

I discovered the "IFDS (Interprocedural, Finite, Distributive, Subset)" (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Inter-procedural-data-flow-analysis-with-IFDS-IDE-Bodden/a3f7557fe673ff0711e9049cf5ece8b02a51f7f1>) problems algorithm by THOMAS reps from UNIVERSITY-of-WISCONSIN-MADISON (<https://www.uwiconsin.edu>), and from "Grammatech" (<https://www.grammatech.com>);

"I really enjoyed this graph-based software system interdependence algorithm; and accompanying free FOSS IBM-wala library (<https://research.ibm.com/publications/program-analysis-using-wala>)".

NEVERTHELESS I tried a personal implementation of the IFDS-framework using SOOT (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>) & Java-SCALA with no successful binaries; BECAUSE the ideology for using "IBM-wala" was quite strange to my understanding !!!

I then renounced & abandoned to pursue and implement "The KILDALL-style" ("Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)") using C++ and a book-Advanced Compiler Design-from ...IBM author... !:

 YERITH-SAINT (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) [23]

2. [Work on "Dynamic PROGRAM Analysis with FRANK-tip" in course CS846] & [Work on "Software System Security by Software VERIFICATION"]

3. [SUMMARY of student research-teaching advisory work both "autonomously" and, from my PH.D.-advisor PATRICK.]

[Sep. 2009 – Mar. 2015]

4. [Previous RESEARCH-development at AGBS—UNIVERSITY-OF-BREMEN.DE] :

"JAN peleska is my 1st best ever professor because I learned the best research skills from him while working in his research group in Germany-bremen-racist (E.g.: Unfortunately for myself; I couldn't get any professional-vocational student software developer position in a commercial company installed in Bremen.). (<https://informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp>)"

[FSE-soqua 2006]

"More importantly we had a paper at Foundations OF Software Engineering research conference in 2006 while I was working on my "Diplom-Informatiker degree [Dipl.-Inf.] (Master of Science equivalent)" in his research group at the University-of-bremen.de (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>): "Test Automation for Hybrid Systems" (www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp/papers/peleska_et_al_soqua2006.pdf) — ("VERIFIED.DE" (<https://www.verified.de/products/model-based-testing>)) !!! "

5. Follow-up on research started by [DIVAM-jain] with following other fellow researchers at ECE:

- o DEREK-rayside
- o PATRICK-lam
- o REID-holmes
- o LIN-tan-idiot-gay-non-sense-girl
- o FELIX-fang
- o etc.

I started collaborating with DIVAM jain because PATRICK-lam sent DIVAM jain to me for learning about static dataflow code analysis using SOOT.

"WHEN divam-jain-racist left, I pursue this same research with FELIX fang, and then with researchers afore-mentioned in office of the director of software engineering program PATRICK-lam; Where we attended to group collaborative meetings."

THEN he was more about the problem itself; IN this occasion, how to automatically generate "JUnit test suites test cases" based on static code dataflow analysis of unit test code of the analyzed projects.

"A benchmark of "at least 100 open source JAVA libraries" was used to test these projects JUnit test code.

From this research came out at least 11 conference peer-reviewed papers and some journal articles, AND i wasn't mentioned as a co-author either:

- 1.) "Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints" (<https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/2807426.2807437>)

1. Create and Present, & Write Research Projects in Computer (Software) Engineering (ECE Department) |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA

[Sep. 2014 – 2018]

["sodomite-peggish-JULIA-rubin-AT-UNIVERSITY-of-british-columbia-CANADIAN-rate-gay-Israelite-ANTI-JESUS-OF-Nazareth",
dynamic binary program analysis,
"INTEL-Pin"]

A. Duties completed by Assisting Professor [Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering (Dr.-Ing.)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou:

4. **DEVELOPMENT of certain features of PHP-JAVA-judo-quebec web application for management of club members:**

[JUNE 2014 – NOV. 2014]

THE research paid-provision was around "1000 \$CAD" a month, which was very insignificant because of all the technologies working together such as: PHP, GWT (Google Web Toolkit), etc.

5. **PATRICK-idiot lam research idea**, and personal sole development of a dynamic binary program analysis for moving "PROGRAM-POINT" during runtime execution based on certain loop-condition; USING "INTEL-Pin" :

[SEP. 2014 – OCT. 2014]

PATRICK-idiot lam didn't allow myself to complete the program under his sole supervision.

I WASN'T really happy because he interrupted my main project on static taint dataflow analysis; HE didn't tell me anything about any outcome, and/or later done publication or whatsoever.

THIS research is more detailed in: [YERITH-SAINT \(https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293\)](https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293) [11].

6. **!!-sodomite-peggish-woman-attention-patrick-JULIA-rubin-ece-british columbia-faineant-chien-tabaweak-canaoe** said she will continue research with myself at UBC (<https://www.ece.ubc.ca/mjulia>) so I WILL GRADUATE as a "PH.D." !

[2018]

" IT was dereak-gayside that said I SHOULD TRY TO apply somewhere else than university-racist-of-waterloo since they-idiot-of-lam could call the police to arrest myself ILLEGALLY on waterloo dirty-racket-pd-cuon-tabaweak-quebec-salaud main campus !!! "

PLEASE FOLK that may think a white-racist Gives you a residence permit to allow yourself to fulfill your peace dreams; IT'S NOT THE CASE.

" THE WHITE-GAY-DAY-nancy-racist is only trying to reduce the speed of perfectionism and development of your country of origin by harassing you there with corrupt-gay authorities so you will try to go outside. "

" All these mansory-free-rotary-club-ETC.; CATHOLIC-gay-church is only a way to hijack your life in anti-christ-of-negger-jesus-of-nazareth like myself I HAVE BEEN experiencing for 7 years in ontarian-CANADA-shit-people-race. "

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (RESEARCH ASSISTANT – DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER – AT THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. CO-create and CO-present, & Co-write Research Projects in Computer (Software) Engineering Students (ECE Department) |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

[Algorithms dis-pension,
finite automaton theories,
"Year 2010 report",
"Year 2011 report",
"1st summer school on formal techniques",
[IDIOT-black-afro-descendant Sandy BEIDU from ghanaian land]]

I. Duties completed by Research Assistant [Diplom-Informatiker (Dipl.-Inf.; MSc)] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou:

1. [SUMMARY of student research-teaching advisory work both "autonomously" and, from my advisor-PH.,D. PATRICK].
2. **SUCCESSFUL attendance of graduate level courses to improve my dissertation writing and research skills** [SEP. 2009 – DEC 2011]
level of knowledge :
 - a.) ["First SUMMER SCHOOL on FORMAL techniques"] "participated with certificate";
 - b.) ["Computer-Aided Verification-racist-nancy"] "Grade 90%";
 - c.) ["Advanced Compiler Design-cuon-plagiarism-of-jon"] "Grade 86%".

3. I went to **menlo-racist-college** (<https://fm.csl.sri.com/SSFT11/index.shtml>) in California, USA, to the 1st summer school on formal techniques from "May 22, 2011" until "May 27, 2011"; under a recommendation-required (from professor doctor **NANCY-idiot-day** (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~nday>)).

I was accompanied by the GHANAIAN called SANDY-cuon-beidu supposed to be a very famous computer scientist originating from my home continent AFRICA.

[THIS hideous ignorant fellow, from a very poor material background arrived at the university of waterloo "WatForm-waterloo formal methods" in year 2010 if I have good memories; Saying to the world he is a JESUS-christian;]

This kind of black-afro-descendant is so disgusting that I believed that the racist **JO-atlee-his-research-advisor** (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~jmatlee>) went to pick him so to dishonest myself in front of the extremely dominant ["iranian female population in ECE graduate student folks"] !

HE even thought that I RENTED my "ford fusion" to tell them (Sandy-idiot-day, and a lady from long-island-black-prostitute) that I AM A WELL-TO-DO-MAN in front of them.

[I JUST remembered my BUSINESS-trip while I WAS TRAVELING for SIEMENS-medical-solutions-erlangen IN concord-ca-usa; And I KNEW I NEEDED to be mobile; THAT's why I RENTED A luxurious "ford fusion" from my savings account from my HARD-job at SIEMENS.]

[SANDY-idiot-poor-man-in-all-system thought when the other ghanaian idiot-story-teller-Dr.-PhD-ERIC-brefomensah brought me to his travesty-basement-slot in WATERLOO, in ontario, 2018; THAT i needed some drink from him !]

[PLEASE folk from basement places in GHANA; Cameroon don't need this kind of down-treatment as CAMEROON is way more advanced as demonstrated ONLY by me !!!!!!!]

4. I have worked on topic "temporal property verification in plugin-based software"; and created a computer-Libreoffice-Impress presentation slides for the **IBM workshop CASCON 2010-CDP-compiler-...** (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump/cdp2010/index.html>); [IBM WORKSHOP-CDP CASCON 2010]

THIS research as "**Master Of Science**" (so called "DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER DEGREE, ABBREVIATED (DIPL.-INF.) (MASTER OF SCIENCE EQUIVALENT)[?]") led to my "**Doctoral Thesis / PhD comprehensive examination**" released research technical document : "**Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software**" (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>)

5. I have created sample program static code analyzes using the **SOOT framework** (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>) so to acquire skills in static code program analysis.

A very short introduction: " " (<https://>) to SOOT framework by

6. I HAVE IMPROVED my algorithm design skills by implementing popular algorithms using the Following ALGORITHM POPULAR BOOKS:

- A. **Computer Systems: A PROGRAMMER'S PERSPECTIVE, 2nd edition** ("ISBN 13 : 978 – 0 – 13 – 610804 – 7"); by "**BYANT**"-racist & "**O'HALLARON**"-racist-sexist;
- B. **Introduction to Algorithms-Isbn: " "**; by **THOMAS cormen** (https://www.amazon.com/Introduction-Algorithms-fourth-Thomas-Cormen/dp/026204630X/ref=sr_1_1?crd=2UBHH37C2Y2J3&dib=eyJ2IjojMSJ9.RxrAGDmePG_uPSHKskT1qe4eJp18_sU0zfGdVfEd1BzcV0qunH6HMFdUvjfBk5T7_hbHBgRqWVHVSmsYFd00P9qIyOhMwCdwVMeRQodxABi7cszQqi1XxeWBu8jZqpGALecudSCyPct_N4de9gw1drRqhl2Alh8huCTZ2PeIofPH8JLCoU0jaTq8vuQ-G7z1Jdit5yRk2hl627B7GRAFGV3fio1k8kSGbcuK5_JsFw6g.AobHaMGD2q1MBzQIcdziArWazLVBUQztj2REK1DRJ0Y&dib_tag=se&keywords=CS+Algorithm+book&qid=1726183252&s=books&prefix=cs+algorithm+book%2Cstripbooks-intl-ship%2C313&sr=1-1).

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (RESEARCH ASSISTANCE FROM FOLK-IDIOT – DIPLOM-INFORMATIKER – AT THE UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA)

1. CO-create and CO-present, & Co-write Research Projects in Computer (Software) Engineering Students (ECE Department) |
UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA [Sep. 2009 – Dec. 2011]

[**"JOHN HOPCROFT"**, **"samaneh navabpour-racist-extreme"**, **"1st Summer School on Formal Techniques"**, **LLVM**, **SOOT**]

I. **People from [the University of Waterloo, Ontario, CANADA] whom I got academic help:**

1. "AAKARSH nair, M.ASc., Computer ENGINEERING, 2009"
 - "AAKARSH nair was the 1st student of DEAR-idiot PATRICK lam I have ever met.

HE is the 1st one to give me sample code on static dataflow analysis with "JAVA-SOOT framework (<https://www.soot-oss.github.io/soot>)" à la "Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)" "
2. "NANCY day"
 - "Professor DAY wrote a very good and tremendous recommendation that was used to admit myself to [**"First Summer School on Formal Techniques"**] (<https://fm.cs1.sri.com/SSFT11/index.shtml>), by THE NATIONAL SCIENCE FOUNDATION, SRI International, Menlo College, Atherton, California, USA; in year 2011".
3. "Samaneh Navabpour, Ph.D., Electrical & Computer Engineering"
 - SAM gave me 1st explanations about LLVM by using her previous work for a **paper-RITHM** (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/TEMPORAL-PROPERTY-VERIFICATION-IN-PLUGIN-BASED-NOUNDOU/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>) [21]; she worked on in SEBASTIAN fischmeister embedded computer research group; She confessed not having exactly applied a static dataflow analysis à la "Gary A. kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)";

BUT used only control flow graph related features to perform static dataflow analysis; this is NOT exactly **CLANG** ([https://](https://clang.llvm.org/)).
4. **Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Nomair Naeem, Ph.D.** (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~nanaeem>)
 - NOMAIR was the 1st person apart from Patrick, my doctoral Ph.D. advisor that took so much time to help me understand and proof read my **doctoral Ph.D. Thesis** (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/TEMPORAL-PROPERTY-VERIFICATION-IN-PLUGIN-BASED-NOUNDOU/c68c2374b1dca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>) [21];
 - NOMAIR helped myself in understanding the intricacies of a context-sensitive static parametric analysis by explaining from his **research paper Multi-object ...** ([https://](https://arxiv.org/abs/1508.02808)).
5. **Prof. Dr. Ondřej Lhoták, Ph.D.** (<https://www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~olhotak>)
 - Professor Lhoták accepted to review my **YERITH-SAINT** algorithm thoroughly.
 - Ondřej was very kind to help me with source code of 1 of his 1st LLVM dataflow analysis, before I started my own.
6. **Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. JOHN hopcroft-SEXIST, Ph.D.** (<https://www.cs.cornell.edu/jeh/>)
 - Explanation, at my email request, and very promptly and generously about an algorithm in his compiler book.

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' AND TEACHING (GRADUATE INTERN AT INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS MACHINERY (IBM))

1. Perform duties assigned by big manager and PATRICK doyle in JAVA-J9 JUST-IN-TIME OPTIMIZATION team (, located in Markham-ONTARIO-canada); (advised by Prof. VIJAY sundaresan, M.Sc. (MCGILL, QC, CANADA) | Patrick Doyle, (M.ASc., UNIVERSITY OF TORONTO, Ontario, CANADA))) | IBM TORONTO-IDIOT SOFTWARE LAB. [01/2012 – 08/2012]

[AS canadian-idiot permanent resident;

Automated Software TESTING with YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIFY (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verify>),

Program OPTIMIZATION (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>), "Clark-salauud Verbrugge, Ph.D. (<https://www.sable.mcgill.ca/~clump>)";

JVM – JAVA virtual machines, IBM – WEBSPPHERE, Managers are really understandable,

Racism from restaurant in india-bangalore-IBM-gay]

[Summary Dr.-Ing. (Ph.D.) Review Research-PAGES]

I. Comfort excellent for work research at IBM:

1. I was working into a brown cubicle and had so much freedom in work that I WAS SOMETIMES afraid that I AM NOT PERFORMING well.

BUT when I STARTED working closely more with VIJAY I felt so busy that I WAS DREAMING of going home around 03 : 00PM in evening;

IN total, IBM in MARKHAM offers very good working and research conditions for his employees, *even better than my previous 1st full-time job as JUNIOR-SOFTWARE-DEVELOPER at SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS in Erlangen, BAVARIA, GERMANY !!!*

SIEMENS MEDical solutions was really good in Erlangen; But i didn't like seeing "BOSS gerhard" watching his arm watch any 2 minutes to make sure we only had 45 minutes lunch-break; "Secretary "gudrun" is also really helpful and smiling ! "

II. ISSUES - Problems with some colleagues:

1. **Prof. Vijay Sundaresan, MSc. – from Bangalore, INDIA**

THIS daemon of work was so kind that I ONLY FEEL I have satisfy him as much as he wanted and could !!!

HE is very attracted to good and fast male workers; because female workers would only try to hijack his time for a snack !!!

I am very proud of having work with such an amazing scientist at all !!!

ALSO the team managers, including the chinese woman, were very kind to myself as the only male afro-descendant from AFRICA !!!

2. **Patrick idiot Doyle, M.ASc. – from Ireland-CANADA**

THIS ignorant as a teacher and / or mentor couldn't even pick myself at time when I Was waiting for my hiring team for the internship to come at my encounter in the biggest room where we all intern were awaiting 1st day of internship.

III. Duties of Graduate INTERN [Doctor of Engineering] Xavier Noumbissi Noundou:

1. **FIX SOFTWARE TESTING FEATURE AUTOMATION USING BASH SCRIPTS**

I felt a lot better at this task because I could feel having a positive impact on the project team lead by manager that I don't remember names and academic titles.

ALSO vijay sundaresan wasn't very disgusting as people working in the restaurant, that always served myself BURNed food, especially paganan-food.

Vijay sundaresan is a very talented software lead and developer that I could ever see in my career; I VERY MUCH LIKED THE INTERACTIONS with him compared to PATRICK doyle.

TODAY I FEEL there are 2 factors that helped:

A. **MCGILL university** (<https://www.mcgill.ca>) graduates in Computing Sciences are very much talented compared to other students from ONTARIO.

B. VIJAY-sundaresan was born also outside of Canada-racist-systemic like my recruiting manager that I forgot about names;

2. **MAINTAIN CERTAIN DAYS BUG DATABASE**

AT all not very difficult, since I WAS USED TO use CHARMNT in my previous full-time job at Siemens Medical Solutions in Erlangen, BAVARIA, germany.

3. **ATTEND TO COURSES AT IBM TORONTO-IDIOT LABORATORY GIVEN BY "pr. prof. dr.-ing. clark-salauud verbrugge" FROM MCGILL.ca** (<https://mcgill.ca>) "on Creating Optimizations for Compilers"

4. **SOLVE AS MANY AS BUGS IN COMPILER OPTIMIZATION CODE SOURCE IN C++**

Coming from a program analysis research team, that performed more static code analysis using framework like S00T, and LLVM; I WAS KIND OF not performing very well at this task at all because of the very applied and complicated data structures; Especially because PATRICK-indigeneous-iranian-irish-from-british-kingdom never even got me to a small talk for explaining me briefly what was the governing ideas leading the development team in MARKHAM.

INSTEAD, i only received so many documents that I had to read and detect understand myself.

Earning as much as 3 000 \$CAD monthly, I FELT SO BAD that I Went to complain to the manager; a very kind person; that allowed then myself to work with the team lead VIJAY sundaresan...

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' (WEB DEVELOPMENT INTERNSHIP AT BREMEN4U-GMBH-RACIST-PEGGIST)

1. CREATE AND MAINTAIN – HTML, CSS, PHP, JSP – CODE SOURCE FOR a Content Management System – as an EVENT MANAGEMENT SOFTWARE ONLINE racist (advised by MARTIN ...) |

BREMEN4U-GMBH-RACIST-PEGGIST, BREMEN, GERMANY-RACIST-PEGGIST

— March. 2004 —

[[WEB software development with PHP, CSS],

Peggist-racist colleague Martin...,

[JSP, HTML5,]

Samsung CONTACT Server on Redhat LINUX]

I. Duties of Web Development Intern [Vordiplom-B.Sc candidate (In Computer Science)] Xavier Noundou:

1. *Before attending and applying for this position; I attended courses workshops on Web development using MariaDB, HTML5, CSS, JSP, PHP during around 1 semester (4 months) at the Department of Computer Science ("FACHBEREICH 3) of the University of Bremen. (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>)*
2. *Create configuration in Redhat LINUX for the Samsung Contact Server system.*
3. *Create HTML5, CSS, JSP, PHP combined code into a Content Management System for managing Event that are to be published on a specific date on the Bremen4u-Gmbh website.*
4. *Martin was always having a very bad mouth-breath because of smoking cigarette all day together with drinking black dark coffee with no milk at all.*
5. *THIS was a very disgusting place to work as a new person living in Germany; also young girls from secondary school as internship workers; With almost no sense on respecting black african race at ALL !*

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' AND TEACHING (JUNIOR SOFTWARE DEVELOPER AT SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS)

1. CREATE AND MAINTAIN C++ CODE SOURCE FOR THE SOFTWARE COMPONENT (which is protocol communication control) TXSUPERVISOR of Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist Software (advised by DARIO MERAUVIGLIA | GERHARD SENG) |

SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS, BAVARIA, GERMANY

[NOV. 2007 – July 2009]

[C++,
Software Integration Testing [12],
 UNDER german-traveler work-permit;
 ROBOTEK-linac,
 Radiation Therapy Treatment,
 IMRT beam treatment,
 TXSUPERVISOR software component development]

1. Duties of Junior Software Developer [Diplom-Informatiker (Dipl.-Inf.) Xavier Noubissi Noundou:

1. "MARVELOUS TRAVEL to Concord, CALIFORNIA, USA : my greatest and high paid experience of work since I was given birth in 1983 !!! — 5 000 EUROS

THANK you boss gerhard-idiot-SENG !!!!!!! "

2. "Participation in cancer treatment (IMRT) radiation therapy training, and all other software development related training for this position as JUNIOR SOFTWARE DEVELOPER."
3. "C++ coding and defects fixing of DMIP control communication protocol as heart of Software component TXSUPERVISOR: around 110 000 Lines of code (SLOC)."
4. Development of an automated software integration test infrastructure:
 - a. Cygwin bash-scripting
 - b. Microsoft COM component as [CORBA] agent communication used

5. *Software Integration testing using "IBM Purify Plus".*

(COMPETITOR FROM "Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing. Xavier noumbissi Noundou":
 YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/10474033>) [?b]):
 <https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif> ;

6. "DMIP Control Console" device as user control management for simulating radiation therapy linear accelerator "SIEMENS Linac Artiste" in our laboratory in Erlangen ground-base;
7. *Focal entry point of all bugs of "Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist" software. INVESTIGATION, and then redistribution, according to defect type, to an appropriate sub-team VIA team-lead "Gehard Seng".*
8. Support technical in writing software user manual with software testers.
9. Support technical with software testers in using "Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist" software.
10. Phone support technical in TROUBLESHOOTING "Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist" software.
11. Maintenance of communication development support from software developers from Siemens Concord in California, USA.
12. *Maintaining using "MS office" of design documents of TXSUPERVISOR and "DMIP control communication protocol"; based on "FSM state machine theory": United States of America's FDA (U.S.A – Federal Drug and Administration), as well as CE (European Community) had to review the digitally signed documents; stored in "SAP-EDM (<https://www.sap.de>)".*
13. Assisting "DARIO meraviglia" in selection of interns based on their qualification as reported on their CV – resume.
14. Advising of 2 software testing maintenance part-time employees:
 1. 1 from Germany, from The University of Bamberg (Bayern, Germany);
 2. 1 as an intern, from India.
15. "VMWare" (<https://www.vmware.com>) as debugging image creator development tool.
16. "MS Windows 2000", as well as, "MS Windows NT", as software development operating systems platforms.
17. "Visual Studio C++" as IDE;
18. "IBM Rational ClearCase" as Code BASE source management control software used;
19. "IBM CharmNT" as bug management platform used;
20. *[LEGAL requirement summary experience with HANDLING of Design Documents Functional Specification for Medical Software according to "CE"; "FDA".]*

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' AND TEACHING (JUNIOR SOFTWARE DEVELOPER AT SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS)

1. CREATE AND MAINTAIN C++ CODE SOURCE FOR THE SOFTWARE COMPONENT (which is protocol communication control) TXSUPERVIROR of Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist Software (advised by DARIO MERAVIGLIA | GERHARD SENG) |

SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS, BAVARIA, GERMANY

[11/2007 – 07/2009]

[C++,
 Software Integration Testing,
 UNDER german-traveler work-permit;
 ROBOTER-linac,
 Radiation Therapy Treatment,
 IMRT beam treatment,
 TXSUPERVISOR software component development]

I. ISSUES – Problems with some colleagues:

1. Gerhard Seng and Dario Meraviglia told myself I should be promoted to the position of Dario as "technical lead of the software module component TXSUPERVISOR (only 1 developer)" if I could succeed in gaining a full-time permanent contract after an initial successful 6 months period of work under direct leadership of DARIO MERAVIGLIA.

"AFTER SUCCEEDING the trial period of 6 months, I obtain a change of software developer contract from a full-time limited contract to a full-time permanent contract with "Siemens Medical Solutions"."

"HOWEVER after an additional 15 months of work, I am not anymore promoted to a higher level position of Technical Lead."

"This is why I decide to make the effort to go back to academia and pursue [a doctoral Ph.D. in Electrical & Computer Engineering (Computer Software)] at the University of Waterloo, in ONTARIO, CANADA; WITH [Dr.-PhD patrick lam as academic adviser] !! "

2. "Merlin Tonka from Cameroon" is calling me even before my first day at job in Erlangen to tell me he hopes I will be able to perform well and thus keep my job beyond the 1st 6 months period of try: He tells myself HE got my email from boss "Gehrad Seng";

"From NORTH of GERMANY WHERE I STUDIED AND LIVED for almost 6 years before being recruited and before moving to Fürth-BAVARIA-Germany, this is not "SACK-ARBEIT": I.E. one shall not mixed private life affairs with business matters at all: THIS IS HOW I LEARNED IT in HAMBURG, and BREMEN ! "

3. "Merlin Tonka" one day follows myself in metro and bus so to tell me that HE shall be promoted as a team of a new testing and developers team, And that he shall be my manager.

" I was wondering silently (because very young in year 2008 with only 23.5) years old ("Merlin Tonka was at least 40 years old in front of my age"), that someone less qualified than myself and currently employed as only a software tester, which is a lower level required qualification; Put aside you are PhD-doctor-of-engineering; and that was recruited only 1 week before my personal recruitment, will become my manager by telling it to me only in streets ! "

"THE italian master of science-level engineer Dario Meraviglia is my technical lead, followed by Gerhard Seng, our common teal lead at Syngo-RTT-Therapist-SW-Realize team" !

4. After leaving "Siemens Medical Solutions" legally by resigning with a signed letter 3 months before leaving my IG-METAL-tariff-vertrag employment in year 2009; I sent a letter to thank "MERLIN TONKA" for the positive professional collaboration I had with him as a fellow cameroonian, despite a lot of troubles we had; I sent this letter only around 1 month after starting studying in Waterloo, Ontario, Canada.

"THE answer from "Merlin Tonka" is so negative minded and outspoken that I need to reply to tell him truth about not trying again to tell me he is superior to myself; I.e. Merlin tries in a letter to tell me I could not perform well in software developer job, that's why I resigned !!! "

"Only smelling the same dirty "grey-shirt" MERLIN was wearing almost every day was not comfortable because he was sitting just opposite side of my office-desk ! "

"I today in year 2024 can remark as a citizen living inside CAMEROON that killer from governmental agency [DGRE wear generally grey-shirts !]"

"UDM-universit des montagnes (<https://WIKIPEDIA.ORG-racist>) later on in year 2009 invited DGRE-activist MERLIN tonka through THE KILLER OF MY GENITOR thodore noumbissi; So called [HUGUES NTOMANI tiako], which is sleeping with genitor ROSE sangnou so to perform crimes on my person even now in year 2024 ! "

"WHITE-blond supremacist slave-maker; PLEASE stop to hijack black afro-descendants that are talented. TILO. MCKE. DARIO. MERAVIGLIA. MERLIN. TONKA ! "

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' AND TEACHING – CONTINUED (1) (JUNIOR SOFTWARE DEVELOPER AT SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS)

1. CREATE AND MAINTAIN C++ CODE SOURCE FOR THE SOFTWARE COMPONENT (which is protocol communication control) TXSUPERVIR of Syngo-RTT-Artiste Therapist Software (advised by DARIO MERAVIGLIA | GERHARD SENG) |
SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS, BAVARIA, GERMANY [11/2007 – 07/2009]

III Students living in Germany I helped during my whole time at Siemens Medical Solutions:

1. **"paternal uncle Demo Noundou from Cameroon".**

Information Technology student in Bachelor of Sciences (BSc) at "TUHH — Technische Universität Hamburg-Harbug".

[Help in proof reading his Bachelor-Thesis.]

IV Students living in Canada I helped during vacation time by my uncle maternal "Théodore Wandji":

1. Co-roommate of Théodore Wandji at 5850 Rue Souart, #7, H3S 2E8, Quebec, Montreal, CANADA:

"Basser from Syria":

Electrical & Computer Engineering student in Master of Applied Sciences (M.ASc.) at "ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE MONTREAL".

NON paid technical support in programming C++, with **"MS Windows 2000 as operating system (OS) platform"**.

2. **"Fabrice TCHOUMI from Cameroon":**

Electrical & Computer Engineering student in Bachelor of Applied Sciences (B.ASc.) at "ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE MONTREAL".

NON paid technical support in programming C++, with **"MS Windows 2000 as operating system (OS) platform"**.

V Software Development Colleagues were:

1. Senior Software Developer "MAMIDI" from INDIA.
2. Senior Software Developer "Detlef Kendelbacker" (Contractor) from Bayern-Germany.
3. Team Lead "Gerhard seng" from Bayern-Germany.
4. Software Architect Balakrishnan; from India.
5. Technical Lead DESIREE görisen; from Bayern-Germany.
6. Technical Lead [Dr.] GANESH gopalakrishnan; from India.
7. Technical Lead [Diplom-Informatiker (FachHochschule) : [Dipl.-Inf. (FH)]] Johannes Bauer; from Bayern-Germany.
8. Technical Lead [Diplom-Informatiker (FachHochschule) : [Dipl.-Inf. (FH)]] Martin Maier; from Bayern-Germany.
9. Technical Lead [Ing., Polytechnico Di Milano] Dario Meraviglia; from Italy.

VI Software Testing Colleagues were:

1. Test Manager [Diplom-Informatiker : [Dipl.-Inf.]] "TILO mücke"; from Germany.
2. Software Tester "Merlin Tonka, M.Sc. (Computational Engineering, University of Erlangen-Nürnberg, Germany)" from Bagangte, Cameroon-French-Island
3. Software Tester "Suschma" from India
4. Software Tester "Swapnil, Bachelor (Mechanical Engineering)" from India
5. Software Tester "Dhananjay" from India

RESEARCH AND TEACHING (STUDENT SOFTWARE DEVELOPER AT GEWETE GMBH)

1. CREATE SQL databases JAVA Servlet programs and C++ communication protocol software programs (advised by SVEN KAMRATH | JENS MÖLLER) | BERGMANN AUTOMATEN GMBH (NOW GEWETE GMBH), GERMANY [03/2005 – 04/2007]

[CE – EUROPEAN COMMUNITY (https://www.single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/single-market/ce-marking_en), C++, MAKE, "JSWING", Hibernate, JAVA, Servlets, apache ANT, Eclipse IDE, XML (e.g: JAXP library), Qt, SQL, Vending machines, Communication protocol – [debugging at YERITH R&D Now !](#)]

I. APPLICATION FOR A STUDENT DEVELOPER POSITION AT "BERGMANN AUTOMATEN GMBH":

I stumble on this offered position while I WAS LOOKING FOR A NEW DEVELOPER position part-time when I KNEW MY PROJECT with "PROF. DR. RER. POL. KLAUS–racist bönkost" would not be renewed.

THE position was advertised on a website for student jobs of the TUHH (<https://www.tuhh.de>).

II. Duties of Student Software Developer [Vordiplom in Informatik] Xavier noumbissi Noundou:

1. "LaDIVA java servlet XML parsing project development, and its installer Graphical User Interface (GUI) program developed using "JSWING" (<https://>) JAVA library technology."
2. "MESO": "LaDIVA java servlet XML parsing follower project development."
The novelty in this follower project is that I INTRODUCED, based on my research skills, acquired in BREMEN, an object–relational database object mapper called "Hibernate (<https://www.hibernate.org>)"; THIS was to be capable of giving newer customers ORACLE 9i functionalities from "LaDIVA java servlet XML parsing project" !!!
3. "C++ coding of a "Sap–ABAP protocol communication interface" to put "Bergmann Automaten GmbH" vending machines in communication with vending machine of Hamburg public library that used "BIBLIOTHECA software library".
4. "C++ coding of SIPv2 control communication protocol (<https://>)."
5. Migration from "ORACLE 9i database tables" onto "MySQL database tables" for the MESO project (follower of LaDIVA software project); I used following technologies:
 - a. BASH–scripting
 - b. AWK scripting language.

III. Students living in Germany I helped during my whole time at "Bergmann Automaten GmbH, Rellingen, Hamburg":

1. "paternal uncle Demo Noundou from Cameroon".
Information Technology student in Bachelor of Sciences (BSc) at "TUHH — Technische Universität Hamburg–Harburg" (<https://www.tuhh.de>).
"Demo" then obtained by "Bergmann Automaten GmbH" a position as "Bachelor student working on its thesis, project–based":
 - a. I talked to "Mister Sven Kamrath of this request", by "Mister Demo Noundou", of a Bachelor Thesis Project.
 - b. HE ("DEMO") then refused a final offer as full–time "JAVA software developer" because he felt he couldn't perform well in a "JAVA plain object (JPO)" software development environment.
 - c. "[2008] Demo Noundou, B.Sc." then accepted a position at "Canon Ltd. as PHP – JAVA Web Software Developer in Osnabrück; HE can–also wear title Dipl.–Ing. (FH).".
 - d. "[2015] DEMO NOUNDOU is now at his own company in web development & training in HAMBURG. (<https://ank-technologies.com>)"
 - e. "[2024] DEMO is also a consultant in african universities curriculum development based in KENYA, and others. NO ONE CAN BE A PROPHET IN HIS HOME–YAOUNDE. (<https://SAINTEBIBLE.COM/jesusquoteTOCHECK>)"

"DEMO NOUNDOU, B.Sc." also had a "grade of (10.5/20)" which is not a very good grade to enter such position as the one I GOT LATER ON AT siemens medical solutions; A "GRADE OF 14.5/20" is required to apply for any entry level position at ["SIEMENS AG GERMANY–low–payer"].

IV. ISSUES - Problems with some colleagues:

1. Herr Sven Kamrath was very angry at myself 1 day during my stay in Rellingen to talk about an ongoing project 'LaDIVA XML Servlet Parser Server' !
"He found a subtle bug that I then fixed the same day."

'RESEARCH & DEVELOPMENT' AND TEACHING (WEB-HTML-CSS DEVELOPER AT ZENTRUM FÜR MULTIMEDIA IN DER LEHRE (ZMML))

1. CREATE AND MAINTAIN websites – www.s-hb.de (<https://www.s-hb.de>) mainly – for KLAUS-racist-extreme BÖNKOST (advised by PROF. DR. RER. POL. criminal Klaus Bönkost) |
 ZMML-UNIVERSITY-RACIST-SEXIST OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY [Feb. 2003 – Feb. 2005]

[*'dunklefarbige mitarbeiter xavier aus Afrika'*,
 HTML5,
 CSS,
 "photoshop",
 IMAGE-dateien,
 FADRI,
 SVEN schu]

I. Duties of WERKSTUDENT [candidate vordiplom in INFORMATIK] Xavier noumbissi Noundou:

1. "Reception, and implementation, of design documents (e.g.: "photoshop images", etc.) from FADRI-racist."
2. ["Programming of HTML5, CSS web pages."];

[Participated 1-month to a training internship at Bremen4u-GmbH.]

3. "Programming of RAD-server programs with Graphical User Interfaces (GUI); With programming support of Sven-schu-nazi."

"RAD-server programming language (<https://wikipedia.org> . . .) is a sample VISUAL BASIC dialect domain specific language. "

4. "Participation in weekly meeting on development of websites and test facilities for students in economia."

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES – UNI–RACIST BREMEN

1. CREATE A MODEL-BASED TESTING FRAMEWORK TO AUTOMATICALLY GENERATE STATECHART MODEL TEST CASES FOR REACTIVE SYSTEM SOFTWARE ([advised by Prof. Dr. rer. nat. habil. Jan Peleska]) |
UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY — "NOT fully described curriculum by myself" [09/2002 – 05/2007]
- a. "Diplom-Informatiker" : "MASTER 2" IN COMPUTER SCIENCE THESIS (DIPLOMARBEIT): "STATISTICAL TEST CASE GENERATION FOR REACTIVE SYSTEMS (GRADE 18/20)"; as part work for the FSE–SOQUA (2006) Research Conference Proceedings full research paper: "Test Automation for Hybrid Systems" (VERIFIED.DE), AGBS–UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY [12/2006 – 05/2007]
- [“V”–“WATER FALL”–MODEL of Software Development, reactive system, UML 2.0, HybridUML profile, statechart, Theoretical Computer Science, TDIOHS (time discrete input output hybrid system), STCT (symbolic test case tree), uniformly distributed statistical test case generation, MBT–RT-Tester, YRI–DB–RUNTIME–VERIF as of now a doctor (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>) .]
- Algorithms developed by myself for this 'Master of Science research–based Thesis ("Diplomarbeit" in German)' (https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/qualifikationsarbeiten/diplomarbeiten_e.html) [1a], based on 'Prof. Dr. Marie–Claude Gaudelle' research outcome, as a mathematician in France, are used in the RT–Tester tool of the verification and validation research and German society "VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GMBH, SPIN–OFF THE UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN" (<https://www.verified.de>) .
- b. C++ CODE GENERATION PLUGIN IMPLEMENTATION WITHIN CASE tool "Borland-Together", AGBS–UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY [09/2006 – 02/2007]
- [reactive system, UML 2.0, statechart, Theoretical Computer Science, TDIOHS (time discrete input output hybrid system), STCT (symbolic test case tree), C++ code generation, MBT–RT-Tester]
- Our algorithms are for the "TDIOHS: Timed Discrete Input / Output Hybrid System" (https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp/papers/peleska_et_al_soqua2006.pdf) state diagram formalism, that could be visualized by statecharts for instance using a 'Verified Systems International GmbH plug–in' for 'Borland-Together 6' (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Micro_Focus_Together) .
- c. "Research Master in Computer Science Software 2-Years PROJECT" : CogAG project : "Robot "Arni" usage in framework of creating mapping recognition algorithms and cartography.", Cognitive Systems Group (CoSy), "Christian Freksa as Project creator and lead", CoSy – University of Bremen, GERMANY [01/2005 – 03/2007]
- [Cognition, Cartography, RFID-tag technology, TEXT–TO–SPEECH (<https://>), Robot control, sensor, actuator, Debian Linux, C++, Qt, systemic racism]
- "My personal contributions were mostly in creating QT user interfaces code for controlling the virtual shop and the roboter "ARNI". I also was very much implicated in Software Engineering round–about code such as blackbox code for keeping a BB–blackboard software architecture between our software components and the MySQL database tables used to share some of the data between components of the software system."
- "I also worked on cognitive cartography algorithms using C/C++, together with "ALINA, Christian, Sasha, and SERDAR". I was moving the robot for scanning RFID sensors stapled onto our real test grocery store, and then trying to find a way for the robot–ARNI based on customer commands on the robot that were at entrance to help them find their way into the real test grocery store. I used text–to–speech technology to talk with robot–ARNI to customers. "
- I was also involved in:
1. HELPING in general project organization for instance:
 - A. Writing project meeting minutes.
 - B. Looking for places in train, buses for project week-end ("PROJEKT WOCHENENDE"). Etc.
 2. Searching for places ("Student sleep places – JUGENDHEBERGE") for project-week-end in groups for fasting our project development;
 3. Writing LaTeX documentation for project reports;
 4. Writing JUnit testing code for GUI code;
 5. Writing BASH–scripts for tackling connection problems between actuators and the Debian Linux Operating System (thanks to Christian).
- "Unfortunately I received a grade of only 2.7 (14/20) because I wasn't interested in cartography and cognition algorithms since this was the specialty of "Christian Freksa" and "CoSy Group of Research" (<https://cosy.informatik.uni-bremen.de>)."
- THIS IS THE REASON our project advisors "FRANK dylla", and "LUTZ frommberger" gave as justification to this baddest grade during my entire curriculum in ACADEMIA at all !
- I also need to mention that I was the only "SCHWARZNEGGER – black from africa" in this research group of mainly white–blond–racists like "MICHA", and "STEPHAN"...
- THESE 4 racists-idiot said some day I may not be very comfortable in group working with white–intellectual. I THINK "frommberger the female-male-gay–BORN-male was at origin of such systemic" sexist discrimination around myself; even during my research time under supervision of male-female-chevalie–boivert-PATRICK-lam !
- d. "A SEMANTIC COMPARISON BETWEEN BÜCHI AUTOMA AND TIMED AUTOMATA (Grade 20/20)", AGBS–UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY [09/2004 – 12/2004]
- [Vordiplom in informatik – INDEPENDENT STUDY, Bachelor Independent Study, MATHEMATICS for Computer Science, Theoretical Computer Science, timed automata, büchi automata, timed csp, set algebra]
- I developed a set of transformations functions that take as input a büchi automaton and generates a timed automaton. This work was the 1st work under supervision of "Jan Peleska", at our request, because we had interest in working in avionics software development in his company "Verified Systems International GmbH" (<https://www.verified.de>)."
- It is my uncle maternal "Théodore Wandji Ngongang" who is the one that gave me this advise at that time of my life where I was around 20 years old in Germany; "Just at my 2nd year of University."
- "Finally a small offer a 200 Euros monthly came after I performed 100 % for this work unpaid [details at link 1b], t hat I used as Independent study. "
- e. "1st & 2nd Semester Software Development PROJECT (Grade 18/20)", ST–UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY [09/2002 – 09/2003]
- [“V”–“WATER FALL”–MODEL of Software Development, Software Engineering, Project Requirements, "Gant Diagrams", UML 2.0, XML, PHP, MySQL, JAVA]
- "This 1st and 2nd semester project, divided in 2 parts consisted in creating a multi–user dungeon server (MUD–server) where a virtual world existed; 1st year was used to elicit user software program requirements, and establish "Requirement documents using UML 2.0".
 - "telnet (port 23)" protocol was used as client–server communication mechanism."
 - "I involved myself in a project where I contributed around 7 000 lines of plain JAVA code of program development."

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES – PSY–CARE – UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN

1. Psychological care | [10/2002 – 07/2007]
UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY
- A. "DIPL.–PSYCH. RALF ERIC STREIBL.", MATHEmatics and Computer Science Department, University of Bremen, Germany [10/2002 – 07/2007]
["Dipl.–Psych. Ralf ERIC Streibl".]
- "As a student of computer science in the "FB3" of the UNIVERSITY OF Bremen, In city Bremen, HANSEATISCHE-CITY, Germany, WE had a psychologist as 1 of our lecturer called "Dipl.–Psych RALF–idiot Eric Streibl". "
- RALF–idiot was kind of very reluctant to discriminative opportunities because I remember having visited courses on web creation based on PHP, and MariaDB, since I WAS having [a student–job (WERKSTUDENT) at "ZMML"].
- Eric RALF–idiot also gave myself a so called course titled "PROPÄDEUTIK" where we students learned on how to effectively, clearly present our projects or work; THIS was done in groups and individually !
- B. "AT–HOME–RACIST–IN–BREMEN PROGRAM", Foreigner office–"Sekretariat für AUSLÄNDISCHE studierende", University of Bremen, Germany [JULY 2005 – AUGUST 2017]
["RAÏNER schulze–smidt".]
- THIS program was exclusively addressed for foreign country students to gain access to german in–born families in order to accustom one to germany as a home country.
- "I joined this program because my maternal uncle "THÉODORE WANDJI" recommended it to myself because He was emigrating to CANADA–montreal, And would have been very far from me. "THÉODORE wandji ngongang" was the one person that welcomed and invited myself to study in BREMEN ! "
- AT this effect, each volunteer foreigner student would be connected to a single volunteering family of BREMEN. IN my specific case, I was assigned to the "ARISTOCRATIC"–bürgerliche family "SCHULZE–SMIDT", originating predominantly from HOLLAND into GERMANIA.
- MISTER "raïner–schulze–smidt", and his 2nd"SPOUSE GABRIELLE schulze–smidt" were really kind and nice to myself.
- "RAINER was "sole investor and proprietor–German–INHABER of an insurance company in Bremen, and in LONDON–great–britain", WHERE he did his apprenticeship as "INSURANCE–business–man". HIS 2nd spouse Gabrielle that I met in person; Was a part–time "physiotherapist" for the football team of Bremen city : "WERDERBREMEN (<https://>)". "
- Through them, I could know more about the origins of the autonomous–HANSE–STADT of Bremen, since "GOVERNOR SMIDT" as upper–upper grandfather of "MR. RAÏNER Schulze–Smidt", was governor of BREMEN for 50–years, and is the one person that acquire land from "HANNOVER–autonomous–STATE", to create a water–port–German–haven; "BREMERHAVEN", as a city and port for the autonomous city–federal–STATE of BREMEN.
- People and places I visit, and met, through organization of RAINER and GABI :
- 1.) HIS cousins from Brazil by talk–only & pictures (<https://>); that I DON'T remember family names;
 - 2.) HIS cousins from JOHANNESBURG by talk–only & pictures (<https://>); that I DON'T remember family names, but that are having a wool factory for exportation in the state of BREMEN–recist germania;
 - 3.) VISIT of "evangelic church" on King–JESUS birth day "December 25th";
 - 4.) VISIT of MUSEUM–"Fockemuseum";
 - 5.) VISIT of "musical–theater" in "BREMEN–DOMSHEIDE";
 - 6.) "Bernhadine", "Caspar", "Johann" & "senior sister JULIA" schulze–smidt.
 - 7.) Several friends of them in need of computer technical help in terms of Software installation, and support.
 - 8.) "DOROTHEE" and "her brother Dr. oec. Sebastian Dettmers (<https://>)";
 - 9.) "Kryenhop family" (<https://>) : a leader in industrial transfer And sale of asian food and products into GERMANY :
 - a.) Father "Rolf";
 - b.) Daughter "SVANTSKE";
 - c.) etc.
- "I quit this family relationship at request of "RAÏNER" and "his 2nd spouse GABRIELLE–gabi", because they thought I lied to them that I have got a position as a temporary "SOFTWARE DEVELOPER" employee earning "70 000 Euros" annually at "AMADEUS Germany GmbH", Via THE frankfurter human resource company "" . "

RESEARCH AND TEACHING OBJECTIVES – PSY-CARE – YERITH-RD-TEST

2. Psychological care |
 COLLÈGE INTEG –FROM-LAQUINTINIE-HOSPITAL-EYOUM-CHRISTIAN-IDIOT-CRIMINAL,
 DOUALA, CAMEROUN [01/2021 – 06/2021]
- A. "DR. (PH.D.) JEAN MOUBEB", Collège Integ –from-LAQUINTINIE-hospital-EYOUM-christian-idiot-criminal,
 Douala, Cameroun [01/2021 – 06/2021]
 ["DR. (Ph.D.) Jean MOUBEB".]

"ROSE sangnou-chienne-génitrice; a sanguinary mégère that is said to have caused a sudden death of her husband THÉODORE noumbissi-idiot; my biological genitor; ORGANIZES that I am brought by force to a psychiatric institute called Douala-laquintie-hospital because we had a talk at her mother's place where I WAS SAYING that I NEED my documents from my real-estate properties be given back to myself by her."

"AS I am currently writing this small report on NOVEMBER 20th, 2024; ALL my belongings weren't given back to me by VICTOR koliou noundou that detains this official documents that I MUST possess by inheritance right as summoned by a judge just after the death of my father and dear genitor THÉODORE noumbissi-idiot."

"INGRID-teuntchou-noumeni-chandriand, born-geboren Ingrid TCHITCHUI noumbissi is trying to take away all my real-estate properties, together with LAURENT-tchandeu free mason !!! "

MAJOR PROFESSIONAL SOCIETAL IMPROVEMENTS I

1. **2003 – 2005:** [ZMML – University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I HAVE ENHANCED LEARNING CAPABILITIES of economics students at the University of Bremen by DEVELOPING WEBSITES AND STUDENT SELF-LEARNING COMPUTER PROGRAMS, together with THE TEAM OF PROFESSOR KLAUS BÖNKOST.
2. **2006:** [FB 3; University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I HAVE created a website for the AFRICAN STUDENT ASSOCIATION "Nasgen e.V (New African Student Generation eingetragener Verein)" !
3. **2006:** [AGBS – University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I HAVE pleaded FORMER CAMEROON STUDENT serge achille fopoussi nono TO COME WITH MYSELF CONTRIBUTE at work research group of PROFESSOR JAN PELESKA.
4. **2006:** [GEWETE GmbH, Rellingen, Hamburg, Germany]: I HAVE completely alone, installed and deployed a networked installation of LaDIVA at a section of "KARLSRUHE city council !", SO TO ALLEVIATE DUTIES OF dear mentor DIPLOM-INGENIEUR (FH) SVEN KAMRATH !
5. **2006:** [GEWETE GmbH, Rellingen, Hamburg, Germany]: I HAVE SUCCESSFULLY pinpoint TU HAMBURG-HARBURG CAMEROON STUDENT david demo noundou TO MR. JENS MÖLLER of GEWETE GmbH ¹, FOR HIM TO HELP MR. DAVID DEMO NOUNDOU with access to FINAL SCHOOL YEAR WORK EXPERIENCE, AND BACHELOR OF SCIENCE THESIS-WORK.
6. **2006:** [University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I could successfully provide "MS WINDOWS SOFTWARE" INSTALLATION, TROUBLESHOOTING, and TRAINING to several GERMAN people because of "DEAR MR. RAINER SCHULZE-SMIDT" and HIS SPOUSE "MS. GABRIELE SCHULZE-SMIDT".
THESE EXPERIENCES WERE VERY POSITIVE FOR my finances !
7. **2005 – 2007:** [AGBS – University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I HAVE CONTRIBUTED TO TESTING EFFORTS BEFORE FIRST LAUNCH OF JET FLIGHT "AIRBUS A380" by my scientific AND engineering contributions in STATISTICAL TEST CASE GENERATION within RT-TESTER software of VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH; THANKS TO MERCIFUL PROFESSOR JAN PELESKA.
8. **2007 – 2009:** [SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS, Erlangen, Bayern, Germany]: I HAVE SUCCESSFULLY MAINTAIN All Oncology Care Systems HOSPITALS customers, throughout the whole planet, ON FRONT-LINE OF problem/defect RESOLUTION WHENEVER technicians on CRITICAL problem phone resolution lines 1, 2, and 3 COULDN'T SOLVE SOFTWARE TECHNICAL ISSUES of linac.
9. **2009 – 2011:** [University of Waterloo, Waterloo, ON, Canada]: I HAVE socially, WITH COMPUTING TECHNOLOGY, helped following afro-descendants from CAMEROON:
 1. CÉLESTIN puene: helped him search on the internet, and call, because of his poor English language knowledge, U.S.A businesses for inquiring on buying trucks for his brother in Cameroon.
 2. FABRICE Kouam Kamdem: maintained and improved an on-line website for FREE for his cameroon oriented professional association.
 3. ALBERT HERVAIS Ngagom Piewe: taught Debian-Linux basic shell command usage, Java and C++ programming on phone and internet.
 4. I HAVE presented orally and given personal written material ON SOFTWARE SECURITY AND SAFETY to CAMEROON ASSOCIATION of migrants in KITCHENER-WATERLOO: "ROWAC".
10. **2012:** [IBM Toronto Software Laboratory, Markham, ON, Canada]: I HAVE INTRODUCED skilled migrant cameroon worker, as ACTUARY in TORONTO, "AUDREY Nguetie Tchamga, B.Sc (Université de Laval, Québec, CANADA)" to use and exploitation of FREE AND OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE (FOSS) "Debian Linux".
11. **2012:** [IBM Toronto Software Laboratory, Markham, ON, Canada]: I HAVE advised, counseled, and even developed an on-line website for fellow CAMEROON expatriate YVES FRANCIS Kamga Mbiele, MBA (ÉCOLE SUPÉRIEURE DE GESTION, Paris) ON HIS ABANDONED PROJECT (WITH DAUGHTER OF FORMER ENERGY MINISTER of cameroon) FOR SOLAR ENERGY PRODUCTION in cameroon.

I WAS INTRODUCED to "YVES FRANCIS Kamga Mbiele, MBA (E.S.G, Paris)" BY MY AUNT-HUSBAND pr. shanda-tonme jean-claude.
12. **YEAR-2012:** I COULD SUCCESSFULLY buy and implement foundations of "IMMEUBLE YERITH_{r&d}" which WILL STEM as a "PREMIER COMPUTING RESEARCH AND "Software Testing & Validation"" center in CENTRAL AFRICA (yaounde, center region, cameroon) !

I BOUGHT THIS PLOT OF LAND FROM hon. THÉODORE DATOOU; vice-president of parliament in YAOUNDE, CENTER REGION IN CAMEROON !

Land title CERTIFICATE nr.: 560 792, in SIMBOK, mfoundi vi (6), vol. 265 !
13. **2014:** [University of Waterloo, Waterloo, ON, Canada]: I HAVE searched information, on how to WELCOME and ACCOMMODATE CAMEROON AMBASSADOR IN OTTAWA, for "ROWAC", a cameroonian ASSOCIATION of high skilled migrants (MOSTLY PROVENING FROM GERMANY) in KITCHENER-WATERLOO.

MAJOR PROFESSIONAL SOCIETAL IMPROVEMENTS II

14. **2021:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]: I HAVE built a partnership with Dr. PETER Akume Ngoe and his societal NGO so to provide his NGO with VERY CHEAP AND APPROPRIATE software solutions for a NGO financed foodstore.
15. **2022:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]: I HAVE SUCCESSFULLY trained Mr. NESTOR Kenfack in ONLY 3 days at basic usage of our ERP software system YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum for hardware shop selling. Mr. NESTOR Kenfack IS ONLY holder of a "B.E.P.C".

USUALLY in Yaounde, a holder of a "B.E.P.C" couldn't be trained to use COMMONLY present ERP SOFTWARE SYSTEMS (e.g.: 'Sage Gescom i7', 'SAP Business One', etc.), BECAUSE THEY ARE MEANT for highly qualified users.

Mr. NESTOR Kenfack HAD NEVER GOT exposure to an ERP system in the past.
16. **2023:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]:
I have given software cyberspace security counsels to Santa Lucia AHALA by talking to a computer technician employee because I could see vulnerabilities at cashier while paying for my goods.
17. **2023:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]:
I have counseled a business owner to start a bigger grocery shop and gave him ideas and ways on how to realize this using YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM, and, also, my unfinished two-storey building.
18. **2023:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]:
I have started YECEFOIQ (YERITH-CENTRE DE FORMATION INFORMATIQUE), so to improve computing skills of fellow citizen, and also, of any other person that conforms to Cameroon laws !
20. **2024:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]:
I try to have SANTA-LUCIA-AHALA AS 1 OF MY CLIENT THESE COMING YEARS so to have YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM there working instead of 'Odo'.
So they (SANTA-LUCIA-AHALA) will contribute in improving quality by thorough usage of this new platinum-platform.
21. **2024:** [YERITH R&D, Yaounde, Center, Cameroon]:
I am now working with ALT PLUS in YDE-AHALA so to have a working Supermarket in one, Instead "of a hardware-shop + a food-store separately, BUT JOINED physically".

MAJOR PROFESSIONAL COMPUTING RESEARCH ACHIEVEMENTS I

1. **YEAR-2005:** IMPLEMENTATION OF the JAVA servlet XML parsing and saving server "LaDIVA", AND ITS GUI (JAVA-SWING) configuration and installer program; for GEWETE GmbH !
2. **YEAR-2006:** IMPLEMENTATION OF "MESO"; the IMPROVED and revised version of the XML parsing and saving server "LaDIVA" for GEWETE GmbH !
3. **YEAR-2006:** IMPLEMENTATION OF the library computer systems communication protocol SIPv2 for GEWETE GmbH vending machines !
4. **YEAR-2005:** INVENTION OF A PROCEDURE TO systematically transform A BÜCHI AUTOMATON into A TIMED AUTOMATON ! TASK COORDINATED BY SHAREHOLDER PROF. DR. RER. NAT. HABIL. JAN PELESKA, of VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH !
5. **YEAR-2006:** CREATION OF (with higher study part team CogAg of the University of Bremen [Cognitive Systems Group led by DEAR LATE PROFESSOR CHRISTIAN FREKSA]) ROBOT "arnie"; AND PROCEDURES TO automatically map a supermarket both geographically AND store item-wise with RFID technology by HELP OF A ROLLING ROBOT "arnie" !
6. **YEAR-2007** [FB 3! AGBS: Diplom-Informatiker (Dipl.-Inf.)]: IMPLEMENTATION OF statistical uniformly distributed test cases generation for HAREL-statecharts ! COMMERCIALIZED BY VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH !
7. **YEAR-2007:** [FB 3! AGBS: University of Bremen, Bremen, Bremen, Germany]: I HAVE CONTRIBUTED TO TESTING EFFORTS BEFORE FIRST LAUNCH OF JET FLIGHT "AIRBUS A380" by my scientific AND engineering contributions in STATISTICAL TEST CASE GENERATION within RT-TESTER software of VERIFIED SYSTEMS INTERNATIONAL GmbH; THANKS TO MERCIFUL PROFESSOR JAN PELESKA.
8. **YEAR-2008:** IMPLEMENTATION OF the communication and control protocol DIGITAL MEVATRON INTERFACE PROTOCOL (DMIP) version 13 for THE LINEAR ACCELERATOR "linac" of SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS, Oncology Care Systems (OCS) !
9. **YEAR-2009:** Stopping my career; AFTER 21 MONTHS; as JUNIOR SOFTWARE DEVELOPER at SIEMENS MEDICAL SOLUTIONS (Oncology Care Systems) in ERLANGEN, BAYERN, GERMANY; with 0 defects / faults returning FROM CUSTOMERS because OF non achievement protocol repair ! Award saying from BOSS GERHARD SENG; MY TEAM LEAD !
10. **YEAR-2011** [ECE! Ph.D. in Computer Science]: I HAVE INVENTED AND INTRODUCED A PRACTICAL AND SIMPLE STATIC ANALYSIS BY ITERATIVE DATAFLOW ANALYSIS, to check temporal safety properties, expressed with tracematches, of JAVA programs !
THIS TECHNIQUE HAS BEEN USED in following:
 1. (* Similarly, but as a dynamic analysis technique) MASC thesis (2011; submitted at the UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA), OF ASSISTANT PROFESSOR JON Eyolfson of the UNIVERSITY OF TORONTO, ON, CANADA !
EVEN THOUGH JON Eyolfson MASC (COMPUTER ENGINEERING) SUBMISSION WAS EARLIER THAN MY Ph.D. in SOFTWARE ENGINEERING THESIS DEFENSE, because of finding an examiner (reporting) within ECE DEPARTMENT, I AM THE ONE THAT GAVE A PROTOTYPE DESIGN AND PROTOTYPE DOCUMENT FOR HIS SUBMISSION !
11. **YEAR-2012:** I COULD SUCCESSFULLY DEVELOP manual and automatic BASH (Bourne Again SHell) programs (scripts), THAT LEAD TO A 0.5% improvement of WEBSPHERE computing performance !
12. **YEAR-2013:** CREATION OF A RUNTIME dynamic taint analysis for the QUERCUS PHP INTERPRETER !
13. **YEAR-2015:** FIRST WORLD-WIDE OPEN-SOURCE (foss) RELEASE OF AN LLVM-BASED ON INTERMEDIATE REPRESENTATION (IR) static iterative KILDALL (gary kildall) DATAFLOW ANALYSIS named 'YERITH-SAINT' !
'YERITH-SAINT': <https://www.github.com/sazzad114/saint> !
14. **YEAR-2015:** CREATION OF A CONTEXT-SENSITIVE FLOW-SENSITIVE tainted paths generation algorithm by iterative dataflow analysis !
THIS TECHNIQUE HAS BEEN USED in following:
 1. (* EXACT same technique) PH.D. dissertation / thesis IN COMPUTER SCIENCE (2020; submitted at VIRGINIA TECH, VA, U.S.A), OF ASSISTANT PROFESSOR SAZZADUR Ahaman AT University of Arizona, Tucson, AZ, U.S.A !
 2. PH.D. dissertation / thesis IN COMPUTER SCIENCE (2020; submitted at the UNIVERSITY OF CALIFORNIA, SANTA BARBARA, CA, U.S.A), OF ASSISTANT PROFESSOR ARAVIND Machiry AT Purdue University, IN, U.S.A !
15. **YEAR-2020:** FIRST OFFICIAL RETESTED RELEASE OF THE full featured OPEN SOURCE enterprise resource planing software "YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE"; FIRST OFFICIAL RELEASE OF THE OPEN SOURCE AUTOMATED BACKUP-SYSTEM AND ALERT ("yerith-erp-3.0"-system-daemon": <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0>) !

"YERITH-ERP-PGI-standalone, server, academic, client" ARE THE DIFFERENT VERSIONS OF THIS FOSS-ERP-PGI-FRENCH !

SERVER AND CLIENT are mainly meant for a supermarket having several cashiers offices, AND A SERVER directing MYSQL-commercial options in common for different client-cashier-OFFICES !

ACADEMIC is meant for use WITH an IN-MEMORY DATABASE like "SQLite" !
16. **YEAR-2021:** First stable release of YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE at PHARMACY FIANGO LYCÉE MAKÊPÈ !

MAJOR PROFESSIONAL COMPUTING RESEARCH ACHIEVEMENTS II

17. **YEAR-2022:** FIRST DELIVERY OF a compendium OF DOCUMENTS concerning OUR ERP SOFTWARE-SYSTEM YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE !
<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>
18. **YEAR-2022:** CREATION OF AN OPEN SOURCE state transition diagram LIBRARY FOR RUNTIME DATAFLOW VERIFICATION (YR_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF) (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif))
20. **YEAR-2022:** MODIFICATION OF A Free Open Source Software (FOSS) "QVGE" (<https://showroom.qt.io/qvge-qt-visual-graph-editor>) TO DESIGN state diagram TEMPORAL SAFETY PROPERTIES ! "YR_QVGE" ! YR_QVGE is a commercial tool of mine priced at 3 000 EUROS a single executable copy.
21. **YEAR-2022:** CREATION OF AN OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE FRAMEWORK for runtime dataflow analysis (YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF | YR_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF) (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif) | 🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif))!
22. **YEAR-2022:** I have added a runtime check verification view within FOSS-ERP ("YERITH-ERP-3.0-SERVER": 🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0)) IN ORDER TO VIEW LOG MESSAGES SENT TO YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF !
23. **YEAR-2022:** CREATION of a systematic method, AND / OR PROCEDURE TO TEST AND / OR verify dataflow of thick-client (or web application), AGAINST A SAFETY TEMPORAL PROPERTY SPECIFICATION expressed as a STATE DIAGRAM (modified mealy machine) !
24. **YEAR-2022:** FIRST OFFICIAL REPORT in FRENCH LANGUAGE OF ACTIVITIES of YERITH R&D SINCE RELEASE OF FIRST STABLE VERSION OF YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum!
"REPORT in french: <https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051568/>" !
25. **YEAR-2023:** creation of a domain-specific language (YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG) to describe *state diagram mealy machines* (📄 SDMM).
26. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION with flex and bison OF A DOMAIN-SPECIFIC LANGUAGE COMPILER to create source C++ code files for YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang)).
27. **YEAR-2023:** SUBMISSION OF A FULL TECHNICAL PAPER ("YR_DB_RUNTIME_VERIF: A FRAMEWORK FOR VERIFYING SQL CORRECTNESS PROPERTIES OF GUI SOFTWARE AT RUNTIME") TO SPLASH-ICTSS 2023 CONFERENCE in May 2023.
28. **YEAR-2023:** Implementation of more than 2-states *state diagram mealy machine* (📄 SDMM) in YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif)), and YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif)).
29. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION of guarded condition expression specification within YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif)), and automated code generation of guarded condition expression in YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF_LANG_COMP (🔗[git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang)).
30. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION OF EMPLOYEE PAY GROUP within YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum.
31. **YEAR-2023:** First release of our CASE (Computer-Aided Software Engineering) drawing design tool "📄 [YRI_QVGE](#)" official commercial document.
32. **YEAR-2023:** online ENGLISH INTO FRENCH, and vice versa LANGUAGE TRANSLATION within YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum.
33. **YEAR-2023:** CREATION of a viewing graphical user interface application for YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF in JUNE.
34. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION OF FIRST RELEASE OF automatic EMPLOYEE PAY GROUP SALARY CALCULATION. Cumulated pay groups for a single employee salary calculation is included.
35. **YEAR-2023:** CREATION OF a user's guide for YERITH_QVGE.
36. **YEAR-2023:** STARTED IMPLEMENTATION OF a user sample project AUTOMATIC binary executable generation in YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.
37. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION OF MULTIPLE programs under analysis (PUA) monitoring within YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.
38. **YEAR-2023:** IMPLEMENTATION OF MULTIPLE runtime monitors WITHIN A SINGLE EXECUTABLE for YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.
39. **YEAR-2023:** STARTED journal article (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8381187>) for STTT official journal release.
40. **YEAR-2023:** started a predicate logic for deriving SOFTWARE RECOVERY ACTIONS for sdmm ("state diagram mealy machine").
41. **YEAR-2023:** started writing YERITH R&D 2023 *annual report* (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/10515549>).
42. **YEAR-2024:** finished writing YERITH R&D 2023 *annual report*: THIS REPORT specifically says that CPDM ruling party has tried to destroy my life using *CHRISTIAN eyoum* (<https://scholar.google.fr/citations?user=eHvsI1UAAAAJ&hl=fr>).
43. **YEAR-2024:** started writing courses curricula and content for several courses of [YECEFOIQ](https://www.yecefoiq-sarl.cm) (<https://www.yecefoiq-sarl.cm>).
44. **YEAR-2024:** started creation of a web site application for teaching computer science center YECEFOIQ.
45. **YEAR-2024:** I have implemented case insensitive search for financial expenses list within YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.
46. **YEAR-March 2024:** I have paused new features in YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM (I.E.: Human resource management, and Financial Accounting management) due to advancements required for their quality assurance, WITH 📄 [YRI_QVGE](#)!

MAJOR PROFESSIONAL COMPUTING RESEARCH ACHIEVEMENTS III

47. **YEAR-March 2024:** I could finally find 1 company commercial that rented my 1st 3-bedrooms apartment in DLA for "90 000 Xaf" monthly !
48. **YEAR-March 2024:** I have paid "50 000 Xaf" as starting advance funds for incorporating YERITH R&D SARL.
49. **YEAR-March 2024:** I am recruiting 1 commercial financial-entrepreneur for ~~YECEFOHQ~~ (LOOKING for investment funds).
50. **YEAR-JUNE 25, 2024:** Returning client N.K hardware shop for YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0 !
51. **YEAR-2024:** Refining automatic stock CSV data entry.
52. **YEAR-JULY 29, 2024:** Still training "Christelle Akamba" for just 1 000 Francs an hour.
THERE is no money outside in Yaounde; and my rental apartments are still not having renters due to LAURENT TCHANDEU that I know has been trying to disrupt my activities in the open source software (OSS) era.
53. **YEAR-September 08, 2024:** *I AM working on ground to perfection building YERITH.*
THERE is lack of funding even though I could have my judicial affair against CHRISTIAN-EYOUM and others to get sent back to NDOKOTI prosecutor.
UNFORTUNATELY attorney SYNCLAIRE-NJEUTCHA-TCHANA has been trying to disrupt my activities with some money-bribery he received from genitor-organizer of assassination of mine !!!
I now try to get ATTORNEY-tchonang-albertine on my side these days. C.P.D.M wolfgang owona idiot political party has been trying to take down all my activities so to destroy a non-gay citizen.
54. **YEAR-2024:** Incorporating unit of measure like gram, etc. for inventory stock entry creation and pricing.
55. **YEAR-2024:** Started incorporating Financial debt entries creation in YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.
I am also specifying YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME for a new idea as good-physical stock exchange start-up marketplace idea.
56. **YEAR-NOVEMBER 2024:** I have re-introduced new color schemes for YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME, AND also started a document for SPECIFYING and DESCRIBING the already existing and ALREADY IMPLEMENTED: C++ runtime monitoring verification library SDMM (STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE) :
1. YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF : [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif) ;
 2. ITS usage as algorithmic trading stock exchange library and runtime monitoring engine with help of a FOSS *"STATE DIAGRAM MEALY MACHINE"* (https://www.archive.org/download/yri_ictss_2023/yri_ictss_2023.pdf) monitoring container for real-timing.
57. **YEAR-JANUARY 2025:** *I have incorporated "FR", "EN", USA-american flag and FRANCE-flag onto YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM so to hint users on Translation from English into FRENCH; And vice versa.*
58. **YEAR-JANUARY 2025:** *We are trying to render incorporating of `sdmm[d]` as plug-gable dynamic libraries into YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF.*
59. **YEAR-FebRUARY 2025:** *I am also trying to check conformant thread calls from runtime QT-QTimer instances whenever a user tries to cancel his modification / insertion work; FOR instance a special case is whenever 'INSERT/UPDATE' button is pressed and then there is intermingling with the checking mechanism introduced for verifying whether a user cancels his work on the window frame or not !*
60. **YEAR-March 2025:** *I am struggling with INGRID-own-sister that digest all time my genitor because of 6 children with less than 2 years separation birth time between them !*
61. **YEAR-April 2025:** *Currently doing major research & inspection work for a web shop by using partly our; At YERITH R&D, new invention WYSIWYG-Tool for web HTML pages (YERITH-WEB-DESIGN-TOOL) !*
62. **YEAR-April 2025:** *NO body originating from West Cameroon seems to be living peacefully in CMR with bulu tribe since event a ["president bulu of the republic"] is embezzling young researcher in science and / or engineering like myself so to perpetuate going to IMF-fucking-idiot to pertain African in under poverty world for ever-devilish !*

20.20 'VALKYRIE' upgrade to DEBIAN BULLSEYE (11.0); QT-5

VALGRIND USER INTERFACE: *valkyrie* (<https://www.valgrind.org/downloads/guis.html>)

July 2023

1. Free open source code:
https://www.github.com/yerothd/valkyrie_NON_OFFICIAL

'VALKYRIE' is a dynamic analysis CASE tool for verifying memory errors, and using VALGRIND as backend program server for analysis.

21.21 CONTEXT SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM ("YERITH-SAINT")

October 2009 – March 2015

1. Free open source code:
<https://www.github.com/sazzad114/saint>

'YERITH-SAINT' is a static taint analysis that computes tainted paths in C programs and that doesn't require any program annotations. 'YERITH-SAINT' is built upon the iterative dataflow framework and has been implemented using the LLVM compiler infrastructure. 'YERITH-SAINT' is interprocedural, flow-sensitive, and developers can choose to run it either with context-sensitivity or without. THE HEARTBLEED bug (april 2014; security breach in open ssl 1.0.1f) IS A POTENTIAL FINDING OF yerith-saint.

22.22 YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE

ERP SOFTWARE SYSTEM 'YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum'

October 2015 – Currently

1. Free open source code:
◆ [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0)

'YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE' is a FOSS (FREE AND OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE) ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANING SOFTWARE !

23.23 YERITH-ERP-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON

'YERITH-ERP-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON': AUTOMATED ALERT, AND DB-BACKUP SYSTEM FOR 'YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum'

October 2015 – Currently

1. Free open source code:
◆ [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon](https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0-system-daemon)

'YERITH-ERP-9.0-SYSTEM-DAEMON' is a FOSS (FREE AND OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE) AUTOMATED ALERT, AND DATABASE BACKUP SYSTEM FOR FOSS-ERP YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE !

24.24 YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF

'YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF': C++ Library FOR RUNTIME MONITORING (Safety Temporal Properties) FOR State Diagram MONITORING !

June 2022 – Currently

1. Free open source code:
◆ [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif)

'YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF' is a FOSS (FREE AND OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE) C++ library, THAT ENABLES TO IMPLEMENT STATE DIAGRAM SAFETY TEMPORAL PROPERTY RUNTIME CHECKING (and/or VERIFICATION).

25.25 YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF

'YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF': RUNTIME VERIFICATION OF TEMPORAL SAFETY PROPERTIES IN 'YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE'

June 2022 – Currently

1. Free open source code:
◆ [git https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif](https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif)
2. YERITH-ERP-9.0 DOCTORAL COMPENDIUM:
<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>

'YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF' is a FOSS (FREE AND OPEN SOURCE SOFTWARE), AND REUSABLE DYNAMIC RUNTIME ANALYSIS AND TESTING INFRASTRUCTURE created for FOSS ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANING SOFTWARE 'YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE' !

26.26 [YRI_QVGE](#)

'YRI_QVGE': Design and Creation of Runtime SAFETY TEMPORAL PROPERTIES FOR State diagram MONITORING C++ Library
'YRI_SD_RUNTIME_VERIF' !

2,500 Euros a single executable copy FOR DEBIAN-LINUX
June 2022 - Currently

27.27 [YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE](#): an enterprise (management / financial) Resource Planing Software

ERP SOFTWARE SYSTEM 'YERITH-ERP-9.0-STANDALONE: an enterprise (management / financial) Resource Planing Software'

PRICE DEPENDS ON installations ! (STARTS AT 200,000 XAF per node-computer; ONLY AVAILABLE FOR DEBIAN-LINUX)
October 2015 - Currently

(GRADUATE) STUDENTS ADVISING / COUNSELING

- 1.) [**AMIRHOSSEIN VAKILI**], Ph.D. (www.cs.uwaterloo.ca/~avakili) (COMPUTER SCIENCE, DAVID R. CHERITON SCHOOL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA)
- 2.) [**DAVID DEMO NOUNDOU**], BACHELOR OF SCIENCE, INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY, TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF HAMBURG–HARBURG, HAMBURG, GERMANY
- 3.) [**DIVAM JAIN**], M.MATH (<https://www.uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/handle/10012/7943>) (COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA) 2013
- 4.) [Dr. **ERIC BREFO-MENSAH**], M.SC (Waterloo) (<https://www.uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/handle/10012/13341>) (CHEMISTRY, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA) 2018
- 5.) [Dr. **ESTHER ELIZABETH LAMBERT**], M.SC (Waterloo) (<https://ca.linkedin.com/in/esther-lambert-5b869414>) (GEOGRAPHY, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA) 2009
- 6.) [**Basser (from Syria)**], MASC (ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING, ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE MONTRÉAL, QC, CANADA) 2008
- 7.) [**FABRICE tchoumi**], MASC (ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING (AVIONICS), ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE MONTRÉAL, QC, CANADA) 2007 – 2008
- 8.) [**FELIX FANG**], MASC (<https://www.uwaterloo.ca/electrical-computer-engineering/profile/p23lam/papers/15.pppj.af-analysis.pdf>) (SOFTWARE ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA) 2014
- 9.) Dr. rer. nat. **"HASHIM CHUNPIR"** (<https://www.igi-global.com/affiliate/hashim-chunpir/324991>) (MSC, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY) 2005 – 2006
- 10.) DR.-ING. DIPL.-INF. **"SERGE ACHILLE FOPOUSSI NONO"**, (DIPLOM–INFORMATIKER, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY) 2004 – 2006
- 11.) **"DERRICK FIEDLER (born YAPI YAPO)"**, (DIPLOM–INFORMATIKER, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY) 2004 – 2006
- 12.) **"INES NGAKOU TEMOU"**, (BACHELOR OF SCIENCE, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY) 2004 – 2006
- 13.) **"DAVID KAMGA ADAMO"**, (DIPLOM–INFORMATIKER, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY) 2004 – 2006
- 14.) C++ MATRIX programming : **"Dr. MOHAMED RIDHA MAHFOUDHI"**, MBA, PhD (Financial Engineering, University of Laval, QC, Canada). 08 / 2009
- 15.) **"MARCELLIN TAALY"** (<https://www.assiwo.com>), (DIPLOM–INFORMATIKER, COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY)
- 16.) **"MATTHIAS (from Germany)"**, DIPLOM–INGENIEUR (FH); INFORMATIK–INGENIEUR, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY
- 17.) **"Virginie kamche"**, DIPLOM–INFORMATIKERIN; COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY
- 18.) **"MAÏMOUNA BAMBA"** (from COTE-D'IVOIRE), DIPLOM–INFORMATIKERIN; COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY
- 19.) [**Dr. Vajih MONTAGHAMI, Ph.D.**] (Ph.D. (<https://www.uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/>)) (SOFTWARE ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA)
- 20.) [**JON EYOLFSON, Ph.D.**] (M.ASc. / Ph.D. (<https://www.uwspace.uwaterloo.ca/handle/10012/6206>)) (SOFTWARE ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ON, CANADA)
- 21.) **"THÉOPHILE TCHIENTCHO"**, DIPLOM–INGENIEUR (FH), INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY, UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED SCIENCES, BREMEN, GERMANY

FAMILY THAT I DON'T KNOW WHEREABOUT - I

1. **SHANDA family as a destructive life for BOTH noumbissi, and NGONGANG and whereabouts families**

"SHANDA Ndjatie Dorothee, and her spouse official TONME-shanda-JEAN-claude" are the 1st persons that started destruction of my life by coming into my family with so called psychiatrist, via WOLFGANG-owona.

"OWONA wolfgang" seemed to getting married with ANGELA which is a cousin maternal of mine because HE WANTS to sell my soul to AMERICAN USA societies in the sense that HE put myself into troubles via GOVERNMENTS AGENCIES, all of them Are linked to secret services to which he belongs, as I HAVE HEARD from ANGELA myself.

Frequently, HE idiot wife says he traveled to USA, so he would talk to people that want my OPEN SOURCE entrepreneurial adventures to be stopped; GET money from them, Then organize hijacking with following agencies:

- 1.) Social Services; so I AM NO MORE independent in the state of biya-regime;
- 2.) HOSPITAL like "laquintinie", etc.

Dr.-wolfgang, which is born from MINISTER owona-joseph-deceased, And mother as daughter of MINISTER owona-Gregoire has tried to put Rosicrucian organization AMORC into my life via Angela who proposed to me to join a so called "lectorium-rosicrucae" based at external relations ministry Where WOLFGANG attends with her.

2. **WAAH (anne), spouse Kemmegni, is a subject of BIYA SPOUSE !!!**

This 'megere' of my grand mother mother's side; Tchuitchui-ELIZABETH;

Is obviously a devilish demon that possesses super-natural powers in dark kingdoms; Based of 3 sacred objects I have last seen in her house in Byemassi-YDE.

1. "Buffle" horns as a representation of Money-laundry-BAPHOMET-satan
2. 2 turtles carapaces in the back of the "Buffle" horns.
3. 2 portraits of girls invoking and respectively crying;

3. **"SANGO, spouse Bernadette Noundou" IS SOMEWHAT a suspect at origin of this family tragedy !!!**

This pseudo-suspect seems to want to acquire my place at KING.

Laurent tchandeu ministry plenipotentiary is a subject of itself at Batchieu-Babouantou kings places.

Obviously, every member of GRAND-FATHER noundou nuclear family is a subject to this GUJA.

4. "Victor Koliou NOUNDOU" IS A NOBODY into my life;

THIS idiot, junior brother of my deceased late father "Théodore Noubissi" is contacting people INCLUDING "derek rayside (drayside@uwaterloo.ca)" (Already talking with other ignorant paternal unwanted uncle "Jules NTETA noundou (julesnteta@gmail.com; julesnteta@yahoo.fr)" from Cameroon external research criminal agency (DGRE));

The idiot Victor presents itself as a chief of a family where I am supposed to belong with some faked official documents from uncle politician LAURENT tchandeu-IDIOT.

OFFICIAL registered document that "Victor KOLIOU NOUNDOU" refused to give a copy to myself when I asked him about, since I am the only, according to documents written by my late grand-father Michel NOUNDOU, Legitimate SUPERVISOR OF HIS left over to children and descendants, WEALTH AND MATERIAL POSSESSIONS !

"Afriland first-bank" and "Intelligentsia employee "Jean-PAUL-yamtche"; And CEO currently as of April 2024", A person that I really don't really know whereabouts in his genealogy or affiliation to my late grand-father; "Jean-PAUL-yamtche" owns a big storey house just opposite face of our main common house entrance in Babouantou idiot village !

"Afriland first-bank" and Intelligentsia MAIN CREATOR AND INSPIRATORY person; "Dr. PAUL fokam-kammogne", was, according to sayings of my genitor Rose Sangnou, 1 of an intimate friend of my late father and genitor "Théodore NOUMBISSI" !

"LAURENT tchandeu and Rose Sangnou" went to a place of "CCEI-bank (former company name and source of AFRILAND FIRST-BANK)", according to "Rose Sangnou" told myself in person when I reached age 32; That they ("LAURENT Tchandeu my paternal uncle" and "Rose SANGNOU" my genitor) gave money (BRIBED) to an employee of "CCEI-BANK" where "late Théodore NOUMBISSI" owed "4 000 000 XAF" at his death so that MORTGAGE ("hypothèque" in French) on his property-land in BONABERI-DLA (700 m²) would be erased everywhere in computers and documents of former 'CCEI-bank' !

"LAURENT tchandeu and Rose Sangnou" also told me, after I had an employment interview with "Dr. PAUL fokam-kammogne"; that my later genitor and father "Théodore NOUMBISSI" is the one, together with "HUGUES NTOMANI TIAKO", his business partner and soul-mate at that former ancient time, THAT computerized totally all enterprises businesses of "CCEI-bank (former company name and source of AFRILAND FIRST-BANK)" !

I remember seeing my late father only 1 time in a day, around 19 : 00 at diner time; this is before we moved to Yaounde in year 1990; After he quits "CA-CORP (Computer Associates Corporation)-DLA" to open and manage solely "CA-CORP (Computer Associates Corporation)-YDE" !

5. "LAURENT tchandeu (ltchandeu@yahoo.fr)" ASSASSINATES in an hospital "THEODORE noumbissi"; late father of mine on January 1992;

AS an orphan at age of 7.5 years old, I remember uncle paternal Laurent came into our biggest house in YDE-Essos to settle in the secondary apartment at the back of our house.

6. "LAURENT tchandeu" Tries with "Hugues Ntomani Tiako" "VIA judith ngaleu in Etobicoke (Toronto, Ontario, Canada)" to crash "my Toyota Corolla LE-2003" in December 2013

This sorcerer freemason ("Hugues Ntomani Tiako"), and Christian-so-called-ORTHODOX-catholic of Roma, acknowledges that IT SHALLN'T be that I gain cause in the court of justice process THAT I have against "LAQUINTINIE and SED", that sent 9 people, including "Christian Eyoum, MD, PsyD"; in February 2021 at night around 23 : 30, to hijack and attempts to kill myself.

SED sent myself 1 time in a CABANON Because they receive 15,000 FCFA from "Henri Bertrand Ngatchou and my genitor ROSE Sangnou", IN douala 2018.

"Galax Yves Landry Etoga" is personally, as a CPDM political party member, AND not as a SED authority implicated in trying to kill myself through psychiatry and / or any other means !

"Laurent Tchandeu (assassin of Ingrid's father and his elder brother in Babouantou-village)" is the one that connected "Ingrid TEUNTCHOU NOUMENI", born (geboren in German) TCHITCHUI NOUMBISSI; my uterine sister, to marry officially "THE IDIOT AND PSY-CHILD since age 12 CHANDRIAND TEUNTCHOU NOUMENI".

7. "LAURENT tchandeu" Deems and Dares OR-DONATES to squeeze my financial money income VIA genitor of mine "Rose SANGNOU" Since September 2023 until TODAY.

8. "***JULES NTETA NOUNDOU extremely dangerous person" is a consanguine brother (same father; another, still living mother, in same marriage) of "LAURENT tchandeu"; And his helper in almost everything dirty and / or clean here in CMR!

FAMILY THAT I DON'T KNOW WHEREABOUT - III

9. ("Derek Rayside drayside@uwaterloo.ca") pays money to MATHGENEALOGY.ORG project so that an equivalence to my "Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering degree from UWATERLOO", will be turned from PhD into the non-academic degree ABD; just 2 weeks after talking with "JULES NTETA NOUNDOU" at his dirty-office in "YDE-élig-essono"
10. "David demo noundou" tries to connect me to Laurent external security research agent "Jean-Daniel-tujilo-tchokote"; "VIA his natal village idiot babouantou friend Célestin puene (cpuene@cscmonavenir.ca)".
11. "David demo noundou" has written documents in Germany that I was mentally ill while staying 3 days in his rental apartment in September 2018.
12. "David demo noundou" is A student of myself at the TUHH; benjamin brother of my late father "THEODORE noumbissi"; since I could help him get an bachelor internship At "GEWETE GmbH", Where I was working while a student at Bremen University state.
13. "LAURENT tchandeu" was a "Minister Plenipotentiary of Cameroon Embassies in France, Belgium, etc. for around 30 years outside of Cameroon". Especially promoted sent outside Cameroon 1 year after assassinating his elder brother "THEODORE noumbissi".
14. "Henri Bertrand Ngatchou" tries to physically arrest and violates myself in front of at least 7 other people in his private residence of Bankepche-Bangou with no apparent reason other than humiliate myself.

"Henri Bertrand Ngatchou" vows a personal and individual cult to 'Shanda Owona Biya', especially as an appointed, not applied CPDM (RDPC) political party, vice-president in Bankepche-Bangou; with "Honorable Datouo Theodore" as his president.

15. "**RODRIGUE alain sienchié ngongang** (sienchie@gmail.com)", Ancient psychiatric patient in Düsseldorf-Germany Sends messages everywhere So I could again be hijacked into a Cabanon-cell FOR mad-ill-people; "Xavier Noumbissi Noundou" paid in total amount 2,000 Euros to help him get back "to his paternal family NGONGANG" in Deido-Dla-CMR !
16. "**Théodore Wandji Ngongang, And Aurélie Kamdoum Yano his spouse** (takouengongang@yahoo.ca; ngongangtietie@yahoo.ca)", ows myself around "1 500 EUROS" since year 2005 as he fled out from Germany to emigrates into "Montréal-Côtes-des-neiges" !
17. "**Idiot Angéla Tchamou Shanda Wolfgang Owona** (krauserminrex@gmail.com)", a maternal cousin of mine, tries to hijack myself in buses because She deems being a very important personality ("VIP") in front of myself.

"HER spouse Dr Wolfgang Junior Fernand Owona" was making her ("Angéla Tchamou Shanda Owona") come to myself and harassed me with: "Wolfgang wants to be president of the republic" !

This idiot of Wolfgang is the grandson mother side of "Grégoire Owona", who was implicated in the sudden death of his former colleague "Theodore Noumbissi (Late father of mine)".

"Grégoire Owona" is today inviting "my remaining genitor Rose SANGNOU" to his village houses in "Gomedzap-Center-Region-CMR"; so to think her How to destroy my life as a black and renowned scientist universally from the University of Waterloo; THIS in conjunction with former uni colleagues such as "Dr. PATRICK lam"; etc. "Grégoire Owona" -

For 2 days now (April 20, 2025.); my profile is down at MATHGENEALOGY.ORG project; And at same time I felt several people trying to hijack my person here in Cameroon because a certain "#PASTOR-landry ENTERS MY PERSONAL HOME WITH A WEAPON."

In cameroon, as I have heard from people in background, CRIMINAL-ASSASSIN FROM yves-galax-landry Wear name PASTOR.

Derek Rayside has put back a vietnamese idiot on my file at MATHGENEALOGY.ORG project so that I cannot be upwell in Cameroon.

My official university of waterloo graduate transcripts says:

"Program: Engineering Doctoral;

"PhD" Comprehensive Examination.

Status: Completed

Date Completed: 12/20/2011

In good english: "Doctor-Ph.D. of Engineering ("PhD" in Electrical & Computer Engineering)".

In french language: Docteur-Ingénieur (Dr.-Ing.).

IT means I must also have *Ph.D.* exactly as My former room colleague Jon Eyolfson that is since 2022 an Assistant Professor in Teaching only at the University of Toronto, ON.

18. **"S2TBED main proprietor-ally A SO-called gangster-Simplice-KAMENI was seen 2 days ago here in a luxurious car by myself.**

"IMMEDIATELY, today, /Friday-Sep.-27th, & Saturday-Sep.-28th/, both days in year 2024, I and neighborhood start again to experience energy supply disruption for more than 4 hours."

SIMPLICE KAMENI seems to be a cocaine dealer that works on laundering money through usage of wood processing & wood sale activities via intermediary White-racist-extremist—italian so-called "MARCO".

ALSO, I could experience certain "neggers" working there from far-north cameroun coming along my foot way to dance kind of like I am their aid.

KAMENI simplice is also implicated in financing together with my cousin culprit-theodore-MOISE-tebiwo-yamkam my properties entirely in Cameroon; Starting year 2013 when TEBIWO-yamkam-moise traveled to Canada.

BOTH moise-yamkam-tebiwo, and SIMPLICE-kameni-ebacka; are sleeping in so-called orgy-sexist-FRANCK-biya gay personal property estate here in YAOUNDE.

19. **"HONORÉ WUCHE, a genitor of mine Spouse; ", EVENTHOUGH her cousin uterin, as hijacker into my life.**

"THIS honore-wouche has been calling me on my phone cell while I was a doctor of Engineering working on my doctoral Ph.D. degree in year 2013; GIVEN TO HIM BY ROSE sangnou."

HONORÉ WUCHE has lost already at least two wives he got kids with them as a guja.

HIS uterine cousin "Rodrigue Alain NGONGANG SIENCHIE", that tried to break my neck last August 2024 while I was attending home for 4 weeks and visiting faked "church Chapelle De la GLOIRE-DE-CHRIST by FAKED-devilish-racist-bassa pastor-so-called MARK-DJENG-DJENG";

Said to myself in front of honore-wouche that: 'SEND "xavier-noundou-ph.d." Again to MAD-person cell at "laquintinie" AS you did twice at least; I didn't even knew who was this gay-honore-wouche with black tattooed wrist-arm-bracelet for gangster and riders.

IT seems this cousin of my mother-genitor; together with another man-lady-cousin-uterine so called NANA; are working on molesting myself in life here in Cameroon; HE-honore-wouche told me laughing that 1 of his daughter was working in south-cameroon in farming for PAUL-biya-family.

20. **"Bulu-Sud-East-Akan tribe AS stealer in CMR"**

- Year 1983 was changed into year 1985-(~~ingrid-teuntchou-noumbissi birth year~~) so to allow later on a hijack of my property via a marriage to a uterine sister; Called "INGRID-teuntchou-noumeni", Born-geboren "Ingrid-tchitchui-noumbissi";

[TEUNTCHOU-isaac & JOSUE-nkwouano; & RICHARD-mfeugwang agreed on a dinner time of my passing away with all means via a psychiatric injection treatment by LAQUINTINIE-hospital;]

[LAURENT-tchandeu could then secure a prosperous career after the killing & hijacking of money of his blood-brother Théodore-noumbissi-rosicrucian-rotarian !]

- "BULU-biya" tribe in CMR-c.p.d.m-r.d.pc are trying to hijack any wealth of Well-to-do rich cameroonian so to secure presidential leadership for ever.
- Bulu notary-justice attorney ["MENYE-Ondo Xavier-FRANCOIS"] & "LIMA-rose (at time in 2012, 2013-years)" change effectively & voluntarily year of birth of mine in my [LAND-title certificate of MFOUNDI-VI.]
- GENOCIDE of West originating people started in CMR

"MARIE-commissary of DLA-05ème arrondissement od City-DOUALA, in Littoral region, sent 8 burglars on street to arrest myself while I was relating to CMRnian that BIYA regime has tried to spoliolate all my belonging via TEUNTCHOU-isaac."

"INGRID-teuntchou couldn't say no to this fake-marriage only to destroy my life as a super engineer and scientist originating from WEST-cmr."

"[TEUNTCHOU-isaac] used since she was aged 15 years old while I went outside of CMR to study in GERMANY-racist-culprit; NGATCHOU-henri-bertrand, a maternal uncle of myself & Ingrid to beat her & accustomate her to perform only what was told to her via JOSUE-nkwouano, senior brother of NGATCHOU-henri ! "

- 2025, AVRIL --18--"DLA-ndokoti-palace seems to be for now out of service due to atrocities that I have related internationally via web-site "zenodo.org"! "<https://www.zenodo.org>

"ATANGA NJI idiot minister; Cannot prepare elections without asserting NON-Sence propaganda to Cameroon people."

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (1.)

28.28 HIJACK OF MY PRIVATELY OWNED PROPERTY BY laquintinie on FEBRUARY 2021

[r-DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM – tALKING AT *BBC-british-broadcast-corporation* (<https://>), AND *+--rotarian--+* club member in douala-sawa-tribe, chief of psy staff of LAQUINTINIE HOSPITAL IN DOUALA (LITTORAL REGION, CAMEROON)], has sent in FEB. 2021, without any official document, 7 people to break into my privately owned (closed with a steel gate) house in DOUALA, so to hijack myself and terrorize me. THIS HAPPENED AT NIGHT AROUND 11:00 PM, with BERTRAND, breaking my gate seals with a weapon of some sort (BERTRAND, was the lead thief of DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM).

THIS HIJACK OR ATTACK on my person happened just 1 day after I denounced to *PRC.CM* and *SHANDY-SHANDY-CABINET.COM* (biological father of my mother's side cousin ANGELA) a fake "BACCALAUÉAT"-DEGREE from 'ANGELA TCHAMOU SHANDA OWONA SPOUSE DR. WOLFGANG FERNAND JR. OWONA', because her sister-cousin CYNTHIA NKWOUANO told me about this: "ANGELA WENT TO CENTRAL AFRICAN REPUBLIC and received her diploma in a hotel".

I ALSO BECAME AN AGENT OF CAMEROONIAN DEFENSE AND SECURITY FORCES ON FEBRUARY 14, 2021.

DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM after this kidnapping, held me at LAQUINTINIE HOSPITAL for poisoning me 2 weeks, AND THEN RELEASED AN OFFICIAL DOCUMENT TO MY RELATIVE ROSE SANGNOU.

ROSE SANGNOU has since been using the fake document to go meet my clients to say that I AM A PSY PATIENT AND THAT THEY SHALL NOT DEAL ANYTHING WITH MYSELF. ROSE SANGNOU also went to meet all my privately-owned real estate properties' neighbors TO DO THE SAME.

I HAVE COMPLAINT BEFORE DOUALA-NDOKOTI JURISDICTIONAL TRIBUNAL in front of JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA SINCE FEB. 2021:

- 3 convocations have been sent by now to DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM; he hasn't come to respond to prosecutors.
- I am now awaiting for a "MANDAT D'EMMENER" AGAINST DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM, a form of order from judge that will bring DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM in front of prosecutors by police force.

29.29 Kidnapping on FEB. 2023 WHILE WALKING BACK IN MY YAOUNDÉ REAL ESTATE PROPERTY

1. DR. LAURE MENGUENE MVINDI accepts to send 2 thugs-burglars on the road to kidnap myself, while I was walking on street to get back into my house, and to bring me in a cab at psychiatric hospital 'JAMOT' in YAOUNDÉ; this is requested by DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA, spouse pr. shanda-tonme jean-claude.

DR. LAURE MENGUENE MVINDI is chief of psychiatry staff at psychiatric hospital 'JAMOT' in YAOUNDÉ.

DR. LAURE MENGUENE MVINDI IS VERY WELL KNOWN IN YAOUNDÉ to say disturbing voices against BAMILEKE-TRIBE, an ethnic group of the west cameroon to which, I by birth, and not by spirit [I AM A BORN AGAIN CHRISTIAN], belong.

2. AFTER 2 WEEKS OF POISONING AND TRYING TO DESTROY MY BODY WITH DRUGS AND PILLS, a yellow clothed (level of BACHELOR OF SCIENCE) gate guard OF "HÔPITAL JAMOT" that I don't remember the name, tries to SNEAK INTO my private life by calling me on my private cell phone number [(+237) 6 52 39 69 50] every other day.

I SAID TO HIM THAT I DON'T ENTERTAIN RELATIONSHIPS WITH PEOPLE LIKE HIM.

PS: THIS GATE GUARD, yellow-clothed with an uniform, is of BETI-TRIBE like DR. LAURE MENGUENE MVINDI!

3. S2TBED, a so-called forestry society here in Yaoundé seems to be a secret agency against black-owned societies here in Cameroon.

30.30 Attempt to give me a psy consultation by ROSE SANGNOU's sister DR. ANNIE POKAM-KWAM

AFTER RELEASED FROM 'JAMOT', i stop taking the drugs that i was forced to intake by drink.

Knowing that this is judicial information time, I accept to talk to DR. ANNIE POKAM-KWAM, which is DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA and ROSE SANGNOU sister, by my own request.

My goal is at time to collect as much information as possible.

She (DR. ANNIE POKAM-KWAM) tries to convince me that i should intake psy drugs in order to be more sociable !

31.31 THREAT ON MY PERSON BY ROSE SANGNOU IN JUNE 2023

In June 2023, in its 25th week, a relative, ROSE SANGNOU, living and based in Douala for more than 60 years, comes into Yaoundé, and settle for 1 week at DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA's house, at her (DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA) invite.

ROSE SANGNOU, whom was told, no more to persecute myself, during her interrogation time at prosecutors' office in Douala-Ndokoti, starts calling me increasingly and says she is in Yaoundé because her sister (DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA) son, PATRICE SHANDA SANOU CABRAL, is very ill and hospitalized at Yaoundé general hospital.

ROSE SANGNOU insists that we shall meet because she is my mother. I then accept, but refused to meet up her at my private owned property in Yaoundé-Ahala-Nsimbock. We then meet up first at DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA house, then at supermarket 'supermarché carrefour EKIE' in YAOUNDÉ-ÉKIE.

THIS PERIOD IS judicial information investigation time, that is mostly why I accepted to meet up with her.

I NOTICE with an impression THAT my mother ROSE SANGNOU COULD HAVE BEEN BRUTALIZED ON HER LEFT KNEE. SHE SAID SHE FELT DOWN IN THE BACK OF HER SISTER'S HOUSE (DOROTHÉE NDJATIÉ SHANDA) because the maid woman SPILLED water with amidon on the floor.

AFTER FINISHING our lunch, my mother ROSE SANGNOU says I SHOULD START AGAIN TO TAKE psychiatric drugs: I IMMEDIATELY STAND UP FROM LUNCH TABLE AND RETURNS TO MY PRIVATELY OWNED PROPERTY, 'immeuble yerith'.

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (2.)

32.32 MY SUSPICIONS about real activities of pr. shanda-tonme jean-claude and his wife

SEVERAL TIMES, pr. shanda-tonme jean-claude invited myself to hotel PARFAIT GARDEN in yaoundé so that I COULD SEE HIM ACTING as managing director of expatriate US CITIZEN ELECTRICAL ENERGY COMPANY.

so i suspect pr. shanda-tonme jean-claude receives money from some big giants NORTH-AMERICAN COMPANIES, so to disrupt my activities in the free open source software (FOSS) AREA.

33.33 THREAT ON MY PERSON BY Victor Koliou Noundou IN JULY 2023

PREVIOUSLY. HÔPITAL ADLUCHEM, a hospital in Douala-BONAMOISSADI, that I went with paternal uncle Victor Koliou Noundou to threat a hyperglycemia, established with him (uncle Victor Koliou Noundou) THAT I SHOULD BE BROUGHT USING AN AMBULANCE to 'LAQUINITIE-CABANON' because Dr. MVONDO felt that I am not well behaving !

Victor Koliou Noundou, a brother of my late father Théodore Noumbissi ASKED MYSELF, relentlessly, if I still take the psychiatric drugs.

I need to note here that, WITHOUT ANY APPARENT REASON, another brother of my late father Théodore Noumbissi, Laurent Tchandeu, former minister plenipotentiary, sent A TRUCK WITH 6 firefighters to take me by force from my privately rented apartment in yaoundé, in the year 2015, SO TO BRING ME TO A PSYCHIATRIST OF 'JAMOT': Dr. Kamga.

IN FRONT OF ME, Dr. Kamga SAYS TO Laurent Tchandeu AND ROSE SANGNOU THAT HE CAN'T KEEP ME THERE AT 'JAMOT' BECAUSE I AM NOT A PSYCHIATRIC DISEASED PERSON.

Dr. Kamga ALSO MENTIONS THAT IF I GO TO COURT AGAINST HIM, HE WOULD PUT ALL TROUBLES on ROSE SANGNOU since WHAT SHE SAID TO HIM SO THAT HE SENT A FIREFIGHTER TRUCK to take myself by force from my privately rented apartment is wrong.

Laurent Tchandeu IS TRYING SINCE Théodore Noumbissi, my deceased (JANUARY 9, 1992) father (and chief of the NOUNDOU family), passed away, to sack my POSITION AS CHIEF OF THE FAMILY NOUNDOU:

- IN MAY 2023, politician GRÉGOIRE OWONA, grand-father of MY COUSIN MOTHER SIDE "ANGELA TCHAMOU SHANDA OWONA SPOUSE DR. WOLFGANG FERNAND JR. OWONA", comes with Laurent Tchandeu (and spouse DR. HENRIETTE POLA) in my village BABOUANTOU to open a primary school as gift from political party R.D.P.C (C.P.D.M).

34.34 THREAT ON MY PERSON BY Laurent Tchandeu ON AUGUST 3rd, 2023

DR. Laurent Tchandeu, a paternal uncle of mine, tries to harass myself with taking psychiatric drugs.

HE DID THIS USING TELEPHONY APPLICATION "whatsapp".

35.35 WAITING FOR judge JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA

JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA SEEMS TO WANT TO destroy evidences against state hospital laquintinie since He (JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA) hasn't call by police force DR. CHRISTIAN EYOUM to come answer allegations against him about TRYING TO KILL ME with psychiatric drugs at night after HIJACKING MY PRIVATE PROPERTY IN DOUALA-CITÉ-DES-PALMIERS !

36.36 ARMY GENDARMERIE COLONEL KÉMAJOU harasses ROSE sangnou my mother

ROSE SANGNOU, my mother, complained to myself that KÉMAJOU is calling her very frequently to tell her I (PROF. DR.-ING. DIPL.-INF. XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU) is not mentally sane since HE is doing a lot of christian cross-sign while walking on Yaoundé streets.

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (3.)

37.37 ARMY GENDARMERIE COLONEL KÉMAJOU destroying my life as a neighbor

A FORMER SED (SÉCRÉTARIAT D'ÉTAT À LA GENDARMERIE) retired colonel of cameroon gendarmerie, who has spying devices AT HOME TO HEAR PHONE, OR WHATSAPP conversations; MAKES CURRENT ELECTRICITY cut-off whenever I RECEIVE MONEY so I cannot cook and refrigerate my food properly.

THIS VERY POOR PERSON, both in spirit and financially; whose wife makes money out of cooking food for street workers, COULD SUCCESSFULLY intimidate people not to come attend work or anything else into my real estate properties.

COLONEL (retired) of Army Gendarmerie KÉMAJOU couldn't lie and convince people that I DON'T POSSESS A Ph.D in Computer Engineering; since his son "Jonas Kémajou" who he also in gendarmerie told me once: "Myself I also POSSESS A Ph.D QUALIFICATION WITH NO DEGREE AT HOME" !

I am wondering in Cameroon why army intermediates in civilian life and affairs; THIS DOESN'T HAPPEN usually in rich and developed countries like Germany.

This day of **Saturday November 18, 2023**; while I was talking to a computer technician neighbor named Gabriel Takoumbe, KÉMAJOU came along walking with an indigo "Garde Présidentielle (special unit of cameroon forces attached only for the President of The Republic.)" T-shirt.

COLONEL kemajou tells me HE WANTS MY PERSON NOT TO WRITE anymore on his forfeitures against myself; in front of at least 7 young men and women, saying He didn't call my genitor mother any day before.

COLONEL kemajou sect named JÉRUSALEM APOSTOLAT, sacks every public entry road to my real estate 2-storey building (unfinished yet).

Yves Landry Galax ETOGA, chief of secret services of Cameroon seems to like to try harassing competent professors of science and technology like myself. May be He works against CAMEROONIAN SKILLED ORPHANS like my humble person in JEOVAH-NISSI in heaven !

PROF. DR. RER. NAT. HABIL. JAN PELESKA and DR. PATRICK LAM have never said anything against what is happening to myself since 3 years ago; ALSO, Patrick is a member of Rotarian organization ROSICRUCIARY !

"29" November 2023: I HAVE RENOUNCED TO AN ATTORNEY since TCHANA NJEUTCHA Synclaire is clearly going against my personal interests !

"03" December 2023: KEMAJOU and its troops that call themselves Christians ARE HARASSING PEOPLE COMING HOME.

"04" December 2023: I cannot recognized Cameroon where someone high qualified by myself is permanently harassed physically by illegal neighbors like KEMAJOU gendarmerie colonel Criminal.

KEMAJOU gendarmerie colonel tries on the street to talk to myself while I am coming back from a hardware shop.

It seems to myself that illegal neighbors religious sect "Jerusalem Apostolat" is trying to make confusion about my humble person wherever I go in my life; Kemajou gendarmerie colonel has tried around my neighborhood, with help of SECTARIAN OF JERUSALEM APOSTOLAT; to make noise that XAVIER noumbissi noundou IS A PSYCHIATRIC PATIENT that doesn't want to take pills !

38.38 THREAT ON MY PERSON BY ROSE SANGNOU IN JANUARY 2024

ROSE SANGNOU, despite that JUDGE HUGUES ALAIN YAGER MABOMA gave her prohibition to come to my home in Yaounde during year 2023, came by force with someone that I don't know whereabouts To my neighbor "CARINE LELE njougep tchana" To incriminate her about chairs she owns by now;

I destroyed chairs that were not in good shape last year from my humble home by throwing them away outside. It seems "CARINE LELE njougep tchana" put them in her personal home without asking myself since I just threw them away; which is normal since They don't belonged to me anymore !

"30" January 2024: It seems my genitor mother ROSE SANGNOU went to talk to gendarmerie people so they could harass myself to go for an illegal psychiatric treatment; because while I was talking to Justice "ME. ANDRÉ Mbet" today, I saw 1 gendarmerie man came into his personal office where he also, with his wife, Owns a financial transaction center.

I immediately told Justice "ME. ANDRE Mbet" about this attitude of gendarmerie people coming inside where I perform businesses to make some kind of visual and gesture signs to owners of businesses, So they wouldn't deal with myself anymore !

"24, 25" April 2024: 1 man wearing a talkie-walkie came across my personal road in Simbock YDE.

I went to talk to him since I was looking for a technician that didn't finish a work in my humble house. For 6 days now, this technician wasn't in my house anymore despite myself telling him to finish his work on my steel door.

I suspect again justice ("huissier") SHANDA-DJATIE and her spouse Pr. JEAN-CLAUDE shanda-tonme to harass my genitor and mother Rose SANGNOU to try to bring myself by force to a psychiatric destructive mind place.

JERUSALEM-APOSTOLAT rosicrucian sect tried to follow myself these last 2 days using the brigand 'Moise BATOMEN', and another person male, THAT I don't know whereabouts but that live behind "Carine Lele Njougep Tchana" house for at least 6 months from now backwards in time !

Just 1 month before, I was stopped from walking by to our main official road by a sectarian female of Jerusalem-APOSTOLAT. I now see that it was meant to bring myself to other roads were they don't have their own people on it, so they could hijack myself properly to bring by force to a psychiatric hospital so to try to deteriorate my physical and psy body.

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (4.)

39.39 SHANDA SANOU patrice cabral idiot son of Dorothée Shanda Owona passes away at age 33 (March 18, 2024)

"Dorothée Shanda Owona" who had tried to make myself sodomized "by Bertrand of Laquintinie" in Feb. 2021, illegally by police force.

SHE leaves now her son out of life after 3.5 years trying to destroy my life; Probably because she got some laundry money for this dirty task against A BORN-AGAIN-CHRISTIAN !

NONE of the people I have heard from coming back "from some kind of obituary ceremony" could even see any corpse of ATTORNEY OF LAW, deceased, Patrick Cabral SHANDA SANOU !

40.40 Dr. Annie Metiam, Spouse Eric-POKAM-WAM tries to say something illegally about my mental health publicly (May 23, 2024)

A sister of my mother and genitor ROSE SANGNOU, DR. ANNIE POKAM-KWAM, sends a RECORDED AUDIO MESSAGE via whatsapp-phone-android-application, without any request from "Rose Sangnou" and / or my person about a supposed mental health abilities report that She as GASTROENTEROLOGIST has wrote based on our investigation whatsapp call that was done in year 2023 during around the month of JUNE.

This retarded personage that was initially at "Alfred Saker School" oriented to perform Commerce AND Accounting, WITH A grade of 10.00/20 is an idiot; Not just because *she doesn't even have a "degree of Doctor of Medicine (Dr. med.)"*.

This happens unsolicited as I am having a talk together with "Rose Sangnou"; AND "PASTOR marco OF Pentecostal Christian CHURCH" ' 'chapelle de la gloire de christ" in DLA.

I AM SUSPICIOUS of this corrupt C.P.D.M aunt that has german citizenship to be from Central Intelligence Agency (CIA); hired specially to try to kill me by any means; even using sorcery.

41.41 YAGER MABOMA is an idiot of justice judge here in CMR

Since 2021, February that I have complaint for a group of harassers that came into my compound to brutalize myself in front of a so called judge of instruction from sawa tribal tribe, I STILL RECEIVE PEOPLE TRYING TO AGGRESS and Harass myself.

42.42 I-xavier-went on roads to shout That I required JUSTICE for my saved life by SYNCLAIRE NJEUTCHA TCHANA

- o **Wednesday 28th of JUNE 2024:** "Proverbs 1 : 18 – 21 (in Holy bible of JEOVAH-NISSI in Heaven)"

Synclaire NJEUTCHA TCHANA was sodomized both physically and mentally to release myself as a client, So I will go in front of a judge without the initial attorney I have chosen myself.

I went to road "in AHALA-simbock" to shout at populace that I MUST HAVE JUSTICE DONE against people who broke my gate in the night of FEBRUARY 2023 to kill me with psy-drugs involuntarily.

Politics is going on thoroughly because the year 2025 must released a president of the republic of cameroon !

43.43 YAGER MABOMA has sent my documents to Attorney-prosecutor

- o **SATURDAY 31th of AUGUST 2024:**

I hope I can finish this matter without a judge that has been sodomized by "BIYA-clique".

"Synclaire NJEUTCHA TCHANA" said to myself on my cell phone that I sent to him at least 2 other attorneys of law so to replace him; Which is FALSE.

"Synclaire NJEUTCHA TCHANA" has received money from PAUL-biya.

"Tchonang albertine" is now the person I asked for, for assistance."

"I received this name and contact from my friend and customer "HAPPINESS POTENTIAL SARL" based in Akwa-douala ! "

44.44 Police of AHALA – 19ème arrondissement harassing myself because of SHANDA-tonmeo **Friday 6th of September 2024:**

"NESTOR kenfack tries to talk to my genitor and adversary ROSE-Sangnou without asking anything to myself."

"ROSE-idiot sangnou went to give certain objects to "NESTOR and VALÉRIE kenfack" that are supposed to be my sole customers and friends; Without any intermingled relationship with ROSE-sangnou since I told both of them THAT I am not interested into talking with someone who has tried to kill myself."

"I KNOW that it is C.P.D.M that went to give money to these burglars ("NESTOR" & "VALÉRIE") so they will try to intervene against my interests when court justice comes AS this has been the case with my personal attorney of law the culprit "SYNCLAIRE NJEUTCHA TCHANA"."

45.45 CLOVIS kemmegne as intelligence service gendarmerie agent against my privacy lifeo **Saturday 10th of November 2024:**

"A culprit called CLOVIS kemmegne, an intelligence secret service agent of GENDARMERIE NATIONALE of CAMEROON is tring to put troubles into my life via false divulged information around my new business relationships with a new tenant that I could gained via a so called "RENTAL PROPERTY MANAGER"-EMMANUEL-idiot."

"NOW that i have been staying in douala for more than 4-days in a row since my last hijack-attempt, in a so-called inherited property of noumbissi-vilain-idiot THÉODORE; I can see that clovis kemmgne changed the colours GREEN-Yellow-gendarmerie of his GAY-young-porn-female-clairvoyant-boy-jackdaniels; INTO a BLUE-presidential-GRAY-porn-DGRE colors."

"INSTEAD of doing is openly called business of electronics computer technician, and also, "GAY-handler-bar-JACKS.", THIS guja-gay is hiding himself behind my sister and my mother-side family to plan a so-called "CONSTAT-de-FAIT" for the idiot of justice judge HUGUES-alain-yager maboma-faineant."

"THE other gay-called napoa-maxime-eteme; a viagra-gay that seems to be a burglar to myself since BAMKOUÏ said to me he didn't worked at all for SEMIL; BUT is working for CMR-navy in DOUALA; came openly salute myself, together with another idiot called KAMGAIN jean-pierre;"

"i hope only "jean-loïc siewe and belvianne" that seemed to be young fellow cameroonian entrepreneurs are not intermeddle here."

"i can already see that siewe's mother is from the idiot-village-Babouantou !."

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (VI (6).)

CLOVIS kemmegne as intelligence service gendarmerie agent against my privacy lifeo **Wednesday 13th of November 2024:**

"SIEWE and BELVIANNE his collaborator of my new rental property seem to be not able to accommodate well due to destructive actions in water plumbery that seemed to be have done by a previous renter called; AND from R.D.P.C-C.P.D.M-south-bulu-tribe: GERMAIN Blaise ndzie and his wife called Geneviève Ndzie."

"~~Dr. —NOMO siméon-replacement by C.P.D.M.-eyoump-psy~~; A so-called MAXIME-napoa-eteme called someone I am not sure "Docteur" while I was crossing a street at DLA-cité-des-palmiers yesterday evening; THIS gay-female-psy-hijackist; THAT seemed to be an organizer of my killing via the hijack of my private property in DLA-FEBRURAY-2024 is the one that talked to my 1st before a same day at night I was hijacked. "

"~~MAXIME-napoa-eteme~~ the gay-female-idiot is also from BETI-ekang-amougou-beling-TRAIBAL-tribe as a previous renter called NDZIE geneviève. "

o **SUNDAY 17th of November 2024:**

"IT seems there are no repression against criminals that come officially against my personal and / or familiar interests in CMR. "

"FOR INSTANCE, a family from "BATIÉ-ouest-cmr" that bake "beignets" and that used to transport "Pouse-Pousse" has built a 'bidon-ville-taudis' directly closed to my compound, Where my late father dear THEODORE-idiot noumbissi built a ground foundation, Without any rejection from SOUS-Préfecture that I contacted using my Attorney at law Mr. JUSTICE (Maître Synclaire NJEUTCHA tchana)."

"Some folk around this place in Béedi told me that:

1. "A beauty-gay hair-cut society wearing black and /or rosa T-SHIRTS, based on the opposite side of road to CLOVIS-telecom-Alias-kemmgne-gendarmerie-nationale-CMR";

"Sent a hijacker wearing finger-female-paint to say to people around where I was sitting reading my Bible-holy; That I AM SAID to be a mad-person; "

"BEFORE this physical attack even though I WASN'T talking to that gendarme that seems to act as a gay-female-hair treater; I COULD see a woman from CHRISTIAN-eyoum-tribal-tribe called Assassin. "

2. "Clovis telecom Alias clovis kemmegne" has repeatedly summon several people to harass me with no fear since he is well connected with ETOO-fils, a burglar called in CMR Soccer-player-female-male-born-again-gay-hijackist-Christian-eyoum "
3. "Maxime NAPOA-eteme is the one who told this very strange family since they don't do anything apparently to survive in Douala other than sneaking other people properties; WHERE enforced by "NAPOA ETEME, MAXIME" to Hijack myself even physically because I AM A NOBODY IN THIS COUNTRY called CAMEROON. "
4. "i suspect the current president of the republic of CMR called PAUL-biya to be behind this multi-attempt to destroy my life; Since for all my legal complaints nothing could be done for at least more than 12 years. "
5. "paul-biya-junior is mad; a culprit from mvomekaa. "

o **WEDNESDAY 27th of November 2024:**

"This new renter of mine a so-called-CALLPRIT jean-loïc siewe, And BELVIANNE meleu nossi seem not to even welcome very nicely their clients because they left so dirty the entrance step-feet of their rented apartment for 138 EUROS monthly. "

"ALSO this belvianne aged of 25th years old seem not to understand that I AM NOT CONFIDENT of renewing their rental agreement because of all inconsistencies I COULD notice since they entered this apartment inherited of mine:"

1. Her national identity card says she is "SCHOOL student of IUT-douala".

THERE was a so-called "gendarme-etoga-idiot" call Jonas-Kemajou-fainénat that scammed myself around 3 000 EUROS, And that was wearing a gendarme-green-attire, And that also has this "SCHOOL student of IUT-douala" instead of something professional-criminal-armed-robber-south-west-CMR.

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (VII (7).)

- **Thursday 28th of November 2024:**

Je met en pièce jointe le contrat supposé conforme OHADA.

"**MAÎTRE synclaire njeutcha tchana avocat au minimum du barreau du cmr**" en est l'auteur et approbateur sous ma requête de ses services; Puisque je ne peux même plus financièrement me permettre d'être chez 1 autre conseil avec la tentative d'assassinat manquée du "**President-de-la-republique-du CAMEROUN**" que j'ai essuyé à l'aide de "**JESUS-de-nazareth**" le 14 FÉVRIER 2021 à 23 : 30 à mon domicile de DOUALA.

- **Tuesday 3rd of December 2024:**

I COULDN'T stay more than 2 years without PAUL-biya sending to myself again people hijacking my life when I WAS SCREAMING ON ROADS that BIYA and its clique MUST LEAVE all my fellow people that are above normal idiot-human being intelligence out of PSYCHIATRIC-psy drugs so to maintain MAN-Kind in caverns.

THIS time the VIOLENT PEOPLE WHO ARRESTED myself with a fake document that they even showed myself because I SAID this is fraud; "NOUMBISSI NOUNDOU jacob"; I am born "NOUMBISSI noundou, XAVIER";

GADAFI was even so prominent in doing this that HE got even places where he was practicing black-people slavery in desert-lybia.

- **FRIDAY 6th of December 2024:**

I couldn't sustain seeing ROSE-idiote SANGNOU-rose, my genitor-precious showing signs of madness in front of people when he entered the office step-door of the WOURI-prefect of police.

I Hope authorities of violence and armies could now understand that IT is her, THAT is a sick person, AND not me per Se.

SHE showed afterwards to myself money-laundry that my sister uterine ingrid-teuntchou planed to give to the MOTHER-rose that is the police commissioner that brought us using a LUXURIOUS toyota corolla grey-color to the PREFECT-office-plaza..

INGRID-teuntchou-noumeni is trying to kill myself so she will be only beneficiarist of my real-estate properties; TOGETHER with her husband in law and families: ISAAQ-teuntchou-INGRID-teuntchou-noumeni sent to myself a picture where she was behind a white-german-dirty-girl having a rose-flour in front of her while she was a student in Freiburg-baden-wuettemberg-GERMANY long years ago I CAN now remember; Meaning she was entering a rosicrucian sectarian sororities-fraternities of violent aggressive people hijacking own families people belonging so to possess a WELL-TO-DO living; This cannot happen to me in The mighty name of JEOVAH-NISSI-in HEAVEN !

I also remember his dirty-finger-idiot-brother-inLAW TEUNTCHOU-galin talking to me of a sorcerer freemason while we were in his car; CALLED allister-crowley; This is teuntchou-family-subject: SORCERY; INGRID and children I strongly believe will turn mad on streets 1 day, Since they are doing this to simple people other than MYSELF since I cannot see any future for such a poor-educated-daughter-adultery-TCHUINDJANG-franklin in this hard-work-life; HER cousin PATRIGE-shanda-fainéant SANOU-cabral passed away this year at age 32 in INDIA and nobody could see his corpse, meaning they (dorothée-ndjatié and her husband Jean-claude SHANDA-tonme) sold it to have eating money luxurious !

- **FRIDAY 15th of December 2024:**

"I was tortured by a police female officer at DLA 05ème ARRONDISSEMENT headquarters; Called : "Renseignements GENERAUX"; Since I wasn't allowed to urinate on due time when I REQUESTED FOR IT. [tHis shows again that PAUL biya barthelemy mvondo-idiot is a murderer of young intelligent people in CMR.] "

"THIS mad paul-biya of cmr republic presidency must already investigate his agents that try to assassinate myself before thinking of investigating why I INSULT him idiot, on streets. "

"Jeovah-nissi in heaven" is the only one being that protects my soul here on earth since even so called europe and america-chiens of human rights are thinking of myself as a simple idiot race black and not as a mischling (Racial mixed white-black) Like PAUL-biya-fainéant-cuon-pédé. "

"this mvondo-idiot called teuntchou noumeni chandriand seems not to understand that people must not come to other people places in reason of getting a wife; While their honest reason to coming to a man's place-home is hijacking his properties. "

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (VIII (8).)

- monDAY 23th of December 2024:

“Je ne sais plus pourquoi je n'ai plus été contacté par madame le commissaire spécial maman-rose de Dla5ème.“

“Elle avait donnée des instructions à l'antigang "NDI" de me donner 1 numéro de téléphone pour que je puisse les recontacter; "Ndi" ne l'a plus fait; IL a tout simplement repris mon numéro de Téléphone que j'avais déjà auparavant donné lors de mon procès verbal entente.“

“IL était question que je puisse rencontrer Monsieur le PREFET-du-Wouri aux fins de recouvrer mon titre foncier de MFOUNDI-06 reconfier Rose SANGNOU par victor koliou noundou sans mon accord !.“

MAMAN-rose de Dla 05ème, merci.

- monDAY 23th of December 2024:

“siewe jean-loïc, a new renter of 1 of my real-estate seems not to understand a fundamental difference between human beings and animals like dogs : "Human beings in order to cooperate in peace and NO mis-understanding must talk peacefully and gently to one another !“

“THE task of being a professor on his own money in a country like Cameroon is not easy at all folk-idiot : I can only understand that "GLOBAL EXPERT SOLUTION Sarl" will then pay their rent manually to myself and directly again starting August 2024.“

“I was kind of afraid hearing a so called attorney of mine possessing a master-professional in practice of law asserting in front of myself on a phone call with him : Synclaire-NJEUTCHA-tchana-idiot on the line outside offices of RENSEIGNEMENTS GENERAUX of DLA5ÈME saying that he finds that I AM NOT CLEAR MINDED.-PERIOD.“

“THE mvondo-country of governance with bribers everywhere is surprising for myself as a world-citizen everyday : I HOPE THIS idiot of attorney of law WILL NOT take money from people like "siewe jean-loïc in my backwards" so to disadvantage myself publicly Even in handling my cases at so called Salaud-NOEL-MOELLE-prosecutor at DLA-ndokoti-justice-palace.“

“the prosecutor of DLA-ndokoti justice palace called ~~r-noël-moëlle~~ is a sawa also and couldn't summoned as FAR AS I KNOW; THIS criminal assassin murderer other sawaian called r-Christian Eyoum; BUT he could send "8 burglars" to hijack my humble Doctorated-person invested with my own hard-working money; to arrest myself with a fake name of mine on a paper that seemed to be from THE REPUBLIC OF mvomekaa !“

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS (IX (9).)

- **MONDAY 03th of February 2024:**

"JUGE hugues alain yager maboma, ce petit morveux de DLA-sawa-bribery-chien n'a pas de temps pour faire son travail conformément aux us et coutumes internationales; En principe des gens de cette acabit d'assassins comme MAMA-rose des renseignements généraux de DLA-05ème devraient savoir que JÉSUS-de-Nazareth est vivant en moi."

- **thursDAY 30th of JANAUARY 2024:**

"TODAY i went to eat mornings at my paternal uncle VICTOR koliou noundou place in DOUALA-makepe-missoke, since ROSE-sangnou-génitrice didn't appear with my belongings at my 1st residence in DLA-ndokoti-CITÉ-des-palmiers."

ROSE sangnou noumbissi-spouse idiot was trying to disrupt my activities in YDE since SHE went on to cancel my renters from DLA-CITÉ-des-palmiers apartments around 1.5 years ago : TRADIS-S.A.R.L; And "bulu-rdpc-tribu Germain BLAISE ndzié"; Without any previous notification to my person; Disrupting my income that I use to create proper technology and service-training for AFRICA for at least 10 years from now; when I started "Startup YERITH R&D" in YDE-siméon-nomo-ASSASSIN-from-Laurent tchandeu seniores paternal uncle and Personal friend of MVONDO-ayolo-samuel, AND grégoire-owona-beriac.

THIS culprit of uncle couldn't call rose in front of myself but agree SHE shall give me back my money, around "45 000 Xaf", additionally to the rent I received from "MELVIANNE meleu nossi" since I wasn't receiving money from our other rented properties of DLA-bonabéri since at least 17 years.

eyoum-christian was saying everywhere in DLA-laquintinie hospital that XAVIER shall regain problems in his life every other 2 years if he doesn't take pills : THIS idiot asserted physician-MD from SAWA-douala-tribu, LIKE judge, Prosecutor and JUSTICE-minister is currently trying to create an issue to support his fake money-laundry bribery money from LAURENT-tchandeu-SAMUEL-ayolo-mvondo "C.P.D.M-via KOLIOU noundou victor" that is also implicitly from this gang of domination (god).

TEBWO-yamkam moïse, a cousin maternal of victor-koliou-noundou, As far as I know from genealogy, Could even try to say at some places he is a lawyer of my family "NOUNDOU".

HOPEFULLY this year 2025 forward, I will not be hijacked again around FEBRUARY as this has been the case for at least 3 years from now backwards by people of "NOUNDOU-beriac-tchandeu-owona-Gregoire-C.P.D.M-aigle-sigipes2" — SAP-Waldorf (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051568/>).

[YERITH R&D is currently working on automated payment service module for employees for product "YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum".]

- **thursDAY 06th of FEBRUARY 2025:**

"Gendarmerie colonel kemajou seems to have opened my house using a key I gave to concrete technician bulu-tribu FRANCIS Nkoulou Come Magloire; To TAKE OVER all my physical belongings in my privately owned apartment of YAOUNDE in "Immeuble YERITH", While I was in Douala trying to get back my money from my german-related sister INGRID teuntchou noumeni; SINCE kemajou and teuntchou know each other very well; I ASSUME this was done in coordination so I will not advance my SAP-other racist-opponent : YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum. "

"MY genitor rose-sangnou even called this FRANCIS nkoulou COME magloireu (cousin of the Bataillon D'intervention Rapide (B.I.R.) Army UNIT criminal-MARCELLIN EMANA NKOA PIERRE. So he will not close the main entrance that I replaced from wood to steel."

Bamileke-indigenous-tribu people would very much be interested in myself taking a woman as a wife before I pursue my entrepreneurship project YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum ant others because I AM INVINCIBLE when I STAY like JEovah-NISSI-in-Heaven with no snake-raped woman-like ROSE-sangnou.

I HOPE donald-idiot trump will help myself coming out of BIYA's regime of dictatorship and crime (Isaiah 14 (<https://www.sainte bible.com/lsg/isaiah/14.htm>)).

o **Vendredi 14th of Février 2025:**

“L’assassinat manqué sur ma propre personne par TEUNTCHOU-ISAAC, Rose-Sangnou, CHRISTIAN-eyoum-idiot-psy; de Février 2021 avait tourné au vinaigre Puisque je ne suis plus 1 païen, mais 1 chrétien né-de-nouveau (English : BORN-AGAIN).“

“Teuntchou chandriand noumeni m’a appris qu’il n’était pas au courant de certains fait tels que : “

- 1.) 1 porte en fer chez moi où son père par le gendarme franc-macon-JERUSALEM-apostolat KEMAJOU; A fait cambriolé tous mes effets dans la maison somptueuse construite à coups d’efforts au Canada.
 - 2.) TEUNTCHOU chandriand noumeni arrive toujours chez moi avec ROSE-sangnou-génitrice comme si elle est 1 otage de quelque chose qui devrait me pourrir la vie éternellement sur la terre de JEOVAH-nissi-Au-CIEL.
 - 3.) J’ai aussi remarqué que depuis que je lui avais montré où je déjeune souvent, Chez 1 camerounais d’origine niGérienne; NOMMÉ ”Mohammed Ali”; PAS select ce petit mochtatek; Mais y’a rien de mieux à Cité-des-PALMIERS-haute-tension-béedi :
- A. IL y’a 1 certain indic de la gendarmerie de NDOG-BONG, je pense la compagnie, Puisque le TERRE, n’est pas souvent très achalandée par des badaux de ce genre sur 1 moto-taxi; Il se prénommerait ”Benjamin”, selon les dires de Mohammed-ALL.

B. Cet indic-benjamin ne cesse de venir s’asseoir et faire des commentaires sur le ”CAMEROUN”, la ”PATRIE”, et tout le tralala que l’on raconte aux illétrés sur la CRTV pour 1 bon fonctionnement du CMR.

AUPARAVANT j’avais aussi beaucoup de temps d’observer des somptueuses mallettes noires portés par des DSP.

DEPUIS vers Novembre 2021, Où je me suis fais agressé physiquement lorsque j’intimais à 1 voisine pseudonyme ”Jeanne”; De ne plus s’asseoir devant l’entrée de portail de nos résidences dès 09h du matin pour discuter avec 1 autre voisine; En l’occurrence 1 des filles de père BASSA-chef-de-block; La jeune fille impétueuse a essayée de me frapper avec des coups de poings que j’ai pu échappés grâce à 1 fuite en avant vers la gendarmerie de NDOG-BONG-compagnie.

C. **Jusques à ce jour, AUCUN gendarme n’est venue à mon secours PUISQUE même ma plainte avait été changé en 1 histoire selon laquelle je choisissais cette pétasse de Jeanne pour copuler; MAIS elle n’acceptait plus; Donc je voulais lui faire des ennuies.**

“MOI qui honnie toute sexualité de cette expérience commandée par ”AUDREY nguetie tchamga”, dont je me suis séparée à Toronto après 1 mois de relation sexuelle et amoureuse infructueuse pour 1 mariage à la non-Homosexuelle (Sainte BIBLE : 1-Corinthiens 38 – 40). “

En passant, j’avais abusé de ma langue face à l’agression physique et verbale de cette façon :

1.) **Son père subissait des chaînes publiques sur tout le corps de ses propres enfants et épouses.**

J’avais bien précisé que je ne chercherais sûrement pas 1 fille de pousse-pousse fou pour 1 mariage, Vu mon statut de ”Docteur-Ph.D.”; 1 intellectuel avec 1 commerçante Sans baccalauréat serait 1 divorce programmé.

2.) BENJAMIN, avec 1 petit blouson bleue-gris et comme chauffeur de moto-taxi de la compagnie de gendarmerie de ndog-bong; Naturellement aux dernières nouvelles commandé par 1 capitaine de la région du SUD-bulu; A tout fait pour faire du Brouhaha lorsque j’étais entrain de consommé ce jour ;;

a. 2 œufs spaghetti;

b. 2 gâteaux farines de patate jaune;

c. 1 tiers de pain de blé blanc avec de la mayonnaise badigonné pour 1 montant de 50-fcfa-petit-euro.

d. Ce petit souillon de bassa d’indic ne sais plus le proverbe :

ON Répond à 1 imbécile par 1 coup de silence; Appris au cmr de collègue confessionnel alfred saker de Douala.

e. EH-EH-EH, nkaghère mbuembe; wantong-ketcha; tossou-BORIS-belzebul-chien-chaîne-au-COU depuis Microsoft-concurrent-de-IBM :

“ON était aussi venue à ”Saker” avec le ROTARY-club en tant que humanisme-secte nous le proposer je me souviens j’avais moins de 14 ans.” :

Même MAMA-mvom-mezam-INGRID-pas YUEGO-komguem était aussi de ces années où l’on proposait juste 1 petite partouze là où on mange le bâton-haricot.

D. **TOUT camerounais sous 1 certains niveau d’éducation par le biais du R.D.P.C est 1 gendarme ou 1 indic de gendarmerie; Ceci permet au R.D.P.C. de faire que des individus travailleurs et entrepreneurs orphelins de papa comme moi aient des difficultés de grandir financièrement Et sur 1 plan de paix et sécurité autour d’eux; Puisque ce sont ces soit-disant Gens d’ARMES (à feu) qui organisent des viols, assassinats, etc..**

JUDICIAL AFFAIR PROSECUTIONS – ATANGA-NJI MINISTER TRYING TO DESTROY WORK RESEARCH OF YERITH R&D—NAZISM <= BIYA-REGIME ((11).)

◦ 🇧🇫 Lundi 17th of Février 2025:

Happiness Potential SARL du culprit-FABRICE-sed-yves-chien-etoga m'appelle pour essayer de résorber 1 problème de possession et d'entrer dans sa machine de son ex employé HECNA-ngayam.

La jeune dame a en effet semble t'il démissionner.

L'ignare me tends "2 000 francs CFA" après près de 2 heures de temps de diagnostic et de formation sur la sécurité informatique pour des TPE comme la sienne; En l'occurrence HAPINESS-bétises SARL-idiot-candien-tabawouek-nji-atanga-enculé.

L'enculé essaye d'avoir accès à mon ordinateur portable en connection avec son ordinateur truffé de programmes pirates; Surement provenant de DEREK-rayside; Aux fins de supprimer mes activités de chercheur indépendant en GENIE.

Le fainéant a aussi pris attache avec des gens reconnues pour leurs visions destructrices dans mes vie tels que koliou-noundou-victor.

◦ February 26th of Wednesday 2025:

"PHARMACY mfuppa, just opened 1 month ago opposite road of my residence in DLA; I went for a pain in my little finger right side and I was diagnosed to ingest 'Sedaspir' from France-CEDEX..."

"CURRENTLY as I am writing this report, I am even wondering how I am alive since I spent 3 days having belly blocked for digestion."

"REALLY I was told to ingest 3 pills a day; When I went back there to report this bad health caused by their prescribed drug "Sedarspir", A lady told me I could instead in-take 1 pill a day ! "

I said I prefer not to in-take this "Sedarspir" at all; Based on what I could feel as pain around my belly and neck.

"I couldn't know personally Dr.-AZEFOUET that is supposed to be a main proprietor of this pharmacy; AZEFOUET, as reported on the advertising plates, Has GRADUATED from UDM-UNIVERSITÉ DES MONTAGNES; In west-cameroon."

◦ February 26th of Wednesday 2025:

"I hope christian-eyoum, a psy-MD from littoral region who has assaulted-hijacked myself in February 2021 is not implicated in this assassination attempt by Dr.-MFUPPA-rdpc-cpdm-GARDE-presidentielle."

"Could normal human being be a president of the republic, chief of state-Army and practiced business equitably ?!"

◦ MARCH 5th of Wednesday 2025:

"A family member of my father's birth's family NOUNDOU, called victor-idiot koliou noundou seems not to understand that when someone lives on itw own without asking him any advice and / or money, HE-victor-gay shall try to stay in its own life without coming around rose-chienne and ingrid-teuntchou to give counsels on how to destroy my life ! "

"SOMEONE like victor-koliou noundou & spouse Josianne-noundou; That never had a prestigious and / or luxurious life and that are sent by TCHANDEU-assassin laurent to defeat my prestigious and luxurious life, by saying for instance WITH a degree of Waterloo-UNIVERSITY I could also teach to get some small money ! "

"SOMEONE like victor-koliou noundou that was born in an indigenous & poor village BABOUANTOU comes in city Douala at age 17 years old & now wants to inculcate indigenous WEST-race idiot life lifestyle to someone born in city ! "

◦ MARCH 17th of Tuesday 2025:

"A culprit called maurice TCHAYA sends to myself someone girl saying she could consult my eyes for a prescription of new medical eyeglasses. ! "

"LADY-gyneco-obstétrique MVONDO-biya-rdpc-cpd.m seemed to be an satanic envoy from CANADA-waterloo-racist ! "

◦ MARCH 30th of Sunday 2025:

C.P.D.M-r.d.pc, CMR ruling political dictatorial party seems to have closed down cabanon and open instead VIP-torture cell-bedrooms.

SCIENTIFIC PRESENTATION TALKS 1

- MAY 2007; STATISTICAL TEST CASE GENERATION FOR REACTIVE SYSTEMS, MASTER'S DEGREE THESIS DEFENSE TALK, DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS AND COMPUTER SCIENCE (FB 3), UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY
- NOVEMBER 2010; STatically VERIFYING API USAGE RULES USING TRACEMATCHES, 9th Workshop on Compiler-Driven Performance, CASCON 2010, Hilton Suites Toronto/Markham Conference Centre, MARKHAM, ONTARIO, CANADA
- DECEMBER 2011; TEMPORAL PROPERTY VERIFICATION IN PLUGIN-based SOFTWARE, PH.D. THESIS EXAMINATION COMPREHENSIVE I, DEPARTMENT OF ELECTRICAL AND COMPUTER ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA
- April 2014; CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM, ECE GRAD TALK, DEPARTMENT OF ELECTRICAL AND COMPUTER ENGINEERING, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA
- JANUARY 2015; CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM, PROGRAMMING LANGUAGES SEMINAR, DAVID R. CHERITON SCHOOL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA
- JANUARY 2016; YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; sns cameroon ltd (Mr. DIVINE Njobati); YAOUNDE; CENTER; CAMEROON
- JANUARY 2016; YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; best car care & services (Mr. HENRI ngatchou); DOUALA; LITTORAL; CAMEROON
- MAY 2016; YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; snob bazar outlet stores (Mr. LAVOISIER); YAOUNDE; CENTER; CAMEROON
- JUNE 2016; YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; expert3dev s.a.r.l (Mr. Momo); YAOUNDE; CENTER; CAMEROON
- JANUARY 2017; YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; bilingual entente bookshop (Mr. JACQUES); YAOUNDE; CENTER; CAMEROON
- JUNE 2017; YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; BLACK & WHITE snack bars (Mr. TOM & Mr. AURÉLIEN iloga iloga (ecobank poste centrale yaoundé)); YAOUNDE; CENTER; CAMEROON
- SEPTEMBER 2017; YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for COMPUTER INFORMATICS ENGINEERING TRAINING; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; IUC [Institut Universitaire de la Côte] (Mr. HYPOLITHE Tekeu); DOUALA; LITTORAL; CAMEROON
- JUNE 2018; YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS TALKS; Dr. SANDY beidu; Dr. ERIC brefo-mensah; WATERLOO; ON; CANADA
- SEPTEMBER 2018; YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for CROWD FUNDING REQUEST PROPOSAL; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION (for "MS WINDOWS"); BAFIASOFT (Mr. CHRISTIAN rikong ngueyong); WATERLOO; ON; CANADA
- MAY 2020; YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; copletec s.a.r.l (Mr. CONSTANT Kemmogne); DOUALA; LITTORAL; CAMEROON
- JANUARY 2021; YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce and drugstore selling; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; pharmacy fiango lycée MAKÊPÈ (Dr. PETER Akume Ngoe); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON
- FEBRUARY 2021; YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce and INDUSTRIAL logistics; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; bontée s.a.r.l (Ms. ARLETTE Sibeufo); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON
- MARCH 2021; YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce and PRODUCTION planing; SOFTWARE DESIGN AND INTRINSICS PRESENTATION; CROQUE-MATIN (Mr. MOUSSA Saliou); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON
- JUNE 2021; YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL ("MS WINDOWS 2000"); elektro makêpè (Mr. ARMSTRONG); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON
- JULY 2021; YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; établissement kenfack (Mr. KENFACK); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON
- SEPTEMBER 2021; YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce, AND client relationship management; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; clinique de l'espérance (Mr. YVES Mogo); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON
- OCTOBER 2021; YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce, AND client relationship management; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; pctb s.a.r.l (Dr. AIMÉE FRANCIS Ngadjeu Tchana); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON
- NOVEMBER 2021; YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; quincaillerie la confiance (Mr. AIMÉE); YAOUNDE; CENTER region; CAMEROON

SCIENTIFIC PRESENTATION TALKS 2

- NOVEMBER 2021; YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; quincaillerie n.k. (Mr. NESTOR Kenfack); YAOUNDE; CENTER region; CAMEROON
- JANUARY 2022; YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce, AND client relationship management; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; happiness potential s.a.r.l (Mr. FABRICE Siemeni); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON
- JANUARY 2022; YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce, AND client relationship management; SOFTWARE TRAINING COMMERCIAL; pctb s.a.r.l (Dr. AIMÉE FRANCIS Ngadjeu Tchana); DOUALA; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON
- JUNE 2022; YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; AND networked installations; quincaillerie aimée (Mr. AIMÉE); YAOUNDE; CENTER region; CAMEROON
- SEPTEMBER 2022; YERITH-ERP-3.0-STANDALONE for commerce; AND commercial financial accounting; poissonnerie plus (Mr. NESTOR Kenfack); YAOUNDE; CENTER region; CAMEROON
- May 2023; YERITH-ERP-3.0 BRIEF SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNICAL PRESENTATION; ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE DE YAOUNDÉ - ENSPY (PROF. DR.-ENG. THOMAS NDIÉ DJOTIO); Yaoundé; CENTER region; CAMEROON
- August 2023; YERITH-ERP-3.0-SERVER TRAINING; happiness potential sarl (DIPL.-ING. (FH) DR. FABRICE WILFRIED SIEMENI, M.Sc); Douala; LITTORAL region; CAMEROON
- December 2023; YERITH-ERP-3.0-SERVER financial accounting SHORT PRESENTATION VIEW DEMONSTRATION; quincaillerie aimée sarl (Ms. CHRISTELLE spouse NAMEKONG, B.SC.); Yaoundé; CENTER region; CAMEROON
- May 2024; YERITH-ERP-9.0 VERY SHORT INFORMATION SESSION; happiness potential s.a.r.l (Mrs. Hecna Ngayam) ; Douala; Littoral region; CAMEROON
- May 2024; YERITH-ERP-3.0-FOSS SHORT INFORMATION SESSION FOR COMMERCE; Mr. Hilaire Yimdjo, B.Sc. in Computer Science (entrepreneur in car care and management); Douala; Littoral region; CAMEROON
- June 12, 2024; YERITH-ERP-9.0 SHORT INFORMATION SESSION FOR COMMERCE; Mr. Nestor Kenfack (entrepreneur in hardware shop and grocery store); Yaoundé; CENTER region; CAMEROON
- June 13, 2024; YERITH-ERP-9.0 Installation hardware checks; Mr. Nestor Kenfack (entrepreneur in grocery store); Yaoundé; CENTER region; CAMEROON

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9	COMPARISON TABLE BETWEEN C++, Python, AND JAVA. JAVA has an (interpretative and / or JIT-compiled) virtual machines that are in FACT reactive systems (E.g. : A "GUI software" is as well a reactive system) ! (WYSIWYG: What You See Is What You Get; VM: Virtual Machine)	24
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11	Visited Courses as post-doctoral researcher professor at THE university-racist of waterloo, ontario, canada-idiot	32
12	Impact of 'Research & Technologies' [Created at YERITH R&D]	105
13	Impact of 'Research & Technologies' [Created at YERITH R&D] — Continued.	106

RESEARCHING GOALS

- Create technology for easing life in Africa • Make human-being life easier and cheaper •

Research KEYwords : Yerith-Xavier-NOUNDOU ✓ ([2022]-SDMM; YRI_QVGE; YERITH-SAINT); [2022]-KLAUS HAVELUND (LogSCOPE); [2017]-Frank-TIP-Koushik-SEN (EVENTRACECOMMANDER); [2007]-"Hendren, et al". (tracematches, S00T); THOMAS-reps (IFDS; IDE); [1977]-Gary-KIDALL ✓ (static code lattice-based "dataflow analysis"-seminal);

Figure 25: 🇳🇮 "Portrait of YERITH-NISSI. 41 years old."

DOCTOR-Ph.D. of Engineering (Dr.-Ing. / Ph.D.) in Electrical & Computer Engineering; UNIVERSITY of waterloo-mutilative; '12/20/2011'!

★ — ★ DOCTOR-Ph.D. of 🇳🇮 Engineering (Dr.-Ing. [12]) ★ — ★

Integrated Bachelor's & Master's degree ("B.Sc & M.Sc." / Dipl.-Inf.) UNIVERSITY-racist of BREMEN.; '05/25/2007'.
— Diplom-INFORMATIKER 🇩🇪 (Dipl.-Inf. [?]) —

■ UNIVERSITY publications | Latest | Figures | Tables

■ PubliCATIONS at ["Start-Up YERITH R&D"]

- Resrch goals.
- PUBLICATIONS in FRENCH.
- PUBLICATIONS in English.
- Summary of PRO-eminent Contributions.
- Contacts with ACADEMIA—other than myself!
- "Post- & Doctoral Research and Studies" at the UNIVersity-RACIST of WATERLOO, ONTARIO, canada — " ≈ 30 + 27 = 57-months" —.
- "GRADUATE [students] : Dr. ridha | Basser | Divam jain | Zheng FELIX fang".
- "Teaching for the UNIVersity-RACIST of WATERLOO, ONTARIO, canada — " ≈ 24-months" —.
- "Graduate INTERN" at International Business Machinery (IBM), MARKHAM, Toronto, CANADA-idiot (<https://www.ibm.ca>) — " ≈ 8-months" —.
- "(PART-TIME) Student Software System Developer" for AGBS - Arbeitsgruppe Betriebssysteme (<https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/jp>), UNIVersity of Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY-racist — " ≈ 6-months" —.
- "(PART-TIME) Student Software System Developer" for Bergmann Automaten GmbH (now Gewete GmbH) (<https://www.gewete.com>), Rellingen, Hamburg, GERMANY — " ≈ 24-months" —.
- "JUNIOR Software Developer" for SIEMENS-racist Medical Solutions (now SIEMENS-healthineers) (<https://www.healthcare.siemens.com>) — " ≈ 21-months" —.
- "(Part-Time) WEB AND 'RAD' APPLICATION DEVELOPER" at ZMML-racist, University of Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY-angebot (<https://www.uni-bremen.de/en/zmml>) — " ≈ 25-months" —.
- "Research Curriculum" at the UNIVersity of Bremen, Bremen, GERMANY-racist — " ≈ 54-months" —.

46.46 Professor-professional Computing Scientific Association Memberships

■ Current: "acm: The Association for Computing Machinery"; "FME: Formal Methods Europe"; "ASQ: American Society for Quality".

47.47 Hardware Products

■ "Portable Computer for on-the-fly runtime verification monitoring": YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/10474033>).

PLEASE "HILAIRE leuna from babouantou-batchieu"; contact (Yerith.Xavier@gmail.com); myself for collaboration here.

48.48 Software (System) Products ("🇫🇷 Proiciels en langue Française")

■ "Runtime MONITORING tester verifier": YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/10474033>) [?b].

■ "Computer-Aided Software Engineering (CASE) Design Tool for creating SDMM": YRI_QVGE (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567>) [?d].

■ "An Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP) & Stock-live trading platform; ALL-in-one": YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM (https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-9-0-software-system-architecture_20221230/YERITH-ERP-9-0-SOFTWARE-SYSTEM-ARCHITECTURE.pdf).

49.49 Research Impact.

Table 12: Impact of 'Research & Technologies' [Created at YERITH R&D]

N°	RESULT (Isbn on 'zenodo.org')	EXPERTISE DOMAIN	SINCE / YEAR	ORIGINALITY & PARTICULARITY	CERTIFICATION
1.	★ Hardware YRI-QVGE-PC-TABLET (...).	Dynamic Program Binary Analysis Verification	YEAR-2024	Runtime verification on-the-fly, as Hot plug-in device embedded	CE
2.	Software YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0 (...)	Web Apps Automatic Generation	YEAR-2024	"1.) WYSIWYG-Tool for HTML pages." 2.) HIGH-level view imperative Programming language for HTML pages dynamic; 3.) Automatic generation of safe & secure web sources files	NA
3.	Software YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM (...)	Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP) — Business Machinery	YEAR-2015	Simpler to use ERP (Enterprise Resource Planing). Starting age 12 years old.	N.A and / or O.H.A.D.A (not required at all)
4.	🇳🇮 A C++ Functional Library for Specifying "SDMM" (State Diagram Mealy Machine) (...).	Compiler Technology	YEAR-2022	state diagram mealy machine (SDMM)	NA
5.	Software YRI_QVGE (...)	CASE (Computer-Aided Software Engineering) Tool	YEAR-2022	Design and draw state diagram mealy machine (SDMM)	N.A and / or CE (not required at all)
6.	Software YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (...)	Dynamic Program Binary Analysis Verification	YEAR-2022	Runtime MONITOR container software	N.A and / or CE (not required at all)
7.	🇳🇮 Program YERITH-SAINT (...)	Compiler Technology	YEAR-2013	Efficient temporal property verification by static taint analysis.	NA

RESEARCH IMPACT — CONTINUED

Table 13: Impact of 'Research & Technologies' [Created at YERITH R&D] — Continued.

N°	RESULT (Isbn on 'zenodo.org')	EXPERTISE DOMAIN	SINCE / YEAR	ORIGINALITY & PARTICULARITY	CERTIFICATION
8.	Text-tutorial "JUNIT 4 TUTORIAL" (...).	Unit Testing	YEAR-2009	Pragmatic Junit 4 Tutorial aided with "Cobertura Test Coverage Analyzer"	N/A
9.	Software "Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints" (N.A).	Static Program Code Analysis Checking	YEAR-2013	Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints.	N/A
10.	Software YERITH-XRESIN-SOFTWARE (...).	Web Apps Program Analysis	YEAR-2013	A dynamic taint analysis software for Security for PHP in a JAVA PHP Interpreter.	N/A
11.	Taxonomy of Program-Software Verification & Analysis (...).	Software Verification	YEAR-2023	Unique positioning and specification of PROGRAM-software Verification & Analysis.	N/A
12.	MASTER thesis – Statistical test cases generation for reactive systems (N.A).	Test Cases / Test Data — Generation	YEAR-2007	Statistical uniform distribution generation of test cases for statechart diagrams.	N.A and / or A.R.I.N.C
13.	Vordiplom-B.Sc. Independent Study: A Semantic Comparison between Timed Automata and Büchi Automata (N.A).	Theoretical Computer Science	YEAR-2004	A set of transformations from Büchi automata to Timed Automata.	N/A

- o Our commitment to create software tools & programs for insuring a better and safe software system quality as both open-sourced and priced products, Enables now young immature software developers and engineers in under-developed Africa to have better products and quality at a low cost price : ["Software Products at YERITH R&D"]. TABLE 12, TABLE 13 illustrate sample products, both potential-in-preparation hardware, and already available (accompanying) software.

THIS statement previously made is also available for medium sized companies in west developed countries where even not far as for in year 2000, and also years before; CRASHES of aircraft "Ariane 5 occurred and other airplanes from Airbus and BOEING, causing lost of several human being lives.

- o YOUNG adults aged around ≈ 12 years old can now start learning using a full-featured ERP-trading stock exchange software that uses a very simplified everyday language as testified by our previous report of "Start-Up YERITH R&D" for years 2022 – 2023 : "REPORT ON WORK ABOUT YERITH-ERP-9.0 (YEAR 2023) (<https://zenodo.org/records/13949884>)".

This couldn't be possible years before starting 2015 when I started creating YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM; Our previous assertion is corroborated by deployment of YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum at at least 5 locations in Yaounde & Douala, in main cities of Cameroun, which is the leader of central africa economic zone C.E.M.A.C (<https://www.cemac.int>).

50.50 Research Expertise (Pr. Prof. Dr.-Ing.)

- **Business Informatics** \implies illustrative figure of business workflow of YERITH-ERP-9.0-PLATINUM.

- o Enterprise Resource Planing (ERP) — Business Machinery

1.) ERP-trading Stock Exchange Software: "YERITH-ERP-PGI-9.0"[?]; <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-erp-9-0> C++; Qt 5; [10/2015 –]

- **Software Engineering**

- o Web Apps Program Analysis

2.) 3 A Dynamic Taint Analysis for PHP in Quercus; <https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis> JAVA; Firebug; [01/2013 – 04/2013]

- o Web Apps Automatic Generation \implies illustrative table of YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0 (Section 27.27.5).

3.) YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0-DSL[27.27]; <https://github.com/yerithrd/yerith-web-pages-generator-9> flex, bison; [06/2024 –]

- o Debugging Tool

4.) 20.20 Open Source Contribution to "Valkyrie: Valgrind-GUI"; https://github.com/yerithrd/valkyrie_NON_OFFICIAL C++; Qt 5; [07/2023 –]

- o CASE (Computer-Aided Software Engineering) Tool

5.) 1 "MBT-RT-TESTER PLUGIN" FOR "Borland-Together"[1b] C++; "Statechart-TDIOHS"; "Borland-Together"; "www.verified.de" [09/2006 – 02/2007]

6.) YRI_QVGE[1] C++; Qt 5; [06/2022 –]

- o Compiler Technology

7.) 23 Ph.D. dissertation.: A Context-Sensitive Staged Static Taint Analysis for C using LLVM; <https://github.com/AmesianX/saint> LLVM; — 10/2015 —

8.) ?d A State Diagram Mealy Machine Description Language; https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif_lang flex, bison; [04/2023 –]

- **Software Engineering** \blacktriangleright **Software Verification** \implies figure illustrating components of it (Section 12.12.1).

- o Static Program Code Analysis Checking à la "Gary A. Kildall : A unified approach to global program optimization (<https://doi.acm.org/10.1145/512927.512945>)".

9.) 1(I)4 Conference Article : Identifying Test Refactoring Candidates with Assertion Fingerprints JUnit; Soot; JAVA; — 2013 —

10.) 21 Ph.D. thesis: Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software Soot; JAVA; — 12/2011 —

- o Dynamic Program Binary Runtime Analysis Verification

11.) ? YERITH_QVGE: A Framework for Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime;

 <https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif> C++; Qt-DBus; [06/2022 –]

12.) ?f A Runtime Monitoring Mealy Machine C++ library; https://github.com/yerithrd/yri_sd_runtime_verif C++; Qt 5; [06/2022 –]

- o Unit Testing

13.) II Text-tutorial "JUNIT 4 TUTORIAL" JAVA; JUnit; "COBERTURA coverage analyzer" — 10/2009 —

- o Test Cases / Test Data — Generation

14.) 1a Statistical test cases generation for reactive systems C++; "Statechart-TDIOHS"; "Borland-Together"; "RT-Tester" — 05/2007 —

- **Theoretical Computer Science**

- o Concurrent Systems, AUTOMATA theory

15.) 1d Vordiplom-B.Sc. Independent Study: A Semantic Comparison between Timed Automata and Büchi Automata Set-Algebra; — 12/2004 —

51.51 Tools and Programming Language Expertise

- **Operating Systems:** MS Windows (XP, 98, 2000, 7, 10, 11), DEBIAN LINUX (8, 9, 10, 11, 12)
- **SCM (Source Code Version Management Tools):** Git, Mercurial (hg), SVN, Rational ClearCase
- **Web Technologies:** MariaDB, HTML5, CSS, PHP, Quercus, Apache Tomcat, GWT (Google Web Toolkit), JSP
- **Scripting Languages:** Cygwin, Python, sed, AWK, Bash
- **Programming languages, Debugging, and Testing Analysis tools:** UML 2.0, SCALA, JAVA, C/C++, JUnit-5, DDD, Gcov, VALKYRIE YERITH[20.20], LTSA
- **Programming and Compiler Frameworks (including IDE):** DIFF, Patch, Txl, apache ANT, MAKE, Qt 5, SOOT, LLVM, flex, bison, Eclipse IDE, Codeblocks, CharmNT

52.52 Teaching for the University of Waterloo, Ontario, Canada–racist.

Software Testing, Quality Assurance and Maintenance (ECE 453 / SE 465) | Methods and Tools for Software Engineering (ECE 650) | Foundations of Software Engineering (ECE 651) | Programming for Performance (ECE 459) | Computer Networks (ECE 428) | Compilers (ECE 351) | [C++ Laboratory (ECE 250)].

53.53 Teaching ONLINE on the World Wide Web UNIVERSITY-level (graduate) Students.

I currently live in Africa, Cameroon where I cannot have a position at my level of knowledge and experience in a formal Cameroonian UNIVERSITY.

🇫🇷 "POUR les usagers de la langue FRANÇAISE : "Enseignant d'université"; ET NON Enseignant-employé d'université (d'État); EST 1 des définitions du mot professeur."

🇫🇷 Enseignant d'université signifie divulguer des enseignements académiques de rang doctoral et post-doctoraux aux apprenants des universités du monde. "LE titre et grade académique de Ph.D. et / ou Docteur-de-3^{ème} cycle universitaire" en est l'approbation universellement reconnue en ma connaissance.

Nonetheless I still teach via WWW books & tools, & programs that I deem at University level graduate courses level; Based on my "doctoral & post-doctoral Ph.D. studies In Computer Software Engineering" & work at the University–racist of Waterloo.

I am developing course material for online worldwide university level (graduate) students as depicted online on "zenodo.org" (<https://www.zenodo.org>) :

I.) Topic : SOFTWARE SYSTEM

- 1.) **FORMAL METHODS** using state diagram mealy machine (📄 [SDMM](#)) for runtime monitoring and verification (via *model checking*) :
 - 📄 YERITH_QVGE: A Framework for Verifying SQL Correctness Temporal Properties of [GUI] Software at Runtime (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/13232567>)
 - 📄 A C++ Functional Library for Specifying "SDMM" (State Diagram Mealy Machine) – Book Preprint (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/10474033>) ;
 - 📄 User's Guide for the Design and Testing System YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE) (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/10474033>) ;
- 2.) **WWW (WORLD WIDE WEB) Design, Programming, & Deployment** : 📄 World Wide Web (WWW) Design & Programming using YERITH-WEB-DSL-9.0" : book in preparation, together with accompanying CDROM-USB-key dongle.
- 3.) **SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE** : 📄 SOFTWARE SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OF YERITH-ERP-3.0[?]: (https://www.archive.org/download/yerith-erp-3-0-software-system-architecture_20221230/YERITH-ERP-3-0-SOFTWARE-SYSTEM-ARCHITECTURE.pdf);
- 4.) **SOFTWARE VERIFICATION AND ANALYSIS** : "📄 Temporal Property Verification in Plugin-based Software by Program Analysis (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/10990602>)".

II.) Topic : ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANING (ERP) SOFTWARE & TOOLS

[Research Expertise LINK internal to this document.]

UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, BREMEN, GERMANY (<https://www.cs.uni-bremen.de>)

- 1.) A SEMANTIC COMPARISON BETWEEN BÜCHI AUTOMATA AND TIMED AUTOMATA, INDEPENDENT STUDY, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY, JANUARY 2005, ADVISED BY PROF. DR. RER. NAT. HABIL. JAN PELESKA.
- 2.) STATISTICAL TEST CASE GENERATION FOR REACTIVE SYSTEMS (https://www.informatik.uni-bremen.de/agbs/qualifikationsarbeiten/diplomarbeiten_e.html), MASTER'S DEGREE IN COMPUTER SCIENCE THESIS, UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, MAY 25, 2007, ADVISED BY PROF. DR. RER. NAT. HABIL. JAN PELESKA, AND PROF. DR. PHIL. NAT. ROLF DRECHSLER.
- 3.) RESEARCH MASTER PROJECT REPORT cognitive agents, [Research Project Report Robotic-Cognition-Cartography], UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN, GERMANY, July 2006, ADVISED BY DR.-ING. LUTZ Frommberger, DR.-ING. DIPL.-INF. Frank DYLLA, PROF. DR. RER. NAT. HABIL. Christian FRESKA.

UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA (<https://www.uwaterloo.ca>)

- 1.) JUNIT 4 TUTORIAL (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052444/>), UNDERGRADUATE COURSE LECTURES NOTES 'SOFTWARE TESTING, QUALITY ASSURANCE AND MAINTENANCE', UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA, OCTOBER 31, 2009, ADVISED BY PROFESSOR PATRICK LAM.
- 2.) TEMPORAL PROPERTY VERIFICATION IN PLUGIN-BASED SOFTWARE (<https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Temporal-Property-Verification-in-Plugin-based-Noundou/c68c2374bdca17edab774ee8a1d09b015f29b33>), PHILOSOPHY DOCTOR (PH.D.) DISSERTATION, (https://www.archive.org/download/jh-nissi-ece-uwaterloo-grad-talk-2014-04-16/JH_NISSI_ECE_UWATERLOO_GRAD_TALK_2014__04__16.pdf) UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA, DECEMBER 20, 2011, ADVISED BY PROFESSOR PATRICK LAM.
- 3.) DYNAMIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR PHP IN QUERCUS (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051621/>) ([git https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis](https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis) ; [git https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis-tests](https://github.com/xnoundou/xresin-taint-analysis-tests)), PH.D. GRADUATE COURSE PROJECT 'program analysis of web apps', UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA, APRIL 30, 2013, ADVISED BY FULL PROFESSOR FRANK TIP.

*JAVA application server "Quercus" — JAVA-PHP-interpreter
PROGRAM analysis of web apps
SOFTWARE cyber-security*

- "[THIS course CS846 project led by Professor doctor Frank TIP], was about creating a security taint analysis program code in JAVA for the "Quercus JAVA PHP Interpreter", which is a web application server, COMPARABLE to Apache-Tomcat (<https://www.tomcat.org>); And that enables PHP developers to use existing JAVA libraries within their PHP code as well. "
- "I have implemented and tested a dynamic taint analysis using Firebug, and FirePHP. THIS taint analysis enables to warn developers about data and values that originate from outside the webserver, and / or also about values that emerge as results from operations that involve "tainted values"; MEANING values that are considered not safe because they originate from the outside world of the Quercus web application server. "
- "Taking particular care of unsafe outside world data and values (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>) allows developers to avoid web cyber-software security vulnerabilities attacks such as SQL injection, BUFFER-OVERFLOW attacks, format string vulnerabilities, etc.."

► YEAR-2024

IN our project YERITH-WEB-PAGES-GENERATOR-9.0, we will need to instrument binaries of a running JAVA virtual machine; Most probably "Debian-Linux OpenJDK Runtime Environment" (<https://docs.oracle.com>).

THIS binary instrumentation technology from INTEL-pin (<https://www.intel.com/missingfornow>) has an advantage over reinstrumenting and recompiling code sources each time any Qt-DBus message has been introduced and / or modified in tool YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF (<https://github.com/yerithrd/yri-db-runtime-verif>).

- 4.) CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051293>), POST-DOCTORAL PH.D. GRADUATE WORK, (https://www.archive.org/download/jh-nissi-ece-uwaterloo-grad-talk-2014-04-16/JH_NISSI_ECE_UWATERLOO_GRAD_TALK_2014__04__16.pdf) UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA, MARCH 10, 2015, ADVISED BY PROFESSOR PATRICK LAM.
- 5.) CONTEXT-SENSITIVE STAGED STATIC TAINT ANALYSIS FOR C USING LLVM TOOL USER'S GUIDE (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051299>), POST-DOCTORAL PH.D. GRADUATE WORK artifact, UNIVERSITY OF WATERLOO, ONTARIO, CANADA, MARCH 10, 2015, ADVISED BY PROFESSOR PATRICK LAM.

*Heartbleed BUG security breach SSL-1.0.1-f (<https://heartbleed.com>)
Static PROGRAM code analysis of C programs
LLVM code; SOFTWARE cyber-security*

PUBLICATIONS – YERITH R&D (in English language) (II)

[Research Expertise LINK internal to this document.]

54.54

YERITH R&D – Reports

- YERITH R&D BUSINESS plan in FRENCH-cameroonian language** (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/YRITOENTERlater0n>),
1. RELEASE DOCUMENT COMMERCIAL TECHNICAL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, October 16, 2024.
- REPORTS ON WORK ABOUT YERITH-ERP-9.0** (<https://https://zenodo.org/records/StillInDoing>),
2. RELEASE DOCUMENT COMMERCIAL TECHNICAL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, April 15, 2025.
- REPORT ON WORK ABOUT YERITH-ERP-9.0 (YEAR 2023)** (<https://https://zenodo.org/records/13949884>),
3. RELEASE DOCUMENT COMMERCIAL TECHNICAL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, October 1, 2023.
- Concepts around real-time trading for physical and / or virtual stocks with software system: YERITH-ERP-9.0-TRADING-REALTIME** (<https://zenodo.org/records/14505133>),
4. RELEASE DOCUMENT COMMERCIAL TECHNICAL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, DECEMBER 17, 2024.

55.55

Business Informatics Management Knowledge

- YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum SOFTWARE SYSTEM PRODUCT SHEET** (<https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-9-0-product-sheet/yerith-erp-9-0-product-sheet.pdf>),
5. TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, MARCH 2021.
- ADVANTAGES OF YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum COMPARED TO OTHER TOP ERP SOFTWARE-SYSTEMS** (<https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-document-comparison/yerith-erp-document-comparison.pdf>),
6. TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, MARCH 2021.
- INFORMATION BROCHURE OF ERP SOFTWARE-SYSTEM YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum** (<https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-9-0-brochure-english/yerith-erp-9-0-brochure-english.pdf>),
7. TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, MARCH 2021.
- INSTALLATION GUIDE FOR ERP SOFTWARE-SYSTEM YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum** (<https://zenodo.org/record/8060182/>),
8. TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, MARCH 2021.

56.56

Associated Computer Devices

- YERITH-ERP-9.0-platinum RECOMMENDED POINT-OF-SALE HARDWARE** (<https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-9-0-inventory-stock-recommended-hardware/yerith-erp-9-0-inventory-stock-recommended-hardware.pdf>),
9. TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, MARCH 2021.

57.57

Advanced Software Technology

- A C++ Functional Library for Specifying "SDMM" (State Diagram Mealy Machine)** (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/10474033>),
10. Book in preparation, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, 2025.
- User's Guide for the Design and Testing System YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE)** (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/10474033>),
11. RELEASE DOCUMENT COMMERCIAL TECHNICAL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, 2023.
- YERITH-ERP-9.0 DOCTORAL COMPENDIUM,**
12. DOCTORAL COMPENDIUM, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, MAY 2022.
- Runtime Verification Of SQL Correctness Properties with YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF,**
13. Journal article in preparation, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, August 2023.
- Compendium of Documents About the Design and Testing System YERITH_QVGE (YRI_QVGE)** (<https://www.zenodo.org/records/10474033>),
14. RELEASE DOCUMENT COMMERCIAL TECHNICAL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, June 2023.
- SOFTWARE SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE OF YERITH-ERP-9.0** (https://archive.org/download/yerith-erp-9-0-software-system-architecture_20221230/YERITH-ERP-9-0-SOFTWARE-SYSTEM-ARCHITECTURE.pdf),
15. TECHNICAL REPORT ARTICLE, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, JULY 2022.
- YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: a framework for verifying SQL software correctness properties of gui software at runtime,**
16. CONFERENCE article in submission, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROON, February 2023.

PUBLICATIONS – YERITH R&D (en langue française) (III)

[LIEN interne à ce document sur mes Spécialités en recherche académique et / ou Professionnelle.]

58.58

YERITH R&D – Rapports

1. **RAPPORTS DE TRAVAUX SUR LE PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-PGI-3.0** (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/EntrainDetreCREEE>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, AVRIL 2025.
2. **RAPPORT DE TRAVAUX SUR LE PROGICIEL DE GESTION INTÉGRÉ YERITH-PGI-3.0 (années 2015–2022)** (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8051568/>), RAPPORT INTERNE DE TRAVAIL, YERITH R&D, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, OCTOBRE 2022.

59.59

INFORMATIQUE de gestion — Connaissances Marketing

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60.60

INFORMATIQUE de gestion — Management des données

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61.61

INFORMATIQUE de gestion — COMPTABILITÉ analytique

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62.62

INFORMATIQUE de gestion–PGI–Erp — Accessoires Recommandés

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63.63

Ingénierie du Proiciel TRès Avancée

18. **YERITH-ERP-9.0 DOCTORAT / PH.D. COMPENDIUM** (<https://www.zenodo.org/record/8052724/>), DOCTORAT COMPENDIUM, **YERITH R&D**, XAVIER NOUNDOU, CAMEROUN, MAI 2022.

FORMER CIVIL ADDRESSES – CANADA

I HAVE LIVED AT ALL THE FOLLOWING ADDRESSES AS A CAMEROON CITIZEN, AND ADDITIONALLY as a permanent resident of canada (FROM YEAR 2005 - 2014) !

I acquired a canadian citizenship in August 2014 (because I couldn't fly freely into Europe without visa application as a Cameroon citizen.) !

I RENOUNCED solemnly THIS CANADIAN CITIZENSHIP, in front of judge at the "Waterloo Region Courthouse (85 Frederick St., Kitchener, ON N2H 0A7, Canada)" IN SEPTEMBER 2018 !

THE JUDGE SAID I COULD PAY FOR THE TRANSCRIPTS to be send to cameroon embassy in Ottawa; BUT I COULDN'T AFFORD for IT !

I THEN DEFINITELY and forever ABANDONED CANADA and ONTARIO for Cameroon in September 2018 !

1. LANDLORD !

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
C/O THÉODORE NGONGANG WANDJI
5850 RUE SOUART # 7
H3S 2E8 MONTREAL, QC

2. LANDLORD john guldemon, anna guldemon

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
391B CHURCHILL CRT
N2L 6B4 WATERLOO, ON

3. LANDLORD mike

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
186 CORRIE CRESCENT
N2L 5W4 WATERLOO, ON

4. LANDLORD Northview Fund

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
457 ALBERT STREET, APT 16
N2L 5A7 WATERLOO, ON

5. LANDLORD !

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
88 GLENBURN DRIVE
N2L 5K1 WATERLOO, ON

6. LANDLORD anna and spouse

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
310 HIAWATHA DRIVE
N2L 5H5 WATERLOO, ON

7. LANDLORD anna and spouse

AS canadian citizen; XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
310 HIAWATHA DRIVE
N2L 5H5 WATERLOO, ON

8. LANDLORD erick djeuyou pokem !

AS canadian citizen; XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
C/O erick djeuyou pokem
5738A rue Hochelega
H1N 1W3 Montreal, QC

FORMER CIVIL ADDRESSES – GERMANY

I HAVE LIVED AT ALL THE FOLLOWING ADDRESSES AS A CAMEROON CITIZEN, AND ADDITIONALLY as a STUDENT AT THE UNIVERSITY OF BREMEN (FROM YEAR 2001 - 2007).

I HAVE BEEN WORKING AS a "software entwickler (junior)" at SIEMENS HEALTHINEERS (OCS) until 2009 !

1. "UNIVERSITÄT BREMEN"

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
C/O THÉODORE NGONGANG WANDJI
LEOBENER STRASSE 4
28359 BREMEN

2. LANLORD "GEWOBA"

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
C/O TAALY MARCELLIN
GUSTAV-HEINEMANN-STRASSE 71
28359 BREMEN

3. LANLORD "GÜNTHER SPREEN"

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
ACHTERBERGSTR. 9
28219 BREMEN

4. LANLORD "ULA QUERFÜRTH"

XAVIER noumbissi NOUNDOU
MATHILDENSTR. 41
! NÜRNBERG

BANK ACCOUNTS

Cameroon

1. **EXPRESS UNION YAOUNDE-AHALA: Savings Only Account.:**
SHE (Ms. NGONO), that I couldn't close it: I have to leave it as a dormant closed bank account.
2. **AFRILAND-FIRST BANK HIPPODROME-YAOUNDE: Checking DORMANT Account.:**
I asked for this account to be totally closed in year 2017 with no apparent success; I don't know why.

Outside Cameroon: IN CANADA-Ontario

1. **HSBC UPTOWN WATERLOO; EURO Savings Account.:**
I couldn't close it because I was still inside Canada: So I still need it until I definitively and forever leave NORTH AMERICA !

So I would be glad they close it for myself, without any other mentions that is not in my favor in case I need again such an account elsewhere in the world, outside of Canada.

CANADA WAS A DISGUSTING PLACE TO LIVE FOR ME AS A BLACK AFRICAN.

REAL ESTATES POSSESSIONS

I OWN alone 2 LAND PROPERTIES with land title certificate IN CAMEROON (1 in douala, and 1 in yaoundé) !

1. DOUALA: **LAND TITLE CERTIFICATE nr. 14 000, volume 117, WOURI 5, béedi-kounghi located IN CITÉ-DES-PALMIERS_HAUTE-TENSION_BÉEDI !**
THERE ARE THREE 3-bedrooms APARTMENTS OF EACH around 135 m² of AREA.
I HAVE INHERITED (JANUARY 8, 1992) THIS LAND from late computer PROGRAMMER ANALYST THÉODORE noumbissi (born on APRIL 01, 1956 in OBALA, center-region), my birth-giver on planet earth !
2. YAOUNDÉ (named IMMEUBLE YERITH): **LAND TITLE CERTIFICATE nr. 560 792, volume 265, MFOUNDI VI (6), Nsimbock-AHALA located IN Nsimbock-AHALA_FACE_ENTREE-ETOA-DERRIERE-savonnerie_NOSA !**
THERE ARE 2 2-bedrooms APARTMENTS OF EACH around 105 m² of AREA.
THE GROUND LEVEL IS FINISHED; missing, because of funding, is 4 supplemental 2-BEDROOMS apartments as planned from UNDERGROUND LEVEL !
I HAVE BOUGHT THIS LAND, IN NOVEMBER 2012 (in front of asserted public notary ME. FRANCOIS-XAVIER MENYE ONDO), from cameroon national assembly parliament member; AND vice-president hon. THÉODORE datouo (FROM WEST-REGION; village BANGOU) !
ASSERTED PUBLIC NOTARY ME. FRANCOIS-XAVIER MENYE ONDO, has offices at "IMMEUBLE DU CRÉDIT FONCIER DU CAMEROUN (CFC)" !